

Pandigital-Type and Pythagorean Triples Patterns

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Abstract

*This work is revised form of author's previous two works [8, 9]. In this paper we worked with generating **Pythagorean triples** by use of two variables **Pythagoras theorem**. Based on these triples **Pythagorean patterns** are also calculated by use of same formula of two variables of **Pythagoras theorem**. Again by use of same formula, **pandigital-type pythagorean triples** are obtained. In other words, three ways study on the same **pythagorean triples** is done. One is of generating-type Second, writing patterns, and third to bring **pandigital-type patterns**. The **pandigital-type patterns** are written in two different ways, one is like, [12345678987654321](#) and the second is of type [102030405060708090807060504030201](#).*

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1 Introduction

Pythagoras theorem is well-known in the literature. By **Pythagoras theorem** it is understood that

$$a^2 + b^2 = c^2.$$

For simplicity, let's write it as (a, b, c) . If we talk of distances, then the numbers a , b and c are real positive numbers, otherwise they can be any real number. The **Pythagorean triple** $(3, 4, 5)$ is understood as $3^2 + 4^2 = 5^2$. Let's consider the following well-known procedure [1] to write Pythagorean triples:

$$\begin{aligned} F(m, n) &:= m^2 - n^2 \\ G(m, n) &:= 2mn \\ H(m, n) &:= m^2 + n^2 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Then we can easily check that

$$\begin{aligned} F(m, n)^2 + G(m, n)^2 &= (m^2 - n^2)^2 + (2mn)^2 \\ &= m^4 - 2m^2n^2 + n^4 + 4m^2n^2 \\ &= m^4 + 2m^2n^2 + n^4 \\ &= (m^2 + n^2)^2 = H(m, n)^2. \end{aligned}$$

We shall use frequently the formula (1) to find Pythagorean triples in subsequent sections. For extensive study on Pythagorean triples refer to online work by Knott [1]. In this paper, our aim is to write procedures to bring Pythagorean triples in a symmetrical way. Also to generate magic squares from the **Pythagorean triples**. The whole work is divided in three big parts:

1. Generating Pythagorean triples;
2. Patterns in Pythagorean Triples;
3. Pandigital-type Pythagorean Triples.

First part is based on writing **Pythagorean triples** based on Equation (1). The second bring patterns in **Pythagorean triples** calculated in first part. It is also based on Equation (1). Third part brings patterns in a little different way, i.e., these of **pandigital-type**. In this case the further valued don't follow the pattern. This work is revised form of author's previous two works [8, 9]. For more study on Pythagorean triples refer author's work [5, 6, 7, 10, 11].

2 Generating Pythagorean Triples

2.1 First Block

This section give simplified procedure to write Pythagorean triples. It is divided in different blocks.

Let's write a number 100 in two parts such that one part is a complete square:

1. $100 = 99 + 01$
2. $100 = 96 + 04$
3. $100 = 91 + 09$
4. $100 = 84 + 16$
5. $100 = 75 + 25$
6. $100 = 64 + 36$
7. $100 = 51 + 49$
8. $100 = 36 + 64$
9. $100 = 19 + 81$ (2)

We observe that the right hand sides of the expression (2) are formed by two sums, where the last two digits are perfect squares written in decreasing order. Let's consider a difference of squares between the terms of *r.h.s.* with 1 in the front of perfect square term. Then this difference is again a perfect square multiple of 20 resulting in Pythagorean triples. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 101^2 - 099^2 = 020^2 &\Rightarrow 099^2 + 020^2 = 101^2 \Rightarrow (099, 020, 101) \\
 104^2 - 096^2 = 040^2 &\Rightarrow 096^2 + 040^2 = 104^2 \Rightarrow (096, 040, 104) \\
 109^2 - 091^2 = 060^2 &\Rightarrow 091^2 + 060^2 = 109^2 \Rightarrow (091, 060, 109) \\
 116^2 - 084^2 = 080^2 &\Rightarrow 084^2 + 080^2 = 116^2 \Rightarrow (084, 080, 116) \\
 125^2 - 075^2 = 100^2 &\Rightarrow 075^2 + 100^2 = 125^2 \Rightarrow (075, 100, 125) \\
 136^2 - 064^2 = 120^2 &\Rightarrow 064^2 + 120^2 = 136^2 \Rightarrow (064, 120, 136) \\
 149^2 - 051^2 = 140^2 &\Rightarrow 051^2 + 140^2 = 149^2 \Rightarrow (051, 140, 149) \\
 164^2 - 036^2 = 160^2 &\Rightarrow 036^2 + 160^2 = 164^2 \Rightarrow (036, 160, 164) \\
 181^2 - 019^2 = 180^2 &\Rightarrow 019^2 + 180^2 = 181^2 \Rightarrow (019, 180, 181)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

The right hand sides of the expression (2) are formed by two sums, where the second sum is a perfect squares written in increasing order. Alternatively, we can get the same triples by using the formula given in (1). It is obtained by by fixing $m = 10$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (3).

2.2 Second Block

This section is continuation of Section 2. It lead us to 99 palindromic patterns. In Equation (3) we divided 100 in two parts. Here, let's divide here 10000 in two parts. The division is done in such a way that second part turns to be a perfect square. In this case we shall have 99 equality expressions. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1. \quad & 10000 = 9999 + 0001 \\
 2. \quad & 10000 = 9996 + 0004 \\
 3. \quad & 10000 = 9991 + 0009 \\
 4. \quad & 10000 = 9984 + 0016 \\
 5. \quad & 10000 = 9975 + 0025 \\
 & \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \\
 96. \quad & 10000 = 0784 + 9216 \\
 97. \quad & 10000 = 0591 + 9409 \\
 98. \quad & 10000 = 0396 + 9604 \\
 99. \quad & 10000 = 0199 + 9801
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

We observe that the second terms in the *r.h.s.* are perfect squares. Consider a difference of squares between the terms of r.h.s. with 1 in the front of perfect square term. Then this difference is again a perfect square multiple of 200. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 10001^2 - 9999^2 &= 00200^2 \Rightarrow 9999^2 + 00200^2 \\
 10004^2 - 9996^2 &= 00400^2 \Rightarrow 9996^2 + 00400^2 \\
 10009^2 - 9991^2 &= 00600^2 \Rightarrow 9991^2 + 00600^2 \\
 10016^2 - 9984^2 &= 00800^2 \Rightarrow 9984^2 + 00800^2 \\
 10025^2 - 9975^2 &= 01000^2 \Rightarrow 9975^2 + 01000^2 \\
 & \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \\
 19216^2 - 0784^2 &= 19200^2 \Rightarrow 0784^2 + 19200^2 \\
 19409^2 - 0591^2 &= 19400^2 \Rightarrow 0591^2 + 19400^2 \\
 19604^2 - 0396^2 &= 19600^2 \Rightarrow 0396^2 + 19600^2 \\
 19801^2 - 0199^2 &= 19800^2 \Rightarrow 0199^2 + 19800^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

2.2.1 Alternative Approach

The **Pythagorean triples** given in (5) can be obtained by an alternative way. For this, let's consider $m = 100$ and varying the values of $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, 99$ in (1), we get respectively the following 99 **Pythagorean triples** written in simplified way. See below:

(9999, 0200, 10001)	(9984, 0800, 10016)	(9951, 1400, 10049)	(9900, 2000, 10100)
(9996, 0400, 10004)	(9975, 1000, 10025)	(9936, 1600, 10064)	(9879, 2200, 10121)
(9991, 0600, 10009)	(9964, 1200, 10036)	(9919, 1800, 10081)	(9856, 2400, 10144)

(9831, 2600, 10169)	(8704, 7200, 11296)	(6519, 11800, 13481)	(3276, 16400, 16724)
(9804, 2800, 10196)	(8631, 7400, 11369)	(6400, 12000, 13600)	(3111, 16600, 16889)
(9775, 3000, 10225)	(8556, 7600, 11444)	(6279, 12200, 13721)	(2944, 16800, 17056)
(9744, 3200, 10256)	(8479, 7800, 11521)	(6156, 12400, 13844)	(2775, 17000, 17225)
(9711, 3400, 10289)	(8400, 8000, 11600)	(6031, 12600, 13969)	(2604, 17200, 17396)
(9676, 3600, 10324)	(8319, 8200, 11681)	(5904, 12800, 14096)	(2431, 17400, 17569)
(9639, 3800, 10361)	(8236, 8400, 11764)	(5775, 13000, 14225)	(2256, 17600, 17744)
(9600, 4000, 10400)	(8151, 8600, 11849)	(5644, 13200, 14356)	(2079, 17800, 17921)
(9559, 4200, 10441)	(8064, 8800, 11936)	(5511, 13400, 14489)	(1900, 18000, 18100)
(9516, 4400, 10484)	(7975, 9000, 12025)	(5376, 13600, 14624)	(1719, 18200, 18281)
(9471, 4600, 10529)	(7884, 9200, 12116)	(5239, 13800, 14761)	(1536, 18400, 18464)
(9424, 4800, 10576)	(7791, 9400, 12209)	(5100, 14000, 14900)	(1351, 18600, 18649)
(9375, 5000, 10625)	(7696, 9600, 12304)	(4959, 14200, 15041)	(1164, 18800, 18836)
(9324, 5200, 10676)	(7599, 9800, 12401)	(4816, 14400, 15184)	(975, 19000, 19025)
(9271, 5400, 10729)	(7500, 10000, 12500)	(4671, 14600, 15329)	(784, 19200, 19216)
(9216, 5600, 10784)	(7399, 10200, 12601)	(4524, 14800, 15476)	(591, 19400, 19409)
(9159, 5800, 10841)	(7296, 10400, 12704)	(4375, 15000, 15625)	(396, 19600, 19604)
(9100, 6000, 10900)	(7191, 10600, 12809)	(4224, 15200, 15776)	(199, 19800, 19801)
(9039, 6200, 10961)	(7084, 10800, 12916)	(4071, 15400, 15929)	(6)
(8976, 6400, 11024)	(6975, 11000, 13025)	(3916, 15600, 16084)	
(8911, 6600, 11089)	(6864, 11200, 13136)	(3759, 15800, 16241)	
(8844, 6800, 11156)	(6751, 11400, 13249)	(3600, 16000, 16400)	
(8775, 7000, 11225)	(6636, 11600, 13364)	(3439, 16200, 16561)	

The triples given in (5) and (6) are the same, but obtained in different ways.

2.3 Third Block

Let's write a number 1000000 as sum of two terms in such a way that second is a perfect square. This gives us 999 expressions with sum of two terms as 1000000. See below

1. $1000000 = 999999 + 000001$
2. $1000000 = 999996 + 000004$
3. $1000000 = 999991 + 000009$
4. $1000000 = 999984 + 000016$
5. $1000000 = 999975 + 000025$
- ...
996. $1000000 = 007984 + 992016$
997. $1000000 = 005991 + 994009$
998. $1000000 = 003996 + 996004$

$$999. 1000000 = 001999 + 998001 \tag{7}$$

The second terms in the *r.h.s.* are perfect squares. Consider a difference of squares between the terms of *r.h.s.* with 1 in the front perfect square term. Then this difference is again a perfect square multiple of 2000. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1000001^2 - 999999^2 &= 0002000^2 \Rightarrow 999999^2 + 0002000^2 = 1000001^2 \Rightarrow (999999, 0002000, 1000001) \\
 1000004^2 - 999996^2 &= 0004000^2 \Rightarrow 999996^2 + 0004000^2 = 1000004^2 \Rightarrow (999996, 0004000, 1000004) \\
 1000009^2 - 999991^2 &= 0006000^2 \Rightarrow 999991^2 + 0006000^2 = 1000009^2 \Rightarrow (999991, 0006000, 1000009) \\
 1000016^2 - 999984^2 &= 0008000^2 \Rightarrow 999984^2 + 0008000^2 = 1000016^2 \Rightarrow (999984, 0008000, 1000016) \\
 1000025^2 - 999975^2 &= 0010000^2 \Rightarrow 999975^2 + 0010000^2 = 1000025^2 \Rightarrow (999975, 0010000, 1000025) \\
 \dots & \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 1992016^2 - 007984^2 &= 1992000^2 \Rightarrow 007984^2 + 1992000^2 = 1992016^2 \Rightarrow (007984, 1992000, 1992016) \\
 1994009^2 - 005991^2 &= 1994000^2 \Rightarrow 005991^2 + 1994000^2 = 1994009^2 \Rightarrow (005991, 1994000, 1994009) \\
 1996004^2 - 003996^2 &= 1996000^2 \Rightarrow 003996^2 + 1996000^2 = 1996004^2 \Rightarrow (003996, 1996000, 1996004) \\
 1998001^2 - 001999^2 &= 1998000^2 \Rightarrow 001999^2 + 1998000^2 = 1998001^2 \Rightarrow (001999, 1998000, 1998001)
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Thus we have a 999 Pythagorean triples given in (8). The same we can generate them using the formula (1). See the subsection below.

2.3.1 Alternative Approach

By considering $m = 1000$ and varying the values of $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, 997, 998, 999$ in (1), we get respectively the following 999 Pythagorean triples:

(999999, 2000, 1000001)	(999516, 44000, 1000484)	(998151, 86000, 1001849)	(995904, 128000, 1004096)
(999996, 4000, 1000004)	(999471, 46000, 1000529)	(998064, 88000, 1001936)	(995775, 130000, 1004225)
(999991, 6000, 1000009)	(999424, 48000, 1000576)	(997975, 90000, 1002025)	(995644, 132000, 1004356)
(999984, 8000, 1000016)	(999375, 50000, 1000625)	(997884, 92000, 1002116)	(995511, 134000, 1004489)
(999975, 10000, 1000025)	(999324, 52000, 1000676)	(997791, 94000, 1002209)	(995376, 136000, 1004624)
(999964, 12000, 1000036)	(999271, 54000, 1000729)	(997696, 96000, 1002304)	(995239, 138000, 1004761)
(999951, 14000, 1000049)	(999216, 56000, 1000784)	(997599, 98000, 1002401)	(995100, 140000, 1004900)
(999936, 16000, 1000064)	(999159, 58000, 1000841)	(997500, 100000, 1002500)	(994959, 142000, 1005041)
(999919, 18000, 1000081)	(999100, 60000, 1000900)	(997399, 102000, 1002601)	(994816, 144000, 1005184)
(999900, 20000, 1000100)	(999039, 62000, 1000961)	(997296, 104000, 1002704)	(994671, 146000, 1005329)
(999879, 22000, 1000121)	(998976, 64000, 1001024)	(997191, 106000, 1002809)	(994524, 148000, 1005476)
(999856, 24000, 1000144)	(998911, 66000, 1001089)	(997084, 108000, 1002916)	(994375, 150000, 1005625)
(999831, 26000, 1000169)	(998844, 68000, 1001156)	(996975, 110000, 1003025)	(994224, 152000, 1005776)
(999804, 28000, 1000196)	(998775, 70000, 1001225)	(996864, 112000, 1003136)	(994071, 154000, 1005929)
(999775, 30000, 1000225)	(998704, 72000, 1001296)	(996751, 114000, 1003249)	(993916, 156000, 1006084)
(999744, 32000, 1000256)	(998631, 74000, 1001369)	(996636, 116000, 1003364)	(993759, 158000, 1006241)
(999711, 34000, 1000289)	(998556, 76000, 1001444)	(996519, 118000, 1003481)	(993600, 160000, 1006400)
(999676, 36000, 1000324)	(998479, 78000, 1001521)	(996400, 120000, 1003600)	(993439, 162000, 1006561)
(999639, 38000, 1000361)	(998400, 80000, 1001600)	(996279, 122000, 1003721)	(993276, 164000, 1006724)
(999600, 40000, 1000400)	(998319, 82000, 1001681)	(996156, 124000, 1003844)	(993111, 166000, 1006889)
(999559, 42000, 1000441)	(998236, 84000, 1001764)	(996031, 126000, 1003969)	(992944, 168000, 1007056)

(992775, 170000, 1007225)	(983100, 260000, 1016900)	(969375, 350000, 1030625)	(951600, 440000, 1048400)
(992604, 172000, 1007396)	(982839, 262000, 1017161)	(969024, 352000, 1030976)	(951159, 442000, 1048841)
(992431, 174000, 1007569)	(982576, 264000, 1017424)	(968671, 354000, 1031329)	(950716, 444000, 1049284)
(992256, 176000, 1007744)	(982311, 266000, 1017689)	(968316, 356000, 1031684)	(950271, 446000, 1049729)
(992079, 178000, 1007921)	(982044, 268000, 1017956)	(967959, 358000, 1032041)	(949824, 448000, 1050176)
(991900, 180000, 1008100)	(981775, 270000, 1018225)	(967600, 360000, 1032400)	(949375, 450000, 1050625)
(991719, 182000, 1008281)	(981504, 272000, 1018496)	(967239, 362000, 1032761)	(948924, 452000, 1051076)
(991536, 184000, 1008464)	(981231, 274000, 1018769)	(966876, 364000, 1033124)	(948471, 454000, 1051529)
(991351, 186000, 1008649)	(980956, 276000, 1019044)	(966511, 366000, 1033489)	(948016, 456000, 1051984)
(991164, 188000, 1008836)	(980679, 278000, 1019321)	(966144, 368000, 1033856)	(947559, 458000, 1052441)
(990975, 190000, 1009025)	(980400, 280000, 1019600)	(965775, 370000, 1034225)	(947100, 460000, 1052900)
(990784, 192000, 1009216)	(980119, 282000, 1019881)	(965404, 372000, 1034596)	(946639, 462000, 1053361)
(990591, 194000, 1009409)	(979836, 284000, 1020164)	(965031, 374000, 1034969)	(946176, 464000, 1053824)
(990396, 196000, 1009604)	(979551, 286000, 1020449)	(964656, 376000, 1035344)	(945711, 466000, 1054289)
(990199, 198000, 1009801)	(979264, 288000, 1020736)	(964279, 378000, 1035721)	(945244, 468000, 1054756)
(990000, 200000, 1010000)	(978975, 290000, 1021025)	(963900, 380000, 1036100)	(944775, 470000, 1055225)
(989799, 202000, 1010201)	(978684, 292000, 1021316)	(963519, 382000, 1036481)	(944304, 472000, 1055696)
(989596, 204000, 1010404)	(978391, 294000, 1021609)	(963136, 384000, 1036864)	(943831, 474000, 1056169)
(989391, 206000, 1010609)	(978096, 296000, 1021904)	(962751, 386000, 1037249)	(943356, 476000, 1056644)
(989184, 208000, 1010816)	(977799, 298000, 1022201)	(962364, 388000, 1037636)	(942879, 478000, 1057121)
(988975, 210000, 1011025)	(977500, 300000, 1022500)	(961975, 390000, 1038025)	(942400, 480000, 1057600)
(988764, 212000, 1011236)	(977199, 302000, 1022801)	(961584, 392000, 1038416)	(941919, 482000, 1058081)
(988551, 214000, 1011449)	(976896, 304000, 1023104)	(961191, 394000, 1038809)	(941436, 484000, 1058564)
(988336, 216000, 1011664)	(976591, 306000, 1023409)	(960796, 396000, 1039204)	(940951, 486000, 1059049)
(988119, 218000, 1011881)	(976284, 308000, 1023716)	(960399, 398000, 1039601)	(940464, 488000, 1059536)
(987900, 220000, 1012100)	(975975, 310000, 1024025)	(960000, 400000, 1040000)	(939975, 490000, 1060025)
(987679, 222000, 1012321)	(975664, 312000, 1024336)	(959599, 402000, 1040401)	(939484, 492000, 1060516)
(987456, 224000, 1012544)	(975351, 314000, 1024649)	(959196, 404000, 1040804)	(938991, 494000, 1061009)
(987231, 226000, 1012769)	(975036, 316000, 1024964)	(958791, 406000, 1041209)	(938496, 496000, 1061504)
(987004, 228000, 1012996)	(974719, 318000, 1025281)	(958384, 408000, 1041616)	(937999, 498000, 1062001)
(986775, 230000, 1013225)	(974400, 320000, 1025600)	(957975, 410000, 1042025)	(937500, 500000, 1062500)
(986544, 232000, 1013456)	(974079, 322000, 1025921)	(957564, 412000, 1042436)	(936999, 502000, 1063001)
(986311, 234000, 1013689)	(973756, 324000, 1026244)	(957151, 414000, 1042849)	(936496, 504000, 1063504)
(986076, 236000, 1013924)	(973431, 326000, 1026569)	(956736, 416000, 1043264)	(935991, 506000, 1064009)
(985839, 238000, 1014161)	(973104, 328000, 1026896)	(956319, 418000, 1043681)	(935484, 508000, 1064516)
(985600, 240000, 1014400)	(972775, 330000, 1027225)	(955900, 420000, 1044100)	(934975, 510000, 1065025)
(985359, 242000, 1014641)	(972444, 332000, 1027556)	(955479, 422000, 1044521)	(934464, 512000, 1065536)
(985116, 244000, 1014884)	(972111, 334000, 1027889)	(955056, 424000, 1044944)	(933951, 514000, 1066049)
(984871, 246000, 1015129)	(971776, 336000, 1028224)	(954631, 426000, 1045369)	(933436, 516000, 1066564)
(984624, 248000, 1015376)	(971439, 338000, 1028561)	(954204, 428000, 1045796)	(932919, 518000, 1067081)
(984375, 250000, 1015625)	(971100, 340000, 1028900)	(953775, 430000, 1046225)	(932400, 520000, 1067600)
(984124, 252000, 1015876)	(970759, 342000, 1029241)	(953344, 432000, 1046656)	(931879, 522000, 1068121)
(983871, 254000, 1016129)	(970416, 344000, 1029584)	(952911, 434000, 1047089)	(931356, 524000, 1068644)
(983616, 256000, 1016384)	(970071, 346000, 1029929)	(952476, 436000, 1047524)	(930831, 526000, 1069169)
(983359, 258000, 1016641)	(969724, 348000, 1030276)	(952039, 438000, 1047961)	(930304, 528000, 1069696)

(929775, 530000, 1070225)	(903900, 620000, 1096100)	(873975, 710000, 1126025)	(840000, 800000, 1160000)
(929244, 532000, 1070756)	(903279, 622000, 1096721)	(873264, 712000, 1126736)	(839199, 802000, 1160801)
(928711, 534000, 1071289)	(902656, 624000, 1097344)	(872551, 714000, 1127449)	(838396, 804000, 1161604)
(928176, 536000, 1071824)	(902031, 626000, 1097969)	(871836, 716000, 1128164)	(837591, 806000, 1162409)
(927639, 538000, 1072361)	(901404, 628000, 1098596)	(871119, 718000, 1128881)	(836784, 808000, 1163216)
(927100, 540000, 1072900)	(900775, 630000, 1099225)	(870400, 720000, 1129600)	(835975, 810000, 1164025)
(926559, 542000, 1073441)	(900144, 632000, 1099856)	(869679, 722000, 1130321)	(835164, 812000, 1164836)
(926016, 544000, 1073984)	(899511, 634000, 1100489)	(868956, 724000, 1131044)	(834351, 814000, 1165649)
(925471, 546000, 1074529)	(898876, 636000, 1101124)	(868231, 726000, 1131769)	(833536, 816000, 1166464)
(924924, 548000, 1075076)	(898239, 638000, 1101761)	(867504, 728000, 1132496)	(832719, 818000, 1167281)
(924375, 550000, 1075625)	(897600, 640000, 1102400)	(866775, 730000, 1133225)	(831900, 820000, 1168100)
(923824, 552000, 1076176)	(896959, 642000, 1103041)	(866044, 732000, 1133956)	(831079, 822000, 1168921)
(923271, 554000, 1076729)	(896316, 644000, 1103684)	(865311, 734000, 1134689)	(830256, 824000, 1169744)
(922716, 556000, 1077284)	(895671, 646000, 1104329)	(864576, 736000, 1135424)	(829431, 826000, 1170569)
(922159, 558000, 1077841)	(895024, 648000, 1104976)	(863839, 738000, 1136161)	(828604, 828000, 1171396)
(921600, 560000, 1078400)	(894375, 650000, 1105625)	(863100, 740000, 1136900)	(827775, 830000, 1172225)
(921039, 562000, 1078961)	(893724, 652000, 1106276)	(862359, 742000, 1137641)	(826944, 832000, 1173056)
(920476, 564000, 1079524)	(893071, 654000, 1106929)	(861616, 744000, 1138384)	(826111, 834000, 1173889)
(919911, 566000, 1080089)	(892416, 656000, 1107584)	(860871, 746000, 1139129)	(825276, 836000, 1174724)
(919344, 568000, 1080656)	(891759, 658000, 1108241)	(860124, 748000, 1139876)	(824439, 838000, 1175561)
(918775, 570000, 1081225)	(891100, 660000, 1108900)	(859375, 750000, 1140625)	(823600, 840000, 1176400)
(918204, 572000, 1081796)	(890439, 662000, 1109561)	(858624, 752000, 1141376)	(822759, 842000, 1177241)
(917631, 574000, 1082369)	(889776, 664000, 1110224)	(857871, 754000, 1142129)	(821916, 844000, 1178084)
(917056, 576000, 1082944)	(889111, 666000, 1110889)	(857116, 756000, 1142884)	(821071, 846000, 1178929)
(916479, 578000, 1083521)	(888444, 668000, 1111556)	(856359, 758000, 1143641)	(820224, 848000, 1179776)
(915900, 580000, 1084100)	(887775, 670000, 1112225)	(855600, 760000, 1144400)	(819375, 850000, 1180625)
(915319, 582000, 1084681)	(887104, 672000, 1112896)	(854839, 762000, 1145161)	(818524, 852000, 1181476)
(914736, 584000, 1085264)	(886431, 674000, 1113569)	(854076, 764000, 1145924)	(817671, 854000, 1182329)
(914151, 586000, 1085849)	(885756, 676000, 1114244)	(853311, 766000, 1146689)	(816816, 856000, 1183184)
(913564, 588000, 1086436)	(885079, 678000, 1114921)	(852544, 768000, 1147456)	(815959, 858000, 1184041)
(912975, 590000, 1087025)	(884400, 680000, 1115600)	(851775, 770000, 1148225)	(815100, 860000, 1184900)
(912384, 592000, 1087616)	(883719, 682000, 1116281)	(851004, 772000, 1148996)	(814239, 862000, 1185761)
(911791, 594000, 1088209)	(883036, 684000, 1116964)	(850231, 774000, 1149769)	(813376, 864000, 1186624)
(911196, 596000, 1088804)	(882351, 686000, 1117649)	(849456, 776000, 1150544)	(812511, 866000, 1187489)
(910599, 598000, 1089401)	(881664, 688000, 1118336)	(848679, 778000, 1151321)	(811644, 868000, 1188356)
(910000, 600000, 1090000)	(880975, 690000, 1119025)	(847900, 780000, 1152100)	(810775, 870000, 1189225)
(909399, 602000, 1090601)	(880284, 692000, 1119716)	(847119, 782000, 1152881)	(809904, 872000, 1190096)
(908796, 604000, 1091204)	(879591, 694000, 1120409)	(846336, 784000, 1153664)	(809031, 874000, 1190969)
(908191, 606000, 1091809)	(878896, 696000, 1121104)	(845551, 786000, 1154449)	(808156, 876000, 1191844)
(907584, 608000, 1092416)	(878199, 698000, 1121801)	(844764, 788000, 1155236)	(807279, 878000, 1192721)
(906975, 610000, 1093025)	(877500, 700000, 1122500)	(843975, 790000, 1156025)	(806400, 880000, 1193600)
(906364, 612000, 1093636)	(876799, 702000, 1123201)	(843184, 792000, 1156816)	(805519, 882000, 1194481)
(905751, 614000, 1094249)	(876096, 704000, 1123904)	(842391, 794000, 1157609)	(804636, 884000, 1195364)
(905136, 616000, 1094864)	(875391, 706000, 1124609)	(841596, 796000, 1158404)	(803751, 886000, 1196249)
(904519, 618000, 1095481)	(874684, 708000, 1125316)	(840799, 798000, 1159201)	(802864, 888000, 1197136)

(29775, 1970000, 1970225)	(21879, 1978000, 1978121)	(13951, 1986000, 1986049)	(5991, 1994000, 1994009)
(27804, 1972000, 1972196)	(19900, 1980000, 1980100)	(11964, 1988000, 1988036)	(3996, 1996000, 1996004)
(25831, 1974000, 1974169)	(17919, 1982000, 1982081)	(9975, 1990000, 1990025)	(1999, 1998000, 1998001) (9)
(23856, 1976000, 1976144)	(15936, 1984000, 1984064)	(7984, 1992000, 1992016)	

The Pythagorean triples given in (8) and (9) are the same. Based on these 999 triples the subsection below given patterns in Pythagorean triples.

3 Patterns in Pythagorean Triples

3.1 First Block

Let's fix the values of m , i.e., $m = 10$, and change the values of n as $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9$, we get respectively the following 9 patterns in Pythagorean Triple:

1)

$$\begin{aligned} 99^2 + 20^2 &= 101^2 \\ 9999^2 + 200^2 &= 10001^2 \\ 999999^2 + 2000^2 &= 1000001^2 \\ 9999999^2 + 20000^2 &= 100000001^2 \end{aligned}$$

5)

$$\begin{aligned} 75^2 + 100^2 &:= 125^2 \\ 9975^2 + 1000^2 &:= 10025^2 \\ 999975^2 + 10000^2 &:= 1000025^2 \\ 99999975^2 + 100000^2 &:= 100000025^2 \end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned} 96^2 + 40^2 &:= 104^2 \\ 9996^2 + 400^2 &:= 10004^2 \\ 999996^2 + 4000^2 &:= 1000004^2 \\ 99999996^2 + 40000^2 &:= 100000004^2 \end{aligned}$$

6)

$$\begin{aligned} 64^2 + 120^2 &:= 136^2 \\ 9964^2 + 1200^2 &:= 10036^2 \\ 999964^2 + 12000^2 &:= 1000036^2 \\ 99999964^2 + 120000^2 &:= 100000036^2 \end{aligned}$$

3)

$$\begin{aligned} 91^2 + 60^2 &:= 109^2 \\ 9991^2 + 600^2 &:= 10009^2 \\ 999991^2 + 6000^2 &:= 1000009^2 \\ 99999991^2 + 60000^2 &:= 100000009^2 \end{aligned}$$

7)

$$\begin{aligned} 51^2 + 140^2 &:= 149^2 \\ 9951^2 + 1400^2 &:= 10049^2 \\ 999951^2 + 14000^2 &:= 1000049^2 \\ 99999951^2 + 140000^2 &:= 100000049^2 \end{aligned}$$

4)

$$\begin{aligned} 84^2 + 80^2 &:= 116^2 \\ 9984^2 + 800^2 &:= 10016^2 \\ 999984^2 + 8000^2 &:= 1000016^2 \\ 99999984^2 + 80000^2 &:= 100000016^2 \end{aligned}$$

8)

$$\begin{aligned} 160^2 + 36^2 &:= 164^2 \\ 19600^2 + 396^2 &:= 19604^2 \\ 1996000^2 + 3996^2 &:= 1996004^2 \\ 199960000^2 + 39996^2 &:= 199960004^2 \end{aligned}$$

9)

$$\begin{aligned} 19^2 + 180^2 &:= 181^2 \\ 9919^2 + 1800^2 &:= 10081^2 \\ 999919^2 + 18000^2 &:= 1000081^2 \\ 99999919^2 + 180000^2 &:= 100000081^2 \end{aligned}$$

In the similar way we can get further Pythagorean triples by considering m as $m = 100, 1000, \dots$, and change the values of n as $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9$. For details refer author's work [8].

3.2 Second Block

Based on the triples given in (5) or (6), let's construct patterns with final sums. This is done for each triple separately. Let's fix the values of m , i.e., $m = 100, 1000, 10000, \dots$ and changing the values of n as $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 97, 98, 99$ in (1), we get respectively the following 99 patterns:

1)

$$\begin{aligned} 9999^2 + 200^2 &:= 10001^2 \\ 999999^2 + 2000^2 &:= 1000001^2 \\ 99999999^2 + 20000^2 &:= 100000001^2 \\ 9999999999^2 + 200000^2 &:= 10000000001^2 \end{aligned}$$

4)

$$\begin{aligned} 9984^2 + 800^2 &:= 10016^2 \\ 999984^2 + 8000^2 &:= 1000016^2 \\ 99999984^2 + 80000^2 &:= 100000016^2 \\ 9999999984^2 + 800000^2 &:= 10000000016^2 \end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned} 9996^2 + 400^2 &:= 10004^2 \\ 999996^2 + 4000^2 &:= 1000004^2 \\ 99999996^2 + 40000^2 &:= 100000004^2 \\ 9999999996^2 + 400000^2 &:= 10000000004^2 \end{aligned}$$

5)

$$\begin{aligned} 9975^2 + 1000^2 &:= 10025^2 \\ 999975^2 + 10000^2 &:= 1000025^2 \\ 99999975^2 + 100000^2 &:= 100000025^2 \\ 9999999975^2 + 1000000^2 &:= 10000000025^2 \end{aligned}$$

3)

$$\begin{aligned} 9991^2 + 600^2 &:= 10009^2 \\ 999991^2 + 6000^2 &:= 1000009^2 \\ 99999991^2 + 60000^2 &:= 100000009^2 \\ 9999999991^2 + 600000^2 &:= 10000000009^2 \end{aligned}$$

6)

$$\begin{aligned} 9964^2 + 1200^2 &:= 10036^2 \\ 999964^2 + 12000^2 &:= 1000036^2 \\ 99999964^2 + 120000^2 &:= 100000036^2 \\ 9999999964^2 + 1200000^2 &:= 10000000036^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 7) $9951^2 + 1400^2 := 10049^2$
 $999951^2 + 14000^2 := 1000049^2$
 $99999951^2 + 140000^2 := 100000049^2$
 $9999999951^2 + 1400000^2 := 10000000049^2$
- 8) $9936^2 + 1600^2 := 10064^2$
 $999936^2 + 16000^2 := 1000064^2$
 $99999936^2 + 160000^2 := 100000064^2$
 $9999999936^2 + 1600000^2 := 10000000064^2$
- 9) $9919^2 + 1800^2 := 10081^2$
 $999919^2 + 18000^2 := 1000081^2$
 $99999919^2 + 180000^2 := 100000081^2$
 $9999999919^2 + 1800000^2 := 10000000081^2$
- 10) $9900^2 + 2000^2 := 10100^2$
 $999900^2 + 20000^2 := 1000100^2$
 $99999900^2 + 200000^2 := 100000100^2$
 $9999999900^2 + 2000000^2 := 10000000100^2$
- 11) $9879^2 + 2200^2 := 10121^2$
 $999879^2 + 22000^2 := 1000121^2$
 $9999879^2 + 220000^2 := 100000121^2$
 $999999879^2 + 2200000^2 := 10000000121^2$
- 12) $9856^2 + 2400^2 := 10144^2$
 $999856^2 + 24000^2 := 1000144^2$
 $9999856^2 + 240000^2 := 100000144^2$
 $999999856^2 + 2400000^2 := 10000000144^2$
- 13) $9831^2 + 2600^2 := 10169^2$
 $999831^2 + 26000^2 := 1000169^2$
 $9999831^2 + 260000^2 := 100000169^2$
 $999999831^2 + 2600000^2 := 10000000169^2$
- 14) $9804^2 + 2800^2 := 10196^2$
 $999804^2 + 28000^2 := 1000196^2$
 $9999804^2 + 280000^2 := 100000196^2$
 $999999804^2 + 2800000^2 := 10000000196^2$
- 15) $9775^2 + 3000^2 := 10225^2$
 $999775^2 + 30000^2 := 1000225^2$
 $9999775^2 + 300000^2 := 100000225^2$
 $999999775^2 + 3000000^2 := 10000000225^2$
- 16) $9744^2 + 3200^2 := 10256^2$
 $999744^2 + 32000^2 := 1000256^2$
 $9999744^2 + 320000^2 := 100000256^2$
 $999999744^2 + 3200000^2 := 10000000256^2$
- 17) $9711^2 + 3400^2 := 10289^2$
 $999711^2 + 34000^2 := 1000289^2$
 $9999711^2 + 340000^2 := 100000289^2$
 $999999711^2 + 3400000^2 := 10000000289^2$

- 18) $9676^2 + 3600^2 := 10324^2$
 $999676^2 + 36000^2 := 1000324^2$
 $99999676^2 + 360000^2 := 100000324^2$
 $9999999676^2 + 3600000^2 := 10000000324^2$
- 19) $9639^2 + 3800^2 := 10361^2$
 $999639^2 + 38000^2 := 1000361^2$
 $99999639^2 + 380000^2 := 100000361^2$
 $9999999639^2 + 3800000^2 := 10000000361^2$
- 20) $9600^2 + 4000^2 := 10400^2$
 $999600^2 + 40000^2 := 1000400^2$
 $99999600^2 + 400000^2 := 100000400^2$
 $9999999600^2 + 4000000^2 := 10000000400^2$
- 21) $9559^2 + 4200^2 := 10441^2$
 $999559^2 + 42000^2 := 1000441^2$
 $99999559^2 + 420000^2 := 100000441^2$
 $9999999559^2 + 4200000^2 := 10000000441^2$
- 22) $9516^2 + 4400^2 := 10484^2$
 $999516^2 + 44000^2 := 1000484^2$
 $99999516^2 + 440000^2 := 100000484^2$
 $9999999516^2 + 4400000^2 := 10000000484^2$
- 23) $9471^2 + 4600^2 := 10529^2$
 $999471^2 + 46000^2 := 1000529^2$
 $99999471^2 + 460000^2 := 100000529^2$
 $9999999471^2 + 4600000^2 := 10000000529^2$
- 24) $9424^2 + 4800^2 := 10576^2$
 $999424^2 + 48000^2 := 1000576^2$
 $99999424^2 + 480000^2 := 100000576^2$
 $9999999424^2 + 4800000^2 := 10000000576^2$
- 25) $9375^2 + 5000^2 := 10625^2$
 $999375^2 + 50000^2 := 1000625^2$
 $99999375^2 + 500000^2 := 100000625^2$
 $9999999375^2 + 5000000^2 := 10000000625^2$
- 26) $9324^2 + 5200^2 := 10676^2$
 $999324^2 + 52000^2 := 1000676^2$
 $99999324^2 + 520000^2 := 100000676^2$
 $9999999324^2 + 5200000^2 := 10000000676^2$
- 27) $9271^2 + 5400^2 := 10729^2$
 $999271^2 + 54000^2 := 1000729^2$
 $99999271^2 + 540000^2 := 100000729^2$
 $9999999271^2 + 5400000^2 := 10000000729^2$
- 28) $9216^2 + 5600^2 := 10784^2$
 $999216^2 + 56000^2 := 1000784^2$
 $99999216^2 + 560000^2 := 100000784^2$
 $9999999216^2 + 5600000^2 := 10000000784^2$

- 29) $9159^2 + 5800^2 := 10841^2$
 $999159^2 + 58000^2 := 1000841^2$
 $99999159^2 + 580000^2 := 100000841^2$
 $9999999159^2 + 5800000^2 := 10000000841^2$
- 30) $9100^2 + 6000^2 := 10900^2$
 $999100^2 + 60000^2 := 1000900^2$
 $99999100^2 + 600000^2 := 100000900^2$
 $9999999100^2 + 6000000^2 := 10000000900^2$
- 31) $9039^2 + 6200^2 := 10961^2$
 $999039^2 + 62000^2 := 1000961^2$
 $99999039^2 + 620000^2 := 100000961^2$
 $9999999039^2 + 6200000^2 := 10000000961^2$
- 32) $8976^2 + 6400^2 := 11024^2$
 $998976^2 + 64000^2 := 1001024^2$
 $99998976^2 + 640000^2 := 100001024^2$
 $9999998976^2 + 6400000^2 := 10000001024^2$
- 33) $8911^2 + 6600^2 := 11089^2$
 $998911^2 + 66000^2 := 1001089^2$
 $99998911^2 + 660000^2 := 100001089^2$
 $9999998911^2 + 6600000^2 := 10000001089^2$
- 34) $8844^2 + 6800^2 := 11156^2$
 $998844^2 + 68000^2 := 1001156^2$
 $99998844^2 + 680000^2 := 100001156^2$
 $9999998844^2 + 6800000^2 := 10000001156^2$
- 35) $8775^2 + 7000^2 := 11225^2$
 $998775^2 + 70000^2 := 1001225^2$
 $99998775^2 + 700000^2 := 100001225^2$
 $9999998775^2 + 7000000^2 := 10000001225^2$
- 36) $8704^2 + 7200^2 := 11296^2$
 $998704^2 + 72000^2 := 1001296^2$
 $99998704^2 + 720000^2 := 100001296^2$
 $9999998704^2 + 7200000^2 := 10000001296^2$
- 37) $8631^2 + 7400^2 := 11369^2$
 $998631^2 + 74000^2 := 1001369^2$
 $99998631^2 + 740000^2 := 100001369^2$
 $9999998631^2 + 7400000^2 := 10000001369^2$
- 38) $8556^2 + 7600^2 := 11444^2$
 $998556^2 + 76000^2 := 1001444^2$
 $99998556^2 + 760000^2 := 100001444^2$
 $9999998556^2 + 7600000^2 := 10000001444^2$
- 39) $8479^2 + 7800^2 := 11521^2$
 $998479^2 + 78000^2 := 1001521^2$
 $99998479^2 + 780000^2 := 100001521^2$
 $9999998479^2 + 7800000^2 := 10000001521^2$

- 40) $8400^2 + 8000^2 := 11600^2$
 $998400^2 + 80000^2 := 1001600^2$
 $99998400^2 + 800000^2 := 100001600^2$
 $9999998400^2 + 8000000^2 := 10000001600^2$
- 41) $8319^2 + 8200^2 := 11681^2$
 $998319^2 + 82000^2 := 1001681^2$
 $99998319^2 + 820000^2 := 100001681^2$
 $9999998319^2 + 8200000^2 := 10000001681^2$
- 42) $8236^2 + 8400^2 := 11764^2$
 $998236^2 + 84000^2 := 1001764^2$
 $99998236^2 + 840000^2 := 100001764^2$
 $9999998236^2 + 8400000^2 := 10000001764^2$
- 43) $8151^2 + 8600^2 := 11849^2$
 $998151^2 + 86000^2 := 1001849^2$
 $99998151^2 + 860000^2 := 100001849^2$
 $9999998151^2 + 8600000^2 := 10000001849^2$
- 44) $8064^2 + 8800^2 := 11936^2$
 $998064^2 + 88000^2 := 1001936^2$
 $99998064^2 + 880000^2 := 100001936^2$
 $9999998064^2 + 8800000^2 := 10000001936^2$
- 45) $7975^2 + 9000^2 := 12025^2$
 $997975^2 + 90000^2 := 1002025^2$
 $99997975^2 + 900000^2 := 100002025^2$
 $9999997975^2 + 9000000^2 := 10000002025^2$
- 46) $7884^2 + 9200^2 := 12116^2$
 $997884^2 + 92000^2 := 1002116^2$
 $99997884^2 + 920000^2 := 100002116^2$
 $9999997884^2 + 9200000^2 := 10000002116^2$
- 47) $7791^2 + 9400^2 := 12209^2$
 $997791^2 + 94000^2 := 1002209^2$
 $99997791^2 + 940000^2 := 100002209^2$
 $9999997791^2 + 9400000^2 := 10000002209^2$
- 48) $7696^2 + 9600^2 := 12304^2$
 $997696^2 + 96000^2 := 1002304^2$
 $99997696^2 + 960000^2 := 100002304^2$
 $9999997696^2 + 9600000^2 := 10000002304^2$
- 49) $7599^2 + 9800^2 := 12401^2$
 $997599^2 + 98000^2 := 1002401^2$
 $99997599^2 + 980000^2 := 100002401^2$
 $9999997599^2 + 9800000^2 := 10000002401^2$
- 50) $7500^2 + 10000^2 := 12500^2$
 $997500^2 + 100000^2 := 1002500^2$
 $99997500^2 + 1000000^2 := 100002500^2$
 $9999997500^2 + 10000000^2 := 10000002500^2$

- 51) $7399^2 + 10200^2 := 12601^2$
 $997399^2 + 102000^2 := 1002601^2$
 $99997399^2 + 1020000^2 := 100002601^2$
 $9999997399^2 + 10200000^2 := 10000002601^2$
- 52) $7296^2 + 10400^2 := 12704^2$
 $997296^2 + 104000^2 := 1002704^2$
 $99997296^2 + 1040000^2 := 100002704^2$
 $9999997296^2 + 10400000^2 := 10000002704^2$
- 53) $7191^2 + 10600^2 := 12809^2$
 $997191^2 + 106000^2 := 1002809^2$
 $99997191^2 + 1060000^2 := 100002809^2$
 $9999997191^2 + 10600000^2 := 10000002809^2$
- 54) $7084^2 + 10800^2 := 12916^2$
 $997084^2 + 108000^2 := 1002916^2$
 $99997084^2 + 1080000^2 := 100002916^2$
 $9999997084^2 + 10800000^2 := 10000002916^2$
- 55) $6975^2 + 11000^2 := 13025^2$
 $996975^2 + 110000^2 := 1003025^2$
 $99996975^2 + 1100000^2 := 100003025^2$
 $9999996975^2 + 11000000^2 := 10000003025^2$
- 56) $6864^2 + 11200^2 := 13136^2$
 $996864^2 + 112000^2 := 1003136^2$
 $99996864^2 + 1120000^2 := 100003136^2$
 $9999996864^2 + 11200000^2 := 10000003136^2$
- 57) $6751^2 + 11400^2 := 13249^2$
 $996751^2 + 114000^2 := 1003249^2$
 $99996751^2 + 1140000^2 := 100003249^2$
 $9999996751^2 + 11400000^2 := 10000003249^2$
- 58) $6636^2 + 11600^2 := 13364^2$
 $996636^2 + 116000^2 := 1003364^2$
 $99996636^2 + 1160000^2 := 100003364^2$
 $9999996636^2 + 11600000^2 := 10000003364^2$
- 59) $6519^2 + 11800^2 := 13481^2$
 $996519^2 + 118000^2 := 1003481^2$
 $99996519^2 + 1180000^2 := 100003481^2$
 $9999996519^2 + 11800000^2 := 10000003481^2$
- 60) $6400^2 + 12000^2 := 13600^2$
 $996400^2 + 120000^2 := 1003600^2$
 $99996400^2 + 1200000^2 := 100003600^2$
 $9999996400^2 + 12000000^2 := 10000003600^2$
- 61) $6279^2 + 12200^2 := 13721^2$
 $996279^2 + 122000^2 := 1003721^2$
 $99996279^2 + 1220000^2 := 100003721^2$
 $9999996279^2 + 12200000^2 := 10000003721^2$

- 62) $6156^2 + 12400^2 := 13844^2$
 $996156^2 + 124000^2 := 1003844^2$
 $99996156^2 + 1240000^2 := 100003844^2$
 $9999996156^2 + 12400000^2 := 10000003844^2$
- 63) $6031^2 + 12600^2 := 13969^2$
 $996031^2 + 126000^2 := 1003969^2$
 $99996031^2 + 1260000^2 := 100003969^2$
 $9999996031^2 + 12600000^2 := 10000003969^2$
- 64) $5904^2 + 12800^2 := 14096^2$
 $995904^2 + 128000^2 := 1004096^2$
 $99995904^2 + 1280000^2 := 100004096^2$
 $9999995904^2 + 12800000^2 := 10000004096^2$
- 65) $5775^2 + 13000^2 := 14225^2$
 $995775^2 + 130000^2 := 1004225^2$
 $99995775^2 + 1300000^2 := 100004225^2$
 $9999995775^2 + 13000000^2 := 10000004225^2$
- 66) $5644^2 + 13200^2 := 14356^2$
 $995644^2 + 132000^2 := 1004356^2$
 $99995644^2 + 1320000^2 := 100004356^2$
 $9999995644^2 + 13200000^2 := 10000004356^2$
- 67) $5511^2 + 13400^2 := 14489^2$
 $995511^2 + 134000^2 := 1004489^2$
 $99995511^2 + 1340000^2 := 100004489^2$
 $9999995511^2 + 13400000^2 := 10000004489^2$
- 68) $5376^2 + 13600^2 := 14624^2$
 $995376^2 + 136000^2 := 1004624^2$
 $99995376^2 + 1360000^2 := 100004624^2$
 $9999995376^2 + 13600000^2 := 10000004624^2$
- 69) $5239^2 + 13800^2 := 14761^2$
 $995239^2 + 138000^2 := 1004761^2$
 $99995239^2 + 1380000^2 := 100004761^2$
 $9999995239^2 + 13800000^2 := 10000004761^2$
- 70) $5100^2 + 14000^2 := 14900^2$
 $995100^2 + 140000^2 := 1004900^2$
 $99995100^2 + 1400000^2 := 100004900^2$
 $9999995100^2 + 14000000^2 := 10000004900^2$
- 71) $4959^2 + 14200^2 := 15041^2$
 $994959^2 + 142000^2 := 1005041^2$
 $99994959^2 + 1420000^2 := 100005041^2$
 $9999994959^2 + 14200000^2 := 10000005041^2$
- 72) $4816^2 + 14400^2 := 15184^2$
 $994816^2 + 144000^2 := 1005184^2$
 $99994816^2 + 1440000^2 := 100005184^2$
 $9999994816^2 + 14400000^2 := 10000005184^2$

- 73) $4671^2 + 14600^2 := 15329^2$
 $994671^2 + 146000^2 := 1005329^2$
 $99994671^2 + 1460000^2 := 100005329^2$
 $9999994671^2 + 14600000^2 := 10000005329^2$
- 74) $4524^2 + 14800^2 := 15476^2$
 $994524^2 + 148000^2 := 1005476^2$
 $99994524^2 + 1480000^2 := 100005476^2$
 $9999994524^2 + 14800000^2 := 10000005476^2$
- 75) $4375^2 + 15000^2 := 15625^2$
 $994375^2 + 150000^2 := 1005625^2$
 $99994375^2 + 1500000^2 := 100005625^2$
 $9999994375^2 + 15000000^2 := 10000005625^2$
- 76) $4224^2 + 15200^2 := 15776^2$
 $994224^2 + 152000^2 := 1005776^2$
 $99994224^2 + 1520000^2 := 100005776^2$
 $9999994224^2 + 15200000^2 := 10000005776^2$
- 77) $4071^2 + 15400^2 := 15929^2$
 $994071^2 + 154000^2 := 1005929^2$
 $99994071^2 + 1540000^2 := 100005929^2$
 $9999994071^2 + 15400000^2 := 10000005929^2$
- 78) $3916^2 + 15600^2 := 16084^2$
 $993916^2 + 156000^2 := 1006084^2$
 $99993916^2 + 1560000^2 := 100006084^2$
 $9999993916^2 + 15600000^2 := 10000006084^2$
- 79) $3759^2 + 15800^2 := 16241^2$
 $993759^2 + 158000^2 := 1006241^2$
 $99993759^2 + 1580000^2 := 100006241^2$
 $9999993759^2 + 15800000^2 := 10000006241^2$
- 80) $3600^2 + 16000^2 := 16400^2$
 $993600^2 + 160000^2 := 1006400^2$
 $99993600^2 + 1600000^2 := 100006400^2$
 $9999993600^2 + 16000000^2 := 10000006400^2$
- 81) $3439^2 + 16200^2 := 16561^2$
 $993439^2 + 162000^2 := 1006561^2$
 $99993439^2 + 1620000^2 := 100006561^2$
 $9999993439^2 + 16200000^2 := 10000006561^2$
- 82) $3276^2 + 16400^2 := 16724^2$
 $993276^2 + 164000^2 := 1006724^2$
 $99993276^2 + 1640000^2 := 100006724^2$
 $9999993276^2 + 16400000^2 := 10000006724^2$
- 83) $3111^2 + 16600^2 := 16889^2$
 $993111^2 + 166000^2 := 1006889^2$
 $99993111^2 + 1660000^2 := 100006889^2$
 $9999993111^2 + 16600000^2 := 10000006889^2$

- 84) $2944^2 + 16800^2 := 17056^2$
 $992944^2 + 168000^2 := 1007056^2$
 $99992944^2 + 1680000^2 := 100007056^2$
 $9999992944^2 + 16800000^2 := 10000007056^2$
- 85) $2775^2 + 17000^2 := 17225^2$
 $992775^2 + 170000^2 := 1007225^2$
 $99992775^2 + 1700000^2 := 100007225^2$
 $9999992775^2 + 17000000^2 := 10000007225^2$
- 86) $2604^2 + 17200^2 := 17396^2$
 $992604^2 + 172000^2 := 1007396^2$
 $99992604^2 + 1720000^2 := 100007396^2$
 $9999992604^2 + 17200000^2 := 10000007396^2$
- 87) $2431^2 + 17400^2 := 17569^2$
 $992431^2 + 174000^2 := 1007569^2$
 $99992431^2 + 1740000^2 := 100007569^2$
 $9999992431^2 + 17400000^2 := 10000007569^2$
- 88) $2256^2 + 17600^2 := 17744^2$
 $992256^2 + 176000^2 := 1007744^2$
 $99992256^2 + 1760000^2 := 100007744^2$
 $9999992256^2 + 17600000^2 := 10000007744^2$
- 89) $2079^2 + 17800^2 := 17921^2$
 $992079^2 + 178000^2 := 1007921^2$
 $99992079^2 + 1780000^2 := 100007921^2$
 $9999992079^2 + 17800000^2 := 10000007921^2$
- 90) $1900^2 + 18000^2 := 18100^2$
 $991900^2 + 180000^2 := 1008100^2$
 $99991900^2 + 1800000^2 := 100008100^2$
 $9999991900^2 + 18000000^2 := 10000008100^2$
- 91) $1719^2 + 18200^2 := 18281^2$
 $991719^2 + 182000^2 := 1008281^2$
 $99991719^2 + 1820000^2 := 100008281^2$
 $9999991719^2 + 18200000^2 := 10000008281^2$
- 92) $1536^2 + 18400^2 := 18464^2$
 $991536^2 + 184000^2 := 1008464^2$
 $99991536^2 + 1840000^2 := 100008464^2$
 $9999991536^2 + 18400000^2 := 10000008464^2$
- 93) $1351^2 + 18600^2 := 18649^2$
 $991351^2 + 186000^2 := 1008649^2$
 $99991351^2 + 1860000^2 := 100008649^2$
 $9999991351^2 + 18600000^2 := 10000008649^2$
- 94) $1164^2 + 18800^2 := 18836^2$
 $991164^2 + 188000^2 := 1008836^2$
 $99991164^2 + 1880000^2 := 100008836^2$
 $9999991164^2 + 18800000^2 := 10000008836^2$

<p>95)</p> $975^2 + 19000^2 := 19025^2$ $990975^2 + 190000^2 := 1009025^2$ $99990975^2 + 1900000^2 := 100009025^2$ $9999990975^2 + 19000000^2 := 10000009025^2$	<p>98)</p> $396^2 + 19600^2 := 19604^2$ $990396^2 + 196000^2 := 1009604^2$ $99990396^2 + 1960000^2 := 100009604^2$ $9999990396^2 + 19600000^2 := 10000009604^2$
<p>96)</p> $784^2 + 19200^2 := 19216^2$ $990784^2 + 192000^2 := 1009216^2$ $99990784^2 + 1920000^2 := 100009216^2$ $9999990784^2 + 19200000^2 := 10000009216^2$	<p>99)</p> $199^2 + 19800^2 := 19801^2$ $990199^2 + 198000^2 := 1009801^2$ $99990199^2 + 1980000^2 := 100009801^2$ $9999990199^2 + 19800000^2 := 10000009801^2$
<p>97)</p> $591^2 + 19400^2 := 19409^2$ $990591^2 + 194000^2 := 1009409^2$ $99990591^2 + 1940000^2 := 100009409^2$ $9999990591^2 + 19400000^2 := 10000009409^2$	

3.3 Third Block

Based on the triples given in (8) or (9), let's construct patterns with final sums. This is done for each triple separately. Let's fix the values of m , i.e., $m = 1000, 10000, \dots$ and changing the values of n as $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 997, 998, 999$ in (1), we get respectively the following 999 patterns given below:

<p>1)</p> $999999^2 + 2000^2 := 1000001^2$ $9999999^2 + 20000^2 := 100000001^2$ $99999999^2 + 200000^2 := 10000000001^2$ $999999999^2 + 2000000^2 := 1000000000001^2$	<p>3)</p> $999991^2 + 6000^2 := 1000009^2$ $9999991^2 + 60000^2 := 100000009^2$ $99999991^2 + 600000^2 := 10000000009^2$ $999999991^2 + 6000000^2 := 1000000000009^2$
<p>2)</p> $999996^2 + 4000^2 := 1000004^2$ $9999996^2 + 40000^2 := 100000004^2$ $99999996^2 + 400000^2 := 10000000004^2$ $999999996^2 + 4000000^2 := 1000000000004^2$	<p>4)</p> $999984^2 + 8000^2 := 1000016^2$ $9999984^2 + 80000^2 := 100000016^2$ $99999984^2 + 800000^2 := 10000000016^2$ $999999984^2 + 8000000^2 := 1000000000016^2$

5)

$$\begin{aligned} 999975^2 + 10000^2 &:= 1000025^2 \\ 99999975^2 + 100000^2 &:= 100000025^2 \\ 9999999975^2 + 1000000^2 &:= 10000000025^2 \\ 999999999975^2 + 10000000^2 &:= 1000000000025^2 \end{aligned}$$

6)

$$\begin{aligned} 999964^2 + 12000^2 &:= 1000036^2 \\ 99999964^2 + 120000^2 &:= 100000036^2 \\ 9999999964^2 + 1200000^2 &:= 10000000036^2 \\ 999999999964^2 + 12000000^2 &:= 1000000000036^2 \end{aligned}$$

7)

$$\begin{aligned} 999951^2 + 14000^2 &:= 1000049^2 \\ 99999951^2 + 140000^2 &:= 100000049^2 \\ 9999999951^2 + 1400000^2 &:= 10000000049^2 \\ 999999999951^2 + 14000000^2 &:= 1000000000049^2 \end{aligned}$$

8)

$$\begin{aligned} 999936^2 + 16000^2 &:= 1000064^2 \\ 99999936^2 + 160000^2 &:= 100000064^2 \\ 9999999936^2 + 1600000^2 &:= 10000000064^2 \\ 999999999936^2 + 16000000^2 &:= 1000000000064^2 \end{aligned}$$

9)

$$\begin{aligned} 999919^2 + 18000^2 &:= 1000081^2 \\ 99999919^2 + 180000^2 &:= 100000081^2 \\ 9999999919^2 + 1800000^2 &:= 10000000081^2 \\ 999999999919^2 + 18000000^2 &:= 1000000000081^2 \end{aligned}$$

10)

$$\begin{aligned} 999900^2 + 20000^2 &:= 1000100^2 \\ 99999900^2 + 200000^2 &:= 100000100^2 \\ 9999999900^2 + 2000000^2 &:= 10000000100^2 \\ 999999999900^2 + 20000000^2 &:= 1000000000100^2 \end{aligned}$$

11)

$$\begin{aligned} 999879^2 + 22000^2 &:= 1000121^2 \\ 99999879^2 + 220000^2 &:= 100000121^2 \\ 9999999879^2 + 2200000^2 &:= 10000000121^2 \\ 999999999879^2 + 22000000^2 &:= 1000000000121^2 \end{aligned}$$

12)

$$\begin{aligned} 999856^2 + 24000^2 &:= 1000144^2 \\ 99999856^2 + 240000^2 &:= 100000144^2 \\ 9999999856^2 + 2400000^2 &:= 10000000144^2 \\ 999999999856^2 + 24000000^2 &:= 1000000000144^2 \end{aligned}$$

13)

$$\begin{aligned} 999831^2 + 26000^2 &:= 1000169^2 \\ 99999831^2 + 260000^2 &:= 100000169^2 \\ 9999999831^2 + 2600000^2 &:= 10000000169^2 \\ 999999999831^2 + 26000000^2 &:= 1000000000169^2 \end{aligned}$$

14)

$$\begin{aligned} 999804^2 + 28000^2 &:= 1000196^2 \\ 99999804^2 + 280000^2 &:= 100000196^2 \\ 9999999804^2 + 2800000^2 &:= 10000000196^2 \\ 999999999804^2 + 28000000^2 &:= 1000000000196^2 \end{aligned}$$

15)

$$\begin{aligned} 999775^2 + 30000^2 &:= 1000225^2 \\ 99999775^2 + 300000^2 &:= 100000225^2 \\ 9999999775^2 + 3000000^2 &:= 10000000225^2 \\ 999999999775^2 + 30000000^2 &:= 1000000000225^2 \end{aligned}$$

16)

$$\begin{aligned} 999744^2 + 32000^2 &:= 1000256^2 \\ 99999744^2 + 320000^2 &:= 100000256^2 \\ 9999999744^2 + 3200000^2 &:= 10000000256^2 \\ 999999999744^2 + 32000000^2 &:= 1000000000256^2 \end{aligned}$$

17)

$$\begin{aligned} 999711^2 + 34000^2 &:= 1000289^2 \\ 99999711^2 + 340000^2 &:= 100000289^2 \\ 9999999711^2 + 3400000^2 &:= 10000000289^2 \\ 999999999711^2 + 34000000^2 &:= 1000000000289^2 \end{aligned}$$

18)

$$\begin{aligned}999676^2 + 36000^2 &:= 1000324^2 \\99999676^2 + 360000^2 &:= 100000324^2 \\9999999676^2 + 3600000^2 &:= 10000000324^2 \\999999999676^2 + 36000000^2 &:= 1000000000324^2\end{aligned}$$

19)

$$\begin{aligned}999639^2 + 38000^2 &:= 1000361^2 \\99999639^2 + 380000^2 &:= 100000361^2 \\9999999639^2 + 3800000^2 &:= 10000000361^2 \\999999999639^2 + 38000000^2 &:= 1000000000361^2\end{aligned}$$

20)

$$\begin{aligned}999600^2 + 40000^2 &:= 1000400^2 \\99999600^2 + 400000^2 &:= 100000400^2 \\9999999600^2 + 4000000^2 &:= 10000000400^2 \\999999999600^2 + 40000000^2 &:= 1000000000400^2\end{aligned}$$

21)

$$\begin{aligned}999559^2 + 42000^2 &:= 1000441^2 \\99999559^2 + 420000^2 &:= 100000441^2 \\9999999559^2 + 4200000^2 &:= 10000000441^2 \\999999999559^2 + 42000000^2 &:= 1000000000441^2\end{aligned}$$

22)

$$\begin{aligned}999516^2 + 44000^2 &:= 1000484^2 \\99999516^2 + 440000^2 &:= 100000484^2 \\9999999516^2 + 4400000^2 &:= 10000000484^2 \\999999999516^2 + 44000000^2 &:= 1000000000484^2\end{aligned}$$

23)

$$\begin{aligned}999471^2 + 46000^2 &:= 1000529^2 \\99999471^2 + 460000^2 &:= 100000529^2 \\9999999471^2 + 4600000^2 &:= 10000000529^2 \\999999999471^2 + 46000000^2 &:= 1000000000529^2\end{aligned}$$

24)

$$\begin{aligned}999424^2 + 48000^2 &:= 1000576^2 \\99999424^2 + 480000^2 &:= 100000576^2 \\9999999424^2 + 4800000^2 &:= 10000000576^2 \\999999999424^2 + 48000000^2 &:= 1000000000576^2\end{aligned}$$

25)

$$\begin{aligned}999375^2 + 50000^2 &:= 1000625^2 \\99999375^2 + 500000^2 &:= 100000625^2 \\9999999375^2 + 5000000^2 &:= 10000000625^2 \\999999999375^2 + 50000000^2 &:= 1000000000625^2\end{aligned}$$

26)

$$\begin{aligned}999324^2 + 52000^2 &:= 1000676^2 \\99999324^2 + 520000^2 &:= 100000676^2 \\9999999324^2 + 5200000^2 &:= 10000000676^2 \\999999999324^2 + 52000000^2 &:= 1000000000676^2\end{aligned}$$

27)

$$\begin{aligned}999271^2 + 54000^2 &:= 1000729^2 \\99999271^2 + 540000^2 &:= 100000729^2 \\9999999271^2 + 5400000^2 &:= 10000000729^2 \\999999999271^2 + 54000000^2 &:= 1000000000729^2\end{aligned}$$

28)

$$\begin{aligned}999216^2 + 56000^2 &:= 1000784^2 \\99999216^2 + 560000^2 &:= 100000784^2 \\9999999216^2 + 5600000^2 &:= 10000000784^2 \\999999999216^2 + 56000000^2 &:= 1000000000784^2\end{aligned}$$

29)

$$\begin{aligned}999159^2 + 58000^2 &:= 1000841^2 \\99999159^2 + 580000^2 &:= 100000841^2 \\9999999159^2 + 5800000^2 &:= 10000000841^2 \\999999999159^2 + 58000000^2 &:= 1000000000841^2\end{aligned}$$

30)

$$\begin{aligned}999100^2 + 60000^2 &:= 1000900^2 \\99999100^2 + 600000^2 &:= 100000900^2 \\9999999100^2 + 6000000^2 &:= 10000000900^2 \\999999999100^2 + 60000000^2 &:= 1000000000900^2\end{aligned}$$

31)

$$\begin{aligned} 999039^2 + 62000^2 &:= 1000961^2 \\ 99999039^2 + 620000^2 &:= 100000961^2 \\ 9999999039^2 + 6200000^2 &:= 10000000961^2 \\ 999999999039^2 + 62000000^2 &:= 1000000000961^2 \end{aligned}$$

32)

$$\begin{aligned} 998976^2 + 64000^2 &:= 1001024^2 \\ 99998976^2 + 640000^2 &:= 100001024^2 \\ 999998976^2 + 6400000^2 &:= 10000001024^2 \\ 9999998976^2 + 64000000^2 &:= 1000000001024^2 \end{aligned}$$

33)

$$\begin{aligned} 998911^2 + 66000^2 &:= 1001089^2 \\ 99998911^2 + 660000^2 &:= 100001089^2 \\ 999998911^2 + 6600000^2 &:= 10000001089^2 \\ 9999998911^2 + 66000000^2 &:= 1000000001089^2 \end{aligned}$$

34)

$$\begin{aligned} 998844^2 + 68000^2 &:= 1001156^2 \\ 99998844^2 + 680000^2 &:= 100001156^2 \\ 999998844^2 + 6800000^2 &:= 10000001156^2 \\ 9999998844^2 + 68000000^2 &:= 1000000001156^2 \end{aligned}$$

35)

$$\begin{aligned} 998775^2 + 70000^2 &:= 1001225^2 \\ 99998775^2 + 700000^2 &:= 100001225^2 \\ 999998775^2 + 7000000^2 &:= 10000001225^2 \\ 9999998775^2 + 70000000^2 &:= 1000000001225^2 \end{aligned}$$

36)

$$\begin{aligned} 998704^2 + 72000^2 &:= 1001296^2 \\ 99998704^2 + 720000^2 &:= 100001296^2 \\ 999998704^2 + 7200000^2 &:= 10000001296^2 \\ 9999998704^2 + 72000000^2 &:= 1000000001296^2 \end{aligned}$$

37)

$$\begin{aligned} 998631^2 + 74000^2 &:= 1001369^2 \\ 99998631^2 + 740000^2 &:= 100001369^2 \\ 999998631^2 + 7400000^2 &:= 10000001369^2 \\ 9999998631^2 + 74000000^2 &:= 1000000001369^2 \end{aligned}$$

38)

$$\begin{aligned} 998556^2 + 76000^2 &:= 1001444^2 \\ 99998556^2 + 760000^2 &:= 100001444^2 \\ 999998556^2 + 7600000^2 &:= 10000001444^2 \\ 9999998556^2 + 76000000^2 &:= 1000000001444^2 \end{aligned}$$

39)

$$\begin{aligned} 998479^2 + 78000^2 &:= 1001521^2 \\ 99998479^2 + 780000^2 &:= 100001521^2 \\ 999998479^2 + 7800000^2 &:= 10000001521^2 \\ 9999998479^2 + 78000000^2 &:= 1000000001521^2 \end{aligned}$$

40)

$$\begin{aligned} 998400^2 + 80000^2 &:= 1001600^2 \\ 99998400^2 + 800000^2 &:= 100001600^2 \\ 999998400^2 + 8000000^2 &:= 10000001600^2 \\ 9999998400^2 + 80000000^2 &:= 1000000001600^2 \end{aligned}$$

41)

$$\begin{aligned} 998319^2 + 82000^2 &:= 1001681^2 \\ 99998319^2 + 820000^2 &:= 100001681^2 \\ 999998319^2 + 8200000^2 &:= 10000001681^2 \\ 9999998319^2 + 82000000^2 &:= 1000000001681^2 \end{aligned}$$

42)

$$\begin{aligned} 998236^2 + 84000^2 &:= 1001764^2 \\ 99998236^2 + 840000^2 &:= 100001764^2 \\ 999998236^2 + 8400000^2 &:= 10000001764^2 \\ 9999998236^2 + 84000000^2 &:= 1000000001764^2 \end{aligned}$$

43)

$$\begin{aligned} 998151^2 + 86000^2 &:= 1001849^2 \\ 99998151^2 + 860000^2 &:= 100001849^2 \\ 999998151^2 + 8600000^2 &:= 10000001849^2 \\ 9999998151^2 + 86000000^2 &:= 1000000001849^2 \end{aligned}$$

44)

$$\begin{aligned}998064^2 + 88000^2 &:= 1001936^2 \\99998064^2 + 880000^2 &:= 100001936^2 \\9999998064^2 + 8800000^2 &:= 10000001936^2 \\99999998064^2 + 88000000^2 &:= 1000000001936^2\end{aligned}$$

45)

$$\begin{aligned}997975^2 + 90000^2 &:= 1002025^2 \\99997975^2 + 900000^2 &:= 100002025^2 \\9999997975^2 + 9000000^2 &:= 10000002025^2 \\99999997975^2 + 90000000^2 &:= 1000000002025^2\end{aligned}$$

46)

$$\begin{aligned}997884^2 + 92000^2 &:= 1002116^2 \\99997884^2 + 920000^2 &:= 100002116^2 \\9999997884^2 + 9200000^2 &:= 10000002116^2 \\99999997884^2 + 92000000^2 &:= 1000000002116^2\end{aligned}$$

47)

$$\begin{aligned}997791^2 + 94000^2 &:= 1002209^2 \\99997791^2 + 940000^2 &:= 100002209^2 \\9999997791^2 + 9400000^2 &:= 10000002209^2 \\99999997791^2 + 94000000^2 &:= 1000000002209^2\end{aligned}$$

48)

$$\begin{aligned}997696^2 + 96000^2 &:= 1002304^2 \\99997696^2 + 960000^2 &:= 100002304^2 \\9999997696^2 + 9600000^2 &:= 10000002304^2 \\99999997696^2 + 96000000^2 &:= 1000000002304^2\end{aligned}$$

49)

$$\begin{aligned}997599^2 + 98000^2 &:= 1002401^2 \\99997599^2 + 980000^2 &:= 100002401^2 \\9999997599^2 + 9800000^2 &:= 10000002401^2 \\99999997599^2 + 98000000^2 &:= 1000000002401^2\end{aligned}$$

50)

$$\begin{aligned}997500^2 + 100000^2 &:= 1002500^2 \\99997500^2 + 1000000^2 &:= 100002500^2 \\9999997500^2 + 10000000^2 &:= 10000002500^2 \\99999997500^2 + 100000000^2 &:= 1000000002500^2\end{aligned}$$

51)

$$\begin{aligned}997399^2 + 102000^2 &:= 1002601^2 \\99997399^2 + 1020000^2 &:= 100002601^2 \\9999997399^2 + 10200000^2 &:= 10000002601^2 \\99999997399^2 + 102000000^2 &:= 1000000002601^2\end{aligned}$$

52)

$$\begin{aligned}997296^2 + 104000^2 &:= 1002704^2 \\99997296^2 + 1040000^2 &:= 100002704^2 \\9999997296^2 + 10400000^2 &:= 10000002704^2 \\99999997296^2 + 104000000^2 &:= 1000000002704^2\end{aligned}$$

53)

$$\begin{aligned}997191^2 + 106000^2 &:= 1002809^2 \\99997191^2 + 1060000^2 &:= 100002809^2 \\9999997191^2 + 10600000^2 &:= 10000002809^2 \\99999997191^2 + 106000000^2 &:= 1000000002809^2\end{aligned}$$

54)

$$\begin{aligned}997084^2 + 108000^2 &:= 1002916^2 \\99997084^2 + 1080000^2 &:= 100002916^2 \\9999997084^2 + 10800000^2 &:= 10000002916^2 \\99999997084^2 + 108000000^2 &:= 1000000002916^2\end{aligned}$$

55)

$$\begin{aligned}996975^2 + 110000^2 &:= 1003025^2 \\99996975^2 + 1100000^2 &:= 100003025^2 \\9999996975^2 + 11000000^2 &:= 10000003025^2 \\99999996975^2 + 110000000^2 &:= 1000000003025^2\end{aligned}$$

56)

$$\begin{aligned}996864^2 + 112000^2 &:= 1003136^2 \\99996864^2 + 1120000^2 &:= 100003136^2 \\9999996864^2 + 11200000^2 &:= 10000003136^2 \\99999996864^2 + 112000000^2 &:= 1000000003136^2\end{aligned}$$

57)

$$\begin{aligned} 996751^2 + 114000^2 &:= 1003249^2 \\ 99996751^2 + 1140000^2 &:= 100003249^2 \\ 9999996751^2 + 11400000^2 &:= 10000003249^2 \\ 999999996751^2 + 114000000^2 &:= 1000000003249^2 \end{aligned}$$

58)

$$\begin{aligned} 996636^2 + 116000^2 &:= 1003364^2 \\ 99996636^2 + 1160000^2 &:= 100003364^2 \\ 9999996636^2 + 11600000^2 &:= 10000003364^2 \\ 999999996636^2 + 116000000^2 &:= 1000000003364^2 \end{aligned}$$

59)

$$\begin{aligned} 996519^2 + 118000^2 &:= 1003481^2 \\ 99996519^2 + 1180000^2 &:= 100003481^2 \\ 9999996519^2 + 11800000^2 &:= 10000003481^2 \\ 999999996519^2 + 118000000^2 &:= 1000000003481^2 \end{aligned}$$

60)

$$\begin{aligned} 996400^2 + 120000^2 &:= 1003600^2 \\ 99996400^2 + 1200000^2 &:= 100003600^2 \\ 9999996400^2 + 12000000^2 &:= 10000003600^2 \\ 999999996400^2 + 120000000^2 &:= 1000000003600^2 \end{aligned}$$

61)

$$\begin{aligned} 996279^2 + 122000^2 &:= 1003721^2 \\ 99996279^2 + 1220000^2 &:= 100003721^2 \\ 9999996279^2 + 12200000^2 &:= 10000003721^2 \\ 999999996279^2 + 122000000^2 &:= 1000000003721^2 \end{aligned}$$

62)

$$\begin{aligned} 996156^2 + 124000^2 &:= 1003844^2 \\ 99996156^2 + 1240000^2 &:= 100003844^2 \\ 9999996156^2 + 12400000^2 &:= 10000003844^2 \\ 999999996156^2 + 124000000^2 &:= 1000000003844^2 \end{aligned}$$

63)

$$\begin{aligned} 996031^2 + 126000^2 &:= 1003969^2 \\ 99996031^2 + 1260000^2 &:= 100003969^2 \\ 9999996031^2 + 12600000^2 &:= 10000003969^2 \\ 999999996031^2 + 126000000^2 &:= 1000000003969^2 \end{aligned}$$

64)

$$\begin{aligned} 995904^2 + 128000^2 &:= 1004096^2 \\ 99995904^2 + 1280000^2 &:= 100004096^2 \\ 9999995904^2 + 12800000^2 &:= 10000004096^2 \\ 999999995904^2 + 128000000^2 &:= 1000000004096^2 \end{aligned}$$

65)

$$\begin{aligned} 995775^2 + 130000^2 &:= 1004225^2 \\ 99995775^2 + 1300000^2 &:= 100004225^2 \\ 9999995775^2 + 13000000^2 &:= 10000004225^2 \\ 999999995775^2 + 130000000^2 &:= 1000000004225^2 \end{aligned}$$

66)

$$\begin{aligned} 995644^2 + 132000^2 &:= 1004356^2 \\ 99995644^2 + 1320000^2 &:= 100004356^2 \\ 9999995644^2 + 13200000^2 &:= 10000004356^2 \\ 999999995644^2 + 132000000^2 &:= 1000000004356^2 \end{aligned}$$

67)

$$\begin{aligned} 995511^2 + 134000^2 &:= 1004489^2 \\ 99995511^2 + 1340000^2 &:= 100004489^2 \\ 9999995511^2 + 13400000^2 &:= 10000004489^2 \\ 999999995511^2 + 134000000^2 &:= 1000000004489^2 \end{aligned}$$

68)

$$\begin{aligned} 995376^2 + 136000^2 &:= 1004624^2 \\ 99995376^2 + 1360000^2 &:= 100004624^2 \\ 9999995376^2 + 13600000^2 &:= 10000004624^2 \\ 999999995376^2 + 136000000^2 &:= 1000000004624^2 \end{aligned}$$

69)

$$\begin{aligned} 995239^2 + 138000^2 &:= 1004761^2 \\ 99995239^2 + 1380000^2 &:= 100004761^2 \\ 9999995239^2 + 13800000^2 &:= 10000004761^2 \\ 999999995239^2 + 138000000^2 &:= 1000000004761^2 \end{aligned}$$

70)

$$\begin{aligned}995100^2 + 140000^2 &:= 1004900^2 \\99995100^2 + 1400000^2 &:= 100004900^2 \\9999995100^2 + 14000000^2 &:= 10000004900^2 \\999999995100^2 + 140000000^2 &:= 1000000004900^2\end{aligned}$$

71)

$$\begin{aligned}994959^2 + 142000^2 &:= 1005041^2 \\99994959^2 + 1420000^2 &:= 100005041^2 \\9999994959^2 + 14200000^2 &:= 10000005041^2 \\999999994959^2 + 142000000^2 &:= 1000000005041^2\end{aligned}$$

72)

$$\begin{aligned}994816^2 + 144000^2 &:= 1005184^2 \\99994816^2 + 1440000^2 &:= 100005184^2 \\9999994816^2 + 14400000^2 &:= 10000005184^2 \\999999994816^2 + 144000000^2 &:= 1000000005184^2\end{aligned}$$

73)

$$\begin{aligned}994671^2 + 146000^2 &:= 1005329^2 \\99994671^2 + 1460000^2 &:= 100005329^2 \\9999994671^2 + 14600000^2 &:= 10000005329^2 \\999999994671^2 + 146000000^2 &:= 1000000005329^2\end{aligned}$$

74)

$$\begin{aligned}994524^2 + 148000^2 &:= 1005476^2 \\99994524^2 + 1480000^2 &:= 100005476^2 \\9999994524^2 + 14800000^2 &:= 10000005476^2 \\999999994524^2 + 148000000^2 &:= 1000000005476^2\end{aligned}$$

75)

$$\begin{aligned}994375^2 + 150000^2 &:= 1005625^2 \\99994375^2 + 1500000^2 &:= 100005625^2 \\9999994375^2 + 15000000^2 &:= 10000005625^2 \\999999994375^2 + 150000000^2 &:= 1000000005625^2\end{aligned}$$

76)

$$\begin{aligned}994224^2 + 152000^2 &:= 1005776^2 \\99994224^2 + 1520000^2 &:= 100005776^2 \\9999994224^2 + 15200000^2 &:= 10000005776^2 \\999999994224^2 + 152000000^2 &:= 1000000005776^2\end{aligned}$$

77)

$$\begin{aligned}994071^2 + 154000^2 &:= 1005929^2 \\99994071^2 + 1540000^2 &:= 100005929^2 \\9999994071^2 + 15400000^2 &:= 10000005929^2 \\999999994071^2 + 154000000^2 &:= 1000000005929^2\end{aligned}$$

78)

$$\begin{aligned}993916^2 + 156000^2 &:= 1006084^2 \\99993916^2 + 1560000^2 &:= 100006084^2 \\9999993916^2 + 15600000^2 &:= 10000006084^2 \\999999993916^2 + 156000000^2 &:= 1000000006084^2\end{aligned}$$

79)

$$\begin{aligned}993759^2 + 158000^2 &:= 1006241^2 \\99993759^2 + 1580000^2 &:= 100006241^2 \\9999993759^2 + 15800000^2 &:= 10000006241^2 \\999999993759^2 + 158000000^2 &:= 1000000006241^2\end{aligned}$$

80)

$$\begin{aligned}993600^2 + 160000^2 &:= 1006400^2 \\99993600^2 + 1600000^2 &:= 100006400^2 \\9999993600^2 + 16000000^2 &:= 10000006400^2 \\999999993600^2 + 160000000^2 &:= 1000000006400^2\end{aligned}$$

81)

$$\begin{aligned}993439^2 + 162000^2 &:= 1006561^2 \\99993439^2 + 1620000^2 &:= 100006561^2 \\9999993439^2 + 16200000^2 &:= 10000006561^2 \\999999993439^2 + 162000000^2 &:= 1000000006561^2\end{aligned}$$

82)

$$\begin{aligned}993276^2 + 164000^2 &:= 1006724^2 \\99993276^2 + 1640000^2 &:= 100006724^2 \\9999993276^2 + 16400000^2 &:= 10000006724^2 \\999999993276^2 + 164000000^2 &:= 1000000006724^2\end{aligned}$$

83)

$$\begin{aligned}993111^2 + 166000^2 &:= 1006889^2 \\99993111^2 + 1660000^2 &:= 100006889^2 \\9999993111^2 + 16600000^2 &:= 10000006889^2 \\999999993111^2 + 166000000^2 &:= 1000000006889^2\end{aligned}$$

84)

$$\begin{aligned}992944^2 + 168000^2 &:= 1007056^2 \\99992944^2 + 1680000^2 &:= 100007056^2 \\9999992944^2 + 16800000^2 &:= 10000007056^2 \\999999992944^2 + 168000000^2 &:= 1000000007056^2\end{aligned}$$

85)

$$\begin{aligned}992775^2 + 170000^2 &:= 1007225^2 \\99992775^2 + 1700000^2 &:= 100007225^2 \\9999992775^2 + 17000000^2 &:= 10000007225^2 \\999999992775^2 + 170000000^2 &:= 1000000007225^2\end{aligned}$$

86)

$$\begin{aligned}992604^2 + 172000^2 &:= 1007396^2 \\99992604^2 + 1720000^2 &:= 100007396^2 \\9999992604^2 + 17200000^2 &:= 10000007396^2 \\999999992604^2 + 172000000^2 &:= 1000000007396^2\end{aligned}$$

87)

$$\begin{aligned}992431^2 + 174000^2 &:= 1007569^2 \\99992431^2 + 1740000^2 &:= 100007569^2 \\9999992431^2 + 17400000^2 &:= 10000007569^2 \\999999992431^2 + 174000000^2 &:= 1000000007569^2\end{aligned}$$

88)

$$\begin{aligned}992256^2 + 176000^2 &:= 1007744^2 \\99992256^2 + 1760000^2 &:= 100007744^2 \\9999992256^2 + 17600000^2 &:= 10000007744^2 \\999999992256^2 + 176000000^2 &:= 1000000007744^2\end{aligned}$$

89)

$$\begin{aligned}992079^2 + 178000^2 &:= 1007921^2 \\99992079^2 + 1780000^2 &:= 100007921^2 \\9999992079^2 + 17800000^2 &:= 10000007921^2 \\999999992079^2 + 178000000^2 &:= 1000000007921^2\end{aligned}$$

90)

$$\begin{aligned}991900^2 + 180000^2 &:= 1008100^2 \\99991900^2 + 1800000^2 &:= 100008100^2 \\9999991900^2 + 18000000^2 &:= 10000008100^2 \\999999991900^2 + 180000000^2 &:= 1000000008100^2\end{aligned}$$

91)

$$\begin{aligned}991719^2 + 182000^2 &:= 1008281^2 \\99991719^2 + 1820000^2 &:= 100008281^2 \\9999991719^2 + 18200000^2 &:= 10000008281^2 \\999999991719^2 + 182000000^2 &:= 1000000008281^2\end{aligned}$$

92)

$$\begin{aligned}991536^2 + 184000^2 &:= 1008464^2 \\99991536^2 + 1840000^2 &:= 100008464^2 \\9999991536^2 + 18400000^2 &:= 10000008464^2 \\999999991536^2 + 184000000^2 &:= 1000000008464^2\end{aligned}$$

93)

$$\begin{aligned}991351^2 + 186000^2 &:= 1008649^2 \\99991351^2 + 1860000^2 &:= 100008649^2 \\9999991351^2 + 18600000^2 &:= 10000008649^2 \\999999991351^2 + 186000000^2 &:= 1000000008649^2\end{aligned}$$

94)

$$\begin{aligned}991164^2 + 188000^2 &:= 1008836^2 \\99991164^2 + 1880000^2 &:= 100008836^2 \\9999991164^2 + 18800000^2 &:= 10000008836^2 \\999999991164^2 + 188000000^2 &:= 1000000008836^2\end{aligned}$$

95)

$$\begin{aligned}990975^2 + 190000^2 &:= 1009025^2 \\99990975^2 + 1900000^2 &:= 100009025^2 \\9999990975^2 + 19000000^2 &:= 10000009025^2 \\999999990975^2 + 190000000^2 &:= 1000000009025^2\end{aligned}$$

96)

$$\begin{aligned} 990784^2 + 192000^2 &:= 1009216^2 \\ 99990784^2 + 1920000^2 &:= 100009216^2 \\ 9999990784^2 + 19200000^2 &:= 10000009216^2 \\ 999999990784^2 + 192000000^2 &:= 1000000009216^2 \end{aligned}$$

97)

$$\begin{aligned} 990591^2 + 194000^2 &:= 1009409^2 \\ 99990591^2 + 1940000^2 &:= 100009409^2 \\ 9999990591^2 + 19400000^2 &:= 10000009409^2 \\ 999999990591^2 + 194000000^2 &:= 1000000009409^2 \end{aligned}$$

98)

$$\begin{aligned} 990396^2 + 196000^2 &:= 1009604^2 \\ 99990396^2 + 1960000^2 &:= 100009604^2 \\ 9999990396^2 + 19600000^2 &:= 10000009604^2 \\ 999999990396^2 + 196000000^2 &:= 1000000009604^2 \end{aligned}$$

99)

$$\begin{aligned} 990199^2 + 198000^2 &:= 1009801^2 \\ 99990199^2 + 1980000^2 &:= 100009801^2 \\ 9999990199^2 + 19800000^2 &:= 10000009801^2 \\ 999999990199^2 + 198000000^2 &:= 1000000009801^2 \end{aligned}$$

100)

$$\begin{aligned} 990000^2 + 200000^2 &:= 1010000^2 \\ 99990000^2 + 2000000^2 &:= 100010000^2 \\ 9999990000^2 + 20000000^2 &:= 10000010000^2 \\ 999999990000^2 + 200000000^2 &:= 1000000010000^2 \end{aligned}$$

101)

$$\begin{aligned} 989799^2 + 202000^2 &:= 1010201^2 \\ 99989799^2 + 2020000^2 &:= 100010201^2 \\ 9999989799^2 + 20200000^2 &:= 10000010201^2 \\ 999999989799^2 + 202000000^2 &:= 1000000010201^2 \end{aligned}$$

102)

$$\begin{aligned} 989596^2 + 204000^2 &:= 1010404^2 \\ 99989596^2 + 2040000^2 &:= 100010404^2 \\ 9999989596^2 + 20400000^2 &:= 10000010404^2 \\ 999999989596^2 + 204000000^2 &:= 1000000010404^2 \end{aligned}$$

103)

$$\begin{aligned} 989391^2 + 206000^2 &:= 1010609^2 \\ 99989391^2 + 2060000^2 &:= 100010609^2 \\ 9999989391^2 + 20600000^2 &:= 10000010609^2 \\ 999999989391^2 + 206000000^2 &:= 1000000010609^2 \end{aligned}$$

104)

$$\begin{aligned} 989184^2 + 208000^2 &:= 1010816^2 \\ 99989184^2 + 2080000^2 &:= 100010816^2 \\ 9999989184^2 + 20800000^2 &:= 10000010816^2 \\ 999999989184^2 + 208000000^2 &:= 1000000010816^2 \end{aligned}$$

105)

$$\begin{aligned} 988975^2 + 210000^2 &:= 1011025^2 \\ 99988975^2 + 2100000^2 &:= 100011025^2 \\ 9999988975^2 + 21000000^2 &:= 10000011025^2 \\ 999999988975^2 + 210000000^2 &:= 1000000011025^2 \end{aligned}$$

106)

$$\begin{aligned} 988764^2 + 212000^2 &:= 1011236^2 \\ 99988764^2 + 2120000^2 &:= 100011236^2 \\ 9999988764^2 + 21200000^2 &:= 10000011236^2 \\ 999999988764^2 + 212000000^2 &:= 1000000011236^2 \end{aligned}$$

107)

$$\begin{aligned} 988551^2 + 214000^2 &:= 1011449^2 \\ 99988551^2 + 2140000^2 &:= 100011449^2 \\ 9999988551^2 + 21400000^2 &:= 10000011449^2 \\ 999999988551^2 + 214000000^2 &:= 1000000011449^2 \end{aligned}$$

108)

$$\begin{aligned} 988336^2 + 216000^2 &:= 1011664^2 \\ 99988336^2 + 2160000^2 &:= 100011664^2 \\ 9999988336^2 + 21600000^2 &:= 10000011664^2 \\ 999999988336^2 + 216000000^2 &:= 1000000011664^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 109) $988119^2 + 218000^2 := 1011881^2$
 $99988119^2 + 2180000^2 := 100011881^2$
 $999988119^2 + 21800000^2 := 10000011881^2$
 $9999988119^2 + 218000000^2 := 1000000011881^2$
- 110) $987900^2 + 220000^2 := 1012100^2$
 $99987900^2 + 2200000^2 := 100012100^2$
 $999987900^2 + 22000000^2 := 10000012100^2$
 $9999987900^2 + 220000000^2 := 1000000012100^2$
- 111) $987679^2 + 222000^2 := 1012321^2$
 $99987679^2 + 2220000^2 := 100012321^2$
 $999987679^2 + 22200000^2 := 10000012321^2$
 $9999987679^2 + 222000000^2 := 1000000012321^2$
- 112) $987456^2 + 224000^2 := 1012544^2$
 $99987456^2 + 2240000^2 := 100012544^2$
 $999987456^2 + 22400000^2 := 10000012544^2$
 $9999987456^2 + 224000000^2 := 1000000012544^2$
- 113) $987231^2 + 226000^2 := 1012769^2$
 $99987231^2 + 2260000^2 := 100012769^2$
 $999987231^2 + 22600000^2 := 10000012769^2$
 $9999987231^2 + 226000000^2 := 1000000012769^2$
- 114) $987004^2 + 228000^2 := 1012996^2$
 $99987004^2 + 2280000^2 := 100012996^2$
 $999987004^2 + 22800000^2 := 10000012996^2$
 $9999987004^2 + 228000000^2 := 1000000012996^2$
- 115) $986775^2 + 230000^2 := 1013225^2$
 $99986775^2 + 2300000^2 := 100013225^2$
 $999986775^2 + 23000000^2 := 10000013225^2$
 $9999986775^2 + 230000000^2 := 1000000013225^2$
- 116) $986544^2 + 232000^2 := 1013456^2$
 $99986544^2 + 2320000^2 := 100013456^2$
 $999986544^2 + 23200000^2 := 10000013456^2$
 $9999986544^2 + 232000000^2 := 1000000013456^2$
- 117) $986311^2 + 234000^2 := 1013689^2$
 $99986311^2 + 2340000^2 := 100013689^2$
 $999986311^2 + 23400000^2 := 10000013689^2$
 $9999986311^2 + 234000000^2 := 1000000013689^2$
- 118) $986076^2 + 236000^2 := 1013924^2$
 $99986076^2 + 2360000^2 := 100013924^2$
 $999986076^2 + 23600000^2 := 10000013924^2$
 $9999986076^2 + 236000000^2 := 1000000013924^2$
- 119) $985839^2 + 238000^2 := 1014161^2$
 $99985839^2 + 2380000^2 := 100014161^2$
 $999985839^2 + 23800000^2 := 10000014161^2$
 $9999985839^2 + 238000000^2 := 1000000014161^2$
- 120) $985600^2 + 240000^2 := 1014400^2$
 $99985600^2 + 2400000^2 := 100014400^2$
 $999985600^2 + 24000000^2 := 10000014400^2$
 $9999985600^2 + 240000000^2 := 1000000014400^2$
- 121) $985359^2 + 242000^2 := 1014641^2$
 $99985359^2 + 2420000^2 := 100014641^2$
 $999985359^2 + 24200000^2 := 10000014641^2$
 $9999985359^2 + 242000000^2 := 1000000014641^2$

- 122) $985116^2 + 244000^2 := 1014884^2$
 $99985116^2 + 2440000^2 := 100014884^2$
 $999985116^2 + 24400000^2 := 10000014884^2$
 $9999985116^2 + 244000000^2 := 1000000014884^2$
- 123) $984871^2 + 246000^2 := 1015129^2$
 $99984871^2 + 2460000^2 := 100015129^2$
 $999984871^2 + 24600000^2 := 10000015129^2$
 $9999984871^2 + 246000000^2 := 1000000015129^2$
- 124) $984624^2 + 248000^2 := 1015376^2$
 $99984624^2 + 2480000^2 := 100015376^2$
 $999984624^2 + 24800000^2 := 10000015376^2$
 $9999984624^2 + 248000000^2 := 1000000015376^2$
- 125) $984375^2 + 250000^2 := 1015625^2$
 $99984375^2 + 2500000^2 := 100015625^2$
 $999984375^2 + 25000000^2 := 10000015625^2$
 $9999984375^2 + 250000000^2 := 1000000015625^2$
- 126) $984124^2 + 252000^2 := 1015876^2$
 $99984124^2 + 2520000^2 := 100015876^2$
 $999984124^2 + 25200000^2 := 10000015876^2$
 $9999984124^2 + 252000000^2 := 1000000015876^2$
- 127) $983871^2 + 254000^2 := 1016129^2$
 $99983871^2 + 2540000^2 := 100016129^2$
 $999983871^2 + 25400000^2 := 10000016129^2$
 $9999983871^2 + 254000000^2 := 1000000016129^2$
- 128) $983616^2 + 256000^2 := 1016384^2$
 $99983616^2 + 2560000^2 := 100016384^2$
 $999983616^2 + 25600000^2 := 10000016384^2$
 $9999983616^2 + 256000000^2 := 1000000016384^2$
- 129) $983359^2 + 258000^2 := 1016641^2$
 $99983359^2 + 2580000^2 := 100016641^2$
 $999983359^2 + 25800000^2 := 10000016641^2$
 $9999983359^2 + 258000000^2 := 1000000016641^2$
- 130) $983100^2 + 260000^2 := 1016900^2$
 $99983100^2 + 2600000^2 := 100016900^2$
 $999983100^2 + 26000000^2 := 10000016900^2$
 $9999983100^2 + 260000000^2 := 1000000016900^2$
- 131) $982839^2 + 262000^2 := 1017161^2$
 $99982839^2 + 2620000^2 := 100017161^2$
 $999982839^2 + 26200000^2 := 10000017161^2$
 $9999982839^2 + 262000000^2 := 1000000017161^2$
- 132) $982576^2 + 264000^2 := 1017424^2$
 $99982576^2 + 2640000^2 := 100017424^2$
 $999982576^2 + 26400000^2 := 10000017424^2$
 $9999982576^2 + 264000000^2 := 1000000017424^2$
- 133) $982311^2 + 266000^2 := 1017689^2$
 $99982311^2 + 2660000^2 := 100017689^2$
 $999982311^2 + 26600000^2 := 10000017689^2$
 $9999982311^2 + 266000000^2 := 1000000017689^2$
- 134) $982044^2 + 268000^2 := 1017956^2$
 $99982044^2 + 2680000^2 := 100017956^2$
 $999982044^2 + 26800000^2 := 10000017956^2$
 $9999982044^2 + 268000000^2 := 1000000017956^2$

135)

$$\begin{aligned}981775^2 + 270000^2 &:= 1018225^2 \\99981775^2 + 2700000^2 &:= 100018225^2 \\9999981775^2 + 27000000^2 &:= 10000018225^2 \\999999981775^2 + 270000000^2 &:= 1000000018225^2\end{aligned}$$

136)

$$\begin{aligned}981504^2 + 272000^2 &:= 1018496^2 \\99981504^2 + 2720000^2 &:= 100018496^2 \\9999981504^2 + 27200000^2 &:= 10000018496^2 \\999999981504^2 + 272000000^2 &:= 1000000018496^2\end{aligned}$$

137)

$$\begin{aligned}981231^2 + 274000^2 &:= 1018769^2 \\99981231^2 + 2740000^2 &:= 100018769^2 \\9999981231^2 + 27400000^2 &:= 10000018769^2 \\999999981231^2 + 274000000^2 &:= 1000000018769^2\end{aligned}$$

138)

$$\begin{aligned}980956^2 + 276000^2 &:= 1019044^2 \\99980956^2 + 2760000^2 &:= 100019044^2 \\9999980956^2 + 27600000^2 &:= 10000019044^2 \\999999980956^2 + 276000000^2 &:= 1000000019044^2\end{aligned}$$

139)

$$\begin{aligned}980679^2 + 278000^2 &:= 1019321^2 \\99980679^2 + 2780000^2 &:= 100019321^2 \\9999980679^2 + 27800000^2 &:= 10000019321^2 \\999999980679^2 + 278000000^2 &:= 1000000019321^2\end{aligned}$$

140)

$$\begin{aligned}980400^2 + 280000^2 &:= 1019600^2 \\99980400^2 + 2800000^2 &:= 100019600^2 \\9999980400^2 + 28000000^2 &:= 10000019600^2 \\999999980400^2 + 280000000^2 &:= 1000000019600^2\end{aligned}$$

141)

$$\begin{aligned}980119^2 + 282000^2 &:= 1019881^2 \\99980119^2 + 2820000^2 &:= 100019881^2 \\9999980119^2 + 28200000^2 &:= 10000019881^2 \\999999980119^2 + 282000000^2 &:= 1000000019881^2\end{aligned}$$

142)

$$\begin{aligned}979836^2 + 284000^2 &:= 1020164^2 \\99979836^2 + 2840000^2 &:= 100020164^2 \\9999979836^2 + 28400000^2 &:= 10000020164^2 \\999999979836^2 + 284000000^2 &:= 1000000020164^2\end{aligned}$$

143)

$$\begin{aligned}979551^2 + 286000^2 &:= 1020449^2 \\99979551^2 + 2860000^2 &:= 100020449^2 \\9999979551^2 + 28600000^2 &:= 10000020449^2 \\999999979551^2 + 286000000^2 &:= 1000000020449^2\end{aligned}$$

144)

$$\begin{aligned}979264^2 + 288000^2 &:= 1020736^2 \\99979264^2 + 2880000^2 &:= 100020736^2 \\9999979264^2 + 28800000^2 &:= 10000020736^2 \\999999979264^2 + 288000000^2 &:= 1000000020736^2\end{aligned}$$

145)

$$\begin{aligned}978975^2 + 290000^2 &:= 1021025^2 \\99978975^2 + 2900000^2 &:= 100021025^2 \\9999978975^2 + 29000000^2 &:= 10000021025^2 \\999999978975^2 + 290000000^2 &:= 1000000021025^2\end{aligned}$$

146)

$$\begin{aligned}978684^2 + 292000^2 &:= 1021316^2 \\99978684^2 + 2920000^2 &:= 100021316^2 \\9999978684^2 + 29200000^2 &:= 10000021316^2 \\999999978684^2 + 292000000^2 &:= 1000000021316^2\end{aligned}$$

147)

$$\begin{aligned}978391^2 + 294000^2 &:= 1021609^2 \\99978391^2 + 2940000^2 &:= 100021609^2 \\9999978391^2 + 29400000^2 &:= 10000021609^2 \\999999978391^2 + 294000000^2 &:= 1000000021609^2\end{aligned}$$

148)

$$\begin{aligned}978096^2 + 296000^2 &:= 1021904^2 \\99978096^2 + 2960000^2 &:= 100021904^2 \\9999978096^2 + 29600000^2 &:= 10000021904^2 \\999999978096^2 + 296000000^2 &:= 1000000021904^2\end{aligned}$$

149)

$$\begin{aligned}977799^2 + 298000^2 &:= 1022201^2 \\99977799^2 + 2980000^2 &:= 100022201^2 \\9999977799^2 + 29800000^2 &:= 10000022201^2 \\999999977799^2 + 298000000^2 &:= 1000000022201^2\end{aligned}$$

150)

$$\begin{aligned}977500^2 + 300000^2 &:= 1022500^2 \\99977500^2 + 3000000^2 &:= 100022500^2 \\9999977500^2 + 30000000^2 &:= 10000022500^2 \\999999977500^2 + 300000000^2 &:= 1000000022500^2\end{aligned}$$

151)

$$\begin{aligned}977199^2 + 302000^2 &:= 1022801^2 \\99977199^2 + 3020000^2 &:= 100022801^2 \\9999977199^2 + 30200000^2 &:= 10000022801^2 \\999999977199^2 + 302000000^2 &:= 1000000022801^2\end{aligned}$$

152)

$$\begin{aligned}976896^2 + 304000^2 &:= 1023104^2 \\99976896^2 + 3040000^2 &:= 100023104^2 \\9999976896^2 + 30400000^2 &:= 10000023104^2 \\999999976896^2 + 304000000^2 &:= 1000000023104^2\end{aligned}$$

153)

$$\begin{aligned}976591^2 + 306000^2 &:= 1023409^2 \\99976591^2 + 3060000^2 &:= 100023409^2 \\9999976591^2 + 30600000^2 &:= 10000023409^2 \\999999976591^2 + 306000000^2 &:= 1000000023409^2\end{aligned}$$

154)

$$\begin{aligned}976284^2 + 308000^2 &:= 1023716^2 \\99976284^2 + 3080000^2 &:= 100023716^2 \\9999976284^2 + 30800000^2 &:= 10000023716^2 \\999999976284^2 + 308000000^2 &:= 1000000023716^2\end{aligned}$$

155)

$$\begin{aligned}975975^2 + 310000^2 &:= 1024025^2 \\99975975^2 + 3100000^2 &:= 100024025^2 \\9999975975^2 + 31000000^2 &:= 10000024025^2 \\999999975975^2 + 310000000^2 &:= 1000000024025^2\end{aligned}$$

156)

$$\begin{aligned}975664^2 + 312000^2 &:= 1024336^2 \\99975664^2 + 3120000^2 &:= 100024336^2 \\9999975664^2 + 31200000^2 &:= 10000024336^2 \\999999975664^2 + 312000000^2 &:= 1000000024336^2\end{aligned}$$

157)

$$\begin{aligned}975351^2 + 314000^2 &:= 1024649^2 \\99975351^2 + 3140000^2 &:= 100024649^2 \\9999975351^2 + 31400000^2 &:= 10000024649^2 \\999999975351^2 + 314000000^2 &:= 1000000024649^2\end{aligned}$$

158)

$$\begin{aligned}975036^2 + 316000^2 &:= 1024964^2 \\99975036^2 + 3160000^2 &:= 100024964^2 \\9999975036^2 + 31600000^2 &:= 10000024964^2 \\999999975036^2 + 316000000^2 &:= 1000000024964^2\end{aligned}$$

159)

$$\begin{aligned}974719^2 + 318000^2 &:= 1025281^2 \\99974719^2 + 3180000^2 &:= 100025281^2 \\9999974719^2 + 31800000^2 &:= 10000025281^2 \\999999974719^2 + 318000000^2 &:= 1000000025281^2\end{aligned}$$

160)

$$\begin{aligned}974400^2 + 320000^2 &:= 1025600^2 \\99974400^2 + 3200000^2 &:= 100025600^2 \\9999974400^2 + 32000000^2 &:= 10000025600^2 \\999999974400^2 + 320000000^2 &:= 1000000025600^2\end{aligned}$$

161)

$$\begin{aligned}974079^2 + 322000^2 &:= 1025921^2 \\99974079^2 + 3220000^2 &:= 100025921^2 \\9999974079^2 + 32200000^2 &:= 10000025921^2 \\999999974079^2 + 322000000^2 &:= 1000000025921^2\end{aligned}$$

162)

$$\begin{aligned}973756^2 + 324000^2 &:= 1026244^2 \\99973756^2 + 3240000^2 &:= 100026244^2 \\9999973756^2 + 32400000^2 &:= 10000026244^2 \\999999973756^2 + 324000000^2 &:= 1000000026244^2\end{aligned}$$

163)

$$\begin{aligned}973431^2 + 326000^2 &:= 1026569^2 \\99973431^2 + 3260000^2 &:= 100026569^2 \\9999973431^2 + 32600000^2 &:= 10000026569^2 \\999999973431^2 + 326000000^2 &:= 1000000026569^2\end{aligned}$$

164)

$$\begin{aligned}973104^2 + 328000^2 &:= 1026896^2 \\99973104^2 + 3280000^2 &:= 100026896^2 \\9999973104^2 + 32800000^2 &:= 10000026896^2 \\999999973104^2 + 328000000^2 &:= 1000000026896^2\end{aligned}$$

165)

$$\begin{aligned}972775^2 + 330000^2 &:= 1027225^2 \\99972775^2 + 3300000^2 &:= 100027225^2 \\9999972775^2 + 33000000^2 &:= 10000027225^2 \\999999972775^2 + 330000000^2 &:= 1000000027225^2\end{aligned}$$

166)

$$\begin{aligned}972444^2 + 332000^2 &:= 1027556^2 \\99972444^2 + 3320000^2 &:= 100027556^2 \\9999972444^2 + 33200000^2 &:= 10000027556^2 \\999999972444^2 + 332000000^2 &:= 1000000027556^2\end{aligned}$$

167)

$$\begin{aligned}972111^2 + 334000^2 &:= 1027889^2 \\99972111^2 + 3340000^2 &:= 100027889^2 \\9999972111^2 + 33400000^2 &:= 10000027889^2 \\999999972111^2 + 334000000^2 &:= 1000000027889^2\end{aligned}$$

168)

$$\begin{aligned}971776^2 + 336000^2 &:= 1028224^2 \\99971776^2 + 3360000^2 &:= 100028224^2 \\9999971776^2 + 33600000^2 &:= 10000028224^2 \\999999971776^2 + 336000000^2 &:= 1000000028224^2\end{aligned}$$

169)

$$\begin{aligned}971439^2 + 338000^2 &:= 1028561^2 \\99971439^2 + 3380000^2 &:= 100028561^2 \\9999971439^2 + 33800000^2 &:= 10000028561^2 \\999999971439^2 + 338000000^2 &:= 1000000028561^2\end{aligned}$$

170)

$$\begin{aligned}971100^2 + 340000^2 &:= 1028900^2 \\99971100^2 + 3400000^2 &:= 100028900^2 \\9999971100^2 + 34000000^2 &:= 10000028900^2 \\999999971100^2 + 340000000^2 &:= 1000000028900^2\end{aligned}$$

171)

$$\begin{aligned}970759^2 + 342000^2 &:= 1029241^2 \\99970759^2 + 3420000^2 &:= 100029241^2 \\9999970759^2 + 34200000^2 &:= 10000029241^2 \\999999970759^2 + 342000000^2 &:= 1000000029241^2\end{aligned}$$

172)

$$\begin{aligned}970416^2 + 344000^2 &:= 1029584^2 \\99970416^2 + 3440000^2 &:= 100029584^2 \\9999970416^2 + 34400000^2 &:= 10000029584^2 \\999999970416^2 + 344000000^2 &:= 1000000029584^2\end{aligned}$$

173)

$$\begin{aligned}970071^2 + 346000^2 &:= 1029929^2 \\99970071^2 + 3460000^2 &:= 100029929^2 \\9999970071^2 + 34600000^2 &:= 10000029929^2 \\999999970071^2 + 346000000^2 &:= 1000000029929^2\end{aligned}$$

- 174) $969724^2 + 348000^2 := 1030276^2$
 $99969724^2 + 3480000^2 := 100030276^2$
 $9999969724^2 + 34800000^2 := 10000030276^2$
 $999999969724^2 + 348000000^2 := 1000000030276^2$
- 175) $969375^2 + 350000^2 := 1030625^2$
 $99969375^2 + 3500000^2 := 100030625^2$
 $9999969375^2 + 35000000^2 := 10000030625^2$
 $999999969375^2 + 350000000^2 := 1000000030625^2$
- 176) $969024^2 + 352000^2 := 1030976^2$
 $99969024^2 + 3520000^2 := 100030976^2$
 $9999969024^2 + 35200000^2 := 10000030976^2$
 $999999969024^2 + 352000000^2 := 1000000030976^2$
- 177) $968671^2 + 354000^2 := 1031329^2$
 $99968671^2 + 3540000^2 := 100031329^2$
 $9999968671^2 + 35400000^2 := 10000031329^2$
 $999999968671^2 + 354000000^2 := 1000000031329^2$
- 178) $968316^2 + 356000^2 := 1031684^2$
 $99968316^2 + 3560000^2 := 100031684^2$
 $9999968316^2 + 35600000^2 := 10000031684^2$
 $999999968316^2 + 356000000^2 := 1000000031684^2$
- 179) $967959^2 + 358000^2 := 1032041^2$
 $99967959^2 + 3580000^2 := 100032041^2$
 $9999967959^2 + 35800000^2 := 10000032041^2$
 $999999967959^2 + 358000000^2 := 1000000032041^2$
- 180) $967600^2 + 360000^2 := 1032400^2$
 $99967600^2 + 3600000^2 := 100032400^2$
 $9999967600^2 + 36000000^2 := 10000032400^2$
 $999999967600^2 + 360000000^2 := 1000000032400^2$
- 181) $967239^2 + 362000^2 := 1032761^2$
 $99967239^2 + 3620000^2 := 100032761^2$
 $9999967239^2 + 36200000^2 := 10000032761^2$
 $999999967239^2 + 362000000^2 := 1000000032761^2$
- 182) $966876^2 + 364000^2 := 1033124^2$
 $99966876^2 + 3640000^2 := 100033124^2$
 $9999966876^2 + 36400000^2 := 10000033124^2$
 $999999966876^2 + 364000000^2 := 1000000033124^2$
- 183) $966511^2 + 366000^2 := 1033489^2$
 $99966511^2 + 3660000^2 := 100033489^2$
 $9999966511^2 + 36600000^2 := 10000033489^2$
 $999999966511^2 + 366000000^2 := 1000000033489^2$
- 184) $966144^2 + 368000^2 := 1033856^2$
 $99966144^2 + 3680000^2 := 100033856^2$
 $9999966144^2 + 36800000^2 := 10000033856^2$
 $999999966144^2 + 368000000^2 := 1000000033856^2$
- 185) $965775^2 + 370000^2 := 1034225^2$
 $99965775^2 + 3700000^2 := 100034225^2$
 $9999965775^2 + 37000000^2 := 10000034225^2$
 $999999965775^2 + 370000000^2 := 1000000034225^2$
- 186) $965404^2 + 372000^2 := 1034596^2$
 $99965404^2 + 3720000^2 := 100034596^2$
 $9999965404^2 + 37200000^2 := 10000034596^2$
 $999999965404^2 + 372000000^2 := 1000000034596^2$

- 187) $965031^2 + 374000^2 := 1034969^2$
 $99965031^2 + 3740000^2 := 100034969^2$
 $9999965031^2 + 37400000^2 := 10000034969^2$
 $999999965031^2 + 374000000^2 := 1000000034969^2$
- 188) $964656^2 + 376000^2 := 1035344^2$
 $99964656^2 + 3760000^2 := 100035344^2$
 $9999964656^2 + 37600000^2 := 10000035344^2$
 $999999964656^2 + 376000000^2 := 1000000035344^2$
- 189) $964279^2 + 378000^2 := 1035721^2$
 $99964279^2 + 3780000^2 := 100035721^2$
 $9999964279^2 + 37800000^2 := 10000035721^2$
 $999999964279^2 + 378000000^2 := 1000000035721^2$
- 190) $963900^2 + 380000^2 := 1036100^2$
 $99963900^2 + 3800000^2 := 100036100^2$
 $9999963900^2 + 38000000^2 := 10000036100^2$
 $999999963900^2 + 380000000^2 := 1000000036100^2$
- 191) $963519^2 + 382000^2 := 1036481^2$
 $99963519^2 + 3820000^2 := 100036481^2$
 $9999963519^2 + 38200000^2 := 10000036481^2$
 $999999963519^2 + 382000000^2 := 1000000036481^2$
- 192) $963136^2 + 384000^2 := 1036864^2$
 $99963136^2 + 3840000^2 := 100036864^2$
 $9999963136^2 + 38400000^2 := 10000036864^2$
 $999999963136^2 + 384000000^2 := 1000000036864^2$
- 193) $962751^2 + 386000^2 := 1037249^2$
 $99962751^2 + 3860000^2 := 100037249^2$
 $9999962751^2 + 38600000^2 := 10000037249^2$
 $999999962751^2 + 386000000^2 := 1000000037249^2$
- 194) $962364^2 + 388000^2 := 1037636^2$
 $99962364^2 + 3880000^2 := 100037636^2$
 $9999962364^2 + 38800000^2 := 10000037636^2$
 $999999962364^2 + 388000000^2 := 1000000037636^2$
- 195) $961975^2 + 390000^2 := 1038025^2$
 $99961975^2 + 3900000^2 := 100038025^2$
 $9999961975^2 + 39000000^2 := 10000038025^2$
 $999999961975^2 + 390000000^2 := 1000000038025^2$
- 196) $961584^2 + 392000^2 := 1038416^2$
 $99961584^2 + 3920000^2 := 100038416^2$
 $9999961584^2 + 39200000^2 := 10000038416^2$
 $999999961584^2 + 392000000^2 := 1000000038416^2$
- 197) $961191^2 + 394000^2 := 1038809^2$
 $99961191^2 + 3940000^2 := 100038809^2$
 $9999961191^2 + 39400000^2 := 10000038809^2$
 $999999961191^2 + 394000000^2 := 1000000038809^2$
- 198) $960796^2 + 396000^2 := 1039204^2$
 $99960796^2 + 3960000^2 := 100039204^2$
 $9999960796^2 + 39600000^2 := 10000039204^2$
 $999999960796^2 + 396000000^2 := 1000000039204^2$
- 199) $960399^2 + 398000^2 := 1039601^2$
 $99960399^2 + 3980000^2 := 100039601^2$
 $9999960399^2 + 39800000^2 := 10000039601^2$
 $999999960399^2 + 398000000^2 := 1000000039601^2$

200)

$$\begin{aligned}960000^2 + 400000^2 &:= 1040000^2 \\99960000^2 + 4000000^2 &:= 100040000^2 \\9999960000^2 + 40000000^2 &:= 10000040000^2 \\999999960000^2 + 400000000^2 &:= 1000000040000^2\end{aligned}$$

201)

$$\begin{aligned}959599^2 + 402000^2 &:= 1040401^2 \\99959599^2 + 4020000^2 &:= 100040401^2 \\9999959599^2 + 40200000^2 &:= 10000040401^2 \\999999959599^2 + 402000000^2 &:= 1000000040401^2\end{aligned}$$

202)

$$\begin{aligned}959196^2 + 404000^2 &:= 1040804^2 \\99959196^2 + 4040000^2 &:= 100040804^2 \\9999959196^2 + 40400000^2 &:= 10000040804^2 \\999999959196^2 + 404000000^2 &:= 1000000040804^2\end{aligned}$$

203)

$$\begin{aligned}958791^2 + 406000^2 &:= 1041209^2 \\99958791^2 + 4060000^2 &:= 100041209^2 \\9999958791^2 + 40600000^2 &:= 10000041209^2 \\999999958791^2 + 406000000^2 &:= 1000000041209^2\end{aligned}$$

204)

$$\begin{aligned}958384^2 + 408000^2 &:= 1041616^2 \\99958384^2 + 4080000^2 &:= 100041616^2 \\9999958384^2 + 40800000^2 &:= 10000041616^2 \\999999958384^2 + 408000000^2 &:= 1000000041616^2\end{aligned}$$

205)

$$\begin{aligned}957975^2 + 410000^2 &:= 1042025^2 \\99957975^2 + 4100000^2 &:= 100042025^2 \\9999957975^2 + 41000000^2 &:= 10000042025^2 \\999999957975^2 + 410000000^2 &:= 1000000042025^2\end{aligned}$$

206)

$$\begin{aligned}957564^2 + 412000^2 &:= 1042436^2 \\99957564^2 + 4120000^2 &:= 100042436^2 \\9999957564^2 + 41200000^2 &:= 10000042436^2 \\999999957564^2 + 412000000^2 &:= 1000000042436^2\end{aligned}$$

207)

$$\begin{aligned}957151^2 + 414000^2 &:= 1042849^2 \\99957151^2 + 4140000^2 &:= 100042849^2 \\9999957151^2 + 41400000^2 &:= 10000042849^2 \\999999957151^2 + 414000000^2 &:= 1000000042849^2\end{aligned}$$

208)

$$\begin{aligned}956736^2 + 416000^2 &:= 1043264^2 \\99956736^2 + 4160000^2 &:= 100043264^2 \\9999956736^2 + 41600000^2 &:= 10000043264^2 \\999999956736^2 + 416000000^2 &:= 1000000043264^2\end{aligned}$$

209)

$$\begin{aligned}956319^2 + 418000^2 &:= 1043681^2 \\99956319^2 + 4180000^2 &:= 100043681^2 \\9999956319^2 + 41800000^2 &:= 10000043681^2 \\999999956319^2 + 418000000^2 &:= 1000000043681^2\end{aligned}$$

210)

$$\begin{aligned}955900^2 + 420000^2 &:= 1044100^2 \\99955900^2 + 4200000^2 &:= 100044100^2 \\9999955900^2 + 42000000^2 &:= 10000044100^2 \\999999955900^2 + 420000000^2 &:= 1000000044100^2\end{aligned}$$

211)

$$\begin{aligned}955479^2 + 422000^2 &:= 1044521^2 \\99955479^2 + 4220000^2 &:= 100044521^2 \\9999955479^2 + 42200000^2 &:= 10000044521^2 \\999999955479^2 + 422000000^2 &:= 1000000044521^2\end{aligned}$$

212)

$$\begin{aligned}955056^2 + 424000^2 &:= 1044944^2 \\99955056^2 + 4240000^2 &:= 100044944^2 \\9999955056^2 + 42400000^2 &:= 10000044944^2 \\999999955056^2 + 424000000^2 &:= 1000000044944^2\end{aligned}$$

213)

$$\begin{aligned} 954631^2 + 426000^2 &:= 1045369^2 \\ 99954631^2 + 4260000^2 &:= 100045369^2 \\ 9999954631^2 + 42600000^2 &:= 10000045369^2 \\ 999999954631^2 + 426000000^2 &:= 1000000045369^2 \end{aligned}$$

214)

$$\begin{aligned} 954204^2 + 428000^2 &:= 1045796^2 \\ 99954204^2 + 4280000^2 &:= 100045796^2 \\ 9999954204^2 + 42800000^2 &:= 10000045796^2 \\ 999999954204^2 + 428000000^2 &:= 1000000045796^2 \end{aligned}$$

215)

$$\begin{aligned} 953775^2 + 430000^2 &:= 1046225^2 \\ 99953775^2 + 4300000^2 &:= 100046225^2 \\ 9999953775^2 + 43000000^2 &:= 10000046225^2 \\ 999999953775^2 + 430000000^2 &:= 1000000046225^2 \end{aligned}$$

216)

$$\begin{aligned} 953344^2 + 432000^2 &:= 1046656^2 \\ 99953344^2 + 4320000^2 &:= 100046656^2 \\ 9999953344^2 + 43200000^2 &:= 10000046656^2 \\ 999999953344^2 + 432000000^2 &:= 1000000046656^2 \end{aligned}$$

217)

$$\begin{aligned} 952911^2 + 434000^2 &:= 1047089^2 \\ 99952911^2 + 4340000^2 &:= 100047089^2 \\ 9999952911^2 + 43400000^2 &:= 10000047089^2 \\ 999999952911^2 + 434000000^2 &:= 1000000047089^2 \end{aligned}$$

218)

$$\begin{aligned} 952476^2 + 436000^2 &:= 1047524^2 \\ 99952476^2 + 4360000^2 &:= 100047524^2 \\ 9999952476^2 + 43600000^2 &:= 10000047524^2 \\ 999999952476^2 + 436000000^2 &:= 1000000047524^2 \end{aligned}$$

219)

$$\begin{aligned} 952039^2 + 438000^2 &:= 1047961^2 \\ 99952039^2 + 4380000^2 &:= 100047961^2 \\ 9999952039^2 + 43800000^2 &:= 10000047961^2 \\ 999999952039^2 + 438000000^2 &:= 1000000047961^2 \end{aligned}$$

220)

$$\begin{aligned} 951600^2 + 440000^2 &:= 1048400^2 \\ 99951600^2 + 4400000^2 &:= 100048400^2 \\ 9999951600^2 + 44000000^2 &:= 10000048400^2 \\ 999999951600^2 + 440000000^2 &:= 1000000048400^2 \end{aligned}$$

221)

$$\begin{aligned} 951159^2 + 442000^2 &:= 1048841^2 \\ 99951159^2 + 4420000^2 &:= 100048841^2 \\ 9999951159^2 + 44200000^2 &:= 10000048841^2 \\ 999999951159^2 + 442000000^2 &:= 1000000048841^2 \end{aligned}$$

222)

$$\begin{aligned} 950716^2 + 444000^2 &:= 1049284^2 \\ 99950716^2 + 4440000^2 &:= 100049284^2 \\ 9999950716^2 + 44400000^2 &:= 10000049284^2 \\ 999999950716^2 + 444000000^2 &:= 1000000049284^2 \end{aligned}$$

223)

$$\begin{aligned} 950271^2 + 446000^2 &:= 1049729^2 \\ 99950271^2 + 4460000^2 &:= 100049729^2 \\ 9999950271^2 + 44600000^2 &:= 10000049729^2 \\ 999999950271^2 + 446000000^2 &:= 1000000049729^2 \end{aligned}$$

224)

$$\begin{aligned} 949824^2 + 448000^2 &:= 1050176^2 \\ 99949824^2 + 4480000^2 &:= 100050176^2 \\ 9999949824^2 + 44800000^2 &:= 10000050176^2 \\ 999999949824^2 + 448000000^2 &:= 1000000050176^2 \end{aligned}$$

225)

$$\begin{aligned} 949375^2 + 450000^2 &:= 1050625^2 \\ 99949375^2 + 4500000^2 &:= 100050625^2 \\ 9999949375^2 + 45000000^2 &:= 10000050625^2 \\ 999999949375^2 + 450000000^2 &:= 1000000050625^2 \end{aligned}$$

226)

$$\begin{aligned}948924^2 + 452000^2 &:= 1051076^2 \\99948924^2 + 4520000^2 &:= 100051076^2 \\9999948924^2 + 45200000^2 &:= 10000051076^2 \\999999948924^2 + 452000000^2 &:= 1000000051076^2\end{aligned}$$

227)

$$\begin{aligned}948471^2 + 454000^2 &:= 1051529^2 \\99948471^2 + 4540000^2 &:= 100051529^2 \\9999948471^2 + 45400000^2 &:= 10000051529^2 \\999999948471^2 + 454000000^2 &:= 1000000051529^2\end{aligned}$$

228)

$$\begin{aligned}948016^2 + 456000^2 &:= 1051984^2 \\99948016^2 + 4560000^2 &:= 100051984^2 \\9999948016^2 + 45600000^2 &:= 10000051984^2 \\999999948016^2 + 456000000^2 &:= 1000000051984^2\end{aligned}$$

229)

$$\begin{aligned}947559^2 + 458000^2 &:= 1052441^2 \\99947559^2 + 4580000^2 &:= 100052441^2 \\9999947559^2 + 45800000^2 &:= 10000052441^2 \\999999947559^2 + 458000000^2 &:= 1000000052441^2\end{aligned}$$

230)

$$\begin{aligned}947100^2 + 460000^2 &:= 1052900^2 \\99947100^2 + 4600000^2 &:= 100052900^2 \\9999947100^2 + 46000000^2 &:= 10000052900^2 \\999999947100^2 + 460000000^2 &:= 1000000052900^2\end{aligned}$$

231)

$$\begin{aligned}946639^2 + 462000^2 &:= 1053361^2 \\99946639^2 + 4620000^2 &:= 100053361^2 \\9999946639^2 + 46200000^2 &:= 10000053361^2 \\999999946639^2 + 462000000^2 &:= 1000000053361^2\end{aligned}$$

232)

$$\begin{aligned}946176^2 + 464000^2 &:= 1053824^2 \\99946176^2 + 4640000^2 &:= 100053824^2 \\9999946176^2 + 46400000^2 &:= 10000053824^2 \\999999946176^2 + 464000000^2 &:= 1000000053824^2\end{aligned}$$

233)

$$\begin{aligned}945711^2 + 466000^2 &:= 1054289^2 \\99945711^2 + 4660000^2 &:= 100054289^2 \\9999945711^2 + 46600000^2 &:= 10000054289^2 \\999999945711^2 + 466000000^2 &:= 1000000054289^2\end{aligned}$$

234)

$$\begin{aligned}945244^2 + 468000^2 &:= 1054756^2 \\99945244^2 + 4680000^2 &:= 100054756^2 \\9999945244^2 + 46800000^2 &:= 10000054756^2 \\999999945244^2 + 468000000^2 &:= 1000000054756^2\end{aligned}$$

235)

$$\begin{aligned}944775^2 + 470000^2 &:= 1055225^2 \\99944775^2 + 4700000^2 &:= 100055225^2 \\9999944775^2 + 47000000^2 &:= 10000055225^2 \\999999944775^2 + 470000000^2 &:= 1000000055225^2\end{aligned}$$

236)

$$\begin{aligned}944304^2 + 472000^2 &:= 1055696^2 \\99944304^2 + 4720000^2 &:= 100055696^2 \\9999944304^2 + 47200000^2 &:= 10000055696^2 \\999999944304^2 + 472000000^2 &:= 1000000055696^2\end{aligned}$$

237)

$$\begin{aligned}943831^2 + 474000^2 &:= 1056169^2 \\99943831^2 + 4740000^2 &:= 100056169^2 \\9999943831^2 + 47400000^2 &:= 10000056169^2 \\999999943831^2 + 474000000^2 &:= 1000000056169^2\end{aligned}$$

238)

$$\begin{aligned}943356^2 + 476000^2 &:= 1056644^2 \\99943356^2 + 4760000^2 &:= 100056644^2 \\9999943356^2 + 47600000^2 &:= 10000056644^2 \\999999943356^2 + 476000000^2 &:= 1000000056644^2\end{aligned}$$

- 239) $942879^2 + 478000^2 := 1057121^2$
 $99942879^2 + 4780000^2 := 100057121^2$
 $9999942879^2 + 47800000^2 := 10000057121^2$
 $999999942879^2 + 478000000^2 := 1000000057121^2$
- 240) $942400^2 + 480000^2 := 1057600^2$
 $99942400^2 + 4800000^2 := 100057600^2$
 $9999942400^2 + 48000000^2 := 10000057600^2$
 $999999942400^2 + 480000000^2 := 1000000057600^2$
- 241) $941919^2 + 482000^2 := 1058081^2$
 $99941919^2 + 4820000^2 := 100058081^2$
 $9999941919^2 + 48200000^2 := 10000058081^2$
 $999999941919^2 + 482000000^2 := 1000000058081^2$
- 242) $941436^2 + 484000^2 := 1058564^2$
 $99941436^2 + 4840000^2 := 100058564^2$
 $9999941436^2 + 48400000^2 := 10000058564^2$
 $999999941436^2 + 484000000^2 := 1000000058564^2$
- 243) $940951^2 + 486000^2 := 1059049^2$
 $99940951^2 + 4860000^2 := 100059049^2$
 $9999940951^2 + 48600000^2 := 10000059049^2$
 $999999940951^2 + 486000000^2 := 1000000059049^2$
- 244) $940464^2 + 488000^2 := 1059536^2$
 $99940464^2 + 4880000^2 := 100059536^2$
 $9999940464^2 + 48800000^2 := 10000059536^2$
 $999999940464^2 + 488000000^2 := 1000000059536^2$
- 245) $939975^2 + 490000^2 := 1060025^2$
 $99939975^2 + 4900000^2 := 100060025^2$
 $9999939975^2 + 49000000^2 := 10000060025^2$
 $999999939975^2 + 490000000^2 := 1000000060025^2$
- 246) $939484^2 + 492000^2 := 1060516^2$
 $99939484^2 + 4920000^2 := 100060516^2$
 $9999939484^2 + 49200000^2 := 10000060516^2$
 $999999939484^2 + 492000000^2 := 1000000060516^2$
- 247) $938991^2 + 494000^2 := 1061009^2$
 $99938991^2 + 4940000^2 := 100061009^2$
 $9999938991^2 + 49400000^2 := 10000061009^2$
 $999999938991^2 + 494000000^2 := 1000000061009^2$
- 248) $938496^2 + 496000^2 := 1061504^2$
 $99938496^2 + 4960000^2 := 100061504^2$
 $9999938496^2 + 49600000^2 := 10000061504^2$
 $999999938496^2 + 496000000^2 := 1000000061504^2$
- 249) $937999^2 + 498000^2 := 1062001^2$
 $99937999^2 + 4980000^2 := 100062001^2$
 $9999937999^2 + 49800000^2 := 10000062001^2$
 $999999937999^2 + 498000000^2 := 1000000062001^2$
- 250) $937500^2 + 500000^2 := 1062500^2$
 $99937500^2 + 5000000^2 := 100062500^2$
 $9999937500^2 + 50000000^2 := 10000062500^2$
 $999999937500^2 + 500000000^2 := 1000000062500^2$
- 251) $936999^2 + 502000^2 := 1063001^2$
 $99936999^2 + 5020000^2 := 100063001^2$
 $9999936999^2 + 50200000^2 := 10000063001^2$
 $999999936999^2 + 502000000^2 := 1000000063001^2$

- 252) $936496^2 + 504000^2 := 1063504^2$
 $99936496^2 + 5040000^2 := 100063504^2$
 $9999936496^2 + 50400000^2 := 10000063504^2$
 $999999936496^2 + 504000000^2 := 1000000063504^2$
- 253) $935991^2 + 506000^2 := 1064009^2$
 $99935991^2 + 5060000^2 := 100064009^2$
 $9999935991^2 + 50600000^2 := 10000064009^2$
 $999999935991^2 + 506000000^2 := 1000000064009^2$
- 254) $935484^2 + 508000^2 := 1064516^2$
 $99935484^2 + 5080000^2 := 100064516^2$
 $9999935484^2 + 50800000^2 := 10000064516^2$
 $999999935484^2 + 508000000^2 := 1000000064516^2$
- 255) $934975^2 + 510000^2 := 1065025^2$
 $99934975^2 + 5100000^2 := 100065025^2$
 $9999934975^2 + 51000000^2 := 10000065025^2$
 $999999934975^2 + 510000000^2 := 1000000065025^2$
- 256) $934464^2 + 512000^2 := 1065536^2$
 $99934464^2 + 5120000^2 := 100065536^2$
 $9999934464^2 + 51200000^2 := 10000065536^2$
 $999999934464^2 + 512000000^2 := 1000000065536^2$
- 257) $933951^2 + 514000^2 := 1066049^2$
 $99933951^2 + 5140000^2 := 100066049^2$
 $9999933951^2 + 51400000^2 := 10000066049^2$
 $999999933951^2 + 514000000^2 := 1000000066049^2$
- 258) $933436^2 + 516000^2 := 1066564^2$
 $99933436^2 + 5160000^2 := 100066564^2$
 $9999933436^2 + 51600000^2 := 10000066564^2$
 $999999933436^2 + 516000000^2 := 1000000066564^2$
- 259) $932919^2 + 518000^2 := 1067081^2$
 $99932919^2 + 5180000^2 := 100067081^2$
 $9999932919^2 + 51800000^2 := 10000067081^2$
 $999999932919^2 + 518000000^2 := 1000000067081^2$
- 260) $932400^2 + 520000^2 := 1067600^2$
 $99932400^2 + 5200000^2 := 100067600^2$
 $9999932400^2 + 52000000^2 := 10000067600^2$
 $999999932400^2 + 520000000^2 := 1000000067600^2$
- 261) $931879^2 + 522000^2 := 1068121^2$
 $99931879^2 + 5220000^2 := 100068121^2$
 $9999931879^2 + 52200000^2 := 10000068121^2$
 $999999931879^2 + 522000000^2 := 1000000068121^2$
- 262) $931356^2 + 524000^2 := 1068644^2$
 $99931356^2 + 5240000^2 := 100068644^2$
 $9999931356^2 + 52400000^2 := 10000068644^2$
 $999999931356^2 + 524000000^2 := 1000000068644^2$
- 263) $930831^2 + 526000^2 := 1069169^2$
 $99930831^2 + 5260000^2 := 100069169^2$
 $9999930831^2 + 52600000^2 := 10000069169^2$
 $999999930831^2 + 526000000^2 := 1000000069169^2$
- 264) $930304^2 + 528000^2 := 1069696^2$
 $99930304^2 + 5280000^2 := 100069696^2$
 $9999930304^2 + 52800000^2 := 10000069696^2$
 $999999930304^2 + 528000000^2 := 1000000069696^2$

265)

$$\begin{aligned} 929775^2 + 530000^2 &:= 1070225^2 \\ 99929775^2 + 5300000^2 &:= 100070225^2 \\ 9999929775^2 + 53000000^2 &:= 10000070225^2 \\ 999999929775^2 + 530000000^2 &:= 1000000070225^2 \end{aligned}$$

266)

$$\begin{aligned} 929244^2 + 532000^2 &:= 1070756^2 \\ 99929244^2 + 5320000^2 &:= 100070756^2 \\ 9999929244^2 + 53200000^2 &:= 10000070756^2 \\ 999999929244^2 + 532000000^2 &:= 1000000070756^2 \end{aligned}$$

267)

$$\begin{aligned} 928711^2 + 534000^2 &:= 1071289^2 \\ 99928711^2 + 5340000^2 &:= 100071289^2 \\ 9999928711^2 + 53400000^2 &:= 10000071289^2 \\ 999999928711^2 + 534000000^2 &:= 1000000071289^2 \end{aligned}$$

268)

$$\begin{aligned} 928176^2 + 536000^2 &:= 1071824^2 \\ 99928176^2 + 5360000^2 &:= 100071824^2 \\ 9999928176^2 + 53600000^2 &:= 10000071824^2 \\ 999999928176^2 + 536000000^2 &:= 1000000071824^2 \end{aligned}$$

269)

$$\begin{aligned} 927639^2 + 538000^2 &:= 1072361^2 \\ 99927639^2 + 5380000^2 &:= 100072361^2 \\ 9999927639^2 + 53800000^2 &:= 10000072361^2 \\ 999999927639^2 + 538000000^2 &:= 1000000072361^2 \end{aligned}$$

270)

$$\begin{aligned} 927100^2 + 540000^2 &:= 1072900^2 \\ 99927100^2 + 5400000^2 &:= 100072900^2 \\ 9999927100^2 + 54000000^2 &:= 10000072900^2 \\ 999999927100^2 + 540000000^2 &:= 1000000072900^2 \end{aligned}$$

271)

$$\begin{aligned} 926559^2 + 542000^2 &:= 1073441^2 \\ 99926559^2 + 5420000^2 &:= 100073441^2 \\ 9999926559^2 + 54200000^2 &:= 10000073441^2 \\ 999999926559^2 + 542000000^2 &:= 1000000073441^2 \end{aligned}$$

272)

$$\begin{aligned} 926016^2 + 544000^2 &:= 1073984^2 \\ 99926016^2 + 5440000^2 &:= 100073984^2 \\ 9999926016^2 + 54400000^2 &:= 10000073984^2 \\ 999999926016^2 + 544000000^2 &:= 1000000073984^2 \end{aligned}$$

273)

$$\begin{aligned} 925471^2 + 546000^2 &:= 1074529^2 \\ 99925471^2 + 5460000^2 &:= 100074529^2 \\ 9999925471^2 + 54600000^2 &:= 10000074529^2 \\ 999999925471^2 + 546000000^2 &:= 1000000074529^2 \end{aligned}$$

274)

$$\begin{aligned} 924924^2 + 548000^2 &:= 1075076^2 \\ 99924924^2 + 5480000^2 &:= 100075076^2 \\ 9999924924^2 + 54800000^2 &:= 10000075076^2 \\ 999999924924^2 + 548000000^2 &:= 1000000075076^2 \end{aligned}$$

275)

$$\begin{aligned} 924375^2 + 550000^2 &:= 1075625^2 \\ 99924375^2 + 5500000^2 &:= 100075625^2 \\ 9999924375^2 + 55000000^2 &:= 10000075625^2 \\ 999999924375^2 + 550000000^2 &:= 1000000075625^2 \end{aligned}$$

276)

$$\begin{aligned} 923824^2 + 552000^2 &:= 1076176^2 \\ 99923824^2 + 5520000^2 &:= 100076176^2 \\ 9999923824^2 + 55200000^2 &:= 10000076176^2 \\ 999999923824^2 + 552000000^2 &:= 1000000076176^2 \end{aligned}$$

277)

$$\begin{aligned} 923271^2 + 554000^2 &:= 1076729^2 \\ 99923271^2 + 5540000^2 &:= 100076729^2 \\ 9999923271^2 + 55400000^2 &:= 10000076729^2 \\ 999999923271^2 + 554000000^2 &:= 1000000076729^2 \end{aligned}$$

278)

$$\begin{aligned} 922716^2 + 556000^2 &:= 1077284^2 \\ 99922716^2 + 5560000^2 &:= 100077284^2 \\ 9999922716^2 + 55600000^2 &:= 10000077284^2 \\ 999999922716^2 + 556000000^2 &:= 1000000077284^2 \end{aligned}$$

279)

$$\begin{aligned} 922159^2 + 558000^2 &:= 1077841^2 \\ 99922159^2 + 5580000^2 &:= 100077841^2 \\ 9999922159^2 + 55800000^2 &:= 10000077841^2 \\ 999999922159^2 + 558000000^2 &:= 1000000077841^2 \end{aligned}$$

280)

$$\begin{aligned} 921600^2 + 560000^2 &:= 1078400^2 \\ 99921600^2 + 5600000^2 &:= 100078400^2 \\ 9999921600^2 + 56000000^2 &:= 10000078400^2 \\ 999999921600^2 + 560000000^2 &:= 1000000078400^2 \end{aligned}$$

281)

$$\begin{aligned} 921039^2 + 562000^2 &:= 1078961^2 \\ 99921039^2 + 5620000^2 &:= 100078961^2 \\ 9999921039^2 + 56200000^2 &:= 10000078961^2 \\ 999999921039^2 + 562000000^2 &:= 1000000078961^2 \end{aligned}$$

282)

$$\begin{aligned} 920476^2 + 564000^2 &:= 1079524^2 \\ 99920476^2 + 5640000^2 &:= 100079524^2 \\ 9999920476^2 + 56400000^2 &:= 10000079524^2 \\ 999999920476^2 + 564000000^2 &:= 1000000079524^2 \end{aligned}$$

283)

$$\begin{aligned} 919911^2 + 566000^2 &:= 1080089^2 \\ 99919911^2 + 5660000^2 &:= 100080089^2 \\ 9999919911^2 + 56600000^2 &:= 10000080089^2 \\ 999999919911^2 + 566000000^2 &:= 1000000080089^2 \end{aligned}$$

284)

$$\begin{aligned} 919344^2 + 568000^2 &:= 1080656^2 \\ 99919344^2 + 5680000^2 &:= 100080656^2 \\ 9999919344^2 + 56800000^2 &:= 10000080656^2 \\ 999999919344^2 + 568000000^2 &:= 1000000080656^2 \end{aligned}$$

285)

$$\begin{aligned} 918775^2 + 570000^2 &:= 1081225^2 \\ 99918775^2 + 5700000^2 &:= 100081225^2 \\ 9999918775^2 + 57000000^2 &:= 10000081225^2 \\ 999999918775^2 + 570000000^2 &:= 1000000081225^2 \end{aligned}$$

286)

$$\begin{aligned} 918204^2 + 572000^2 &:= 1081796^2 \\ 99918204^2 + 5720000^2 &:= 100081796^2 \\ 9999918204^2 + 57200000^2 &:= 10000081796^2 \\ 999999918204^2 + 572000000^2 &:= 1000000081796^2 \end{aligned}$$

287)

$$\begin{aligned} 917631^2 + 574000^2 &:= 1082369^2 \\ 99917631^2 + 5740000^2 &:= 100082369^2 \\ 9999917631^2 + 57400000^2 &:= 10000082369^2 \\ 999999917631^2 + 574000000^2 &:= 1000000082369^2 \end{aligned}$$

288)

$$\begin{aligned} 917056^2 + 576000^2 &:= 1082944^2 \\ 99917056^2 + 5760000^2 &:= 100082944^2 \\ 9999917056^2 + 57600000^2 &:= 10000082944^2 \\ 999999917056^2 + 576000000^2 &:= 1000000082944^2 \end{aligned}$$

289)

$$\begin{aligned} 916479^2 + 578000^2 &:= 1083521^2 \\ 99916479^2 + 5780000^2 &:= 100083521^2 \\ 9999916479^2 + 57800000^2 &:= 10000083521^2 \\ 999999916479^2 + 578000000^2 &:= 1000000083521^2 \end{aligned}$$

290)

$$\begin{aligned} 915900^2 + 580000^2 &:= 1084100^2 \\ 99915900^2 + 5800000^2 &:= 100084100^2 \\ 9999915900^2 + 58000000^2 &:= 10000084100^2 \\ 999999915900^2 + 580000000^2 &:= 1000000084100^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 291) $915319^2 + 582000^2 := 1084681^2$
 $99915319^2 + 5820000^2 := 100084681^2$
 $9999915319^2 + 58200000^2 := 10000084681^2$
 $999999915319^2 + 582000000^2 := 1000000084681^2$
- 292) $914736^2 + 584000^2 := 1085264^2$
 $99914736^2 + 5840000^2 := 100085264^2$
 $9999914736^2 + 58400000^2 := 10000085264^2$
 $999999914736^2 + 584000000^2 := 1000000085264^2$
- 293) $914151^2 + 586000^2 := 1085849^2$
 $99914151^2 + 5860000^2 := 100085849^2$
 $9999914151^2 + 58600000^2 := 10000085849^2$
 $999999914151^2 + 586000000^2 := 1000000085849^2$
- 294) $913564^2 + 588000^2 := 1086436^2$
 $99913564^2 + 5880000^2 := 100086436^2$
 $9999913564^2 + 58800000^2 := 10000086436^2$
 $999999913564^2 + 588000000^2 := 1000000086436^2$
- 295) $912975^2 + 590000^2 := 1087025^2$
 $99912975^2 + 5900000^2 := 100087025^2$
 $9999912975^2 + 59000000^2 := 10000087025^2$
 $999999912975^2 + 590000000^2 := 1000000087025^2$
- 296) $912384^2 + 592000^2 := 1087616^2$
 $99912384^2 + 5920000^2 := 100087616^2$
 $9999912384^2 + 59200000^2 := 10000087616^2$
 $999999912384^2 + 592000000^2 := 1000000087616^2$
- 297) $911791^2 + 594000^2 := 1088209^2$
 $99911791^2 + 5940000^2 := 100088209^2$
 $9999911791^2 + 59400000^2 := 10000088209^2$
 $999999911791^2 + 594000000^2 := 1000000088209^2$
- 298) $911196^2 + 596000^2 := 1088804^2$
 $99911196^2 + 5960000^2 := 100088804^2$
 $9999911196^2 + 59600000^2 := 10000088804^2$
 $999999911196^2 + 596000000^2 := 1000000088804^2$
- 299) $910599^2 + 598000^2 := 1089401^2$
 $99910599^2 + 5980000^2 := 100089401^2$
 $9999910599^2 + 59800000^2 := 10000089401^2$
 $999999910599^2 + 598000000^2 := 1000000089401^2$
- 300) $910000^2 + 600000^2 := 1090000^2$
 $99910000^2 + 6000000^2 := 100090000^2$
 $9999910000^2 + 60000000^2 := 10000090000^2$
 $999999910000^2 + 600000000^2 := 1000000090000^2$
- 301) $909399^2 + 602000^2 := 1090601^2$
 $99909399^2 + 6020000^2 := 100090601^2$
 $9999909399^2 + 60200000^2 := 10000090601^2$
 $999999909399^2 + 602000000^2 := 1000000090601^2$
- 302) $908796^2 + 604000^2 := 1091204^2$
 $99908796^2 + 6040000^2 := 100091204^2$
 $9999908796^2 + 60400000^2 := 10000091204^2$
 $999999908796^2 + 604000000^2 := 1000000091204^2$
- 303) $908191^2 + 606000^2 := 1091809^2$
 $99908191^2 + 6060000^2 := 100091809^2$
 $9999908191^2 + 60600000^2 := 10000091809^2$
 $999999908191^2 + 606000000^2 := 1000000091809^2$

- 304) $907584^2 + 608000^2 := 1092416^2$
 $99907584^2 + 6080000^2 := 100092416^2$
 $9999907584^2 + 60800000^2 := 10000092416^2$
 $999999907584^2 + 608000000^2 := 1000000092416^2$
- 305) $906975^2 + 610000^2 := 1093025^2$
 $99906975^2 + 6100000^2 := 100093025^2$
 $9999906975^2 + 61000000^2 := 10000093025^2$
 $999999906975^2 + 610000000^2 := 1000000093025^2$
- 306) $906364^2 + 612000^2 := 1093636^2$
 $99906364^2 + 6120000^2 := 100093636^2$
 $9999906364^2 + 61200000^2 := 10000093636^2$
 $999999906364^2 + 612000000^2 := 1000000093636^2$
- 307) $905751^2 + 614000^2 := 1094249^2$
 $99905751^2 + 6140000^2 := 100094249^2$
 $9999905751^2 + 61400000^2 := 10000094249^2$
 $999999905751^2 + 614000000^2 := 1000000094249^2$
- 308) $905136^2 + 616000^2 := 1094864^2$
 $99905136^2 + 6160000^2 := 100094864^2$
 $9999905136^2 + 61600000^2 := 10000094864^2$
 $999999905136^2 + 616000000^2 := 1000000094864^2$
- 309) $904519^2 + 618000^2 := 1095481^2$
 $99904519^2 + 6180000^2 := 100095481^2$
 $9999904519^2 + 61800000^2 := 10000095481^2$
 $999999904519^2 + 618000000^2 := 1000000095481^2$
- 310) $903900^2 + 620000^2 := 1096100^2$
 $99903900^2 + 6200000^2 := 100096100^2$
 $9999903900^2 + 62000000^2 := 10000096100^2$
 $999999903900^2 + 620000000^2 := 1000000096100^2$
- 311) $903279^2 + 622000^2 := 1096721^2$
 $99903279^2 + 6220000^2 := 100096721^2$
 $9999903279^2 + 62200000^2 := 10000096721^2$
 $999999903279^2 + 622000000^2 := 1000000096721^2$
- 312) $902656^2 + 624000^2 := 1097344^2$
 $99902656^2 + 6240000^2 := 100097344^2$
 $9999902656^2 + 62400000^2 := 10000097344^2$
 $999999902656^2 + 624000000^2 := 1000000097344^2$
- 313) $902031^2 + 626000^2 := 1097969^2$
 $99902031^2 + 6260000^2 := 100097969^2$
 $9999902031^2 + 62600000^2 := 10000097969^2$
 $999999902031^2 + 626000000^2 := 1000000097969^2$
- 314) $901404^2 + 628000^2 := 1098596^2$
 $99901404^2 + 6280000^2 := 100098596^2$
 $9999901404^2 + 62800000^2 := 10000098596^2$
 $999999901404^2 + 628000000^2 := 1000000098596^2$
- 315) $900775^2 + 630000^2 := 1099225^2$
 $99900775^2 + 6300000^2 := 100099225^2$
 $9999900775^2 + 63000000^2 := 10000099225^2$
 $999999900775^2 + 630000000^2 := 1000000099225^2$
- 316) $900144^2 + 632000^2 := 1099856^2$
 $99900144^2 + 6320000^2 := 100099856^2$
 $9999900144^2 + 63200000^2 := 10000099856^2$
 $999999900144^2 + 632000000^2 := 1000000099856^2$

- 317) $899511^2 + 634000^2 := 1100489^2$
 $99899511^2 + 6340000^2 := 100100489^2$
 $9999899511^2 + 63400000^2 := 10000100489^2$
 $99999899511^2 + 634000000^2 := 1000000100489^2$
- 318) $898876^2 + 636000^2 := 1101124^2$
 $99898876^2 + 6360000^2 := 100101124^2$
 $9999898876^2 + 63600000^2 := 10000101124^2$
 $99999898876^2 + 636000000^2 := 1000000101124^2$
- 319) $898239^2 + 638000^2 := 1101761^2$
 $99898239^2 + 6380000^2 := 100101761^2$
 $9999898239^2 + 63800000^2 := 10000101761^2$
 $99999898239^2 + 638000000^2 := 1000000101761^2$
- 320) $897600^2 + 640000^2 := 1102400^2$
 $99897600^2 + 6400000^2 := 100102400^2$
 $9999897600^2 + 64000000^2 := 10000102400^2$
 $99999897600^2 + 640000000^2 := 1000000102400^2$
- 321) $896959^2 + 642000^2 := 1103041^2$
 $99896959^2 + 6420000^2 := 100103041^2$
 $9999896959^2 + 64200000^2 := 10000103041^2$
 $99999896959^2 + 642000000^2 := 1000000103041^2$
- 322) $896316^2 + 644000^2 := 1103684^2$
 $99896316^2 + 6440000^2 := 100103684^2$
 $9999896316^2 + 64400000^2 := 10000103684^2$
 $99999896316^2 + 644000000^2 := 1000000103684^2$
- 323) $895671^2 + 646000^2 := 1104329^2$
 $99895671^2 + 6460000^2 := 100104329^2$
 $9999895671^2 + 64600000^2 := 10000104329^2$
 $99999895671^2 + 646000000^2 := 1000000104329^2$
- 324) $895024^2 + 648000^2 := 1104976^2$
 $99895024^2 + 6480000^2 := 100104976^2$
 $9999895024^2 + 64800000^2 := 10000104976^2$
 $99999895024^2 + 648000000^2 := 1000000104976^2$
- 325) $894375^2 + 650000^2 := 1105625^2$
 $99894375^2 + 6500000^2 := 100105625^2$
 $9999894375^2 + 65000000^2 := 10000105625^2$
 $99999894375^2 + 650000000^2 := 1000000105625^2$
- 326) $893724^2 + 652000^2 := 1106276^2$
 $99893724^2 + 6520000^2 := 100106276^2$
 $9999893724^2 + 65200000^2 := 10000106276^2$
 $99999893724^2 + 652000000^2 := 1000000106276^2$
- 327) $893071^2 + 654000^2 := 1106929^2$
 $99893071^2 + 6540000^2 := 100106929^2$
 $9999893071^2 + 65400000^2 := 10000106929^2$
 $99999893071^2 + 654000000^2 := 1000000106929^2$
- 328) $892416^2 + 656000^2 := 1107584^2$
 $99892416^2 + 6560000^2 := 100107584^2$
 $9999892416^2 + 65600000^2 := 10000107584^2$
 $99999892416^2 + 656000000^2 := 1000000107584^2$
- 329) $891759^2 + 658000^2 := 1108241^2$
 $99891759^2 + 6580000^2 := 100108241^2$
 $9999891759^2 + 65800000^2 := 10000108241^2$
 $99999891759^2 + 658000000^2 := 1000000108241^2$

330)

$$\begin{aligned}891100^2 + 660000^2 &:= 1108900^2 \\99891100^2 + 6600000^2 &:= 100108900^2 \\999891100^2 + 66000000^2 &:= 10000108900^2 \\9999891100^2 + 660000000^2 &:= 1000000108900^2\end{aligned}$$

331)

$$\begin{aligned}890439^2 + 662000^2 &:= 1109561^2 \\99890439^2 + 6620000^2 &:= 100109561^2 \\999890439^2 + 66200000^2 &:= 10000109561^2 \\9999890439^2 + 662000000^2 &:= 1000000109561^2\end{aligned}$$

332)

$$\begin{aligned}889776^2 + 664000^2 &:= 1110224^2 \\99889776^2 + 6640000^2 &:= 100110224^2 \\999889776^2 + 66400000^2 &:= 10000110224^2 \\9999889776^2 + 664000000^2 &:= 1000000110224^2\end{aligned}$$

333)

$$\begin{aligned}889111^2 + 666000^2 &:= 1110889^2 \\99889111^2 + 6660000^2 &:= 100110889^2 \\999889111^2 + 66600000^2 &:= 10000110889^2 \\9999889111^2 + 666000000^2 &:= 1000000110889^2\end{aligned}$$

334)

$$\begin{aligned}888444^2 + 668000^2 &:= 1111556^2 \\99888444^2 + 6680000^2 &:= 100111556^2 \\999888444^2 + 66800000^2 &:= 10000111556^2 \\9999888444^2 + 668000000^2 &:= 1000000111556^2\end{aligned}$$

335)

$$\begin{aligned}887775^2 + 670000^2 &:= 1112225^2 \\99887775^2 + 6700000^2 &:= 100112225^2 \\999887775^2 + 67000000^2 &:= 10000112225^2 \\9999887775^2 + 670000000^2 &:= 1000000112225^2\end{aligned}$$

336)

$$\begin{aligned}887104^2 + 672000^2 &:= 1112896^2 \\99887104^2 + 6720000^2 &:= 100112896^2 \\999887104^2 + 67200000^2 &:= 10000112896^2 \\9999887104^2 + 672000000^2 &:= 1000000112896^2\end{aligned}$$

337)

$$\begin{aligned}886431^2 + 674000^2 &:= 1113569^2 \\99886431^2 + 6740000^2 &:= 100113569^2 \\999886431^2 + 67400000^2 &:= 10000113569^2 \\9999886431^2 + 674000000^2 &:= 1000000113569^2\end{aligned}$$

338)

$$\begin{aligned}885756^2 + 676000^2 &:= 1114244^2 \\99885756^2 + 6760000^2 &:= 100114244^2 \\999885756^2 + 67600000^2 &:= 10000114244^2 \\9999885756^2 + 676000000^2 &:= 1000000114244^2\end{aligned}$$

339)

$$\begin{aligned}885079^2 + 678000^2 &:= 1114921^2 \\99885079^2 + 6780000^2 &:= 100114921^2 \\999885079^2 + 67800000^2 &:= 10000114921^2 \\9999885079^2 + 678000000^2 &:= 1000000114921^2\end{aligned}$$

340)

$$\begin{aligned}884400^2 + 680000^2 &:= 1115600^2 \\99884400^2 + 6800000^2 &:= 100115600^2 \\999884400^2 + 68000000^2 &:= 10000115600^2 \\9999884400^2 + 680000000^2 &:= 1000000115600^2\end{aligned}$$

341)

$$\begin{aligned}883719^2 + 682000^2 &:= 1116281^2 \\99883719^2 + 6820000^2 &:= 100116281^2 \\999883719^2 + 68200000^2 &:= 10000116281^2 \\9999883719^2 + 682000000^2 &:= 1000000116281^2\end{aligned}$$

342)

$$\begin{aligned}883036^2 + 684000^2 &:= 1116964^2 \\99883036^2 + 6840000^2 &:= 100116964^2 \\999883036^2 + 68400000^2 &:= 10000116964^2 \\9999883036^2 + 684000000^2 &:= 1000000116964^2\end{aligned}$$

343)

$$\begin{aligned}882351^2 + 686000^2 &:= 1117649^2 \\99882351^2 + 6860000^2 &:= 100117649^2 \\9999882351^2 + 68600000^2 &:= 10000117649^2 \\99999882351^2 + 686000000^2 &:= 1000000117649^2\end{aligned}$$

344)

$$\begin{aligned}881664^2 + 688000^2 &:= 1118336^2 \\99881664^2 + 6880000^2 &:= 100118336^2 \\9999881664^2 + 68800000^2 &:= 10000118336^2 \\99999881664^2 + 688000000^2 &:= 1000000118336^2\end{aligned}$$

345)

$$\begin{aligned}880975^2 + 690000^2 &:= 1119025^2 \\99880975^2 + 6900000^2 &:= 100119025^2 \\9999880975^2 + 69000000^2 &:= 10000119025^2 \\99999880975^2 + 690000000^2 &:= 1000000119025^2\end{aligned}$$

346)

$$\begin{aligned}880284^2 + 692000^2 &:= 1119716^2 \\99880284^2 + 6920000^2 &:= 100119716^2 \\9999880284^2 + 69200000^2 &:= 10000119716^2 \\99999880284^2 + 692000000^2 &:= 1000000119716^2\end{aligned}$$

347)

$$\begin{aligned}879591^2 + 694000^2 &:= 1120409^2 \\99879591^2 + 6940000^2 &:= 100120409^2 \\9999879591^2 + 69400000^2 &:= 10000120409^2 \\99999879591^2 + 694000000^2 &:= 1000000120409^2\end{aligned}$$

348)

$$\begin{aligned}878896^2 + 696000^2 &:= 1121104^2 \\99878896^2 + 6960000^2 &:= 100121104^2 \\9999878896^2 + 69600000^2 &:= 10000121104^2 \\99999878896^2 + 696000000^2 &:= 1000000121104^2\end{aligned}$$

349)

$$\begin{aligned}878199^2 + 698000^2 &:= 1121801^2 \\99878199^2 + 6980000^2 &:= 100121801^2 \\9999878199^2 + 69800000^2 &:= 10000121801^2 \\99999878199^2 + 698000000^2 &:= 1000000121801^2\end{aligned}$$

350)

$$\begin{aligned}877500^2 + 700000^2 &:= 1122500^2 \\99877500^2 + 7000000^2 &:= 100122500^2 \\9999877500^2 + 70000000^2 &:= 10000122500^2 \\99999877500^2 + 700000000^2 &:= 1000000122500^2\end{aligned}$$

351)

$$\begin{aligned}876799^2 + 702000^2 &:= 1123201^2 \\99876799^2 + 7020000^2 &:= 100123201^2 \\9999876799^2 + 70200000^2 &:= 10000123201^2 \\99999876799^2 + 702000000^2 &:= 1000000123201^2\end{aligned}$$

352)

$$\begin{aligned}876096^2 + 704000^2 &:= 1123904^2 \\99876096^2 + 7040000^2 &:= 100123904^2 \\9999876096^2 + 70400000^2 &:= 10000123904^2 \\99999876096^2 + 704000000^2 &:= 1000000123904^2\end{aligned}$$

353)

$$\begin{aligned}875391^2 + 706000^2 &:= 1124609^2 \\99875391^2 + 7060000^2 &:= 100124609^2 \\9999875391^2 + 70600000^2 &:= 10000124609^2 \\99999875391^2 + 706000000^2 &:= 1000000124609^2\end{aligned}$$

354)

$$\begin{aligned}874684^2 + 708000^2 &:= 1125316^2 \\99874684^2 + 7080000^2 &:= 100125316^2 \\9999874684^2 + 70800000^2 &:= 10000125316^2 \\99999874684^2 + 708000000^2 &:= 1000000125316^2\end{aligned}$$

355)

$$\begin{aligned}873975^2 + 710000^2 &:= 1126025^2 \\99873975^2 + 7100000^2 &:= 100126025^2 \\9999873975^2 + 71000000^2 &:= 10000126025^2 \\99999873975^2 + 710000000^2 &:= 1000000126025^2\end{aligned}$$

- 356) $873264^2 + 712000^2 := 1126736^2$
 $99873264^2 + 7120000^2 := 100126736^2$
 $9999873264^2 + 71200000^2 := 10000126736^2$
 $999999873264^2 + 712000000^2 := 1000000126736^2$
- 357) $872551^2 + 714000^2 := 1127449^2$
 $99872551^2 + 7140000^2 := 100127449^2$
 $9999872551^2 + 71400000^2 := 10000127449^2$
 $999999872551^2 + 714000000^2 := 1000000127449^2$
- 358) $871836^2 + 716000^2 := 1128164^2$
 $99871836^2 + 7160000^2 := 100128164^2$
 $9999871836^2 + 71600000^2 := 10000128164^2$
 $999999871836^2 + 716000000^2 := 1000000128164^2$
- 359) $871119^2 + 718000^2 := 1128881^2$
 $99871119^2 + 7180000^2 := 100128881^2$
 $9999871119^2 + 71800000^2 := 10000128881^2$
 $999999871119^2 + 718000000^2 := 1000000128881^2$
- 360) $870400^2 + 720000^2 := 1129600^2$
 $99870400^2 + 7200000^2 := 100129600^2$
 $9999870400^2 + 72000000^2 := 10000129600^2$
 $999999870400^2 + 720000000^2 := 1000000129600^2$
- 361) $869679^2 + 722000^2 := 1130321^2$
 $99869679^2 + 7220000^2 := 100130321^2$
 $9999869679^2 + 72200000^2 := 10000130321^2$
 $999999869679^2 + 722000000^2 := 1000000130321^2$
- 362) $868956^2 + 724000^2 := 1131044^2$
 $99868956^2 + 7240000^2 := 100131044^2$
 $9999868956^2 + 72400000^2 := 10000131044^2$
 $999999868956^2 + 724000000^2 := 1000000131044^2$
- 363) $868231^2 + 726000^2 := 1131769^2$
 $99868231^2 + 7260000^2 := 100131769^2$
 $9999868231^2 + 72600000^2 := 10000131769^2$
 $999999868231^2 + 726000000^2 := 1000000131769^2$
- 364) $867504^2 + 728000^2 := 1132496^2$
 $99867504^2 + 7280000^2 := 100132496^2$
 $9999867504^2 + 72800000^2 := 10000132496^2$
 $999999867504^2 + 728000000^2 := 1000000132496^2$
- 365) $866775^2 + 730000^2 := 1133225^2$
 $99866775^2 + 7300000^2 := 100133225^2$
 $9999866775^2 + 73000000^2 := 10000133225^2$
 $999999866775^2 + 730000000^2 := 1000000133225^2$
- 366) $866044^2 + 732000^2 := 1133956^2$
 $99866044^2 + 7320000^2 := 100133956^2$
 $9999866044^2 + 73200000^2 := 10000133956^2$
 $999999866044^2 + 732000000^2 := 1000000133956^2$
- 367) $865311^2 + 734000^2 := 1134689^2$
 $99865311^2 + 7340000^2 := 100134689^2$
 $9999865311^2 + 73400000^2 := 10000134689^2$
 $999999865311^2 + 734000000^2 := 1000000134689^2$
- 368) $864576^2 + 736000^2 := 1135424^2$
 $99864576^2 + 7360000^2 := 100135424^2$
 $9999864576^2 + 73600000^2 := 10000135424^2$
 $999999864576^2 + 736000000^2 := 1000000135424^2$

- 369) $863839^2 + 738000^2 := 1136161^2$
 $99863839^2 + 7380000^2 := 100136161^2$
 $9999863839^2 + 73800000^2 := 10000136161^2$
 $999999863839^2 + 738000000^2 := 1000000136161^2$
- 370) $863100^2 + 740000^2 := 1136900^2$
 $99863100^2 + 7400000^2 := 100136900^2$
 $9999863100^2 + 74000000^2 := 10000136900^2$
 $999999863100^2 + 740000000^2 := 1000000136900^2$
- 371) $862359^2 + 742000^2 := 1137641^2$
 $99862359^2 + 7420000^2 := 100137641^2$
 $9999862359^2 + 74200000^2 := 10000137641^2$
 $999999862359^2 + 742000000^2 := 1000000137641^2$
- 372) $861616^2 + 744000^2 := 1138384^2$
 $99861616^2 + 7440000^2 := 100138384^2$
 $9999861616^2 + 74400000^2 := 10000138384^2$
 $999999861616^2 + 744000000^2 := 1000000138384^2$
- 373) $860871^2 + 746000^2 := 1139129^2$
 $99860871^2 + 7460000^2 := 100139129^2$
 $9999860871^2 + 74600000^2 := 10000139129^2$
 $999999860871^2 + 746000000^2 := 1000000139129^2$
- 374) $860124^2 + 748000^2 := 1139876^2$
 $99860124^2 + 7480000^2 := 100139876^2$
 $9999860124^2 + 74800000^2 := 10000139876^2$
 $999999860124^2 + 748000000^2 := 1000000139876^2$
- 375) $859375^2 + 750000^2 := 1140625^2$
 $99859375^2 + 7500000^2 := 100140625^2$
 $9999859375^2 + 75000000^2 := 10000140625^2$
 $999999859375^2 + 750000000^2 := 1000000140625^2$
- 376) $858624^2 + 752000^2 := 1141376^2$
 $99858624^2 + 7520000^2 := 100141376^2$
 $9999858624^2 + 75200000^2 := 10000141376^2$
 $999999858624^2 + 752000000^2 := 1000000141376^2$
- 377) $857871^2 + 754000^2 := 1142129^2$
 $99857871^2 + 7540000^2 := 100142129^2$
 $9999857871^2 + 75400000^2 := 10000142129^2$
 $999999857871^2 + 754000000^2 := 1000000142129^2$
- 378) $857116^2 + 756000^2 := 1142884^2$
 $99857116^2 + 7560000^2 := 100142884^2$
 $9999857116^2 + 75600000^2 := 10000142884^2$
 $999999857116^2 + 756000000^2 := 1000000142884^2$
- 379) $856359^2 + 758000^2 := 1143641^2$
 $99856359^2 + 7580000^2 := 100143641^2$
 $9999856359^2 + 75800000^2 := 10000143641^2$
 $999999856359^2 + 758000000^2 := 1000000143641^2$
- 380) $855600^2 + 760000^2 := 1144400^2$
 $99855600^2 + 7600000^2 := 100144400^2$
 $9999855600^2 + 76000000^2 := 10000144400^2$
 $999999855600^2 + 760000000^2 := 1000000144400^2$
- 381) $854839^2 + 762000^2 := 1145161^2$
 $99854839^2 + 7620000^2 := 100145161^2$
 $9999854839^2 + 76200000^2 := 10000145161^2$
 $999999854839^2 + 762000000^2 := 1000000145161^2$

- 382) $854076^2 + 764000^2 := 1145924^2$
 $99854076^2 + 7640000^2 := 100145924^2$
 $9999854076^2 + 76400000^2 := 10000145924^2$
 $99999854076^2 + 764000000^2 := 1000000145924^2$
- 383) $853311^2 + 766000^2 := 1146689^2$
 $99853311^2 + 7660000^2 := 100146689^2$
 $9999853311^2 + 76600000^2 := 10000146689^2$
 $99999853311^2 + 766000000^2 := 1000000146689^2$
- 384) $852544^2 + 768000^2 := 1147456^2$
 $99852544^2 + 7680000^2 := 100147456^2$
 $9999852544^2 + 76800000^2 := 10000147456^2$
 $99999852544^2 + 768000000^2 := 1000000147456^2$
- 385) $851775^2 + 770000^2 := 1148225^2$
 $99851775^2 + 7700000^2 := 100148225^2$
 $9999851775^2 + 77000000^2 := 10000148225^2$
 $99999851775^2 + 770000000^2 := 1000000148225^2$
- 386) $851004^2 + 772000^2 := 1148996^2$
 $99851004^2 + 7720000^2 := 100148996^2$
 $9999851004^2 + 77200000^2 := 10000148996^2$
 $99999851004^2 + 772000000^2 := 1000000148996^2$
- 387) $850231^2 + 774000^2 := 1149769^2$
 $99850231^2 + 7740000^2 := 100149769^2$
 $9999850231^2 + 77400000^2 := 10000149769^2$
 $99999850231^2 + 774000000^2 := 1000000149769^2$
- 388) $849456^2 + 776000^2 := 1150544^2$
 $99849456^2 + 7760000^2 := 100150544^2$
 $9999849456^2 + 77600000^2 := 10000150544^2$
 $99999849456^2 + 776000000^2 := 1000000150544^2$
- 389) $848679^2 + 778000^2 := 1151321^2$
 $99848679^2 + 7780000^2 := 100151321^2$
 $9999848679^2 + 77800000^2 := 10000151321^2$
 $99999848679^2 + 778000000^2 := 1000000151321^2$
- 390) $847900^2 + 780000^2 := 1152100^2$
 $99847900^2 + 7800000^2 := 100152100^2$
 $9999847900^2 + 78000000^2 := 10000152100^2$
 $99999847900^2 + 780000000^2 := 1000000152100^2$
- 391) $847119^2 + 782000^2 := 1152881^2$
 $99847119^2 + 7820000^2 := 100152881^2$
 $9999847119^2 + 78200000^2 := 10000152881^2$
 $99999847119^2 + 782000000^2 := 1000000152881^2$
- 392) $846336^2 + 784000^2 := 1153664^2$
 $99846336^2 + 7840000^2 := 100153664^2$
 $9999846336^2 + 78400000^2 := 10000153664^2$
 $99999846336^2 + 784000000^2 := 1000000153664^2$
- 393) $845551^2 + 786000^2 := 1154449^2$
 $99845551^2 + 7860000^2 := 100154449^2$
 $9999845551^2 + 78600000^2 := 10000154449^2$
 $99999845551^2 + 786000000^2 := 1000000154449^2$
- 394) $844764^2 + 788000^2 := 1155236^2$
 $99844764^2 + 7880000^2 := 100155236^2$
 $9999844764^2 + 78800000^2 := 10000155236^2$
 $99999844764^2 + 788000000^2 := 1000000155236^2$

- 395) $843975^2 + 790000^2 := 1156025^2$
 $99843975^2 + 7900000^2 := 100156025^2$
 $9999843975^2 + 79000000^2 := 10000156025^2$
 $999999843975^2 + 790000000^2 := 1000000156025^2$
- 396) $843184^2 + 792000^2 := 1156816^2$
 $99843184^2 + 7920000^2 := 100156816^2$
 $9999843184^2 + 79200000^2 := 10000156816^2$
 $999999843184^2 + 792000000^2 := 1000000156816^2$
- 397) $842391^2 + 794000^2 := 1157609^2$
 $99842391^2 + 7940000^2 := 100157609^2$
 $9999842391^2 + 79400000^2 := 10000157609^2$
 $999999842391^2 + 794000000^2 := 1000000157609^2$
- 398) $841596^2 + 796000^2 := 1158404^2$
 $99841596^2 + 7960000^2 := 100158404^2$
 $9999841596^2 + 79600000^2 := 10000158404^2$
 $999999841596^2 + 796000000^2 := 1000000158404^2$
- 399) $840799^2 + 798000^2 := 1159201^2$
 $99840799^2 + 7980000^2 := 100159201^2$
 $9999840799^2 + 79800000^2 := 10000159201^2$
 $999999840799^2 + 798000000^2 := 1000000159201^2$
- 400) $840000^2 + 800000^2 := 1160000^2$
 $99840000^2 + 8000000^2 := 100160000^2$
 $9999840000^2 + 80000000^2 := 10000160000^2$
 $999999840000^2 + 800000000^2 := 1000000160000^2$
- 401) $839199^2 + 802000^2 := 1160801^2$
 $99839199^2 + 8020000^2 := 100160801^2$
 $9999839199^2 + 80200000^2 := 10000160801^2$
 $999999839199^2 + 802000000^2 := 1000000160801^2$
- 402) $838396^2 + 804000^2 := 1161604^2$
 $99838396^2 + 8040000^2 := 100161604^2$
 $9999838396^2 + 80400000^2 := 10000161604^2$
 $999999838396^2 + 804000000^2 := 1000000161604^2$
- 403) $837591^2 + 806000^2 := 1162409^2$
 $99837591^2 + 8060000^2 := 100162409^2$
 $9999837591^2 + 80600000^2 := 10000162409^2$
 $999999837591^2 + 806000000^2 := 1000000162409^2$
- 404) $836784^2 + 808000^2 := 1163216^2$
 $99836784^2 + 8080000^2 := 100163216^2$
 $9999836784^2 + 80800000^2 := 10000163216^2$
 $999999836784^2 + 808000000^2 := 1000000163216^2$
- 405) $835975^2 + 810000^2 := 1164025^2$
 $99835975^2 + 8100000^2 := 100164025^2$
 $9999835975^2 + 81000000^2 := 10000164025^2$
 $999999835975^2 + 810000000^2 := 1000000164025^2$
- 406) $835164^2 + 812000^2 := 1164836^2$
 $99835164^2 + 8120000^2 := 100164836^2$
 $9999835164^2 + 81200000^2 := 10000164836^2$
 $999999835164^2 + 812000000^2 := 1000000164836^2$
- 407) $834351^2 + 814000^2 := 1165649^2$
 $99834351^2 + 8140000^2 := 100165649^2$
 $9999834351^2 + 81400000^2 := 10000165649^2$
 $999999834351^2 + 814000000^2 := 1000000165649^2$

- 408) $833536^2 + 816000^2 := 1166464^2$
 $99833536^2 + 8160000^2 := 100166464^2$
 $9999833536^2 + 81600000^2 := 10000166464^2$
 $99999833536^2 + 816000000^2 := 1000000166464^2$
- 409) $832719^2 + 818000^2 := 1167281^2$
 $99832719^2 + 8180000^2 := 100167281^2$
 $9999832719^2 + 81800000^2 := 10000167281^2$
 $99999832719^2 + 818000000^2 := 1000000167281^2$
- 410) $831900^2 + 820000^2 := 1168100^2$
 $99831900^2 + 8200000^2 := 100168100^2$
 $9999831900^2 + 82000000^2 := 10000168100^2$
 $99999831900^2 + 820000000^2 := 1000000168100^2$
- 411) $831079^2 + 822000^2 := 1168921^2$
 $99831079^2 + 8220000^2 := 100168921^2$
 $9999831079^2 + 82200000^2 := 10000168921^2$
 $99999831079^2 + 822000000^2 := 1000000168921^2$
- 412) $830256^2 + 824000^2 := 1169744^2$
 $99830256^2 + 8240000^2 := 100169744^2$
 $9999830256^2 + 82400000^2 := 10000169744^2$
 $99999830256^2 + 824000000^2 := 1000000169744^2$
- 413) $829431^2 + 826000^2 := 1170569^2$
 $99829431^2 + 8260000^2 := 100170569^2$
 $9999829431^2 + 82600000^2 := 10000170569^2$
 $99999829431^2 + 826000000^2 := 1000000170569^2$
- 414) $828604^2 + 828000^2 := 1171396^2$
 $99828604^2 + 8280000^2 := 100171396^2$
 $9999828604^2 + 82800000^2 := 10000171396^2$
 $99999828604^2 + 828000000^2 := 1000000171396^2$
- 415) $827775^2 + 830000^2 := 1172225^2$
 $99827775^2 + 8300000^2 := 100172225^2$
 $9999827775^2 + 83000000^2 := 10000172225^2$
 $99999827775^2 + 830000000^2 := 1000000172225^2$
- 416) $826944^2 + 832000^2 := 1173056^2$
 $99826944^2 + 8320000^2 := 100173056^2$
 $9999826944^2 + 83200000^2 := 10000173056^2$
 $99999826944^2 + 832000000^2 := 1000000173056^2$
- 417) $826111^2 + 834000^2 := 1173889^2$
 $99826111^2 + 8340000^2 := 100173889^2$
 $9999826111^2 + 83400000^2 := 10000173889^2$
 $99999826111^2 + 834000000^2 := 1000000173889^2$
- 418) $825276^2 + 836000^2 := 1174724^2$
 $99825276^2 + 8360000^2 := 100174724^2$
 $9999825276^2 + 83600000^2 := 10000174724^2$
 $99999825276^2 + 836000000^2 := 1000000174724^2$
- 419) $824439^2 + 838000^2 := 1175561^2$
 $99824439^2 + 8380000^2 := 100175561^2$
 $9999824439^2 + 83800000^2 := 10000175561^2$
 $99999824439^2 + 838000000^2 := 1000000175561^2$
- 420) $823600^2 + 840000^2 := 1176400^2$
 $99823600^2 + 8400000^2 := 100176400^2$
 $9999823600^2 + 84000000^2 := 10000176400^2$
 $99999823600^2 + 840000000^2 := 1000000176400^2$

421)

$$\begin{aligned}822759^2 + 842000^2 &:= 1177241^2 \\99822759^2 + 8420000^2 &:= 100177241^2 \\9999822759^2 + 84200000^2 &:= 10000177241^2 \\999999822759^2 + 842000000^2 &:= 1000000177241^2\end{aligned}$$

422)

$$\begin{aligned}821916^2 + 844000^2 &:= 1178084^2 \\99821916^2 + 8440000^2 &:= 100178084^2 \\9999821916^2 + 84400000^2 &:= 10000178084^2 \\999999821916^2 + 844000000^2 &:= 1000000178084^2\end{aligned}$$

423)

$$\begin{aligned}821071^2 + 846000^2 &:= 1178929^2 \\99821071^2 + 8460000^2 &:= 100178929^2 \\9999821071^2 + 84600000^2 &:= 10000178929^2 \\999999821071^2 + 846000000^2 &:= 1000000178929^2\end{aligned}$$

424)

$$\begin{aligned}820224^2 + 848000^2 &:= 1179776^2 \\99820224^2 + 8480000^2 &:= 100179776^2 \\9999820224^2 + 84800000^2 &:= 10000179776^2 \\999999820224^2 + 848000000^2 &:= 1000000179776^2\end{aligned}$$

425)

$$\begin{aligned}819375^2 + 850000^2 &:= 1180625^2 \\99819375^2 + 8500000^2 &:= 100180625^2 \\9999819375^2 + 85000000^2 &:= 10000180625^2 \\999999819375^2 + 850000000^2 &:= 1000000180625^2\end{aligned}$$

426)

$$\begin{aligned}818524^2 + 852000^2 &:= 1181476^2 \\99818524^2 + 8520000^2 &:= 100181476^2 \\9999818524^2 + 85200000^2 &:= 10000181476^2 \\999999818524^2 + 852000000^2 &:= 1000000181476^2\end{aligned}$$

427)

$$\begin{aligned}817671^2 + 854000^2 &:= 1182329^2 \\99817671^2 + 8540000^2 &:= 100182329^2 \\9999817671^2 + 85400000^2 &:= 10000182329^2 \\999999817671^2 + 854000000^2 &:= 1000000182329^2\end{aligned}$$

428)

$$\begin{aligned}816816^2 + 856000^2 &:= 1183184^2 \\99816816^2 + 8560000^2 &:= 100183184^2 \\9999816816^2 + 85600000^2 &:= 10000183184^2 \\999999816816^2 + 856000000^2 &:= 1000000183184^2\end{aligned}$$

429)

$$\begin{aligned}815959^2 + 858000^2 &:= 1184041^2 \\99815959^2 + 8580000^2 &:= 100184041^2 \\9999815959^2 + 85800000^2 &:= 10000184041^2 \\999999815959^2 + 858000000^2 &:= 1000000184041^2\end{aligned}$$

430)

$$\begin{aligned}815100^2 + 860000^2 &:= 1184900^2 \\99815100^2 + 8600000^2 &:= 100184900^2 \\9999815100^2 + 86000000^2 &:= 10000184900^2 \\999999815100^2 + 860000000^2 &:= 1000000184900^2\end{aligned}$$

431)

$$\begin{aligned}814239^2 + 862000^2 &:= 1185761^2 \\99814239^2 + 8620000^2 &:= 100185761^2 \\9999814239^2 + 86200000^2 &:= 10000185761^2 \\999999814239^2 + 862000000^2 &:= 1000000185761^2\end{aligned}$$

432)

$$\begin{aligned}813376^2 + 864000^2 &:= 1186624^2 \\99813376^2 + 8640000^2 &:= 100186624^2 \\9999813376^2 + 86400000^2 &:= 10000186624^2 \\999999813376^2 + 864000000^2 &:= 1000000186624^2\end{aligned}$$

433)

$$\begin{aligned}812511^2 + 866000^2 &:= 1187489^2 \\99812511^2 + 8660000^2 &:= 100187489^2 \\9999812511^2 + 86600000^2 &:= 10000187489^2 \\999999812511^2 + 866000000^2 &:= 1000000187489^2\end{aligned}$$

434)

$$\begin{aligned} 811644^2 + 868000^2 &:= 1188356^2 \\ 99811644^2 + 8680000^2 &:= 100188356^2 \\ 9999811644^2 + 86800000^2 &:= 10000188356^2 \\ 999999811644^2 + 868000000^2 &:= 1000000188356^2 \end{aligned}$$

435)

$$\begin{aligned} 810775^2 + 870000^2 &:= 1189225^2 \\ 99810775^2 + 8700000^2 &:= 100189225^2 \\ 9999810775^2 + 87000000^2 &:= 10000189225^2 \\ 999999810775^2 + 870000000^2 &:= 1000000189225^2 \end{aligned}$$

436)

$$\begin{aligned} 809904^2 + 872000^2 &:= 1190096^2 \\ 99809904^2 + 8720000^2 &:= 100190096^2 \\ 9999809904^2 + 87200000^2 &:= 10000190096^2 \\ 999999809904^2 + 872000000^2 &:= 1000000190096^2 \end{aligned}$$

437)

$$\begin{aligned} 809031^2 + 874000^2 &:= 1190969^2 \\ 99809031^2 + 8740000^2 &:= 100190969^2 \\ 9999809031^2 + 87400000^2 &:= 10000190969^2 \\ 999999809031^2 + 874000000^2 &:= 1000000190969^2 \end{aligned}$$

438)

$$\begin{aligned} 808156^2 + 876000^2 &:= 1191844^2 \\ 99808156^2 + 8760000^2 &:= 100191844^2 \\ 9999808156^2 + 87600000^2 &:= 10000191844^2 \\ 999999808156^2 + 876000000^2 &:= 1000000191844^2 \end{aligned}$$

439)

$$\begin{aligned} 807279^2 + 878000^2 &:= 1192721^2 \\ 99807279^2 + 8780000^2 &:= 100192721^2 \\ 9999807279^2 + 87800000^2 &:= 10000192721^2 \\ 999999807279^2 + 878000000^2 &:= 1000000192721^2 \end{aligned}$$

440)

$$\begin{aligned} 806400^2 + 880000^2 &:= 1193600^2 \\ 99806400^2 + 8800000^2 &:= 100193600^2 \\ 9999806400^2 + 88000000^2 &:= 10000193600^2 \\ 999999806400^2 + 880000000^2 &:= 1000000193600^2 \end{aligned}$$

441)

$$\begin{aligned} 805519^2 + 882000^2 &:= 1194481^2 \\ 99805519^2 + 8820000^2 &:= 100194481^2 \\ 9999805519^2 + 88200000^2 &:= 10000194481^2 \\ 999999805519^2 + 882000000^2 &:= 1000000194481^2 \end{aligned}$$

442)

$$\begin{aligned} 804636^2 + 884000^2 &:= 1195364^2 \\ 99804636^2 + 8840000^2 &:= 100195364^2 \\ 9999804636^2 + 88400000^2 &:= 10000195364^2 \\ 999999804636^2 + 884000000^2 &:= 1000000195364^2 \end{aligned}$$

443)

$$\begin{aligned} 803751^2 + 886000^2 &:= 1196249^2 \\ 99803751^2 + 8860000^2 &:= 100196249^2 \\ 9999803751^2 + 88600000^2 &:= 10000196249^2 \\ 999999803751^2 + 886000000^2 &:= 1000000196249^2 \end{aligned}$$

444)

$$\begin{aligned} 802864^2 + 888000^2 &:= 1197136^2 \\ 99802864^2 + 8880000^2 &:= 100197136^2 \\ 9999802864^2 + 88800000^2 &:= 10000197136^2 \\ 999999802864^2 + 888000000^2 &:= 1000000197136^2 \end{aligned}$$

445)

$$\begin{aligned} 801975^2 + 890000^2 &:= 1198025^2 \\ 99801975^2 + 8900000^2 &:= 100198025^2 \\ 9999801975^2 + 89000000^2 &:= 10000198025^2 \\ 999999801975^2 + 890000000^2 &:= 1000000198025^2 \end{aligned}$$

446)

$$\begin{aligned} 801084^2 + 892000^2 &:= 1198916^2 \\ 99801084^2 + 8920000^2 &:= 100198916^2 \\ 9999801084^2 + 89200000^2 &:= 10000198916^2 \\ 999999801084^2 + 892000000^2 &:= 1000000198916^2 \end{aligned}$$

447)

$$\begin{aligned} 800191^2 + 894000^2 &:= 1199809^2 \\ 99800191^2 + 8940000^2 &:= 100199809^2 \\ 9999800191^2 + 89400000^2 &:= 10000199809^2 \\ 999999800191^2 + 894000000^2 &:= 1000000199809^2 \end{aligned}$$

448)

$$\begin{aligned} 799296^2 + 896000^2 &:= 1200704^2 \\ 99799296^2 + 8960000^2 &:= 100200704^2 \\ 9999799296^2 + 89600000^2 &:= 10000200704^2 \\ 999999799296^2 + 896000000^2 &:= 1000000200704^2 \end{aligned}$$

449)

$$\begin{aligned} 798399^2 + 898000^2 &:= 1201601^2 \\ 99798399^2 + 8980000^2 &:= 100201601^2 \\ 9999798399^2 + 89800000^2 &:= 10000201601^2 \\ 999999798399^2 + 898000000^2 &:= 1000000201601^2 \end{aligned}$$

450)

$$\begin{aligned} 797500^2 + 900000^2 &:= 1202500^2 \\ 99797500^2 + 9000000^2 &:= 100202500^2 \\ 9999797500^2 + 90000000^2 &:= 10000202500^2 \\ 999999797500^2 + 900000000^2 &:= 1000000202500^2 \end{aligned}$$

451)

$$\begin{aligned} 796599^2 + 902000^2 &:= 1203401^2 \\ 99796599^2 + 9020000^2 &:= 100203401^2 \\ 9999796599^2 + 90200000^2 &:= 10000203401^2 \\ 999999796599^2 + 902000000^2 &:= 1000000203401^2 \end{aligned}$$

452)

$$\begin{aligned} 795696^2 + 904000^2 &:= 1204304^2 \\ 99795696^2 + 9040000^2 &:= 100204304^2 \\ 9999795696^2 + 90400000^2 &:= 10000204304^2 \\ 999999795696^2 + 904000000^2 &:= 1000000204304^2 \end{aligned}$$

453)

$$\begin{aligned} 794791^2 + 906000^2 &:= 1205209^2 \\ 99794791^2 + 9060000^2 &:= 100205209^2 \\ 9999794791^2 + 90600000^2 &:= 10000205209^2 \\ 999999794791^2 + 906000000^2 &:= 1000000205209^2 \end{aligned}$$

454)

$$\begin{aligned} 793884^2 + 908000^2 &:= 1206116^2 \\ 99793884^2 + 9080000^2 &:= 100206116^2 \\ 9999793884^2 + 90800000^2 &:= 10000206116^2 \\ 999999793884^2 + 908000000^2 &:= 1000000206116^2 \end{aligned}$$

455)

$$\begin{aligned} 792975^2 + 910000^2 &:= 1207025^2 \\ 99792975^2 + 9100000^2 &:= 100207025^2 \\ 9999792975^2 + 91000000^2 &:= 10000207025^2 \\ 999999792975^2 + 910000000^2 &:= 1000000207025^2 \end{aligned}$$

456)

$$\begin{aligned} 792064^2 + 912000^2 &:= 1207936^2 \\ 99792064^2 + 9120000^2 &:= 100207936^2 \\ 9999792064^2 + 91200000^2 &:= 10000207936^2 \\ 999999792064^2 + 912000000^2 &:= 1000000207936^2 \end{aligned}$$

457)

$$\begin{aligned} 791151^2 + 914000^2 &:= 1208849^2 \\ 99791151^2 + 9140000^2 &:= 100208849^2 \\ 9999791151^2 + 91400000^2 &:= 10000208849^2 \\ 999999791151^2 + 914000000^2 &:= 1000000208849^2 \end{aligned}$$

458)

$$\begin{aligned} 790236^2 + 916000^2 &:= 1209764^2 \\ 99790236^2 + 9160000^2 &:= 100209764^2 \\ 9999790236^2 + 91600000^2 &:= 10000209764^2 \\ 999999790236^2 + 916000000^2 &:= 1000000209764^2 \end{aligned}$$

459)

$$\begin{aligned} 789319^2 + 918000^2 &:= 1210681^2 \\ 99789319^2 + 9180000^2 &:= 100210681^2 \\ 9999789319^2 + 91800000^2 &:= 10000210681^2 \\ 999999789319^2 + 918000000^2 &:= 1000000210681^2 \end{aligned}$$

460)

$$\begin{aligned}788400^2 + 920000^2 &:= 1211600^2 \\99788400^2 + 9200000^2 &:= 100211600^2 \\9999788400^2 + 92000000^2 &:= 10000211600^2 \\999999788400^2 + 920000000^2 &:= 1000000211600^2\end{aligned}$$

461)

$$\begin{aligned}787479^2 + 922000^2 &:= 1212521^2 \\99787479^2 + 9220000^2 &:= 100212521^2 \\9999787479^2 + 92200000^2 &:= 10000212521^2 \\999999787479^2 + 922000000^2 &:= 1000000212521^2\end{aligned}$$

462)

$$\begin{aligned}786556^2 + 924000^2 &:= 1213444^2 \\99786556^2 + 9240000^2 &:= 100213444^2 \\9999786556^2 + 92400000^2 &:= 10000213444^2 \\999999786556^2 + 924000000^2 &:= 1000000213444^2\end{aligned}$$

463)

$$\begin{aligned}785631^2 + 926000^2 &:= 1214369^2 \\99785631^2 + 9260000^2 &:= 100214369^2 \\9999785631^2 + 92600000^2 &:= 10000214369^2 \\999999785631^2 + 926000000^2 &:= 1000000214369^2\end{aligned}$$

464)

$$\begin{aligned}784704^2 + 928000^2 &:= 1215296^2 \\99784704^2 + 9280000^2 &:= 100215296^2 \\9999784704^2 + 92800000^2 &:= 10000215296^2 \\999999784704^2 + 928000000^2 &:= 1000000215296^2\end{aligned}$$

465)

$$\begin{aligned}783775^2 + 930000^2 &:= 1216225^2 \\99783775^2 + 9300000^2 &:= 100216225^2 \\9999783775^2 + 93000000^2 &:= 10000216225^2 \\999999783775^2 + 930000000^2 &:= 1000000216225^2\end{aligned}$$

466)

$$\begin{aligned}782844^2 + 932000^2 &:= 1217156^2 \\99782844^2 + 9320000^2 &:= 100217156^2 \\9999782844^2 + 93200000^2 &:= 10000217156^2 \\999999782844^2 + 932000000^2 &:= 1000000217156^2\end{aligned}$$

467)

$$\begin{aligned}781911^2 + 934000^2 &:= 1218089^2 \\99781911^2 + 9340000^2 &:= 100218089^2 \\9999781911^2 + 93400000^2 &:= 10000218089^2 \\999999781911^2 + 934000000^2 &:= 1000000218089^2\end{aligned}$$

468)

$$\begin{aligned}780976^2 + 936000^2 &:= 1219024^2 \\99780976^2 + 9360000^2 &:= 100219024^2 \\9999780976^2 + 93600000^2 &:= 10000219024^2 \\999999780976^2 + 936000000^2 &:= 1000000219024^2\end{aligned}$$

469)

$$\begin{aligned}780039^2 + 938000^2 &:= 1219961^2 \\99780039^2 + 9380000^2 &:= 100219961^2 \\9999780039^2 + 93800000^2 &:= 10000219961^2 \\999999780039^2 + 938000000^2 &:= 1000000219961^2\end{aligned}$$

470)

$$\begin{aligned}779100^2 + 940000^2 &:= 1220900^2 \\99779100^2 + 9400000^2 &:= 100220900^2 \\9999779100^2 + 94000000^2 &:= 10000220900^2 \\999999779100^2 + 940000000^2 &:= 1000000220900^2\end{aligned}$$

471)

$$\begin{aligned}778159^2 + 942000^2 &:= 1221841^2 \\99778159^2 + 9420000^2 &:= 100221841^2 \\9999778159^2 + 94200000^2 &:= 10000221841^2 \\999999778159^2 + 942000000^2 &:= 1000000221841^2\end{aligned}$$

472)

$$\begin{aligned}777216^2 + 944000^2 &:= 1222784^2 \\99777216^2 + 9440000^2 &:= 100222784^2 \\9999777216^2 + 94400000^2 &:= 10000222784^2 \\999999777216^2 + 944000000^2 &:= 1000000222784^2\end{aligned}$$

- 473) $776271^2 + 946000^2 := 1223729^2$
 $99776271^2 + 9460000^2 := 100223729^2$
 $9999776271^2 + 94600000^2 := 10000223729^2$
 $999999776271^2 + 946000000^2 := 1000000223729^2$
- 474) $775324^2 + 948000^2 := 1224676^2$
 $99775324^2 + 9480000^2 := 100224676^2$
 $9999775324^2 + 94800000^2 := 10000224676^2$
 $999999775324^2 + 948000000^2 := 1000000224676^2$
- 475) $774375^2 + 950000^2 := 1225625^2$
 $99774375^2 + 9500000^2 := 100225625^2$
 $9999774375^2 + 95000000^2 := 10000225625^2$
 $999999774375^2 + 950000000^2 := 1000000225625^2$
- 476) $773424^2 + 952000^2 := 1226576^2$
 $99773424^2 + 9520000^2 := 100226576^2$
 $9999773424^2 + 95200000^2 := 10000226576^2$
 $999999773424^2 + 952000000^2 := 1000000226576^2$
- 477) $772471^2 + 954000^2 := 1227529^2$
 $99772471^2 + 9540000^2 := 100227529^2$
 $9999772471^2 + 95400000^2 := 10000227529^2$
 $999999772471^2 + 954000000^2 := 1000000227529^2$
- 478) $771516^2 + 956000^2 := 1228484^2$
 $99771516^2 + 9560000^2 := 100228484^2$
 $9999771516^2 + 95600000^2 := 10000228484^2$
 $999999771516^2 + 956000000^2 := 1000000228484^2$
- 479) $770559^2 + 958000^2 := 1229441^2$
 $99770559^2 + 9580000^2 := 100229441^2$
 $9999770559^2 + 95800000^2 := 10000229441^2$
 $999999770559^2 + 958000000^2 := 1000000229441^2$
- 480) $769600^2 + 960000^2 := 1230400^2$
 $99769600^2 + 9600000^2 := 100230400^2$
 $9999769600^2 + 96000000^2 := 10000230400^2$
 $999999769600^2 + 960000000^2 := 1000000230400^2$
- 481) $768639^2 + 962000^2 := 1231361^2$
 $99768639^2 + 9620000^2 := 100231361^2$
 $9999768639^2 + 96200000^2 := 10000231361^2$
 $999999768639^2 + 962000000^2 := 1000000231361^2$
- 482) $767676^2 + 964000^2 := 1232324^2$
 $99767676^2 + 9640000^2 := 100232324^2$
 $9999767676^2 + 96400000^2 := 10000232324^2$
 $999999767676^2 + 964000000^2 := 1000000232324^2$
- 483) $766711^2 + 966000^2 := 1233289^2$
 $99766711^2 + 9660000^2 := 100233289^2$
 $9999766711^2 + 96600000^2 := 10000233289^2$
 $999999766711^2 + 966000000^2 := 1000000233289^2$
- 484) $765744^2 + 968000^2 := 1234256^2$
 $99765744^2 + 9680000^2 := 100234256^2$
 $9999765744^2 + 96800000^2 := 10000234256^2$
 $999999765744^2 + 968000000^2 := 1000000234256^2$
- 485) $764775^2 + 970000^2 := 1235225^2$
 $99764775^2 + 9700000^2 := 100235225^2$
 $9999764775^2 + 97000000^2 := 10000235225^2$
 $999999764775^2 + 970000000^2 := 1000000235225^2$

486)

$$763804^2 + 972000^2 := 1236196^2$$

$$99763804^2 + 9720000^2 := 100236196^2$$

$$9999763804^2 + 97200000^2 := 10000236196^2$$

$$999999763804^2 + 972000000^2 := 1000000236196^2$$

487)

$$762831^2 + 974000^2 := 1237169^2$$

$$99762831^2 + 9740000^2 := 100237169^2$$

$$9999762831^2 + 97400000^2 := 10000237169^2$$

$$999999762831^2 + 974000000^2 := 1000000237169^2$$

488)

$$761856^2 + 976000^2 := 1238144^2$$

$$99761856^2 + 9760000^2 := 100238144^2$$

$$9999761856^2 + 97600000^2 := 10000238144^2$$

$$999999761856^2 + 976000000^2 := 1000000238144^2$$

489)

$$760879^2 + 978000^2 := 1239121^2$$

$$99760879^2 + 9780000^2 := 100239121^2$$

$$9999760879^2 + 97800000^2 := 10000239121^2$$

$$999999760879^2 + 978000000^2 := 1000000239121^2$$

490)

$$759900^2 + 980000^2 := 1240100^2$$

$$99759900^2 + 9800000^2 := 100240100^2$$

$$9999759900^2 + 98000000^2 := 10000240100^2$$

$$999999759900^2 + 980000000^2 := 1000000240100^2$$

491)

$$758919^2 + 982000^2 := 1241081^2$$

$$99758919^2 + 9820000^2 := 100241081^2$$

$$9999758919^2 + 98200000^2 := 10000241081^2$$

$$999999758919^2 + 982000000^2 := 1000000241081^2$$

492)

$$757936^2 + 984000^2 := 1242064^2$$

$$99757936^2 + 9840000^2 := 100242064^2$$

$$9999757936^2 + 98400000^2 := 10000242064^2$$

$$999999757936^2 + 984000000^2 := 1000000242064^2$$

493)

$$756951^2 + 986000^2 := 1243049^2$$

$$99756951^2 + 9860000^2 := 100243049^2$$

$$9999756951^2 + 98600000^2 := 10000243049^2$$

$$999999756951^2 + 986000000^2 := 1000000243049^2$$

494)

$$755964^2 + 988000^2 := 1244036^2$$

$$99755964^2 + 9880000^2 := 100244036^2$$

$$9999755964^2 + 98800000^2 := 10000244036^2$$

$$999999755964^2 + 988000000^2 := 1000000244036^2$$

495)

$$754975^2 + 990000^2 := 1245025^2$$

$$99754975^2 + 9900000^2 := 100245025^2$$

$$9999754975^2 + 99000000^2 := 10000245025^2$$

$$999999754975^2 + 990000000^2 := 1000000245025^2$$

496)

$$753984^2 + 992000^2 := 1246016^2$$

$$99753984^2 + 9920000^2 := 100246016^2$$

$$9999753984^2 + 99200000^2 := 10000246016^2$$

$$999999753984^2 + 992000000^2 := 1000000246016^2$$

497)

$$752991^2 + 994000^2 := 1247009^2$$

$$99752991^2 + 9940000^2 := 100247009^2$$

$$9999752991^2 + 99400000^2 := 10000247009^2$$

$$999999752991^2 + 994000000^2 := 1000000247009^2$$

498)

$$751996^2 + 996000^2 := 1248004^2$$

$$99751996^2 + 9960000^2 := 100248004^2$$

$$9999751996^2 + 99600000^2 := 10000248004^2$$

$$999999751996^2 + 996000000^2 := 1000000248004^2$$

- 499) $750999^2 + 998000^2 := 1249001^2$
 $99750999^2 + 9980000^2 := 100249001^2$
 $9999750999^2 + 99800000^2 := 10000249001^2$
 $999999750999^2 + 998000000^2 := 1000000249001^2$
- 500) $750000^2 + 1000000^2 := 1250000^2$
 $99750000^2 + 10000000^2 := 100250000^2$
 $9999750000^2 + 100000000^2 := 10000250000^2$
 $999999750000^2 + 1000000000^2 := 1000000250000^2$
- 501) $748999^2 + 1002000^2 := 1251001^2$
 $99748999^2 + 10020000^2 := 100251001^2$
 $9999748999^2 + 100200000^2 := 10000251001^2$
 $999999748999^2 + 1002000000^2 := 1000000251001^2$
- 502) $747996^2 + 1004000^2 := 1252004^2$
 $99747996^2 + 10040000^2 := 100252004^2$
 $9999747996^2 + 100400000^2 := 10000252004^2$
 $999999747996^2 + 1004000000^2 := 1000000252004^2$
- 503) $746991^2 + 1006000^2 := 1253009^2$
 $99746991^2 + 10060000^2 := 100253009^2$
 $9999746991^2 + 100600000^2 := 10000253009^2$
 $999999746991^2 + 1006000000^2 := 1000000253009^2$
- 504) $745984^2 + 1008000^2 := 1254016^2$
 $99745984^2 + 10080000^2 := 100254016^2$
 $9999745984^2 + 100800000^2 := 10000254016^2$
 $999999745984^2 + 1008000000^2 := 1000000254016^2$
- 505) $744975^2 + 1010000^2 := 1255025^2$
 $99744975^2 + 10100000^2 := 100255025^2$
 $9999744975^2 + 101000000^2 := 10000255025^2$
 $999999744975^2 + 1010000000^2 := 1000000255025^2$
- 506) $743964^2 + 1012000^2 := 1256036^2$
 $99743964^2 + 10120000^2 := 100256036^2$
 $9999743964^2 + 101200000^2 := 10000256036^2$
 $999999743964^2 + 1012000000^2 := 1000000256036^2$
- 507) $742951^2 + 1014000^2 := 1257049^2$
 $99742951^2 + 10140000^2 := 100257049^2$
 $9999742951^2 + 101400000^2 := 10000257049^2$
 $999999742951^2 + 1014000000^2 := 1000000257049^2$
- 508) $741936^2 + 1016000^2 := 1258064^2$
 $99741936^2 + 10160000^2 := 100258064^2$
 $9999741936^2 + 101600000^2 := 10000258064^2$
 $999999741936^2 + 1016000000^2 := 1000000258064^2$
- 509) $740919^2 + 1018000^2 := 1259081^2$
 $99740919^2 + 10180000^2 := 100259081^2$
 $9999740919^2 + 101800000^2 := 10000259081^2$
 $999999740919^2 + 1018000000^2 := 1000000259081^2$
- 510) $739900^2 + 1020000^2 := 1260100^2$
 $99739900^2 + 10200000^2 := 100260100^2$
 $9999739900^2 + 102000000^2 := 10000260100^2$
 $999999739900^2 + 1020000000^2 := 1000000260100^2$
- 511) $738879^2 + 1022000^2 := 1261121^2$
 $99738879^2 + 10220000^2 := 100261121^2$
 $9999738879^2 + 102200000^2 := 10000261121^2$
 $999999738879^2 + 1022000000^2 := 1000000261121^2$

- 512) $737856^2 + 1024000^2 := 1262144^2$
 $99737856^2 + 10240000^2 := 100262144^2$
 $9999737856^2 + 102400000^2 := 10000262144^2$
 $999999737856^2 + 1024000000^2 := 1000000262144^2$
- 513) $736831^2 + 1026000^2 := 1263169^2$
 $99736831^2 + 10260000^2 := 100263169^2$
 $9999736831^2 + 102600000^2 := 10000263169^2$
 $999999736831^2 + 1026000000^2 := 1000000263169^2$
- 514) $735804^2 + 1028000^2 := 1264196^2$
 $99735804^2 + 10280000^2 := 100264196^2$
 $9999735804^2 + 102800000^2 := 10000264196^2$
 $999999735804^2 + 1028000000^2 := 1000000264196^2$
- 515) $734775^2 + 1030000^2 := 1265225^2$
 $99734775^2 + 10300000^2 := 100265225^2$
 $9999734775^2 + 103000000^2 := 10000265225^2$
 $999999734775^2 + 1030000000^2 := 1000000265225^2$
- 516) $733744^2 + 1032000^2 := 1266256^2$
 $99733744^2 + 10320000^2 := 100266256^2$
 $9999733744^2 + 103200000^2 := 10000266256^2$
 $999999733744^2 + 1032000000^2 := 1000000266256^2$
- 517) $732711^2 + 1034000^2 := 1267289^2$
 $99732711^2 + 10340000^2 := 100267289^2$
 $9999732711^2 + 103400000^2 := 10000267289^2$
 $999999732711^2 + 1034000000^2 := 1000000267289^2$
- 518) $731676^2 + 1036000^2 := 1268324^2$
 $99731676^2 + 10360000^2 := 100268324^2$
 $9999731676^2 + 103600000^2 := 10000268324^2$
 $999999731676^2 + 1036000000^2 := 1000000268324^2$
- 519) $730639^2 + 1038000^2 := 1269361^2$
 $99730639^2 + 10380000^2 := 100269361^2$
 $9999730639^2 + 103800000^2 := 10000269361^2$
 $999999730639^2 + 1038000000^2 := 1000000269361^2$
- 520) $729600^2 + 1040000^2 := 1270400^2$
 $99729600^2 + 10400000^2 := 100270400^2$
 $9999729600^2 + 104000000^2 := 10000270400^2$
 $999999729600^2 + 1040000000^2 := 1000000270400^2$
- 521) $728559^2 + 1042000^2 := 1271441^2$
 $99728559^2 + 10420000^2 := 100271441^2$
 $9999728559^2 + 104200000^2 := 10000271441^2$
 $999999728559^2 + 1042000000^2 := 1000000271441^2$
- 522) $727516^2 + 1044000^2 := 1272484^2$
 $99727516^2 + 10440000^2 := 100272484^2$
 $9999727516^2 + 104400000^2 := 10000272484^2$
 $999999727516^2 + 1044000000^2 := 1000000272484^2$
- 523) $726471^2 + 1046000^2 := 1273529^2$
 $99726471^2 + 10460000^2 := 100273529^2$
 $9999726471^2 + 104600000^2 := 10000273529^2$
 $999999726471^2 + 1046000000^2 := 1000000273529^2$
- 524) $725424^2 + 1048000^2 := 1274576^2$
 $99725424^2 + 10480000^2 := 100274576^2$
 $9999725424^2 + 104800000^2 := 10000274576^2$
 $999999725424^2 + 1048000000^2 := 1000000274576^2$

- 525) $724375^2 + 1050000^2 := 1275625^2$
 $99724375^2 + 10500000^2 := 100275625^2$
 $9999724375^2 + 105000000^2 := 10000275625^2$
 $999999724375^2 + 1050000000^2 := 1000000275625^2$
- 526) $723324^2 + 1052000^2 := 1276676^2$
 $99723324^2 + 10520000^2 := 100276676^2$
 $9999723324^2 + 105200000^2 := 10000276676^2$
 $999999723324^2 + 1052000000^2 := 1000000276676^2$
- 527) $722271^2 + 1054000^2 := 1277729^2$
 $99722271^2 + 10540000^2 := 100277729^2$
 $9999722271^2 + 105400000^2 := 10000277729^2$
 $999999722271^2 + 1054000000^2 := 1000000277729^2$
- 528) $721216^2 + 1056000^2 := 1278784^2$
 $99721216^2 + 10560000^2 := 100278784^2$
 $9999721216^2 + 105600000^2 := 10000278784^2$
 $999999721216^2 + 1056000000^2 := 1000000278784^2$
- 529) $720159^2 + 1058000^2 := 1279841^2$
 $99720159^2 + 10580000^2 := 100279841^2$
 $9999720159^2 + 105800000^2 := 10000279841^2$
 $999999720159^2 + 1058000000^2 := 1000000279841^2$
- 530) $719100^2 + 1060000^2 := 1280900^2$
 $99719100^2 + 10600000^2 := 100280900^2$
 $9999719100^2 + 106000000^2 := 10000280900^2$
 $999999719100^2 + 1060000000^2 := 1000000280900^2$
- 531) $718039^2 + 1062000^2 := 1281961^2$
 $99718039^2 + 10620000^2 := 100281961^2$
 $9999718039^2 + 106200000^2 := 10000281961^2$
 $999999718039^2 + 1062000000^2 := 1000000281961^2$
- 532) $716976^2 + 1064000^2 := 1283024^2$
 $99716976^2 + 10640000^2 := 100283024^2$
 $9999716976^2 + 106400000^2 := 10000283024^2$
 $999999716976^2 + 1064000000^2 := 1000000283024^2$
- 533) $715911^2 + 1066000^2 := 1284089^2$
 $99715911^2 + 10660000^2 := 100284089^2$
 $9999715911^2 + 106600000^2 := 10000284089^2$
 $999999715911^2 + 1066000000^2 := 1000000284089^2$
- 534) $714844^2 + 1068000^2 := 1285156^2$
 $99714844^2 + 10680000^2 := 100285156^2$
 $9999714844^2 + 106800000^2 := 10000285156^2$
 $999999714844^2 + 1068000000^2 := 1000000285156^2$
- 535) $713775^2 + 1070000^2 := 1286225^2$
 $99713775^2 + 10700000^2 := 100286225^2$
 $9999713775^2 + 107000000^2 := 10000286225^2$
 $999999713775^2 + 1070000000^2 := 1000000286225^2$
- 536) $712704^2 + 1072000^2 := 1287296^2$
 $99712704^2 + 10720000^2 := 100287296^2$
 $9999712704^2 + 107200000^2 := 10000287296^2$
 $999999712704^2 + 1072000000^2 := 1000000287296^2$
- 537) $711631^2 + 1074000^2 := 1288369^2$
 $99711631^2 + 10740000^2 := 100288369^2$
 $9999711631^2 + 107400000^2 := 10000288369^2$
 $999999711631^2 + 1074000000^2 := 1000000288369^2$

538)

$$\begin{aligned} 710556^2 + 1076000^2 &:= 1289444^2 \\ 99710556^2 + 10760000^2 &:= 100289444^2 \\ 9999710556^2 + 107600000^2 &:= 10000289444^2 \\ 999999710556^2 + 1076000000^2 &:= 1000000289444^2 \end{aligned}$$

539)

$$\begin{aligned} 709479^2 + 1078000^2 &:= 1290521^2 \\ 99709479^2 + 10780000^2 &:= 100290521^2 \\ 9999709479^2 + 107800000^2 &:= 10000290521^2 \\ 999999709479^2 + 1078000000^2 &:= 1000000290521^2 \end{aligned}$$

540)

$$\begin{aligned} 708400^2 + 1080000^2 &:= 1291600^2 \\ 99708400^2 + 10800000^2 &:= 100291600^2 \\ 9999708400^2 + 108000000^2 &:= 10000291600^2 \\ 999999708400^2 + 1080000000^2 &:= 1000000291600^2 \end{aligned}$$

541)

$$\begin{aligned} 707319^2 + 1082000^2 &:= 1292681^2 \\ 99707319^2 + 10820000^2 &:= 100292681^2 \\ 9999707319^2 + 108200000^2 &:= 10000292681^2 \\ 999999707319^2 + 1082000000^2 &:= 1000000292681^2 \end{aligned}$$

542)

$$\begin{aligned} 706236^2 + 1084000^2 &:= 1293764^2 \\ 99706236^2 + 10840000^2 &:= 100293764^2 \\ 9999706236^2 + 108400000^2 &:= 10000293764^2 \\ 999999706236^2 + 1084000000^2 &:= 1000000293764^2 \end{aligned}$$

543)

$$\begin{aligned} 705151^2 + 1086000^2 &:= 1294849^2 \\ 99705151^2 + 10860000^2 &:= 100294849^2 \\ 9999705151^2 + 108600000^2 &:= 10000294849^2 \\ 999999705151^2 + 1086000000^2 &:= 1000000294849^2 \end{aligned}$$

544)

$$\begin{aligned} 704064^2 + 1088000^2 &:= 1295936^2 \\ 99704064^2 + 10880000^2 &:= 100295936^2 \\ 9999704064^2 + 108800000^2 &:= 10000295936^2 \\ 999999704064^2 + 1088000000^2 &:= 1000000295936^2 \end{aligned}$$

545)

$$\begin{aligned} 702975^2 + 1090000^2 &:= 1297025^2 \\ 99702975^2 + 10900000^2 &:= 100297025^2 \\ 9999702975^2 + 109000000^2 &:= 10000297025^2 \\ 999999702975^2 + 1090000000^2 &:= 1000000297025^2 \end{aligned}$$

546)

$$\begin{aligned} 701884^2 + 1092000^2 &:= 1298116^2 \\ 99701884^2 + 10920000^2 &:= 100298116^2 \\ 9999701884^2 + 109200000^2 &:= 10000298116^2 \\ 999999701884^2 + 1092000000^2 &:= 1000000298116^2 \end{aligned}$$

547)

$$\begin{aligned} 700791^2 + 1094000^2 &:= 1299209^2 \\ 99700791^2 + 10940000^2 &:= 100299209^2 \\ 9999700791^2 + 109400000^2 &:= 10000299209^2 \\ 999999700791^2 + 1094000000^2 &:= 1000000299209^2 \end{aligned}$$

548)

$$\begin{aligned} 699696^2 + 1096000^2 &:= 1300304^2 \\ 99699696^2 + 10960000^2 &:= 100300304^2 \\ 9999699696^2 + 109600000^2 &:= 10000300304^2 \\ 999999699696^2 + 1096000000^2 &:= 1000000300304^2 \end{aligned}$$

549)

$$\begin{aligned} 698599^2 + 1098000^2 &:= 1301401^2 \\ 99698599^2 + 10980000^2 &:= 100301401^2 \\ 9999698599^2 + 109800000^2 &:= 10000301401^2 \\ 999999698599^2 + 1098000000^2 &:= 1000000301401^2 \end{aligned}$$

550)

$$\begin{aligned} 697500^2 + 1100000^2 &:= 1302500^2 \\ 99697500^2 + 11000000^2 &:= 100302500^2 \\ 9999697500^2 + 110000000^2 &:= 10000302500^2 \\ 999999697500^2 + 1100000000^2 &:= 1000000302500^2 \end{aligned}$$

551)

$$\begin{aligned}696399^2 + 1102000^2 &:= 1303601^2 \\99696399^2 + 11020000^2 &:= 100303601^2 \\9999696399^2 + 110200000^2 &:= 10000303601^2 \\999999696399^2 + 1102000000^2 &:= 1000000303601^2\end{aligned}$$

552)

$$\begin{aligned}695296^2 + 1104000^2 &:= 1304704^2 \\99695296^2 + 11040000^2 &:= 100304704^2 \\9999695296^2 + 110400000^2 &:= 10000304704^2 \\999999695296^2 + 1104000000^2 &:= 1000000304704^2\end{aligned}$$

553)

$$\begin{aligned}694191^2 + 1106000^2 &:= 1305809^2 \\99694191^2 + 11060000^2 &:= 100305809^2 \\9999694191^2 + 110600000^2 &:= 10000305809^2 \\999999694191^2 + 1106000000^2 &:= 1000000305809^2\end{aligned}$$

554)

$$\begin{aligned}693084^2 + 1108000^2 &:= 1306916^2 \\99693084^2 + 11080000^2 &:= 100306916^2 \\9999693084^2 + 110800000^2 &:= 10000306916^2 \\999999693084^2 + 1108000000^2 &:= 1000000306916^2\end{aligned}$$

555)

$$\begin{aligned}691975^2 + 1110000^2 &:= 1308025^2 \\99691975^2 + 11100000^2 &:= 100308025^2 \\9999691975^2 + 111000000^2 &:= 10000308025^2 \\999999691975^2 + 1110000000^2 &:= 1000000308025^2\end{aligned}$$

556)

$$\begin{aligned}690864^2 + 1112000^2 &:= 1309136^2 \\99690864^2 + 11120000^2 &:= 100309136^2 \\9999690864^2 + 111200000^2 &:= 10000309136^2 \\999999690864^2 + 1112000000^2 &:= 1000000309136^2\end{aligned}$$

557)

$$\begin{aligned}689751^2 + 1114000^2 &:= 1310249^2 \\99689751^2 + 11140000^2 &:= 100310249^2 \\9999689751^2 + 111400000^2 &:= 10000310249^2 \\999999689751^2 + 1114000000^2 &:= 1000000310249^2\end{aligned}$$

558)

$$\begin{aligned}688636^2 + 1116000^2 &:= 1311364^2 \\99688636^2 + 11160000^2 &:= 100311364^2 \\9999688636^2 + 111600000^2 &:= 10000311364^2 \\999999688636^2 + 1116000000^2 &:= 1000000311364^2\end{aligned}$$

559)

$$\begin{aligned}687519^2 + 1118000^2 &:= 1312481^2 \\99687519^2 + 11180000^2 &:= 100312481^2 \\9999687519^2 + 111800000^2 &:= 10000312481^2 \\999999687519^2 + 1118000000^2 &:= 1000000312481^2\end{aligned}$$

560)

$$\begin{aligned}686400^2 + 1120000^2 &:= 1313600^2 \\99686400^2 + 11200000^2 &:= 100313600^2 \\9999686400^2 + 112000000^2 &:= 10000313600^2 \\999999686400^2 + 1120000000^2 &:= 1000000313600^2\end{aligned}$$

561)

$$\begin{aligned}685279^2 + 1122000^2 &:= 1314721^2 \\99685279^2 + 11220000^2 &:= 100314721^2 \\9999685279^2 + 112200000^2 &:= 10000314721^2 \\999999685279^2 + 1122000000^2 &:= 1000000314721^2\end{aligned}$$

562)

$$\begin{aligned}684156^2 + 1124000^2 &:= 1315844^2 \\99684156^2 + 11240000^2 &:= 100315844^2 \\9999684156^2 + 112400000^2 &:= 10000315844^2 \\999999684156^2 + 1124000000^2 &:= 1000000315844^2\end{aligned}$$

563)

$$\begin{aligned}683031^2 + 1126000^2 &:= 1316969^2 \\99683031^2 + 11260000^2 &:= 100316969^2 \\9999683031^2 + 112600000^2 &:= 10000316969^2 \\999999683031^2 + 1126000000^2 &:= 1000000316969^2\end{aligned}$$

564)

$$\begin{aligned}681904^2 + 1128000^2 &:= 1318096^2 \\99681904^2 + 11280000^2 &:= 100318096^2 \\9999681904^2 + 112800000^2 &:= 10000318096^2 \\999999681904^2 + 1128000000^2 &:= 1000000318096^2\end{aligned}$$

565)

$$\begin{aligned}680775^2 + 1130000^2 &:= 1319225^2 \\99680775^2 + 11300000^2 &:= 100319225^2 \\9999680775^2 + 113000000^2 &:= 10000319225^2 \\999999680775^2 + 1130000000^2 &:= 1000000319225^2\end{aligned}$$

566)

$$\begin{aligned}679644^2 + 1132000^2 &:= 1320356^2 \\99679644^2 + 11320000^2 &:= 100320356^2 \\9999679644^2 + 113200000^2 &:= 10000320356^2 \\999999679644^2 + 1132000000^2 &:= 1000000320356^2\end{aligned}$$

567)

$$\begin{aligned}678511^2 + 1134000^2 &:= 1321489^2 \\99678511^2 + 11340000^2 &:= 100321489^2 \\9999678511^2 + 113400000^2 &:= 10000321489^2 \\999999678511^2 + 1134000000^2 &:= 1000000321489^2\end{aligned}$$

568)

$$\begin{aligned}677376^2 + 1136000^2 &:= 1322624^2 \\99677376^2 + 11360000^2 &:= 100322624^2 \\9999677376^2 + 113600000^2 &:= 10000322624^2 \\999999677376^2 + 1136000000^2 &:= 1000000322624^2\end{aligned}$$

569)

$$\begin{aligned}676239^2 + 1138000^2 &:= 1323761^2 \\99676239^2 + 11380000^2 &:= 100323761^2 \\9999676239^2 + 113800000^2 &:= 10000323761^2 \\999999676239^2 + 1138000000^2 &:= 1000000323761^2\end{aligned}$$

570)

$$\begin{aligned}675100^2 + 1140000^2 &:= 1324900^2 \\99675100^2 + 11400000^2 &:= 100324900^2 \\9999675100^2 + 114000000^2 &:= 10000324900^2 \\999999675100^2 + 1140000000^2 &:= 1000000324900^2\end{aligned}$$

571)

$$\begin{aligned}673959^2 + 1142000^2 &:= 1326041^2 \\99673959^2 + 11420000^2 &:= 100326041^2 \\9999673959^2 + 114200000^2 &:= 10000326041^2 \\999999673959^2 + 1142000000^2 &:= 1000000326041^2\end{aligned}$$

572)

$$\begin{aligned}672816^2 + 1144000^2 &:= 1327184^2 \\99672816^2 + 11440000^2 &:= 100327184^2 \\9999672816^2 + 114400000^2 &:= 10000327184^2 \\999999672816^2 + 1144000000^2 &:= 1000000327184^2\end{aligned}$$

573)

$$\begin{aligned}671671^2 + 1146000^2 &:= 1328329^2 \\99671671^2 + 11460000^2 &:= 100328329^2 \\9999671671^2 + 114600000^2 &:= 10000328329^2 \\999999671671^2 + 1146000000^2 &:= 1000000328329^2\end{aligned}$$

574)

$$\begin{aligned}670524^2 + 1148000^2 &:= 1329476^2 \\99670524^2 + 11480000^2 &:= 100329476^2 \\9999670524^2 + 114800000^2 &:= 10000329476^2 \\999999670524^2 + 1148000000^2 &:= 1000000329476^2\end{aligned}$$

575)

$$\begin{aligned}669375^2 + 1150000^2 &:= 1330625^2 \\99669375^2 + 11500000^2 &:= 100330625^2 \\9999669375^2 + 115000000^2 &:= 10000330625^2 \\999999669375^2 + 1150000000^2 &:= 1000000330625^2\end{aligned}$$

576)

$$\begin{aligned}668224^2 + 1152000^2 &:= 1331776^2 \\99668224^2 + 11520000^2 &:= 100331776^2 \\9999668224^2 + 115200000^2 &:= 10000331776^2 \\999999668224^2 + 1152000000^2 &:= 1000000331776^2\end{aligned}$$

577)

$$\begin{aligned}667071^2 + 1154000^2 &:= 1332929^2 \\99667071^2 + 11540000^2 &:= 100332929^2 \\9999667071^2 + 115400000^2 &:= 10000332929^2 \\999999667071^2 + 1154000000^2 &:= 1000000332929^2\end{aligned}$$

578)

$$\begin{aligned}665916^2 + 1156000^2 &:= 1334084^2 \\99665916^2 + 11560000^2 &:= 100334084^2 \\9999665916^2 + 115600000^2 &:= 10000334084^2 \\999999665916^2 + 1156000000^2 &:= 1000000334084^2\end{aligned}$$

579)

$$\begin{aligned}664759^2 + 1158000^2 &:= 1335241^2 \\99664759^2 + 11580000^2 &:= 100335241^2 \\9999664759^2 + 115800000^2 &:= 10000335241^2 \\999999664759^2 + 1158000000^2 &:= 1000000335241^2\end{aligned}$$

580)

$$\begin{aligned}663600^2 + 1160000^2 &:= 1336400^2 \\99663600^2 + 11600000^2 &:= 100336400^2 \\9999663600^2 + 116000000^2 &:= 10000336400^2 \\999999663600^2 + 1160000000^2 &:= 1000000336400^2\end{aligned}$$

581)

$$\begin{aligned}662439^2 + 1162000^2 &:= 1337561^2 \\99662439^2 + 11620000^2 &:= 100337561^2 \\9999662439^2 + 116200000^2 &:= 10000337561^2 \\999999662439^2 + 1162000000^2 &:= 1000000337561^2\end{aligned}$$

582)

$$\begin{aligned}661276^2 + 1164000^2 &:= 1338724^2 \\99661276^2 + 11640000^2 &:= 100338724^2 \\9999661276^2 + 116400000^2 &:= 10000338724^2 \\999999661276^2 + 1164000000^2 &:= 1000000338724^2\end{aligned}$$

583)

$$\begin{aligned}660111^2 + 1166000^2 &:= 1339889^2 \\99660111^2 + 11660000^2 &:= 100339889^2 \\9999660111^2 + 116600000^2 &:= 10000339889^2 \\999999660111^2 + 1166000000^2 &:= 1000000339889^2\end{aligned}$$

584)

$$\begin{aligned}658944^2 + 1168000^2 &:= 1341056^2 \\99658944^2 + 11680000^2 &:= 100341056^2 \\9999658944^2 + 116800000^2 &:= 10000341056^2 \\999999658944^2 + 1168000000^2 &:= 1000000341056^2\end{aligned}$$

585)

$$\begin{aligned}657775^2 + 1170000^2 &:= 1342225^2 \\99657775^2 + 11700000^2 &:= 100342225^2 \\9999657775^2 + 117000000^2 &:= 10000342225^2 \\999999657775^2 + 1170000000^2 &:= 1000000342225^2\end{aligned}$$

586)

$$\begin{aligned}656604^2 + 1172000^2 &:= 1343396^2 \\99656604^2 + 11720000^2 &:= 100343396^2 \\9999656604^2 + 117200000^2 &:= 10000343396^2 \\999999656604^2 + 1172000000^2 &:= 1000000343396^2\end{aligned}$$

587)

$$\begin{aligned}655431^2 + 1174000^2 &:= 1344569^2 \\99655431^2 + 11740000^2 &:= 100344569^2 \\9999655431^2 + 117400000^2 &:= 10000344569^2 \\999999655431^2 + 1174000000^2 &:= 1000000344569^2\end{aligned}$$

588)

$$\begin{aligned}654256^2 + 1176000^2 &:= 1345744^2 \\99654256^2 + 11760000^2 &:= 100345744^2 \\9999654256^2 + 117600000^2 &:= 10000345744^2 \\999999654256^2 + 1176000000^2 &:= 1000000345744^2\end{aligned}$$

589)

$$\begin{aligned}653079^2 + 1178000^2 &:= 1346921^2 \\99653079^2 + 11780000^2 &:= 100346921^2 \\9999653079^2 + 117800000^2 &:= 10000346921^2 \\999999653079^2 + 1178000000^2 &:= 1000000346921^2\end{aligned}$$

- 590) $651900^2 + 1180000^2 := 1348100^2$
 $99651900^2 + 11800000^2 := 100348100^2$
 $9999651900^2 + 118000000^2 := 10000348100^2$
 $999999651900^2 + 1180000000^2 := 1000000348100^2$
- 591) $650719^2 + 1182000^2 := 1349281^2$
 $99650719^2 + 11820000^2 := 100349281^2$
 $9999650719^2 + 118200000^2 := 10000349281^2$
 $999999650719^2 + 1182000000^2 := 1000000349281^2$
- 592) $649536^2 + 1184000^2 := 1350464^2$
 $99649536^2 + 11840000^2 := 100350464^2$
 $9999649536^2 + 118400000^2 := 10000350464^2$
 $999999649536^2 + 1184000000^2 := 1000000350464^2$
- 593) $648351^2 + 1186000^2 := 1351649^2$
 $99648351^2 + 11860000^2 := 100351649^2$
 $9999648351^2 + 118600000^2 := 10000351649^2$
 $999999648351^2 + 1186000000^2 := 1000000351649^2$
- 594) $647164^2 + 1188000^2 := 1352836^2$
 $99647164^2 + 11880000^2 := 100352836^2$
 $9999647164^2 + 118800000^2 := 10000352836^2$
 $999999647164^2 + 1188000000^2 := 1000000352836^2$
- 595) $645975^2 + 1190000^2 := 1354025^2$
 $99645975^2 + 11900000^2 := 100354025^2$
 $9999645975^2 + 119000000^2 := 10000354025^2$
 $999999645975^2 + 1190000000^2 := 1000000354025^2$
- 596) $644784^2 + 1192000^2 := 1355216^2$
 $99644784^2 + 11920000^2 := 100355216^2$
 $9999644784^2 + 119200000^2 := 10000355216^2$
 $999999644784^2 + 1192000000^2 := 1000000355216^2$
- 597) $643591^2 + 1194000^2 := 1356409^2$
 $99643591^2 + 11940000^2 := 100356409^2$
 $9999643591^2 + 119400000^2 := 10000356409^2$
 $999999643591^2 + 1194000000^2 := 1000000356409^2$
- 598) $642396^2 + 1196000^2 := 1357604^2$
 $99642396^2 + 11960000^2 := 100357604^2$
 $9999642396^2 + 119600000^2 := 10000357604^2$
 $999999642396^2 + 1196000000^2 := 1000000357604^2$
- 599) $641199^2 + 1198000^2 := 1358801^2$
 $99641199^2 + 11980000^2 := 100358801^2$
 $9999641199^2 + 119800000^2 := 10000358801^2$
 $999999641199^2 + 1198000000^2 := 1000000358801^2$
- 600) $640000^2 + 1200000^2 := 1360000^2$
 $99640000^2 + 12000000^2 := 100360000^2$
 $9999640000^2 + 120000000^2 := 10000360000^2$
 $999999640000^2 + 1200000000^2 := 1000000360000^2$
- 601) $638799^2 + 1202000^2 := 1361201^2$
 $99638799^2 + 12020000^2 := 100361201^2$
 $9999638799^2 + 120200000^2 := 10000361201^2$
 $999999638799^2 + 1202000000^2 := 1000000361201^2$
- 602) $637596^2 + 1204000^2 := 1362404^2$
 $99637596^2 + 12040000^2 := 100362404^2$
 $9999637596^2 + 120400000^2 := 10000362404^2$
 $999999637596^2 + 1204000000^2 := 1000000362404^2$

603)

$$\begin{aligned}636391^2 + 1206000^2 &:= 1363609^2 \\99636391^2 + 12060000^2 &:= 100363609^2 \\9999636391^2 + 120600000^2 &:= 10000363609^2 \\999999636391^2 + 1206000000^2 &:= 1000000363609^2\end{aligned}$$

604)

$$\begin{aligned}635184^2 + 1208000^2 &:= 1364816^2 \\99635184^2 + 12080000^2 &:= 100364816^2 \\9999635184^2 + 120800000^2 &:= 10000364816^2 \\999999635184^2 + 1208000000^2 &:= 1000000364816^2\end{aligned}$$

605)

$$\begin{aligned}633975^2 + 1210000^2 &:= 1366025^2 \\99633975^2 + 12100000^2 &:= 100366025^2 \\9999633975^2 + 121000000^2 &:= 10000366025^2 \\999999633975^2 + 1210000000^2 &:= 1000000366025^2\end{aligned}$$

606)

$$\begin{aligned}632764^2 + 1212000^2 &:= 1367236^2 \\99632764^2 + 12120000^2 &:= 100367236^2 \\9999632764^2 + 121200000^2 &:= 10000367236^2 \\999999632764^2 + 1212000000^2 &:= 1000000367236^2\end{aligned}$$

607)

$$\begin{aligned}631551^2 + 1214000^2 &:= 1368449^2 \\99631551^2 + 12140000^2 &:= 100368449^2 \\9999631551^2 + 121400000^2 &:= 10000368449^2 \\999999631551^2 + 1214000000^2 &:= 1000000368449^2\end{aligned}$$

608)

$$\begin{aligned}630336^2 + 1216000^2 &:= 1369664^2 \\99630336^2 + 12160000^2 &:= 100369664^2 \\9999630336^2 + 121600000^2 &:= 10000369664^2 \\999999630336^2 + 1216000000^2 &:= 1000000369664^2\end{aligned}$$

609)

$$\begin{aligned}629119^2 + 1218000^2 &:= 1370881^2 \\99629119^2 + 12180000^2 &:= 100370881^2 \\9999629119^2 + 121800000^2 &:= 10000370881^2 \\999999629119^2 + 1218000000^2 &:= 1000000370881^2\end{aligned}$$

610)

$$\begin{aligned}627900^2 + 1220000^2 &:= 1372100^2 \\99627900^2 + 12200000^2 &:= 100372100^2 \\9999627900^2 + 122000000^2 &:= 10000372100^2 \\999999627900^2 + 1220000000^2 &:= 1000000372100^2\end{aligned}$$

611)

$$\begin{aligned}626679^2 + 1222000^2 &:= 1373321^2 \\99626679^2 + 12220000^2 &:= 100373321^2 \\9999626679^2 + 122200000^2 &:= 10000373321^2 \\999999626679^2 + 1222000000^2 &:= 1000000373321^2\end{aligned}$$

612)

$$\begin{aligned}625456^2 + 1224000^2 &:= 1374544^2 \\99625456^2 + 12240000^2 &:= 100374544^2 \\9999625456^2 + 122400000^2 &:= 10000374544^2 \\999999625456^2 + 1224000000^2 &:= 1000000374544^2\end{aligned}$$

613)

$$\begin{aligned}624231^2 + 1226000^2 &:= 1375769^2 \\99624231^2 + 12260000^2 &:= 100375769^2 \\9999624231^2 + 122600000^2 &:= 10000375769^2 \\999999624231^2 + 1226000000^2 &:= 1000000375769^2\end{aligned}$$

614)

$$\begin{aligned}623004^2 + 1228000^2 &:= 1376996^2 \\99623004^2 + 12280000^2 &:= 100376996^2 \\9999623004^2 + 122800000^2 &:= 10000376996^2 \\999999623004^2 + 1228000000^2 &:= 1000000376996^2\end{aligned}$$

615)

$$\begin{aligned}621775^2 + 1230000^2 &:= 1378225^2 \\99621775^2 + 12300000^2 &:= 100378225^2 \\9999621775^2 + 123000000^2 &:= 10000378225^2 \\999999621775^2 + 1230000000^2 &:= 1000000378225^2\end{aligned}$$

- 616) $620544^2 + 1232000^2 := 1379456^2$
 $99620544^2 + 12320000^2 := 100379456^2$
 $9999620544^2 + 123200000^2 := 10000379456^2$
 $999999620544^2 + 1232000000^2 := 1000000379456^2$
- 617) $619311^2 + 1234000^2 := 1380689^2$
 $99619311^2 + 12340000^2 := 100380689^2$
 $9999619311^2 + 123400000^2 := 10000380689^2$
 $999999619311^2 + 1234000000^2 := 1000000380689^2$
- 618) $618076^2 + 1236000^2 := 1381924^2$
 $99618076^2 + 12360000^2 := 100381924^2$
 $9999618076^2 + 123600000^2 := 10000381924^2$
 $999999618076^2 + 1236000000^2 := 1000000381924^2$
- 619) $616839^2 + 1238000^2 := 1383161^2$
 $99616839^2 + 12380000^2 := 100383161^2$
 $9999616839^2 + 123800000^2 := 10000383161^2$
 $999999616839^2 + 1238000000^2 := 1000000383161^2$
- 620) $615600^2 + 1240000^2 := 1384400^2$
 $99615600^2 + 12400000^2 := 100384400^2$
 $9999615600^2 + 124000000^2 := 10000384400^2$
 $999999615600^2 + 1240000000^2 := 1000000384400^2$
- 621) $614359^2 + 1242000^2 := 1385641^2$
 $99614359^2 + 12420000^2 := 100385641^2$
 $9999614359^2 + 124200000^2 := 10000385641^2$
 $999999614359^2 + 1242000000^2 := 1000000385641^2$
- 622) $613116^2 + 1244000^2 := 1386884^2$
 $99613116^2 + 12440000^2 := 100386884^2$
 $9999613116^2 + 124400000^2 := 10000386884^2$
 $999999613116^2 + 1244000000^2 := 1000000386884^2$
- 623) $611871^2 + 1246000^2 := 1388129^2$
 $99611871^2 + 12460000^2 := 100388129^2$
 $9999611871^2 + 124600000^2 := 10000388129^2$
 $999999611871^2 + 1246000000^2 := 1000000388129^2$
- 624) $610624^2 + 1248000^2 := 1389376^2$
 $99610624^2 + 12480000^2 := 100389376^2$
 $9999610624^2 + 124800000^2 := 10000389376^2$
 $999999610624^2 + 1248000000^2 := 1000000389376^2$
- 625) $609375^2 + 1250000^2 := 1390625^2$
 $99609375^2 + 12500000^2 := 100390625^2$
 $9999609375^2 + 125000000^2 := 10000390625^2$
 $999999609375^2 + 1250000000^2 := 1000000390625^2$
- 626) $608124^2 + 1252000^2 := 1391876^2$
 $99608124^2 + 12520000^2 := 100391876^2$
 $9999608124^2 + 125200000^2 := 10000391876^2$
 $999999608124^2 + 1252000000^2 := 1000000391876^2$
- 627) $606871^2 + 1254000^2 := 1393129^2$
 $99606871^2 + 12540000^2 := 100393129^2$
 $9999606871^2 + 125400000^2 := 10000393129^2$
 $999999606871^2 + 1254000000^2 := 1000000393129^2$
- 628) $605616^2 + 1256000^2 := 1394384^2$
 $99605616^2 + 12560000^2 := 100394384^2$
 $9999605616^2 + 125600000^2 := 10000394384^2$
 $999999605616^2 + 1256000000^2 := 1000000394384^2$

629)

$$\begin{aligned}604359^2 + 1258000^2 &:= 1395641^2 \\99604359^2 + 12580000^2 &:= 100395641^2 \\9999604359^2 + 125800000^2 &:= 10000395641^2 \\999999604359^2 + 1258000000^2 &:= 1000000395641^2\end{aligned}$$

630)

$$\begin{aligned}603100^2 + 1260000^2 &:= 1396900^2 \\99603100^2 + 12600000^2 &:= 100396900^2 \\9999603100^2 + 126000000^2 &:= 10000396900^2 \\999999603100^2 + 1260000000^2 &:= 1000000396900^2\end{aligned}$$

631)

$$\begin{aligned}601839^2 + 1262000^2 &:= 1398161^2 \\99601839^2 + 12620000^2 &:= 100398161^2 \\9999601839^2 + 126200000^2 &:= 10000398161^2 \\999999601839^2 + 1262000000^2 &:= 1000000398161^2\end{aligned}$$

632)

$$\begin{aligned}600576^2 + 1264000^2 &:= 1399424^2 \\99600576^2 + 12640000^2 &:= 100399424^2 \\9999600576^2 + 126400000^2 &:= 10000399424^2 \\999999600576^2 + 1264000000^2 &:= 1000000399424^2\end{aligned}$$

633)

$$\begin{aligned}599311^2 + 1266000^2 &:= 1400689^2 \\99599311^2 + 12660000^2 &:= 100400689^2 \\9999599311^2 + 126600000^2 &:= 10000400689^2 \\999999599311^2 + 1266000000^2 &:= 1000000400689^2\end{aligned}$$

634)

$$\begin{aligned}598044^2 + 1268000^2 &:= 1401956^2 \\99598044^2 + 12680000^2 &:= 100401956^2 \\9999598044^2 + 126800000^2 &:= 10000401956^2 \\999999598044^2 + 1268000000^2 &:= 1000000401956^2\end{aligned}$$

635)

$$\begin{aligned}596775^2 + 1270000^2 &:= 1403225^2 \\99596775^2 + 12700000^2 &:= 100403225^2 \\9999596775^2 + 127000000^2 &:= 10000403225^2 \\999999596775^2 + 1270000000^2 &:= 1000000403225^2\end{aligned}$$

636)

$$\begin{aligned}595504^2 + 1272000^2 &:= 1404496^2 \\99595504^2 + 12720000^2 &:= 100404496^2 \\9999595504^2 + 127200000^2 &:= 10000404496^2 \\999999595504^2 + 1272000000^2 &:= 1000000404496^2\end{aligned}$$

637)

$$\begin{aligned}594231^2 + 1274000^2 &:= 1405769^2 \\99594231^2 + 12740000^2 &:= 100405769^2 \\9999594231^2 + 127400000^2 &:= 10000405769^2 \\999999594231^2 + 1274000000^2 &:= 1000000405769^2\end{aligned}$$

638)

$$\begin{aligned}592956^2 + 1276000^2 &:= 1407044^2 \\99592956^2 + 12760000^2 &:= 100407044^2 \\9999592956^2 + 127600000^2 &:= 10000407044^2 \\999999592956^2 + 1276000000^2 &:= 1000000407044^2\end{aligned}$$

639)

$$\begin{aligned}591679^2 + 1278000^2 &:= 1408321^2 \\99591679^2 + 12780000^2 &:= 100408321^2 \\9999591679^2 + 127800000^2 &:= 10000408321^2 \\999999591679^2 + 1278000000^2 &:= 1000000408321^2\end{aligned}$$

640)

$$\begin{aligned}590400^2 + 1280000^2 &:= 1409600^2 \\99590400^2 + 12800000^2 &:= 100409600^2 \\9999590400^2 + 128000000^2 &:= 10000409600^2 \\999999590400^2 + 1280000000^2 &:= 1000000409600^2\end{aligned}$$

641)

$$\begin{aligned}589119^2 + 1282000^2 &:= 1410881^2 \\99589119^2 + 12820000^2 &:= 100410881^2 \\9999589119^2 + 128200000^2 &:= 10000410881^2 \\999999589119^2 + 1282000000^2 &:= 1000000410881^2\end{aligned}$$

642)

$$\begin{aligned}587836^2 + 1284000^2 &:= 1412164^2 \\99587836^2 + 12840000^2 &:= 100412164^2 \\9999587836^2 + 128400000^2 &:= 10000412164^2 \\999999587836^2 + 1284000000^2 &:= 1000000412164^2\end{aligned}$$

643)

$$\begin{aligned}586551^2 + 1286000^2 &:= 1413449^2 \\99586551^2 + 12860000^2 &:= 100413449^2 \\9999586551^2 + 128600000^2 &:= 10000413449^2 \\999999586551^2 + 1286000000^2 &:= 1000000413449^2\end{aligned}$$

644)

$$\begin{aligned}585264^2 + 1288000^2 &:= 1414736^2 \\99585264^2 + 12880000^2 &:= 100414736^2 \\9999585264^2 + 128800000^2 &:= 10000414736^2 \\999999585264^2 + 1288000000^2 &:= 1000000414736^2\end{aligned}$$

645)

$$\begin{aligned}583975^2 + 1290000^2 &:= 1416025^2 \\99583975^2 + 12900000^2 &:= 100416025^2 \\9999583975^2 + 129000000^2 &:= 10000416025^2 \\999999583975^2 + 1290000000^2 &:= 1000000416025^2\end{aligned}$$

646)

$$\begin{aligned}582684^2 + 1292000^2 &:= 1417316^2 \\99582684^2 + 12920000^2 &:= 100417316^2 \\9999582684^2 + 129200000^2 &:= 10000417316^2 \\999999582684^2 + 1292000000^2 &:= 1000000417316^2\end{aligned}$$

647)

$$\begin{aligned}581391^2 + 1294000^2 &:= 1418609^2 \\99581391^2 + 12940000^2 &:= 100418609^2 \\9999581391^2 + 129400000^2 &:= 10000418609^2 \\999999581391^2 + 1294000000^2 &:= 1000000418609^2\end{aligned}$$

648)

$$\begin{aligned}580096^2 + 1296000^2 &:= 1419904^2 \\99580096^2 + 12960000^2 &:= 100419904^2 \\9999580096^2 + 129600000^2 &:= 10000419904^2 \\999999580096^2 + 1296000000^2 &:= 1000000419904^2\end{aligned}$$

649)

$$\begin{aligned}578799^2 + 1298000^2 &:= 1421201^2 \\99578799^2 + 12980000^2 &:= 100421201^2 \\9999578799^2 + 129800000^2 &:= 10000421201^2 \\999999578799^2 + 1298000000^2 &:= 1000000421201^2\end{aligned}$$

650)

$$\begin{aligned}577500^2 + 1300000^2 &:= 1422500^2 \\99577500^2 + 13000000^2 &:= 100422500^2 \\9999577500^2 + 130000000^2 &:= 10000422500^2 \\999999577500^2 + 1300000000^2 &:= 1000000422500^2\end{aligned}$$

651)

$$\begin{aligned}576199^2 + 1302000^2 &:= 1423801^2 \\99576199^2 + 13020000^2 &:= 100423801^2 \\9999576199^2 + 130200000^2 &:= 10000423801^2 \\999999576199^2 + 1302000000^2 &:= 1000000423801^2\end{aligned}$$

652)

$$\begin{aligned}574896^2 + 1304000^2 &:= 1425104^2 \\99574896^2 + 13040000^2 &:= 100425104^2 \\9999574896^2 + 130400000^2 &:= 10000425104^2 \\999999574896^2 + 1304000000^2 &:= 1000000425104^2\end{aligned}$$

653)

$$\begin{aligned}573591^2 + 1306000^2 &:= 1426409^2 \\99573591^2 + 13060000^2 &:= 100426409^2 \\9999573591^2 + 130600000^2 &:= 10000426409^2 \\999999573591^2 + 1306000000^2 &:= 1000000426409^2\end{aligned}$$

654)

$$\begin{aligned}572284^2 + 1308000^2 &:= 1427716^2 \\99572284^2 + 13080000^2 &:= 100427716^2 \\9999572284^2 + 130800000^2 &:= 10000427716^2 \\999999572284^2 + 1308000000^2 &:= 1000000427716^2\end{aligned}$$

- 655) $570975^2 + 1310000^2 := 1429025^2$
 $99570975^2 + 13100000^2 := 100429025^2$
 $9999570975^2 + 131000000^2 := 10000429025^2$
 $999999570975^2 + 1310000000^2 := 1000000429025^2$
- 656) $569664^2 + 1312000^2 := 1430336^2$
 $99569664^2 + 13120000^2 := 100430336^2$
 $9999569664^2 + 131200000^2 := 10000430336^2$
 $999999569664^2 + 1312000000^2 := 1000000430336^2$
- 657) $568351^2 + 1314000^2 := 1431649^2$
 $99568351^2 + 13140000^2 := 100431649^2$
 $9999568351^2 + 131400000^2 := 10000431649^2$
 $999999568351^2 + 1314000000^2 := 1000000431649^2$
- 658) $567036^2 + 1316000^2 := 1432964^2$
 $99567036^2 + 13160000^2 := 100432964^2$
 $9999567036^2 + 131600000^2 := 10000432964^2$
 $999999567036^2 + 1316000000^2 := 1000000432964^2$
- 659) $565719^2 + 1318000^2 := 1434281^2$
 $99565719^2 + 13180000^2 := 100434281^2$
 $9999565719^2 + 131800000^2 := 10000434281^2$
 $999999565719^2 + 1318000000^2 := 1000000434281^2$
- 660) $564400^2 + 1320000^2 := 1435600^2$
 $99564400^2 + 13200000^2 := 100435600^2$
 $9999564400^2 + 132000000^2 := 10000435600^2$
 $999999564400^2 + 1320000000^2 := 1000000435600^2$
- 661) $563079^2 + 1322000^2 := 1436921^2$
 $99563079^2 + 13220000^2 := 100436921^2$
 $9999563079^2 + 132200000^2 := 10000436921^2$
 $999999563079^2 + 1322000000^2 := 1000000436921^2$
- 662) $561756^2 + 1324000^2 := 1438244^2$
 $99561756^2 + 13240000^2 := 100438244^2$
 $9999561756^2 + 132400000^2 := 10000438244^2$
 $999999561756^2 + 1324000000^2 := 1000000438244^2$
- 663) $560431^2 + 1326000^2 := 1439569^2$
 $99560431^2 + 13260000^2 := 100439569^2$
 $9999560431^2 + 132600000^2 := 10000439569^2$
 $999999560431^2 + 1326000000^2 := 1000000439569^2$
- 664) $559104^2 + 1328000^2 := 1440896^2$
 $99559104^2 + 13280000^2 := 100440896^2$
 $9999559104^2 + 132800000^2 := 10000440896^2$
 $999999559104^2 + 1328000000^2 := 1000000440896^2$
- 665) $557775^2 + 1330000^2 := 1442225^2$
 $99557775^2 + 13300000^2 := 100442225^2$
 $9999557775^2 + 133000000^2 := 10000442225^2$
 $999999557775^2 + 1330000000^2 := 1000000442225^2$
- 666) $556444^2 + 1332000^2 := 1443556^2$
 $99556444^2 + 13320000^2 := 100443556^2$
 $9999556444^2 + 133200000^2 := 10000443556^2$
 $999999556444^2 + 1332000000^2 := 1000000443556^2$
- 667) $555111^2 + 1334000^2 := 1444889^2$
 $99555111^2 + 13340000^2 := 100444889^2$
 $9999555111^2 + 133400000^2 := 10000444889^2$
 $999999555111^2 + 1334000000^2 := 1000000444889^2$

668)

$$\begin{aligned}553776^2 + 1336000^2 &:= 1446224^2 \\99553776^2 + 13360000^2 &:= 100446224^2 \\9999553776^2 + 133600000^2 &:= 10000446224^2 \\999999553776^2 + 1336000000^2 &:= 1000000446224^2\end{aligned}$$

669)

$$\begin{aligned}552439^2 + 1338000^2 &:= 1447561^2 \\99552439^2 + 13380000^2 &:= 100447561^2 \\9999552439^2 + 133800000^2 &:= 10000447561^2 \\999999552439^2 + 1338000000^2 &:= 1000000447561^2\end{aligned}$$

670)

$$\begin{aligned}551100^2 + 1340000^2 &:= 1448900^2 \\99551100^2 + 13400000^2 &:= 100448900^2 \\9999551100^2 + 134000000^2 &:= 10000448900^2 \\999999551100^2 + 1340000000^2 &:= 1000000448900^2\end{aligned}$$

671)

$$\begin{aligned}549759^2 + 1342000^2 &:= 1450241^2 \\99549759^2 + 13420000^2 &:= 100450241^2 \\9999549759^2 + 134200000^2 &:= 10000450241^2 \\999999549759^2 + 1342000000^2 &:= 1000000450241^2\end{aligned}$$

672)

$$\begin{aligned}548416^2 + 1344000^2 &:= 1451584^2 \\99548416^2 + 13440000^2 &:= 100451584^2 \\9999548416^2 + 134400000^2 &:= 10000451584^2 \\999999548416^2 + 1344000000^2 &:= 1000000451584^2\end{aligned}$$

673)

$$\begin{aligned}547071^2 + 1346000^2 &:= 1452929^2 \\99547071^2 + 13460000^2 &:= 100452929^2 \\9999547071^2 + 134600000^2 &:= 10000452929^2 \\999999547071^2 + 1346000000^2 &:= 1000000452929^2\end{aligned}$$

674)

$$\begin{aligned}545724^2 + 1348000^2 &:= 1454276^2 \\99545724^2 + 13480000^2 &:= 100454276^2 \\9999545724^2 + 134800000^2 &:= 10000454276^2 \\999999545724^2 + 1348000000^2 &:= 1000000454276^2\end{aligned}$$

675)

$$\begin{aligned}544375^2 + 1350000^2 &:= 1455625^2 \\99544375^2 + 13500000^2 &:= 100455625^2 \\9999544375^2 + 135000000^2 &:= 10000455625^2 \\999999544375^2 + 1350000000^2 &:= 1000000455625^2\end{aligned}$$

676)

$$\begin{aligned}543024^2 + 1352000^2 &:= 1456976^2 \\99543024^2 + 13520000^2 &:= 100456976^2 \\9999543024^2 + 135200000^2 &:= 10000456976^2 \\999999543024^2 + 1352000000^2 &:= 1000000456976^2\end{aligned}$$

677)

$$\begin{aligned}541671^2 + 1354000^2 &:= 1458329^2 \\99541671^2 + 13540000^2 &:= 100458329^2 \\9999541671^2 + 135400000^2 &:= 10000458329^2 \\999999541671^2 + 1354000000^2 &:= 1000000458329^2\end{aligned}$$

678)

$$\begin{aligned}540316^2 + 1356000^2 &:= 1459684^2 \\99540316^2 + 13560000^2 &:= 100459684^2 \\9999540316^2 + 135600000^2 &:= 10000459684^2 \\999999540316^2 + 1356000000^2 &:= 1000000459684^2\end{aligned}$$

679)

$$\begin{aligned}538959^2 + 1358000^2 &:= 1461041^2 \\99538959^2 + 13580000^2 &:= 100461041^2 \\9999538959^2 + 135800000^2 &:= 10000461041^2 \\999999538959^2 + 1358000000^2 &:= 1000000461041^2\end{aligned}$$

680)

$$\begin{aligned}537600^2 + 1360000^2 &:= 1462400^2 \\99537600^2 + 13600000^2 &:= 100462400^2 \\9999537600^2 + 136000000^2 &:= 10000462400^2 \\999999537600^2 + 1360000000^2 &:= 1000000462400^2\end{aligned}$$

- 681) $536239^2 + 1362000^2 := 1463761^2$
 $99536239^2 + 13620000^2 := 100463761^2$
 $9999536239^2 + 136200000^2 := 10000463761^2$
 $999999536239^2 + 1362000000^2 := 1000000463761^2$
- 682) $534876^2 + 1364000^2 := 1465124^2$
 $99534876^2 + 13640000^2 := 100465124^2$
 $9999534876^2 + 136400000^2 := 10000465124^2$
 $999999534876^2 + 1364000000^2 := 1000000465124^2$
- 683) $533511^2 + 1366000^2 := 1466489^2$
 $99533511^2 + 13660000^2 := 100466489^2$
 $9999533511^2 + 136600000^2 := 10000466489^2$
 $999999533511^2 + 1366000000^2 := 1000000466489^2$
- 684) $532144^2 + 1368000^2 := 1467856^2$
 $99532144^2 + 13680000^2 := 100467856^2$
 $9999532144^2 + 136800000^2 := 10000467856^2$
 $999999532144^2 + 1368000000^2 := 1000000467856^2$
- 685) $530775^2 + 1370000^2 := 1469225^2$
 $99530775^2 + 13700000^2 := 100469225^2$
 $9999530775^2 + 137000000^2 := 10000469225^2$
 $999999530775^2 + 1370000000^2 := 1000000469225^2$
- 686) $529404^2 + 1372000^2 := 1470596^2$
 $99529404^2 + 13720000^2 := 100470596^2$
 $9999529404^2 + 137200000^2 := 10000470596^2$
 $999999529404^2 + 1372000000^2 := 1000000470596^2$
- 687) $528031^2 + 1374000^2 := 1471969^2$
 $99528031^2 + 13740000^2 := 100471969^2$
 $9999528031^2 + 137400000^2 := 10000471969^2$
 $999999528031^2 + 1374000000^2 := 1000000471969^2$
- 688) $526656^2 + 1376000^2 := 1473344^2$
 $99526656^2 + 13760000^2 := 100473344^2$
 $9999526656^2 + 137600000^2 := 10000473344^2$
 $999999526656^2 + 1376000000^2 := 1000000473344^2$
- 689) $525279^2 + 1378000^2 := 1474721^2$
 $99525279^2 + 13780000^2 := 100474721^2$
 $9999525279^2 + 137800000^2 := 10000474721^2$
 $999999525279^2 + 1378000000^2 := 1000000474721^2$
- 690) $523900^2 + 1380000^2 := 1476100^2$
 $99523900^2 + 13800000^2 := 100476100^2$
 $9999523900^2 + 138000000^2 := 10000476100^2$
 $999999523900^2 + 1380000000^2 := 1000000476100^2$
- 691) $522519^2 + 1382000^2 := 1477481^2$
 $99522519^2 + 13820000^2 := 100477481^2$
 $9999522519^2 + 138200000^2 := 10000477481^2$
 $999999522519^2 + 1382000000^2 := 1000000477481^2$
- 692) $521136^2 + 1384000^2 := 1478864^2$
 $99521136^2 + 13840000^2 := 100478864^2$
 $9999521136^2 + 138400000^2 := 10000478864^2$
 $999999521136^2 + 1384000000^2 := 1000000478864^2$
- 693) $519751^2 + 1386000^2 := 1480249^2$
 $99519751^2 + 13860000^2 := 100480249^2$
 $9999519751^2 + 138600000^2 := 10000480249^2$
 $999999519751^2 + 1386000000^2 := 1000000480249^2$

- 694) $518364^2 + 1388000^2 := 1481636^2$
 $99518364^2 + 13880000^2 := 100481636^2$
 $9999518364^2 + 138800000^2 := 10000481636^2$
 $999999518364^2 + 1388000000^2 := 1000000481636^2$
- 695) $516975^2 + 1390000^2 := 1483025^2$
 $99516975^2 + 13900000^2 := 100483025^2$
 $9999516975^2 + 139000000^2 := 10000483025^2$
 $999999516975^2 + 1390000000^2 := 1000000483025^2$
- 696) $515584^2 + 1392000^2 := 1484416^2$
 $99515584^2 + 13920000^2 := 100484416^2$
 $9999515584^2 + 139200000^2 := 10000484416^2$
 $999999515584^2 + 1392000000^2 := 1000000484416^2$
- 697) $514191^2 + 1394000^2 := 1485809^2$
 $99514191^2 + 13940000^2 := 100485809^2$
 $9999514191^2 + 139400000^2 := 10000485809^2$
 $999999514191^2 + 1394000000^2 := 1000000485809^2$
- 698) $512796^2 + 1396000^2 := 1487204^2$
 $99512796^2 + 13960000^2 := 100487204^2$
 $9999512796^2 + 139600000^2 := 10000487204^2$
 $999999512796^2 + 1396000000^2 := 1000000487204^2$
- 699) $511399^2 + 1398000^2 := 1488601^2$
 $99511399^2 + 13980000^2 := 100488601^2$
 $9999511399^2 + 139800000^2 := 10000488601^2$
 $999999511399^2 + 1398000000^2 := 1000000488601^2$
- 700) $510000^2 + 1400000^2 := 1490000^2$
 $99510000^2 + 14000000^2 := 100490000^2$
 $9999510000^2 + 140000000^2 := 10000490000^2$
 $999999510000^2 + 1400000000^2 := 1000000490000^2$
- 701) $508599^2 + 1402000^2 := 1491401^2$
 $99508599^2 + 14020000^2 := 100491401^2$
 $9999508599^2 + 140200000^2 := 10000491401^2$
 $999999508599^2 + 1402000000^2 := 1000000491401^2$
- 702) $507196^2 + 1404000^2 := 1492804^2$
 $99507196^2 + 14040000^2 := 100492804^2$
 $9999507196^2 + 140400000^2 := 10000492804^2$
 $999999507196^2 + 1404000000^2 := 1000000492804^2$
- 703) $505791^2 + 1406000^2 := 1494209^2$
 $99505791^2 + 14060000^2 := 100494209^2$
 $9999505791^2 + 140600000^2 := 10000494209^2$
 $999999505791^2 + 1406000000^2 := 1000000494209^2$
- 704) $504384^2 + 1408000^2 := 1495616^2$
 $99504384^2 + 14080000^2 := 100495616^2$
 $9999504384^2 + 140800000^2 := 10000495616^2$
 $999999504384^2 + 1408000000^2 := 1000000495616^2$
- 705) $502975^2 + 1410000^2 := 1497025^2$
 $99502975^2 + 14100000^2 := 100497025^2$
 $9999502975^2 + 141000000^2 := 10000497025^2$
 $999999502975^2 + 1410000000^2 := 1000000497025^2$
- 706) $501564^2 + 1412000^2 := 1498436^2$
 $99501564^2 + 14120000^2 := 100498436^2$
 $9999501564^2 + 141200000^2 := 10000498436^2$
 $999999501564^2 + 1412000000^2 := 1000000498436^2$

- 707) $500151^2 + 1414000^2 := 1499849^2$
 $99500151^2 + 14140000^2 := 100499849^2$
 $9999500151^2 + 141400000^2 := 10000499849^2$
 $999999500151^2 + 1414000000^2 := 1000000499849^2$
- 708) $498736^2 + 1416000^2 := 1501264^2$
 $99498736^2 + 14160000^2 := 100501264^2$
 $9999498736^2 + 141600000^2 := 10000501264^2$
 $999999498736^2 + 1416000000^2 := 1000000501264^2$
- 709) $497319^2 + 1418000^2 := 1502681^2$
 $99497319^2 + 14180000^2 := 100502681^2$
 $9999497319^2 + 141800000^2 := 10000502681^2$
 $999999497319^2 + 1418000000^2 := 1000000502681^2$
- 710) $495900^2 + 1420000^2 := 1504100^2$
 $99495900^2 + 14200000^2 := 100504100^2$
 $9999495900^2 + 142000000^2 := 10000504100^2$
 $999999495900^2 + 1420000000^2 := 1000000504100^2$
- 711) $494479^2 + 1422000^2 := 1505521^2$
 $99494479^2 + 14220000^2 := 100505521^2$
 $9999494479^2 + 142200000^2 := 10000505521^2$
 $999999494479^2 + 1422000000^2 := 1000000505521^2$
- 712) $493056^2 + 1424000^2 := 1506944^2$
 $99493056^2 + 14240000^2 := 100506944^2$
 $9999493056^2 + 142400000^2 := 10000506944^2$
 $999999493056^2 + 1424000000^2 := 1000000506944^2$
- 713) $491631^2 + 1426000^2 := 1508369^2$
 $99491631^2 + 14260000^2 := 100508369^2$
 $9999491631^2 + 142600000^2 := 10000508369^2$
 $999999491631^2 + 1426000000^2 := 1000000508369^2$
- 714) $490204^2 + 1428000^2 := 1509796^2$
 $99490204^2 + 14280000^2 := 100509796^2$
 $9999490204^2 + 142800000^2 := 10000509796^2$
 $999999490204^2 + 1428000000^2 := 1000000509796^2$
- 715) $488775^2 + 1430000^2 := 1511225^2$
 $99488775^2 + 14300000^2 := 100511225^2$
 $9999488775^2 + 143000000^2 := 10000511225^2$
 $999999488775^2 + 1430000000^2 := 1000000511225^2$
- 716) $487344^2 + 1432000^2 := 1512656^2$
 $99487344^2 + 14320000^2 := 100512656^2$
 $9999487344^2 + 143200000^2 := 10000512656^2$
 $999999487344^2 + 1432000000^2 := 1000000512656^2$
- 717) $485911^2 + 1434000^2 := 1514089^2$
 $99485911^2 + 14340000^2 := 100514089^2$
 $9999485911^2 + 143400000^2 := 10000514089^2$
 $999999485911^2 + 1434000000^2 := 1000000514089^2$
- 718) $484476^2 + 1436000^2 := 1515524^2$
 $99484476^2 + 14360000^2 := 100515524^2$
 $9999484476^2 + 143600000^2 := 10000515524^2$
 $999999484476^2 + 1436000000^2 := 1000000515524^2$
- 719) $483039^2 + 1438000^2 := 1516961^2$
 $99483039^2 + 14380000^2 := 100516961^2$
 $9999483039^2 + 143800000^2 := 10000516961^2$
 $999999483039^2 + 1438000000^2 := 1000000516961^2$

- 720) $481600^2 + 1440000^2 := 1518400^2$
 $99481600^2 + 14400000^2 := 100518400^2$
 $9999481600^2 + 144000000^2 := 10000518400^2$
 $999999481600^2 + 1440000000^2 := 1000000518400^2$
- 721) $480159^2 + 1442000^2 := 1519841^2$
 $99480159^2 + 14420000^2 := 100519841^2$
 $9999480159^2 + 144200000^2 := 10000519841^2$
 $999999480159^2 + 1442000000^2 := 1000000519841^2$
- 722) $478716^2 + 1444000^2 := 1521284^2$
 $99478716^2 + 14440000^2 := 100521284^2$
 $9999478716^2 + 144400000^2 := 10000521284^2$
 $999999478716^2 + 1444000000^2 := 1000000521284^2$
- 723) $477271^2 + 1446000^2 := 1522729^2$
 $99477271^2 + 14460000^2 := 100522729^2$
 $9999477271^2 + 144600000^2 := 10000522729^2$
 $999999477271^2 + 1446000000^2 := 1000000522729^2$
- 724) $475824^2 + 1448000^2 := 1524176^2$
 $99475824^2 + 14480000^2 := 100524176^2$
 $9999475824^2 + 144800000^2 := 10000524176^2$
 $999999475824^2 + 1448000000^2 := 1000000524176^2$
- 725) $474375^2 + 1450000^2 := 1525625^2$
 $99474375^2 + 14500000^2 := 100525625^2$
 $9999474375^2 + 145000000^2 := 10000525625^2$
 $999999474375^2 + 1450000000^2 := 1000000525625^2$
- 726) $472924^2 + 1452000^2 := 1527076^2$
 $99472924^2 + 14520000^2 := 100527076^2$
 $9999472924^2 + 145200000^2 := 10000527076^2$
 $999999472924^2 + 1452000000^2 := 1000000527076^2$
- 727) $471471^2 + 1454000^2 := 1528529^2$
 $99471471^2 + 14540000^2 := 100528529^2$
 $9999471471^2 + 145400000^2 := 10000528529^2$
 $999999471471^2 + 1454000000^2 := 1000000528529^2$
- 728) $470016^2 + 1456000^2 := 1529984^2$
 $99470016^2 + 14560000^2 := 100529984^2$
 $9999470016^2 + 145600000^2 := 10000529984^2$
 $999999470016^2 + 1456000000^2 := 1000000529984^2$
- 729) $468559^2 + 1458000^2 := 1531441^2$
 $99468559^2 + 14580000^2 := 100531441^2$
 $9999468559^2 + 145800000^2 := 10000531441^2$
 $999999468559^2 + 1458000000^2 := 1000000531441^2$
- 730) $467100^2 + 1460000^2 := 1532900^2$
 $99467100^2 + 14600000^2 := 100532900^2$
 $9999467100^2 + 146000000^2 := 10000532900^2$
 $999999467100^2 + 1460000000^2 := 1000000532900^2$
- 731) $465639^2 + 1462000^2 := 1534361^2$
 $99465639^2 + 14620000^2 := 100534361^2$
 $9999465639^2 + 146200000^2 := 10000534361^2$
 $999999465639^2 + 1462000000^2 := 1000000534361^2$
- 732) $464176^2 + 1464000^2 := 1535824^2$
 $99464176^2 + 14640000^2 := 100535824^2$
 $9999464176^2 + 146400000^2 := 10000535824^2$
 $999999464176^2 + 1464000000^2 := 1000000535824^2$

- 733) $462711^2 + 1466000^2 := 1537289^2$
 $99462711^2 + 14660000^2 := 100537289^2$
 $9999462711^2 + 146600000^2 := 10000537289^2$
 $999999462711^2 + 1466000000^2 := 1000000537289^2$
- 734) $461244^2 + 1468000^2 := 1538756^2$
 $99461244^2 + 14680000^2 := 100538756^2$
 $9999461244^2 + 146800000^2 := 10000538756^2$
 $999999461244^2 + 1468000000^2 := 1000000538756^2$
- 735) $459775^2 + 1470000^2 := 1540225^2$
 $99459775^2 + 14700000^2 := 100540225^2$
 $9999459775^2 + 147000000^2 := 10000540225^2$
 $999999459775^2 + 1470000000^2 := 1000000540225^2$
- 736) $458304^2 + 1472000^2 := 1541696^2$
 $99458304^2 + 14720000^2 := 100541696^2$
 $9999458304^2 + 147200000^2 := 10000541696^2$
 $999999458304^2 + 1472000000^2 := 1000000541696^2$
- 737) $456831^2 + 1474000^2 := 1543169^2$
 $99456831^2 + 14740000^2 := 100543169^2$
 $9999456831^2 + 147400000^2 := 10000543169^2$
 $999999456831^2 + 1474000000^2 := 1000000543169^2$
- 738) $455356^2 + 1476000^2 := 1544644^2$
 $99455356^2 + 14760000^2 := 100544644^2$
 $9999455356^2 + 147600000^2 := 10000544644^2$
 $999999455356^2 + 1476000000^2 := 1000000544644^2$
- 739) $453879^2 + 1478000^2 := 1546121^2$
 $99453879^2 + 14780000^2 := 100546121^2$
 $9999453879^2 + 147800000^2 := 10000546121^2$
 $999999453879^2 + 1478000000^2 := 1000000546121^2$
- 740) $452400^2 + 1480000^2 := 1547600^2$
 $99452400^2 + 14800000^2 := 100547600^2$
 $9999452400^2 + 148000000^2 := 10000547600^2$
 $999999452400^2 + 1480000000^2 := 1000000547600^2$
- 741) $450919^2 + 1482000^2 := 1549081^2$
 $99450919^2 + 14820000^2 := 100549081^2$
 $9999450919^2 + 148200000^2 := 10000549081^2$
 $999999450919^2 + 1482000000^2 := 1000000549081^2$
- 742) $449436^2 + 1484000^2 := 1550564^2$
 $99449436^2 + 14840000^2 := 100550564^2$
 $9999449436^2 + 148400000^2 := 10000550564^2$
 $999999449436^2 + 1484000000^2 := 1000000550564^2$
- 743) $447951^2 + 1486000^2 := 1552049^2$
 $99447951^2 + 14860000^2 := 100552049^2$
 $9999447951^2 + 148600000^2 := 10000552049^2$
 $999999447951^2 + 1486000000^2 := 1000000552049^2$
- 744) $446464^2 + 1488000^2 := 1553536^2$
 $99446464^2 + 14880000^2 := 100553536^2$
 $9999446464^2 + 148800000^2 := 10000553536^2$
 $999999446464^2 + 1488000000^2 := 1000000553536^2$
- 745) $444975^2 + 1490000^2 := 1555025^2$
 $99444975^2 + 14900000^2 := 100555025^2$
 $9999444975^2 + 149000000^2 := 10000555025^2$
 $999999444975^2 + 1490000000^2 := 1000000555025^2$

- 746) $443484^2 + 1492000^2 := 1556516^2$
 $99443484^2 + 14920000^2 := 100556516^2$
 $9999443484^2 + 149200000^2 := 10000556516^2$
 $999999443484^2 + 1492000000^2 := 1000000556516^2$
- 747) $441991^2 + 1494000^2 := 1558009^2$
 $99441991^2 + 14940000^2 := 100558009^2$
 $9999441991^2 + 149400000^2 := 10000558009^2$
 $999999441991^2 + 1494000000^2 := 1000000558009^2$
- 748) $440496^2 + 1496000^2 := 1559504^2$
 $99440496^2 + 14960000^2 := 100559504^2$
 $9999440496^2 + 149600000^2 := 10000559504^2$
 $999999440496^2 + 1496000000^2 := 1000000559504^2$
- 749) $438999^2 + 1498000^2 := 1561001^2$
 $99438999^2 + 14980000^2 := 100561001^2$
 $9999438999^2 + 149800000^2 := 10000561001^2$
 $999999438999^2 + 1498000000^2 := 1000000561001^2$
- 750) $437500^2 + 1500000^2 := 1562500^2$
 $99437500^2 + 15000000^2 := 100562500^2$
 $9999437500^2 + 150000000^2 := 10000562500^2$
 $999999437500^2 + 1500000000^2 := 1000000562500^2$
- 751) $435999^2 + 1502000^2 := 1564001^2$
 $99435999^2 + 15020000^2 := 100564001^2$
 $9999435999^2 + 150200000^2 := 10000564001^2$
 $999999435999^2 + 1502000000^2 := 1000000564001^2$
- 752) $434496^2 + 1504000^2 := 1565504^2$
 $99434496^2 + 15040000^2 := 100565504^2$
 $9999434496^2 + 150400000^2 := 10000565504^2$
 $999999434496^2 + 1504000000^2 := 1000000565504^2$
- 753) $432991^2 + 1506000^2 := 1567009^2$
 $99432991^2 + 15060000^2 := 100567009^2$
 $9999432991^2 + 150600000^2 := 10000567009^2$
 $999999432991^2 + 1506000000^2 := 1000000567009^2$
- 754) $431484^2 + 1508000^2 := 1568516^2$
 $99431484^2 + 15080000^2 := 100568516^2$
 $9999431484^2 + 150800000^2 := 10000568516^2$
 $999999431484^2 + 1508000000^2 := 1000000568516^2$
- 755) $429975^2 + 1510000^2 := 1570025^2$
 $99429975^2 + 15100000^2 := 100570025^2$
 $9999429975^2 + 151000000^2 := 10000570025^2$
 $999999429975^2 + 1510000000^2 := 1000000570025^2$
- 756) $428464^2 + 1512000^2 := 1571536^2$
 $99428464^2 + 15120000^2 := 100571536^2$
 $9999428464^2 + 151200000^2 := 10000571536^2$
 $999999428464^2 + 1512000000^2 := 1000000571536^2$
- 757) $426951^2 + 1514000^2 := 1573049^2$
 $99426951^2 + 15140000^2 := 100573049^2$
 $9999426951^2 + 151400000^2 := 10000573049^2$
 $999999426951^2 + 1514000000^2 := 1000000573049^2$
- 758) $425436^2 + 1516000^2 := 1574564^2$
 $99425436^2 + 15160000^2 := 100574564^2$
 $9999425436^2 + 151600000^2 := 10000574564^2$
 $999999425436^2 + 1516000000^2 := 1000000574564^2$

- 759) $423919^2 + 1518000^2 := 1576081^2$
 $99423919^2 + 15180000^2 := 100576081^2$
 $9999423919^2 + 151800000^2 := 10000576081^2$
 $999999423919^2 + 1518000000^2 := 1000000576081^2$
- 760) $422400^2 + 1520000^2 := 1577600^2$
 $99422400^2 + 15200000^2 := 100577600^2$
 $9999422400^2 + 152000000^2 := 10000577600^2$
 $999999422400^2 + 1520000000^2 := 1000000577600^2$
- 761) $420879^2 + 1522000^2 := 1579121^2$
 $99420879^2 + 15220000^2 := 100579121^2$
 $9999420879^2 + 152200000^2 := 10000579121^2$
 $999999420879^2 + 1522000000^2 := 1000000579121^2$
- 762) $419356^2 + 1524000^2 := 1580644^2$
 $99419356^2 + 15240000^2 := 100580644^2$
 $9999419356^2 + 152400000^2 := 10000580644^2$
 $999999419356^2 + 1524000000^2 := 1000000580644^2$
- 763) $417831^2 + 1526000^2 := 1582169^2$
 $99417831^2 + 15260000^2 := 100582169^2$
 $9999417831^2 + 152600000^2 := 10000582169^2$
 $999999417831^2 + 1526000000^2 := 1000000582169^2$
- 764) $416304^2 + 1528000^2 := 1583696^2$
 $99416304^2 + 15280000^2 := 100583696^2$
 $9999416304^2 + 152800000^2 := 10000583696^2$
 $999999416304^2 + 1528000000^2 := 1000000583696^2$
- 765) $414775^2 + 1530000^2 := 1585225^2$
 $99414775^2 + 15300000^2 := 100585225^2$
 $9999414775^2 + 153000000^2 := 10000585225^2$
 $999999414775^2 + 1530000000^2 := 1000000585225^2$
- 766) $413244^2 + 1532000^2 := 1586756^2$
 $99413244^2 + 15320000^2 := 100586756^2$
 $9999413244^2 + 153200000^2 := 10000586756^2$
 $999999413244^2 + 1532000000^2 := 1000000586756^2$
- 767) $411711^2 + 1534000^2 := 1588289^2$
 $99411711^2 + 15340000^2 := 100588289^2$
 $9999411711^2 + 153400000^2 := 10000588289^2$
 $999999411711^2 + 1534000000^2 := 1000000588289^2$
- 768) $410176^2 + 1536000^2 := 1589824^2$
 $99410176^2 + 15360000^2 := 100589824^2$
 $9999410176^2 + 153600000^2 := 10000589824^2$
 $999999410176^2 + 1536000000^2 := 1000000589824^2$
- 769) $408639^2 + 1538000^2 := 1591361^2$
 $99408639^2 + 15380000^2 := 100591361^2$
 $9999408639^2 + 153800000^2 := 10000591361^2$
 $999999408639^2 + 1538000000^2 := 1000000591361^2$
- 770) $407100^2 + 1540000^2 := 1592900^2$
 $99407100^2 + 15400000^2 := 100592900^2$
 $9999407100^2 + 154000000^2 := 10000592900^2$
 $999999407100^2 + 1540000000^2 := 1000000592900^2$
- 771) $405559^2 + 1542000^2 := 1594441^2$
 $99405559^2 + 15420000^2 := 100594441^2$
 $9999405559^2 + 154200000^2 := 10000594441^2$
 $999999405559^2 + 1542000000^2 := 1000000594441^2$

- 772) $404016^2 + 1544000^2 := 1595984^2$
 $99404016^2 + 15440000^2 := 100595984^2$
 $9999404016^2 + 154400000^2 := 10000595984^2$
 $999999404016^2 + 1544000000^2 := 1000000595984^2$
- 773) $402471^2 + 1546000^2 := 1597529^2$
 $99402471^2 + 15460000^2 := 100597529^2$
 $9999402471^2 + 154600000^2 := 10000597529^2$
 $999999402471^2 + 1546000000^2 := 1000000597529^2$
- 774) $400924^2 + 1548000^2 := 1599076^2$
 $99400924^2 + 15480000^2 := 100599076^2$
 $9999400924^2 + 154800000^2 := 10000599076^2$
 $999999400924^2 + 1548000000^2 := 1000000599076^2$
- 775) $399375^2 + 1550000^2 := 1600625^2$
 $99399375^2 + 15500000^2 := 100600625^2$
 $9999399375^2 + 155000000^2 := 10000600625^2$
 $999999399375^2 + 1550000000^2 := 1000000600625^2$
- 776) $397824^2 + 1552000^2 := 1602176^2$
 $99397824^2 + 15520000^2 := 100602176^2$
 $9999397824^2 + 155200000^2 := 10000602176^2$
 $999999397824^2 + 1552000000^2 := 1000000602176^2$
- 777) $396271^2 + 1554000^2 := 1603729^2$
 $99396271^2 + 15540000^2 := 100603729^2$
 $9999396271^2 + 155400000^2 := 10000603729^2$
 $999999396271^2 + 1554000000^2 := 1000000603729^2$
- 778) $394716^2 + 1556000^2 := 1605284^2$
 $99394716^2 + 15560000^2 := 100605284^2$
 $9999394716^2 + 155600000^2 := 10000605284^2$
 $999999394716^2 + 1556000000^2 := 1000000605284^2$
- 779) $393159^2 + 1558000^2 := 1606841^2$
 $99393159^2 + 15580000^2 := 100606841^2$
 $9999393159^2 + 155800000^2 := 10000606841^2$
 $999999393159^2 + 1558000000^2 := 1000000606841^2$
- 780) $391600^2 + 1560000^2 := 1608400^2$
 $99391600^2 + 15600000^2 := 100608400^2$
 $9999391600^2 + 156000000^2 := 10000608400^2$
 $999999391600^2 + 1560000000^2 := 1000000608400^2$
- 781) $390039^2 + 1562000^2 := 1609961^2$
 $99390039^2 + 15620000^2 := 100609961^2$
 $9999390039^2 + 156200000^2 := 10000609961^2$
 $999999390039^2 + 1562000000^2 := 1000000609961^2$
- 782) $388476^2 + 1564000^2 := 1611524^2$
 $99388476^2 + 15640000^2 := 100611524^2$
 $9999388476^2 + 156400000^2 := 10000611524^2$
 $999999388476^2 + 1564000000^2 := 1000000611524^2$
- 783) $386911^2 + 1566000^2 := 1613089^2$
 $99386911^2 + 15660000^2 := 100613089^2$
 $9999386911^2 + 156600000^2 := 10000613089^2$
 $999999386911^2 + 1566000000^2 := 1000000613089^2$
- 784) $385344^2 + 1568000^2 := 1614656^2$
 $99385344^2 + 15680000^2 := 100614656^2$
 $9999385344^2 + 156800000^2 := 10000614656^2$
 $999999385344^2 + 1568000000^2 := 1000000614656^2$

- 785) $383775^2 + 1570000^2 := 1616225^2$
 $99383775^2 + 15700000^2 := 100616225^2$
 $9999383775^2 + 157000000^2 := 10000616225^2$
 $999999383775^2 + 1570000000^2 := 1000000616225^2$
- 786) $382204^2 + 1572000^2 := 1617796^2$
 $99382204^2 + 15720000^2 := 100617796^2$
 $9999382204^2 + 157200000^2 := 10000617796^2$
 $999999382204^2 + 1572000000^2 := 1000000617796^2$
- 787) $380631^2 + 1574000^2 := 1619369^2$
 $99380631^2 + 15740000^2 := 100619369^2$
 $9999380631^2 + 157400000^2 := 10000619369^2$
 $999999380631^2 + 1574000000^2 := 1000000619369^2$
- 788) $379056^2 + 1576000^2 := 1620944^2$
 $99379056^2 + 15760000^2 := 100620944^2$
 $9999379056^2 + 157600000^2 := 10000620944^2$
 $999999379056^2 + 1576000000^2 := 1000000620944^2$
- 789) $377479^2 + 1578000^2 := 1622521^2$
 $99377479^2 + 15780000^2 := 100622521^2$
 $9999377479^2 + 157800000^2 := 10000622521^2$
 $999999377479^2 + 1578000000^2 := 1000000622521^2$
- 790) $375900^2 + 1580000^2 := 1624100^2$
 $99375900^2 + 15800000^2 := 100624100^2$
 $9999375900^2 + 158000000^2 := 10000624100^2$
 $999999375900^2 + 1580000000^2 := 1000000624100^2$
- 791) $374319^2 + 1582000^2 := 1625681^2$
 $99374319^2 + 15820000^2 := 100625681^2$
 $9999374319^2 + 158200000^2 := 10000625681^2$
 $999999374319^2 + 1582000000^2 := 1000000625681^2$
- 792) $372736^2 + 1584000^2 := 1627264^2$
 $99372736^2 + 15840000^2 := 100627264^2$
 $9999372736^2 + 158400000^2 := 10000627264^2$
 $999999372736^2 + 1584000000^2 := 1000000627264^2$
- 793) $371151^2 + 1586000^2 := 1628849^2$
 $99371151^2 + 15860000^2 := 100628849^2$
 $9999371151^2 + 158600000^2 := 10000628849^2$
 $999999371151^2 + 1586000000^2 := 1000000628849^2$
- 794) $369564^2 + 1588000^2 := 1630436^2$
 $99369564^2 + 15880000^2 := 100630436^2$
 $9999369564^2 + 158800000^2 := 10000630436^2$
 $999999369564^2 + 1588000000^2 := 1000000630436^2$
- 795) $367975^2 + 1590000^2 := 1632025^2$
 $99367975^2 + 15900000^2 := 100632025^2$
 $9999367975^2 + 159000000^2 := 10000632025^2$
 $999999367975^2 + 1590000000^2 := 1000000632025^2$
- 796) $366384^2 + 1592000^2 := 1633616^2$
 $99366384^2 + 15920000^2 := 100633616^2$
 $9999366384^2 + 159200000^2 := 10000633616^2$
 $999999366384^2 + 1592000000^2 := 1000000633616^2$
- 797) $364791^2 + 1594000^2 := 1635209^2$
 $99364791^2 + 15940000^2 := 100635209^2$
 $9999364791^2 + 159400000^2 := 10000635209^2$
 $999999364791^2 + 1594000000^2 := 1000000635209^2$

- 798) $363196^2 + 1596000^2 := 1636804^2$
 $99363196^2 + 15960000^2 := 100636804^2$
 $9999363196^2 + 159600000^2 := 10000636804^2$
 $999999363196^2 + 1596000000^2 := 1000000636804^2$
- 799) $361599^2 + 1598000^2 := 1638401^2$
 $99361599^2 + 15980000^2 := 100638401^2$
 $9999361599^2 + 159800000^2 := 10000638401^2$
 $999999361599^2 + 1598000000^2 := 1000000638401^2$
- 800) $360000^2 + 1600000^2 := 1640000^2$
 $99360000^2 + 16000000^2 := 100640000^2$
 $9999360000^2 + 160000000^2 := 10000640000^2$
 $999999360000^2 + 1600000000^2 := 1000000640000^2$
- 801) $358399^2 + 1602000^2 := 1641601^2$
 $99358399^2 + 16020000^2 := 100641601^2$
 $9999358399^2 + 160200000^2 := 10000641601^2$
 $999999358399^2 + 1602000000^2 := 1000000641601^2$
- 802) $356796^2 + 1604000^2 := 1643204^2$
 $99356796^2 + 16040000^2 := 100643204^2$
 $9999356796^2 + 160400000^2 := 10000643204^2$
 $999999356796^2 + 1604000000^2 := 1000000643204^2$
- 803) $355191^2 + 1606000^2 := 1644809^2$
 $99355191^2 + 16060000^2 := 100644809^2$
 $9999355191^2 + 160600000^2 := 10000644809^2$
 $999999355191^2 + 1606000000^2 := 1000000644809^2$
- 804) $353584^2 + 1608000^2 := 1646416^2$
 $99353584^2 + 16080000^2 := 100646416^2$
 $9999353584^2 + 160800000^2 := 10000646416^2$
 $999999353584^2 + 1608000000^2 := 1000000646416^2$
- 805) $351975^2 + 1610000^2 := 1648025^2$
 $99351975^2 + 16100000^2 := 100648025^2$
 $9999351975^2 + 161000000^2 := 10000648025^2$
 $999999351975^2 + 1610000000^2 := 1000000648025^2$
- 806) $350364^2 + 1612000^2 := 1649636^2$
 $99350364^2 + 16120000^2 := 100649636^2$
 $9999350364^2 + 161200000^2 := 10000649636^2$
 $999999350364^2 + 1612000000^2 := 1000000649636^2$
- 807) $348751^2 + 1614000^2 := 1651249^2$
 $99348751^2 + 16140000^2 := 100651249^2$
 $9999348751^2 + 161400000^2 := 10000651249^2$
 $999999348751^2 + 1614000000^2 := 1000000651249^2$
- 808) $347136^2 + 1616000^2 := 1652864^2$
 $99347136^2 + 16160000^2 := 100652864^2$
 $9999347136^2 + 161600000^2 := 10000652864^2$
 $999999347136^2 + 1616000000^2 := 1000000652864^2$
- 809) $345519^2 + 1618000^2 := 1654481^2$
 $99345519^2 + 16180000^2 := 100654481^2$
 $9999345519^2 + 161800000^2 := 10000654481^2$
 $999999345519^2 + 1618000000^2 := 1000000654481^2$
- 810) $343900^2 + 1620000^2 := 1656100^2$
 $99343900^2 + 16200000^2 := 100656100^2$
 $9999343900^2 + 162000000^2 := 10000656100^2$
 $999999343900^2 + 1620000000^2 := 1000000656100^2$

811)

$$\begin{aligned}342279^2 + 1622000^2 &:= 1657721^2 \\99342279^2 + 16220000^2 &:= 100657721^2 \\9999342279^2 + 162200000^2 &:= 10000657721^2 \\999999342279^2 + 1622000000^2 &:= 1000000657721^2\end{aligned}$$

812)

$$\begin{aligned}340656^2 + 1624000^2 &:= 1659344^2 \\99340656^2 + 16240000^2 &:= 100659344^2 \\9999340656^2 + 162400000^2 &:= 10000659344^2 \\999999340656^2 + 1624000000^2 &:= 1000000659344^2\end{aligned}$$

813)

$$\begin{aligned}339031^2 + 1626000^2 &:= 1660969^2 \\99339031^2 + 16260000^2 &:= 100660969^2 \\9999339031^2 + 162600000^2 &:= 10000660969^2 \\999999339031^2 + 1626000000^2 &:= 1000000660969^2\end{aligned}$$

814)

$$\begin{aligned}337404^2 + 1628000^2 &:= 1662596^2 \\99337404^2 + 16280000^2 &:= 100662596^2 \\9999337404^2 + 162800000^2 &:= 10000662596^2 \\999999337404^2 + 1628000000^2 &:= 1000000662596^2\end{aligned}$$

815)

$$\begin{aligned}335775^2 + 1630000^2 &:= 1664225^2 \\99335775^2 + 16300000^2 &:= 100664225^2 \\9999335775^2 + 163000000^2 &:= 10000664225^2 \\999999335775^2 + 1630000000^2 &:= 1000000664225^2\end{aligned}$$

816)

$$\begin{aligned}334144^2 + 1632000^2 &:= 1665856^2 \\99334144^2 + 16320000^2 &:= 100665856^2 \\9999334144^2 + 163200000^2 &:= 10000665856^2 \\999999334144^2 + 1632000000^2 &:= 1000000665856^2\end{aligned}$$

817)

$$\begin{aligned}332511^2 + 1634000^2 &:= 1667489^2 \\99332511^2 + 16340000^2 &:= 100667489^2 \\9999332511^2 + 163400000^2 &:= 10000667489^2 \\999999332511^2 + 1634000000^2 &:= 1000000667489^2\end{aligned}$$

818)

$$\begin{aligned}330876^2 + 1636000^2 &:= 1669124^2 \\99330876^2 + 16360000^2 &:= 100669124^2 \\9999330876^2 + 163600000^2 &:= 10000669124^2 \\999999330876^2 + 1636000000^2 &:= 1000000669124^2\end{aligned}$$

819)

$$\begin{aligned}329239^2 + 1638000^2 &:= 1670761^2 \\99329239^2 + 16380000^2 &:= 100670761^2 \\9999329239^2 + 163800000^2 &:= 10000670761^2 \\999999329239^2 + 1638000000^2 &:= 1000000670761^2\end{aligned}$$

820)

$$\begin{aligned}327600^2 + 1640000^2 &:= 1672400^2 \\99327600^2 + 16400000^2 &:= 100672400^2 \\9999327600^2 + 164000000^2 &:= 10000672400^2 \\999999327600^2 + 1640000000^2 &:= 1000000672400^2\end{aligned}$$

821)

$$\begin{aligned}325959^2 + 1642000^2 &:= 1674041^2 \\99325959^2 + 16420000^2 &:= 100674041^2 \\9999325959^2 + 164200000^2 &:= 10000674041^2 \\999999325959^2 + 1642000000^2 &:= 1000000674041^2\end{aligned}$$

822)

$$\begin{aligned}324316^2 + 1644000^2 &:= 1675684^2 \\99324316^2 + 16440000^2 &:= 100675684^2 \\9999324316^2 + 164400000^2 &:= 10000675684^2 \\999999324316^2 + 1644000000^2 &:= 1000000675684^2\end{aligned}$$

823)

$$\begin{aligned}322671^2 + 1646000^2 &:= 1677329^2 \\99322671^2 + 16460000^2 &:= 100677329^2 \\9999322671^2 + 164600000^2 &:= 10000677329^2 \\999999322671^2 + 1646000000^2 &:= 1000000677329^2\end{aligned}$$

824)

$$\begin{aligned}321024^2 + 1648000^2 &:= 1678976^2 \\99321024^2 + 16480000^2 &:= 100678976^2 \\9999321024^2 + 164800000^2 &:= 10000678976^2 \\999999321024^2 + 1648000000^2 &:= 1000000678976^2\end{aligned}$$

825)

$$\begin{aligned}319375^2 + 1650000^2 &:= 1680625^2 \\99319375^2 + 16500000^2 &:= 100680625^2 \\9999319375^2 + 165000000^2 &:= 10000680625^2 \\999999319375^2 + 1650000000^2 &:= 1000000680625^2\end{aligned}$$

826)

$$\begin{aligned}317724^2 + 1652000^2 &:= 1682276^2 \\99317724^2 + 16520000^2 &:= 100682276^2 \\9999317724^2 + 165200000^2 &:= 10000682276^2 \\999999317724^2 + 1652000000^2 &:= 1000000682276^2\end{aligned}$$

827)

$$\begin{aligned}316071^2 + 1654000^2 &:= 1683929^2 \\99316071^2 + 16540000^2 &:= 100683929^2 \\9999316071^2 + 165400000^2 &:= 10000683929^2 \\999999316071^2 + 1654000000^2 &:= 1000000683929^2\end{aligned}$$

828)

$$\begin{aligned}314416^2 + 1656000^2 &:= 1685584^2 \\99314416^2 + 16560000^2 &:= 100685584^2 \\9999314416^2 + 165600000^2 &:= 10000685584^2 \\999999314416^2 + 1656000000^2 &:= 1000000685584^2\end{aligned}$$

829)

$$\begin{aligned}312759^2 + 1658000^2 &:= 1687241^2 \\99312759^2 + 16580000^2 &:= 100687241^2 \\9999312759^2 + 165800000^2 &:= 10000687241^2 \\999999312759^2 + 1658000000^2 &:= 1000000687241^2\end{aligned}$$

830)

$$\begin{aligned}311100^2 + 1660000^2 &:= 1688900^2 \\99311100^2 + 16600000^2 &:= 100688900^2 \\9999311100^2 + 166000000^2 &:= 10000688900^2 \\999999311100^2 + 1660000000^2 &:= 1000000688900^2\end{aligned}$$

831)

$$\begin{aligned}309439^2 + 1662000^2 &:= 1690561^2 \\99309439^2 + 16620000^2 &:= 100690561^2 \\9999309439^2 + 166200000^2 &:= 10000690561^2 \\999999309439^2 + 1662000000^2 &:= 1000000690561^2\end{aligned}$$

832)

$$\begin{aligned}307776^2 + 1664000^2 &:= 1692224^2 \\99307776^2 + 16640000^2 &:= 100692224^2 \\9999307776^2 + 166400000^2 &:= 10000692224^2 \\999999307776^2 + 1664000000^2 &:= 1000000692224^2\end{aligned}$$

833)

$$\begin{aligned}306111^2 + 1666000^2 &:= 1693889^2 \\99306111^2 + 16660000^2 &:= 100693889^2 \\9999306111^2 + 166600000^2 &:= 10000693889^2 \\999999306111^2 + 1666000000^2 &:= 1000000693889^2\end{aligned}$$

834)

$$\begin{aligned}304444^2 + 1668000^2 &:= 1695556^2 \\99304444^2 + 16680000^2 &:= 100695556^2 \\9999304444^2 + 166800000^2 &:= 10000695556^2 \\999999304444^2 + 1668000000^2 &:= 1000000695556^2\end{aligned}$$

835)

$$\begin{aligned}302775^2 + 1670000^2 &:= 1697225^2 \\99302775^2 + 16700000^2 &:= 100697225^2 \\9999302775^2 + 167000000^2 &:= 10000697225^2 \\999999302775^2 + 1670000000^2 &:= 1000000697225^2\end{aligned}$$

836)

$$\begin{aligned}301104^2 + 1672000^2 &:= 1698896^2 \\99301104^2 + 16720000^2 &:= 100698896^2 \\9999301104^2 + 167200000^2 &:= 10000698896^2 \\999999301104^2 + 1672000000^2 &:= 1000000698896^2\end{aligned}$$

837)

$$\begin{aligned}299431^2 + 1674000^2 &:= 1700569^2 \\99299431^2 + 16740000^2 &:= 100700569^2 \\9999299431^2 + 167400000^2 &:= 10000700569^2 \\999999299431^2 + 1674000000^2 &:= 1000000700569^2\end{aligned}$$

838)

$$\begin{aligned}297756^2 + 1676000^2 &:= 1702244^2 \\99297756^2 + 16760000^2 &:= 100702244^2 \\9999297756^2 + 167600000^2 &:= 10000702244^2 \\999999297756^2 + 1676000000^2 &:= 1000000702244^2\end{aligned}$$

839)

$$\begin{aligned}296079^2 + 1678000^2 &:= 1703921^2 \\99296079^2 + 16780000^2 &:= 100703921^2 \\9999296079^2 + 167800000^2 &:= 10000703921^2 \\999999296079^2 + 1678000000^2 &:= 1000000703921^2\end{aligned}$$

840)

$$\begin{aligned}294400^2 + 1680000^2 &:= 1705600^2 \\99294400^2 + 16800000^2 &:= 100705600^2 \\9999294400^2 + 168000000^2 &:= 10000705600^2 \\999999294400^2 + 1680000000^2 &:= 1000000705600^2\end{aligned}$$

841)

$$\begin{aligned}292719^2 + 1682000^2 &:= 1707281^2 \\99292719^2 + 16820000^2 &:= 100707281^2 \\9999292719^2 + 168200000^2 &:= 10000707281^2 \\999999292719^2 + 1682000000^2 &:= 1000000707281^2\end{aligned}$$

842)

$$\begin{aligned}291036^2 + 1684000^2 &:= 1708964^2 \\99291036^2 + 16840000^2 &:= 100708964^2 \\9999291036^2 + 168400000^2 &:= 10000708964^2 \\999999291036^2 + 1684000000^2 &:= 1000000708964^2\end{aligned}$$

843)

$$\begin{aligned}289351^2 + 1686000^2 &:= 1710649^2 \\99289351^2 + 16860000^2 &:= 100710649^2 \\9999289351^2 + 168600000^2 &:= 10000710649^2 \\999999289351^2 + 1686000000^2 &:= 1000000710649^2\end{aligned}$$

844)

$$\begin{aligned}287664^2 + 1688000^2 &:= 1712336^2 \\99287664^2 + 16880000^2 &:= 100712336^2 \\9999287664^2 + 168800000^2 &:= 10000712336^2 \\999999287664^2 + 1688000000^2 &:= 1000000712336^2\end{aligned}$$

845)

$$\begin{aligned}285975^2 + 1690000^2 &:= 1714025^2 \\99285975^2 + 16900000^2 &:= 100714025^2 \\9999285975^2 + 169000000^2 &:= 10000714025^2 \\999999285975^2 + 1690000000^2 &:= 1000000714025^2\end{aligned}$$

846)

$$\begin{aligned}284284^2 + 1692000^2 &:= 1715716^2 \\99284284^2 + 16920000^2 &:= 100715716^2 \\9999284284^2 + 169200000^2 &:= 10000715716^2 \\999999284284^2 + 1692000000^2 &:= 1000000715716^2\end{aligned}$$

847)

$$\begin{aligned}282591^2 + 1694000^2 &:= 1717409^2 \\99282591^2 + 16940000^2 &:= 100717409^2 \\9999282591^2 + 169400000^2 &:= 10000717409^2 \\999999282591^2 + 1694000000^2 &:= 1000000717409^2\end{aligned}$$

848)

$$\begin{aligned}280896^2 + 1696000^2 &:= 1719104^2 \\99280896^2 + 16960000^2 &:= 100719104^2 \\9999280896^2 + 169600000^2 &:= 10000719104^2 \\999999280896^2 + 1696000000^2 &:= 1000000719104^2\end{aligned}$$

849)

$$\begin{aligned}279199^2 + 1698000^2 &:= 1720801^2 \\99279199^2 + 16980000^2 &:= 100720801^2 \\9999279199^2 + 169800000^2 &:= 10000720801^2 \\999999279199^2 + 1698000000^2 &:= 1000000720801^2\end{aligned}$$

- 850) $277500^2 + 1700000^2 := 1722500^2$
 $99277500^2 + 17000000^2 := 100722500^2$
 $9999277500^2 + 170000000^2 := 10000722500^2$
 $999999277500^2 + 1700000000^2 := 1000000722500^2$
- 851) $275799^2 + 1702000^2 := 1724201^2$
 $99275799^2 + 17020000^2 := 100724201^2$
 $9999275799^2 + 170200000^2 := 10000724201^2$
 $999999275799^2 + 1702000000^2 := 1000000724201^2$
- 852) $274096^2 + 1704000^2 := 1725904^2$
 $99274096^2 + 17040000^2 := 100725904^2$
 $9999274096^2 + 170400000^2 := 10000725904^2$
 $999999274096^2 + 1704000000^2 := 1000000725904^2$
- 853) $272391^2 + 1706000^2 := 1727609^2$
 $99272391^2 + 17060000^2 := 100727609^2$
 $9999272391^2 + 170600000^2 := 10000727609^2$
 $999999272391^2 + 1706000000^2 := 1000000727609^2$
- 854) $270684^2 + 1708000^2 := 1729316^2$
 $99270684^2 + 17080000^2 := 100729316^2$
 $9999270684^2 + 170800000^2 := 10000729316^2$
 $999999270684^2 + 1708000000^2 := 1000000729316^2$
- 855) $268975^2 + 1710000^2 := 1731025^2$
 $99268975^2 + 17100000^2 := 100731025^2$
 $9999268975^2 + 171000000^2 := 10000731025^2$
 $999999268975^2 + 1710000000^2 := 1000000731025^2$
- 856) $267264^2 + 1712000^2 := 1732736^2$
 $99267264^2 + 17120000^2 := 100732736^2$
 $9999267264^2 + 171200000^2 := 10000732736^2$
 $999999267264^2 + 1712000000^2 := 1000000732736^2$
- 857) $265551^2 + 1714000^2 := 1734449^2$
 $99265551^2 + 17140000^2 := 100734449^2$
 $9999265551^2 + 171400000^2 := 10000734449^2$
 $999999265551^2 + 1714000000^2 := 1000000734449^2$
- 858) $263836^2 + 1716000^2 := 1736164^2$
 $99263836^2 + 17160000^2 := 100736164^2$
 $9999263836^2 + 171600000^2 := 10000736164^2$
 $999999263836^2 + 1716000000^2 := 1000000736164^2$
- 859) $262119^2 + 1718000^2 := 1737881^2$
 $99262119^2 + 17180000^2 := 100737881^2$
 $9999262119^2 + 171800000^2 := 10000737881^2$
 $999999262119^2 + 1718000000^2 := 1000000737881^2$
- 860) $260400^2 + 1720000^2 := 1739600^2$
 $99260400^2 + 17200000^2 := 100739600^2$
 $9999260400^2 + 172000000^2 := 10000739600^2$
 $999999260400^2 + 1720000000^2 := 1000000739600^2$
- 861) $258679^2 + 1722000^2 := 1741321^2$
 $99258679^2 + 17220000^2 := 100741321^2$
 $9999258679^2 + 172200000^2 := 10000741321^2$
 $999999258679^2 + 1722000000^2 := 1000000741321^2$
- 862) $256956^2 + 1724000^2 := 1743044^2$
 $99256956^2 + 17240000^2 := 100743044^2$
 $9999256956^2 + 172400000^2 := 10000743044^2$
 $999999256956^2 + 1724000000^2 := 1000000743044^2$

863)

$$\begin{aligned}255231^2 + 1726000^2 &:= 1744769^2 \\99255231^2 + 17260000^2 &:= 100744769^2 \\9999255231^2 + 172600000^2 &:= 10000744769^2 \\999999255231^2 + 1726000000^2 &:= 1000000744769^2\end{aligned}$$

864)

$$\begin{aligned}253504^2 + 1728000^2 &:= 1746496^2 \\99253504^2 + 17280000^2 &:= 100746496^2 \\9999253504^2 + 172800000^2 &:= 10000746496^2 \\999999253504^2 + 1728000000^2 &:= 1000000746496^2\end{aligned}$$

865)

$$\begin{aligned}251775^2 + 1730000^2 &:= 1748225^2 \\99251775^2 + 17300000^2 &:= 100748225^2 \\9999251775^2 + 173000000^2 &:= 10000748225^2 \\999999251775^2 + 1730000000^2 &:= 1000000748225^2\end{aligned}$$

866)

$$\begin{aligned}250044^2 + 1732000^2 &:= 1749956^2 \\99250044^2 + 17320000^2 &:= 100749956^2 \\9999250044^2 + 173200000^2 &:= 10000749956^2 \\999999250044^2 + 1732000000^2 &:= 1000000749956^2\end{aligned}$$

867)

$$\begin{aligned}248311^2 + 1734000^2 &:= 1751689^2 \\99248311^2 + 17340000^2 &:= 100751689^2 \\9999248311^2 + 173400000^2 &:= 10000751689^2 \\999999248311^2 + 1734000000^2 &:= 1000000751689^2\end{aligned}$$

868)

$$\begin{aligned}246576^2 + 1736000^2 &:= 1753424^2 \\99246576^2 + 17360000^2 &:= 100753424^2 \\9999246576^2 + 173600000^2 &:= 10000753424^2 \\999999246576^2 + 1736000000^2 &:= 1000000753424^2\end{aligned}$$

869)

$$\begin{aligned}244839^2 + 1738000^2 &:= 1755161^2 \\99244839^2 + 17380000^2 &:= 100755161^2 \\9999244839^2 + 173800000^2 &:= 10000755161^2 \\999999244839^2 + 1738000000^2 &:= 1000000755161^2\end{aligned}$$

870)

$$\begin{aligned}243100^2 + 1740000^2 &:= 1756900^2 \\99243100^2 + 17400000^2 &:= 100756900^2 \\9999243100^2 + 174000000^2 &:= 10000756900^2 \\999999243100^2 + 1740000000^2 &:= 1000000756900^2\end{aligned}$$

871)

$$\begin{aligned}241359^2 + 1742000^2 &:= 1758641^2 \\99241359^2 + 17420000^2 &:= 100758641^2 \\9999241359^2 + 174200000^2 &:= 10000758641^2 \\999999241359^2 + 1742000000^2 &:= 1000000758641^2\end{aligned}$$

872)

$$\begin{aligned}239616^2 + 1744000^2 &:= 1760384^2 \\99239616^2 + 17440000^2 &:= 100760384^2 \\9999239616^2 + 174400000^2 &:= 10000760384^2 \\999999239616^2 + 1744000000^2 &:= 1000000760384^2\end{aligned}$$

873)

$$\begin{aligned}237871^2 + 1746000^2 &:= 1762129^2 \\99237871^2 + 17460000^2 &:= 100762129^2 \\9999237871^2 + 174600000^2 &:= 10000762129^2 \\999999237871^2 + 1746000000^2 &:= 1000000762129^2\end{aligned}$$

874)

$$\begin{aligned}236124^2 + 1748000^2 &:= 1763876^2 \\99236124^2 + 17480000^2 &:= 100763876^2 \\9999236124^2 + 174800000^2 &:= 10000763876^2 \\999999236124^2 + 1748000000^2 &:= 1000000763876^2\end{aligned}$$

875)

$$\begin{aligned}234375^2 + 1750000^2 &:= 1765625^2 \\99234375^2 + 17500000^2 &:= 100765625^2 \\9999234375^2 + 175000000^2 &:= 10000765625^2 \\999999234375^2 + 1750000000^2 &:= 1000000765625^2\end{aligned}$$

- 876) $232624^2 + 1752000^2 := 1767376^2$
 $99232624^2 + 17520000^2 := 100767376^2$
 $9999232624^2 + 175200000^2 := 10000767376^2$
 $999999232624^2 + 1752000000^2 := 1000000767376^2$
- 877) $230871^2 + 1754000^2 := 1769129^2$
 $99230871^2 + 17540000^2 := 100769129^2$
 $9999230871^2 + 175400000^2 := 10000769129^2$
 $999999230871^2 + 1754000000^2 := 1000000769129^2$
- 878) $229116^2 + 1756000^2 := 1770884^2$
 $99229116^2 + 17560000^2 := 100770884^2$
 $9999229116^2 + 175600000^2 := 10000770884^2$
 $999999229116^2 + 1756000000^2 := 1000000770884^2$
- 879) $227359^2 + 1758000^2 := 1772641^2$
 $99227359^2 + 17580000^2 := 100772641^2$
 $9999227359^2 + 175800000^2 := 10000772641^2$
 $999999227359^2 + 1758000000^2 := 1000000772641^2$
- 880) $225600^2 + 1760000^2 := 1774400^2$
 $99225600^2 + 17600000^2 := 100774400^2$
 $9999225600^2 + 176000000^2 := 10000774400^2$
 $999999225600^2 + 1760000000^2 := 1000000774400^2$
- 881) $223839^2 + 1762000^2 := 1776161^2$
 $99223839^2 + 17620000^2 := 100776161^2$
 $9999223839^2 + 176200000^2 := 10000776161^2$
 $999999223839^2 + 1762000000^2 := 1000000776161^2$
- 882) $222076^2 + 1764000^2 := 1777924^2$
 $99222076^2 + 17640000^2 := 100777924^2$
 $9999222076^2 + 176400000^2 := 10000777924^2$
 $999999222076^2 + 1764000000^2 := 1000000777924^2$
- 883) $220311^2 + 1766000^2 := 1779689^2$
 $99220311^2 + 17660000^2 := 100779689^2$
 $9999220311^2 + 176600000^2 := 10000779689^2$
 $999999220311^2 + 1766000000^2 := 1000000779689^2$
- 884) $218544^2 + 1768000^2 := 1781456^2$
 $99218544^2 + 17680000^2 := 100781456^2$
 $9999218544^2 + 176800000^2 := 10000781456^2$
 $999999218544^2 + 1768000000^2 := 1000000781456^2$
- 885) $216775^2 + 1770000^2 := 1783225^2$
 $99216775^2 + 17700000^2 := 100783225^2$
 $9999216775^2 + 177000000^2 := 10000783225^2$
 $999999216775^2 + 1770000000^2 := 1000000783225^2$
- 886) $215004^2 + 1772000^2 := 1784996^2$
 $99215004^2 + 17720000^2 := 100784996^2$
 $9999215004^2 + 177200000^2 := 10000784996^2$
 $999999215004^2 + 1772000000^2 := 1000000784996^2$
- 887) $213231^2 + 1774000^2 := 1786769^2$
 $99213231^2 + 17740000^2 := 100786769^2$
 $9999213231^2 + 177400000^2 := 10000786769^2$
 $999999213231^2 + 1774000000^2 := 1000000786769^2$
- 888) $211456^2 + 1776000^2 := 1788544^2$
 $99211456^2 + 17760000^2 := 100788544^2$
 $9999211456^2 + 177600000^2 := 10000788544^2$
 $999999211456^2 + 1776000000^2 := 1000000788544^2$

- 889) $209679^2 + 1778000^2 := 1790321^2$
 $99209679^2 + 17780000^2 := 100790321^2$
 $9999209679^2 + 177800000^2 := 10000790321^2$
 $999999209679^2 + 1778000000^2 := 1000000790321^2$
- 890) $207900^2 + 1780000^2 := 1792100^2$
 $99207900^2 + 17800000^2 := 100792100^2$
 $9999207900^2 + 178000000^2 := 10000792100^2$
 $999999207900^2 + 1780000000^2 := 1000000792100^2$
- 891) $206119^2 + 1782000^2 := 1793881^2$
 $99206119^2 + 17820000^2 := 100793881^2$
 $9999206119^2 + 178200000^2 := 10000793881^2$
 $999999206119^2 + 1782000000^2 := 1000000793881^2$
- 892) $204336^2 + 1784000^2 := 1795664^2$
 $99204336^2 + 17840000^2 := 100795664^2$
 $9999204336^2 + 178400000^2 := 10000795664^2$
 $999999204336^2 + 1784000000^2 := 1000000795664^2$
- 893) $202551^2 + 1786000^2 := 1797449^2$
 $99202551^2 + 17860000^2 := 100797449^2$
 $9999202551^2 + 178600000^2 := 10000797449^2$
 $999999202551^2 + 1786000000^2 := 1000000797449^2$
- 894) $200764^2 + 1788000^2 := 1799236^2$
 $99200764^2 + 17880000^2 := 100799236^2$
 $9999200764^2 + 178800000^2 := 10000799236^2$
 $999999200764^2 + 1788000000^2 := 1000000799236^2$
- 895) $198975^2 + 1790000^2 := 1801025^2$
 $99198975^2 + 17900000^2 := 100801025^2$
 $9999198975^2 + 179000000^2 := 10000801025^2$
 $999999198975^2 + 1790000000^2 := 1000000801025^2$
- 896) $197184^2 + 1792000^2 := 1802816^2$
 $99197184^2 + 17920000^2 := 100802816^2$
 $9999197184^2 + 179200000^2 := 10000802816^2$
 $999999197184^2 + 1792000000^2 := 1000000802816^2$
- 897) $195391^2 + 1794000^2 := 1804609^2$
 $99195391^2 + 17940000^2 := 100804609^2$
 $9999195391^2 + 179400000^2 := 10000804609^2$
 $999999195391^2 + 1794000000^2 := 1000000804609^2$
- 898) $193596^2 + 1796000^2 := 1806404^2$
 $99193596^2 + 17960000^2 := 100806404^2$
 $9999193596^2 + 179600000^2 := 10000806404^2$
 $999999193596^2 + 1796000000^2 := 1000000806404^2$
- 899) $191799^2 + 1798000^2 := 1808201^2$
 $99191799^2 + 17980000^2 := 100808201^2$
 $9999191799^2 + 179800000^2 := 10000808201^2$
 $999999191799^2 + 1798000000^2 := 1000000808201^2$
- 900) $190000^2 + 1800000^2 := 1810000^2$
 $99190000^2 + 18000000^2 := 100810000^2$
 $9999190000^2 + 180000000^2 := 10000810000^2$
 $999999190000^2 + 1800000000^2 := 1000000810000^2$
- 901) $188199^2 + 1802000^2 := 1811801^2$
 $99188199^2 + 18020000^2 := 100811801^2$
 $9999188199^2 + 180200000^2 := 10000811801^2$
 $999999188199^2 + 1802000000^2 := 1000000811801^2$

- 902) $186396^2 + 1804000^2 := 1813604^2$
 $99186396^2 + 18040000^2 := 100813604^2$
 $9999186396^2 + 180400000^2 := 10000813604^2$
 $999999186396^2 + 1804000000^2 := 1000000813604^2$
- 903) $184591^2 + 1806000^2 := 1815409^2$
 $99184591^2 + 18060000^2 := 100815409^2$
 $9999184591^2 + 180600000^2 := 10000815409^2$
 $999999184591^2 + 1806000000^2 := 1000000815409^2$
- 904) $182784^2 + 1808000^2 := 1817216^2$
 $99182784^2 + 18080000^2 := 100817216^2$
 $9999182784^2 + 180800000^2 := 10000817216^2$
 $999999182784^2 + 1808000000^2 := 1000000817216^2$
- 905) $180975^2 + 1810000^2 := 1819025^2$
 $99180975^2 + 18100000^2 := 100819025^2$
 $9999180975^2 + 181000000^2 := 10000819025^2$
 $999999180975^2 + 1810000000^2 := 1000000819025^2$
- 906) $179164^2 + 1812000^2 := 1820836^2$
 $99179164^2 + 18120000^2 := 100820836^2$
 $9999179164^2 + 181200000^2 := 10000820836^2$
 $999999179164^2 + 1812000000^2 := 1000000820836^2$
- 907) $177351^2 + 1814000^2 := 1822649^2$
 $99177351^2 + 18140000^2 := 100822649^2$
 $9999177351^2 + 181400000^2 := 10000822649^2$
 $999999177351^2 + 1814000000^2 := 1000000822649^2$
- 908) $175536^2 + 1816000^2 := 1824464^2$
 $99175536^2 + 18160000^2 := 100824464^2$
 $9999175536^2 + 181600000^2 := 10000824464^2$
 $999999175536^2 + 1816000000^2 := 1000000824464^2$
- 909) $173719^2 + 1818000^2 := 1826281^2$
 $99173719^2 + 18180000^2 := 100826281^2$
 $9999173719^2 + 181800000^2 := 10000826281^2$
 $999999173719^2 + 1818000000^2 := 1000000826281^2$
- 910) $171900^2 + 1820000^2 := 1828100^2$
 $99171900^2 + 18200000^2 := 100828100^2$
 $9999171900^2 + 182000000^2 := 10000828100^2$
 $999999171900^2 + 1820000000^2 := 1000000828100^2$
- 911) $170079^2 + 1822000^2 := 1829921^2$
 $99170079^2 + 18220000^2 := 100829921^2$
 $9999170079^2 + 182200000^2 := 10000829921^2$
 $999999170079^2 + 1822000000^2 := 1000000829921^2$
- 912) $168256^2 + 1824000^2 := 1831744^2$
 $99168256^2 + 18240000^2 := 100831744^2$
 $9999168256^2 + 182400000^2 := 10000831744^2$
 $999999168256^2 + 1824000000^2 := 1000000831744^2$
- 913) $166431^2 + 1826000^2 := 1833569^2$
 $99166431^2 + 18260000^2 := 100833569^2$
 $9999166431^2 + 182600000^2 := 10000833569^2$
 $999999166431^2 + 1826000000^2 := 1000000833569^2$
- 914) $164604^2 + 1828000^2 := 1835396^2$
 $99164604^2 + 18280000^2 := 100835396^2$
 $9999164604^2 + 182800000^2 := 10000835396^2$
 $999999164604^2 + 1828000000^2 := 1000000835396^2$

- 915) $162775^2 + 1830000^2 := 1837225^2$
 $99162775^2 + 18300000^2 := 100837225^2$
 $9999162775^2 + 183000000^2 := 10000837225^2$
 $999999162775^2 + 1830000000^2 := 1000000837225^2$
- 916) $160944^2 + 1832000^2 := 1839056^2$
 $99160944^2 + 18320000^2 := 100839056^2$
 $9999160944^2 + 183200000^2 := 10000839056^2$
 $999999160944^2 + 1832000000^2 := 1000000839056^2$
- 917) $159111^2 + 1834000^2 := 1840889^2$
 $99159111^2 + 18340000^2 := 100840889^2$
 $9999159111^2 + 183400000^2 := 10000840889^2$
 $999999159111^2 + 1834000000^2 := 1000000840889^2$
- 918) $157276^2 + 1836000^2 := 1842724^2$
 $99157276^2 + 18360000^2 := 100842724^2$
 $9999157276^2 + 183600000^2 := 10000842724^2$
 $999999157276^2 + 1836000000^2 := 1000000842724^2$
- 919) $155439^2 + 1838000^2 := 1844561^2$
 $99155439^2 + 18380000^2 := 100844561^2$
 $9999155439^2 + 183800000^2 := 10000844561^2$
 $999999155439^2 + 1838000000^2 := 1000000844561^2$
- 920) $153600^2 + 1840000^2 := 1846400^2$
 $99153600^2 + 18400000^2 := 100846400^2$
 $9999153600^2 + 184000000^2 := 10000846400^2$
 $999999153600^2 + 1840000000^2 := 1000000846400^2$
- 921) $151759^2 + 1842000^2 := 1848241^2$
 $99151759^2 + 18420000^2 := 100848241^2$
 $9999151759^2 + 184200000^2 := 10000848241^2$
 $999999151759^2 + 1842000000^2 := 1000000848241^2$
- 922) $149916^2 + 1844000^2 := 1850084^2$
 $99149916^2 + 18440000^2 := 100850084^2$
 $9999149916^2 + 184400000^2 := 10000850084^2$
 $999999149916^2 + 1844000000^2 := 1000000850084^2$
- 923) $148071^2 + 1846000^2 := 1851929^2$
 $99148071^2 + 18460000^2 := 100851929^2$
 $9999148071^2 + 184600000^2 := 10000851929^2$
 $999999148071^2 + 1846000000^2 := 1000000851929^2$
- 924) $146224^2 + 1848000^2 := 1853776^2$
 $99146224^2 + 18480000^2 := 100853776^2$
 $9999146224^2 + 184800000^2 := 10000853776^2$
 $999999146224^2 + 1848000000^2 := 1000000853776^2$
- 925) $144375^2 + 1850000^2 := 1855625^2$
 $99144375^2 + 18500000^2 := 100855625^2$
 $9999144375^2 + 185000000^2 := 10000855625^2$
 $999999144375^2 + 1850000000^2 := 1000000855625^2$
- 926) $142524^2 + 1852000^2 := 1857476^2$
 $99142524^2 + 18520000^2 := 100857476^2$
 $9999142524^2 + 185200000^2 := 10000857476^2$
 $999999142524^2 + 1852000000^2 := 1000000857476^2$
- 927) $140671^2 + 1854000^2 := 1859329^2$
 $99140671^2 + 18540000^2 := 100859329^2$
 $9999140671^2 + 185400000^2 := 10000859329^2$
 $999999140671^2 + 1854000000^2 := 1000000859329^2$

- 928) $138816^2 + 1856000^2 := 1861184^2$
 $99138816^2 + 18560000^2 := 100861184^2$
 $9999138816^2 + 185600000^2 := 10000861184^2$
 $999999138816^2 + 1856000000^2 := 1000000861184^2$
- 929) $136959^2 + 1858000^2 := 1863041^2$
 $99136959^2 + 18580000^2 := 100863041^2$
 $9999136959^2 + 185800000^2 := 10000863041^2$
 $999999136959^2 + 1858000000^2 := 1000000863041^2$
- 930) $135100^2 + 1860000^2 := 1864900^2$
 $99135100^2 + 18600000^2 := 100864900^2$
 $9999135100^2 + 186000000^2 := 10000864900^2$
 $999999135100^2 + 1860000000^2 := 1000000864900^2$
- 931) $133239^2 + 1862000^2 := 1866761^2$
 $99133239^2 + 18620000^2 := 100866761^2$
 $9999133239^2 + 186200000^2 := 10000866761^2$
 $999999133239^2 + 1862000000^2 := 1000000866761^2$
- 932) $131376^2 + 1864000^2 := 1868624^2$
 $99131376^2 + 18640000^2 := 100868624^2$
 $9999131376^2 + 186400000^2 := 10000868624^2$
 $999999131376^2 + 1864000000^2 := 1000000868624^2$
- 933) $129511^2 + 1866000^2 := 1870489^2$
 $99129511^2 + 18660000^2 := 100870489^2$
 $9999129511^2 + 186600000^2 := 10000870489^2$
 $999999129511^2 + 1866000000^2 := 1000000870489^2$
- 934) $127644^2 + 1868000^2 := 1872356^2$
 $99127644^2 + 18680000^2 := 100872356^2$
 $9999127644^2 + 186800000^2 := 10000872356^2$
 $999999127644^2 + 1868000000^2 := 1000000872356^2$
- 935) $125775^2 + 1870000^2 := 1874225^2$
 $99125775^2 + 18700000^2 := 100874225^2$
 $9999125775^2 + 187000000^2 := 10000874225^2$
 $999999125775^2 + 1870000000^2 := 1000000874225^2$
- 936) $123904^2 + 1872000^2 := 1876096^2$
 $99123904^2 + 18720000^2 := 100876096^2$
 $9999123904^2 + 187200000^2 := 10000876096^2$
 $999999123904^2 + 1872000000^2 := 1000000876096^2$
- 937) $122031^2 + 1874000^2 := 1877969^2$
 $99122031^2 + 18740000^2 := 100877969^2$
 $9999122031^2 + 187400000^2 := 10000877969^2$
 $999999122031^2 + 1874000000^2 := 1000000877969^2$
- 938) $120156^2 + 1876000^2 := 1879844^2$
 $99120156^2 + 18760000^2 := 100879844^2$
 $9999120156^2 + 187600000^2 := 10000879844^2$
 $999999120156^2 + 1876000000^2 := 1000000879844^2$
- 939) $118279^2 + 1878000^2 := 1881721^2$
 $99118279^2 + 18780000^2 := 100881721^2$
 $9999118279^2 + 187800000^2 := 10000881721^2$
 $999999118279^2 + 1878000000^2 := 1000000881721^2$
- 940) $116400^2 + 1880000^2 := 1883600^2$
 $99116400^2 + 18800000^2 := 100883600^2$
 $9999116400^2 + 188000000^2 := 10000883600^2$
 $999999116400^2 + 1880000000^2 := 1000000883600^2$

941)

$$\begin{aligned}114519^2 + 1882000^2 &:= 1885481^2 \\99114519^2 + 18820000^2 &:= 100885481^2 \\9999114519^2 + 188200000^2 &:= 10000885481^2 \\999999114519^2 + 1882000000^2 &:= 1000000885481^2\end{aligned}$$

942)

$$\begin{aligned}112636^2 + 1884000^2 &:= 1887364^2 \\99112636^2 + 18840000^2 &:= 100887364^2 \\9999112636^2 + 188400000^2 &:= 10000887364^2 \\999999112636^2 + 1884000000^2 &:= 1000000887364^2\end{aligned}$$

943)

$$\begin{aligned}110751^2 + 1886000^2 &:= 1889249^2 \\99110751^2 + 18860000^2 &:= 100889249^2 \\9999110751^2 + 188600000^2 &:= 10000889249^2 \\999999110751^2 + 1886000000^2 &:= 1000000889249^2\end{aligned}$$

944)

$$\begin{aligned}108864^2 + 1888000^2 &:= 1891136^2 \\99108864^2 + 18880000^2 &:= 100891136^2 \\9999108864^2 + 188800000^2 &:= 10000891136^2 \\999999108864^2 + 1888000000^2 &:= 1000000891136^2\end{aligned}$$

945)

$$\begin{aligned}106975^2 + 1890000^2 &:= 1893025^2 \\99106975^2 + 18900000^2 &:= 100893025^2 \\9999106975^2 + 189000000^2 &:= 10000893025^2 \\999999106975^2 + 1890000000^2 &:= 1000000893025^2\end{aligned}$$

946)

$$\begin{aligned}105084^2 + 1892000^2 &:= 1894916^2 \\99105084^2 + 18920000^2 &:= 100894916^2 \\9999105084^2 + 189200000^2 &:= 10000894916^2 \\999999105084^2 + 1892000000^2 &:= 1000000894916^2\end{aligned}$$

947)

$$\begin{aligned}103191^2 + 1894000^2 &:= 1896809^2 \\99103191^2 + 18940000^2 &:= 100896809^2 \\9999103191^2 + 189400000^2 &:= 10000896809^2 \\999999103191^2 + 1894000000^2 &:= 1000000896809^2\end{aligned}$$

948)

$$\begin{aligned}101296^2 + 1896000^2 &:= 1898704^2 \\99101296^2 + 18960000^2 &:= 100898704^2 \\9999101296^2 + 189600000^2 &:= 10000898704^2 \\999999101296^2 + 1896000000^2 &:= 1000000898704^2\end{aligned}$$

949)

$$\begin{aligned}99399^2 + 1898000^2 &:= 1900601^2 \\99099399^2 + 18980000^2 &:= 100900601^2 \\9999099399^2 + 189800000^2 &:= 10000900601^2 \\999999099399^2 + 1898000000^2 &:= 1000000900601^2\end{aligned}$$

950)

$$\begin{aligned}97500^2 + 1900000^2 &:= 1902500^2 \\99097500^2 + 19000000^2 &:= 100902500^2 \\9999097500^2 + 190000000^2 &:= 10000902500^2 \\999999097500^2 + 1900000000^2 &:= 1000000902500^2\end{aligned}$$

951)

$$\begin{aligned}95599^2 + 1902000^2 &:= 1904401^2 \\99095599^2 + 19020000^2 &:= 100904401^2 \\9999095599^2 + 190200000^2 &:= 10000904401^2 \\999999095599^2 + 1902000000^2 &:= 1000000904401^2\end{aligned}$$

952)

$$\begin{aligned}93696^2 + 1904000^2 &:= 1906304^2 \\99093696^2 + 19040000^2 &:= 100906304^2 \\9999093696^2 + 190400000^2 &:= 10000906304^2 \\999999093696^2 + 1904000000^2 &:= 1000000906304^2\end{aligned}$$

953)

$$\begin{aligned}91791^2 + 1906000^2 &:= 1908209^2 \\99091791^2 + 19060000^2 &:= 100908209^2 \\9999091791^2 + 190600000^2 &:= 10000908209^2 \\999999091791^2 + 1906000000^2 &:= 1000000908209^2\end{aligned}$$

- 954) $89884^2 + 1908000^2 := 1910116^2$
 $99089884^2 + 19080000^2 := 100910116^2$
 $9999089884^2 + 190800000^2 := 10000910116^2$
 $999999089884^2 + 1908000000^2 := 1000000910116^2$
- 955) $87975^2 + 1910000^2 := 1912025^2$
 $99087975^2 + 19100000^2 := 100912025^2$
 $9999087975^2 + 191000000^2 := 10000912025^2$
 $999999087975^2 + 1910000000^2 := 1000000912025^2$
- 956) $86064^2 + 1912000^2 := 1913936^2$
 $99086064^2 + 19120000^2 := 100913936^2$
 $9999086064^2 + 191200000^2 := 10000913936^2$
 $999999086064^2 + 1912000000^2 := 1000000913936^2$
- 957) $84151^2 + 1914000^2 := 1915849^2$
 $99084151^2 + 19140000^2 := 100915849^2$
 $9999084151^2 + 191400000^2 := 10000915849^2$
 $999999084151^2 + 1914000000^2 := 1000000915849^2$
- 958) $82236^2 + 1916000^2 := 1917764^2$
 $99082236^2 + 19160000^2 := 100917764^2$
 $9999082236^2 + 191600000^2 := 10000917764^2$
 $999999082236^2 + 1916000000^2 := 1000000917764^2$
- 959) $80319^2 + 1918000^2 := 1919681^2$
 $99080319^2 + 19180000^2 := 100919681^2$
 $9999080319^2 + 191800000^2 := 10000919681^2$
 $999999080319^2 + 1918000000^2 := 1000000919681^2$
- 960) $78400^2 + 1920000^2 := 1921600^2$
 $99078400^2 + 19200000^2 := 100921600^2$
 $9999078400^2 + 192000000^2 := 10000921600^2$
 $999999078400^2 + 1920000000^2 := 1000000921600^2$
- 961) $76479^2 + 1922000^2 := 1923521^2$
 $99076479^2 + 19220000^2 := 100923521^2$
 $9999076479^2 + 192200000^2 := 10000923521^2$
 $999999076479^2 + 1922000000^2 := 1000000923521^2$
- 962) $74556^2 + 1924000^2 := 1925444^2$
 $99074556^2 + 19240000^2 := 100925444^2$
 $9999074556^2 + 192400000^2 := 10000925444^2$
 $999999074556^2 + 1924000000^2 := 1000000925444^2$
- 963) $72631^2 + 1926000^2 := 1927369^2$
 $99072631^2 + 19260000^2 := 100927369^2$
 $9999072631^2 + 192600000^2 := 10000927369^2$
 $999999072631^2 + 1926000000^2 := 1000000927369^2$
- 964) $70704^2 + 1928000^2 := 1929296^2$
 $99070704^2 + 19280000^2 := 100929296^2$
 $9999070704^2 + 192800000^2 := 10000929296^2$
 $999999070704^2 + 1928000000^2 := 1000000929296^2$
- 965) $68775^2 + 1930000^2 := 1931225^2$
 $99068775^2 + 19300000^2 := 100931225^2$
 $9999068775^2 + 193000000^2 := 10000931225^2$
 $999999068775^2 + 1930000000^2 := 1000000931225^2$
- 966) $66844^2 + 1932000^2 := 1933156^2$
 $99066844^2 + 19320000^2 := 100933156^2$
 $9999066844^2 + 193200000^2 := 10000933156^2$
 $999999066844^2 + 1932000000^2 := 1000000933156^2$

- 967) $64911^2 + 1934000^2 := 1935089^2$
 $99064911^2 + 19340000^2 := 100935089^2$
 $9999064911^2 + 193400000^2 := 10000935089^2$
 $999999064911^2 + 1934000000^2 := 1000000935089^2$
- 968) $62976^2 + 1936000^2 := 1937024^2$
 $99062976^2 + 19360000^2 := 100937024^2$
 $9999062976^2 + 193600000^2 := 10000937024^2$
 $999999062976^2 + 1936000000^2 := 1000000937024^2$
- 969) $61039^2 + 1938000^2 := 1938961^2$
 $99061039^2 + 19380000^2 := 100938961^2$
 $9999061039^2 + 193800000^2 := 10000938961^2$
 $999999061039^2 + 1938000000^2 := 1000000938961^2$
- 970) $59100^2 + 1940000^2 := 1940900^2$
 $99059100^2 + 19400000^2 := 100940900^2$
 $9999059100^2 + 194000000^2 := 10000940900^2$
 $999999059100^2 + 1940000000^2 := 1000000940900^2$
- 971) $57159^2 + 1942000^2 := 1942841^2$
 $99057159^2 + 19420000^2 := 100942841^2$
 $9999057159^2 + 194200000^2 := 10000942841^2$
 $999999057159^2 + 1942000000^2 := 1000000942841^2$
- 972) $55216^2 + 1944000^2 := 1944784^2$
 $99055216^2 + 19440000^2 := 100944784^2$
 $9999055216^2 + 194400000^2 := 10000944784^2$
 $999999055216^2 + 1944000000^2 := 1000000944784^2$
- 973) $53271^2 + 1946000^2 := 1946729^2$
 $99053271^2 + 19460000^2 := 100946729^2$
 $9999053271^2 + 194600000^2 := 10000946729^2$
 $999999053271^2 + 1946000000^2 := 1000000946729^2$
- 974) $51324^2 + 1948000^2 := 1948676^2$
 $99051324^2 + 19480000^2 := 100948676^2$
 $9999051324^2 + 194800000^2 := 10000948676^2$
 $999999051324^2 + 1948000000^2 := 1000000948676^2$
- 975) $49375^2 + 1950000^2 := 1950625^2$
 $99049375^2 + 19500000^2 := 100950625^2$
 $9999049375^2 + 195000000^2 := 10000950625^2$
 $999999049375^2 + 1950000000^2 := 1000000950625^2$
- 976) $47424^2 + 1952000^2 := 1952576^2$
 $99047424^2 + 19520000^2 := 100952576^2$
 $9999047424^2 + 195200000^2 := 10000952576^2$
 $999999047424^2 + 1952000000^2 := 1000000952576^2$
- 977) $45471^2 + 1954000^2 := 1954529^2$
 $99045471^2 + 19540000^2 := 100954529^2$
 $9999045471^2 + 195400000^2 := 10000954529^2$
 $999999045471^2 + 1954000000^2 := 1000000954529^2$
- 978) $43516^2 + 1956000^2 := 1956484^2$
 $99043516^2 + 19560000^2 := 100956484^2$
 $9999043516^2 + 195600000^2 := 10000956484^2$
 $999999043516^2 + 1956000000^2 := 1000000956484^2$
- 979) $41559^2 + 1958000^2 := 1958441^2$
 $99041559^2 + 19580000^2 := 100958441^2$
 $9999041559^2 + 195800000^2 := 10000958441^2$
 $999999041559^2 + 1958000000^2 := 1000000958441^2$

980)

$$39600^2 + 1960000^2 := 1960400^2$$

$$99039600^2 + 19600000^2 := 100960400^2$$

$$9999039600^2 + 196000000^2 := 10000960400^2$$

$$999999039600^2 + 1960000000^2 := 1000000960400^2$$

981)

$$37639^2 + 1962000^2 := 1962361^2$$

$$99037639^2 + 19620000^2 := 100962361^2$$

$$9999037639^2 + 196200000^2 := 10000962361^2$$

$$999999037639^2 + 1962000000^2 := 1000000962361^2$$

982)

$$35676^2 + 1964000^2 := 1964324^2$$

$$99035676^2 + 19640000^2 := 100964324^2$$

$$9999035676^2 + 196400000^2 := 10000964324^2$$

$$999999035676^2 + 1964000000^2 := 1000000964324^2$$

983)

$$33711^2 + 1966000^2 := 1966289^2$$

$$99033711^2 + 19660000^2 := 100966289^2$$

$$9999033711^2 + 196600000^2 := 10000966289^2$$

$$999999033711^2 + 1966000000^2 := 1000000966289^2$$

984)

$$31744^2 + 1968000^2 := 1968256^2$$

$$99031744^2 + 19680000^2 := 100968256^2$$

$$9999031744^2 + 196800000^2 := 10000968256^2$$

$$999999031744^2 + 1968000000^2 := 1000000968256^2$$

985)

$$29775^2 + 1970000^2 := 1970225^2$$

$$99029775^2 + 19700000^2 := 100970225^2$$

$$9999029775^2 + 197000000^2 := 10000970225^2$$

$$999999029775^2 + 1970000000^2 := 1000000970225^2$$

986)

$$27804^2 + 1972000^2 := 1972196^2$$

$$99027804^2 + 19720000^2 := 100972196^2$$

$$9999027804^2 + 197200000^2 := 10000972196^2$$

$$999999027804^2 + 1972000000^2 := 1000000972196^2$$

987)

$$25831^2 + 1974000^2 := 1974169^2$$

$$99025831^2 + 19740000^2 := 100974169^2$$

$$9999025831^2 + 197400000^2 := 10000974169^2$$

$$999999025831^2 + 1974000000^2 := 1000000974169^2$$

988)

$$23856^2 + 1976000^2 := 1976144^2$$

$$99023856^2 + 19760000^2 := 100976144^2$$

$$9999023856^2 + 197600000^2 := 10000976144^2$$

$$999999023856^2 + 1976000000^2 := 1000000976144^2$$

989)

$$21879^2 + 1978000^2 := 1978121^2$$

$$99021879^2 + 19780000^2 := 100978121^2$$

$$9999021879^2 + 197800000^2 := 10000978121^2$$

$$999999021879^2 + 1978000000^2 := 1000000978121^2$$

990)

$$19900^2 + 1980000^2 := 1980100^2$$

$$99019900^2 + 19800000^2 := 100980100^2$$

$$9999019900^2 + 198000000^2 := 10000980100^2$$

$$999999019900^2 + 1980000000^2 := 1000000980100^2$$

991)

$$17919^2 + 1982000^2 := 1982081^2$$

$$99017919^2 + 19820000^2 := 100982081^2$$

$$9999017919^2 + 198200000^2 := 10000982081^2$$

$$999999017919^2 + 1982000000^2 := 1000000982081^2$$

992)

$$15936^2 + 1984000^2 := 1984064^2$$

$$99015936^2 + 19840000^2 := 100984064^2$$

$$9999015936^2 + 198400000^2 := 10000984064^2$$

$$999999015936^2 + 1984000000^2 := 1000000984064^2$$

993)	$13951^2 + 1986000^2 := 1986049^2$ $99013951^2 + 19860000^2 := 100986049^2$ $9999013951^2 + 198600000^2 := 10000986049^2$ $999999013951^2 + 1986000000^2 := 1000000986049^2$	997)	$5991^2 + 1994000^2 := 1994009^2$ $99005991^2 + 19940000^2 := 100994009^2$ $9999005991^2 + 199400000^2 := 10000994009^2$ $999999005991^2 + 1994000000^2 := 1000000994009^2$
994)	$11964^2 + 1988000^2 := 1988036^2$ $99011964^2 + 19880000^2 := 100988036^2$ $9999011964^2 + 198800000^2 := 10000988036^2$ $999999011964^2 + 1988000000^2 := 1000000988036^2$	998)	$3996^2 + 1996000^2 := 1996004^2$ $99003996^2 + 19960000^2 := 100996004^2$ $9999003996^2 + 199600000^2 := 10000996004^2$ $999999003996^2 + 1996000000^2 := 1000000996004^2$
995)	$9975^2 + 1990000^2 := 1990025^2$ $99009975^2 + 19900000^2 := 100990025^2$ $9999009975^2 + 199000000^2 := 10000990025^2$ $999999009975^2 + 1990000000^2 := 1000000990025^2$	999)	$1999^2 + 1998000^2 := 1998001^2$ $99001999^2 + 19980000^2 := 100998001^2$ $9999001999^2 + 199800000^2 := 10000998001^2$ $999999001999^2 + 1998000000^2 := 1000000998001^2$
996)	$7984^2 + 1992000^2 := 1992016^2$ $99007984^2 + 19920000^2 := 100992016^2$ $9999007984^2 + 199200000^2 := 10000992016^2$ $999999007984^2 + 1992000000^2 := 1000000992016^2$		

4 Palindromic-Type Pandigital Patterns

4.1 First Block

Below are 9 **palindromic-type pandigital patterns** based on Pythagorean triples given in (3). There are two ways to write these patterns. One is normal **palindromic-type**, i.e., 1, 121, 12321, 1234321, ..., 12345678987654321 and second is **palindromic-type** with 0 between each digit, i.e., 1, 10201, 102030201, ..., 102030405060708090807060504030201.

4.1.1 First Way

Let's consider

$$(ii) \ m = 10, 1010, 101010, 10101010, 1010101010, 101010101010, 10101010101010, 1010101010101010, 101010101010101010$$

in (1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 8, 9$; below are 9 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns**:

1)

$$\begin{aligned}099^2 + 20^2 &= 101^2 \\12099^2 + 220^2 &= 12101^2 \\1232099^2 + 2220^2 &= 1232101^2 \\123432099^2 + 22220^2 &= 123432101^2 \\12345432099^2 + 222220^2 &= 12345432101^2 \\1234565432099^2 + 2222220^2 &= 1234565432101^2 \\123456765432099^2 + 22222220^2 &= 123456765432101^2 \\12345678765432099^2 + 222222220^2 &= 12345678765432101^2 \\1234567898765432099^2 + 2222222220^2 &= 1234567898765432101^2\end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned}096^2 + 40^2 &= 104^2 \\12096^2 + 440^2 &= 12104^2 \\1232096^2 + 4440^2 &= 1232104^2 \\123432096^2 + 44440^2 &= 123432104^2 \\12345432096^2 + 444440^2 &= 12345432104^2 \\1234565432096^2 + 4444440^2 &= 1234565432104^2 \\123456765432096^2 + 44444440^2 &= 123456765432104^2 \\12345678765432096^2 + 444444440^2 &= 12345678765432104^2 \\1234567898765432096^2 + 4444444440^2 &= 1234567898765432104^2\end{aligned}$$

3)

$$\begin{aligned}091^2 + 60^2 &= 109^2 \\12091^2 + 660^2 &= 12109^2 \\1232091^2 + 6660^2 &= 1232109^2 \\123432091^2 + 66660^2 &= 123432109^2 \\12345432091^2 + 666660^2 &= 12345432109^2 \\1234565432091^2 + 6666660^2 &= 1234565432109^2 \\123456765432091^2 + 66666660^2 &= 123456765432109^2 \\12345678765432091^2 + 666666660^2 &= 12345678765432109^2 \\1234567898765432091^2 + 6666666660^2 &= 1234567898765432109^2\end{aligned}$$

4)

$$\begin{aligned}084^2 + 80^2 &= \mathbf{1} 16^2 \\12 084^2 + 880^2 &= \mathbf{121} 16^2 \\1232 084^2 + 8880^2 &= \mathbf{12321} 16^2 \\123432 084^2 + 88880^2 &= \mathbf{1234321} 16^2 \\12345432 084^2 + 888880^2 &= \mathbf{123454321} 16^2 \\1234565432 084^2 + 8888880^2 &= \mathbf{12345654321} 16^2 \\123456765432 084^2 + 88888880^2 &= \mathbf{1234567654321} 16^2 \\12345678765432 084^2 + 888888880^2 &= \mathbf{123456787654321} 16^2 \\1234567898765432 084^2 + 8888888880^2 &= \mathbf{12345678987654321} 16^2\end{aligned}$$

5)

$$\begin{aligned}075^2 + 100^2 &= \mathbf{1} 25^2 \\12 075^2 + 1100^2 &= \mathbf{121} 25^2 \\1232 075^2 + 11100^2 &= \mathbf{12321} 25^2 \\123432 075^2 + 111100^2 &= \mathbf{1234321} 25^2 \\12345432 075^2 + 1111100^2 &= \mathbf{123454321} 25^2 \\1234565432 075^2 + 11111100^2 &= \mathbf{12345654321} 25^2 \\123456765432 075^2 + 111111100^2 &= \mathbf{1234567654321} 25^2 \\12345678765432 075^2 + 1111111100^2 &= \mathbf{123456787654321} 25^2 \\1234567898765432 075^2 + 11111111100^2 &= \mathbf{12345678987654321} 25^2\end{aligned}$$

6)

$$\begin{aligned}064^2 + 120^2 &= \mathbf{1} 36^2 \\12 064^2 + 1320^2 &= \mathbf{121} 36^2 \\1232 064^2 + 13320^2 &= \mathbf{12321} 36^2 \\123432 064^2 + 133320^2 &= \mathbf{1234321} 36^2 \\12345432 064^2 + 1333320^2 &= \mathbf{123454321} 36^2 \\1234565432 064^2 + 13333320^2 &= \mathbf{12345654321} 36^2 \\123456765432 064^2 + 133333320^2 &= \mathbf{1234567654321} 36^2 \\12345678765432 064^2 + 1333333320^2 &= \mathbf{123456787654321} 36^2 \\1234567898765432 064^2 + 13333333320^2 &= \mathbf{12345678987654321} 36^2\end{aligned}$$

7)

$$\begin{aligned}051^2 + 140^2 &= 149^2 \\12051^2 + 1540^2 &= 12149^2 \\1232051^2 + 15540^2 &= 1232149^2 \\123432051^2 + 155540^2 &= 123432149^2 \\12345432051^2 + 1555540^2 &= 12345432149^2 \\1234565432051^2 + 15555540^2 &= 1234565432149^2 \\123456765432051^2 + 155555540^2 &= 123456765432149^2 \\12345678765432051^2 + 1555555540^2 &= 12345678765432149^2 \\1234567898765432051^2 + 15555555540^2 &= 1234567898765432149^2\end{aligned}$$

8)

$$\begin{aligned}036^2 + 160^2 &= 164^2 \\12036^2 + 1760^2 &= 12164^2 \\1232036^2 + 17760^2 &= 1232164^2 \\123432036^2 + 177760^2 &= 123432164^2 \\12345432036^2 + 1777760^2 &= 12345432164^2 \\1234565432036^2 + 17777760^2 &= 1234565432164^2 \\123456765432036^2 + 177777760^2 &= 123456765432164^2 \\12345678765432036^2 + 1777777760^2 &= 12345678765432164^2 \\1234567898765432036^2 + 17777777760^2 &= 1234567898765432164^2\end{aligned}$$

9)

$$\begin{aligned}019^2 + 180^2 &= 181^2 \\12019^2 + 1980^2 &= 12181^2 \\1232019^2 + 19980^2 &= 1232181^2 \\123432019^2 + 199980^2 &= 123432181^2 \\12345432019^2 + 1999980^2 &= 12345432181^2 \\1234565432019^2 + 19999980^2 &= 1234565432181^2 \\123456765432019^2 + 199999980^2 &= 123456765432181^2 \\12345678765432019^2 + 1999999980^2 &= 12345678765432181^2 \\1234567898765432019^2 + 19999999980^2 &= 1234567898765432181^2\end{aligned}$$

4.1.2 Uniformity in Patterns

The above 9 patterns can also be written in the following way:

1)

$$\begin{aligned}099^2 + 20^2 &:= 101^2 \\12\ 099^2 + 220^2 &:= 12\ 101^2 \\1232\ 099^2 + 2220^2 &:= 1232\ 101^2 \\123432\ 099^2 + 22220^2 &:= 123432\ 101^2 \\12345432\ 099^2 + 222220^2 &:= 12345432\ 101^2 \\1234565432\ 099^2 + 2222220^2 &:= 1234565432\ 101^2 \\123456765432\ 099^2 + 22222220^2 &:= 123456765432\ 101^2 \\12345678765432\ 099^2 + 222222220^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 101^2 \\1234567898765432\ 099^2 + 2222222220^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 101^2\end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned}096^2 + 40^2 &:= 104^2 \\12\ 096^2 + 440^2 &:= 12\ 104^2 \\1232\ 096^2 + 4440^2 &:= 1232\ 104^2 \\123432\ 096^2 + 44440^2 &:= 123432\ 104^2 \\12345432\ 096^2 + 444440^2 &:= 12345432\ 104^2 \\1234565432\ 096^2 + 4444440^2 &:= 1234565432\ 104^2 \\123456765432\ 096^2 + 44444440^2 &:= 123456765432\ 104^2 \\12345678765432\ 096^2 + 444444440^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 104^2 \\1234567898765432\ 096^2 + 4444444440^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 104^2\end{aligned}$$

3)

$$\begin{aligned}091^2 + 60^2 &:= 109^2 \\12\ 091^2 + 660^2 &:= 12\ 109^2 \\1232\ 091^2 + 6660^2 &:= 1232\ 109^2 \\123432\ 091^2 + 66660^2 &:= 123432\ 109^2 \\12345432\ 091^2 + 666660^2 &:= 12345432\ 109^2 \\1234565432\ 091^2 + 6666660^2 &:= 1234565432\ 109^2 \\123456765432\ 091^2 + 66666660^2 &:= 123456765432\ 109^2 \\12345678765432\ 091^2 + 666666660^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 109^2 \\1234567898765432\ 091^2 + 6666666660^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 109^2\end{aligned}$$

4)

$$\begin{aligned}084^2 + 80^2 &:= 116^2 \\12\ 084^2 + 880^2 &:= 12\ 116^2 \\1232\ 084^2 + 8880^2 &:= 1232\ 116^2 \\123432\ 084^2 + 88880^2 &:= 123432\ 116^2 \\12345432\ 084^2 + 888880^2 &:= 12345432\ 116^2 \\1234565432\ 084^2 + 8888880^2 &:= 1234565432\ 116^2 \\123456765432\ 084^2 + 88888880^2 &:= 123456765432\ 116^2 \\12345678765432\ 084^2 + 888888880^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 116^2 \\1234567898765432\ 084^2 + 8888888880^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 116^2\end{aligned}$$

5)

$$\begin{aligned}075^2 + 100^2 &:= 125^2 \\12\ 075^2 + 1100^2 &:= 12\ 125^2 \\1232\ 075^2 + 11100^2 &:= 1232\ 125^2 \\123432\ 075^2 + 111100^2 &:= 123432\ 125^2 \\12345432\ 075^2 + 1111100^2 &:= 12345432\ 125^2 \\1234565432\ 075^2 + 11111100^2 &:= 1234565432\ 125^2 \\123456765432\ 075^2 + 111111100^2 &:= 123456765432\ 125^2 \\12345678765432\ 075^2 + 1111111100^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 125^2 \\1234567898765432\ 075^2 + 11111111100^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 125^2\end{aligned}$$

6)

$$\begin{aligned}064^2 + 120^2 &:= 136^2 \\12\ 064^2 + 1320^2 &:= 12\ 136^2 \\1232\ 064^2 + 13320^2 &:= 1232\ 136^2 \\123432\ 064^2 + 133320^2 &:= 123432\ 136^2 \\12345432\ 064^2 + 1333320^2 &:= 12345432\ 136^2 \\1234565432\ 064^2 + 13333320^2 &:= 1234565432\ 136^2 \\123456765432\ 064^2 + 133333320^2 &:= 123456765432\ 136^2 \\12345678765432\ 064^2 + 1333333320^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 136^2 \\1234567898765432\ 064^2 + 13333333320^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 136^2\end{aligned}$$

7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &051^2 + 140^2 && := 149^2 \\
 &12\ 051^2 + 1540^2 && := 12\ 149^2 \\
 &1232\ 051^2 + 15540^2 && := 1232\ 149^2 \\
 &123432\ 051^2 + 155540^2 && := 123432\ 149^2 \\
 &12345432\ 051^2 + 1555540^2 && := 12345432\ 149^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 051^2 + 15555540^2 && := 1234565432\ 149^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 051^2 + 155555540^2 && := 123456765432\ 149^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 051^2 + 1555555540^2 && := 12345678765432\ 149^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 051^2 + 15555555540^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 149^2
 \end{aligned}$$

8)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &036^2 + 160^2 && := 164^2 \\
 &12\ 036^2 + 1760^2 && := 12\ 164^2 \\
 &1232\ 036^2 + 17760^2 && := 1232\ 164^2 \\
 &123432\ 036^2 + 177760^2 && := 123432\ 164^2 \\
 &12345432\ 036^2 + 1777760^2 && := 12345432\ 164^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 036^2 + 17777760^2 && := 1234565432\ 164^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 036^2 + 177777760^2 && := 123456765432\ 164^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 036^2 + 1777777760^2 && := 12345678765432\ 164^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 036^2 + 17777777760^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 164^2
 \end{aligned}$$

9)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &019^2 + 180^2 && := 181^2 \\
 &12\ 019^2 + 1980^2 && := 12\ 181^2 \\
 &1232\ 019^2 + 19980^2 && := 1232\ 181^2 \\
 &123432\ 019^2 + 199980^2 && := 123432\ 181^2 \\
 &12345432\ 019^2 + 1999980^2 && := 12345432\ 181^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 019^2 + 19999980^2 && := 1234565432\ 181^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 019^2 + 199999980^2 && := 123456765432\ 181^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 019^2 + 1999999980^2 && := 12345678765432\ 181^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 019^2 + 19999999980^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 181^2
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1. We observe from above 9 patterns that there is beautiful uniformity in both sides. From now onwards, all the patterns of similar kind shall be written in a uniform way.

4.1.3 Second Way

Let's consider

$$(ii) \ m = 10, 1010, 101010, 10101010, 1010101010, 101010101010, 10101010101010, 1010101010101010, 101010101010101010$$

in (1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 8, 9$; below are 9 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns**:

1)

$$\begin{aligned} & 099^2 + 20^2 && := 101^2 \\ & 1020\ 099^2 + 2020^2 && := 1020\ 101^2 \\ & 10203020\ 099^2 + 202020^2 && := 10203020\ 101^2 \\ & 102030403020\ 099^2 + 20202020^2 && := 102030403020\ 101^2 \\ & 1020304050403020\ 099^2 + 2020202020^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 101^2 \\ & 10203040506050403020\ 099^2 + 202020202020^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 101^2 \\ & 102030405060706050403020\ 099^2 + 20202020202020^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 101^2 \\ & 1020304050607080706050403020\ 099^2 + 2020202020202020^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 101^2 \\ & 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 099^2 + 202020202020202020^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 101^2 \end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned} & 096^2 + 40^2 && := 104^2 \\ & 1020\ 096^2 + 4040^2 && := 1020\ 104^2 \\ & 10203020\ 096^2 + 404040^2 && := 10203020\ 104^2 \\ & 102030403020\ 096^2 + 40404040^2 && := 102030403020\ 104^2 \\ & 1020304050403020\ 096^2 + 4040404040^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 104^2 \\ & 10203040506050403020\ 096^2 + 404040404040^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 104^2 \\ & 102030405060706050403020\ 096^2 + 40404040404040^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 104^2 \\ & 1020304050607080706050403020\ 096^2 + 4040404040404040^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 104^2 \\ & 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 096^2 + 404040404040404040^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 104^2 \end{aligned}$$

3)

$$\begin{aligned} & 091^2 + 60^2 && := 109^2 \\ & 1020\ 091^2 + 6060^2 && := 1020\ 109^2 \\ & 10203020\ 091^2 + 606060^2 && := 10203020\ 109^2 \\ & 102030403020\ 091^2 + 60606060^2 && := 102030403020\ 109^2 \\ & 1020304050403020\ 091^2 + 6060606060^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 109^2 \\ & 10203040506050403020\ 091^2 + 606060606060^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 109^2 \\ & 102030405060706050403020\ 091^2 + 60606060606060^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 109^2 \\ & 1020304050607080706050403020\ 091^2 + 6060606060606060^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 109^2 \\ & 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 091^2 + 606060606060606060^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 109^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 4)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $084^2 + 80^2$ | $:= 116^2$ |
| $1020\ 084^2 + 8080^2$ | $:= 1020\ 116^2$ |
| $10203020\ 084^2 + 808080^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 116^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 084^2 + 80808080^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 116^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 084^2 + 8080808080^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 116^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 084^2 + 808080808080^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 116^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 084^2 + 80808080808080^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 116^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 084^2 + 8080808080808080^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 116^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 084^2 + 808080808080808080^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 116^2$ |
- 5)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $075^2 + 100^2$ | $:= 125^2$ |
| $1020\ 075^2 + 10100^2$ | $:= 1020\ 125^2$ |
| $10203020\ 075^2 + 1010100^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 125^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 075^2 + 101010100^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 125^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 075^2 + 10101010100^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 125^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 075^2 + 1010101010100^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 125^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 075^2 + 101010101010100^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 125^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 075^2 + 10101010101010100^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 125^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 075^2 + 1010101010101010100^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 125^2$ |
- 6)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $064^2 + 120^2$ | $:= 136^2$ |
| $1020\ 064^2 + 12120^2$ | $:= 1020\ 136^2$ |
| $10203020\ 064^2 + 1212120^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 136^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 064^2 + 121212120^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 136^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 064^2 + 12121212120^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 136^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 064^2 + 1212121212120^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 136^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 064^2 + 121212121212120^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 136^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 064^2 + 12121212121212120^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 136^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 064^2 + 1212121212121212120^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 136^2$ |
- 7)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $051^2 + 140^2$ | $:= 149^2$ |
| $1020\ 051^2 + 14140^2$ | $:= 1020\ 149^2$ |
| $10203020\ 051^2 + 1414140^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 149^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 051^2 + 141414140^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 149^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 051^2 + 14141414140^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 149^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 051^2 + 1414141414140^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 149^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 051^2 + 141414141414140^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 149^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 051^2 + 14141414141414140^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 149^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 051^2 + 1414141414141414140^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 149^2$ |

8)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &036^2 + 160^2 && := 164^2 \\
 &1020\ 036^2 + 16160^2 && := 1020\ 164^2 \\
 &10203020\ 036^2 + 1616160^2 && := 10203020\ 164^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 036^2 + 161616160^2 && := 102030403020\ 164^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 036^2 + 16161616160^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 164^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 036^2 + 1616161616160^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 164^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 036^2 + 161616161616160^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 164^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 036^2 + 16161616161616160^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 164^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 036^2 + 1616161616161616160^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 164^2
 \end{aligned}$$

9)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &019^2 + 180^2 && := 181^2 \\
 &1020\ 019^2 + 18180^2 && := 1020\ 181^2 \\
 &10203020\ 019^2 + 1818180^2 && := 10203020\ 181^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 019^2 + 181818180^2 && := 102030403020\ 181^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 019^2 + 18181818180^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 181^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 019^2 + 1818181818180^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 181^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 019^2 + 181818181818180^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 181^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 019^2 + 18181818181818180^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 181^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 019^2 + 1818181818181818180^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 181^2
 \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Second Block

Below are 99 examples of **palindromic-type pandigital patterns** written in uniform way. These are divided in two parts. First part is without 0 and the second part is with 0. These are based on Pythagorean triples given in (5) or (6)

4.2.1 First Way

Let's consider

$$(iii) \ m = 100, 1100, 11100, 111100, 1111100, 11111100, 111111100, 1111111100, 11111111100$$

in (1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 99$; below are 99 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns**:

1)

$$\begin{aligned} &09999^2 + 200^2 && := 10001^2 \\ &12\ 09999^2 + 2200^2 && := 12\ 10001^2 \\ &1232\ 09999^2 + 22200^2 && := 1232\ 10001^2 \\ &123432\ 09999^2 + 222200^2 && := 123432\ 10001^2 \\ &12345432\ 09999^2 + 2222200^2 && := 12345432\ 10001^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09999^2 + 22222200^2 && := 1234565432\ 10001^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09999^2 + 222222200^2 && := 123456765432\ 10001^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09999^2 + 2222222200^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10001^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09999^2 + 22222222200^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10001^2 \end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned} &09996^2 + 400^2 && := 10004^2 \\ &12\ 09996^2 + 4400^2 && := 12\ 10004^2 \\ &1232\ 09996^2 + 44400^2 && := 1232\ 10004^2 \\ &123432\ 09996^2 + 444400^2 && := 123432\ 10004^2 \\ &12345432\ 09996^2 + 4444400^2 && := 12345432\ 10004^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09996^2 + 44444400^2 && := 1234565432\ 10004^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09996^2 + 444444400^2 && := 123456765432\ 10004^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09996^2 + 4444444400^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10004^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09996^2 + 44444444400^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10004^2 \end{aligned}$$

3)

$$\begin{aligned} &09991^2 + 600^2 && := 10009^2 \\ &12\ 09991^2 + 6600^2 && := 12\ 10009^2 \\ &1232\ 09991^2 + 66600^2 && := 1232\ 10009^2 \\ &123432\ 09991^2 + 666600^2 && := 123432\ 10009^2 \\ &12345432\ 09991^2 + 6666600^2 && := 12345432\ 10009^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09991^2 + 66666600^2 && := 1234565432\ 10009^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09991^2 + 666666600^2 && := 123456765432\ 10009^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09991^2 + 6666666600^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10009^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09991^2 + 66666666600^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10009^2 \end{aligned}$$

4)

$$\begin{aligned}09984^2 + 800^2 &:= 10016^2 \\12\ 09984^2 + 8800^2 &:= 12\ 10016^2 \\1232\ 09984^2 + 88800^2 &:= 1232\ 10016^2 \\123432\ 09984^2 + 888800^2 &:= 123432\ 10016^2 \\12345432\ 09984^2 + 8888800^2 &:= 12345432\ 10016^2 \\1234565432\ 09984^2 + 88888800^2 &:= 1234565432\ 10016^2 \\123456765432\ 09984^2 + 888888800^2 &:= 123456765432\ 10016^2 \\12345678765432\ 09984^2 + 8888888800^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 10016^2 \\1234567898765432\ 09984^2 + 88888888800^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 10016^2\end{aligned}$$

5)

$$\begin{aligned}09975^2 + 1000^2 &:= 10025^2 \\12\ 09975^2 + 11000^2 &:= 12\ 10025^2 \\1232\ 09975^2 + 111000^2 &:= 1232\ 10025^2 \\123432\ 09975^2 + 1111000^2 &:= 123432\ 10025^2 \\12345432\ 09975^2 + 11111000^2 &:= 12345432\ 10025^2 \\1234565432\ 09975^2 + 111111000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 10025^2 \\123456765432\ 09975^2 + 1111111000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 10025^2 \\12345678765432\ 09975^2 + 11111111000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 10025^2 \\1234567898765432\ 09975^2 + 111111111000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 10025^2\end{aligned}$$

6)

$$\begin{aligned}09964^2 + 1200^2 &:= 10036^2 \\12\ 09964^2 + 13200^2 &:= 12\ 10036^2 \\1232\ 09964^2 + 133200^2 &:= 1232\ 10036^2 \\123432\ 09964^2 + 1333200^2 &:= 123432\ 10036^2 \\12345432\ 09964^2 + 13333200^2 &:= 12345432\ 10036^2 \\1234565432\ 09964^2 + 133333200^2 &:= 1234565432\ 10036^2 \\123456765432\ 09964^2 + 1333333200^2 &:= 123456765432\ 10036^2 \\12345678765432\ 09964^2 + 13333333200^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 10036^2 \\1234567898765432\ 09964^2 + 133333333200^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 10036^2\end{aligned}$$

7)

$$\begin{aligned} &09951^2 + 1400^2 &:=& 10049^2 \\ &12\ 09951^2 + 15400^2 &:=& 12\ 10049^2 \\ &1232\ 09951^2 + 155400^2 &:=& 1232\ 10049^2 \\ &123432\ 09951^2 + 1555400^2 &:=& 123432\ 10049^2 \\ &12345432\ 09951^2 + 15555400^2 &:=& 12345432\ 10049^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09951^2 + 155555400^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 10049^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09951^2 + 1555555400^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 10049^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09951^2 + 15555555400^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 10049^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09951^2 + 155555555400^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 10049^2 \end{aligned}$$

8)

$$\begin{aligned} &09936^2 + 1600^2 &:=& 10064^2 \\ &12\ 09936^2 + 17600^2 &:=& 12\ 10064^2 \\ &1232\ 09936^2 + 177600^2 &:=& 1232\ 10064^2 \\ &123432\ 09936^2 + 1777600^2 &:=& 123432\ 10064^2 \\ &12345432\ 09936^2 + 17777600^2 &:=& 12345432\ 10064^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09936^2 + 177777600^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 10064^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09936^2 + 1777777600^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 10064^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09936^2 + 17777777600^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 10064^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09936^2 + 177777777600^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 10064^2 \end{aligned}$$

9)

$$\begin{aligned} &09919^2 + 1800^2 &:=& 10081^2 \\ &12\ 09919^2 + 19800^2 &:=& 12\ 10081^2 \\ &1232\ 09919^2 + 199800^2 &:=& 1232\ 10081^2 \\ &123432\ 09919^2 + 1999800^2 &:=& 123432\ 10081^2 \\ &12345432\ 09919^2 + 19999800^2 &:=& 12345432\ 10081^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09919^2 + 199999800^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 10081^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09919^2 + 1999999800^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 10081^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09919^2 + 19999999800^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 10081^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09919^2 + 199999999800^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 10081^2 \end{aligned}$$

10)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09900^2 + 2000^2 & := & 10100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09900^2 + 22000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09900^2 + 222000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09900^2 + 2222000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09900^2 + 22222000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09900^2 + 222222000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09900^2 + 2222222000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09900^2 + 22222222000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09900^2 + 222222222000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10100^2 \end{aligned}$$

11)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09879^2 + 2200^2 & := & 10121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09879^2 + 24200^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09879^2 + 244200^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10121^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09879^2 + 2444200^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09879^2 + 24444200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09879^2 + 244444200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10121^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09879^2 + 2444444200^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09879^2 + 24444444200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09879^2 + 244444444200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10121^2 \end{aligned}$$

12)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09856^2 + 2400^2 & := & 10144^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09856^2 + 26400^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10144^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09856^2 + 266400^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10144^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09856^2 + 2666400^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10144^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09856^2 + 26666400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10144^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09856^2 + 266666400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10144^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09856^2 + 2666666400^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10144^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09856^2 + 26666666400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10144^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09856^2 + 266666666400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10144^2 \end{aligned}$$

13)

$$\begin{aligned} &09831^2 + 2600^2 &:=& 10169^2 \\ &12\ 09831^2 + 28600^2 &:=& 12\ 10169^2 \\ &1232\ 09831^2 + 288600^2 &:=& 1232\ 10169^2 \\ &123432\ 09831^2 + 2888600^2 &:=& 123432\ 10169^2 \\ &12345432\ 09831^2 + 28888600^2 &:=& 12345432\ 10169^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09831^2 + 288888600^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 10169^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09831^2 + 2888888600^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 10169^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09831^2 + 28888888600^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 10169^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09831^2 + 288888888600^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 10169^2 \end{aligned}$$

14)

$$\begin{aligned} &09804^2 + 2800^2 &:=& 10196^2 \\ &12\ 09804^2 + 30800^2 &:=& 12\ 10196^2 \\ &1232\ 09804^2 + 310800^2 &:=& 1232\ 10196^2 \\ &123432\ 09804^2 + 3110800^2 &:=& 123432\ 10196^2 \\ &12345432\ 09804^2 + 31110800^2 &:=& 12345432\ 10196^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09804^2 + 311110800^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 10196^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09804^2 + 3111110800^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 10196^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09804^2 + 31111110800^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 10196^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09804^2 + 311111110800^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 10196^2 \end{aligned}$$

15)

$$\begin{aligned} &09775^2 + 3000^2 &:=& 10225^2 \\ &12\ 09775^2 + 33000^2 &:=& 12\ 10225^2 \\ &1232\ 09775^2 + 333000^2 &:=& 1232\ 10225^2 \\ &123432\ 09775^2 + 3333000^2 &:=& 123432\ 10225^2 \\ &12345432\ 09775^2 + 33333000^2 &:=& 12345432\ 10225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09775^2 + 333333000^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 10225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09775^2 + 3333333000^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 10225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09775^2 + 33333333000^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 10225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09775^2 + 333333333000^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 10225^2 \end{aligned}$$

16)

$$\begin{aligned} &09744^2 + 3200^2 && := 10256^2 \\ &12\ 09744^2 + 35200^2 && := 12\ 10256^2 \\ &1232\ 09744^2 + 355200^2 && := 1232\ 10256^2 \\ &123432\ 09744^2 + 3555200^2 && := 123432\ 10256^2 \\ &12345432\ 09744^2 + 35555200^2 && := 12345432\ 10256^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09744^2 + 355555200^2 && := 1234565432\ 10256^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09744^2 + 3555555200^2 && := 123456765432\ 10256^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09744^2 + 35555555200^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10256^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09744^2 + 355555555200^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10256^2 \end{aligned}$$

17)

$$\begin{aligned} &09711^2 + 3400^2 && := 10289^2 \\ &12\ 09711^2 + 37400^2 && := 12\ 10289^2 \\ &1232\ 09711^2 + 377400^2 && := 1232\ 10289^2 \\ &123432\ 09711^2 + 3777400^2 && := 123432\ 10289^2 \\ &12345432\ 09711^2 + 37777400^2 && := 12345432\ 10289^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09711^2 + 377777400^2 && := 1234565432\ 10289^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09711^2 + 3777777400^2 && := 123456765432\ 10289^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09711^2 + 37777777400^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10289^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09711^2 + 377777777400^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10289^2 \end{aligned}$$

18)

$$\begin{aligned} &09676^2 + 3600^2 && := 10324^2 \\ &12\ 09676^2 + 39600^2 && := 12\ 10324^2 \\ &1232\ 09676^2 + 399600^2 && := 1232\ 10324^2 \\ &123432\ 09676^2 + 3999600^2 && := 123432\ 10324^2 \\ &12345432\ 09676^2 + 39999600^2 && := 12345432\ 10324^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09676^2 + 399999600^2 && := 1234565432\ 10324^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09676^2 + 3999999600^2 && := 123456765432\ 10324^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09676^2 + 39999999600^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10324^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09676^2 + 399999999600^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10324^2 \end{aligned}$$

19)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09639^2 + 3800^2 & := & 10361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09639^2 + 41800^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09639^2 + 421800^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10361^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09639^2 + 4221800^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09639^2 + 42221800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09639^2 + 422221800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10361^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09639^2 + 4222221800^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09639^2 + 42222221800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09639^2 + 422222221800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10361^2 \end{aligned}$$

20)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09600^2 + 4000^2 & := & 10400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09600^2 + 44000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09600^2 + 444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09600^2 + 4444000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09600^2 + 44444000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09600^2 + 444444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09600^2 + 4444444000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09600^2 + 44444444000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09600^2 + 444444444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10400^2 \end{aligned}$$

21)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09559^2 + 4200^2 & := & 10441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09559^2 + 46200^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09559^2 + 466200^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10441^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09559^2 + 4666200^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09559^2 + 46666200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09559^2 + 466666200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10441^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09559^2 + 4666666200^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09559^2 + 46666666200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09559^2 + 466666666200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10441^2 \end{aligned}$$

22)

$$\begin{aligned} &09516^2 + 4400^2 && := 10484^2 \\ &12\ 09516^2 + 48400^2 && := 12\ 10484^2 \\ &1232\ 09516^2 + 488400^2 && := 1232\ 10484^2 \\ &123432\ 09516^2 + 4888400^2 && := 123432\ 10484^2 \\ &12345432\ 09516^2 + 48888400^2 && := 12345432\ 10484^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09516^2 + 488888400^2 && := 1234565432\ 10484^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09516^2 + 4888888400^2 && := 123456765432\ 10484^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09516^2 + 48888888400^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10484^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09516^2 + 488888888400^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10484^2 \end{aligned}$$

23)

$$\begin{aligned} &09471^2 + 4600^2 && := 10529^2 \\ &12\ 09471^2 + 50600^2 && := 12\ 10529^2 \\ &1232\ 09471^2 + 510600^2 && := 1232\ 10529^2 \\ &123432\ 09471^2 + 5110600^2 && := 123432\ 10529^2 \\ &12345432\ 09471^2 + 51110600^2 && := 12345432\ 10529^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09471^2 + 511110600^2 && := 1234565432\ 10529^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09471^2 + 5111110600^2 && := 123456765432\ 10529^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09471^2 + 51111110600^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10529^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09471^2 + 511111110600^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10529^2 \end{aligned}$$

24)

$$\begin{aligned} &09424^2 + 4800^2 && := 10576^2 \\ &12\ 09424^2 + 52800^2 && := 12\ 10576^2 \\ &1232\ 09424^2 + 532800^2 && := 1232\ 10576^2 \\ &123432\ 09424^2 + 5332800^2 && := 123432\ 10576^2 \\ &12345432\ 09424^2 + 53332800^2 && := 12345432\ 10576^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09424^2 + 533332800^2 && := 1234565432\ 10576^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09424^2 + 5333332800^2 && := 123456765432\ 10576^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09424^2 + 53333332800^2 && := 12345678765432\ 10576^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09424^2 + 533333332800^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 10576^2 \end{aligned}$$

25)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09375^2 + 5000^2 & := & 10625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09375^2 + 55000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09375^2 + 555000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09375^2 + 5555000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09375^2 + 55555000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09375^2 + 555555000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09375^2 + 5555555000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09375^2 + 55555555000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09375^2 + 555555555000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10625^2 \end{aligned}$$

26)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09324^2 + 5200^2 & := & 10676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09324^2 + 57200^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09324^2 + 577200^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10676^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09324^2 + 5777200^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09324^2 + 57777200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09324^2 + 577777200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10676^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09324^2 + 5777777200^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09324^2 + 57777777200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09324^2 + 577777777200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10676^2 \end{aligned}$$

27)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09271^2 + 5400^2 & := & 10729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09271^2 + 59400^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09271^2 + 599400^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09271^2 + 5999400^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09271^2 + 59999400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09271^2 + 599999400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09271^2 + 5999999400^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09271^2 + 59999999400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09271^2 + 599999999400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10729^2 \end{aligned}$$

28)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09216^2 + 5600^2 & := & 10784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09216^2 + 61600^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09216^2 + 621600^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10784^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09216^2 + 6221600^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09216^2 + 62221600^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09216^2 + 622221600^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10784^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09216^2 + 6222221600^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09216^2 + 62222221600^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09216^2 + 622222221600^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10784^2 \end{aligned}$$

29)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09159^2 + 5800^2 & := & 10841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09159^2 + 63800^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09159^2 + 643800^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09159^2 + 6443800^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09159^2 + 64443800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09159^2 + 644443800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09159^2 + 6444443800^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09159^2 + 64444443800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09159^2 + 644444443800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10841^2 \end{aligned}$$

30)

$$\begin{aligned} & 09100^2 + 6000^2 & := & 10900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 09100^2 + 66000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 10900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 09100^2 + 666000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 10900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 09100^2 + 6666000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 10900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 09100^2 + 66666000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 10900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 09100^2 + 666666000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 10900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 09100^2 + 6666666000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 10900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 09100^2 + 66666666000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 10900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 09100^2 + 666666666000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 10900^2 \end{aligned}$$

31)

$$\begin{aligned} &09039^2 + 6200^2 &:=& 10961^2 \\ &12\ 09039^2 + 68200^2 &:=& 12\ 10961^2 \\ &1232\ 09039^2 + 688200^2 &:=& 1232\ 10961^2 \\ &123432\ 09039^2 + 6888200^2 &:=& 123432\ 10961^2 \\ &12345432\ 09039^2 + 68888200^2 &:=& 12345432\ 10961^2 \\ &1234565432\ 09039^2 + 688888200^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 10961^2 \\ &123456765432\ 09039^2 + 6888888200^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 10961^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 09039^2 + 68888888200^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 10961^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 09039^2 + 688888888200^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 10961^2 \end{aligned}$$

32)

$$\begin{aligned} &08976^2 + 6400^2 &:=& 11024^2 \\ &12\ 08976^2 + 70400^2 &:=& 12\ 11024^2 \\ &1232\ 08976^2 + 710400^2 &:=& 1232\ 11024^2 \\ &123432\ 08976^2 + 7110400^2 &:=& 123432\ 11024^2 \\ &12345432\ 08976^2 + 71110400^2 &:=& 12345432\ 11024^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08976^2 + 711110400^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 11024^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08976^2 + 7111110400^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 11024^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08976^2 + 71111110400^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 11024^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08976^2 + 711111110400^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 11024^2 \end{aligned}$$

33)

$$\begin{aligned} &08911^2 + 6600^2 &:=& 11089^2 \\ &12\ 08911^2 + 72600^2 &:=& 12\ 11089^2 \\ &1232\ 08911^2 + 732600^2 &:=& 1232\ 11089^2 \\ &123432\ 08911^2 + 7332600^2 &:=& 123432\ 11089^2 \\ &12345432\ 08911^2 + 73332600^2 &:=& 12345432\ 11089^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08911^2 + 733332600^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 11089^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08911^2 + 7333332600^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 11089^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08911^2 + 73333332600^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 11089^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08911^2 + 733333332600^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 11089^2 \end{aligned}$$

34)

$$\begin{aligned} &08844^2 + 6800^2 && := 11156^2 \\ &12\ 08844^2 + 74800^2 && := 12\ 11156^2 \\ &1232\ 08844^2 + 754800^2 && := 1232\ 11156^2 \\ &123432\ 08844^2 + 7554800^2 && := 123432\ 11156^2 \\ &12345432\ 08844^2 + 75554800^2 && := 12345432\ 11156^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08844^2 + 755554800^2 && := 1234565432\ 11156^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08844^2 + 7555554800^2 && := 123456765432\ 11156^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08844^2 + 75555554800^2 && := 12345678765432\ 11156^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08844^2 + 755555554800^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 11156^2 \end{aligned}$$

35)

$$\begin{aligned} &08775^2 + 7000^2 && := 11225^2 \\ &12\ 08775^2 + 77000^2 && := 12\ 11225^2 \\ &1232\ 08775^2 + 777000^2 && := 1232\ 11225^2 \\ &123432\ 08775^2 + 7777000^2 && := 123432\ 11225^2 \\ &12345432\ 08775^2 + 77777000^2 && := 12345432\ 11225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08775^2 + 777777000^2 && := 1234565432\ 11225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08775^2 + 7777777000^2 && := 123456765432\ 11225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08775^2 + 77777777000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 11225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08775^2 + 777777777000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 11225^2 \end{aligned}$$

36)

$$\begin{aligned} &08704^2 + 7200^2 && := 11296^2 \\ &12\ 08704^2 + 79200^2 && := 12\ 11296^2 \\ &1232\ 08704^2 + 799200^2 && := 1232\ 11296^2 \\ &123432\ 08704^2 + 7999200^2 && := 123432\ 11296^2 \\ &12345432\ 08704^2 + 79999200^2 && := 12345432\ 11296^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08704^2 + 799999200^2 && := 1234565432\ 11296^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08704^2 + 7999999200^2 && := 123456765432\ 11296^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08704^2 + 79999999200^2 && := 12345678765432\ 11296^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08704^2 + 799999999200^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 11296^2 \end{aligned}$$

37)

$$\begin{aligned} & 08631^2 + 7400^2 & := & 11369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 08631^2 + 81400^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 11369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 08631^2 + 821400^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 11369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 08631^2 + 8221400^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 11369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 08631^2 + 82221400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 11369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 08631^2 + 822221400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 11369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 08631^2 + 8222221400^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 11369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 08631^2 + 82222221400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 11369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 08631^2 + 822222221400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 11369^2 \end{aligned}$$

38)

$$\begin{aligned} & 08556^2 + 7600^2 & := & 11444^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 08556^2 + 83600^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 11444^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 08556^2 + 843600^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 11444^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 08556^2 + 8443600^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 11444^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 08556^2 + 84443600^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 11444^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 08556^2 + 844443600^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 11444^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 08556^2 + 8444443600^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 11444^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 08556^2 + 84444443600^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 11444^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 08556^2 + 844444443600^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 11444^2 \end{aligned}$$

39)

$$\begin{aligned} & 08479^2 + 7800^2 & := & 11521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 08479^2 + 85800^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 11521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 08479^2 + 865800^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 11521^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 08479^2 + 8665800^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 11521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 08479^2 + 86665800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 11521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 08479^2 + 866665800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 11521^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 08479^2 + 8666665800^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 11521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 08479^2 + 86666665800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 11521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 08479^2 + 866666665800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 11521^2 \end{aligned}$$

40)

$$\begin{aligned} &08400^2 + 8000^2 && := 11600^2 \\ &12\ 08400^2 + 88000^2 && := 12\ 11600^2 \\ &1232\ 08400^2 + 888000^2 && := 1232\ 11600^2 \\ &123432\ 08400^2 + 8888000^2 && := 123432\ 11600^2 \\ &12345432\ 08400^2 + 88888000^2 && := 12345432\ 11600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08400^2 + 888888000^2 && := 1234565432\ 11600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08400^2 + 8888888000^2 && := 123456765432\ 11600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08400^2 + 88888888000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 11600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08400^2 + 888888888000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 11600^2 \end{aligned}$$

41)

$$\begin{aligned} &08319^2 + 8200^2 && := 11681^2 \\ &12\ 08319^2 + 90200^2 && := 12\ 11681^2 \\ &1232\ 08319^2 + 910200^2 && := 1232\ 11681^2 \\ &123432\ 08319^2 + 9110200^2 && := 123432\ 11681^2 \\ &12345432\ 08319^2 + 91110200^2 && := 12345432\ 11681^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08319^2 + 911110200^2 && := 1234565432\ 11681^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08319^2 + 9111110200^2 && := 123456765432\ 11681^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08319^2 + 91111110200^2 && := 12345678765432\ 11681^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08319^2 + 911111110200^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 11681^2 \end{aligned}$$

42)

$$\begin{aligned} &08236^2 + 8400^2 && := 11764^2 \\ &12\ 08236^2 + 92400^2 && := 12\ 11764^2 \\ &1232\ 08236^2 + 932400^2 && := 1232\ 11764^2 \\ &123432\ 08236^2 + 9332400^2 && := 123432\ 11764^2 \\ &12345432\ 08236^2 + 93332400^2 && := 12345432\ 11764^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08236^2 + 933332400^2 && := 1234565432\ 11764^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08236^2 + 9333332400^2 && := 123456765432\ 11764^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08236^2 + 93333332400^2 && := 12345678765432\ 11764^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08236^2 + 933333332400^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 11764^2 \end{aligned}$$

43)

$$\begin{aligned} &08151^2 + 8600^2 &:=& 11849^2 \\ &12\ 08151^2 + 94600^2 &:=& 12\ 11849^2 \\ &1232\ 08151^2 + 954600^2 &:=& 1232\ 11849^2 \\ &123432\ 08151^2 + 9554600^2 &:=& 123432\ 11849^2 \\ &12345432\ 08151^2 + 95554600^2 &:=& 12345432\ 11849^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08151^2 + 955554600^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 11849^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08151^2 + 9555554600^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 11849^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08151^2 + 95555554600^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 11849^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08151^2 + 955555554600^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 11849^2 \end{aligned}$$

44)

$$\begin{aligned} &08064^2 + 8800^2 &:=& 11936^2 \\ &12\ 08064^2 + 96800^2 &:=& 12\ 11936^2 \\ &1232\ 08064^2 + 976800^2 &:=& 1232\ 11936^2 \\ &123432\ 08064^2 + 9776800^2 &:=& 123432\ 11936^2 \\ &12345432\ 08064^2 + 97776800^2 &:=& 12345432\ 11936^2 \\ &1234565432\ 08064^2 + 977776800^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 11936^2 \\ &123456765432\ 08064^2 + 9777776800^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 11936^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 08064^2 + 97777776800^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 11936^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 08064^2 + 977777776800^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 11936^2 \end{aligned}$$

45)

$$\begin{aligned} &07975^2 + 9000^2 &:=& 12025^2 \\ &12\ 07975^2 + 99000^2 &:=& 12\ 12025^2 \\ &1232\ 07975^2 + 999000^2 &:=& 1232\ 12025^2 \\ &123432\ 07975^2 + 9999000^2 &:=& 123432\ 12025^2 \\ &12345432\ 07975^2 + 99999000^2 &:=& 12345432\ 12025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 07975^2 + 999999000^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 12025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 07975^2 + 9999999000^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 12025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 07975^2 + 99999999000^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 12025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 07975^2 + 999999999000^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 12025^2 \end{aligned}$$

46)

$$\begin{aligned} &07884^2 + 9200^2 &&:= 12116^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 07884^2 + 101200^2 &&:= \mathbf{12} 12116^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 07884^2 + 1021200^2 &&:= \mathbf{1232} 12116^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 07884^2 + 10221200^2 &&:= \mathbf{123432} 12116^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 07884^2 + 102221200^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345432} 12116^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 07884^2 + 1022221200^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234565432} 12116^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 07884^2 + 10222221200^2 &&:= \mathbf{123456765432} 12116^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 07884^2 + 102222221200^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 12116^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 07884^2 + 1022222221200^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 12116^2 \end{aligned}$$

47)

$$\begin{aligned} &07791^2 + 9400^2 &&:= 12209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 07791^2 + 103400^2 &&:= \mathbf{12} 12209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 07791^2 + 1043400^2 &&:= \mathbf{1232} 12209^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 07791^2 + 10443400^2 &&:= \mathbf{123432} 12209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 07791^2 + 104443400^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345432} 12209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 07791^2 + 1044443400^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234565432} 12209^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 07791^2 + 10444443400^2 &&:= \mathbf{123456765432} 12209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 07791^2 + 104444443400^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 12209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 07791^2 + 1044444443400^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 12209^2 \end{aligned}$$

48)

$$\begin{aligned} &07696^2 + 9600^2 &&:= 12304^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 07696^2 + 105600^2 &&:= \mathbf{12} 12304^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 07696^2 + 1065600^2 &&:= \mathbf{1232} 12304^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 07696^2 + 10665600^2 &&:= \mathbf{123432} 12304^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 07696^2 + 106665600^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345432} 12304^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 07696^2 + 1066665600^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234565432} 12304^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 07696^2 + 10666665600^2 &&:= \mathbf{123456765432} 12304^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 07696^2 + 106666665600^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 12304^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 07696^2 + 1066666665600^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 12304^2 \end{aligned}$$

49)

$$\begin{aligned} &07599^2 + 9800^2 && := 12401^2 \\ &12\ 07599^2 + 107800^2 && := 12\ 12401^2 \\ &1232\ 07599^2 + 1087800^2 && := 1232\ 12401^2 \\ &123432\ 07599^2 + 10887800^2 && := 123432\ 12401^2 \\ &12345432\ 07599^2 + 108887800^2 && := 12345432\ 12401^2 \\ &1234565432\ 07599^2 + 1088887800^2 && := 1234565432\ 12401^2 \\ &123456765432\ 07599^2 + 10888887800^2 && := 123456765432\ 12401^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 07599^2 + 108888887800^2 && := 12345678765432\ 12401^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 07599^2 + 1088888887800^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 12401^2 \end{aligned}$$

50)

$$\begin{aligned} &07500^2 + 10000^2 && := 12500^2 \\ &12\ 07500^2 + 110000^2 && := 12\ 12500^2 \\ &1232\ 07500^2 + 1110000^2 && := 1232\ 12500^2 \\ &123432\ 07500^2 + 11110000^2 && := 123432\ 12500^2 \\ &12345432\ 07500^2 + 111110000^2 && := 12345432\ 12500^2 \\ &1234565432\ 07500^2 + 1111110000^2 && := 1234565432\ 12500^2 \\ &123456765432\ 07500^2 + 11111110000^2 && := 123456765432\ 12500^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 07500^2 + 111111110000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 12500^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 07500^2 + 1111111110000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 12500^2 \end{aligned}$$

51)

$$\begin{aligned} &07399^2 + 10200^2 && := 12601^2 \\ &12\ 07399^2 + 112200^2 && := 12\ 12601^2 \\ &1232\ 07399^2 + 1132200^2 && := 1232\ 12601^2 \\ &123432\ 07399^2 + 11332200^2 && := 123432\ 12601^2 \\ &12345432\ 07399^2 + 113332200^2 && := 12345432\ 12601^2 \\ &1234565432\ 07399^2 + 1133332200^2 && := 1234565432\ 12601^2 \\ &123456765432\ 07399^2 + 11333332200^2 && := 123456765432\ 12601^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 07399^2 + 113333332200^2 && := 12345678765432\ 12601^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 07399^2 + 1133333332200^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 12601^2 \end{aligned}$$

52)

$$\begin{aligned}07296^2 + 10400^2 &:= 12704^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 07296^2 + 114400^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 12704^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 07296^2 + 1154400^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 12704^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 07296^2 + 11554400^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 12704^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 07296^2 + 115554400^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 12704^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 07296^2 + 1155554400^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 12704^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 07296^2 + 11555554400^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 12704^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 07296^2 + 115555554400^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 12704^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 07296^2 + 1155555554400^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 12704^2\end{aligned}$$

53)

$$\begin{aligned}07191^2 + 10600^2 &:= 12809^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 07191^2 + 116600^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 12809^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 07191^2 + 1176600^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 12809^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 07191^2 + 11776600^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 12809^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 07191^2 + 117776600^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 12809^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 07191^2 + 1177776600^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 12809^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 07191^2 + 11777776600^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 12809^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 07191^2 + 117777776600^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 12809^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 07191^2 + 1177777776600^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 12809^2\end{aligned}$$

54)

$$\begin{aligned}07084^2 + 10800^2 &:= 12916^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 07084^2 + 118800^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 12916^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 07084^2 + 1198800^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 12916^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 07084^2 + 11998800^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 12916^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 07084^2 + 119998800^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 12916^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 07084^2 + 1199998800^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 12916^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 07084^2 + 11999998800^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 12916^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 07084^2 + 119999998800^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 12916^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 07084^2 + 1199999998800^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 12916^2\end{aligned}$$

55)

$$\begin{aligned} & 06975^2 + 11000^2 & := & 13025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 06975^2 + 121000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 13025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 06975^2 + 1221000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 13025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 06975^2 + 12221000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 13025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 06975^2 + 122221000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 13025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 06975^2 + 1222221000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 13025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 06975^2 + 12222221000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 13025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 06975^2 + 122222221000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 13025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 06975^2 + 1222222221000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 13025^2 \end{aligned}$$

56)

$$\begin{aligned} & 06864^2 + 11200^2 & := & 13136^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 06864^2 + 123200^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 13136^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 06864^2 + 1243200^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 13136^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 06864^2 + 12443200^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 13136^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 06864^2 + 124443200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 13136^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 06864^2 + 1244443200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 13136^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 06864^2 + 12444443200^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 13136^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 06864^2 + 124444443200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 13136^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 06864^2 + 1244444443200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 13136^2 \end{aligned}$$

57)

$$\begin{aligned} & 06751^2 + 11400^2 & := & 13249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 06751^2 + 125400^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 13249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 06751^2 + 1265400^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 13249^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 06751^2 + 12665400^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 13249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 06751^2 + 126665400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 13249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 06751^2 + 1266665400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 13249^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 06751^2 + 12666665400^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 13249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 06751^2 + 126666665400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 13249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 06751^2 + 1266666665400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 13249^2 \end{aligned}$$

58)

$$\begin{aligned}06636^2 + 11600^2 &:= 13364^2 \\12\ 06636^2 + 127600^2 &:= 12\ 13364^2 \\1232\ 06636^2 + 1287600^2 &:= 1232\ 13364^2 \\123432\ 06636^2 + 12887600^2 &:= 123432\ 13364^2 \\12345432\ 06636^2 + 128887600^2 &:= 12345432\ 13364^2 \\1234565432\ 06636^2 + 1288887600^2 &:= 1234565432\ 13364^2 \\123456765432\ 06636^2 + 12888887600^2 &:= 123456765432\ 13364^2 \\12345678765432\ 06636^2 + 128888887600^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 13364^2 \\1234567898765432\ 06636^2 + 1288888887600^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 13364^2\end{aligned}$$

59)

$$\begin{aligned}06519^2 + 11800^2 &:= 13481^2 \\12\ 06519^2 + 129800^2 &:= 12\ 13481^2 \\1232\ 06519^2 + 1309800^2 &:= 1232\ 13481^2 \\123432\ 06519^2 + 13109800^2 &:= 123432\ 13481^2 \\12345432\ 06519^2 + 131109800^2 &:= 12345432\ 13481^2 \\1234565432\ 06519^2 + 1311109800^2 &:= 1234565432\ 13481^2 \\123456765432\ 06519^2 + 13111109800^2 &:= 123456765432\ 13481^2 \\12345678765432\ 06519^2 + 131111109800^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 13481^2 \\1234567898765432\ 06519^2 + 1311111109800^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 13481^2\end{aligned}$$

60)

$$\begin{aligned}06400^2 + 12000^2 &:= 13600^2 \\12\ 06400^2 + 132000^2 &:= 12\ 13600^2 \\1232\ 06400^2 + 1332000^2 &:= 1232\ 13600^2 \\123432\ 06400^2 + 13332000^2 &:= 123432\ 13600^2 \\12345432\ 06400^2 + 133332000^2 &:= 12345432\ 13600^2 \\1234565432\ 06400^2 + 1333332000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 13600^2 \\123456765432\ 06400^2 + 13333332000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 13600^2 \\12345678765432\ 06400^2 + 133333332000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 13600^2 \\1234567898765432\ 06400^2 + 1333333332000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 13600^2\end{aligned}$$

61)

$$\begin{aligned}06279^2 + 12200^2 &:= 13721^2 \\12\ 06279^2 + 134200^2 &:= 12\ 13721^2 \\1232\ 06279^2 + 1354200^2 &:= 1232\ 13721^2 \\123432\ 06279^2 + 13554200^2 &:= 123432\ 13721^2 \\12345432\ 06279^2 + 135554200^2 &:= 12345432\ 13721^2 \\1234565432\ 06279^2 + 1355554200^2 &:= 1234565432\ 13721^2 \\123456765432\ 06279^2 + 13555554200^2 &:= 123456765432\ 13721^2 \\12345678765432\ 06279^2 + 135555554200^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 13721^2 \\1234567898765432\ 06279^2 + 1355555554200^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 13721^2\end{aligned}$$

62)

$$\begin{aligned}06156^2 + 12400^2 &:= 13844^2 \\12\ 06156^2 + 136400^2 &:= 12\ 13844^2 \\1232\ 06156^2 + 1376400^2 &:= 1232\ 13844^2 \\123432\ 06156^2 + 13776400^2 &:= 123432\ 13844^2 \\12345432\ 06156^2 + 137776400^2 &:= 12345432\ 13844^2 \\1234565432\ 06156^2 + 1377776400^2 &:= 1234565432\ 13844^2 \\123456765432\ 06156^2 + 13777776400^2 &:= 123456765432\ 13844^2 \\12345678765432\ 06156^2 + 137777776400^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 13844^2 \\1234567898765432\ 06156^2 + 1377777776400^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 13844^2\end{aligned}$$

63)

$$\begin{aligned}06031^2 + 12600^2 &:= 13969^2 \\12\ 06031^2 + 138600^2 &:= 12\ 13969^2 \\1232\ 06031^2 + 1398600^2 &:= 1232\ 13969^2 \\123432\ 06031^2 + 13998600^2 &:= 123432\ 13969^2 \\12345432\ 06031^2 + 139998600^2 &:= 12345432\ 13969^2 \\1234565432\ 06031^2 + 1399998600^2 &:= 1234565432\ 13969^2 \\123456765432\ 06031^2 + 13999998600^2 &:= 123456765432\ 13969^2 \\12345678765432\ 06031^2 + 139999998600^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 13969^2 \\1234567898765432\ 06031^2 + 1399999998600^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 13969^2\end{aligned}$$

64)

$$\begin{aligned} &05904^2 + 12800^2 && := 14096^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 05904^2 + 140800^2 && := \mathbf{12} 14096^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 05904^2 + 1420800^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 14096^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 05904^2 + 14220800^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 14096^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 05904^2 + 142220800^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 14096^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 05904^2 + 1422220800^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 14096^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 05904^2 + 14222220800^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 14096^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 05904^2 + 142222220800^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 14096^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 05904^2 + 1422222220800^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 14096^2 \end{aligned}$$

65)

$$\begin{aligned} &05775^2 + 13000^2 && := 14225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 05775^2 + 143000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 14225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 05775^2 + 1443000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 14225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 05775^2 + 14443000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 14225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 05775^2 + 144443000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 14225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 05775^2 + 1444443000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 14225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 05775^2 + 14444443000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 14225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 05775^2 + 144444443000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 14225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 05775^2 + 1444444443000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 14225^2 \end{aligned}$$

66)

$$\begin{aligned} &05644^2 + 13200^2 && := 14356^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 05644^2 + 145200^2 && := \mathbf{12} 14356^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 05644^2 + 1465200^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 14356^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 05644^2 + 14665200^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 14356^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 05644^2 + 146665200^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 14356^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 05644^2 + 1466665200^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 14356^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 05644^2 + 14666665200^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 14356^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 05644^2 + 146666665200^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 14356^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 05644^2 + 1466666665200^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 14356^2 \end{aligned}$$

67)

$$\begin{aligned} & 05511^2 + 13400^2 & := & 14489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 05511^2 + 147400^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 14489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 05511^2 + 1487400^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 14489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 05511^2 + 14887400^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 14489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 05511^2 + 148887400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 14489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 05511^2 + 1488887400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 14489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 05511^2 + 14888887400^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 14489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 05511^2 + 148888887400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 14489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 05511^2 + 1488888887400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 14489^2 \end{aligned}$$

68)

$$\begin{aligned} & 05376^2 + 13600^2 & := & 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 05376^2 + 149600^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 05376^2 + 1509600^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 05376^2 + 15109600^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 05376^2 + 151109600^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 05376^2 + 1511109600^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 05376^2 + 15111109600^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 05376^2 + 151111109600^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 05376^2 + 1511111109600^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 14624^2 \end{aligned}$$

69)

$$\begin{aligned} & 05239^2 + 13800^2 & := & 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 05239^2 + 151800^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 05239^2 + 1531800^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 05239^2 + 15331800^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 05239^2 + 153331800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 05239^2 + 1533331800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 05239^2 + 15333331800^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 05239^2 + 153333331800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 05239^2 + 1533333331800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 14761^2 \end{aligned}$$

70)

$$\begin{aligned} &05100^2 + 14000^2 && := 14900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 05100^2 + 154000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 14900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 05100^2 + 1554000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 14900^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 05100^2 + 15554000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 14900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 05100^2 + 155554000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 14900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 05100^2 + 1555554000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 14900^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 05100^2 + 15555554000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 14900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 05100^2 + 155555554000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 14900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 05100^2 + 1555555554000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 14900^2 \end{aligned}$$

71)

$$\begin{aligned} &04959^2 + 14200^2 && := 15041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 04959^2 + 156200^2 && := \mathbf{12} 15041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 04959^2 + 1576200^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 15041^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 04959^2 + 15776200^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 15041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 04959^2 + 157776200^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 15041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 04959^2 + 1577776200^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 15041^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 04959^2 + 15777776200^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 15041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 04959^2 + 157777776200^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 15041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 04959^2 + 1577777776200^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 15041^2 \end{aligned}$$

72)

$$\begin{aligned} &04816^2 + 14400^2 && := 15184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 04816^2 + 158400^2 && := \mathbf{12} 15184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 04816^2 + 1598400^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 15184^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 04816^2 + 15998400^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 15184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 04816^2 + 159998400^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 15184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 04816^2 + 1599998400^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 15184^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 04816^2 + 15999998400^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 15184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 04816^2 + 159999998400^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 15184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 04816^2 + 1599999998400^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 15184^2 \end{aligned}$$

73)

$$\begin{aligned}04671^2 + 14600^2 &:= 15329^2 \\12\ 04671^2 + 160600^2 &:= 12\ 15329^2 \\1232\ 04671^2 + 1620600^2 &:= 1232\ 15329^2 \\123432\ 04671^2 + 16220600^2 &:= 123432\ 15329^2 \\12345432\ 04671^2 + 162220600^2 &:= 12345432\ 15329^2 \\1234565432\ 04671^2 + 1622220600^2 &:= 1234565432\ 15329^2 \\123456765432\ 04671^2 + 16222220600^2 &:= 123456765432\ 15329^2 \\12345678765432\ 04671^2 + 162222220600^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 15329^2 \\1234567898765432\ 04671^2 + 1622222220600^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 15329^2\end{aligned}$$

74)

$$\begin{aligned}04524^2 + 14800^2 &:= 15476^2 \\12\ 04524^2 + 162800^2 &:= 12\ 15476^2 \\1232\ 04524^2 + 1642800^2 &:= 1232\ 15476^2 \\123432\ 04524^2 + 16442800^2 &:= 123432\ 15476^2 \\12345432\ 04524^2 + 164442800^2 &:= 12345432\ 15476^2 \\1234565432\ 04524^2 + 1644442800^2 &:= 1234565432\ 15476^2 \\123456765432\ 04524^2 + 16444442800^2 &:= 123456765432\ 15476^2 \\12345678765432\ 04524^2 + 164444442800^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 15476^2 \\1234567898765432\ 04524^2 + 1644444442800^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 15476^2\end{aligned}$$

75)

$$\begin{aligned}04375^2 + 15000^2 &:= 15625^2 \\12\ 04375^2 + 165000^2 &:= 12\ 15625^2 \\1232\ 04375^2 + 1665000^2 &:= 1232\ 15625^2 \\123432\ 04375^2 + 16665000^2 &:= 123432\ 15625^2 \\12345432\ 04375^2 + 166665000^2 &:= 12345432\ 15625^2 \\1234565432\ 04375^2 + 1666665000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 15625^2 \\123456765432\ 04375^2 + 16666665000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 15625^2 \\12345678765432\ 04375^2 + 166666665000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 15625^2 \\1234567898765432\ 04375^2 + 1666666665000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 15625^2\end{aligned}$$

76)

$$\begin{aligned}04224^2 + 15200^2 &:= 15776^2 \\12\ 04224^2 + 167200^2 &:= 12\ 15776^2 \\1232\ 04224^2 + 1687200^2 &:= 1232\ 15776^2 \\123432\ 04224^2 + 16887200^2 &:= 123432\ 15776^2 \\12345432\ 04224^2 + 168887200^2 &:= 12345432\ 15776^2 \\1234565432\ 04224^2 + 1688887200^2 &:= 1234565432\ 15776^2 \\123456765432\ 04224^2 + 16888887200^2 &:= 123456765432\ 15776^2 \\12345678765432\ 04224^2 + 168888887200^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 15776^2 \\1234567898765432\ 04224^2 + 1688888887200^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 15776^2\end{aligned}$$

77)

$$\begin{aligned}04071^2 + 15400^2 &:= 15929^2 \\12\ 04071^2 + 169400^2 &:= 12\ 15929^2 \\1232\ 04071^2 + 1709400^2 &:= 1232\ 15929^2 \\123432\ 04071^2 + 17109400^2 &:= 123432\ 15929^2 \\12345432\ 04071^2 + 171109400^2 &:= 12345432\ 15929^2 \\1234565432\ 04071^2 + 1711109400^2 &:= 1234565432\ 15929^2 \\123456765432\ 04071^2 + 17111109400^2 &:= 123456765432\ 15929^2 \\12345678765432\ 04071^2 + 171111109400^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 15929^2 \\1234567898765432\ 04071^2 + 1711111109400^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 15929^2\end{aligned}$$

78)

$$\begin{aligned}03916^2 + 15600^2 &:= 16084^2 \\12\ 03916^2 + 171600^2 &:= 12\ 16084^2 \\1232\ 03916^2 + 1731600^2 &:= 1232\ 16084^2 \\123432\ 03916^2 + 17331600^2 &:= 123432\ 16084^2 \\12345432\ 03916^2 + 173331600^2 &:= 12345432\ 16084^2 \\1234565432\ 03916^2 + 1733331600^2 &:= 1234565432\ 16084^2 \\123456765432\ 03916^2 + 17333331600^2 &:= 123456765432\ 16084^2 \\12345678765432\ 03916^2 + 173333331600^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 16084^2 \\1234567898765432\ 03916^2 + 1733333331600^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 16084^2\end{aligned}$$

79)

$$\begin{aligned} & 03759^2 + 15800^2 & := & 16241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 03759^2 + 173800^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 16241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 03759^2 + 1753800^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 16241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 03759^2 + 17553800^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 16241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 03759^2 + 175553800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 16241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 03759^2 + 1755553800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 16241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 03759^2 + 17555553800^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 16241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 03759^2 + 175555553800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 16241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 03759^2 + 1755555553800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 16241^2 \end{aligned}$$

80)

$$\begin{aligned} & 03600^2 + 16000^2 & := & 16400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 03600^2 + 176000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 16400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 03600^2 + 1776000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 16400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 03600^2 + 17776000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 16400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 03600^2 + 177776000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 16400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 03600^2 + 1777776000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 16400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 03600^2 + 17777776000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 16400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 03600^2 + 177777776000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 16400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 03600^2 + 1777777776000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 16400^2 \end{aligned}$$

81)

$$\begin{aligned} & 03439^2 + 16200^2 & := & 16561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 03439^2 + 178200^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 16561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 03439^2 + 1798200^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 16561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 03439^2 + 17998200^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 16561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 03439^2 + 179998200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 16561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 03439^2 + 1799998200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 16561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 03439^2 + 17999998200^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 16561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 03439^2 + 179999998200^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 16561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 03439^2 + 1799999998200^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 16561^2 \end{aligned}$$

82)

$$\begin{aligned} &03276^2 + 16400^2 && := 16724^2 \\ &12\ 03276^2 + 180400^2 && := 12\ 16724^2 \\ &1232\ 03276^2 + 1820400^2 && := 1232\ 16724^2 \\ &123432\ 03276^2 + 18220400^2 && := 123432\ 16724^2 \\ &12345432\ 03276^2 + 182220400^2 && := 12345432\ 16724^2 \\ &1234565432\ 03276^2 + 1822220400^2 && := 1234565432\ 16724^2 \\ &123456765432\ 03276^2 + 18222220400^2 && := 123456765432\ 16724^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 03276^2 + 182222220400^2 && := 12345678765432\ 16724^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 03276^2 + 1822222220400^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 16724^2 \end{aligned}$$

83)

$$\begin{aligned} &03111^2 + 16600^2 && := 16889^2 \\ &12\ 03111^2 + 182600^2 && := 12\ 16889^2 \\ &1232\ 03111^2 + 1842600^2 && := 1232\ 16889^2 \\ &123432\ 03111^2 + 18442600^2 && := 123432\ 16889^2 \\ &12345432\ 03111^2 + 184442600^2 && := 12345432\ 16889^2 \\ &1234565432\ 03111^2 + 1844442600^2 && := 1234565432\ 16889^2 \\ &123456765432\ 03111^2 + 18444442600^2 && := 123456765432\ 16889^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 03111^2 + 184444442600^2 && := 12345678765432\ 16889^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 03111^2 + 1844444442600^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 16889^2 \end{aligned}$$

84)

$$\begin{aligned} &02944^2 + 16800^2 && := 17056^2 \\ &12\ 02944^2 + 184800^2 && := 12\ 17056^2 \\ &1232\ 02944^2 + 1864800^2 && := 1232\ 17056^2 \\ &123432\ 02944^2 + 18664800^2 && := 123432\ 17056^2 \\ &12345432\ 02944^2 + 186664800^2 && := 12345432\ 17056^2 \\ &1234565432\ 02944^2 + 1866664800^2 && := 1234565432\ 17056^2 \\ &123456765432\ 02944^2 + 18666664800^2 && := 123456765432\ 17056^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 02944^2 + 186666664800^2 && := 12345678765432\ 17056^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 02944^2 + 1866666664800^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 17056^2 \end{aligned}$$

85)

$$\begin{aligned} &02775^2 + 17000^2 && := 17225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 02775^2 + 187000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 17225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 02775^2 + 1887000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 17225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 02775^2 + 18887000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 17225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 02775^2 + 188887000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 17225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 02775^2 + 1888887000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 17225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 02775^2 + 18888887000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 17225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 02775^2 + 188888887000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 17225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 02775^2 + 1888888887000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 17225^2 \end{aligned}$$

86)

$$\begin{aligned} &02604^2 + 17200^2 && := 17396^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 02604^2 + 189200^2 && := \mathbf{12} 17396^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 02604^2 + 1909200^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 17396^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 02604^2 + 19109200^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 17396^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 02604^2 + 191109200^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 17396^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 02604^2 + 1911109200^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 17396^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 02604^2 + 19111109200^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 17396^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 02604^2 + 191111109200^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 17396^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 02604^2 + 1911111109200^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 17396^2 \end{aligned}$$

87)

$$\begin{aligned} &02431^2 + 17400^2 && := 17569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 02431^2 + 191400^2 && := \mathbf{12} 17569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 02431^2 + 1931400^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 17569^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 02431^2 + 19331400^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 17569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 02431^2 + 193331400^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 17569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 02431^2 + 1933331400^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 17569^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 02431^2 + 19333331400^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 17569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 02431^2 + 193333331400^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 17569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 02431^2 + 1933333331400^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 17569^2 \end{aligned}$$

88)

$$\begin{aligned} &02256^2 + 17600^2 && := 17744^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 02256^2 + 193600^2 && := \mathbf{12} 17744^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 02256^2 + 1953600^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 17744^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 02256^2 + 19553600^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 17744^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 02256^2 + 195553600^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 17744^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 02256^2 + 1955553600^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 17744^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 02256^2 + 19555553600^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 17744^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 02256^2 + 195555553600^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 17744^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 02256^2 + 1955555553600^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 17744^2 \end{aligned}$$

89)

$$\begin{aligned} &02079^2 + 17800^2 && := 17921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 02079^2 + 195800^2 && := \mathbf{12} 17921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 02079^2 + 1975800^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 17921^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 02079^2 + 19775800^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 17921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 02079^2 + 197775800^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 17921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 02079^2 + 1977775800^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 17921^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 02079^2 + 19777775800^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 17921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 02079^2 + 197777775800^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 17921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 02079^2 + 1977777775800^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 17921^2 \end{aligned}$$

90)

$$\begin{aligned} &01900^2 + 18000^2 && := 18100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 01900^2 + 198000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 18100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 01900^2 + 1998000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 18100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 01900^2 + 19998000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 18100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 01900^2 + 199998000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 18100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 01900^2 + 1999998000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 18100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 01900^2 + 19999998000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 18100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 01900^2 + 199999998000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 18100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 01900^2 + 1999999998000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 18100^2 \end{aligned}$$

91)

$$\begin{aligned}01719^2 + 18200^2 &:= 18281^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 01719^2 + 200200^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 18281^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 01719^2 + 2020200^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 18281^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 01719^2 + 20220200^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 18281^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 01719^2 + 202220200^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 18281^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 01719^2 + 2022220200^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 18281^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 01719^2 + 20222220200^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 18281^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 01719^2 + 202222220200^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 18281^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 01719^2 + 2022222220200^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 18281^2\end{aligned}$$

92)

$$\begin{aligned}01536^2 + 18400^2 &:= 18464^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 01536^2 + 202400^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 18464^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 01536^2 + 2042400^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 18464^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 01536^2 + 20442400^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 18464^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 01536^2 + 204442400^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 18464^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 01536^2 + 2044442400^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 18464^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 01536^2 + 20444442400^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 18464^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 01536^2 + 204444442400^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 18464^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 01536^2 + 2044444442400^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 18464^2\end{aligned}$$

93)

$$\begin{aligned}01351^2 + 18600^2 &:= 18649^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 01351^2 + 204600^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 18649^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 01351^2 + 2064600^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 18649^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 01351^2 + 20664600^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 18649^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 01351^2 + 206664600^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 18649^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 01351^2 + 2066664600^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 18649^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 01351^2 + 20666664600^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 18649^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 01351^2 + 206666664600^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 18649^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 01351^2 + 2066666664600^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 18649^2\end{aligned}$$

94)

$$\begin{aligned}01164^2 + 18800^2 &:= 18836^2 \\12\ 01164^2 + 206800^2 &:= 12\ 18836^2 \\1232\ 01164^2 + 2086800^2 &:= 1232\ 18836^2 \\123432\ 01164^2 + 20886800^2 &:= 123432\ 18836^2 \\12345432\ 01164^2 + 208886800^2 &:= 12345432\ 18836^2 \\1234565432\ 01164^2 + 2088886800^2 &:= 1234565432\ 18836^2 \\123456765432\ 01164^2 + 20888886800^2 &:= 123456765432\ 18836^2 \\12345678765432\ 01164^2 + 208888886800^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 18836^2 \\1234567898765432\ 01164^2 + 2088888886800^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 18836^2\end{aligned}$$

95)

$$\begin{aligned}00975^2 + 19000^2 &:= 19025^2 \\12\ 00975^2 + 209000^2 &:= 12\ 19025^2 \\1232\ 00975^2 + 2109000^2 &:= 1232\ 19025^2 \\123432\ 00975^2 + 21109000^2 &:= 123432\ 19025^2 \\12345432\ 00975^2 + 211109000^2 &:= 12345432\ 19025^2 \\1234565432\ 00975^2 + 2111109000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 19025^2 \\123456765432\ 00975^2 + 21111109000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 19025^2 \\12345678765432\ 00975^2 + 211111109000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 19025^2 \\1234567898765432\ 00975^2 + 2111111109000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 19025^2\end{aligned}$$

96)

$$\begin{aligned}00784^2 + 19200^2 &:= 19216^2 \\12\ 00784^2 + 211200^2 &:= 12\ 19216^2 \\1232\ 00784^2 + 2131200^2 &:= 1232\ 19216^2 \\123432\ 00784^2 + 21331200^2 &:= 123432\ 19216^2 \\12345432\ 00784^2 + 213331200^2 &:= 12345432\ 19216^2 \\1234565432\ 00784^2 + 2133331200^2 &:= 1234565432\ 19216^2 \\123456765432\ 00784^2 + 21333331200^2 &:= 123456765432\ 19216^2 \\12345678765432\ 00784^2 + 213333331200^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 19216^2 \\1234567898765432\ 00784^2 + 2133333331200^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 19216^2\end{aligned}$$

97)

$$\begin{aligned} & 00591^2 + 19400^2 & := & 19409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 00591^2 + 213400^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 19409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 00591^2 + 2153400^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 19409^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 00591^2 + 21553400^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 19409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 00591^2 + 215553400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 19409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 00591^2 + 2155553400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 19409^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 00591^2 + 21555553400^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 19409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 00591^2 + 215555553400^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 19409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 00591^2 + 2155555553400^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 19409^2 \end{aligned}$$

98)

$$\begin{aligned} & 00396^2 + 19600^2 & := & 19604^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 00396^2 + 215600^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 19604^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 00396^2 + 2175600^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 19604^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 00396^2 + 21775600^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 19604^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 00396^2 + 217775600^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 19604^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 00396^2 + 2177775600^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 19604^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 00396^2 + 21777775600^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 19604^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 00396^2 + 217777775600^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 19604^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 00396^2 + 2177777775600^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 19604^2 \end{aligned}$$

99)

$$\begin{aligned} & 00199^2 + 19800^2 & := & 19801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 00199^2 + 217800^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 19801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 00199^2 + 2197800^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 19801^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 00199^2 + 21997800^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 19801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 00199^2 + 219997800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 19801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 00199^2 + 2199997800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 19801^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 00199^2 + 21999997800^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 19801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 00199^2 + 219999997800^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 19801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 00199^2 + 2199999997800^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 19801^2 \end{aligned}$$

4.2.2 Second Way

Let's consider

(iv) $m = 100, 10100, 1010100, 101010100, 10101010100, 1010101010100, 101010101010100, 10101010101010100, 10101010101010100.$

in (1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 99$; below are 99 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns**:

1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09999^2 + 200^2 && := 10001^2 \\
 &1020\ 09999^2 + 20200^2 && := 1020\ 10001^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09999^2 + 2020200^2 && := 10203020\ 10001^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09999^2 + 202020200^2 && := 102030403020\ 10001^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09999^2 + 20202020200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10001^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09999^2 + 2020202020200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10001^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09999^2 + 202020202020200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10001^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09999^2 + 20202020202020200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10001^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09999^2 + 2020202020202020200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10001^2
 \end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09996^2 + 400^2 && := 10004^2 \\
 &1020\ 09996^2 + 40400^2 && := 1020\ 10004^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09996^2 + 4040400^2 && := 10203020\ 10004^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09996^2 + 404040400^2 && := 102030403020\ 10004^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09996^2 + 40404040400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10004^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09996^2 + 4040404040400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10004^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09996^2 + 404040404040400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10004^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09996^2 + 40404040404040400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10004^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09996^2 + 4040404040404040400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10004^2
 \end{aligned}$$

3)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09991^2 + 600^2 && := 10009^2 \\
 &1020\ 09991^2 + 60600^2 && := 1020\ 10009^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09991^2 + 6060600^2 && := 10203020\ 10009^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09991^2 + 606060600^2 && := 102030403020\ 10009^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09991^2 + 60606060600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10009^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09991^2 + 6060606060600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10009^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09991^2 + 606060606060600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10009^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09991^2 + 60606060606060600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10009^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09991^2 + 6060606060606060600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10009^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 4)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &09984^2 + 800^2 && := 10016^2 \\
 &1020\ 09984^2 + 80800^2 && := 1020\ 10016^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09984^2 + 8080800^2 && := 10203020\ 10016^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09984^2 + 808080800^2 && := 102030403020\ 10016^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09984^2 + 80808080800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10016^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09984^2 + 8080808080800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10016^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09984^2 + 808080808080800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10016^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09984^2 + 80808080808080800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10016^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09984^2 + 8080808080808080800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10016^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 5)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &09975^2 + 1000^2 && := 10025^2 \\
 &1020\ 09975^2 + 101000^2 && := 1020\ 10025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09975^2 + 10101000^2 && := 10203020\ 10025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09975^2 + 1010101000^2 && := 102030403020\ 10025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09975^2 + 101010101000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09975^2 + 10101010101000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09975^2 + 1010101010101000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09975^2 + 101010101010101000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09975^2 + 10101010101010101000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 6)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &09964^2 + 1200^2 && := 10036^2 \\
 &1020\ 09964^2 + 121200^2 && := 1020\ 10036^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09964^2 + 12121200^2 && := 10203020\ 10036^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09964^2 + 1212121200^2 && := 102030403020\ 10036^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09964^2 + 121212121200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10036^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09964^2 + 12121212121200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10036^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09964^2 + 1212121212121200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10036^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09964^2 + 121212121212121200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10036^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09964^2 + 12121212121212121200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10036^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 7)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &09951^2 + 1400^2 && := 10049^2 \\
 &1020\ 09951^2 + 141400^2 && := 1020\ 10049^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09951^2 + 14141400^2 && := 10203020\ 10049^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09951^2 + 1414141400^2 && := 102030403020\ 10049^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09951^2 + 141414141400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10049^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09951^2 + 14141414141400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10049^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09951^2 + 1414141414141400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10049^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09951^2 + 141414141414141400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10049^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09951^2 + 14141414141414141400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10049^2
 \end{aligned}$$

8)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09936^2 + 1600^2 && := 10064^2 \\
 &1020\ 09936^2 + 161600^2 && := 1020\ 10064^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09936^2 + 16161600^2 && := 10203020\ 10064^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09936^2 + 1616161600^2 && := 102030403020\ 10064^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09936^2 + 161616161600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10064^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09936^2 + 16161616161600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10064^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09936^2 + 1616161616161600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10064^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09936^2 + 161616161616161600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10064^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09936^2 + 16161616161616161600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10064^2
 \end{aligned}$$

9)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09919^2 + 1800^2 && := 10081^2 \\
 &1020\ 09919^2 + 181800^2 && := 1020\ 10081^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09919^2 + 18181800^2 && := 10203020\ 10081^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09919^2 + 1818181800^2 && := 102030403020\ 10081^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09919^2 + 181818181800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10081^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09919^2 + 18181818181800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10081^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09919^2 + 1818181818181800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10081^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09919^2 + 181818181818181800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10081^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09919^2 + 18181818181818181800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10081^2
 \end{aligned}$$

10)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09900^2 + 2000^2 && := 10100^2 \\
 &1020\ 09900^2 + 202000^2 && := 1020\ 10100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09900^2 + 20202000^2 && := 10203020\ 10100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09900^2 + 2020202000^2 && := 102030403020\ 10100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09900^2 + 202020202000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09900^2 + 20202020202000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09900^2 + 2020202020202000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09900^2 + 202020202020202000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09900^2 + 20202020202020202000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10100^2
 \end{aligned}$$

11)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09879^2 + 2200^2 && := 010121^2 \\
 &102009879^2 + 222200^2 && := 102010121^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09879^2 + 2222200^2 && := 10203020\ 10121^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09879^2 + 22222200^2 && := 102030403020\ 10121^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09879^2 + 222222200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10121^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09879^2 + 2222222200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10121^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09879^2 + 22222222200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10121^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09879^2 + 222222222200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10121^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09879^2 + 2222222222200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10121^2
 \end{aligned}$$

12)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09856^2 + 2400^2 && := 10144^2 \\
 &1020\ 09856^2 + 242400^2 && := 1020\ 10144^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09856^2 + 24242400^2 && := 10203020\ 10144^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09856^2 + 2424242400^2 && := 102030403020\ 10144^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09856^2 + 242424242400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10144^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09856^2 + 24242424242400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10144^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09856^2 + 2424242424242400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10144^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09856^2 + 242424242424242400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10144^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09856^2 + 24242424242424242400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10144^2
 \end{aligned}$$

13)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09831^2 + 2600^2 && := 10169^2 \\
 &1020\ 09831^2 + 262600^2 && := 1020\ 10169^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09831^2 + 26262600^2 && := 10203020\ 10169^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09831^2 + 2626262600^2 && := 102030403020\ 10169^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09831^2 + 262626262600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10169^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09831^2 + 26262626262600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10169^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09831^2 + 2626262626262600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10169^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09831^2 + 262626262626262600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10169^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09831^2 + 26262626262626262600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10169^2
 \end{aligned}$$

14)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09804^2 + 2800^2 && := 10196^2 \\
 &1020\ 09804^2 + 282800^2 && := 1020\ 10196^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09804^2 + 28282800^2 && := 10203020\ 10196^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09804^2 + 2828282800^2 && := 102030403020\ 10196^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09804^2 + 282828282800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10196^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09804^2 + 28282828282800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10196^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09804^2 + 2828282828282800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10196^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09804^2 + 282828282828282800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10196^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09804^2 + 28282828282828282800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10196^2
 \end{aligned}$$

15)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09775^2 + 3000^2 && := 10225^2 \\
 &1020\ 09775^2 + 303000^2 && := 1020\ 10225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09775^2 + 30303000^2 && := 10203020\ 10225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09775^2 + 3030303000^2 && := 102030403020\ 10225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09775^2 + 303030303000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09775^2 + 30303030303000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09775^2 + 3030303030303000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09775^2 + 303030303030303000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09775^2 + 30303030303030303000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10225^2
 \end{aligned}$$

16)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09744^2 + 3200^2 && := 10256^2 \\
 &1020\ 09744^2 + 323200^2 && := 1020\ 10256^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09744^2 + 32323200^2 && := 10203020\ 10256^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09744^2 + 3232323200^2 && := 102030403020\ 10256^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09744^2 + 323232323200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10256^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09744^2 + 32323232323200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10256^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09744^2 + 3232323232323200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10256^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09744^2 + 323232323232323200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10256^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09744^2 + 32323232323232323200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10256^2
 \end{aligned}$$

17)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09711^2 + 3400^2 && := 10289^2 \\
 &1020\ 09711^2 + 343400^2 && := 1020\ 10289^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09711^2 + 34343400^2 && := 10203020\ 10289^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09711^2 + 3434343400^2 && := 102030403020\ 10289^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09711^2 + 343434343400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10289^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09711^2 + 34343434343400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10289^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09711^2 + 3434343434343400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10289^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09711^2 + 343434343434343400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10289^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09711^2 + 34343434343434343400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10289^2
 \end{aligned}$$

18)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09676^2 + 3600^2 && := 10324^2 \\
 &1020\ 09676^2 + 363600^2 && := 1020\ 10324^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09676^2 + 36363600^2 && := 10203020\ 10324^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09676^2 + 3636363600^2 && := 102030403020\ 10324^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09676^2 + 363636363600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10324^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09676^2 + 36363636363600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10324^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09676^2 + 3636363636363600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10324^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09676^2 + 363636363636363600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10324^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09676^2 + 36363636363636363600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10324^2
 \end{aligned}$$

19)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09639^2 + 3800^2 && := 10361^2 \\
 &1020\ 09639^2 + 383800^2 && := 1020\ 10361^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09639^2 + 38383800^2 && := 10203020\ 10361^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09639^2 + 3838383800^2 && := 102030403020\ 10361^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09639^2 + 383838383800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10361^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09639^2 + 38383838383800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10361^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09639^2 + 3838383838383800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10361^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09639^2 + 383838383838383800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10361^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09639^2 + 38383838383838383800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10361^2
 \end{aligned}$$

20)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09600^2 + 4000^2 && := 10400^2 \\
 &1020\ 09600^2 + 404000^2 && := 1020\ 10400^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09600^2 + 40404000^2 && := 10203020\ 10400^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09600^2 + 4040404000^2 && := 102030403020\ 10400^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09600^2 + 404040404000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10400^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09600^2 + 40404040404000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10400^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09600^2 + 4040404040404000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10400^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09600^2 + 404040404040404000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10400^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09600^2 + 40404040404040404000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10400^2
 \end{aligned}$$

21)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09559^2 + 4200^2 && := 10441^2 \\
 &1020\ 09559^2 + 424200^2 && := 1020\ 10441^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09559^2 + 42424200^2 && := 10203020\ 10441^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09559^2 + 4242424200^2 && := 102030403020\ 10441^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09559^2 + 424242424200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10441^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09559^2 + 42424242424200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10441^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09559^2 + 4242424242424200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10441^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09559^2 + 424242424242424200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10441^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09559^2 + 42424242424242424200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10441^2
 \end{aligned}$$

22)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09516^2 + 4400^2 && := 10484^2 \\
 &1020\ 09516^2 + 444400^2 && := 1020\ 10484^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09516^2 + 44444400^2 && := 10203020\ 10484^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09516^2 + 4444444400^2 && := 102030403020\ 10484^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09516^2 + 444444444400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10484^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09516^2 + 44444444444400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10484^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09516^2 + 4444444444444400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10484^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09516^2 + 444444444444444400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10484^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09516^2 + 44444444444444444400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10484^2
 \end{aligned}$$

23)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09471^2 + 4600^2 && := 10529^2 \\
 &1020\ 09471^2 + 464600^2 && := 1020\ 10529^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09471^2 + 46464600^2 && := 10203020\ 10529^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09471^2 + 4646464600^2 && := 102030403020\ 10529^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09471^2 + 464646464600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10529^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09471^2 + 46464646464600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10529^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09471^2 + 4646464646464600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10529^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09471^2 + 464646464646464600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10529^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09471^2 + 46464646464646464600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10529^2
 \end{aligned}$$

24)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09424^2 + 4800^2 && := 10576^2 \\
 &1020\ 09424^2 + 484800^2 && := 1020\ 10576^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09424^2 + 48484800^2 && := 10203020\ 10576^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09424^2 + 4848484800^2 && := 102030403020\ 10576^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09424^2 + 484848484800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10576^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09424^2 + 48484848484800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10576^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09424^2 + 4848484848484800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10576^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09424^2 + 484848484848484800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10576^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09424^2 + 48484848484848484800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10576^2
 \end{aligned}$$

25)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09375^2 + 5000^2 && := 10625^2 \\
 &1020\ 09375^2 + 505000^2 && := 1020\ 10625^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09375^2 + 50505000^2 && := 10203020\ 10625^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09375^2 + 5050505000^2 && := 102030403020\ 10625^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09375^2 + 505050505000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10625^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09375^2 + 50505050505000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10625^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09375^2 + 5050505050505000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10625^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09375^2 + 505050505050505000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10625^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09375^2 + 50505050505050505000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10625^2
 \end{aligned}$$

26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09324^2 + 5200^2 && := 10676^2 \\
 &1020\ 09324^2 + 525200^2 && := 1020\ 10676^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09324^2 + 52525200^2 && := 10203020\ 10676^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09324^2 + 5252525200^2 && := 102030403020\ 10676^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09324^2 + 525252525200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10676^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09324^2 + 52525252525200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10676^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09324^2 + 5252525252525200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10676^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09324^2 + 525252525252525200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10676^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09324^2 + 52525252525252525200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10676^2
 \end{aligned}$$

27)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09271^2 + 5400^2 && := 10729^2 \\
 &1020\ 09271^2 + 545400^2 && := 1020\ 10729^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09271^2 + 54545400^2 && := 10203020\ 10729^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09271^2 + 5454545400^2 && := 102030403020\ 10729^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09271^2 + 545454545400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10729^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09271^2 + 54545454545400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10729^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09271^2 + 5454545454545400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10729^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09271^2 + 545454545454545400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10729^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09271^2 + 54545454545454545400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10729^2
 \end{aligned}$$

28)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09216^2 + 5600^2 && := 10784^2 \\
 &1020\ 09216^2 + 565600^2 && := 1020\ 10784^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09216^2 + 56565600^2 && := 10203020\ 10784^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09216^2 + 5656565600^2 && := 102030403020\ 10784^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09216^2 + 565656565600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10784^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09216^2 + 56565656565600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10784^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09216^2 + 5656565656565600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10784^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09216^2 + 565656565656565600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10784^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09216^2 + 56565656565656565600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10784^2
 \end{aligned}$$

29)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09159^2 + 5800^2 && := 10841^2 \\
 &1020\ 09159^2 + 585800^2 && := 1020\ 10841^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09159^2 + 58585800^2 && := 10203020\ 10841^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09159^2 + 5858585800^2 && := 102030403020\ 10841^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09159^2 + 585858585800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10841^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09159^2 + 58585858585800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10841^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09159^2 + 5858585858585800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10841^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09159^2 + 585858585858585800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10841^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09159^2 + 58585858585858585800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10841^2
 \end{aligned}$$

30)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09100^2 + 6000^2 && := 10900^2 \\
 &1020\ 09100^2 + 606000^2 && := 1020\ 10900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09100^2 + 60606000^2 && := 10203020\ 10900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09100^2 + 6060606000^2 && := 102030403020\ 10900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09100^2 + 606060606000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09100^2 + 60606060606000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09100^2 + 6060606060606000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09100^2 + 606060606060606000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09100^2 + 60606060606060606000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

31)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09039^2 + 6200^2 && := 10961^2 \\
 &1020\ 09039^2 + 626200^2 && := 1020\ 10961^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09039^2 + 62626200^2 && := 10203020\ 10961^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09039^2 + 6262626200^2 && := 102030403020\ 10961^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09039^2 + 626262626200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 10961^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09039^2 + 62626262626200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 10961^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09039^2 + 6262626262626200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 10961^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09039^2 + 626262626262626200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 10961^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09039^2 + 62626262626262626200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 10961^2
 \end{aligned}$$

32)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08976^2 + 6400^2 && := 11024^2 \\
 &1020\ 08976^2 + 646400^2 && := 1020\ 11024^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08976^2 + 64646400^2 && := 10203020\ 11024^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08976^2 + 6464646400^2 && := 102030403020\ 11024^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08976^2 + 646464646400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11024^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08976^2 + 64646464646400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11024^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08976^2 + 6464646464646400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11024^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08976^2 + 646464646464646400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11024^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08976^2 + 64646464646464646400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11024^2
 \end{aligned}$$

33)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08911^2 + 6600^2 && := 11089^2 \\
 &1020\ 08911^2 + 666600^2 && := 1020\ 11089^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08911^2 + 66666600^2 && := 10203020\ 11089^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08911^2 + 6666666600^2 && := 102030403020\ 11089^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08911^2 + 666666666600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11089^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08911^2 + 66666666666600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11089^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08911^2 + 6666666666666600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11089^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08911^2 + 666666666666666600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11089^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08911^2 + 66666666666666666600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11089^2
 \end{aligned}$$

34)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08844^2 + 6800^2 && := 11156^2 \\
 &1020\ 08844^2 + 686800^2 && := 1020\ 11156^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08844^2 + 68686800^2 && := 10203020\ 11156^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08844^2 + 6868686800^2 && := 102030403020\ 11156^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08844^2 + 686868686800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11156^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08844^2 + 68686868686800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11156^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08844^2 + 6868686868686800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11156^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08844^2 + 686868686868686800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11156^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08844^2 + 68686868686868686800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11156^2
 \end{aligned}$$

35)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08775^2 + 7000^2 && := 11225^2 \\
 &1020\ 08775^2 + 707000^2 && := 1020\ 11225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08775^2 + 70707000^2 && := 10203020\ 11225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08775^2 + 7070707000^2 && := 102030403020\ 11225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08775^2 + 707070707000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08775^2 + 70707070707000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08775^2 + 7070707070707000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08775^2 + 707070707070707000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08775^2 + 70707070707070707000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11225^2
 \end{aligned}$$

36)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08704^2 + 7200^2 && := 11296^2 \\
 &1020\ 08704^2 + 727200^2 && := 1020\ 11296^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08704^2 + 72727200^2 && := 10203020\ 11296^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08704^2 + 7272727200^2 && := 102030403020\ 11296^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08704^2 + 727272727200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11296^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08704^2 + 72727272727200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11296^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08704^2 + 7272727272727200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11296^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08704^2 + 727272727272727200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11296^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08704^2 + 72727272727272727200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11296^2
 \end{aligned}$$

37)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08631^2 + 7400^2 && := 11369^2 \\
 &1020\ 08631^2 + 747400^2 && := 1020\ 11369^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08631^2 + 74747400^2 && := 10203020\ 11369^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08631^2 + 7474747400^2 && := 102030403020\ 11369^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08631^2 + 747474747400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11369^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08631^2 + 74747474747400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11369^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08631^2 + 7474747474747400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11369^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08631^2 + 747474747474747400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11369^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08631^2 + 74747474747474747400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11369^2
 \end{aligned}$$

38)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08556^2 + 7600^2 && := 11444^2 \\
 &1020\ 08556^2 + 767600^2 && := 1020\ 11444^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08556^2 + 76767600^2 && := 10203020\ 11444^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08556^2 + 7676767600^2 && := 102030403020\ 11444^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08556^2 + 767676767600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11444^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08556^2 + 76767676767600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11444^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08556^2 + 7676767676767600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11444^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08556^2 + 767676767676767600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11444^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08556^2 + 76767676767676767600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11444^2
 \end{aligned}$$

39)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08479^2 + 7800^2 && := 11521^2 \\
 &1020\ 08479^2 + 787800^2 && := 1020\ 11521^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08479^2 + 78787800^2 && := 10203020\ 11521^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08479^2 + 7878787800^2 && := 102030403020\ 11521^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08479^2 + 787878787800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11521^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08479^2 + 78787878787800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11521^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08479^2 + 7878787878787800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11521^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08479^2 + 787878787878787800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11521^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08479^2 + 78787878787878787800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11521^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 40)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &08400^2 + 8000^2 && := 11600^2 \\
 &1020\ 08400^2 + 808000^2 && := 1020\ 11600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08400^2 + 80808000^2 && := 10203020\ 11600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08400^2 + 8080808000^2 && := 102030403020\ 11600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08400^2 + 808080808000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08400^2 + 80808080808000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08400^2 + 8080808080808000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08400^2 + 808080808080808000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08400^2 + 80808080808080808000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 41)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &08319^2 + 8200^2 && := 11681^2 \\
 &1020\ 08319^2 + 828200^2 && := 1020\ 11681^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08319^2 + 82828200^2 && := 10203020\ 11681^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08319^2 + 8282828200^2 && := 102030403020\ 11681^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08319^2 + 828282828200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11681^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08319^2 + 82828282828200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11681^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08319^2 + 8282828282828200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11681^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08319^2 + 828282828282828200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11681^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08319^2 + 82828282828282828200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11681^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 42)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &08236^2 + 8400^2 && := 11764^2 \\
 &1020\ 08236^2 + 848400^2 && := 1020\ 11764^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08236^2 + 84848400^2 && := 10203020\ 11764^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08236^2 + 8484848400^2 && := 102030403020\ 11764^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08236^2 + 848484848400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11764^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08236^2 + 84848484848400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11764^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08236^2 + 8484848484848400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11764^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08236^2 + 848484848484848400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11764^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08236^2 + 84848484848484848400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11764^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 43)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &08151^2 + 8600^2 && := 11849^2 \\
 &1020\ 08151^2 + 868600^2 && := 1020\ 11849^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08151^2 + 86868600^2 && := 10203020\ 11849^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08151^2 + 8686868600^2 && := 102030403020\ 11849^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08151^2 + 868686868600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11849^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08151^2 + 86868686868600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11849^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08151^2 + 8686868686868600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11849^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08151^2 + 868686868686868600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11849^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08151^2 + 86868686868686868600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11849^2
 \end{aligned}$$

44)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &08064^2 + 8800^2 && := 11936^2 \\
 &1020\ 08064^2 + 888800^2 && := 1020\ 11936^2 \\
 &10203020\ 08064^2 + 88888800^2 && := 10203020\ 11936^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 08064^2 + 8888888800^2 && := 102030403020\ 11936^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 08064^2 + 888888888800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 11936^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 08064^2 + 88888888888800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 11936^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 08064^2 + 8888888888888800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 11936^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 08064^2 + 888888888888888800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 11936^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 08064^2 + 88888888888888888800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 11936^2
 \end{aligned}$$

45)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07975^2 + 9000^2 && := 12025^2 \\
 &1020\ 07975^2 + 909000^2 && := 1020\ 12025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07975^2 + 90909000^2 && := 10203020\ 12025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07975^2 + 9090909000^2 && := 102030403020\ 12025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07975^2 + 909090909000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07975^2 + 90909090909000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07975^2 + 9090909090909000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07975^2 + 909090909090909000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07975^2 + 90909090909090909000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12025^2
 \end{aligned}$$

46)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07884^2 + 9200^2 && := 12116^2 \\
 &1020\ 07884^2 + 929200^2 && := 1020\ 12116^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07884^2 + 92929200^2 && := 10203020\ 12116^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07884^2 + 9292929200^2 && := 102030403020\ 12116^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07884^2 + 929292929200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12116^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07884^2 + 92929292929200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12116^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07884^2 + 9292929292929200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12116^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07884^2 + 929292929292929200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12116^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07884^2 + 92929292929292929200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12116^2
 \end{aligned}$$

47)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07791^2 + 9400^2 && := 12209^2 \\
 &1020\ 07791^2 + 949400^2 && := 1020\ 12209^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07791^2 + 94949400^2 && := 10203020\ 12209^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07791^2 + 9494949400^2 && := 102030403020\ 12209^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07791^2 + 949494949400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12209^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07791^2 + 94949494949400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12209^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07791^2 + 9494949494949400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12209^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07791^2 + 949494949494949400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12209^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07791^2 + 94949494949494949400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12209^2
 \end{aligned}$$

48)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07696^2 + 9600^2 && := 12304^2 \\
 &1020\ 07696^2 + 969600^2 && := 1020\ 12304^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07696^2 + 96969600^2 && := 10203020\ 12304^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07696^2 + 9696969600^2 && := 102030403020\ 12304^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07696^2 + 969696969600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12304^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07696^2 + 96969696969600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12304^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07696^2 + 9696969696969600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12304^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07696^2 + 969696969696969600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12304^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07696^2 + 96969696969696969600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12304^2
 \end{aligned}$$

49)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07599^2 + 9800^2 && := 12401^2 \\
 &1020\ 07599^2 + 989800^2 && := 1020\ 12401^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07599^2 + 98989800^2 && := 10203020\ 12401^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07599^2 + 9898989800^2 && := 102030403020\ 12401^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07599^2 + 989898989800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12401^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07599^2 + 98989898989800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12401^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07599^2 + 9898989898989800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12401^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07599^2 + 989898989898989800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12401^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07599^2 + 98989898989898989800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12401^2
 \end{aligned}$$

50)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07500^2 + 10000^2 && := 12500^2 \\
 &1020\ 07500^2 + 1010000^2 && := 1020\ 12500^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07500^2 + 101010000^2 && := 10203020\ 12500^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07500^2 + 10101010000^2 && := 102030403020\ 12500^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07500^2 + 1010101010000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12500^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07500^2 + 101010101010000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12500^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07500^2 + 10101010101010000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12500^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07500^2 + 1010101010101010000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12500^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07500^2 + 101010101010101010000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12500^2
 \end{aligned}$$

51)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07399^2 + 10200^2 && := 12601^2 \\
 &1020\ 07399^2 + 1030200^2 && := 1020\ 12601^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07399^2 + 103030200^2 && := 10203020\ 12601^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07399^2 + 10303030200^2 && := 102030403020\ 12601^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07399^2 + 1030303030200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12601^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07399^2 + 103030303030200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12601^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07399^2 + 10303030303030200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12601^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07399^2 + 1030303030303030200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12601^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07399^2 + 103030303030303030200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12601^2
 \end{aligned}$$

52)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07296^2 + 10400^2 && := 12704^2 \\
 &1020\ 07296^2 + 1050400^2 && := 1020\ 12704^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07296^2 + 105050400^2 && := 10203020\ 12704^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07296^2 + 10505050400^2 && := 102030403020\ 12704^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07296^2 + 1050505050400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12704^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07296^2 + 105050505050400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12704^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07296^2 + 10505050505050400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12704^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07296^2 + 1050505050505050400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12704^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07296^2 + 105050505050505050400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12704^2
 \end{aligned}$$

53)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07191^2 + 10600^2 && := 12809^2 \\
 &1020\ 07191^2 + 1070600^2 && := 1020\ 12809^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07191^2 + 107070600^2 && := 10203020\ 12809^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07191^2 + 10707070600^2 && := 102030403020\ 12809^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07191^2 + 1070707070600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12809^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07191^2 + 107070707070600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12809^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07191^2 + 10707070707070600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12809^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07191^2 + 1070707070707070600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12809^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07191^2 + 107070707070707070600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12809^2
 \end{aligned}$$

54)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &07084^2 + 10800^2 && := 12916^2 \\
 &1020\ 07084^2 + 1090800^2 && := 1020\ 12916^2 \\
 &10203020\ 07084^2 + 109090800^2 && := 10203020\ 12916^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 07084^2 + 10909090800^2 && := 102030403020\ 12916^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 07084^2 + 1090909090800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 12916^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 07084^2 + 109090909090800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 12916^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 07084^2 + 10909090909090800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 12916^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 07084^2 + 1090909090909090800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 12916^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 07084^2 + 109090909090909090800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 12916^2
 \end{aligned}$$

55)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06975^2 + 11000^2 && := 13025^2 \\
 &1020\ 06975^2 + 1111000^2 && := 1020\ 13025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06975^2 + 111111000^2 && := 10203020\ 13025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06975^2 + 11111111000^2 && := 102030403020\ 13025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06975^2 + 1111111111000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06975^2 + 111111111111000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06975^2 + 11111111111111000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06975^2 + 1111111111111111000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06975^2 + 111111111111111111000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13025^2
 \end{aligned}$$

56)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06864^2 + 11200^2 && := 13136^2 \\
 &1020\ 06864^2 + 1131200^2 && := 1020\ 13136^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06864^2 + 113131200^2 && := 10203020\ 13136^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06864^2 + 11313131200^2 && := 102030403020\ 13136^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06864^2 + 1131313131200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13136^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06864^2 + 113131313131200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13136^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06864^2 + 11313131313131200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13136^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06864^2 + 1131313131313131200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13136^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06864^2 + 113131313131313131200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13136^2
 \end{aligned}$$

57)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06751^2 + 11400^2 && := 13249^2 \\
 &1020\ 06751^2 + 1151400^2 && := 1020\ 13249^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06751^2 + 115151400^2 && := 10203020\ 13249^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06751^2 + 11515151400^2 && := 102030403020\ 13249^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06751^2 + 1151515151400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13249^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06751^2 + 115151515151400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13249^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06751^2 + 11515151515151400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13249^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06751^2 + 1151515151515151400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13249^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06751^2 + 115151515151515151400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13249^2
 \end{aligned}$$

58)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06636^2 + 11600^2 && := 13364^2 \\
 &1020\ 06636^2 + 1171600^2 && := 1020\ 13364^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06636^2 + 117171600^2 && := 10203020\ 13364^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06636^2 + 11717171600^2 && := 102030403020\ 13364^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06636^2 + 1171717171600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13364^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06636^2 + 117171717171600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13364^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06636^2 + 11717171717171600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13364^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06636^2 + 1171717171717171600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13364^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06636^2 + 117171717171717171600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13364^2
 \end{aligned}$$

59)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06519^2 + 11800^2 && := 13481^2 \\
 &1020\ 06519^2 + 1191800^2 && := 1020\ 13481^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06519^2 + 119191800^2 && := 10203020\ 13481^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06519^2 + 11919191800^2 && := 102030403020\ 13481^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06519^2 + 1191919191800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13481^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06519^2 + 119191919191800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13481^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06519^2 + 11919191919191800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13481^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06519^2 + 1191919191919191800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13481^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06519^2 + 119191919191919191800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13481^2
 \end{aligned}$$

60)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06400^2 + 12000^2 && := 13600^2 \\
 &1020\ 06400^2 + 1212000^2 && := 1020\ 13600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06400^2 + 121212000^2 && := 10203020\ 13600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06400^2 + 12121212000^2 && := 102030403020\ 13600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06400^2 + 1212121212000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06400^2 + 121212121212000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06400^2 + 12121212121212000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06400^2 + 1212121212121212000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06400^2 + 121212121212121212000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13600^2
 \end{aligned}$$

61)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06279^2 + 12200^2 && := 13721^2 \\
 &1020\ 06279^2 + 1232200^2 && := 1020\ 13721^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06279^2 + 123232200^2 && := 10203020\ 13721^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06279^2 + 12323232200^2 && := 102030403020\ 13721^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06279^2 + 1232323232200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13721^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06279^2 + 123232323232200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13721^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06279^2 + 12323232323232200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13721^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06279^2 + 1232323232323232200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13721^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06279^2 + 1232323232323232200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13721^2
 \end{aligned}$$

62)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06156^2 + 12400^2 && := 13844^2 \\
 &1020\ 06156^2 + 1252400^2 && := 1020\ 13844^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06156^2 + 125252400^2 && := 10203020\ 13844^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06156^2 + 12525252400^2 && := 102030403020\ 13844^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06156^2 + 1252525252400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13844^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06156^2 + 125252525252400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13844^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06156^2 + 12525252525252400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13844^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06156^2 + 1252525252525252400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13844^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06156^2 + 1252525252525252400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13844^2
 \end{aligned}$$

63)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &06031^2 + 12600^2 && := 13969^2 \\
 &1020\ 06031^2 + 1272600^2 && := 1020\ 13969^2 \\
 &10203020\ 06031^2 + 127272600^2 && := 10203020\ 13969^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 06031^2 + 12727272600^2 && := 102030403020\ 13969^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 06031^2 + 1272727272600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 13969^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 06031^2 + 127272727272600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 13969^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 06031^2 + 12727272727272600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 13969^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 06031^2 + 1272727272727272600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 13969^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 06031^2 + 1272727272727272600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 13969^2
 \end{aligned}$$

64)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &05904^2 + 12800^2 && := 14096^2 \\
 &1020\ 05904^2 + 1292800^2 && := 1020\ 14096^2 \\
 &10203020\ 05904^2 + 129292800^2 && := 10203020\ 14096^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 05904^2 + 12929292800^2 && := 102030403020\ 14096^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 05904^2 + 1292929292800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 14096^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 05904^2 + 129292929292800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 14096^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 05904^2 + 12929292929292800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 14096^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 05904^2 + 1292929292929292800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 14096^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 05904^2 + 129292929292929292800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 14096^2
 \end{aligned}$$

65)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &05775^2 + 13000^2 && := 14225^2 \\
 &1020\ 05775^2 + 1313000^2 && := 1020\ 14225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 05775^2 + 131313000^2 && := 10203020\ 14225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 05775^2 + 13131313000^2 && := 102030403020\ 14225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 05775^2 + 1313131313000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 14225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 05775^2 + 131313131313000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 14225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 05775^2 + 13131313131313000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 14225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 05775^2 + 1313131313131313000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 14225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 05775^2 + 131313131313131313000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 14225^2
 \end{aligned}$$

66)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &05644^2 + 13200^2 && := 14356^2 \\
 &1020\ 05644^2 + 1333200^2 && := 1020\ 14356^2 \\
 &10203020\ 05644^2 + 133333200^2 && := 10203020\ 14356^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 05644^2 + 13333333200^2 && := 102030403020\ 14356^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 05644^2 + 1333333333200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 14356^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 05644^2 + 133333333333200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 14356^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 05644^2 + 13333333333333200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 14356^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 05644^2 + 1333333333333333200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 14356^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 05644^2 + 133333333333333333200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 14356^2
 \end{aligned}$$

67)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &05511^2 + 13400^2 && := 14489^2 \\
 &1020\ 05511^2 + 1353400^2 && := 1020\ 14489^2 \\
 &10203020\ 05511^2 + 135353400^2 && := 10203020\ 14489^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 05511^2 + 13535353400^2 && := 102030403020\ 14489^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 05511^2 + 1353535353400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 14489^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 05511^2 + 135353535353400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 14489^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 05511^2 + 13535353535353400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 14489^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 05511^2 + 1353535353535353400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 14489^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 05511^2 + 135353535353535353400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 14489^2
 \end{aligned}$$

68)

$$\begin{aligned} & 05376^2 + 13600^2 && := 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 05376^2 + 1373600^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 05376^2 + 137373600^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 05376^2 + 13737373600^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 05376^2 + 1373737373600^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 05376^2 + 137373737373600^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 05376^2 + 13737373737373600^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 05376^2 + 1373737373737373600^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 14624^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 05376^2 + 137373737373737373600^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 14624^2 \end{aligned}$$

69)

$$\begin{aligned} & 05239^2 + 13800^2 && := 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 05239^2 + 1393800^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 05239^2 + 139393800^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 05239^2 + 13939393800^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 05239^2 + 1393939393800^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 05239^2 + 139393939393800^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 05239^2 + 13939393939393800^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 05239^2 + 1393939393939393800^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 14761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 05239^2 + 139393939393939393800^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 14761^2 \end{aligned}$$

70)

$$\begin{aligned} & 05100^2 + 14000^2 && := 14900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 05100^2 + 1414000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 14900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 05100^2 + 141414000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 14900^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 05100^2 + 14141414000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 14900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 05100^2 + 1414141414000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 14900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 05100^2 + 141414141414000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 14900^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 05100^2 + 14141414141414000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 14900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 05100^2 + 1414141414141414000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 14900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 05100^2 + 141414141414141414000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 14900^2 \end{aligned}$$

71)

$$\begin{aligned} & 04959^2 + 14200^2 && := 15041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 04959^2 + 1434200^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 15041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 04959^2 + 143434200^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 15041^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 04959^2 + 14343434200^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 15041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 04959^2 + 1434343434200^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 15041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 04959^2 + 143434343434200^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 15041^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 04959^2 + 14343434343434200^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 15041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 04959^2 + 1434343434343434200^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 15041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 04959^2 + 1434343434343434200^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 15041^2 \end{aligned}$$

72)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &04816^2 + 14400^2 && := 15184^2 \\
 &1020\ 04816^2 + 1454400^2 && := 1020\ 15184^2 \\
 &10203020\ 04816^2 + 145454400^2 && := 10203020\ 15184^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 04816^2 + 14545454400^2 && := 102030403020\ 15184^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 04816^2 + 1454545454400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 15184^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 04816^2 + 145454545454400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 15184^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 04816^2 + 14545454545454400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 15184^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 04816^2 + 1454545454545454400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 15184^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 04816^2 + 145454545454545454400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 15184^2
 \end{aligned}$$

73)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &04671^2 + 14600^2 && := 15329^2 \\
 &1020\ 04671^2 + 1474600^2 && := 1020\ 15329^2 \\
 &10203020\ 04671^2 + 147474600^2 && := 10203020\ 15329^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 04671^2 + 14747474600^2 && := 102030403020\ 15329^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 04671^2 + 1474747474600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 15329^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 04671^2 + 147474747474600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 15329^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 04671^2 + 14747474747474600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 15329^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 04671^2 + 1474747474747474600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 15329^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 04671^2 + 147474747474747474600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 15329^2
 \end{aligned}$$

74)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &04524^2 + 14800^2 && := 15476^2 \\
 &1020\ 04524^2 + 1494800^2 && := 1020\ 15476^2 \\
 &10203020\ 04524^2 + 149494800^2 && := 10203020\ 15476^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 04524^2 + 14949494800^2 && := 102030403020\ 15476^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 04524^2 + 1494949494800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 15476^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 04524^2 + 149494949494800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 15476^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 04524^2 + 14949494949494800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 15476^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 04524^2 + 1494949494949494800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 15476^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 04524^2 + 149494949494949494800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 15476^2
 \end{aligned}$$

75)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &04375^2 + 15000^2 && := 15625^2 \\
 &1020\ 04375^2 + 1515000^2 && := 1020\ 15625^2 \\
 &10203020\ 04375^2 + 151515000^2 && := 10203020\ 15625^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 04375^2 + 15151515000^2 && := 102030403020\ 15625^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 04375^2 + 1515151515000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 15625^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 04375^2 + 151515151515000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 15625^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 04375^2 + 15151515151515000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 15625^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 04375^2 + 1515151515151515000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 15625^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 04375^2 + 151515151515151515000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 15625^2
 \end{aligned}$$

76)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &04224^2 + 15200^2 && := 15776^2 \\
 &1020\ 04224^2 + 1535200^2 && := 1020\ 15776^2 \\
 &10203020\ 04224^2 + 153535200^2 && := 10203020\ 15776^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 04224^2 + 15353535200^2 && := 102030403020\ 15776^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 04224^2 + 1535353535200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 15776^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 04224^2 + 153535353535200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 15776^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 04224^2 + 15353535353535200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 15776^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 04224^2 + 1535353535353535200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 15776^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 04224^2 + 153535353535353535200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 15776^2
 \end{aligned}$$

77)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &04071^2 + 15400^2 && := 15929^2 \\
 &1020\ 04071^2 + 1555400^2 && := 1020\ 15929^2 \\
 &10203020\ 04071^2 + 155555400^2 && := 10203020\ 15929^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 04071^2 + 15555555400^2 && := 102030403020\ 15929^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 04071^2 + 1555555555400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 15929^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 04071^2 + 155555555555400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 15929^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 04071^2 + 15555555555555400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 15929^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 04071^2 + 1555555555555555400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 15929^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 04071^2 + 155555555555555555400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 15929^2
 \end{aligned}$$

78)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &03916^2 + 15600^2 && := 16084^2 \\
 &1020\ 03916^2 + 1575600^2 && := 1020\ 16084^2 \\
 &10203020\ 03916^2 + 157575600^2 && := 10203020\ 16084^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 03916^2 + 15757575600^2 && := 102030403020\ 16084^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 03916^2 + 1575757575600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 16084^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 03916^2 + 157575757575600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 16084^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 03916^2 + 15757575757575600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 16084^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 03916^2 + 1575757575757575600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 16084^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 03916^2 + 157575757575757575600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 16084^2
 \end{aligned}$$

79)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &03759^2 + 15800^2 && := 16241^2 \\
 &1020\ 03759^2 + 1595800^2 && := 1020\ 16241^2 \\
 &10203020\ 03759^2 + 159595800^2 && := 10203020\ 16241^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 03759^2 + 15959595800^2 && := 102030403020\ 16241^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 03759^2 + 1595959595800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 16241^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 03759^2 + 159595959595800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 16241^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 03759^2 + 15959595959595800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 16241^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 03759^2 + 1595959595959595800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 16241^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 03759^2 + 159595959595959595800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 16241^2
 \end{aligned}$$

80)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &03600^2 + 16000^2 && := 16400^2 \\
 &1020\ 03600^2 + 1616000^2 && := 1020\ 16400^2 \\
 &10203020\ 03600^2 + 161616000^2 && := 10203020\ 16400^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 03600^2 + 16161616000^2 && := 102030403020\ 16400^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 03600^2 + 1616161616000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 16400^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 03600^2 + 161616161616000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 16400^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 03600^2 + 16161616161616000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 16400^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 03600^2 + 1616161616161616000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 16400^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 03600^2 + 161616161616161616000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 16400^2
 \end{aligned}$$

81)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &03439^2 + 16200^2 && := 16561^2 \\
 &1020\ 03439^2 + 1636200^2 && := 1020\ 16561^2 \\
 &10203020\ 03439^2 + 163636200^2 && := 10203020\ 16561^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 03439^2 + 16363636200^2 && := 102030403020\ 16561^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 03439^2 + 1636363636200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 16561^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 03439^2 + 163636363636200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 16561^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 03439^2 + 16363636363636200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 16561^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 03439^2 + 1636363636363636200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 16561^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 03439^2 + 163636363636363636200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 16561^2
 \end{aligned}$$

82)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &03276^2 + 16400^2 && := 16724^2 \\
 &1020\ 03276^2 + 1656400^2 && := 1020\ 16724^2 \\
 &10203020\ 03276^2 + 165656400^2 && := 10203020\ 16724^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 03276^2 + 16565656400^2 && := 102030403020\ 16724^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 03276^2 + 1656565656400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 16724^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 03276^2 + 165656565656400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 16724^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 03276^2 + 16565656565656400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 16724^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 03276^2 + 1656565656565656400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 16724^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 03276^2 + 165656565656565656400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 16724^2
 \end{aligned}$$

83)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &03111^2 + 16600^2 && := 16889^2 \\
 &1020\ 03111^2 + 1676600^2 && := 1020\ 16889^2 \\
 &10203020\ 03111^2 + 167676600^2 && := 10203020\ 16889^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 03111^2 + 16767676600^2 && := 102030403020\ 16889^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 03111^2 + 1676767676600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 16889^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 03111^2 + 167676767676600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 16889^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 03111^2 + 16767676767676600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 16889^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 03111^2 + 1676767676767676600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 16889^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 03111^2 + 167676767676767676600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 16889^2
 \end{aligned}$$

84)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &02944^2 + 16800^2 && := 17056^2 \\
 &1020\ 02944^2 + 1696800^2 && := 1020\ 17056^2 \\
 &10203020\ 02944^2 + 169696800^2 && := 10203020\ 17056^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 02944^2 + 16969696800^2 && := 102030403020\ 17056^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 02944^2 + 1696969696800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 17056^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 02944^2 + 169696969696800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 17056^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 02944^2 + 16969696969696800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 17056^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 02944^2 + 1696969696969696800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 17056^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 02944^2 + 1696969696969696800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 17056^2
 \end{aligned}$$

85)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &02775^2 + 17000^2 && := 17225^2 \\
 &1020\ 02775^2 + 1717000^2 && := 1020\ 17225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 02775^2 + 171717000^2 && := 10203020\ 17225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 02775^2 + 17171717000^2 && := 102030403020\ 17225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 02775^2 + 1717171717000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 17225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 02775^2 + 171717171717000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 17225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 02775^2 + 17171717171717000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 17225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 02775^2 + 1717171717171717000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 17225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 02775^2 + 171717171717171717000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 17225^2
 \end{aligned}$$

86)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &02604^2 + 17200^2 && := 17396^2 \\
 &1020\ 02604^2 + 1737200^2 && := 1020\ 17396^2 \\
 &10203020\ 02604^2 + 173737200^2 && := 10203020\ 17396^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 02604^2 + 17373737200^2 && := 102030403020\ 17396^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 02604^2 + 1737373737200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 17396^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 02604^2 + 173737373737200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 17396^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 02604^2 + 17373737373737200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 17396^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 02604^2 + 1737373737373737200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 17396^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 02604^2 + 173737373737373737200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 17396^2
 \end{aligned}$$

87)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &02431^2 + 17400^2 && := 17569^2 \\
 &1020\ 02431^2 + 1757400^2 && := 1020\ 17569^2 \\
 &10203020\ 02431^2 + 175757400^2 && := 10203020\ 17569^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 02431^2 + 17575757400^2 && := 102030403020\ 17569^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 02431^2 + 1757575757400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 17569^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 02431^2 + 175757575757400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 17569^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 02431^2 + 17575757575757400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 17569^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 02431^2 + 1757575757575757400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 17569^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 02431^2 + 1757575757575757400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 17569^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 88)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $02256^2 + 17600^2$ | $:= 17744^2$ |
| | $1020\ 02256^2 + 1777600^2$ | $:= 1020\ 17744^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 02256^2 + 177777600^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 17744^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 02256^2 + 1777777600^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 17744^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 02256^2 + 17777777600^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 17744^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 02256^2 + 177777777600^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 17744^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 02256^2 + 1777777777600^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 17744^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 02256^2 + 17777777777600^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 17744^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 02256^2 + 177777777777600^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 17744^2$ |
- 89)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $02079^2 + 17800^2$ | $:= 17921^2$ |
| | $1020\ 02079^2 + 1797800^2$ | $:= 1020\ 17921^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 02079^2 + 179797800^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 17921^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 02079^2 + 17979797800^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 17921^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 02079^2 + 1797979797800^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 17921^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 02079^2 + 179797979797800^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 17921^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 02079^2 + 17979797979797800^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 17921^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 02079^2 + 1797979797979797800^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 17921^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 02079^2 + 179797979797979797800^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 17921^2$ |
- 90)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $01900^2 + 18000^2$ | $:= 18100^2$ |
| | $1020\ 01900^2 + 1818000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 18100^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 01900^2 + 181818000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 18100^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 01900^2 + 18181818000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 18100^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 01900^2 + 1818181818000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 18100^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 01900^2 + 181818181818000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 18100^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 01900^2 + 18181818181818000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 18100^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 01900^2 + 1818181818181818000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 18100^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 01900^2 + 181818181818181818000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 18100^2$ |
- 91)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $01719^2 + 18200^2$ | $:= 18281^2$ |
| | $1020\ 01719^2 + 1838200^2$ | $:= 1020\ 18281^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 01719^2 + 183838200^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 18281^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 01719^2 + 18383838200^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 18281^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 01719^2 + 1838383838200^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 18281^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 01719^2 + 183838383838200^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 18281^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 01719^2 + 18383838383838200^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 18281^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 01719^2 + 1838383838383838200^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 18281^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 01719^2 + 183838383838383838200^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 18281^2$ |

92)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &01536^2 + 18400^2 && := 18464^2 \\
 &1020\ 01536^2 + 1858400^2 && := 1020\ 18464^2 \\
 &10203020\ 01536^2 + 185858400^2 && := 10203020\ 18464^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 01536^2 + 18585858400^2 && := 102030403020\ 18464^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 01536^2 + 1858585858400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 18464^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 01536^2 + 185858585858400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 18464^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 01536^2 + 18585858585858400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 18464^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 01536^2 + 1858585858585858400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 18464^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 01536^2 + 185858585858585858400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 18464^2
 \end{aligned}$$

93)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &01351^2 + 18600^2 && := 18649^2 \\
 &1020\ 01351^2 + 1878600^2 && := 1020\ 18649^2 \\
 &10203020\ 01351^2 + 187878600^2 && := 10203020\ 18649^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 01351^2 + 18787878600^2 && := 102030403020\ 18649^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 01351^2 + 1878787878600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 18649^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 01351^2 + 187878787878600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 18649^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 01351^2 + 18787878787878600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 18649^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 01351^2 + 1878787878787878600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 18649^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 01351^2 + 187878787878787878600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 18649^2
 \end{aligned}$$

94)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &01164^2 + 18800^2 && := 18836^2 \\
 &1020\ 01164^2 + 1898800^2 && := 1020\ 18836^2 \\
 &10203020\ 01164^2 + 189898800^2 && := 10203020\ 18836^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 01164^2 + 18989898800^2 && := 102030403020\ 18836^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 01164^2 + 1898989898800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 18836^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 01164^2 + 189898989898800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 18836^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 01164^2 + 18989898989898800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 18836^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 01164^2 + 1898989898989898800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 18836^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 01164^2 + 1898989898989898800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 18836^2
 \end{aligned}$$

95)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &00975^2 + 19000^2 && := 19025^2 \\
 &1020\ 00975^2 + 1919000^2 && := 1020\ 19025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 00975^2 + 191919000^2 && := 10203020\ 19025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 00975^2 + 19191919000^2 && := 102030403020\ 19025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 00975^2 + 1919191919000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 19025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 00975^2 + 191919191919000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 19025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 00975^2 + 19191919191919000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 19025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 00975^2 + 1919191919191919000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 19025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 00975^2 + 191919191919191919000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 19025^2
 \end{aligned}$$

96)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &00784^2 + 19200^2 && := 19216^2 \\
 &1020\ 00784^2 + 1939200^2 && := 1020\ 19216^2 \\
 &10203020\ 00784^2 + 193939200^2 && := 10203020\ 19216^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 00784^2 + 19393939200^2 && := 102030403020\ 19216^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 00784^2 + 1939393939200^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 19216^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 00784^2 + 193939393939200^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 19216^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 00784^2 + 19393939393939200^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 19216^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 00784^2 + 1939393939393939200^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 19216^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 00784^2 + 193939393939393939200^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 19216^2
 \end{aligned}$$

97)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &00591^2 + 19400^2 && := 19409^2 \\
 &1020\ 00591^2 + 1959400^2 && := 1020\ 19409^2 \\
 &10203020\ 00591^2 + 195959400^2 && := 10203020\ 19409^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 00591^2 + 19595959400^2 && := 102030403020\ 19409^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 00591^2 + 1959595959400^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 19409^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 00591^2 + 195959595959400^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 19409^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 00591^2 + 19595959595959400^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 19409^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 00591^2 + 1959595959595959400^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 19409^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 00591^2 + 195959595959595959400^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 19409^2
 \end{aligned}$$

98)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &00396^2 + 19600^2 && := 19604^2 \\
 &1020\ 00396^2 + 1979600^2 && := 1020\ 19604^2 \\
 &10203020\ 00396^2 + 197979600^2 && := 10203020\ 19604^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 00396^2 + 19797979600^2 && := 102030403020\ 19604^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 00396^2 + 1979797979600^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 19604^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 00396^2 + 197979797979600^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 19604^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 00396^2 + 19797979797979600^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 19604^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 00396^2 + 1979797979797979600^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 19604^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 00396^2 + 197979797979797979600^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 19604^2
 \end{aligned}$$

99)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &00199^2 + 19800^2 && := 19801^2 \\
 &1020\ 00199^2 + 1999800^2 && := 1020\ 19801^2 \\
 &10203020\ 00199^2 + 199999800^2 && := 10203020\ 19801^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 00199^2 + 19999999800^2 && := 102030403020\ 19801^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 00199^2 + 1999999999800^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 19801^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 00199^2 + 199999999999800^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 19801^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 00199^2 + 19999999999999800^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 19801^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 00199^2 + 1999999999999999800^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 19801^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 00199^2 + 199999999999999999800^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 19801^2
 \end{aligned}$$

4.3 Third Block

4.3.1 First Way

Let's consider

$$(v) \ m = 1000, 11000, 111000, 1111000, 11111000, 111111000, 1111111000, 11111111000$$

in (1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 999$; below are 999 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns**:

1)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999999^2 + 2000^2 & := & 1000001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999999^2 + 22000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999999^2 + 222000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000001^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999999^2 + 2222000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999999^2 + 22222000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999999^2 + 222222000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000001^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999999^2 + 2222222000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999999^2 + 22222222000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999999^2 + 222222222000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000001^2 \end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999996^2 + 4000^2 & := & 1000004^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999996^2 + 44000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000004^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999996^2 + 444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000004^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999996^2 + 4444000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000004^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999996^2 + 44444000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000004^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999996^2 + 444444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000004^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999996^2 + 4444444000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000004^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999996^2 + 44444444000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000004^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999996^2 + 444444444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000004^2 \end{aligned}$$

3)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999991^2 + 6000^2 &:=& 1000009^2 \\
 &12\ 0999991^2 + 66000^2 &:=& 12\ 1000009^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999991^2 + 666000^2 &:=& 1232\ 1000009^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999991^2 + 6666000^2 &:=& 123432\ 1000009^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999991^2 + 66666000^2 &:=& 12345432\ 1000009^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999991^2 + 666666000^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 1000009^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999991^2 + 6666666000^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 1000009^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999991^2 + 66666666000^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 1000009^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999991^2 + 666666666000^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 1000009^2
 \end{aligned}$$

4)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999984^2 + 8000^2 &:=& 1000016^2 \\
 &12\ 0999984^2 + 88000^2 &:=& 12\ 1000016^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999984^2 + 888000^2 &:=& 1232\ 1000016^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999984^2 + 8888000^2 &:=& 123432\ 1000016^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999984^2 + 88888000^2 &:=& 12345432\ 1000016^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999984^2 + 888888000^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 1000016^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999984^2 + 8888888000^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 1000016^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999984^2 + 88888888000^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 1000016^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999984^2 + 888888888000^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 1000016^2
 \end{aligned}$$

5)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999975^2 + 10000^2 &:=& 1000025^2 \\
 &12\ 0999975^2 + 110000^2 &:=& 12\ 1000025^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999975^2 + 1110000^2 &:=& 1232\ 1000025^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999975^2 + 11110000^2 &:=& 123432\ 1000025^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999975^2 + 111110000^2 &:=& 12345432\ 1000025^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999975^2 + 1111110000^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 1000025^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999975^2 + 11111110000^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 1000025^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999975^2 + 111111110000^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 1000025^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999975^2 + 1111111110000^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 1000025^2
 \end{aligned}$$

6)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999964^2 + 12000^2 && := 1000036^2 \\
 &12\ 0999964^2 + 132000^2 && := 12\ 1000036^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999964^2 + 1332000^2 && := 1232\ 1000036^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999964^2 + 13332000^2 && := 123432\ 1000036^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999964^2 + 133332000^2 && := 12345432\ 1000036^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999964^2 + 1333332000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1000036^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999964^2 + 13333332000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1000036^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999964^2 + 133333332000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1000036^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999964^2 + 1333333332000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1000036^2
 \end{aligned}$$

7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999951^2 + 14000^2 && := 1000049^2 \\
 &12\ 0999951^2 + 154000^2 && := 12\ 1000049^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999951^2 + 1554000^2 && := 1232\ 1000049^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999951^2 + 15554000^2 && := 123432\ 1000049^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999951^2 + 155554000^2 && := 12345432\ 1000049^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999951^2 + 1555554000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1000049^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999951^2 + 15555554000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1000049^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999951^2 + 155555554000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1000049^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999951^2 + 1555555554000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1000049^2
 \end{aligned}$$

8)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999936^2 + 16000^2 && := 1000064^2 \\
 &12\ 0999936^2 + 176000^2 && := 12\ 1000064^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999936^2 + 1776000^2 && := 1232\ 1000064^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999936^2 + 17776000^2 && := 123432\ 1000064^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999936^2 + 177776000^2 && := 12345432\ 1000064^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999936^2 + 1777776000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1000064^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999936^2 + 17777776000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1000064^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999936^2 + 177777776000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1000064^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999936^2 + 1777777776000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1000064^2
 \end{aligned}$$

9)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999919^2 + 18000^2 & := & 1000081^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999919^2 + 198000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000081^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999919^2 + 1998000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000081^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999919^2 + 19998000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000081^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999919^2 + 199998000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000081^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999919^2 + 1999998000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000081^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999919^2 + 19999998000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000081^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999919^2 + 199999998000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000081^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999919^2 + 1999999998000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000081^2 \end{aligned}$$

10)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999900^2 + 20000^2 & := & 1000100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999900^2 + 220000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999900^2 + 2220000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999900^2 + 22220000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999900^2 + 222220000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999900^2 + 2222220000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999900^2 + 22222220000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999900^2 + 222222220000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999900^2 + 2222222220000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000100^2 \end{aligned}$$

11)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999879^2 + 22000^2 & := & 1000121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999879^2 + 242000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999879^2 + 2442000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000121^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999879^2 + 24442000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999879^2 + 244442000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999879^2 + 2444442000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000121^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999879^2 + 24444442000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999879^2 + 244444442000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999879^2 + 2444444442000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000121^2 \end{aligned}$$

12)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999856^2 + 24000^2 && := 1000144^2 \\
 &12\ 0999856^2 + 264000^2 && := 12\ 1000144^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999856^2 + 2664000^2 && := 1232\ 1000144^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999856^2 + 26664000^2 && := 123432\ 1000144^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999856^2 + 266664000^2 && := 12345432\ 1000144^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999856^2 + 2666664000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1000144^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999856^2 + 26666664000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1000144^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999856^2 + 266666664000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1000144^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999856^2 + 2666666664000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1000144^2
 \end{aligned}$$

13)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999831^2 + 26000^2 && := 1000169^2 \\
 &12\ 0999831^2 + 286000^2 && := 12\ 1000169^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999831^2 + 2886000^2 && := 1232\ 1000169^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999831^2 + 28886000^2 && := 123432\ 1000169^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999831^2 + 288886000^2 && := 12345432\ 1000169^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999831^2 + 2888886000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1000169^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999831^2 + 28888886000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1000169^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999831^2 + 288888886000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1000169^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999831^2 + 2888888886000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1000169^2
 \end{aligned}$$

14)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999804^2 + 28000^2 && := 1000196^2 \\
 &12\ 0999804^2 + 308000^2 && := 12\ 1000196^2 \\
 &1232\ 0999804^2 + 3108000^2 && := 1232\ 1000196^2 \\
 &123432\ 0999804^2 + 31108000^2 && := 123432\ 1000196^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0999804^2 + 311108000^2 && := 12345432\ 1000196^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0999804^2 + 3111108000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1000196^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0999804^2 + 31111108000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1000196^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0999804^2 + 311111108000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1000196^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0999804^2 + 3111111108000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1000196^2
 \end{aligned}$$

15)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999775^2 + 30000^2 & := & 1000225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999775^2 + 330000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999775^2 + 3330000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999775^2 + 33330000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999775^2 + 333330000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999775^2 + 3333330000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999775^2 + 33333330000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999775^2 + 333333330000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999775^2 + 3333333330000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000225^2 \end{aligned}$$

16)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999744^2 + 32000^2 & := & 1000256^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999744^2 + 352000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000256^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999744^2 + 3552000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000256^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999744^2 + 35552000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000256^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999744^2 + 355552000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000256^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999744^2 + 3555552000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000256^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999744^2 + 35555552000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000256^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999744^2 + 355555552000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000256^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999744^2 + 3555555552000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000256^2 \end{aligned}$$

17)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999711^2 + 34000^2 & := & 1000289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999711^2 + 374000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999711^2 + 3774000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000289^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999711^2 + 37774000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999711^2 + 377774000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999711^2 + 3777774000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000289^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999711^2 + 37777774000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999711^2 + 377777774000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999711^2 + 3777777774000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000289^2 \end{aligned}$$

18)

$$\begin{aligned}0999676^2 + 36000^2 &:= 1000324^2 \\12\ 0999676^2 + 396000^2 &:= 12\ 1000324^2 \\1232\ 0999676^2 + 3996000^2 &:= 1232\ 1000324^2 \\123432\ 0999676^2 + 39996000^2 &:= 123432\ 1000324^2 \\12345432\ 0999676^2 + 399996000^2 &:= 12345432\ 1000324^2 \\1234565432\ 0999676^2 + 3999996000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 1000324^2 \\123456765432\ 0999676^2 + 39999996000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 1000324^2 \\12345678765432\ 0999676^2 + 399999996000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 1000324^2 \\1234567898765432\ 0999676^2 + 3999999996000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 1000324^2\end{aligned}$$

19)

$$\begin{aligned}0999639^2 + 38000^2 &:= 1000361^2 \\12\ 0999639^2 + 418000^2 &:= 12\ 1000361^2 \\1232\ 0999639^2 + 4218000^2 &:= 1232\ 1000361^2 \\123432\ 0999639^2 + 42218000^2 &:= 123432\ 1000361^2 \\12345432\ 0999639^2 + 422218000^2 &:= 12345432\ 1000361^2 \\1234565432\ 0999639^2 + 4222218000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 1000361^2 \\123456765432\ 0999639^2 + 42222218000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 1000361^2 \\12345678765432\ 0999639^2 + 422222218000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 1000361^2 \\1234567898765432\ 0999639^2 + 4222222218000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 1000361^2\end{aligned}$$

20)

$$\begin{aligned}0999600^2 + 40000^2 &:= 1000400^2 \\12\ 0999600^2 + 440000^2 &:= 12\ 1000400^2 \\1232\ 0999600^2 + 4440000^2 &:= 1232\ 1000400^2 \\123432\ 0999600^2 + 44440000^2 &:= 123432\ 1000400^2 \\12345432\ 0999600^2 + 444440000^2 &:= 12345432\ 1000400^2 \\1234565432\ 0999600^2 + 4444440000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 1000400^2 \\123456765432\ 0999600^2 + 44444440000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 1000400^2 \\12345678765432\ 0999600^2 + 444444440000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 1000400^2 \\1234567898765432\ 0999600^2 + 4444444440000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 1000400^2\end{aligned}$$

21)

$$\begin{aligned} &0999559^2 + 42000^2 &&:= 1000441^2 \\ &12\ 0999559^2 + 462000^2 &&:= 12\ 1000441^2 \\ &1232\ 0999559^2 + 4662000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1000441^2 \\ &123432\ 0999559^2 + 46662000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1000441^2 \\ &12345432\ 0999559^2 + 466662000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1000441^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0999559^2 + 4666662000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1000441^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0999559^2 + 46666662000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1000441^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0999559^2 + 466666662000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1000441^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0999559^2 + 4666666662000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1000441^2 \end{aligned}$$

22)

$$\begin{aligned} &0999516^2 + 44000^2 &&:= 1000484^2 \\ &12\ 0999516^2 + 484000^2 &&:= 12\ 1000484^2 \\ &1232\ 0999516^2 + 4884000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1000484^2 \\ &123432\ 0999516^2 + 48884000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1000484^2 \\ &12345432\ 0999516^2 + 488884000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1000484^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0999516^2 + 4888884000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1000484^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0999516^2 + 48888884000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1000484^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0999516^2 + 488888884000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1000484^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0999516^2 + 4888888884000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1000484^2 \end{aligned}$$

23)

$$\begin{aligned} &0999471^2 + 46000^2 &&:= 1000529^2 \\ &12\ 0999471^2 + 506000^2 &&:= 12\ 1000529^2 \\ &1232\ 0999471^2 + 5106000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1000529^2 \\ &123432\ 0999471^2 + 51106000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1000529^2 \\ &12345432\ 0999471^2 + 511106000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1000529^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0999471^2 + 5111106000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1000529^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0999471^2 + 51111106000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1000529^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0999471^2 + 511111106000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1000529^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0999471^2 + 5111111106000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1000529^2 \end{aligned}$$

24)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999424^2 + 48000^2 & := & 1000576^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999424^2 + 528000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000576^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999424^2 + 5328000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000576^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999424^2 + 53328000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000576^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999424^2 + 533328000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000576^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999424^2 + 5333328000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000576^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999424^2 + 53333328000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000576^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999424^2 + 533333328000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000576^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999424^2 + 5333333328000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000576^2 \end{aligned}$$

25)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999375^2 + 50000^2 & := & 1000625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999375^2 + 550000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999375^2 + 5550000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999375^2 + 55550000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999375^2 + 555550000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999375^2 + 5555550000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999375^2 + 55555550000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999375^2 + 555555550000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999375^2 + 5555555550000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000625^2 \end{aligned}$$

26)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999324^2 + 52000^2 & := & 1000676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999324^2 + 572000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999324^2 + 5772000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000676^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999324^2 + 57772000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999324^2 + 577772000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999324^2 + 5777772000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000676^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999324^2 + 57777772000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999324^2 + 577777772000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999324^2 + 5777777772000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000676^2 \end{aligned}$$

27)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999271^2 + 54000^2 & := & 1000729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999271^2 + 594000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999271^2 + 5994000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999271^2 + 59994000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999271^2 + 599994000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999271^2 + 5999994000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999271^2 + 59999994000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999271^2 + 599999994000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999271^2 + 5999999994000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000729^2 \end{aligned}$$

28)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999216^2 + 56000^2 & := & 1000784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999216^2 + 616000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999216^2 + 6216000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000784^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999216^2 + 62216000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999216^2 + 622216000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999216^2 + 6222216000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000784^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999216^2 + 62222216000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999216^2 + 622222216000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999216^2 + 6222222216000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000784^2 \end{aligned}$$

29)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0999159^2 + 58000^2 & := & 1000841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0999159^2 + 638000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1000841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0999159^2 + 6438000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1000841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0999159^2 + 64438000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1000841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0999159^2 + 644438000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1000841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0999159^2 + 6444438000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1000841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0999159^2 + 64444438000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1000841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0999159^2 + 644444438000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1000841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0999159^2 + 6444444438000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1000841^2 \end{aligned}$$

30)

$$\begin{aligned} &0999100^2 + 60000^2 && := 1000900^2 \\ &12\ 0999100^2 + 660000^2 && := 12\ 1000900^2 \\ &1232\ 0999100^2 + 6660000^2 && := 1232\ 1000900^2 \\ &123432\ 0999100^2 + 66660000^2 && := 123432\ 1000900^2 \\ &12345432\ 0999100^2 + 666660000^2 && := 12345432\ 1000900^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0999100^2 + 6666660000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1000900^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0999100^2 + 66666660000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1000900^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0999100^2 + 666666660000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1000900^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0999100^2 + 6666666660000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1000900^2 \end{aligned}$$

31)

$$\begin{aligned} &0999039^2 + 62000^2 && := 1000961^2 \\ &12\ 0999039^2 + 682000^2 && := 12\ 1000961^2 \\ &1232\ 0999039^2 + 6882000^2 && := 1232\ 1000961^2 \\ &123432\ 0999039^2 + 68882000^2 && := 123432\ 1000961^2 \\ &12345432\ 0999039^2 + 688882000^2 && := 12345432\ 1000961^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0999039^2 + 6888882000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1000961^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0999039^2 + 68888882000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1000961^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0999039^2 + 688888882000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1000961^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0999039^2 + 6888888882000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1000961^2 \end{aligned}$$

32)

$$\begin{aligned} &0998976^2 + 64000^2 && := 1001024^2 \\ &12\ 0998976^2 + 704000^2 && := 12\ 1001024^2 \\ &1232\ 0998976^2 + 7104000^2 && := 1232\ 1001024^2 \\ &123432\ 0998976^2 + 71104000^2 && := 123432\ 1001024^2 \\ &12345432\ 0998976^2 + 711104000^2 && := 12345432\ 1001024^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0998976^2 + 7111104000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1001024^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0998976^2 + 71111104000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1001024^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0998976^2 + 711111104000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1001024^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0998976^2 + 7111111104000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1001024^2 \end{aligned}$$

33)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0998911^2 + 66000^2 & := & 1001089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0998911^2 + 726000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1001089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0998911^2 + 7326000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1001089^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0998911^2 + 73326000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1001089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0998911^2 + 733326000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1001089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0998911^2 + 7333326000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1001089^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0998911^2 + 73333326000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1001089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998911^2 + 733333326000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998911^2 + 7333333326000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001089^2 \end{aligned}$$

34)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0998844^2 + 68000^2 & := & 1001156^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0998844^2 + 748000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1001156^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0998844^2 + 7548000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1001156^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0998844^2 + 75548000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1001156^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0998844^2 + 755548000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1001156^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0998844^2 + 7555548000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1001156^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0998844^2 + 75555548000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1001156^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998844^2 + 755555548000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001156^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998844^2 + 7555555548000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001156^2 \end{aligned}$$

35)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0998775^2 + 70000^2 & := & 1001225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0998775^2 + 770000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1001225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0998775^2 + 7770000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1001225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0998775^2 + 77770000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1001225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0998775^2 + 777770000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1001225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0998775^2 + 7777770000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1001225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0998775^2 + 77777770000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1001225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998775^2 + 777777770000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998775^2 + 7777777770000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001225^2 \end{aligned}$$

36)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0998704^2 + 72000^2 & := & 1001296^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0998704^2 + 792000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1001296^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0998704^2 + 7992000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1001296^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0998704^2 + 79992000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1001296^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0998704^2 + 799992000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1001296^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0998704^2 + 7999992000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1001296^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0998704^2 + 79999992000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1001296^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998704^2 + 799999992000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001296^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998704^2 + 7999999992000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001296^2 \end{aligned}$$

37)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0998631^2 + 74000^2 & := & 1001369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0998631^2 + 814000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1001369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0998631^2 + 8214000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1001369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0998631^2 + 82214000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1001369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0998631^2 + 822214000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1001369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0998631^2 + 8222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1001369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0998631^2 + 82222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1001369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998631^2 + 822222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998631^2 + 8222222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001369^2 \end{aligned}$$

38)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0998556^2 + 76000^2 & := & 1001444^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0998556^2 + 836000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1001444^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0998556^2 + 8436000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1001444^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0998556^2 + 84436000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1001444^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0998556^2 + 844436000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1001444^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0998556^2 + 8444436000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1001444^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0998556^2 + 84444436000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1001444^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998556^2 + 844444436000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001444^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998556^2 + 8444444436000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001444^2 \end{aligned}$$

39)

$$\begin{aligned} 0998479^2 + 78000^2 &:= 1001521^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 0998479^2 + 858000^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 1001521^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 0998479^2 + 8658000^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 1001521^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 0998479^2 + 86658000^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 1001521^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 0998479^2 + 866658000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 1001521^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 0998479^2 + 8666658000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1001521^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 0998479^2 + 86666658000^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1001521^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998479^2 + 866666658000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001521^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998479^2 + 8666666658000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001521^2 \end{aligned}$$

40)

$$\begin{aligned} 0998400^2 + 80000^2 &:= 1001600^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 0998400^2 + 880000^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 1001600^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 0998400^2 + 8880000^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 1001600^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 0998400^2 + 88880000^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 1001600^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 0998400^2 + 888880000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 1001600^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 0998400^2 + 8888880000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1001600^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 0998400^2 + 88888880000^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1001600^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998400^2 + 888888880000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001600^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998400^2 + 8888888880000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001600^2 \end{aligned}$$

41)

$$\begin{aligned} 0998319^2 + 82000^2 &:= 1001681^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 0998319^2 + 902000^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 1001681^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 0998319^2 + 9102000^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 1001681^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 0998319^2 + 91102000^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 1001681^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 0998319^2 + 911102000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 1001681^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 0998319^2 + 9111102000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1001681^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 0998319^2 + 91111102000^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1001681^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 0998319^2 + 911111102000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1001681^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0998319^2 + 9111111102000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1001681^2 \end{aligned}$$

42)

$$\begin{aligned} &0998236^2 + 84000^2 && := 1001764^2 \\ &12\ 0998236^2 + 924000^2 && := 12\ 1001764^2 \\ &1232\ 0998236^2 + 9324000^2 && := 1232\ 1001764^2 \\ &123432\ 0998236^2 + 93324000^2 && := 123432\ 1001764^2 \\ &12345432\ 0998236^2 + 933324000^2 && := 12345432\ 1001764^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0998236^2 + 9333324000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1001764^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0998236^2 + 93333324000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1001764^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0998236^2 + 933333324000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1001764^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0998236^2 + 9333333324000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1001764^2 \end{aligned}$$

43)

$$\begin{aligned} &0998151^2 + 86000^2 && := 1001849^2 \\ &12\ 0998151^2 + 946000^2 && := 12\ 1001849^2 \\ &1232\ 0998151^2 + 9546000^2 && := 1232\ 1001849^2 \\ &123432\ 0998151^2 + 95546000^2 && := 123432\ 1001849^2 \\ &12345432\ 0998151^2 + 955546000^2 && := 12345432\ 1001849^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0998151^2 + 9555546000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1001849^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0998151^2 + 95555546000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1001849^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0998151^2 + 955555546000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1001849^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0998151^2 + 9555555546000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1001849^2 \end{aligned}$$

44)

$$\begin{aligned} &0998064^2 + 88000^2 && := 1001936^2 \\ &12\ 0998064^2 + 968000^2 && := 12\ 1001936^2 \\ &1232\ 0998064^2 + 9768000^2 && := 1232\ 1001936^2 \\ &123432\ 0998064^2 + 97768000^2 && := 123432\ 1001936^2 \\ &12345432\ 0998064^2 + 977768000^2 && := 12345432\ 1001936^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0998064^2 + 9777768000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1001936^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0998064^2 + 97777768000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1001936^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0998064^2 + 977777768000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1001936^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0998064^2 + 9777777768000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1001936^2 \end{aligned}$$

45)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0997975^2 + 90000^2 && := 1002025^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12} 0997975^2 + 990000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1002025^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1232} 0997975^2 + 9990000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1002025^2 \\
 &\mathbf{123432} 0997975^2 + 99990000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1002025^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12345432} 0997975^2 + 999990000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1002025^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1234565432} 0997975^2 + 9999990000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1002025^2 \\
 &\mathbf{123456765432} 0997975^2 + 99999990000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1002025^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0997975^2 + 999999990000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1002025^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0997975^2 + 9999999990000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1002025^2
 \end{aligned}$$

46)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0997884^2 + 92000^2 && := 1002116^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12} 0997884^2 + 1012000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1002116^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1232} 0997884^2 + 10212000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1002116^2 \\
 &\mathbf{123432} 0997884^2 + 102212000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1002116^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12345432} 0997884^2 + 1022212000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1002116^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1234565432} 0997884^2 + 10222212000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1002116^2 \\
 &\mathbf{123456765432} 0997884^2 + 102222212000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1002116^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0997884^2 + 1022222212000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1002116^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0997884^2 + 10222222212000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1002116^2
 \end{aligned}$$

47)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0997791^2 + 94000^2 && := 1002209^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12} 0997791^2 + 1034000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1002209^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1232} 0997791^2 + 10434000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1002209^2 \\
 &\mathbf{123432} 0997791^2 + 104434000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1002209^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12345432} 0997791^2 + 1044434000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1002209^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1234565432} 0997791^2 + 10444434000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1002209^2 \\
 &\mathbf{123456765432} 0997791^2 + 104444434000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1002209^2 \\
 &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0997791^2 + 1044444434000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1002209^2 \\
 &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0997791^2 + 10444444434000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1002209^2
 \end{aligned}$$

48)

$$\begin{aligned} &0997696^2 + 96000^2 && := 1002304^2 \\ &12\ 0997696^2 + 1056000^2 && := 12\ 1002304^2 \\ &1232\ 0997696^2 + 10656000^2 && := 1232\ 1002304^2 \\ &123432\ 0997696^2 + 106656000^2 && := 123432\ 1002304^2 \\ &12345432\ 0997696^2 + 1066656000^2 && := 12345432\ 1002304^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0997696^2 + 10666656000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1002304^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0997696^2 + 106666656000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1002304^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0997696^2 + 1066666656000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1002304^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0997696^2 + 10666666656000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1002304^2 \end{aligned}$$

49)

$$\begin{aligned} &0997599^2 + 98000^2 && := 1002401^2 \\ &12\ 0997599^2 + 1078000^2 && := 12\ 1002401^2 \\ &1232\ 0997599^2 + 10878000^2 && := 1232\ 1002401^2 \\ &123432\ 0997599^2 + 108878000^2 && := 123432\ 1002401^2 \\ &12345432\ 0997599^2 + 1088878000^2 && := 12345432\ 1002401^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0997599^2 + 10888878000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1002401^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0997599^2 + 108888878000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1002401^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0997599^2 + 1088888878000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1002401^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0997599^2 + 10888888878000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1002401^2 \end{aligned}$$

50)

$$\begin{aligned} &0997500^2 + 100000^2 && := 1002500^2 \\ &12\ 0997500^2 + 1100000^2 && := 12\ 1002500^2 \\ &1232\ 0997500^2 + 11100000^2 && := 1232\ 1002500^2 \\ &123432\ 0997500^2 + 111100000^2 && := 123432\ 1002500^2 \\ &12345432\ 0997500^2 + 1111100000^2 && := 12345432\ 1002500^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0997500^2 + 11111100000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1002500^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0997500^2 + 111111100000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1002500^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0997500^2 + 1111111100000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1002500^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0997500^2 + 11111111100000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1002500^2 \end{aligned}$$

51)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0997399^2 + 102000^2 & := & 1002601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0997399^2 + 1122000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1002601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0997399^2 + 11322000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1002601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0997399^2 + 113322000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1002601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0997399^2 + 1133322000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1002601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0997399^2 + 11333322000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1002601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0997399^2 + 113333322000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1002601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0997399^2 + 1133333322000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1002601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0997399^2 + 11333333322000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1002601^2 \end{aligned}$$

52)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0997296^2 + 104000^2 & := & 1002704^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0997296^2 + 1144000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1002704^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0997296^2 + 11544000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1002704^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0997296^2 + 115544000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1002704^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0997296^2 + 1155544000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1002704^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0997296^2 + 11555544000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1002704^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0997296^2 + 115555544000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1002704^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0997296^2 + 1155555544000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1002704^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0997296^2 + 11555555544000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1002704^2 \end{aligned}$$

53)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0997191^2 + 106000^2 & := & 1002809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0997191^2 + 1166000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1002809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0997191^2 + 11766000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1002809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0997191^2 + 117766000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1002809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0997191^2 + 1177766000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1002809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0997191^2 + 11777766000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1002809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0997191^2 + 117777766000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1002809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0997191^2 + 1177777766000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1002809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0997191^2 + 11777777766000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1002809^2 \end{aligned}$$

54)

$$\begin{aligned} &0997084^2 + 108000^2 && := 1002916^2 \\ &12\ 0997084^2 + 1188000^2 && := 12\ 1002916^2 \\ &1232\ 0997084^2 + 11988000^2 && := 1232\ 1002916^2 \\ &123432\ 0997084^2 + 119988000^2 && := 123432\ 1002916^2 \\ &12345432\ 0997084^2 + 1199988000^2 && := 12345432\ 1002916^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0997084^2 + 11999988000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1002916^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0997084^2 + 119999988000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1002916^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0997084^2 + 1199999988000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1002916^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0997084^2 + 11999999988000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1002916^2 \end{aligned}$$

55)

$$\begin{aligned} &0996975^2 + 110000^2 && := 1003025^2 \\ &12\ 0996975^2 + 1210000^2 && := 12\ 1003025^2 \\ &1232\ 0996975^2 + 12210000^2 && := 1232\ 1003025^2 \\ &123432\ 0996975^2 + 122210000^2 && := 123432\ 1003025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0996975^2 + 1222210000^2 && := 12345432\ 1003025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0996975^2 + 12222210000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1003025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0996975^2 + 122222210000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1003025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0996975^2 + 1222222210000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1003025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0996975^2 + 12222222210000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1003025^2 \end{aligned}$$

56)

$$\begin{aligned} &0996864^2 + 112000^2 && := 1003136^2 \\ &12\ 0996864^2 + 1232000^2 && := 12\ 1003136^2 \\ &1232\ 0996864^2 + 12432000^2 && := 1232\ 1003136^2 \\ &123432\ 0996864^2 + 124432000^2 && := 123432\ 1003136^2 \\ &12345432\ 0996864^2 + 1244432000^2 && := 12345432\ 1003136^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0996864^2 + 12444432000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1003136^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0996864^2 + 124444432000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1003136^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0996864^2 + 1244444432000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1003136^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0996864^2 + 12444444432000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1003136^2 \end{aligned}$$

57)

$$\begin{aligned} &0996751^2 + 114000^2 && := 1003249^2 \\ &12\ 0996751^2 + 1254000^2 && := 12\ 1003249^2 \\ &1232\ 0996751^2 + 12654000^2 && := 1232\ 1003249^2 \\ &123432\ 0996751^2 + 126654000^2 && := 123432\ 1003249^2 \\ &12345432\ 0996751^2 + 1266654000^2 && := 12345432\ 1003249^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0996751^2 + 12666654000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1003249^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0996751^2 + 126666654000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1003249^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0996751^2 + 1266666654000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1003249^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0996751^2 + 12666666654000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1003249^2 \end{aligned}$$

58)

$$\begin{aligned} &0996636^2 + 116000^2 && := 1003364^2 \\ &12\ 0996636^2 + 1276000^2 && := 12\ 1003364^2 \\ &1232\ 0996636^2 + 12876000^2 && := 1232\ 1003364^2 \\ &123432\ 0996636^2 + 128876000^2 && := 123432\ 1003364^2 \\ &12345432\ 0996636^2 + 1288876000^2 && := 12345432\ 1003364^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0996636^2 + 12888876000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1003364^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0996636^2 + 128888876000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1003364^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0996636^2 + 1288888876000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1003364^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0996636^2 + 12888888876000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1003364^2 \end{aligned}$$

59)

$$\begin{aligned} &0996519^2 + 118000^2 && := 1003481^2 \\ &12\ 0996519^2 + 1298000^2 && := 12\ 1003481^2 \\ &1232\ 0996519^2 + 13098000^2 && := 1232\ 1003481^2 \\ &123432\ 0996519^2 + 131098000^2 && := 123432\ 1003481^2 \\ &12345432\ 0996519^2 + 1311098000^2 && := 12345432\ 1003481^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0996519^2 + 13111098000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1003481^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0996519^2 + 131111098000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1003481^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0996519^2 + 1311111098000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1003481^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0996519^2 + 13111111098000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1003481^2 \end{aligned}$$

60)

$$\begin{aligned} &0996400^2 + 120000^2 && := 1003600^2 \\ &12\ 0996400^2 + 1320000^2 && := 12\ 1003600^2 \\ &1232\ 0996400^2 + 13320000^2 && := 1232\ 1003600^2 \\ &123432\ 0996400^2 + 133320000^2 && := 123432\ 1003600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0996400^2 + 1333320000^2 && := 12345432\ 1003600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0996400^2 + 13333320000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1003600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0996400^2 + 133333320000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1003600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0996400^2 + 1333333320000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1003600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0996400^2 + 13333333320000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1003600^2 \end{aligned}$$

61)

$$\begin{aligned} &0996279^2 + 122000^2 && := 1003721^2 \\ &12\ 0996279^2 + 1342000^2 && := 12\ 1003721^2 \\ &1232\ 0996279^2 + 13542000^2 && := 1232\ 1003721^2 \\ &123432\ 0996279^2 + 135542000^2 && := 123432\ 1003721^2 \\ &12345432\ 0996279^2 + 1355542000^2 && := 12345432\ 1003721^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0996279^2 + 13555542000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1003721^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0996279^2 + 135555542000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1003721^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0996279^2 + 1355555542000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1003721^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0996279^2 + 13555555542000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1003721^2 \end{aligned}$$

62)

$$\begin{aligned} &0996156^2 + 124000^2 && := 1003844^2 \\ &12\ 0996156^2 + 1364000^2 && := 12\ 1003844^2 \\ &1232\ 0996156^2 + 13764000^2 && := 1232\ 1003844^2 \\ &123432\ 0996156^2 + 137764000^2 && := 123432\ 1003844^2 \\ &12345432\ 0996156^2 + 1377764000^2 && := 12345432\ 1003844^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0996156^2 + 13777764000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1003844^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0996156^2 + 137777764000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1003844^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0996156^2 + 1377777764000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1003844^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0996156^2 + 13777777764000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1003844^2 \end{aligned}$$

63)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0996031^2 + 126000^2 & := & 1003969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0996031^2 + 1386000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1003969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0996031^2 + 13986000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1003969^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0996031^2 + 139986000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1003969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0996031^2 + 1399986000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1003969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0996031^2 + 13999986000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1003969^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0996031^2 + 139999986000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1003969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0996031^2 + 1399999986000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1003969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0996031^2 + 13999999986000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1003969^2 \end{aligned}$$

64)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0995904^2 + 128000^2 & := & 1004096^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0995904^2 + 1408000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1004096^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0995904^2 + 14208000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1004096^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0995904^2 + 142208000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1004096^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0995904^2 + 1422208000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1004096^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0995904^2 + 14222208000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1004096^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0995904^2 + 142222208000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1004096^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0995904^2 + 1422222208000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1004096^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0995904^2 + 14222222208000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1004096^2 \end{aligned}$$

65)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0995775^2 + 130000^2 & := & 1004225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0995775^2 + 1430000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1004225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0995775^2 + 14430000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1004225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0995775^2 + 144430000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1004225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0995775^2 + 1444430000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1004225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0995775^2 + 14444430000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1004225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0995775^2 + 144444430000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1004225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0995775^2 + 1444444430000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1004225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0995775^2 + 14444444430000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1004225^2 \end{aligned}$$

66)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0995644^2 + 132000^2 & := & 1004356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0995644^2 + 1452000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1004356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0995644^2 + 14652000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1004356^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0995644^2 + 146652000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1004356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0995644^2 + 1466652000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1004356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0995644^2 + 14666652000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1004356^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0995644^2 + 146666652000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1004356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0995644^2 + 1466666652000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1004356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0995644^2 + 14666666652000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1004356^2 \end{aligned}$$

67)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0995511^2 + 134000^2 & := & 1004489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0995511^2 + 1474000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1004489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0995511^2 + 14874000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1004489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0995511^2 + 148874000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1004489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0995511^2 + 1488874000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1004489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0995511^2 + 14888874000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1004489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0995511^2 + 148888874000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1004489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0995511^2 + 1488888874000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1004489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0995511^2 + 14888888874000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1004489^2 \end{aligned}$$

68)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0995376^2 + 136000^2 & := & 1004624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0995376^2 + 1496000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1004624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0995376^2 + 15096000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1004624^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0995376^2 + 151096000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1004624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0995376^2 + 1511096000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1004624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0995376^2 + 15111096000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1004624^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0995376^2 + 151111096000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1004624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0995376^2 + 1511111096000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1004624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0995376^2 + 15111111096000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1004624^2 \end{aligned}$$

69)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0995239^2 + 138000^2 & := & 1004761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0995239^2 + 1518000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1004761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0995239^2 + 15318000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1004761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0995239^2 + 153318000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1004761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0995239^2 + 1533318000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1004761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0995239^2 + 15333318000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1004761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0995239^2 + 153333318000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1004761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0995239^2 + 1533333318000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1004761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0995239^2 + 15333333318000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1004761^2 \end{aligned}$$

70)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0995100^2 + 140000^2 & := & 1004900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0995100^2 + 1540000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1004900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0995100^2 + 15540000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1004900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0995100^2 + 155540000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1004900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0995100^2 + 1555540000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1004900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0995100^2 + 15555540000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1004900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0995100^2 + 155555540000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1004900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0995100^2 + 1555555540000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1004900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0995100^2 + 15555555540000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1004900^2 \end{aligned}$$

71)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0994959^2 + 142000^2 & := & 1005041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0994959^2 + 1562000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1005041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0994959^2 + 15762000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1005041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0994959^2 + 157762000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1005041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0994959^2 + 1577762000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1005041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0994959^2 + 15777762000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1005041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0994959^2 + 157777762000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1005041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0994959^2 + 1577777762000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1005041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0994959^2 + 15777777762000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1005041^2 \end{aligned}$$

72)

$$\begin{aligned} &0994816^2 + 144000^2 && := 1005184^2 \\ &12\ 0994816^2 + 1584000^2 && := 12\ 1005184^2 \\ &1232\ 0994816^2 + 15984000^2 && := 1232\ 1005184^2 \\ &123432\ 0994816^2 + 159984000^2 && := 123432\ 1005184^2 \\ &12345432\ 0994816^2 + 1599984000^2 && := 12345432\ 1005184^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0994816^2 + 15999984000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1005184^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0994816^2 + 159999984000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1005184^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0994816^2 + 1599999984000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1005184^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0994816^2 + 15999999984000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1005184^2 \end{aligned}$$

73)

$$\begin{aligned} &0994671^2 + 146000^2 && := 1005329^2 \\ &12\ 0994671^2 + 1606000^2 && := 12\ 1005329^2 \\ &1232\ 0994671^2 + 16206000^2 && := 1232\ 1005329^2 \\ &123432\ 0994671^2 + 162206000^2 && := 123432\ 1005329^2 \\ &12345432\ 0994671^2 + 1622206000^2 && := 12345432\ 1005329^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0994671^2 + 16222206000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1005329^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0994671^2 + 162222206000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1005329^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0994671^2 + 1622222206000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1005329^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0994671^2 + 16222222206000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1005329^2 \end{aligned}$$

74)

$$\begin{aligned} &0994524^2 + 148000^2 && := 1005476^2 \\ &12\ 0994524^2 + 1628000^2 && := 12\ 1005476^2 \\ &1232\ 0994524^2 + 16428000^2 && := 1232\ 1005476^2 \\ &123432\ 0994524^2 + 164428000^2 && := 123432\ 1005476^2 \\ &12345432\ 0994524^2 + 1644428000^2 && := 12345432\ 1005476^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0994524^2 + 16444428000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1005476^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0994524^2 + 164444428000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1005476^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0994524^2 + 1644444428000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1005476^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0994524^2 + 16444444428000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1005476^2 \end{aligned}$$

75)

$$\begin{aligned} &0994375^2 + 150000^2 && := 1005625^2 \\ &12\ 0994375^2 + 1650000^2 && := 12\ 1005625^2 \\ &1232\ 0994375^2 + 16650000^2 && := 1232\ 1005625^2 \\ &123432\ 0994375^2 + 166650000^2 && := 123432\ 1005625^2 \\ &12345432\ 0994375^2 + 1666650000^2 && := 12345432\ 1005625^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0994375^2 + 16666650000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1005625^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0994375^2 + 166666650000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1005625^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0994375^2 + 1666666650000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1005625^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0994375^2 + 16666666650000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1005625^2 \end{aligned}$$

76)

$$\begin{aligned} &0994224^2 + 152000^2 && := 1005776^2 \\ &12\ 0994224^2 + 1672000^2 && := 12\ 1005776^2 \\ &1232\ 0994224^2 + 16872000^2 && := 1232\ 1005776^2 \\ &123432\ 0994224^2 + 168872000^2 && := 123432\ 1005776^2 \\ &12345432\ 0994224^2 + 1688872000^2 && := 12345432\ 1005776^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0994224^2 + 16888872000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1005776^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0994224^2 + 168888872000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1005776^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0994224^2 + 1688888872000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1005776^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0994224^2 + 16888888872000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1005776^2 \end{aligned}$$

77)

$$\begin{aligned} &0994071^2 + 154000^2 && := 1005929^2 \\ &12\ 0994071^2 + 1694000^2 && := 12\ 1005929^2 \\ &1232\ 0994071^2 + 17094000^2 && := 1232\ 1005929^2 \\ &123432\ 0994071^2 + 171094000^2 && := 123432\ 1005929^2 \\ &12345432\ 0994071^2 + 1711094000^2 && := 12345432\ 1005929^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0994071^2 + 17111094000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1005929^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0994071^2 + 171111094000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1005929^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0994071^2 + 1711111094000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1005929^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0994071^2 + 17111111094000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1005929^2 \end{aligned}$$

78)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0993916^2 + 156000^2 & := & 1006084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0993916^2 + 1716000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1006084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0993916^2 + 17316000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1006084^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0993916^2 + 173316000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1006084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0993916^2 + 1733316000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1006084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0993916^2 + 17333316000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1006084^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0993916^2 + 173333316000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1006084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0993916^2 + 1733333316000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1006084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0993916^2 + 17333333316000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1006084^2 \end{aligned}$$

79)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0993759^2 + 158000^2 & := & 1006241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0993759^2 + 1738000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1006241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0993759^2 + 17538000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1006241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0993759^2 + 175538000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1006241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0993759^2 + 1755538000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1006241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0993759^2 + 17555538000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1006241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0993759^2 + 175555538000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1006241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0993759^2 + 1755555538000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1006241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0993759^2 + 17555555538000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1006241^2 \end{aligned}$$

80)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0993600^2 + 160000^2 & := & 1006400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0993600^2 + 1760000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1006400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0993600^2 + 17760000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1006400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0993600^2 + 177760000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1006400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0993600^2 + 1777760000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1006400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0993600^2 + 17777760000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1006400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0993600^2 + 177777760000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1006400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0993600^2 + 1777777760000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1006400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0993600^2 + 17777777760000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1006400^2 \end{aligned}$$

81)

$$\begin{aligned} &0993439^2 + 162000^2 && := 1006561^2 \\ &12\ 0993439^2 + 1782000^2 && := 12\ 1006561^2 \\ &1232\ 0993439^2 + 17982000^2 && := 1232\ 1006561^2 \\ &123432\ 0993439^2 + 179982000^2 && := 123432\ 1006561^2 \\ &12345432\ 0993439^2 + 1799982000^2 && := 12345432\ 1006561^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0993439^2 + 17999982000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1006561^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0993439^2 + 179999982000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1006561^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0993439^2 + 1799999982000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1006561^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0993439^2 + 17999999982000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1006561^2 \end{aligned}$$

82)

$$\begin{aligned} &0993276^2 + 164000^2 && := 1006724^2 \\ &12\ 0993276^2 + 1804000^2 && := 12\ 1006724^2 \\ &1232\ 0993276^2 + 18204000^2 && := 1232\ 1006724^2 \\ &123432\ 0993276^2 + 182204000^2 && := 123432\ 1006724^2 \\ &12345432\ 0993276^2 + 1822204000^2 && := 12345432\ 1006724^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0993276^2 + 18222204000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1006724^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0993276^2 + 182222204000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1006724^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0993276^2 + 1822222204000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1006724^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0993276^2 + 18222222204000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1006724^2 \end{aligned}$$

83)

$$\begin{aligned} &0993111^2 + 166000^2 && := 1006889^2 \\ &12\ 0993111^2 + 1826000^2 && := 12\ 1006889^2 \\ &1232\ 0993111^2 + 18426000^2 && := 1232\ 1006889^2 \\ &123432\ 0993111^2 + 184426000^2 && := 123432\ 1006889^2 \\ &12345432\ 0993111^2 + 1844426000^2 && := 12345432\ 1006889^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0993111^2 + 18444426000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1006889^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0993111^2 + 184444426000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1006889^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0993111^2 + 1844444426000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1006889^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0993111^2 + 18444444426000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1006889^2 \end{aligned}$$

84)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0992944^2 + 168000^2 & := & 1007056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0992944^2 + 1848000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1007056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0992944^2 + 18648000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1007056^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0992944^2 + 186648000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1007056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0992944^2 + 1866648000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1007056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0992944^2 + 18666648000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1007056^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0992944^2 + 186666648000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1007056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0992944^2 + 1866666648000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1007056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0992944^2 + 18666666648000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1007056^2 \end{aligned}$$

85)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0992775^2 + 170000^2 & := & 1007225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0992775^2 + 1870000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1007225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0992775^2 + 18870000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1007225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0992775^2 + 188870000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1007225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0992775^2 + 1888870000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1007225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0992775^2 + 18888870000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1007225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0992775^2 + 188888870000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1007225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0992775^2 + 1888888870000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1007225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0992775^2 + 18888888870000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1007225^2 \end{aligned}$$

86)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0992604^2 + 172000^2 & := & 1007396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0992604^2 + 1892000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1007396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0992604^2 + 19092000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1007396^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0992604^2 + 191092000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1007396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0992604^2 + 1911092000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1007396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0992604^2 + 19111092000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1007396^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0992604^2 + 191111092000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1007396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0992604^2 + 1911111092000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1007396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0992604^2 + 19111111092000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1007396^2 \end{aligned}$$

87)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0992431^2 + 174000^2 & := & 1007569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0992431^2 + 1914000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1007569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0992431^2 + 19314000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1007569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0992431^2 + 193314000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1007569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0992431^2 + 1933314000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1007569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0992431^2 + 19333314000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1007569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0992431^2 + 193333314000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1007569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0992431^2 + 1933333314000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1007569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0992431^2 + 19333333314000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1007569^2 \end{aligned}$$

88)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0992256^2 + 176000^2 & := & 1007744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0992256^2 + 1936000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1007744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0992256^2 + 19536000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1007744^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0992256^2 + 195536000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1007744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0992256^2 + 1955536000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1007744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0992256^2 + 19555536000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1007744^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0992256^2 + 195555536000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1007744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0992256^2 + 1955555536000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1007744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0992256^2 + 19555555536000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1007744^2 \end{aligned}$$

89)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0992079^2 + 178000^2 & := & 1007921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0992079^2 + 1958000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1007921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0992079^2 + 19758000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1007921^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0992079^2 + 197758000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1007921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0992079^2 + 1977758000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1007921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0992079^2 + 19777758000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1007921^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0992079^2 + 197777758000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1007921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0992079^2 + 1977777758000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1007921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0992079^2 + 19777777758000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1007921^2 \end{aligned}$$

90)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0991900^2 + 180000^2 & := & 1008100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0991900^2 + 1980000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1008100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0991900^2 + 19980000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1008100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0991900^2 + 199980000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1008100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0991900^2 + 1999980000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1008100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0991900^2 + 19999980000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1008100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0991900^2 + 199999980000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1008100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0991900^2 + 1999999980000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1008100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0991900^2 + 19999999980000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1008100^2 \end{aligned}$$

91)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0991719^2 + 182000^2 & := & 1008281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0991719^2 + 2002000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1008281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0991719^2 + 20202000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1008281^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0991719^2 + 202202000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1008281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0991719^2 + 2022202000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1008281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0991719^2 + 20222202000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1008281^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0991719^2 + 202222202000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1008281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0991719^2 + 2022222202000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1008281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0991719^2 + 20222222202000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1008281^2 \end{aligned}$$

92)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0991536^2 + 184000^2 & := & 1008464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0991536^2 + 2024000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1008464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0991536^2 + 20424000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1008464^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0991536^2 + 204424000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1008464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0991536^2 + 2044424000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1008464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0991536^2 + 20444424000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1008464^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0991536^2 + 204444424000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1008464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0991536^2 + 2044444424000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1008464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0991536^2 + 20444444424000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1008464^2 \end{aligned}$$

93)

$$\begin{aligned} &0991351^2 + 186000^2 && := 1008649^2 \\ &12\ 0991351^2 + 2046000^2 && := 12\ 1008649^2 \\ &1232\ 0991351^2 + 20646000^2 && := 1232\ 1008649^2 \\ &123432\ 0991351^2 + 206646000^2 && := 123432\ 1008649^2 \\ &12345432\ 0991351^2 + 2066646000^2 && := 12345432\ 1008649^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0991351^2 + 20666646000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1008649^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0991351^2 + 206666646000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1008649^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0991351^2 + 2066666646000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1008649^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0991351^2 + 20666666646000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1008649^2 \end{aligned}$$

94)

$$\begin{aligned} &0991164^2 + 188000^2 && := 1008836^2 \\ &12\ 0991164^2 + 2068000^2 && := 12\ 1008836^2 \\ &1232\ 0991164^2 + 20868000^2 && := 1232\ 1008836^2 \\ &123432\ 0991164^2 + 208868000^2 && := 123432\ 1008836^2 \\ &12345432\ 0991164^2 + 2088868000^2 && := 12345432\ 1008836^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0991164^2 + 20888868000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1008836^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0991164^2 + 208888868000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1008836^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0991164^2 + 2088888868000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1008836^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0991164^2 + 20888888868000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1008836^2 \end{aligned}$$

95)

$$\begin{aligned} &0990975^2 + 190000^2 && := 1009025^2 \\ &12\ 0990975^2 + 2090000^2 && := 12\ 1009025^2 \\ &1232\ 0990975^2 + 21090000^2 && := 1232\ 1009025^2 \\ &123432\ 0990975^2 + 211090000^2 && := 123432\ 1009025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0990975^2 + 2111090000^2 && := 12345432\ 1009025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0990975^2 + 21111090000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1009025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0990975^2 + 211111090000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1009025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0990975^2 + 2111111090000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1009025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0990975^2 + 21111111090000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1009025^2 \end{aligned}$$

96)

$$\begin{aligned} &0990784^2 + 192000^2 && := 1009216^2 \\ &12\ 0990784^2 + 2112000^2 && := 12\ 1009216^2 \\ &1232\ 0990784^2 + 21312000^2 && := 1232\ 1009216^2 \\ &123432\ 0990784^2 + 213312000^2 && := 123432\ 1009216^2 \\ &12345432\ 0990784^2 + 2133312000^2 && := 12345432\ 1009216^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0990784^2 + 21333312000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1009216^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0990784^2 + 213333312000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1009216^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0990784^2 + 2133333312000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1009216^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0990784^2 + 21333333312000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1009216^2 \end{aligned}$$

97)

$$\begin{aligned} &0990591^2 + 194000^2 && := 1009409^2 \\ &12\ 0990591^2 + 2134000^2 && := 12\ 1009409^2 \\ &1232\ 0990591^2 + 21534000^2 && := 1232\ 1009409^2 \\ &123432\ 0990591^2 + 215534000^2 && := 123432\ 1009409^2 \\ &12345432\ 0990591^2 + 2155534000^2 && := 12345432\ 1009409^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0990591^2 + 21555534000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1009409^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0990591^2 + 215555534000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1009409^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0990591^2 + 2155555534000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1009409^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0990591^2 + 21555555534000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1009409^2 \end{aligned}$$

98)

$$\begin{aligned} &0990396^2 + 196000^2 && := 1009604^2 \\ &12\ 0990396^2 + 2156000^2 && := 12\ 1009604^2 \\ &1232\ 0990396^2 + 21756000^2 && := 1232\ 1009604^2 \\ &123432\ 0990396^2 + 217756000^2 && := 123432\ 1009604^2 \\ &12345432\ 0990396^2 + 2177756000^2 && := 12345432\ 1009604^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0990396^2 + 21777756000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1009604^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0990396^2 + 217777756000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1009604^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0990396^2 + 2177777756000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1009604^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0990396^2 + 21777777756000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1009604^2 \end{aligned}$$

99)

$$\begin{aligned} &0990199^2 + 198000^2 && := 1009801^2 \\ &12\ 0990199^2 + 2178000^2 && := 12\ 1009801^2 \\ &1232\ 0990199^2 + 21978000^2 && := 1232\ 1009801^2 \\ &123432\ 0990199^2 + 219978000^2 && := 123432\ 1009801^2 \\ &12345432\ 0990199^2 + 2199978000^2 && := 12345432\ 1009801^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0990199^2 + 21999978000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1009801^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0990199^2 + 219999978000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1009801^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0990199^2 + 2199999978000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1009801^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0990199^2 + 21999999978000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1009801^2 \end{aligned}$$

100)

$$\begin{aligned} &0990000^2 + 200000^2 && := 1010000^2 \\ &12\ 0990000^2 + 2200000^2 && := 12\ 1010000^2 \\ &1232\ 0990000^2 + 22200000^2 && := 1232\ 1010000^2 \\ &123432\ 0990000^2 + 222200000^2 && := 123432\ 1010000^2 \\ &12345432\ 0990000^2 + 2222200000^2 && := 12345432\ 1010000^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0990000^2 + 22222200000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1010000^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0990000^2 + 222222200000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1010000^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0990000^2 + 2222222200000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1010000^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0990000^2 + 22222222200000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1010000^2 \end{aligned}$$

101)

$$\begin{aligned} &0989799^2 + 202000^2 && := 1010201^2 \\ &12\ 0989799^2 + 2222000^2 && := 12\ 1010201^2 \\ &1232\ 0989799^2 + 22422000^2 && := 1232\ 1010201^2 \\ &123432\ 0989799^2 + 224422000^2 && := 123432\ 1010201^2 \\ &12345432\ 0989799^2 + 2244422000^2 && := 12345432\ 1010201^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0989799^2 + 22444422000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1010201^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0989799^2 + 224444422000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1010201^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0989799^2 + 2244444422000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1010201^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0989799^2 + 22444444422000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1010201^2 \end{aligned}$$

102)

$$\begin{aligned} &0989596^2 + 204000^2 && := 1010404^2 \\ &12\ 0989596^2 + 2244000^2 && := 12\ 1010404^2 \\ &1232\ 0989596^2 + 22644000^2 && := 1232\ 1010404^2 \\ &123432\ 0989596^2 + 226644000^2 && := 123432\ 1010404^2 \\ &12345432\ 0989596^2 + 2266644000^2 && := 12345432\ 1010404^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0989596^2 + 22666644000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1010404^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0989596^2 + 226666644000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1010404^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0989596^2 + 2266666644000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1010404^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0989596^2 + 22666666644000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1010404^2 \end{aligned}$$

103)

$$\begin{aligned} &0989391^2 + 206000^2 && := 1010609^2 \\ &12\ 0989391^2 + 2266000^2 && := 12\ 1010609^2 \\ &1232\ 0989391^2 + 22866000^2 && := 1232\ 1010609^2 \\ &123432\ 0989391^2 + 228866000^2 && := 123432\ 1010609^2 \\ &12345432\ 0989391^2 + 2288866000^2 && := 12345432\ 1010609^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0989391^2 + 22888866000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1010609^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0989391^2 + 228888866000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1010609^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0989391^2 + 2288888866000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1010609^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0989391^2 + 22888888866000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1010609^2 \end{aligned}$$

104)

$$\begin{aligned} &0989184^2 + 208000^2 && := 1010816^2 \\ &12\ 0989184^2 + 2288000^2 && := 12\ 1010816^2 \\ &1232\ 0989184^2 + 23088000^2 && := 1232\ 1010816^2 \\ &123432\ 0989184^2 + 231088000^2 && := 123432\ 1010816^2 \\ &12345432\ 0989184^2 + 2311088000^2 && := 12345432\ 1010816^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0989184^2 + 23111088000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1010816^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0989184^2 + 231111088000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1010816^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0989184^2 + 2311111088000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1010816^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0989184^2 + 23111111088000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1010816^2 \end{aligned}$$

105)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0988975^2 + 210000^2 & := & 1011025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0988975^2 + 2310000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1011025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0988975^2 + 23310000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1011025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0988975^2 + 233310000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1011025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0988975^2 + 2333310000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1011025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0988975^2 + 23333310000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1011025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0988975^2 + 233333310000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1011025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0988975^2 + 2333333310000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1011025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0988975^2 + 23333333310000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1011025^2 \end{aligned}$$

106)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0988764^2 + 212000^2 & := & 1011236^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0988764^2 + 2332000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1011236^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0988764^2 + 23532000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1011236^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0988764^2 + 235532000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1011236^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0988764^2 + 2355532000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1011236^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0988764^2 + 23555532000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1011236^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0988764^2 + 235555532000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1011236^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0988764^2 + 2355555532000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1011236^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0988764^2 + 23555555532000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1011236^2 \end{aligned}$$

107)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0988551^2 + 214000^2 & := & 1011449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0988551^2 + 2354000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1011449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0988551^2 + 23754000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1011449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0988551^2 + 237754000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1011449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0988551^2 + 2377754000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1011449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0988551^2 + 23777754000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1011449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0988551^2 + 237777754000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1011449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0988551^2 + 2377777754000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1011449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0988551^2 + 23777777754000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1011449^2 \end{aligned}$$

108)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0988336^2 + 216000^2 & := & 1011664^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0988336^2 + 2376000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1011664^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0988336^2 + 23976000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1011664^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0988336^2 + 239976000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1011664^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0988336^2 + 2399976000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1011664^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0988336^2 + 23999976000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1011664^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0988336^2 + 239999976000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1011664^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0988336^2 + 2399999976000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1011664^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0988336^2 + 23999999976000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1011664^2 \end{aligned}$$

109)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0988119^2 + 218000^2 & := & 1011881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0988119^2 + 2398000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1011881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0988119^2 + 24198000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1011881^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0988119^2 + 242198000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1011881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0988119^2 + 2422198000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1011881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0988119^2 + 24222198000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1011881^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0988119^2 + 242222198000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1011881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0988119^2 + 2422222198000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1011881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0988119^2 + 24222222198000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1011881^2 \end{aligned}$$

110)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0987900^2 + 220000^2 & := & 1012100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0987900^2 + 2420000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1012100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0987900^2 + 24420000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1012100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0987900^2 + 244420000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1012100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0987900^2 + 2444420000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1012100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0987900^2 + 24444420000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1012100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0987900^2 + 244444420000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1012100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0987900^2 + 2444444420000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1012100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0987900^2 + 24444444420000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1012100^2 \end{aligned}$$

111)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0987679^2 + 222000^2 & := & 1012321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0987679^2 + 2442000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1012321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0987679^2 + 24642000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1012321^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0987679^2 + 246642000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1012321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0987679^2 + 2466642000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1012321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0987679^2 + 24666642000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1012321^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0987679^2 + 246666642000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1012321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0987679^2 + 2466666642000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1012321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0987679^2 + 24666666642000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1012321^2 \end{aligned}$$

112)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0987456^2 + 224000^2 & := & 1012544^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0987456^2 + 2464000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1012544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0987456^2 + 24864000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1012544^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0987456^2 + 248864000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1012544^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0987456^2 + 2488864000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1012544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0987456^2 + 24888864000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1012544^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0987456^2 + 248888864000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1012544^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0987456^2 + 2488888864000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1012544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0987456^2 + 24888888864000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1012544^2 \end{aligned}$$

113)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0987231^2 + 226000^2 & := & 1012769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0987231^2 + 2486000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1012769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0987231^2 + 25086000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1012769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0987231^2 + 251086000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1012769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0987231^2 + 2511086000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1012769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0987231^2 + 25111086000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1012769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0987231^2 + 251111086000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1012769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0987231^2 + 2511111086000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1012769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0987231^2 + 25111111086000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1012769^2 \end{aligned}$$

114)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0987004^2 + 228000^2 & := & 1012996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0987004^2 + 2508000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1012996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0987004^2 + 25308000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1012996^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0987004^2 + 253308000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1012996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0987004^2 + 2533308000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1012996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0987004^2 + 25333308000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1012996^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0987004^2 + 253333308000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1012996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0987004^2 + 2533333308000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1012996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0987004^2 + 25333333308000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1012996^2 \end{aligned}$$

115)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0986775^2 + 230000^2 & := & 1013225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0986775^2 + 2530000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1013225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0986775^2 + 25530000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1013225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0986775^2 + 255530000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1013225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0986775^2 + 2555530000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1013225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0986775^2 + 25555530000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1013225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0986775^2 + 255555530000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1013225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0986775^2 + 2555555530000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1013225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0986775^2 + 25555555530000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1013225^2 \end{aligned}$$

116)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0986544^2 + 232000^2 & := & 1013456^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0986544^2 + 2552000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1013456^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0986544^2 + 25752000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1013456^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0986544^2 + 257752000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1013456^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0986544^2 + 2577752000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1013456^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0986544^2 + 25777752000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1013456^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0986544^2 + 257777752000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1013456^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0986544^2 + 2577777752000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1013456^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0986544^2 + 25777777752000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1013456^2 \end{aligned}$$

117)

$$\begin{aligned} &0986311^2 + 234000^2 && := 1013689^2 \\ &12\ 0986311^2 + 2574000^2 && := 12\ 1013689^2 \\ &1232\ 0986311^2 + 25974000^2 && := 1232\ 1013689^2 \\ &123432\ 0986311^2 + 259974000^2 && := 123432\ 1013689^2 \\ &12345432\ 0986311^2 + 2599974000^2 && := 12345432\ 1013689^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0986311^2 + 25999974000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1013689^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0986311^2 + 259999974000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1013689^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0986311^2 + 2599999974000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1013689^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0986311^2 + 25999999974000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1013689^2 \end{aligned}$$

118)

$$\begin{aligned} &0986076^2 + 236000^2 && := 1013924^2 \\ &12\ 0986076^2 + 2596000^2 && := 12\ 1013924^2 \\ &1232\ 0986076^2 + 26196000^2 && := 1232\ 1013924^2 \\ &123432\ 0986076^2 + 262196000^2 && := 123432\ 1013924^2 \\ &12345432\ 0986076^2 + 2622196000^2 && := 12345432\ 1013924^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0986076^2 + 26222196000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1013924^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0986076^2 + 262222196000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1013924^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0986076^2 + 2622222196000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1013924^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0986076^2 + 26222222196000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1013924^2 \end{aligned}$$

119)

$$\begin{aligned} &0985839^2 + 238000^2 && := 1014161^2 \\ &12\ 0985839^2 + 2618000^2 && := 12\ 1014161^2 \\ &1232\ 0985839^2 + 26418000^2 && := 1232\ 1014161^2 \\ &123432\ 0985839^2 + 264418000^2 && := 123432\ 1014161^2 \\ &12345432\ 0985839^2 + 2644418000^2 && := 12345432\ 1014161^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0985839^2 + 26444418000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1014161^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0985839^2 + 264444418000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1014161^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0985839^2 + 2644444418000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1014161^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0985839^2 + 26444444418000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1014161^2 \end{aligned}$$

120)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0985600^2 + 240000^2 & := & 1014400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0985600^2 + 2640000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1014400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0985600^2 + 26640000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1014400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0985600^2 + 266640000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1014400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0985600^2 + 2666640000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1014400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0985600^2 + 26666640000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1014400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0985600^2 + 266666640000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1014400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0985600^2 + 2666666640000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1014400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0985600^2 + 26666666640000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1014400^2 \end{aligned}$$

121)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0985359^2 + 242000^2 & := & 1014641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0985359^2 + 2662000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1014641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0985359^2 + 26862000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1014641^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0985359^2 + 268862000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1014641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0985359^2 + 2688862000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1014641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0985359^2 + 26888862000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1014641^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0985359^2 + 268888862000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1014641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0985359^2 + 2688888862000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1014641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0985359^2 + 26888888862000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1014641^2 \end{aligned}$$

122)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0985116^2 + 244000^2 & := & 1014884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0985116^2 + 2684000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1014884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0985116^2 + 27084000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1014884^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0985116^2 + 271084000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1014884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0985116^2 + 2711084000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1014884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0985116^2 + 27111084000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1014884^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0985116^2 + 271111084000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1014884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0985116^2 + 2711111084000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1014884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0985116^2 + 27111111084000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1014884^2 \end{aligned}$$

123)

$$\begin{aligned} &0984871^2 + 246000^2 && := 1015129^2 \\ &12\ 0984871^2 + 2706000^2 && := 12\ 1015129^2 \\ &1232\ 0984871^2 + 27306000^2 && := 1232\ 1015129^2 \\ &123432\ 0984871^2 + 273306000^2 && := 123432\ 1015129^2 \\ &12345432\ 0984871^2 + 2733306000^2 && := 12345432\ 1015129^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0984871^2 + 27333306000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1015129^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0984871^2 + 273333306000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1015129^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0984871^2 + 2733333306000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1015129^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0984871^2 + 27333333306000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1015129^2 \end{aligned}$$

124)

$$\begin{aligned} &0984624^2 + 248000^2 && := 1015376^2 \\ &12\ 0984624^2 + 2728000^2 && := 12\ 1015376^2 \\ &1232\ 0984624^2 + 27528000^2 && := 1232\ 1015376^2 \\ &123432\ 0984624^2 + 275528000^2 && := 123432\ 1015376^2 \\ &12345432\ 0984624^2 + 2755528000^2 && := 12345432\ 1015376^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0984624^2 + 27555528000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1015376^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0984624^2 + 275555528000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1015376^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0984624^2 + 2755555528000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1015376^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0984624^2 + 27555555528000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1015376^2 \end{aligned}$$

125)

$$\begin{aligned} &0984375^2 + 250000^2 && := 1015625^2 \\ &12\ 0984375^2 + 2750000^2 && := 12\ 1015625^2 \\ &1232\ 0984375^2 + 27750000^2 && := 1232\ 1015625^2 \\ &123432\ 0984375^2 + 277750000^2 && := 123432\ 1015625^2 \\ &12345432\ 0984375^2 + 2777750000^2 && := 12345432\ 1015625^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0984375^2 + 27777750000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1015625^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0984375^2 + 277777750000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1015625^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0984375^2 + 2777777750000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1015625^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0984375^2 + 27777777750000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1015625^2 \end{aligned}$$

126)

$$\begin{aligned} &0984124^2 + 252000^2 && := 1015876^2 \\ &12\ 0984124^2 + 2772000^2 && := 12\ 1015876^2 \\ &1232\ 0984124^2 + 27972000^2 && := 1232\ 1015876^2 \\ &123432\ 0984124^2 + 279972000^2 && := 123432\ 1015876^2 \\ &12345432\ 0984124^2 + 2799972000^2 && := 12345432\ 1015876^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0984124^2 + 27999972000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1015876^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0984124^2 + 279999972000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1015876^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0984124^2 + 2799999972000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1015876^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0984124^2 + 27999999972000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1015876^2 \end{aligned}$$

127)

$$\begin{aligned} &0983871^2 + 254000^2 && := 1016129^2 \\ &12\ 0983871^2 + 2794000^2 && := 12\ 1016129^2 \\ &1232\ 0983871^2 + 28194000^2 && := 1232\ 1016129^2 \\ &123432\ 0983871^2 + 282194000^2 && := 123432\ 1016129^2 \\ &12345432\ 0983871^2 + 2822194000^2 && := 12345432\ 1016129^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0983871^2 + 28222194000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1016129^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0983871^2 + 282222194000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1016129^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0983871^2 + 2822222194000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1016129^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0983871^2 + 28222222194000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1016129^2 \end{aligned}$$

128)

$$\begin{aligned} &0983616^2 + 256000^2 && := 1016384^2 \\ &12\ 0983616^2 + 2816000^2 && := 12\ 1016384^2 \\ &1232\ 0983616^2 + 28416000^2 && := 1232\ 1016384^2 \\ &123432\ 0983616^2 + 284416000^2 && := 123432\ 1016384^2 \\ &12345432\ 0983616^2 + 2844416000^2 && := 12345432\ 1016384^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0983616^2 + 28444416000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1016384^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0983616^2 + 284444416000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1016384^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0983616^2 + 2844444416000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1016384^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0983616^2 + 28444444416000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1016384^2 \end{aligned}$$

129)

$$\begin{aligned} &0983359^2 + 258000^2 && := 1016641^2 \\ &12\ 0983359^2 + 2838000^2 && := 12\ 1016641^2 \\ &1232\ 0983359^2 + 28638000^2 && := 1232\ 1016641^2 \\ &123432\ 0983359^2 + 286638000^2 && := 123432\ 1016641^2 \\ &12345432\ 0983359^2 + 2866638000^2 && := 12345432\ 1016641^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0983359^2 + 28666638000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1016641^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0983359^2 + 286666638000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1016641^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0983359^2 + 2866666638000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1016641^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0983359^2 + 28666666638000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1016641^2 \end{aligned}$$

130)

$$\begin{aligned} &0983100^2 + 260000^2 && := 1016900^2 \\ &12\ 0983100^2 + 2860000^2 && := 12\ 1016900^2 \\ &1232\ 0983100^2 + 28860000^2 && := 1232\ 1016900^2 \\ &123432\ 0983100^2 + 288860000^2 && := 123432\ 1016900^2 \\ &12345432\ 0983100^2 + 2888860000^2 && := 12345432\ 1016900^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0983100^2 + 28888860000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1016900^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0983100^2 + 288888860000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1016900^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0983100^2 + 2888888860000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1016900^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0983100^2 + 28888888860000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1016900^2 \end{aligned}$$

131)

$$\begin{aligned} &0982839^2 + 262000^2 && := 1017161^2 \\ &12\ 0982839^2 + 2882000^2 && := 12\ 1017161^2 \\ &1232\ 0982839^2 + 29082000^2 && := 1232\ 1017161^2 \\ &123432\ 0982839^2 + 291082000^2 && := 123432\ 1017161^2 \\ &12345432\ 0982839^2 + 2911082000^2 && := 12345432\ 1017161^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0982839^2 + 29111082000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1017161^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0982839^2 + 291111082000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1017161^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0982839^2 + 2911111082000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1017161^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0982839^2 + 29111111082000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1017161^2 \end{aligned}$$

132)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0982576^2 + 264000^2 & := & 1017424^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0982576^2 + 2904000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1017424^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0982576^2 + 29304000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1017424^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0982576^2 + 293304000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1017424^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0982576^2 + 2933304000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1017424^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0982576^2 + 29333304000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1017424^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0982576^2 + 293333304000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1017424^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0982576^2 + 2933333304000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1017424^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0982576^2 + 29333333304000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1017424^2 \end{aligned}$$

133)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0982311^2 + 266000^2 & := & 1017689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0982311^2 + 2926000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1017689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0982311^2 + 29526000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1017689^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0982311^2 + 295526000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1017689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0982311^2 + 2955526000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1017689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0982311^2 + 29555526000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1017689^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0982311^2 + 295555526000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1017689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0982311^2 + 2955555526000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1017689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0982311^2 + 29555555526000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1017689^2 \end{aligned}$$

134)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0982044^2 + 268000^2 & := & 1017956^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0982044^2 + 2948000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1017956^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0982044^2 + 29748000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1017956^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0982044^2 + 297748000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1017956^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0982044^2 + 2977748000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1017956^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0982044^2 + 29777748000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1017956^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0982044^2 + 297777748000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1017956^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0982044^2 + 2977777748000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1017956^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0982044^2 + 29777777748000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1017956^2 \end{aligned}$$

135)

$$\begin{aligned} &0981775^2 + 270000^2 && := 1018225^2 \\ &12\ 0981775^2 + 2970000^2 && := 12\ 1018225^2 \\ &1232\ 0981775^2 + 29970000^2 && := 1232\ 1018225^2 \\ &123432\ 0981775^2 + 299970000^2 && := 123432\ 1018225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0981775^2 + 2999970000^2 && := 12345432\ 1018225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0981775^2 + 29999970000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1018225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0981775^2 + 299999970000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1018225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0981775^2 + 2999999970000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1018225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0981775^2 + 29999999970000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1018225^2 \end{aligned}$$

136)

$$\begin{aligned} &0981504^2 + 272000^2 && := 1018496^2 \\ &12\ 0981504^2 + 2992000^2 && := 12\ 1018496^2 \\ &1232\ 0981504^2 + 30192000^2 && := 1232\ 1018496^2 \\ &123432\ 0981504^2 + 302192000^2 && := 123432\ 1018496^2 \\ &12345432\ 0981504^2 + 3022192000^2 && := 12345432\ 1018496^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0981504^2 + 30222192000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1018496^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0981504^2 + 302222192000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1018496^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0981504^2 + 3022222192000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1018496^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0981504^2 + 30222222192000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1018496^2 \end{aligned}$$

137)

$$\begin{aligned} &0981231^2 + 274000^2 && := 1018769^2 \\ &12\ 0981231^2 + 3014000^2 && := 12\ 1018769^2 \\ &1232\ 0981231^2 + 30414000^2 && := 1232\ 1018769^2 \\ &123432\ 0981231^2 + 304414000^2 && := 123432\ 1018769^2 \\ &12345432\ 0981231^2 + 3044414000^2 && := 12345432\ 1018769^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0981231^2 + 30444414000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1018769^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0981231^2 + 304444414000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1018769^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0981231^2 + 3044444414000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1018769^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0981231^2 + 30444444414000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1018769^2 \end{aligned}$$

138)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0980956^2 + 276000^2 & := & 1019044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0980956^2 + 3036000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1019044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0980956^2 + 30636000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1019044^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0980956^2 + 306636000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1019044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0980956^2 + 3066636000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1019044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0980956^2 + 30666636000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1019044^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0980956^2 + 306666636000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1019044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0980956^2 + 3066666636000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1019044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0980956^2 + 30666666636000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1019044^2 \end{aligned}$$

139)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0980679^2 + 278000^2 & := & 1019321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0980679^2 + 3058000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1019321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0980679^2 + 30858000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1019321^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0980679^2 + 308858000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1019321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0980679^2 + 3088858000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1019321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0980679^2 + 30888858000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1019321^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0980679^2 + 308888858000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1019321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0980679^2 + 3088888858000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1019321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0980679^2 + 30888888858000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1019321^2 \end{aligned}$$

140)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0980400^2 + 280000^2 & := & 1019600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0980400^2 + 3080000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1019600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0980400^2 + 31080000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1019600^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0980400^2 + 311080000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1019600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0980400^2 + 3111080000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1019600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0980400^2 + 31111080000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1019600^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0980400^2 + 311111080000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1019600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0980400^2 + 3111111080000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1019600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0980400^2 + 31111111080000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1019600^2 \end{aligned}$$

141)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0980119^2 + 282000^2 & := & 1019881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0980119^2 + 3102000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1019881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0980119^2 + 31302000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1019881^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0980119^2 + 313302000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1019881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0980119^2 + 3133302000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1019881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0980119^2 + 31333302000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1019881^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0980119^2 + 313333302000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1019881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0980119^2 + 3133333302000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1019881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0980119^2 + 31333333302000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1019881^2 \end{aligned}$$

142)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0979836^2 + 284000^2 & := & 1020164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0979836^2 + 3124000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1020164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0979836^2 + 31524000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1020164^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0979836^2 + 315524000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1020164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0979836^2 + 3155524000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1020164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0979836^2 + 31555524000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1020164^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0979836^2 + 315555524000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1020164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0979836^2 + 3155555524000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1020164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0979836^2 + 31555555524000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1020164^2 \end{aligned}$$

143)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0979551^2 + 286000^2 & := & 1020449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0979551^2 + 3146000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1020449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0979551^2 + 31746000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1020449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0979551^2 + 317746000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1020449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0979551^2 + 3177746000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1020449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0979551^2 + 31777746000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1020449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0979551^2 + 317777746000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1020449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0979551^2 + 3177777746000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1020449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0979551^2 + 31777777746000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1020449^2 \end{aligned}$$

144)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0979264^2 + 288000^2 & := & 1020736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0979264^2 + 3168000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1020736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0979264^2 + 31968000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1020736^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0979264^2 + 319968000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1020736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0979264^2 + 3199968000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1020736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0979264^2 + 31999968000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1020736^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0979264^2 + 319999968000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1020736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0979264^2 + 3199999968000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1020736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0979264^2 + 31999999968000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1020736^2 \end{aligned}$$

145)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0978975^2 + 290000^2 & := & 1021025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0978975^2 + 3190000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1021025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0978975^2 + 32190000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1021025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0978975^2 + 322190000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1021025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0978975^2 + 3222190000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1021025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0978975^2 + 32222190000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1021025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0978975^2 + 322222190000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1021025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0978975^2 + 3222222190000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1021025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0978975^2 + 32222222190000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1021025^2 \end{aligned}$$

146)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0978684^2 + 292000^2 & := & 1021316^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0978684^2 + 3212000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1021316^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0978684^2 + 32412000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1021316^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0978684^2 + 324412000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1021316^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0978684^2 + 3244412000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1021316^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0978684^2 + 32444412000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1021316^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0978684^2 + 324444412000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1021316^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0978684^2 + 3244444412000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1021316^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0978684^2 + 32444444412000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1021316^2 \end{aligned}$$

147)

$$\begin{aligned} &0978391^2 + 294000^2 && := 1021609^2 \\ &12\ 0978391^2 + 3234000^2 && := 12\ 1021609^2 \\ &1232\ 0978391^2 + 32634000^2 && := 1232\ 1021609^2 \\ &123432\ 0978391^2 + 326634000^2 && := 123432\ 1021609^2 \\ &12345432\ 0978391^2 + 3266634000^2 && := 12345432\ 1021609^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0978391^2 + 32666634000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1021609^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0978391^2 + 326666634000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1021609^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0978391^2 + 3266666634000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1021609^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0978391^2 + 32666666634000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1021609^2 \end{aligned}$$

148)

$$\begin{aligned} &0978096^2 + 296000^2 && := 1021904^2 \\ &12\ 0978096^2 + 3256000^2 && := 12\ 1021904^2 \\ &1232\ 0978096^2 + 32856000^2 && := 1232\ 1021904^2 \\ &123432\ 0978096^2 + 328856000^2 && := 123432\ 1021904^2 \\ &12345432\ 0978096^2 + 3288856000^2 && := 12345432\ 1021904^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0978096^2 + 32888856000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1021904^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0978096^2 + 328888856000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1021904^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0978096^2 + 3288888856000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1021904^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0978096^2 + 32888888856000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1021904^2 \end{aligned}$$

149)

$$\begin{aligned} &0977799^2 + 298000^2 && := 1022201^2 \\ &12\ 0977799^2 + 3278000^2 && := 12\ 1022201^2 \\ &1232\ 0977799^2 + 33078000^2 && := 1232\ 1022201^2 \\ &123432\ 0977799^2 + 331078000^2 && := 123432\ 1022201^2 \\ &12345432\ 0977799^2 + 3311078000^2 && := 12345432\ 1022201^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0977799^2 + 33111078000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1022201^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0977799^2 + 331111078000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1022201^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0977799^2 + 3311111078000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1022201^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0977799^2 + 33111111078000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1022201^2 \end{aligned}$$

150)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0977500^2 + 300000^2 & := & 1022500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0977500^2 + 3300000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1022500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0977500^2 + 33300000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1022500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0977500^2 + 333300000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1022500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0977500^2 + 3333300000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1022500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0977500^2 + 33333300000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1022500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0977500^2 + 333333300000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1022500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0977500^2 + 3333333300000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1022500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0977500^2 + 33333333300000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1022500^2 \end{aligned}$$

151)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0977199^2 + 302000^2 & := & 1022801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0977199^2 + 3322000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1022801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0977199^2 + 33522000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1022801^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0977199^2 + 335522000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1022801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0977199^2 + 3355522000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1022801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0977199^2 + 33555522000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1022801^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0977199^2 + 335555522000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1022801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0977199^2 + 3355555522000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1022801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0977199^2 + 33555555522000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1022801^2 \end{aligned}$$

152)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0976896^2 + 304000^2 & := & 1023104^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0976896^2 + 3344000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1023104^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0976896^2 + 33744000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1023104^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0976896^2 + 337744000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1023104^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0976896^2 + 3377744000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1023104^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0976896^2 + 33777744000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1023104^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0976896^2 + 337777744000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1023104^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0976896^2 + 3377777744000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1023104^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0976896^2 + 33777777744000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1023104^2 \end{aligned}$$

153)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0976591^2 + 306000^2 & := & 1023409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0976591^2 + 3366000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1023409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0976591^2 + 33966000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1023409^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0976591^2 + 339966000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1023409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0976591^2 + 3399966000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1023409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0976591^2 + 33999966000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1023409^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0976591^2 + 339999966000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1023409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0976591^2 + 3399999966000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1023409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0976591^2 + 33999999966000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1023409^2 \end{aligned}$$

154)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0976284^2 + 308000^2 & := & 1023716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0976284^2 + 3388000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1023716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0976284^2 + 34188000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1023716^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0976284^2 + 342188000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1023716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0976284^2 + 3422188000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1023716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0976284^2 + 34222188000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1023716^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0976284^2 + 342222188000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1023716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0976284^2 + 3422222188000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1023716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0976284^2 + 34222222188000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1023716^2 \end{aligned}$$

155)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0975975^2 + 310000^2 & := & 1024025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0975975^2 + 3410000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1024025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0975975^2 + 34410000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1024025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0975975^2 + 344410000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1024025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0975975^2 + 3444410000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1024025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0975975^2 + 34444410000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1024025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0975975^2 + 344444410000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1024025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0975975^2 + 3444444410000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1024025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0975975^2 + 34444444410000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1024025^2 \end{aligned}$$

156)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0975664^2 + 312000^2 & := & 1024336^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0975664^2 + 3432000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1024336^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0975664^2 + 34632000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1024336^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0975664^2 + 346632000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1024336^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0975664^2 + 3466632000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1024336^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0975664^2 + 34666632000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1024336^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0975664^2 + 346666632000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1024336^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0975664^2 + 3466666632000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1024336^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0975664^2 + 34666666632000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1024336^2 \end{aligned}$$

157)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0975351^2 + 314000^2 & := & 1024649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0975351^2 + 3454000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1024649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0975351^2 + 34854000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1024649^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0975351^2 + 348854000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1024649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0975351^2 + 3488854000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1024649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0975351^2 + 34888854000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1024649^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0975351^2 + 348888854000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1024649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0975351^2 + 3488888854000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1024649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0975351^2 + 34888888854000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1024649^2 \end{aligned}$$

158)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0975036^2 + 316000^2 & := & 1024964^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0975036^2 + 3476000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1024964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0975036^2 + 35076000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1024964^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0975036^2 + 351076000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1024964^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0975036^2 + 3511076000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1024964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0975036^2 + 35111076000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1024964^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0975036^2 + 351111076000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1024964^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0975036^2 + 3511111076000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1024964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0975036^2 + 35111111076000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1024964^2 \end{aligned}$$

159)

$$\begin{aligned} &0974719^2 + 318000^2 && := 1025281^2 \\ &12\ 0974719^2 + 3498000^2 && := 12\ 1025281^2 \\ &1232\ 0974719^2 + 35298000^2 && := 1232\ 1025281^2 \\ &123432\ 0974719^2 + 353298000^2 && := 123432\ 1025281^2 \\ &12345432\ 0974719^2 + 3533298000^2 && := 12345432\ 1025281^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0974719^2 + 35333298000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1025281^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0974719^2 + 353333298000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1025281^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0974719^2 + 3533333298000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1025281^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0974719^2 + 35333333298000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1025281^2 \end{aligned}$$

160)

$$\begin{aligned} &0974400^2 + 320000^2 && := 1025600^2 \\ &12\ 0974400^2 + 3520000^2 && := 12\ 1025600^2 \\ &1232\ 0974400^2 + 35520000^2 && := 1232\ 1025600^2 \\ &123432\ 0974400^2 + 355520000^2 && := 123432\ 1025600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0974400^2 + 3555520000^2 && := 12345432\ 1025600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0974400^2 + 35555520000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1025600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0974400^2 + 355555520000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1025600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0974400^2 + 3555555520000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1025600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0974400^2 + 35555555520000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1025600^2 \end{aligned}$$

161)

$$\begin{aligned} &0974079^2 + 322000^2 && := 1025921^2 \\ &12\ 0974079^2 + 3542000^2 && := 12\ 1025921^2 \\ &1232\ 0974079^2 + 35742000^2 && := 1232\ 1025921^2 \\ &123432\ 0974079^2 + 357742000^2 && := 123432\ 1025921^2 \\ &12345432\ 0974079^2 + 3577742000^2 && := 12345432\ 1025921^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0974079^2 + 35777742000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1025921^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0974079^2 + 357777742000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1025921^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0974079^2 + 3577777742000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1025921^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0974079^2 + 35777777742000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1025921^2 \end{aligned}$$

162)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0973756^2 + 324000^2 & := & 1026244^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0973756^2 + 3564000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1026244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0973756^2 + 35964000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1026244^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0973756^2 + 359964000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1026244^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0973756^2 + 3599964000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1026244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0973756^2 + 35999964000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1026244^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0973756^2 + 359999964000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1026244^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0973756^2 + 3599999964000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1026244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0973756^2 + 35999999964000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1026244^2 \end{aligned}$$

163)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0973431^2 + 326000^2 & := & 1026569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0973431^2 + 3586000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1026569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0973431^2 + 36186000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1026569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0973431^2 + 362186000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1026569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0973431^2 + 3622186000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1026569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0973431^2 + 36222186000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1026569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0973431^2 + 362222186000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1026569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0973431^2 + 3622222186000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1026569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0973431^2 + 36222222186000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1026569^2 \end{aligned}$$

164)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0973104^2 + 328000^2 & := & 1026896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0973104^2 + 3608000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1026896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0973104^2 + 36408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1026896^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0973104^2 + 364408000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1026896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0973104^2 + 3644408000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1026896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0973104^2 + 36444408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1026896^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0973104^2 + 364444408000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1026896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0973104^2 + 3644444408000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1026896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0973104^2 + 36444444408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1026896^2 \end{aligned}$$

165)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0972775^2 + 330000^2 & := & 1027225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0972775^2 + 3630000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1027225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0972775^2 + 36630000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1027225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0972775^2 + 366630000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1027225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0972775^2 + 3666630000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1027225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0972775^2 + 36666630000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1027225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0972775^2 + 366666630000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1027225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0972775^2 + 3666666630000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1027225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0972775^2 + 36666666630000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1027225^2 \end{aligned}$$

166)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0972444^2 + 332000^2 & := & 1027556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0972444^2 + 3652000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1027556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0972444^2 + 36852000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1027556^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0972444^2 + 368852000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1027556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0972444^2 + 3688852000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1027556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0972444^2 + 36888852000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1027556^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0972444^2 + 368888852000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1027556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0972444^2 + 3688888852000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1027556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0972444^2 + 36888888852000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1027556^2 \end{aligned}$$

167)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0972111^2 + 334000^2 & := & 1027889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0972111^2 + 3674000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1027889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0972111^2 + 37074000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1027889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0972111^2 + 371074000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1027889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0972111^2 + 3711074000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1027889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0972111^2 + 37111074000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1027889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0972111^2 + 371111074000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1027889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0972111^2 + 3711111074000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1027889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0972111^2 + 37111111074000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1027889^2 \end{aligned}$$

168)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0971776^2 + 336000^2 & := & 1028224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0971776^2 + 3696000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1028224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0971776^2 + 37296000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1028224^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0971776^2 + 373296000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1028224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0971776^2 + 3733296000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1028224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0971776^2 + 37333296000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1028224^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0971776^2 + 373333296000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1028224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0971776^2 + 3733333296000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1028224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0971776^2 + 37333333296000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1028224^2 \end{aligned}$$

169)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0971439^2 + 338000^2 & := & 1028561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0971439^2 + 3718000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1028561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0971439^2 + 37518000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1028561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0971439^2 + 375518000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1028561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0971439^2 + 3755518000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1028561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0971439^2 + 37555518000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1028561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0971439^2 + 375555518000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1028561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0971439^2 + 3755555518000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1028561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0971439^2 + 37555555518000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1028561^2 \end{aligned}$$

170)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0971100^2 + 340000^2 & := & 1028900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0971100^2 + 3740000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1028900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0971100^2 + 37740000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1028900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0971100^2 + 377740000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1028900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0971100^2 + 3777740000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1028900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0971100^2 + 37777740000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1028900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0971100^2 + 377777740000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1028900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0971100^2 + 3777777740000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1028900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0971100^2 + 37777777740000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1028900^2 \end{aligned}$$

171)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0970759^2 + 342000^2 & := & 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0970759^2 + 3762000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0970759^2 + 37962000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0970759^2 + 379962000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0970759^2 + 3799962000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0970759^2 + 37999962000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0970759^2 + 379999962000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0970759^2 + 3799999962000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0970759^2 + 37999999962000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1029241^2 \end{aligned}$$

172)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0970416^2 + 344000^2 & := & 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0970416^2 + 3784000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0970416^2 + 38184000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0970416^2 + 382184000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0970416^2 + 3822184000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0970416^2 + 38222184000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0970416^2 + 382222184000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0970416^2 + 3822222184000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0970416^2 + 38222222184000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1029584^2 \end{aligned}$$

173)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0970071^2 + 346000^2 & := & 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0970071^2 + 3806000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0970071^2 + 38406000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0970071^2 + 384406000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0970071^2 + 3844406000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0970071^2 + 38444406000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0970071^2 + 384444406000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0970071^2 + 3844444406000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0970071^2 + 38444444406000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1029929^2 \end{aligned}$$

174)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0969724^2 + 348000^2 & := & 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0969724^2 + 3828000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0969724^2 + 38628000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0969724^2 + 386628000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0969724^2 + 3866628000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0969724^2 + 38666628000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0969724^2 + 386666628000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0969724^2 + 3866666628000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0969724^2 + 38666666628000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1030276^2 \end{aligned}$$

175)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0969375^2 + 350000^2 & := & 1030625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0969375^2 + 3850000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1030625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0969375^2 + 38850000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1030625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0969375^2 + 388850000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1030625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0969375^2 + 3888850000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1030625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0969375^2 + 38888850000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1030625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0969375^2 + 388888850000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1030625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0969375^2 + 3888888850000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1030625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0969375^2 + 38888888850000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1030625^2 \end{aligned}$$

176)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0969024^2 + 352000^2 & := & 1030976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0969024^2 + 3872000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1030976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0969024^2 + 39072000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1030976^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0969024^2 + 391072000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1030976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0969024^2 + 3911072000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1030976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0969024^2 + 39111072000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1030976^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0969024^2 + 391111072000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1030976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0969024^2 + 3911111072000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1030976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0969024^2 + 39111111072000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1030976^2 \end{aligned}$$

177)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0968671^2 + 354000^2 & := & 1031329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0968671^2 + 3894000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1031329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0968671^2 + 39294000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1031329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0968671^2 + 393294000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1031329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0968671^2 + 3933294000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1031329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0968671^2 + 39333294000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1031329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0968671^2 + 393333294000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1031329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0968671^2 + 3933333294000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1031329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0968671^2 + 39333333294000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1031329^2 \end{aligned}$$

178)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0968316^2 + 356000^2 & := & 1031684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0968316^2 + 3916000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1031684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0968316^2 + 39516000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1031684^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0968316^2 + 395516000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1031684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0968316^2 + 3955516000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1031684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0968316^2 + 39555516000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1031684^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0968316^2 + 395555516000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1031684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0968316^2 + 3955555516000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1031684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0968316^2 + 39555555516000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1031684^2 \end{aligned}$$

179)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0967959^2 + 358000^2 & := & 1032041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0967959^2 + 3938000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1032041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0967959^2 + 39738000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1032041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0967959^2 + 397738000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1032041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0967959^2 + 3977738000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1032041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0967959^2 + 39777738000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1032041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0967959^2 + 397777738000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1032041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0967959^2 + 3977777738000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1032041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0967959^2 + 39777777738000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1032041^2 \end{aligned}$$

180)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0967600^2 + 360000^2 & := & 1032400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0967600^2 + 3960000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1032400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0967600^2 + 39960000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1032400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0967600^2 + 399960000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1032400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0967600^2 + 3999960000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1032400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0967600^2 + 39999960000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1032400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0967600^2 + 399999960000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1032400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0967600^2 + 3999999960000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1032400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0967600^2 + 39999999960000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1032400^2 \end{aligned}$$

181)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0967239^2 + 362000^2 & := & 1032761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0967239^2 + 3982000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1032761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0967239^2 + 40182000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1032761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0967239^2 + 402182000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1032761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0967239^2 + 4022182000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1032761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0967239^2 + 40222182000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1032761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0967239^2 + 402222182000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1032761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0967239^2 + 4022222182000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1032761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0967239^2 + 40222222182000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1032761^2 \end{aligned}$$

182)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0966876^2 + 364000^2 & := & 1033124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0966876^2 + 4004000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1033124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0966876^2 + 40404000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1033124^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0966876^2 + 404404000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1033124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0966876^2 + 4044404000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1033124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0966876^2 + 40444404000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1033124^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0966876^2 + 404444404000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1033124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0966876^2 + 4044444404000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1033124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0966876^2 + 40444444404000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1033124^2 \end{aligned}$$

183)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0966511^2 + 366000^2 & := & 1033489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0966511^2 + 4026000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1033489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0966511^2 + 40626000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1033489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0966511^2 + 406626000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1033489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0966511^2 + 4066626000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1033489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0966511^2 + 40666626000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1033489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0966511^2 + 406666626000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1033489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0966511^2 + 4066666626000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1033489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0966511^2 + 40666666626000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1033489^2 \end{aligned}$$

184)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0966144^2 + 368000^2 & := & 1033856^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0966144^2 + 4048000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1033856^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0966144^2 + 40848000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1033856^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0966144^2 + 408848000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1033856^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0966144^2 + 4088848000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1033856^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0966144^2 + 40888848000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1033856^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0966144^2 + 408888848000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1033856^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0966144^2 + 4088888848000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1033856^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0966144^2 + 40888888848000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1033856^2 \end{aligned}$$

185)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0965775^2 + 370000^2 & := & 1034225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0965775^2 + 4070000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1034225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0965775^2 + 41070000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1034225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0965775^2 + 411070000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1034225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0965775^2 + 4111070000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1034225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0965775^2 + 41111070000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1034225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0965775^2 + 411111070000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1034225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0965775^2 + 4111111070000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1034225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0965775^2 + 41111111070000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1034225^2 \end{aligned}$$

186)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0965404^2 + 372000^2 & := & 1034596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0965404^2 + 4092000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1034596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0965404^2 + 41292000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1034596^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0965404^2 + 413292000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1034596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0965404^2 + 4133292000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1034596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0965404^2 + 41333292000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1034596^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0965404^2 + 413333292000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1034596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0965404^2 + 4133333292000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1034596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0965404^2 + 41333333292000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1034596^2 \end{aligned}$$

187)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0965031^2 + 374000^2 & := & 1034969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0965031^2 + 4114000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1034969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0965031^2 + 41514000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1034969^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0965031^2 + 415514000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1034969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0965031^2 + 4155514000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1034969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0965031^2 + 41555514000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1034969^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0965031^2 + 415555514000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1034969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0965031^2 + 4155555514000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1034969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0965031^2 + 41555555514000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1034969^2 \end{aligned}$$

188)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0964656^2 + 376000^2 & := & 1035344^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0964656^2 + 4136000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1035344^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0964656^2 + 41736000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1035344^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0964656^2 + 417736000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1035344^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0964656^2 + 4177736000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1035344^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0964656^2 + 41777736000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1035344^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0964656^2 + 417777736000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1035344^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0964656^2 + 4177777736000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1035344^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0964656^2 + 41777777736000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1035344^2 \end{aligned}$$

189)

$$\begin{aligned} &0964279^2 + 378000^2 && := 1035721^2 \\ &12\ 0964279^2 + 4158000^2 && := 12\ 1035721^2 \\ &1232\ 0964279^2 + 41958000^2 && := 1232\ 1035721^2 \\ &123432\ 0964279^2 + 419958000^2 && := 123432\ 1035721^2 \\ &12345432\ 0964279^2 + 4199958000^2 && := 12345432\ 1035721^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0964279^2 + 41999958000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1035721^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0964279^2 + 419999958000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1035721^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0964279^2 + 4199999958000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1035721^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0964279^2 + 41999999958000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1035721^2 \end{aligned}$$

190)

$$\begin{aligned} &0963900^2 + 380000^2 && := 1036100^2 \\ &12\ 0963900^2 + 4180000^2 && := 12\ 1036100^2 \\ &1232\ 0963900^2 + 42180000^2 && := 1232\ 1036100^2 \\ &123432\ 0963900^2 + 422180000^2 && := 123432\ 1036100^2 \\ &12345432\ 0963900^2 + 4222180000^2 && := 12345432\ 1036100^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0963900^2 + 42222180000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1036100^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0963900^2 + 422222180000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1036100^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0963900^2 + 4222222180000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1036100^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0963900^2 + 42222222180000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1036100^2 \end{aligned}$$

191)

$$\begin{aligned} &0963519^2 + 382000^2 && := 1036481^2 \\ &12\ 0963519^2 + 4202000^2 && := 12\ 1036481^2 \\ &1232\ 0963519^2 + 42402000^2 && := 1232\ 1036481^2 \\ &123432\ 0963519^2 + 424402000^2 && := 123432\ 1036481^2 \\ &12345432\ 0963519^2 + 4244402000^2 && := 12345432\ 1036481^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0963519^2 + 42444402000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1036481^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0963519^2 + 424444402000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1036481^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0963519^2 + 4244444402000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1036481^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0963519^2 + 42444444402000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1036481^2 \end{aligned}$$

192)

$$\begin{aligned} &0963136^2 + 384000^2 && := 1036864^2 \\ &12\ 0963136^2 + 4224000^2 && := 12\ 1036864^2 \\ &1232\ 0963136^2 + 42624000^2 && := 1232\ 1036864^2 \\ &123432\ 0963136^2 + 426624000^2 && := 123432\ 1036864^2 \\ &12345432\ 0963136^2 + 4266624000^2 && := 12345432\ 1036864^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0963136^2 + 42666624000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1036864^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0963136^2 + 426666624000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1036864^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0963136^2 + 4266666624000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1036864^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0963136^2 + 42666666624000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1036864^2 \end{aligned}$$

193)

$$\begin{aligned} &0962751^2 + 386000^2 && := 1037249^2 \\ &12\ 0962751^2 + 4246000^2 && := 12\ 1037249^2 \\ &1232\ 0962751^2 + 42846000^2 && := 1232\ 1037249^2 \\ &123432\ 0962751^2 + 428846000^2 && := 123432\ 1037249^2 \\ &12345432\ 0962751^2 + 4288846000^2 && := 12345432\ 1037249^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0962751^2 + 42888846000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1037249^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0962751^2 + 428888846000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1037249^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0962751^2 + 4288888846000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1037249^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0962751^2 + 42888888846000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1037249^2 \end{aligned}$$

194)

$$\begin{aligned} &0962364^2 + 388000^2 && := 1037636^2 \\ &12\ 0962364^2 + 4268000^2 && := 12\ 1037636^2 \\ &1232\ 0962364^2 + 43068000^2 && := 1232\ 1037636^2 \\ &123432\ 0962364^2 + 431068000^2 && := 123432\ 1037636^2 \\ &12345432\ 0962364^2 + 4311068000^2 && := 12345432\ 1037636^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0962364^2 + 43111068000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1037636^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0962364^2 + 431111068000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1037636^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0962364^2 + 4311111068000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1037636^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0962364^2 + 43111111068000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1037636^2 \end{aligned}$$

195)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0961975^2 + 390000^2 & := & 1038025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0961975^2 + 4290000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1038025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0961975^2 + 43290000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1038025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0961975^2 + 433290000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1038025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0961975^2 + 4333290000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1038025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0961975^2 + 43333290000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1038025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0961975^2 + 433333290000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1038025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0961975^2 + 4333333290000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1038025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0961975^2 + 43333333290000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1038025^2 \end{aligned}$$

196)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0961584^2 + 392000^2 & := & 1038416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0961584^2 + 4312000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1038416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0961584^2 + 43512000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1038416^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0961584^2 + 435512000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1038416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0961584^2 + 4355512000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1038416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0961584^2 + 43555512000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1038416^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0961584^2 + 435555512000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1038416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0961584^2 + 4355555512000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1038416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0961584^2 + 43555555512000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1038416^2 \end{aligned}$$

197)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0961191^2 + 394000^2 & := & 1038809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0961191^2 + 4334000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1038809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0961191^2 + 43734000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1038809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0961191^2 + 437734000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1038809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0961191^2 + 4377734000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1038809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0961191^2 + 43777734000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1038809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0961191^2 + 437777734000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1038809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0961191^2 + 4377777734000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1038809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0961191^2 + 43777777734000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1038809^2 \end{aligned}$$

198)

$$\begin{aligned} &0960796^2 + 396000^2 && := 1039204^2 \\ &12\ 0960796^2 + 4356000^2 && := 12\ 1039204^2 \\ &1232\ 0960796^2 + 43956000^2 && := 1232\ 1039204^2 \\ &123432\ 0960796^2 + 439956000^2 && := 123432\ 1039204^2 \\ &12345432\ 0960796^2 + 4399956000^2 && := 12345432\ 1039204^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0960796^2 + 43999956000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1039204^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0960796^2 + 439999956000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1039204^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0960796^2 + 4399999956000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1039204^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0960796^2 + 43999999956000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1039204^2 \end{aligned}$$

199)

$$\begin{aligned} &0960399^2 + 398000^2 && := 1039601^2 \\ &12\ 0960399^2 + 4378000^2 && := 12\ 1039601^2 \\ &1232\ 0960399^2 + 44178000^2 && := 1232\ 1039601^2 \\ &123432\ 0960399^2 + 442178000^2 && := 123432\ 1039601^2 \\ &12345432\ 0960399^2 + 4422178000^2 && := 12345432\ 1039601^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0960399^2 + 44222178000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1039601^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0960399^2 + 442222178000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1039601^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0960399^2 + 4422222178000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1039601^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0960399^2 + 44222222178000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1039601^2 \end{aligned}$$

200)

$$\begin{aligned} &0960000^2 + 400000^2 && := 1040000^2 \\ &12\ 0960000^2 + 4400000^2 && := 12\ 1040000^2 \\ &1232\ 0960000^2 + 44400000^2 && := 1232\ 1040000^2 \\ &123432\ 0960000^2 + 444400000^2 && := 123432\ 1040000^2 \\ &12345432\ 0960000^2 + 4444400000^2 && := 12345432\ 1040000^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0960000^2 + 44444400000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1040000^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0960000^2 + 444444400000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1040000^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0960000^2 + 4444444400000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1040000^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0960000^2 + 44444444400000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1040000^2 \end{aligned}$$

201)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0959599^2 + 402000^2 & := & 1040401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0959599^2 + 4422000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1040401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0959599^2 + 44622000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1040401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0959599^2 + 446622000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1040401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0959599^2 + 4466622000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1040401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0959599^2 + 44666622000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1040401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0959599^2 + 446666622000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1040401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0959599^2 + 4466666622000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1040401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0959599^2 + 44666666622000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1040401^2 \end{aligned}$$

202)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0959196^2 + 404000^2 & := & 1040804^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0959196^2 + 4444000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1040804^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0959196^2 + 44844000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1040804^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0959196^2 + 448844000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1040804^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0959196^2 + 4488844000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1040804^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0959196^2 + 44888844000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1040804^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0959196^2 + 448888844000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1040804^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0959196^2 + 4488888844000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1040804^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0959196^2 + 44888888844000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1040804^2 \end{aligned}$$

203)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0958791^2 + 406000^2 & := & 1041209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0958791^2 + 4466000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1041209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0958791^2 + 45066000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1041209^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0958791^2 + 451066000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1041209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0958791^2 + 4511066000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1041209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0958791^2 + 45111066000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1041209^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0958791^2 + 451111066000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1041209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0958791^2 + 4511111066000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1041209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0958791^2 + 45111111066000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1041209^2 \end{aligned}$$

204)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0958384^2 + 408000^2 & := & 1041616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0958384^2 + 4488000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1041616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0958384^2 + 45288000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1041616^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0958384^2 + 453288000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1041616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0958384^2 + 4533288000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1041616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0958384^2 + 45333288000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1041616^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0958384^2 + 453333288000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1041616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0958384^2 + 4533333288000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1041616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0958384^2 + 45333333288000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1041616^2 \end{aligned}$$

205)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0957975^2 + 410000^2 & := & 1042025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0957975^2 + 4510000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1042025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0957975^2 + 45510000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1042025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0957975^2 + 455510000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1042025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0957975^2 + 4555510000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1042025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0957975^2 + 45555510000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1042025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0957975^2 + 455555510000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1042025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0957975^2 + 4555555510000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1042025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0957975^2 + 45555555510000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1042025^2 \end{aligned}$$

206)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0957564^2 + 412000^2 & := & 1042436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0957564^2 + 4532000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1042436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0957564^2 + 45732000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1042436^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0957564^2 + 457732000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1042436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0957564^2 + 4577732000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1042436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0957564^2 + 45777732000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1042436^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0957564^2 + 457777732000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1042436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0957564^2 + 4577777732000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1042436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0957564^2 + 45777777732000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1042436^2 \end{aligned}$$

207)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0957151^2 + 414000^2 & := & 1042849^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0957151^2 + 4554000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1042849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0957151^2 + 45954000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1042849^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0957151^2 + 459954000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1042849^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0957151^2 + 4599954000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1042849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0957151^2 + 45999954000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1042849^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0957151^2 + 459999954000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1042849^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0957151^2 + 4599999954000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1042849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0957151^2 + 45999999954000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1042849^2 \end{aligned}$$

208)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0956736^2 + 416000^2 & := & 1043264^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0956736^2 + 4576000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1043264^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0956736^2 + 46176000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1043264^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0956736^2 + 462176000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1043264^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0956736^2 + 4622176000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1043264^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0956736^2 + 46222176000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1043264^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0956736^2 + 462222176000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1043264^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0956736^2 + 4622222176000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1043264^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0956736^2 + 46222222176000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1043264^2 \end{aligned}$$

209)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0956319^2 + 418000^2 & := & 1043681^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0956319^2 + 4598000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1043681^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0956319^2 + 46398000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1043681^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0956319^2 + 464398000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1043681^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0956319^2 + 4644398000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1043681^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0956319^2 + 46444398000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1043681^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0956319^2 + 464444398000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1043681^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0956319^2 + 4644444398000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1043681^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0956319^2 + 46444444398000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1043681^2 \end{aligned}$$

210)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0955900^2 + 420000^2 & := & 1044100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0955900^2 + 4620000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1044100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0955900^2 + 46620000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1044100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0955900^2 + 466620000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1044100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0955900^2 + 4666620000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1044100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0955900^2 + 46666620000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1044100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0955900^2 + 466666620000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1044100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0955900^2 + 4666666620000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1044100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0955900^2 + 46666666620000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1044100^2 \end{aligned}$$

211)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0955479^2 + 422000^2 & := & 1044521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0955479^2 + 4642000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1044521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0955479^2 + 46842000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1044521^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0955479^2 + 468842000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1044521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0955479^2 + 4688842000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1044521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0955479^2 + 46888842000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1044521^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0955479^2 + 468888842000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1044521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0955479^2 + 4688888842000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1044521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0955479^2 + 46888888842000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1044521^2 \end{aligned}$$

212)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0955056^2 + 424000^2 & := & 1044944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0955056^2 + 4664000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1044944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0955056^2 + 47064000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1044944^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0955056^2 + 471064000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1044944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0955056^2 + 4711064000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1044944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0955056^2 + 47111064000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1044944^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0955056^2 + 471111064000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1044944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0955056^2 + 4711111064000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1044944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0955056^2 + 47111111064000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1044944^2 \end{aligned}$$

213)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0954631^2 + 426000^2 & := & 1045369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0954631^2 + 4686000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1045369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0954631^2 + 47286000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1045369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0954631^2 + 473286000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1045369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0954631^2 + 4733286000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1045369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0954631^2 + 47333286000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1045369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0954631^2 + 473333286000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1045369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0954631^2 + 4733333286000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1045369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0954631^2 + 47333333286000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1045369^2 \end{aligned}$$

214)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0954204^2 + 428000^2 & := & 1045796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0954204^2 + 4708000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1045796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0954204^2 + 47508000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1045796^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0954204^2 + 475508000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1045796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0954204^2 + 4755508000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1045796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0954204^2 + 47555508000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1045796^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0954204^2 + 475555508000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1045796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0954204^2 + 4755555508000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1045796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0954204^2 + 47555555508000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1045796^2 \end{aligned}$$

215)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0953775^2 + 430000^2 & := & 1046225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0953775^2 + 4730000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1046225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0953775^2 + 47730000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1046225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0953775^2 + 477730000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1046225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0953775^2 + 4777730000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1046225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0953775^2 + 47777730000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1046225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0953775^2 + 477777730000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1046225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0953775^2 + 4777777730000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1046225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0953775^2 + 47777777730000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1046225^2 \end{aligned}$$

216)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0953344^2 + 432000^2 & := & 1046656^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0953344^2 + 4752000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1046656^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0953344^2 + 47952000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1046656^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0953344^2 + 479952000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1046656^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0953344^2 + 4799952000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1046656^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0953344^2 + 47999952000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1046656^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0953344^2 + 479999952000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1046656^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0953344^2 + 4799999952000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1046656^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0953344^2 + 47999999952000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1046656^2 \end{aligned}$$

217)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0952911^2 + 434000^2 & := & 1047089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0952911^2 + 4774000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1047089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0952911^2 + 48174000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1047089^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0952911^2 + 482174000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1047089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0952911^2 + 4822174000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1047089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0952911^2 + 48222174000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1047089^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0952911^2 + 482222174000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1047089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0952911^2 + 4822222174000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1047089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0952911^2 + 48222222174000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1047089^2 \end{aligned}$$

218)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0952476^2 + 436000^2 & := & 1047524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0952476^2 + 4796000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1047524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0952476^2 + 48396000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1047524^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0952476^2 + 484396000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1047524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0952476^2 + 4844396000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1047524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0952476^2 + 48444396000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1047524^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0952476^2 + 484444396000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1047524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0952476^2 + 4844444396000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1047524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0952476^2 + 48444444396000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1047524^2 \end{aligned}$$

219)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0952039^2 + 438000^2 & := & 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0952039^2 + 4818000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0952039^2 + 48618000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0952039^2 + 486618000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0952039^2 + 4866618000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0952039^2 + 48666618000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0952039^2 + 486666618000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0952039^2 + 4866666618000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0952039^2 + 48666666618000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1047961^2 \end{aligned}$$

220)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0951600^2 + 440000^2 & := & 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0951600^2 + 4840000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0951600^2 + 48840000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0951600^2 + 488840000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0951600^2 + 4888840000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0951600^2 + 48888840000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0951600^2 + 488888840000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0951600^2 + 4888888840000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0951600^2 + 48888888840000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1048400^2 \end{aligned}$$

221)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0951159^2 + 442000^2 & := & 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0951159^2 + 4862000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0951159^2 + 49062000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0951159^2 + 491062000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0951159^2 + 4911062000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0951159^2 + 49111062000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0951159^2 + 491111062000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0951159^2 + 4911111062000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0951159^2 + 49111111062000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1048841^2 \end{aligned}$$

222)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0950716^2 + 444000^2 & := & 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0950716^2 + 4884000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0950716^2 + 49284000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0950716^2 + 493284000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0950716^2 + 4933284000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0950716^2 + 49333284000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0950716^2 + 493333284000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0950716^2 + 4933333284000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0950716^2 + 49333333284000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1049284^2 \end{aligned}$$

223)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0950271^2 + 446000^2 & := & 1049729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0950271^2 + 4906000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1049729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0950271^2 + 49506000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1049729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0950271^2 + 495506000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1049729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0950271^2 + 4955506000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1049729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0950271^2 + 49555506000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1049729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0950271^2 + 495555506000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1049729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0950271^2 + 4955555506000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1049729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0950271^2 + 49555555506000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1049729^2 \end{aligned}$$

224)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0949824^2 + 448000^2 & := & 1050176^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0949824^2 + 4928000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1050176^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0949824^2 + 49728000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1050176^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0949824^2 + 497728000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1050176^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0949824^2 + 4977728000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1050176^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0949824^2 + 49777728000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1050176^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0949824^2 + 497777728000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1050176^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0949824^2 + 4977777728000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1050176^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0949824^2 + 49777777728000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1050176^2 \end{aligned}$$

225)

$$\begin{aligned} &0949375^2 + 450000^2 && := 1050625^2 \\ &12\ 0949375^2 + 4950000^2 && := 12\ 1050625^2 \\ &1232\ 0949375^2 + 49950000^2 && := 1232\ 1050625^2 \\ &123432\ 0949375^2 + 499950000^2 && := 123432\ 1050625^2 \\ &12345432\ 0949375^2 + 4999950000^2 && := 12345432\ 1050625^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0949375^2 + 49999950000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1050625^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0949375^2 + 499999950000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1050625^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0949375^2 + 4999999950000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1050625^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0949375^2 + 49999999950000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1050625^2 \end{aligned}$$

226)

$$\begin{aligned} &0948924^2 + 452000^2 && := 1051076^2 \\ &12\ 0948924^2 + 4972000^2 && := 12\ 1051076^2 \\ &1232\ 0948924^2 + 50172000^2 && := 1232\ 1051076^2 \\ &123432\ 0948924^2 + 502172000^2 && := 123432\ 1051076^2 \\ &12345432\ 0948924^2 + 5022172000^2 && := 12345432\ 1051076^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0948924^2 + 50222172000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1051076^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0948924^2 + 502222172000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1051076^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0948924^2 + 5022222172000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1051076^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0948924^2 + 50222222172000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1051076^2 \end{aligned}$$

227)

$$\begin{aligned} &0948471^2 + 454000^2 && := 1051529^2 \\ &12\ 0948471^2 + 4994000^2 && := 12\ 1051529^2 \\ &1232\ 0948471^2 + 50394000^2 && := 1232\ 1051529^2 \\ &123432\ 0948471^2 + 504394000^2 && := 123432\ 1051529^2 \\ &12345432\ 0948471^2 + 5044394000^2 && := 12345432\ 1051529^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0948471^2 + 50444394000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1051529^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0948471^2 + 504444394000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1051529^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0948471^2 + 5044444394000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1051529^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0948471^2 + 50444444394000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1051529^2 \end{aligned}$$

228)

$$\begin{aligned} &0948016^2 + 456000^2 && := 1051984^2 \\ &12\ 0948016^2 + 5016000^2 && := 12\ 1051984^2 \\ &1232\ 0948016^2 + 50616000^2 && := 1232\ 1051984^2 \\ &123432\ 0948016^2 + 506616000^2 && := 123432\ 1051984^2 \\ &12345432\ 0948016^2 + 5066616000^2 && := 12345432\ 1051984^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0948016^2 + 50666616000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1051984^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0948016^2 + 506666616000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1051984^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0948016^2 + 5066666616000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1051984^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0948016^2 + 50666666616000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1051984^2 \end{aligned}$$

229)

$$\begin{aligned} &0947559^2 + 458000^2 && := 1052441^2 \\ &12\ 0947559^2 + 5038000^2 && := 12\ 1052441^2 \\ &1232\ 0947559^2 + 50838000^2 && := 1232\ 1052441^2 \\ &123432\ 0947559^2 + 508838000^2 && := 123432\ 1052441^2 \\ &12345432\ 0947559^2 + 5088838000^2 && := 12345432\ 1052441^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0947559^2 + 50888838000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1052441^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0947559^2 + 508888838000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1052441^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0947559^2 + 5088888838000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1052441^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0947559^2 + 50888888838000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1052441^2 \end{aligned}$$

230)

$$\begin{aligned} &0947100^2 + 460000^2 && := 1052900^2 \\ &12\ 0947100^2 + 5060000^2 && := 12\ 1052900^2 \\ &1232\ 0947100^2 + 51060000^2 && := 1232\ 1052900^2 \\ &123432\ 0947100^2 + 511060000^2 && := 123432\ 1052900^2 \\ &12345432\ 0947100^2 + 5111060000^2 && := 12345432\ 1052900^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0947100^2 + 51111060000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1052900^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0947100^2 + 511111060000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1052900^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0947100^2 + 5111111060000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1052900^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0947100^2 + 51111111060000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1052900^2 \end{aligned}$$

231)

$$\begin{aligned} &0946639^2 + 462000^2 && := 1053361^2 \\ &12\ 0946639^2 + 5082000^2 && := 12\ 1053361^2 \\ &1232\ 0946639^2 + 51282000^2 && := 1232\ 1053361^2 \\ &123432\ 0946639^2 + 513282000^2 && := 123432\ 1053361^2 \\ &12345432\ 0946639^2 + 5133282000^2 && := 12345432\ 1053361^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0946639^2 + 51333282000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1053361^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0946639^2 + 513333282000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1053361^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0946639^2 + 5133333282000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1053361^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0946639^2 + 51333333282000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1053361^2 \end{aligned}$$

232)

$$\begin{aligned} &0946176^2 + 464000^2 && := 1053824^2 \\ &12\ 0946176^2 + 5104000^2 && := 12\ 1053824^2 \\ &1232\ 0946176^2 + 51504000^2 && := 1232\ 1053824^2 \\ &123432\ 0946176^2 + 515504000^2 && := 123432\ 1053824^2 \\ &12345432\ 0946176^2 + 5155504000^2 && := 12345432\ 1053824^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0946176^2 + 51555504000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1053824^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0946176^2 + 515555504000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1053824^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0946176^2 + 5155555504000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1053824^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0946176^2 + 51555555504000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1053824^2 \end{aligned}$$

233)

$$\begin{aligned} &0945711^2 + 466000^2 && := 1054289^2 \\ &12\ 0945711^2 + 5126000^2 && := 12\ 1054289^2 \\ &1232\ 0945711^2 + 51726000^2 && := 1232\ 1054289^2 \\ &123432\ 0945711^2 + 517726000^2 && := 123432\ 1054289^2 \\ &12345432\ 0945711^2 + 5177726000^2 && := 12345432\ 1054289^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0945711^2 + 51777726000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1054289^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0945711^2 + 517777726000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1054289^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0945711^2 + 5177777726000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1054289^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0945711^2 + 51777777726000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1054289^2 \end{aligned}$$

234)

$$\begin{aligned} &0945244^2 + 468000^2 && := 1054756^2 \\ &12\ 0945244^2 + 5148000^2 && := 12\ 1054756^2 \\ &1232\ 0945244^2 + 51948000^2 && := 1232\ 1054756^2 \\ &123432\ 0945244^2 + 519948000^2 && := 123432\ 1054756^2 \\ &12345432\ 0945244^2 + 5199948000^2 && := 12345432\ 1054756^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0945244^2 + 51999948000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1054756^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0945244^2 + 519999948000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1054756^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0945244^2 + 5199999948000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1054756^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0945244^2 + 51999999948000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1054756^2 \end{aligned}$$

235)

$$\begin{aligned} &0944775^2 + 470000^2 && := 1055225^2 \\ &12\ 0944775^2 + 5170000^2 && := 12\ 1055225^2 \\ &1232\ 0944775^2 + 52170000^2 && := 1232\ 1055225^2 \\ &123432\ 0944775^2 + 522170000^2 && := 123432\ 1055225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0944775^2 + 5222170000^2 && := 12345432\ 1055225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0944775^2 + 52222170000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1055225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0944775^2 + 522222170000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1055225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0944775^2 + 5222222170000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1055225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0944775^2 + 52222222170000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1055225^2 \end{aligned}$$

236)

$$\begin{aligned} &0944304^2 + 472000^2 && := 1055696^2 \\ &12\ 0944304^2 + 5192000^2 && := 12\ 1055696^2 \\ &1232\ 0944304^2 + 52392000^2 && := 1232\ 1055696^2 \\ &123432\ 0944304^2 + 524392000^2 && := 123432\ 1055696^2 \\ &12345432\ 0944304^2 + 5244392000^2 && := 12345432\ 1055696^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0944304^2 + 52444392000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1055696^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0944304^2 + 524444392000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1055696^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0944304^2 + 5244444392000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1055696^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0944304^2 + 52444444392000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1055696^2 \end{aligned}$$

237)

$$\begin{aligned} &0943831^2 + 474000^2 && := 1056169^2 \\ &12\ 0943831^2 + 5214000^2 && := 12\ 1056169^2 \\ &1232\ 0943831^2 + 52614000^2 && := 1232\ 1056169^2 \\ &123432\ 0943831^2 + 526614000^2 && := 123432\ 1056169^2 \\ &12345432\ 0943831^2 + 5266614000^2 && := 12345432\ 1056169^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0943831^2 + 52666614000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1056169^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0943831^2 + 526666614000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1056169^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0943831^2 + 5266666614000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1056169^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0943831^2 + 52666666614000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1056169^2 \end{aligned}$$

238)

$$\begin{aligned} &0943356^2 + 476000^2 && := 1056644^2 \\ &12\ 0943356^2 + 5236000^2 && := 12\ 1056644^2 \\ &1232\ 0943356^2 + 52836000^2 && := 1232\ 1056644^2 \\ &123432\ 0943356^2 + 528836000^2 && := 123432\ 1056644^2 \\ &12345432\ 0943356^2 + 5288836000^2 && := 12345432\ 1056644^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0943356^2 + 52888836000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1056644^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0943356^2 + 528888836000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1056644^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0943356^2 + 5288888836000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1056644^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0943356^2 + 52888888836000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1056644^2 \end{aligned}$$

239)

$$\begin{aligned} &0942879^2 + 478000^2 && := 1057121^2 \\ &12\ 0942879^2 + 5258000^2 && := 12\ 1057121^2 \\ &1232\ 0942879^2 + 53058000^2 && := 1232\ 1057121^2 \\ &123432\ 0942879^2 + 531058000^2 && := 123432\ 1057121^2 \\ &12345432\ 0942879^2 + 5311058000^2 && := 12345432\ 1057121^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0942879^2 + 53111058000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1057121^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0942879^2 + 531111058000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1057121^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0942879^2 + 5311111058000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1057121^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0942879^2 + 53111111058000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1057121^2 \end{aligned}$$

240)

$$\begin{aligned} &0942400^2 + 480000^2 && := 1057600^2 \\ &12\ 0942400^2 + 5280000^2 && := 12\ 1057600^2 \\ &1232\ 0942400^2 + 53280000^2 && := 1232\ 1057600^2 \\ &123432\ 0942400^2 + 533280000^2 && := 123432\ 1057600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0942400^2 + 5333280000^2 && := 12345432\ 1057600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0942400^2 + 53333280000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1057600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0942400^2 + 533333280000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1057600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0942400^2 + 5333333280000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1057600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0942400^2 + 53333333280000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1057600^2 \end{aligned}$$

241)

$$\begin{aligned} &0941919^2 + 482000^2 && := 1058081^2 \\ &12\ 0941919^2 + 5302000^2 && := 12\ 1058081^2 \\ &1232\ 0941919^2 + 53502000^2 && := 1232\ 1058081^2 \\ &123432\ 0941919^2 + 535502000^2 && := 123432\ 1058081^2 \\ &12345432\ 0941919^2 + 5355502000^2 && := 12345432\ 1058081^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0941919^2 + 53555502000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1058081^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0941919^2 + 535555502000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1058081^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0941919^2 + 5355555502000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1058081^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0941919^2 + 53555555502000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1058081^2 \end{aligned}$$

242)

$$\begin{aligned} &0941436^2 + 484000^2 && := 1058564^2 \\ &12\ 0941436^2 + 5324000^2 && := 12\ 1058564^2 \\ &1232\ 0941436^2 + 53724000^2 && := 1232\ 1058564^2 \\ &123432\ 0941436^2 + 537724000^2 && := 123432\ 1058564^2 \\ &12345432\ 0941436^2 + 5377724000^2 && := 12345432\ 1058564^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0941436^2 + 53777724000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1058564^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0941436^2 + 537777724000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1058564^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0941436^2 + 5377777724000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1058564^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0941436^2 + 53777777724000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1058564^2 \end{aligned}$$

243)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0940951^2 + 486000^2 & := & 1059049^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0940951^2 + 5346000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1059049^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0940951^2 + 53946000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1059049^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0940951^2 + 539946000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1059049^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0940951^2 + 5399946000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1059049^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0940951^2 + 53999946000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1059049^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0940951^2 + 539999946000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1059049^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0940951^2 + 5399999946000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1059049^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0940951^2 + 53999999946000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1059049^2 \end{aligned}$$

244)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0940464^2 + 488000^2 & := & 1059536^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0940464^2 + 5368000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1059536^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0940464^2 + 54168000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1059536^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0940464^2 + 542168000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1059536^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0940464^2 + 5422168000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1059536^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0940464^2 + 54222168000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1059536^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0940464^2 + 542222168000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1059536^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0940464^2 + 5422222168000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1059536^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0940464^2 + 54222222168000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1059536^2 \end{aligned}$$

245)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0939975^2 + 490000^2 & := & 1060025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0939975^2 + 5390000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1060025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0939975^2 + 54390000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1060025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0939975^2 + 544390000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1060025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0939975^2 + 5444390000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1060025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0939975^2 + 54444390000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1060025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0939975^2 + 544444390000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1060025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0939975^2 + 5444444390000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1060025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0939975^2 + 54444444390000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1060025^2 \end{aligned}$$

246)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0939484^2 + 492000^2 & := & 1060516^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0939484^2 + 5412000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1060516^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0939484^2 + 54612000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1060516^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0939484^2 + 546612000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1060516^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0939484^2 + 5466612000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1060516^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0939484^2 + 54666612000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1060516^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0939484^2 + 546666612000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1060516^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0939484^2 + 5466666612000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1060516^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0939484^2 + 54666666612000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1060516^2 \end{aligned}$$

247)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0938991^2 + 494000^2 & := & 1061009^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0938991^2 + 5434000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1061009^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0938991^2 + 54834000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1061009^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0938991^2 + 548834000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1061009^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0938991^2 + 5488834000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1061009^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0938991^2 + 54888834000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1061009^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0938991^2 + 548888834000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1061009^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0938991^2 + 5488888834000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1061009^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0938991^2 + 54888888834000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1061009^2 \end{aligned}$$

248)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0938496^2 + 496000^2 & := & 1061504^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0938496^2 + 5456000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1061504^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0938496^2 + 55056000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1061504^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0938496^2 + 551056000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1061504^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0938496^2 + 5511056000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1061504^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0938496^2 + 55111056000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1061504^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0938496^2 + 551111056000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1061504^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0938496^2 + 5511111056000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1061504^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0938496^2 + 55111111056000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1061504^2 \end{aligned}$$

249)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0937999^2 + 498000^2 & := & 1062001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0937999^2 + 5478000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1062001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0937999^2 + 55278000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1062001^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0937999^2 + 553278000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1062001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0937999^2 + 5533278000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1062001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0937999^2 + 55333278000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1062001^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0937999^2 + 553333278000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1062001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0937999^2 + 5533333278000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1062001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0937999^2 + 55333333278000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1062001^2 \end{aligned}$$

250)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0937500^2 + 500000^2 & := & 1062500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0937500^2 + 5500000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1062500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0937500^2 + 55500000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1062500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0937500^2 + 555500000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1062500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0937500^2 + 5555500000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1062500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0937500^2 + 55555500000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1062500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0937500^2 + 555555500000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1062500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0937500^2 + 5555555500000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1062500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0937500^2 + 55555555500000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1062500^2 \end{aligned}$$

251)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0936999^2 + 502000^2 & := & 1063001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0936999^2 + 5522000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1063001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0936999^2 + 55722000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1063001^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0936999^2 + 557722000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1063001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0936999^2 + 5577722000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1063001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0936999^2 + 55777722000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1063001^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0936999^2 + 557777722000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1063001^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0936999^2 + 5577777722000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1063001^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0936999^2 + 55777777722000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1063001^2 \end{aligned}$$

252)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0936496^2 + 504000^2 & := & 1063504^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0936496^2 + 5544000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1063504^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0936496^2 + 55944000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1063504^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0936496^2 + 559944000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1063504^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0936496^2 + 5599944000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1063504^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0936496^2 + 55999944000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1063504^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0936496^2 + 559999944000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1063504^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0936496^2 + 5599999944000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1063504^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0936496^2 + 55999999944000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1063504^2 \end{aligned}$$

253)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0935991^2 + 506000^2 & := & 1064009^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0935991^2 + 5566000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1064009^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0935991^2 + 56166000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1064009^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0935991^2 + 562166000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1064009^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0935991^2 + 5622166000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1064009^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0935991^2 + 56222166000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1064009^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0935991^2 + 562222166000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1064009^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0935991^2 + 5622222166000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1064009^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0935991^2 + 56222222166000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1064009^2 \end{aligned}$$

254)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0935484^2 + 508000^2 & := & 1064516^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0935484^2 + 5588000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1064516^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0935484^2 + 56388000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1064516^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0935484^2 + 564388000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1064516^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0935484^2 + 5644388000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1064516^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0935484^2 + 56444388000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1064516^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0935484^2 + 564444388000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1064516^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0935484^2 + 5644444388000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1064516^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0935484^2 + 56444444388000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1064516^2 \end{aligned}$$

255)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0934975^2 + 510000^2 & := & 1065025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0934975^2 + 5610000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1065025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0934975^2 + 56610000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1065025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0934975^2 + 566610000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1065025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0934975^2 + 5666610000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1065025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0934975^2 + 56666610000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1065025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0934975^2 + 566666610000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1065025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0934975^2 + 5666666610000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1065025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0934975^2 + 56666666610000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1065025^2 \end{aligned}$$

256)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0934464^2 + 512000^2 & := & 1065536^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0934464^2 + 5632000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1065536^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0934464^2 + 56832000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1065536^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0934464^2 + 568832000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1065536^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0934464^2 + 5688832000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1065536^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0934464^2 + 56888832000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1065536^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0934464^2 + 568888832000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1065536^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0934464^2 + 5688888832000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1065536^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0934464^2 + 56888888832000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1065536^2 \end{aligned}$$

257)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0933951^2 + 514000^2 & := & 1066049^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0933951^2 + 5654000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1066049^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0933951^2 + 57054000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1066049^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0933951^2 + 571054000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1066049^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0933951^2 + 5711054000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1066049^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0933951^2 + 57111054000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1066049^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0933951^2 + 571111054000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1066049^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0933951^2 + 5711111054000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1066049^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0933951^2 + 57111111054000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1066049^2 \end{aligned}$$

258)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0933436^2 + 516000^2 & := & 1066564^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0933436^2 + 5676000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1066564^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0933436^2 + 57276000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1066564^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0933436^2 + 573276000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1066564^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0933436^2 + 5733276000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1066564^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0933436^2 + 57333276000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1066564^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0933436^2 + 573333276000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1066564^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0933436^2 + 5733333276000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1066564^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0933436^2 + 57333333276000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1066564^2 \end{aligned}$$

259)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0932919^2 + 518000^2 & := & 1067081^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0932919^2 + 5698000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1067081^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0932919^2 + 57498000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1067081^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0932919^2 + 575498000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1067081^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0932919^2 + 5755498000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1067081^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0932919^2 + 57555498000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1067081^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0932919^2 + 575555498000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1067081^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0932919^2 + 5755555498000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1067081^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0932919^2 + 57555555498000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1067081^2 \end{aligned}$$

260)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0932400^2 + 520000^2 & := & 1067600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0932400^2 + 5720000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1067600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0932400^2 + 57720000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1067600^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0932400^2 + 577720000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1067600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0932400^2 + 5777720000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1067600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0932400^2 + 57777720000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1067600^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0932400^2 + 577777720000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1067600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0932400^2 + 5777777720000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1067600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0932400^2 + 57777777720000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1067600^2 \end{aligned}$$

261)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0931879^2 + 522000^2 & := & 1068121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0931879^2 + 5742000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1068121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0931879^2 + 57942000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1068121^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0931879^2 + 579942000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1068121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0931879^2 + 5799942000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1068121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0931879^2 + 57999942000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1068121^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0931879^2 + 579999942000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1068121^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0931879^2 + 5799999942000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1068121^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0931879^2 + 57999999942000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1068121^2 \end{aligned}$$

262)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0931356^2 + 524000^2 & := & 1068644^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0931356^2 + 5764000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1068644^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0931356^2 + 58164000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1068644^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0931356^2 + 582164000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1068644^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0931356^2 + 5822164000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1068644^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0931356^2 + 58222164000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1068644^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0931356^2 + 582222164000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1068644^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0931356^2 + 5822222164000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1068644^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0931356^2 + 58222222164000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1068644^2 \end{aligned}$$

263)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0930831^2 + 526000^2 & := & 1069169^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0930831^2 + 5786000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1069169^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0930831^2 + 58386000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1069169^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0930831^2 + 584386000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1069169^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0930831^2 + 5844386000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1069169^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0930831^2 + 58444386000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1069169^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0930831^2 + 584444386000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1069169^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0930831^2 + 5844444386000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1069169^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0930831^2 + 58444444386000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1069169^2 \end{aligned}$$

264)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0930304^2 + 528000^2 & := & 1069696^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0930304^2 + 5808000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1069696^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0930304^2 + 58608000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1069696^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0930304^2 + 586608000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1069696^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0930304^2 + 5866608000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1069696^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0930304^2 + 58666608000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1069696^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0930304^2 + 586666608000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1069696^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0930304^2 + 5866666608000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1069696^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0930304^2 + 58666666608000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1069696^2 \end{aligned}$$

265)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0929775^2 + 530000^2 & := & 1070225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0929775^2 + 5830000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1070225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0929775^2 + 58830000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1070225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0929775^2 + 588830000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1070225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0929775^2 + 5888830000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1070225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0929775^2 + 58888830000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1070225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0929775^2 + 588888830000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1070225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0929775^2 + 5888888830000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1070225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0929775^2 + 58888888830000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1070225^2 \end{aligned}$$

266)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0929244^2 + 532000^2 & := & 1070756^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0929244^2 + 5852000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1070756^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0929244^2 + 59052000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1070756^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0929244^2 + 591052000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1070756^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0929244^2 + 5911052000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1070756^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0929244^2 + 59111052000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1070756^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0929244^2 + 591111052000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1070756^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0929244^2 + 5911111052000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1070756^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0929244^2 + 59111111052000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1070756^2 \end{aligned}$$

267)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0928711^2 + 534000^2 & := & 1071289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0928711^2 + 5874000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1071289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0928711^2 + 59274000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1071289^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0928711^2 + 593274000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1071289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0928711^2 + 5933274000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1071289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0928711^2 + 59333274000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1071289^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0928711^2 + 593333274000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1071289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0928711^2 + 5933333274000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1071289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0928711^2 + 59333333274000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1071289^2 \end{aligned}$$

268)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0928176^2 + 536000^2 & := & 1071824^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0928176^2 + 5896000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1071824^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0928176^2 + 59496000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1071824^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0928176^2 + 595496000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1071824^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0928176^2 + 5955496000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1071824^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0928176^2 + 59555496000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1071824^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0928176^2 + 595555496000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1071824^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0928176^2 + 5955555496000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1071824^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0928176^2 + 59555555496000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1071824^2 \end{aligned}$$

269)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0927639^2 + 538000^2 & := & 1072361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0927639^2 + 5918000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1072361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0927639^2 + 59718000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1072361^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0927639^2 + 597718000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1072361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0927639^2 + 5977718000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1072361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0927639^2 + 59777718000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1072361^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0927639^2 + 597777718000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1072361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0927639^2 + 5977777718000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1072361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0927639^2 + 59777777718000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1072361^2 \end{aligned}$$

270)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0927100^2 + 540000^2 & := & 1072900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0927100^2 + 5940000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1072900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0927100^2 + 59940000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1072900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0927100^2 + 599940000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1072900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0927100^2 + 5999940000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1072900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0927100^2 + 59999940000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1072900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0927100^2 + 599999940000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1072900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0927100^2 + 5999999940000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1072900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0927100^2 + 59999999940000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1072900^2 \end{aligned}$$

271)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0926559^2 + 542000^2 & := & 1073441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0926559^2 + 5962000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1073441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0926559^2 + 60162000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1073441^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0926559^2 + 602162000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1073441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0926559^2 + 6022162000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1073441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0926559^2 + 60222162000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1073441^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0926559^2 + 602222162000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1073441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0926559^2 + 6022222162000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1073441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0926559^2 + 60222222162000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1073441^2 \end{aligned}$$

272)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0926016^2 + 544000^2 & := & 1073984^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0926016^2 + 5984000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1073984^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0926016^2 + 60384000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1073984^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0926016^2 + 604384000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1073984^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0926016^2 + 6044384000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1073984^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0926016^2 + 60444384000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1073984^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0926016^2 + 604444384000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1073984^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0926016^2 + 6044444384000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1073984^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0926016^2 + 60444444384000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1073984^2 \end{aligned}$$

273)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0925471^2 + 546000^2 & := & 1074529^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0925471^2 + 6006000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1074529^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0925471^2 + 60606000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1074529^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0925471^2 + 606606000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1074529^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0925471^2 + 6066606000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1074529^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0925471^2 + 60666606000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1074529^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0925471^2 + 606666606000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1074529^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0925471^2 + 6066666606000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1074529^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0925471^2 + 60666666606000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1074529^2 \end{aligned}$$

274)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0924924^2 + 548000^2 & := & 1075076^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0924924^2 + 6028000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1075076^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0924924^2 + 60828000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1075076^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0924924^2 + 608828000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1075076^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0924924^2 + 6088828000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1075076^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0924924^2 + 60888828000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1075076^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0924924^2 + 608888828000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1075076^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0924924^2 + 6088888828000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1075076^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0924924^2 + 60888888828000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1075076^2 \end{aligned}$$

275)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0924375^2 + 550000^2 & := & 1075625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0924375^2 + 6050000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1075625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0924375^2 + 61050000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1075625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0924375^2 + 611050000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1075625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0924375^2 + 6111050000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1075625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0924375^2 + 61111050000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1075625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0924375^2 + 611111050000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1075625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0924375^2 + 6111111050000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1075625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0924375^2 + 61111111050000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1075625^2 \end{aligned}$$

276)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0923824^2 + 552000^2 & := & 1076176^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0923824^2 + 6072000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1076176^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0923824^2 + 61272000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1076176^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0923824^2 + 613272000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1076176^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0923824^2 + 6133272000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1076176^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0923824^2 + 61333272000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1076176^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0923824^2 + 613333272000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1076176^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0923824^2 + 6133333272000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1076176^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0923824^2 + 61333333272000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1076176^2 \end{aligned}$$

277)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0923271^2 + 554000^2 & := & 1076729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0923271^2 + 6094000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1076729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0923271^2 + 61494000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1076729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0923271^2 + 615494000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1076729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0923271^2 + 6155494000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1076729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0923271^2 + 61555494000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1076729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0923271^2 + 615555494000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1076729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0923271^2 + 6155555494000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1076729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0923271^2 + 61555555494000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1076729^2 \end{aligned}$$

278)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0922716^2 + 556000^2 & := & 1077284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0922716^2 + 6116000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1077284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0922716^2 + 61716000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1077284^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0922716^2 + 617716000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1077284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0922716^2 + 6177716000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1077284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0922716^2 + 61777716000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1077284^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0922716^2 + 617777716000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1077284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0922716^2 + 6177777716000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1077284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0922716^2 + 61777777716000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1077284^2 \end{aligned}$$

279)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0922159^2 + 558000^2 & := & 1077841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0922159^2 + 6138000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1077841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0922159^2 + 61938000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1077841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0922159^2 + 619938000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1077841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0922159^2 + 6199938000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1077841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0922159^2 + 61999938000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1077841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0922159^2 + 619999938000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1077841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0922159^2 + 6199999938000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1077841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0922159^2 + 61999999938000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1077841^2 \end{aligned}$$

280)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0921600^2 + 560000^2 & := & 1078400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0921600^2 + 6160000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1078400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0921600^2 + 62160000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1078400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0921600^2 + 622160000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1078400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0921600^2 + 6222160000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1078400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0921600^2 + 62222160000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1078400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0921600^2 + 622222160000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1078400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0921600^2 + 6222222160000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1078400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0921600^2 + 62222222160000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1078400^2 \end{aligned}$$

281)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0921039^2 + 562000^2 & := & 1078961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0921039^2 + 6182000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1078961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0921039^2 + 62382000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1078961^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0921039^2 + 624382000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1078961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0921039^2 + 6244382000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1078961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0921039^2 + 62444382000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1078961^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0921039^2 + 624444382000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1078961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0921039^2 + 6244444382000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1078961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0921039^2 + 62444444382000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1078961^2 \end{aligned}$$

282)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0920476^2 + 564000^2 & := & 1079524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0920476^2 + 6204000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1079524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0920476^2 + 62604000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1079524^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0920476^2 + 626604000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1079524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0920476^2 + 6266604000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1079524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0920476^2 + 62666604000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1079524^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0920476^2 + 626666604000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1079524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0920476^2 + 6266666604000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1079524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0920476^2 + 62666666604000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1079524^2 \end{aligned}$$

283)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0919911^2 + 566000^2 & := & 1080089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0919911^2 + 6226000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1080089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0919911^2 + 62826000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1080089^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0919911^2 + 628826000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1080089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0919911^2 + 6288826000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1080089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0919911^2 + 62888826000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1080089^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0919911^2 + 628888826000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1080089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0919911^2 + 6288888826000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1080089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0919911^2 + 62888888826000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1080089^2 \end{aligned}$$

284)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0919344^2 + 568000^2 & := & 1080656^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0919344^2 + 6248000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1080656^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0919344^2 + 63048000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1080656^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0919344^2 + 631048000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1080656^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0919344^2 + 6311048000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1080656^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0919344^2 + 63111048000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1080656^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0919344^2 + 631111048000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1080656^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0919344^2 + 6311111048000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1080656^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0919344^2 + 63111111048000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1080656^2 \end{aligned}$$

285)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0918775^2 + 570000^2 & := & 1081225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0918775^2 + 6270000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1081225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0918775^2 + 63270000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1081225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0918775^2 + 633270000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1081225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0918775^2 + 6333270000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1081225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0918775^2 + 63333270000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1081225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0918775^2 + 633333270000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1081225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0918775^2 + 6333333270000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1081225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0918775^2 + 63333333270000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1081225^2 \end{aligned}$$

286)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0918204^2 + 572000^2 & := & 1081796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0918204^2 + 6292000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1081796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0918204^2 + 63492000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1081796^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0918204^2 + 635492000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1081796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0918204^2 + 6355492000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1081796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0918204^2 + 63555492000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1081796^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0918204^2 + 635555492000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1081796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0918204^2 + 6355555492000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1081796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0918204^2 + 63555555492000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1081796^2 \end{aligned}$$

287)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0917631^2 + 574000^2 & := & 1082369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0917631^2 + 6314000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1082369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0917631^2 + 63714000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1082369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0917631^2 + 637714000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1082369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0917631^2 + 6377714000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1082369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0917631^2 + 63777714000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1082369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0917631^2 + 637777714000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1082369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0917631^2 + 6377777714000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1082369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0917631^2 + 63777777714000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1082369^2 \end{aligned}$$

288)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0917056^2 + 576000^2 & := & 1082944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0917056^2 + 6336000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1082944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0917056^2 + 63936000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1082944^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0917056^2 + 639936000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1082944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0917056^2 + 6399936000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1082944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0917056^2 + 63999936000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1082944^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0917056^2 + 639999936000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1082944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0917056^2 + 6399999936000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1082944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0917056^2 + 63999999936000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1082944^2 \end{aligned}$$

289)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0916479^2 + 578000^2 & := & 1083521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0916479^2 + 6358000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1083521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0916479^2 + 64158000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1083521^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0916479^2 + 642158000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1083521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0916479^2 + 6422158000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1083521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0916479^2 + 64222158000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1083521^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0916479^2 + 642222158000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1083521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0916479^2 + 6422222158000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1083521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0916479^2 + 64222222158000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1083521^2 \end{aligned}$$

290)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0915900^2 + 580000^2 & := & 1084100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0915900^2 + 6380000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1084100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0915900^2 + 64380000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1084100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0915900^2 + 644380000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1084100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0915900^2 + 6444380000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1084100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0915900^2 + 64444380000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1084100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0915900^2 + 644444380000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1084100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0915900^2 + 6444444380000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1084100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0915900^2 + 64444444380000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1084100^2 \end{aligned}$$

291)

$$\begin{aligned} &0915319^2 + 582000^2 && := 1084681^2 \\ &12\ 0915319^2 + 6402000^2 && := 12\ 1084681^2 \\ &1232\ 0915319^2 + 64602000^2 && := 1232\ 1084681^2 \\ &123432\ 0915319^2 + 646602000^2 && := 123432\ 1084681^2 \\ &12345432\ 0915319^2 + 6466602000^2 && := 12345432\ 1084681^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0915319^2 + 64666602000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1084681^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0915319^2 + 646666602000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1084681^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0915319^2 + 6466666602000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1084681^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0915319^2 + 64666666602000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1084681^2 \end{aligned}$$

292)

$$\begin{aligned} &0914736^2 + 584000^2 && := 1085264^2 \\ &12\ 0914736^2 + 6424000^2 && := 12\ 1085264^2 \\ &1232\ 0914736^2 + 64824000^2 && := 1232\ 1085264^2 \\ &123432\ 0914736^2 + 648824000^2 && := 123432\ 1085264^2 \\ &12345432\ 0914736^2 + 6488824000^2 && := 12345432\ 1085264^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0914736^2 + 64888824000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1085264^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0914736^2 + 648888824000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1085264^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0914736^2 + 6488888824000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1085264^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0914736^2 + 64888888824000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1085264^2 \end{aligned}$$

293)

$$\begin{aligned} &0914151^2 + 586000^2 && := 1085849^2 \\ &12\ 0914151^2 + 6446000^2 && := 12\ 1085849^2 \\ &1232\ 0914151^2 + 65046000^2 && := 1232\ 1085849^2 \\ &123432\ 0914151^2 + 651046000^2 && := 123432\ 1085849^2 \\ &12345432\ 0914151^2 + 6511046000^2 && := 12345432\ 1085849^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0914151^2 + 65111046000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1085849^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0914151^2 + 651111046000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1085849^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0914151^2 + 6511111046000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1085849^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0914151^2 + 65111111046000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1085849^2 \end{aligned}$$

294)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0913564^2 + 588000^2 & := & 1086436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0913564^2 + 6468000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1086436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0913564^2 + 65268000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1086436^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0913564^2 + 653268000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1086436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0913564^2 + 6533268000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1086436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0913564^2 + 65333268000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1086436^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0913564^2 + 653333268000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1086436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0913564^2 + 6533333268000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1086436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0913564^2 + 65333333268000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1086436^2 \end{aligned}$$

295)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0912975^2 + 590000^2 & := & 1087025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0912975^2 + 6490000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1087025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0912975^2 + 65490000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1087025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0912975^2 + 655490000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1087025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0912975^2 + 6555490000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1087025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0912975^2 + 65555490000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1087025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0912975^2 + 655555490000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1087025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0912975^2 + 6555555490000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1087025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0912975^2 + 65555555490000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1087025^2 \end{aligned}$$

296)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0912384^2 + 592000^2 & := & 1087616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0912384^2 + 6512000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1087616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0912384^2 + 65712000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1087616^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0912384^2 + 657712000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1087616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0912384^2 + 6577712000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1087616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0912384^2 + 65777712000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1087616^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0912384^2 + 657777712000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1087616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0912384^2 + 6577777712000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1087616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0912384^2 + 65777777712000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1087616^2 \end{aligned}$$

297)

$$\begin{aligned} &0911791^2 + 594000^2 && := 1088209^2 \\ &12\ 0911791^2 + 6534000^2 && := 12\ 1088209^2 \\ &1232\ 0911791^2 + 65934000^2 && := 1232\ 1088209^2 \\ &123432\ 0911791^2 + 659934000^2 && := 123432\ 1088209^2 \\ &12345432\ 0911791^2 + 6599934000^2 && := 12345432\ 1088209^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0911791^2 + 65999934000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1088209^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0911791^2 + 659999934000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1088209^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0911791^2 + 6599999934000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1088209^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0911791^2 + 65999999934000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1088209^2 \end{aligned}$$

298)

$$\begin{aligned} &0911196^2 + 596000^2 && := 1088804^2 \\ &12\ 0911196^2 + 6556000^2 && := 12\ 1088804^2 \\ &1232\ 0911196^2 + 66156000^2 && := 1232\ 1088804^2 \\ &123432\ 0911196^2 + 662156000^2 && := 123432\ 1088804^2 \\ &12345432\ 0911196^2 + 6622156000^2 && := 12345432\ 1088804^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0911196^2 + 66222156000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1088804^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0911196^2 + 662222156000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1088804^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0911196^2 + 6622222156000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1088804^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0911196^2 + 66222222156000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1088804^2 \end{aligned}$$

299)

$$\begin{aligned} &0910599^2 + 598000^2 && := 1089401^2 \\ &12\ 0910599^2 + 6578000^2 && := 12\ 1089401^2 \\ &1232\ 0910599^2 + 66378000^2 && := 1232\ 1089401^2 \\ &123432\ 0910599^2 + 664378000^2 && := 123432\ 1089401^2 \\ &12345432\ 0910599^2 + 6644378000^2 && := 12345432\ 1089401^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0910599^2 + 66444378000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1089401^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0910599^2 + 664444378000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1089401^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0910599^2 + 6644444378000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1089401^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0910599^2 + 66444444378000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1089401^2 \end{aligned}$$

300)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0910000^2 + 600000^2 & := & 1090000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0910000^2 + 6600000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1090000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0910000^2 + 66600000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1090000^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0910000^2 + 666600000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1090000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0910000^2 + 6666600000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1090000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0910000^2 + 66666600000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1090000^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0910000^2 + 666666600000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1090000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0910000^2 + 6666666600000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1090000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0910000^2 + 66666666600000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1090000^2 \end{aligned}$$

301)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0909399^2 + 602000^2 & := & 1090601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0909399^2 + 6622000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1090601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0909399^2 + 66822000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1090601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0909399^2 + 668822000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1090601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0909399^2 + 6688822000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1090601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0909399^2 + 66888822000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1090601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0909399^2 + 668888822000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1090601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0909399^2 + 6688888822000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1090601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0909399^2 + 66888888822000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1090601^2 \end{aligned}$$

302)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0908796^2 + 604000^2 & := & 1091204^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0908796^2 + 6644000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1091204^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0908796^2 + 67044000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1091204^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0908796^2 + 671044000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1091204^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0908796^2 + 6711044000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1091204^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0908796^2 + 67111044000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1091204^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0908796^2 + 671111044000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1091204^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0908796^2 + 6711111044000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1091204^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0908796^2 + 67111111044000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1091204^2 \end{aligned}$$

303)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0908191^2 + 606000^2 & := & 1091809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0908191^2 + 6666000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1091809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0908191^2 + 67266000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1091809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0908191^2 + 673266000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1091809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0908191^2 + 6733266000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1091809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0908191^2 + 67333266000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1091809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0908191^2 + 673333266000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1091809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0908191^2 + 6733333266000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1091809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0908191^2 + 67333333266000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1091809^2 \end{aligned}$$

304)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0907584^2 + 608000^2 & := & 1092416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0907584^2 + 6688000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1092416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0907584^2 + 67488000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1092416^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0907584^2 + 675488000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1092416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0907584^2 + 6755488000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1092416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0907584^2 + 67555488000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1092416^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0907584^2 + 675555488000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1092416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0907584^2 + 6755555488000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1092416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0907584^2 + 67555555488000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1092416^2 \end{aligned}$$

305)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0906975^2 + 610000^2 & := & 1093025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0906975^2 + 6710000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1093025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0906975^2 + 67710000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1093025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0906975^2 + 677710000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1093025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0906975^2 + 6777710000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1093025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0906975^2 + 67777710000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1093025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0906975^2 + 677777710000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1093025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0906975^2 + 6777777710000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1093025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0906975^2 + 67777777710000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1093025^2 \end{aligned}$$

306)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0906364^2 + 612000^2 & := & 1093636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0906364^2 + 6732000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1093636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0906364^2 + 67932000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1093636^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0906364^2 + 679932000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1093636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0906364^2 + 6799932000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1093636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0906364^2 + 67999932000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1093636^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0906364^2 + 679999932000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1093636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0906364^2 + 6799999932000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1093636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0906364^2 + 67999999932000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1093636^2 \end{aligned}$$

307)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0905751^2 + 614000^2 & := & 1094249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0905751^2 + 6754000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1094249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0905751^2 + 68154000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1094249^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0905751^2 + 682154000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1094249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0905751^2 + 6822154000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1094249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0905751^2 + 68222154000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1094249^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0905751^2 + 682222154000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1094249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0905751^2 + 6822222154000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1094249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0905751^2 + 68222222154000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1094249^2 \end{aligned}$$

308)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0905136^2 + 616000^2 & := & 1094864^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0905136^2 + 6776000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1094864^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0905136^2 + 68376000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1094864^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0905136^2 + 684376000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1094864^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0905136^2 + 6844376000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1094864^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0905136^2 + 68444376000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1094864^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0905136^2 + 684444376000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1094864^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0905136^2 + 6844444376000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1094864^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0905136^2 + 68444444376000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1094864^2 \end{aligned}$$

309)

$$\begin{aligned} &0904519^2 + 618000^2 && := 1095481^2 \\ &12\ 0904519^2 + 6798000^2 && := 12\ 1095481^2 \\ &1232\ 0904519^2 + 68598000^2 && := 1232\ 1095481^2 \\ &123432\ 0904519^2 + 686598000^2 && := 123432\ 1095481^2 \\ &12345432\ 0904519^2 + 6866598000^2 && := 12345432\ 1095481^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0904519^2 + 68666598000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1095481^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0904519^2 + 686666598000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1095481^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0904519^2 + 6866666598000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1095481^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0904519^2 + 68666666598000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1095481^2 \end{aligned}$$

310)

$$\begin{aligned} &0903900^2 + 620000^2 && := 1096100^2 \\ &12\ 0903900^2 + 6820000^2 && := 12\ 1096100^2 \\ &1232\ 0903900^2 + 68820000^2 && := 1232\ 1096100^2 \\ &123432\ 0903900^2 + 688820000^2 && := 123432\ 1096100^2 \\ &12345432\ 0903900^2 + 6888820000^2 && := 12345432\ 1096100^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0903900^2 + 68888820000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1096100^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0903900^2 + 688888820000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1096100^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0903900^2 + 6888888820000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1096100^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0903900^2 + 68888888820000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1096100^2 \end{aligned}$$

311)

$$\begin{aligned} &0903279^2 + 622000^2 && := 1096721^2 \\ &12\ 0903279^2 + 6842000^2 && := 12\ 1096721^2 \\ &1232\ 0903279^2 + 69042000^2 && := 1232\ 1096721^2 \\ &123432\ 0903279^2 + 691042000^2 && := 123432\ 1096721^2 \\ &12345432\ 0903279^2 + 6911042000^2 && := 12345432\ 1096721^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0903279^2 + 69111042000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1096721^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0903279^2 + 691111042000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1096721^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0903279^2 + 6911111042000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1096721^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0903279^2 + 69111111042000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1096721^2 \end{aligned}$$

312)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0902656^2 + 624000^2 & := & 1097344^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0902656^2 + 6864000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1097344^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0902656^2 + 69264000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1097344^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0902656^2 + 693264000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1097344^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0902656^2 + 6933264000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1097344^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0902656^2 + 69333264000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1097344^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0902656^2 + 693333264000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1097344^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0902656^2 + 6933333264000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1097344^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0902656^2 + 69333333264000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1097344^2 \end{aligned}$$

313)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0902031^2 + 626000^2 & := & 1097969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0902031^2 + 6886000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1097969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0902031^2 + 69486000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1097969^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0902031^2 + 695486000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1097969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0902031^2 + 6955486000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1097969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0902031^2 + 69555486000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1097969^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0902031^2 + 695555486000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1097969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0902031^2 + 6955555486000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1097969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0902031^2 + 69555555486000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1097969^2 \end{aligned}$$

314)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0901404^2 + 628000^2 & := & 1098596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0901404^2 + 6908000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1098596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0901404^2 + 69708000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1098596^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0901404^2 + 697708000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1098596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0901404^2 + 6977708000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1098596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0901404^2 + 69777708000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1098596^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0901404^2 + 697777708000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1098596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0901404^2 + 6977777708000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1098596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0901404^2 + 69777777708000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1098596^2 \end{aligned}$$

315)

$$\begin{aligned} &0900775^2 + 630000^2 && := 1099225^2 \\ &12\ 0900775^2 + 6930000^2 && := 12\ 1099225^2 \\ &1232\ 0900775^2 + 69930000^2 && := 1232\ 1099225^2 \\ &123432\ 0900775^2 + 699930000^2 && := 123432\ 1099225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0900775^2 + 6999930000^2 && := 12345432\ 1099225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0900775^2 + 69999930000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1099225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0900775^2 + 699999930000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1099225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0900775^2 + 6999999930000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1099225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0900775^2 + 69999999930000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1099225^2 \end{aligned}$$

316)

$$\begin{aligned} &0900144^2 + 632000^2 && := 1099856^2 \\ &12\ 0900144^2 + 6952000^2 && := 12\ 1099856^2 \\ &1232\ 0900144^2 + 70152000^2 && := 1232\ 1099856^2 \\ &123432\ 0900144^2 + 702152000^2 && := 123432\ 1099856^2 \\ &12345432\ 0900144^2 + 7022152000^2 && := 12345432\ 1099856^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0900144^2 + 70222152000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1099856^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0900144^2 + 702222152000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1099856^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0900144^2 + 7022222152000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1099856^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0900144^2 + 70222222152000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1099856^2 \end{aligned}$$

317)

$$\begin{aligned} &0899511^2 + 634000^2 && := 1100489^2 \\ &12\ 0899511^2 + 6974000^2 && := 12\ 1100489^2 \\ &1232\ 0899511^2 + 70374000^2 && := 1232\ 1100489^2 \\ &123432\ 0899511^2 + 704374000^2 && := 123432\ 1100489^2 \\ &12345432\ 0899511^2 + 7044374000^2 && := 12345432\ 1100489^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0899511^2 + 70444374000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1100489^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0899511^2 + 704444374000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1100489^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0899511^2 + 7044444374000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1100489^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0899511^2 + 70444444374000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1100489^2 \end{aligned}$$

318)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0898876^2 + 636000^2 & := & 1101124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0898876^2 + 6996000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1101124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0898876^2 + 70596000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1101124^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0898876^2 + 706596000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1101124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0898876^2 + 7066596000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1101124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0898876^2 + 70666596000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1101124^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0898876^2 + 706666596000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1101124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0898876^2 + 7066666596000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1101124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0898876^2 + 70666666596000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1101124^2 \end{aligned}$$

319)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0898239^2 + 638000^2 & := & 1101761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0898239^2 + 7018000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1101761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0898239^2 + 70818000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1101761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0898239^2 + 708818000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1101761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0898239^2 + 7088818000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1101761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0898239^2 + 70888818000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1101761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0898239^2 + 708888818000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1101761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0898239^2 + 7088888818000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1101761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0898239^2 + 70888888818000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1101761^2 \end{aligned}$$

320)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0897600^2 + 640000^2 & := & 1102400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0897600^2 + 7040000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1102400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0897600^2 + 71040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1102400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0897600^2 + 711040000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1102400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0897600^2 + 7111040000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1102400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0897600^2 + 71111040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1102400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0897600^2 + 711111040000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1102400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0897600^2 + 7111111040000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1102400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0897600^2 + 71111111040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1102400^2 \end{aligned}$$

321)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0896959^2 + 642000^2 & := & 1103041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0896959^2 + 7062000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1103041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0896959^2 + 71262000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1103041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0896959^2 + 713262000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1103041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0896959^2 + 7133262000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1103041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0896959^2 + 71333262000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1103041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0896959^2 + 713333262000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1103041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0896959^2 + 7133333262000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1103041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0896959^2 + 71333333262000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1103041^2 \end{aligned}$$

322)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0896316^2 + 644000^2 & := & 1103684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0896316^2 + 7084000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1103684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0896316^2 + 71484000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1103684^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0896316^2 + 715484000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1103684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0896316^2 + 7155484000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1103684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0896316^2 + 71555484000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1103684^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0896316^2 + 715555484000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1103684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0896316^2 + 7155555484000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1103684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0896316^2 + 71555555484000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1103684^2 \end{aligned}$$

323)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0895671^2 + 646000^2 & := & 1104329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0895671^2 + 7106000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1104329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0895671^2 + 71706000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1104329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0895671^2 + 717706000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1104329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0895671^2 + 7177706000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1104329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0895671^2 + 71777706000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1104329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0895671^2 + 717777706000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1104329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0895671^2 + 7177777706000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1104329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0895671^2 + 71777777706000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1104329^2 \end{aligned}$$

324)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0895024^2 + 648000^2 & := & 1104976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0895024^2 + 7128000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1104976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0895024^2 + 71928000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1104976^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0895024^2 + 719928000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1104976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0895024^2 + 7199928000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1104976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0895024^2 + 71999928000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1104976^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0895024^2 + 719999928000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1104976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0895024^2 + 7199999928000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1104976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0895024^2 + 71999999928000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1104976^2 \end{aligned}$$

325)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0894375^2 + 650000^2 & := & 1105625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0894375^2 + 7150000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1105625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0894375^2 + 72150000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1105625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0894375^2 + 722150000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1105625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0894375^2 + 7222150000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1105625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0894375^2 + 72222150000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1105625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0894375^2 + 722222150000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1105625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0894375^2 + 7222222150000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1105625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0894375^2 + 72222222150000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1105625^2 \end{aligned}$$

326)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0893724^2 + 652000^2 & := & 1106276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0893724^2 + 7172000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1106276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0893724^2 + 72372000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1106276^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0893724^2 + 724372000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1106276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0893724^2 + 7244372000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1106276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0893724^2 + 72444372000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1106276^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0893724^2 + 724444372000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1106276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0893724^2 + 7244444372000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1106276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0893724^2 + 72444444372000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1106276^2 \end{aligned}$$

327)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0893071^2 + 654000^2 & := & 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0893071^2 + 7194000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0893071^2 + 72594000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0893071^2 + 726594000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0893071^2 + 7266594000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0893071^2 + 72666594000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0893071^2 + 726666594000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0893071^2 + 7266666594000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0893071^2 + 72666666594000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1106929^2 \end{aligned}$$

328)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0892416^2 + 656000^2 & := & 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0892416^2 + 7216000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0892416^2 + 72816000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0892416^2 + 728816000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0892416^2 + 7288816000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0892416^2 + 72888816000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0892416^2 + 728888816000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0892416^2 + 7288888816000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0892416^2 + 72888888816000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1107584^2 \end{aligned}$$

329)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0891759^2 + 658000^2 & := & 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0891759^2 + 7238000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0891759^2 + 73038000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0891759^2 + 731038000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0891759^2 + 7311038000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0891759^2 + 73111038000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0891759^2 + 731111038000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0891759^2 + 7311111038000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0891759^2 + 73111111038000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1108241^2 \end{aligned}$$

330)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0891100^2 + 660000^2 & := & 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0891100^2 + 7260000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0891100^2 + 73260000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0891100^2 + 733260000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0891100^2 + 7333260000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0891100^2 + 73333260000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0891100^2 + 733333260000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0891100^2 + 7333333260000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0891100^2 + 73333333260000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1108900^2 \end{aligned}$$

331)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0890439^2 + 662000^2 & := & 1109561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0890439^2 + 7282000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1109561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0890439^2 + 73482000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1109561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0890439^2 + 735482000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1109561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0890439^2 + 7355482000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1109561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0890439^2 + 73555482000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1109561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0890439^2 + 735555482000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1109561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0890439^2 + 7355555482000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1109561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0890439^2 + 73555555482000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1109561^2 \end{aligned}$$

332)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0889776^2 + 664000^2 & := & 1110224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0889776^2 + 7304000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1110224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0889776^2 + 73704000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1110224^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0889776^2 + 737704000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1110224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0889776^2 + 7377704000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1110224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0889776^2 + 73777704000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1110224^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0889776^2 + 737777704000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1110224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0889776^2 + 7377777704000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1110224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0889776^2 + 73777777704000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1110224^2 \end{aligned}$$

333)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0889111^2 + 666000^2 & := & 1110889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0889111^2 + 7326000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1110889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0889111^2 + 73926000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1110889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0889111^2 + 739926000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1110889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0889111^2 + 7399926000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1110889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0889111^2 + 73999926000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1110889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0889111^2 + 739999926000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1110889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0889111^2 + 7399999926000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1110889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0889111^2 + 73999999926000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1110889^2 \end{aligned}$$

334)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0888444^2 + 668000^2 & := & 1111556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0888444^2 + 7348000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1111556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0888444^2 + 74148000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1111556^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0888444^2 + 742148000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1111556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0888444^2 + 7422148000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1111556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0888444^2 + 74222148000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1111556^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0888444^2 + 742222148000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1111556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0888444^2 + 7422222148000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1111556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0888444^2 + 74222222148000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1111556^2 \end{aligned}$$

335)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0887775^2 + 670000^2 & := & 1112225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0887775^2 + 7370000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1112225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0887775^2 + 74370000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1112225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0887775^2 + 744370000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1112225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0887775^2 + 7444370000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1112225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0887775^2 + 74444370000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1112225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0887775^2 + 744444370000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1112225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0887775^2 + 7444444370000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1112225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0887775^2 + 74444444370000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1112225^2 \end{aligned}$$

336)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0887104^2 + 672000^2 & := & 1112896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0887104^2 + 7392000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1112896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0887104^2 + 74592000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1112896^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0887104^2 + 746592000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1112896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0887104^2 + 7466592000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1112896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0887104^2 + 74666592000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1112896^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0887104^2 + 746666592000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1112896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0887104^2 + 7466666592000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1112896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0887104^2 + 74666666592000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1112896^2 \end{aligned}$$

337)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0886431^2 + 674000^2 & := & 1113569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0886431^2 + 7414000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1113569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0886431^2 + 74814000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1113569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0886431^2 + 748814000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1113569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0886431^2 + 7488814000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1113569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0886431^2 + 74888814000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1113569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0886431^2 + 748888814000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1113569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0886431^2 + 7488888814000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1113569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0886431^2 + 74888888814000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1113569^2 \end{aligned}$$

338)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0885756^2 + 676000^2 & := & 1114244^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0885756^2 + 7436000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1114244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0885756^2 + 75036000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1114244^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0885756^2 + 751036000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1114244^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0885756^2 + 7511036000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1114244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0885756^2 + 75111036000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1114244^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0885756^2 + 751111036000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1114244^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0885756^2 + 7511111036000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1114244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0885756^2 + 75111111036000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1114244^2 \end{aligned}$$

339)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0885079^2 + 678000^2 & := & 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0885079^2 + 7458000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0885079^2 + 75258000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0885079^2 + 753258000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0885079^2 + 7533258000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0885079^2 + 75333258000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0885079^2 + 753333258000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0885079^2 + 7533333258000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0885079^2 + 75333333258000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1114921^2 \end{aligned}$$

340)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0884400^2 + 680000^2 & := & 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0884400^2 + 7480000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0884400^2 + 75480000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0884400^2 + 755480000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0884400^2 + 7555480000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0884400^2 + 75555480000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0884400^2 + 755555480000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0884400^2 + 7555555480000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0884400^2 + 75555555480000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1115600^2 \end{aligned}$$

341)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0883719^2 + 682000^2 & := & 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0883719^2 + 7502000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0883719^2 + 75702000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0883719^2 + 757702000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0883719^2 + 7577702000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0883719^2 + 75777702000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0883719^2 + 757777702000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0883719^2 + 7577777702000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0883719^2 + 75777777702000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1116281^2 \end{aligned}$$

342)

$$\begin{aligned} &0883036^2 + 684000^2 && := 1116964^2 \\ &12\ 0883036^2 + 7524000^2 && := 12\ 1116964^2 \\ &1232\ 0883036^2 + 75924000^2 && := 1232\ 1116964^2 \\ &123432\ 0883036^2 + 759924000^2 && := 123432\ 1116964^2 \\ &12345432\ 0883036^2 + 7599924000^2 && := 12345432\ 1116964^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0883036^2 + 75999924000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1116964^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0883036^2 + 759999924000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1116964^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0883036^2 + 7599999924000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1116964^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0883036^2 + 75999999924000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1116964^2 \end{aligned}$$

343)

$$\begin{aligned} &0882351^2 + 686000^2 && := 1117649^2 \\ &12\ 0882351^2 + 7546000^2 && := 12\ 1117649^2 \\ &1232\ 0882351^2 + 76146000^2 && := 1232\ 1117649^2 \\ &123432\ 0882351^2 + 762146000^2 && := 123432\ 1117649^2 \\ &12345432\ 0882351^2 + 7622146000^2 && := 12345432\ 1117649^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0882351^2 + 76222146000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1117649^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0882351^2 + 762222146000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1117649^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0882351^2 + 7622222146000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1117649^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0882351^2 + 76222222146000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1117649^2 \end{aligned}$$

344)

$$\begin{aligned} &0881664^2 + 688000^2 && := 1118336^2 \\ &12\ 0881664^2 + 7568000^2 && := 12\ 1118336^2 \\ &1232\ 0881664^2 + 76368000^2 && := 1232\ 1118336^2 \\ &123432\ 0881664^2 + 764368000^2 && := 123432\ 1118336^2 \\ &12345432\ 0881664^2 + 7644368000^2 && := 12345432\ 1118336^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0881664^2 + 76444368000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1118336^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0881664^2 + 764444368000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1118336^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0881664^2 + 7644444368000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1118336^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0881664^2 + 76444444368000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1118336^2 \end{aligned}$$

345)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0880975^2 + 690000^2 & := & 1119025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0880975^2 + 7590000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1119025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0880975^2 + 76590000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1119025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0880975^2 + 766590000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1119025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0880975^2 + 7666590000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1119025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0880975^2 + 76666590000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1119025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0880975^2 + 766666590000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1119025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0880975^2 + 7666666590000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1119025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0880975^2 + 76666666590000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1119025^2 \end{aligned}$$

346)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0880284^2 + 692000^2 & := & 1119716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0880284^2 + 7612000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1119716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0880284^2 + 76812000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1119716^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0880284^2 + 768812000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1119716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0880284^2 + 7688812000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1119716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0880284^2 + 76888812000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1119716^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0880284^2 + 768888812000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1119716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0880284^2 + 7688888812000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1119716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0880284^2 + 76888888812000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1119716^2 \end{aligned}$$

347)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0879591^2 + 694000^2 & := & 1120409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0879591^2 + 7634000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1120409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0879591^2 + 77034000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1120409^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0879591^2 + 771034000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1120409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0879591^2 + 7711034000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1120409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0879591^2 + 77111034000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1120409^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0879591^2 + 771111034000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1120409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0879591^2 + 7711111034000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1120409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0879591^2 + 77111111034000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1120409^2 \end{aligned}$$

348)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0878896^2 + 696000^2 & := & 1121104^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0878896^2 + 7656000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1121104^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0878896^2 + 77256000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1121104^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0878896^2 + 773256000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1121104^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0878896^2 + 7733256000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1121104^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0878896^2 + 77333256000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1121104^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0878896^2 + 773333256000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1121104^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0878896^2 + 7733333256000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1121104^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0878896^2 + 77333333256000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1121104^2 \end{aligned}$$

349)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0878199^2 + 698000^2 & := & 1121801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0878199^2 + 7678000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1121801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0878199^2 + 77478000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1121801^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0878199^2 + 775478000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1121801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0878199^2 + 7755478000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1121801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0878199^2 + 77555478000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1121801^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0878199^2 + 775555478000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1121801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0878199^2 + 7755555478000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1121801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0878199^2 + 77555555478000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1121801^2 \end{aligned}$$

350)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0877500^2 + 700000^2 & := & 1122500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0877500^2 + 7700000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1122500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0877500^2 + 77700000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1122500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0877500^2 + 777700000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1122500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0877500^2 + 7777700000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1122500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0877500^2 + 77777700000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1122500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0877500^2 + 777777700000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1122500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0877500^2 + 7777777700000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1122500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0877500^2 + 77777777700000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1122500^2 \end{aligned}$$

351)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0876799^2 + 702000^2 & := & 1123201^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0876799^2 + 7722000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1123201^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0876799^2 + 77922000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1123201^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0876799^2 + 779922000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1123201^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0876799^2 + 7799922000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1123201^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0876799^2 + 77999922000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1123201^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0876799^2 + 779999922000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1123201^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0876799^2 + 7799999922000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1123201^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0876799^2 + 77999999922000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1123201^2 \end{aligned}$$

352)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0876096^2 + 704000^2 & := & 1123904^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0876096^2 + 7744000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1123904^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0876096^2 + 78144000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1123904^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0876096^2 + 782144000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1123904^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0876096^2 + 7822144000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1123904^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0876096^2 + 78222144000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1123904^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0876096^2 + 782222144000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1123904^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0876096^2 + 7822222144000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1123904^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0876096^2 + 78222222144000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1123904^2 \end{aligned}$$

353)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0875391^2 + 706000^2 & := & 1124609^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0875391^2 + 7766000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1124609^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0875391^2 + 78366000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1124609^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0875391^2 + 784366000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1124609^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0875391^2 + 7844366000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1124609^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0875391^2 + 78444366000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1124609^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0875391^2 + 784444366000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1124609^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0875391^2 + 7844444366000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1124609^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0875391^2 + 78444444366000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1124609^2 \end{aligned}$$

354)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0874684^2 + 708000^2 & := & 1125316^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0874684^2 + 7788000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1125316^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0874684^2 + 78588000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1125316^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0874684^2 + 786588000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1125316^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0874684^2 + 7866588000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1125316^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0874684^2 + 78666588000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1125316^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0874684^2 + 786666588000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1125316^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0874684^2 + 7866666588000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1125316^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0874684^2 + 78666666588000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1125316^2 \end{aligned}$$

355)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0873975^2 + 710000^2 & := & 1126025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0873975^2 + 7810000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1126025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0873975^2 + 78810000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1126025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0873975^2 + 788810000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1126025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0873975^2 + 7888810000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1126025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0873975^2 + 78888810000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1126025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0873975^2 + 788888810000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1126025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0873975^2 + 7888888810000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1126025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0873975^2 + 78888888810000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1126025^2 \end{aligned}$$

356)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0873264^2 + 712000^2 & := & 1126736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0873264^2 + 7832000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1126736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0873264^2 + 79032000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1126736^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0873264^2 + 791032000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1126736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0873264^2 + 7911032000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1126736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0873264^2 + 79111032000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1126736^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0873264^2 + 791111032000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1126736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0873264^2 + 7911111032000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1126736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0873264^2 + 79111111032000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1126736^2 \end{aligned}$$

357)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0872551^2 + 714000^2 & := & 1127449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0872551^2 + 7854000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1127449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0872551^2 + 79254000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1127449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0872551^2 + 793254000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1127449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0872551^2 + 7933254000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1127449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0872551^2 + 79333254000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1127449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0872551^2 + 793333254000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1127449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0872551^2 + 7933333254000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1127449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0872551^2 + 79333333254000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1127449^2 \end{aligned}$$

358)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0871836^2 + 716000^2 & := & 1128164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0871836^2 + 7876000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1128164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0871836^2 + 79476000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1128164^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0871836^2 + 795476000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1128164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0871836^2 + 7955476000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1128164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0871836^2 + 79555476000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1128164^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0871836^2 + 795555476000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1128164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0871836^2 + 7955555476000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1128164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0871836^2 + 79555555476000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1128164^2 \end{aligned}$$

359)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0871119^2 + 718000^2 & := & 1128881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0871119^2 + 7898000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1128881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0871119^2 + 79698000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1128881^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0871119^2 + 797698000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1128881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0871119^2 + 7977698000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1128881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0871119^2 + 79777698000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1128881^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0871119^2 + 797777698000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1128881^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0871119^2 + 7977777698000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1128881^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0871119^2 + 79777777698000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1128881^2 \end{aligned}$$

360)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0870400^2 + 720000^2 & := & 1129600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0870400^2 + 7920000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1129600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0870400^2 + 79920000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1129600^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0870400^2 + 799920000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1129600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0870400^2 + 7999920000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1129600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0870400^2 + 79999920000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1129600^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0870400^2 + 799999920000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1129600^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0870400^2 + 7999999920000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1129600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0870400^2 + 79999999920000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1129600^2 \end{aligned}$$

361)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0869679^2 + 722000^2 & := & 1130321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0869679^2 + 7942000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1130321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0869679^2 + 80142000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1130321^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0869679^2 + 802142000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1130321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0869679^2 + 8022142000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1130321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0869679^2 + 80222142000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1130321^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0869679^2 + 802222142000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1130321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0869679^2 + 8022222142000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1130321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0869679^2 + 80222222142000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1130321^2 \end{aligned}$$

362)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0868956^2 + 724000^2 & := & 1131044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0868956^2 + 7964000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1131044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0868956^2 + 80364000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1131044^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0868956^2 + 804364000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1131044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0868956^2 + 8044364000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1131044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0868956^2 + 80444364000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1131044^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0868956^2 + 804444364000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1131044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0868956^2 + 8044444364000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1131044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0868956^2 + 80444444364000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1131044^2 \end{aligned}$$

363)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0868231^2 + 726000^2 & := & 1131769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0868231^2 + 7986000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1131769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0868231^2 + 80586000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1131769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0868231^2 + 806586000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1131769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0868231^2 + 8066586000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1131769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0868231^2 + 80666586000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1131769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0868231^2 + 806666586000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1131769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0868231^2 + 8066666586000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1131769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0868231^2 + 80666666586000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1131769^2 \end{aligned}$$

364)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0867504^2 + 728000^2 & := & 1132496^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0867504^2 + 8008000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1132496^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0867504^2 + 80808000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1132496^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0867504^2 + 808808000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1132496^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0867504^2 + 8088808000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1132496^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0867504^2 + 80888808000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1132496^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0867504^2 + 808888808000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1132496^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0867504^2 + 8088888808000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1132496^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0867504^2 + 80888888808000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1132496^2 \end{aligned}$$

365)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0866775^2 + 730000^2 & := & 1133225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0866775^2 + 8030000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1133225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0866775^2 + 81030000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1133225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0866775^2 + 811030000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1133225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0866775^2 + 8111030000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1133225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0866775^2 + 81111030000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1133225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0866775^2 + 811111030000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1133225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0866775^2 + 8111111030000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1133225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0866775^2 + 81111111030000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1133225^2 \end{aligned}$$

366)

$$\begin{aligned} &0866044^2 + 732000^2 && := 1133956^2 \\ &12\ 0866044^2 + 8052000^2 && := 12\ 1133956^2 \\ &1232\ 0866044^2 + 81252000^2 && := 1232\ 1133956^2 \\ &123432\ 0866044^2 + 813252000^2 && := 123432\ 1133956^2 \\ &12345432\ 0866044^2 + 8133252000^2 && := 12345432\ 1133956^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0866044^2 + 81333252000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1133956^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0866044^2 + 813333252000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1133956^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0866044^2 + 8133333252000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1133956^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0866044^2 + 81333333252000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1133956^2 \end{aligned}$$

367)

$$\begin{aligned} &0865311^2 + 734000^2 && := 1134689^2 \\ &12\ 0865311^2 + 8074000^2 && := 12\ 1134689^2 \\ &1232\ 0865311^2 + 81474000^2 && := 1232\ 1134689^2 \\ &123432\ 0865311^2 + 815474000^2 && := 123432\ 1134689^2 \\ &12345432\ 0865311^2 + 8155474000^2 && := 12345432\ 1134689^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0865311^2 + 81555474000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1134689^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0865311^2 + 815555474000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1134689^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0865311^2 + 8155555474000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1134689^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0865311^2 + 81555555474000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1134689^2 \end{aligned}$$

368)

$$\begin{aligned} &0864576^2 + 736000^2 && := 1135424^2 \\ &12\ 0864576^2 + 8096000^2 && := 12\ 1135424^2 \\ &1232\ 0864576^2 + 81696000^2 && := 1232\ 1135424^2 \\ &123432\ 0864576^2 + 817696000^2 && := 123432\ 1135424^2 \\ &12345432\ 0864576^2 + 8177696000^2 && := 12345432\ 1135424^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0864576^2 + 81777696000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1135424^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0864576^2 + 817777696000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1135424^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0864576^2 + 8177777696000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1135424^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0864576^2 + 81777777696000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1135424^2 \end{aligned}$$

369)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0863839^2 + 738000^2 & := & 1136161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0863839^2 + 8118000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1136161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0863839^2 + 81918000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1136161^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0863839^2 + 819918000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1136161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0863839^2 + 8199918000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1136161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0863839^2 + 81999918000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1136161^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0863839^2 + 819999918000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1136161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0863839^2 + 8199999918000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1136161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0863839^2 + 81999999918000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1136161^2 \end{aligned}$$

370)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0863100^2 + 740000^2 & := & 1136900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0863100^2 + 8140000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1136900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0863100^2 + 82140000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1136900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0863100^2 + 822140000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1136900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0863100^2 + 8222140000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1136900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0863100^2 + 82222140000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1136900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0863100^2 + 822222140000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1136900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0863100^2 + 8222222140000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1136900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0863100^2 + 82222222140000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1136900^2 \end{aligned}$$

371)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0862359^2 + 742000^2 & := & 1137641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0862359^2 + 8162000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1137641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0862359^2 + 82362000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1137641^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0862359^2 + 824362000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1137641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0862359^2 + 8244362000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1137641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0862359^2 + 82444362000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1137641^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0862359^2 + 824444362000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1137641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0862359^2 + 8244444362000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1137641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0862359^2 + 82444444362000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1137641^2 \end{aligned}$$

372)

$$\begin{aligned} &0861616^2 + 744000^2 && := 1138384^2 \\ &12\ 0861616^2 + 8184000^2 && := 12\ 1138384^2 \\ &1232\ 0861616^2 + 82584000^2 && := 1232\ 1138384^2 \\ &123432\ 0861616^2 + 826584000^2 && := 123432\ 1138384^2 \\ &12345432\ 0861616^2 + 8266584000^2 && := 12345432\ 1138384^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0861616^2 + 82666584000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1138384^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0861616^2 + 826666584000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1138384^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0861616^2 + 8266666584000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1138384^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0861616^2 + 82666666584000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1138384^2 \end{aligned}$$

373)

$$\begin{aligned} &0860871^2 + 746000^2 && := 1139129^2 \\ &12\ 0860871^2 + 8206000^2 && := 12\ 1139129^2 \\ &1232\ 0860871^2 + 82806000^2 && := 1232\ 1139129^2 \\ &123432\ 0860871^2 + 828806000^2 && := 123432\ 1139129^2 \\ &12345432\ 0860871^2 + 8288806000^2 && := 12345432\ 1139129^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0860871^2 + 82888806000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1139129^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0860871^2 + 828888806000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1139129^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0860871^2 + 8288888806000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1139129^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0860871^2 + 82888888806000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1139129^2 \end{aligned}$$

374)

$$\begin{aligned} &0860124^2 + 748000^2 && := 1139876^2 \\ &12\ 0860124^2 + 8228000^2 && := 12\ 1139876^2 \\ &1232\ 0860124^2 + 83028000^2 && := 1232\ 1139876^2 \\ &123432\ 0860124^2 + 831028000^2 && := 123432\ 1139876^2 \\ &12345432\ 0860124^2 + 8311028000^2 && := 12345432\ 1139876^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0860124^2 + 83111028000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1139876^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0860124^2 + 831111028000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1139876^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0860124^2 + 8311111028000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1139876^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0860124^2 + 83111111028000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1139876^2 \end{aligned}$$

375)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0859375^2 + 750000^2 & := & 1140625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0859375^2 + 8250000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1140625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0859375^2 + 83250000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1140625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0859375^2 + 833250000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1140625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0859375^2 + 8333250000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1140625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0859375^2 + 83333250000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1140625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0859375^2 + 833333250000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1140625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0859375^2 + 8333333250000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1140625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0859375^2 + 83333333250000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1140625^2 \end{aligned}$$

376)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0858624^2 + 752000^2 & := & 1141376^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0858624^2 + 8272000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1141376^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0858624^2 + 83472000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1141376^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0858624^2 + 835472000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1141376^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0858624^2 + 8355472000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1141376^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0858624^2 + 83555472000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1141376^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0858624^2 + 835555472000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1141376^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0858624^2 + 8355555472000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1141376^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0858624^2 + 83555555472000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1141376^2 \end{aligned}$$

377)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0857871^2 + 754000^2 & := & 1142129^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0857871^2 + 8294000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1142129^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0857871^2 + 83694000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1142129^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0857871^2 + 837694000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1142129^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0857871^2 + 8377694000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1142129^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0857871^2 + 83777694000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1142129^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0857871^2 + 837777694000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1142129^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0857871^2 + 8377777694000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1142129^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0857871^2 + 83777777694000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1142129^2 \end{aligned}$$

378)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0857116^2 + 756000^2 & := & 1142884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0857116^2 + 8316000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1142884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0857116^2 + 83916000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1142884^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0857116^2 + 839916000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1142884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0857116^2 + 8399916000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1142884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0857116^2 + 83999916000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1142884^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0857116^2 + 839999916000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1142884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0857116^2 + 8399999916000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1142884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0857116^2 + 83999999916000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1142884^2 \end{aligned}$$

379)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0856359^2 + 758000^2 & := & 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0856359^2 + 8338000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0856359^2 + 84138000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0856359^2 + 842138000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0856359^2 + 8422138000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0856359^2 + 84222138000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0856359^2 + 842222138000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0856359^2 + 8422222138000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0856359^2 + 84222222138000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1143641^2 \end{aligned}$$

380)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0855600^2 + 760000^2 & := & 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0855600^2 + 8360000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0855600^2 + 84360000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0855600^2 + 844360000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0855600^2 + 8444360000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0855600^2 + 84444360000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0855600^2 + 844444360000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0855600^2 + 8444444360000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0855600^2 + 84444444360000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1144400^2 \end{aligned}$$

381)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0854839^2 + 762000^2 & := & 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0854839^2 + 8382000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0854839^2 + 84582000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0854839^2 + 846582000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0854839^2 + 8466582000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0854839^2 + 84666582000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0854839^2 + 846666582000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0854839^2 + 8466666582000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0854839^2 + 84666666582000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1145161^2 \end{aligned}$$

382)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0854076^2 + 764000^2 & := & 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0854076^2 + 8404000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0854076^2 + 84804000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0854076^2 + 848804000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0854076^2 + 8488804000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0854076^2 + 84888804000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0854076^2 + 848888804000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0854076^2 + 8488888804000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0854076^2 + 84888888804000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1145924^2 \end{aligned}$$

383)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0853311^2 + 766000^2 & := & 1146689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0853311^2 + 8426000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1146689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0853311^2 + 85026000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1146689^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0853311^2 + 851026000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1146689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0853311^2 + 8511026000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1146689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0853311^2 + 85111026000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1146689^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0853311^2 + 851111026000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1146689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0853311^2 + 8511111026000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1146689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0853311^2 + 85111111026000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1146689^2 \end{aligned}$$

384)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0852544^2 + 768000^2 & := & 1147456^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0852544^2 + 8448000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1147456^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0852544^2 + 85248000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1147456^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0852544^2 + 853248000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1147456^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0852544^2 + 8533248000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1147456^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0852544^2 + 85333248000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1147456^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0852544^2 + 853333248000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1147456^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0852544^2 + 8533333248000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1147456^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0852544^2 + 85333333248000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1147456^2 \end{aligned}$$

385)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0851775^2 + 770000^2 & := & 1148225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0851775^2 + 8470000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1148225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0851775^2 + 85470000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1148225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0851775^2 + 855470000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1148225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0851775^2 + 8555470000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1148225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0851775^2 + 85555470000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1148225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0851775^2 + 855555470000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1148225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0851775^2 + 8555555470000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1148225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0851775^2 + 85555555470000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1148225^2 \end{aligned}$$

386)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0851004^2 + 772000^2 & := & 1148996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0851004^2 + 8492000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1148996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0851004^2 + 85692000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1148996^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0851004^2 + 857692000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1148996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0851004^2 + 8577692000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1148996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0851004^2 + 85777692000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1148996^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0851004^2 + 857777692000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1148996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0851004^2 + 8577777692000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1148996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0851004^2 + 85777777692000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1148996^2 \end{aligned}$$

387)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0850231^2 + 774000^2 & := & 1149769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0850231^2 + 8514000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1149769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0850231^2 + 85914000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1149769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0850231^2 + 859914000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1149769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0850231^2 + 8599914000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1149769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0850231^2 + 85999914000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1149769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0850231^2 + 859999914000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1149769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0850231^2 + 8599999914000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1149769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0850231^2 + 85999999914000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1149769^2 \end{aligned}$$

388)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0849456^2 + 776000^2 & := & 1150544^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0849456^2 + 8536000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1150544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0849456^2 + 86136000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1150544^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0849456^2 + 862136000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1150544^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0849456^2 + 8622136000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1150544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0849456^2 + 86222136000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1150544^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0849456^2 + 862222136000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1150544^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0849456^2 + 8622222136000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1150544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0849456^2 + 86222222136000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1150544^2 \end{aligned}$$

389)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0848679^2 + 778000^2 & := & 1151321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0848679^2 + 8558000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1151321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0848679^2 + 86358000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1151321^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0848679^2 + 864358000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1151321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0848679^2 + 8644358000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1151321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0848679^2 + 86444358000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1151321^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0848679^2 + 864444358000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1151321^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0848679^2 + 8644444358000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1151321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0848679^2 + 86444444358000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1151321^2 \end{aligned}$$

390)

$$\begin{aligned} &0847900^2 + 780000^2 &&:= 1152100^2 \\ &12\ 0847900^2 + 8580000^2 &&:= 12\ 1152100^2 \\ &1232\ 0847900^2 + 86580000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1152100^2 \\ &123432\ 0847900^2 + 866580000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1152100^2 \\ &12345432\ 0847900^2 + 8666580000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1152100^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0847900^2 + 86666580000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1152100^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0847900^2 + 866666580000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1152100^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0847900^2 + 8666666580000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1152100^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0847900^2 + 86666666580000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1152100^2 \end{aligned}$$

391)

$$\begin{aligned} &0847119^2 + 782000^2 &&:= 1152881^2 \\ &12\ 0847119^2 + 8602000^2 &&:= 12\ 1152881^2 \\ &1232\ 0847119^2 + 86802000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1152881^2 \\ &123432\ 0847119^2 + 868802000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1152881^2 \\ &12345432\ 0847119^2 + 8688802000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1152881^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0847119^2 + 86888802000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1152881^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0847119^2 + 868888802000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1152881^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0847119^2 + 8688888802000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1152881^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0847119^2 + 86888888802000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1152881^2 \end{aligned}$$

392)

$$\begin{aligned} &0846336^2 + 784000^2 &&:= 1153664^2 \\ &12\ 0846336^2 + 8624000^2 &&:= 12\ 1153664^2 \\ &1232\ 0846336^2 + 87024000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1153664^2 \\ &123432\ 0846336^2 + 871024000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1153664^2 \\ &12345432\ 0846336^2 + 8711024000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1153664^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0846336^2 + 87111024000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1153664^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0846336^2 + 871111024000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1153664^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0846336^2 + 8711111024000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1153664^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0846336^2 + 87111111024000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1153664^2 \end{aligned}$$

393)

$$\begin{aligned} &0845551^2 + 786000^2 &:=& 1154449^2 \\ &12\ 0845551^2 + 8646000^2 &:=& 12\ 1154449^2 \\ &1232\ 0845551^2 + 87246000^2 &:=& 1232\ 1154449^2 \\ &123432\ 0845551^2 + 873246000^2 &:=& 123432\ 1154449^2 \\ &12345432\ 0845551^2 + 8733246000^2 &:=& 12345432\ 1154449^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0845551^2 + 87333246000^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 1154449^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0845551^2 + 873333246000^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 1154449^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0845551^2 + 8733333246000^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 1154449^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0845551^2 + 87333333246000^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 1154449^2 \end{aligned}$$

394)

$$\begin{aligned} &0844764^2 + 788000^2 &:=& 1155236^2 \\ &12\ 0844764^2 + 8668000^2 &:=& 12\ 1155236^2 \\ &1232\ 0844764^2 + 87468000^2 &:=& 1232\ 1155236^2 \\ &123432\ 0844764^2 + 875468000^2 &:=& 123432\ 1155236^2 \\ &12345432\ 0844764^2 + 8755468000^2 &:=& 12345432\ 1155236^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0844764^2 + 87555468000^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 1155236^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0844764^2 + 875555468000^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 1155236^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0844764^2 + 8755555468000^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 1155236^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0844764^2 + 87555555468000^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 1155236^2 \end{aligned}$$

395)

$$\begin{aligned} &0843975^2 + 790000^2 &:=& 1156025^2 \\ &12\ 0843975^2 + 8690000^2 &:=& 12\ 1156025^2 \\ &1232\ 0843975^2 + 87690000^2 &:=& 1232\ 1156025^2 \\ &123432\ 0843975^2 + 877690000^2 &:=& 123432\ 1156025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0843975^2 + 8777690000^2 &:=& 12345432\ 1156025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0843975^2 + 87777690000^2 &:=& 1234565432\ 1156025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0843975^2 + 877777690000^2 &:=& 123456765432\ 1156025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0843975^2 + 8777777690000^2 &:=& 12345678765432\ 1156025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0843975^2 + 87777777690000^2 &:=& 1234567898765432\ 1156025^2 \end{aligned}$$

396)

$$\begin{aligned} &0843184^2 + 792000^2 && := 1156816^2 \\ &12\ 0843184^2 + 8712000^2 && := 12\ 1156816^2 \\ &1232\ 0843184^2 + 87912000^2 && := 1232\ 1156816^2 \\ &123432\ 0843184^2 + 879912000^2 && := 123432\ 1156816^2 \\ &12345432\ 0843184^2 + 8799912000^2 && := 12345432\ 1156816^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0843184^2 + 87999912000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1156816^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0843184^2 + 879999912000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1156816^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0843184^2 + 8799999912000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1156816^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0843184^2 + 87999999912000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1156816^2 \end{aligned}$$

397)

$$\begin{aligned} &0842391^2 + 794000^2 && := 1157609^2 \\ &12\ 0842391^2 + 8734000^2 && := 12\ 1157609^2 \\ &1232\ 0842391^2 + 88134000^2 && := 1232\ 1157609^2 \\ &123432\ 0842391^2 + 882134000^2 && := 123432\ 1157609^2 \\ &12345432\ 0842391^2 + 8822134000^2 && := 12345432\ 1157609^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0842391^2 + 88222134000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1157609^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0842391^2 + 882222134000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1157609^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0842391^2 + 8822222134000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1157609^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0842391^2 + 88222222134000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1157609^2 \end{aligned}$$

398)

$$\begin{aligned} &0841596^2 + 796000^2 && := 1158404^2 \\ &12\ 0841596^2 + 8756000^2 && := 12\ 1158404^2 \\ &1232\ 0841596^2 + 88356000^2 && := 1232\ 1158404^2 \\ &123432\ 0841596^2 + 884356000^2 && := 123432\ 1158404^2 \\ &12345432\ 0841596^2 + 8844356000^2 && := 12345432\ 1158404^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0841596^2 + 88444356000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1158404^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0841596^2 + 884444356000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1158404^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0841596^2 + 8844444356000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1158404^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0841596^2 + 88444444356000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1158404^2 \end{aligned}$$

399)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0840799^2 + 798000^2 & := & 1159201^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0840799^2 + 8778000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1159201^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0840799^2 + 88578000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1159201^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0840799^2 + 886578000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1159201^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0840799^2 + 8866578000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1159201^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0840799^2 + 88666578000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1159201^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0840799^2 + 886666578000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1159201^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0840799^2 + 8866666578000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1159201^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0840799^2 + 88666666578000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1159201^2 \end{aligned}$$

400)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0840000^2 + 800000^2 & := & 1160000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0840000^2 + 8800000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1160000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0840000^2 + 88800000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1160000^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0840000^2 + 888800000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1160000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0840000^2 + 8888800000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1160000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0840000^2 + 88888800000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1160000^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0840000^2 + 888888800000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1160000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0840000^2 + 8888888800000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1160000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0840000^2 + 88888888800000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1160000^2 \end{aligned}$$

401)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0839199^2 + 802000^2 & := & 1160801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0839199^2 + 8822000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1160801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0839199^2 + 89022000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1160801^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0839199^2 + 891022000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1160801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0839199^2 + 8911022000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1160801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0839199^2 + 89111022000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1160801^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0839199^2 + 891111022000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1160801^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0839199^2 + 8911111022000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1160801^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0839199^2 + 89111111022000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1160801^2 \end{aligned}$$

402)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0838396^2 + 804000^2 & := & 1161604^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0838396^2 + 8844000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1161604^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0838396^2 + 89244000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1161604^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0838396^2 + 893244000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1161604^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0838396^2 + 8933244000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1161604^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0838396^2 + 89333244000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1161604^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0838396^2 + 893333244000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1161604^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0838396^2 + 8933333244000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1161604^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0838396^2 + 89333333244000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1161604^2 \end{aligned}$$

403)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0837591^2 + 806000^2 & := & 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0837591^2 + 8866000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0837591^2 + 89466000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0837591^2 + 895466000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0837591^2 + 8955466000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0837591^2 + 89555466000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0837591^2 + 895555466000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0837591^2 + 8955555466000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0837591^2 + 89555555466000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1162409^2 \end{aligned}$$

404)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0836784^2 + 808000^2 & := & 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0836784^2 + 8888000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0836784^2 + 89688000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0836784^2 + 897688000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0836784^2 + 8977688000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0836784^2 + 89777688000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0836784^2 + 897777688000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0836784^2 + 8977777688000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0836784^2 + 89777777688000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1163216^2 \end{aligned}$$

405)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0835975^2 + 810000^2 & := & 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0835975^2 + 8910000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0835975^2 + 89910000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0835975^2 + 899910000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0835975^2 + 8999910000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0835975^2 + 89999910000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0835975^2 + 899999910000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0835975^2 + 8999999910000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0835975^2 + 89999999910000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1164025^2 \end{aligned}$$

406)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0835164^2 + 812000^2 & := & 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0835164^2 + 8932000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0835164^2 + 90132000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0835164^2 + 902132000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0835164^2 + 9022132000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0835164^2 + 90222132000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0835164^2 + 902222132000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0835164^2 + 9022222132000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0835164^2 + 90222222132000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1164836^2 \end{aligned}$$

407)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0834351^2 + 814000^2 & := & 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0834351^2 + 8954000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0834351^2 + 90354000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0834351^2 + 904354000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0834351^2 + 9044354000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0834351^2 + 90444354000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0834351^2 + 904444354000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0834351^2 + 9044444354000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0834351^2 + 90444444354000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1165649^2 \end{aligned}$$

408)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0833536^2 + 816000^2 & := & 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0833536^2 + 8976000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0833536^2 + 90576000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0833536^2 + 906576000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0833536^2 + 9066576000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0833536^2 + 90666576000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0833536^2 + 906666576000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0833536^2 + 9066666576000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0833536^2 + 90666666576000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1166464^2 \end{aligned}$$

409)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0832719^2 + 818000^2 & := & 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0832719^2 + 8998000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0832719^2 + 90798000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0832719^2 + 908798000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0832719^2 + 9088798000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0832719^2 + 90888798000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0832719^2 + 908888798000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0832719^2 + 9088888798000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0832719^2 + 90888888798000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1167281^2 \end{aligned}$$

410)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0831900^2 + 820000^2 & := & 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0831900^2 + 9020000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0831900^2 + 91020000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0831900^2 + 911020000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0831900^2 + 9111020000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0831900^2 + 91111020000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0831900^2 + 911111020000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0831900^2 + 9111111020000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0831900^2 + 91111111020000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1168100^2 \end{aligned}$$

411)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0831079^2 + 822000^2 & := & 1168921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0831079^2 + 9042000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1168921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0831079^2 + 91242000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1168921^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0831079^2 + 913242000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1168921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0831079^2 + 9133242000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1168921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0831079^2 + 91333242000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1168921^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0831079^2 + 913333242000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1168921^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0831079^2 + 9133333242000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1168921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0831079^2 + 91333333242000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1168921^2 \end{aligned}$$

412)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0830256^2 + 824000^2 & := & 1169744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0830256^2 + 9064000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1169744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0830256^2 + 91464000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1169744^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0830256^2 + 915464000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1169744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0830256^2 + 9155464000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1169744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0830256^2 + 91555464000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1169744^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0830256^2 + 915555464000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1169744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0830256^2 + 9155555464000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1169744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0830256^2 + 91555555464000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1169744^2 \end{aligned}$$

413)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0829431^2 + 826000^2 & := & 1170569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0829431^2 + 9086000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1170569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0829431^2 + 91686000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1170569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0829431^2 + 917686000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1170569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0829431^2 + 9177686000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1170569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0829431^2 + 91777686000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1170569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0829431^2 + 917777686000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1170569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0829431^2 + 9177777686000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1170569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0829431^2 + 91777777686000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1170569^2 \end{aligned}$$

414)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0828604^2 + 828000^2 & := & 1171396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0828604^2 + 9108000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1171396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0828604^2 + 91908000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1171396^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0828604^2 + 919908000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1171396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0828604^2 + 9199908000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1171396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0828604^2 + 91999908000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1171396^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0828604^2 + 919999908000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1171396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0828604^2 + 9199999908000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1171396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0828604^2 + 91999999908000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1171396^2 \end{aligned}$$

415)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0827775^2 + 830000^2 & := & 1172225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0827775^2 + 9130000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1172225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0827775^2 + 92130000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1172225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0827775^2 + 922130000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1172225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0827775^2 + 9222130000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1172225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0827775^2 + 92222130000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1172225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0827775^2 + 922222130000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1172225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0827775^2 + 9222222130000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1172225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0827775^2 + 92222222130000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1172225^2 \end{aligned}$$

416)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0826944^2 + 832000^2 & := & 1173056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0826944^2 + 9152000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1173056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0826944^2 + 92352000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1173056^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0826944^2 + 924352000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1173056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0826944^2 + 9244352000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1173056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0826944^2 + 92444352000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1173056^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0826944^2 + 924444352000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1173056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0826944^2 + 9244444352000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1173056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0826944^2 + 92444444352000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1173056^2 \end{aligned}$$

417)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0826111^2 + 834000^2 & := & 1173889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0826111^2 + 9174000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1173889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0826111^2 + 92574000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1173889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0826111^2 + 926574000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1173889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0826111^2 + 9266574000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1173889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0826111^2 + 92666574000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1173889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0826111^2 + 926666574000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1173889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0826111^2 + 9266666574000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1173889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0826111^2 + 92666666574000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1173889^2 \end{aligned}$$

418)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0825276^2 + 836000^2 & := & 1174724^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0825276^2 + 9196000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1174724^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0825276^2 + 92796000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1174724^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0825276^2 + 928796000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1174724^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0825276^2 + 9288796000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1174724^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0825276^2 + 92888796000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1174724^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0825276^2 + 928888796000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1174724^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0825276^2 + 9288888796000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1174724^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0825276^2 + 92888888796000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1174724^2 \end{aligned}$$

419)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0824439^2 + 838000^2 & := & 1175561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0824439^2 + 9218000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1175561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0824439^2 + 93018000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1175561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0824439^2 + 931018000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1175561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0824439^2 + 9311018000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1175561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0824439^2 + 93111018000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1175561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0824439^2 + 931111018000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1175561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0824439^2 + 9311111018000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1175561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0824439^2 + 93111111018000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1175561^2 \end{aligned}$$

420)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0823600^2 + 840000^2 & := & 1176400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0823600^2 + 9240000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1176400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0823600^2 + 93240000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1176400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0823600^2 + 933240000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1176400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0823600^2 + 9333240000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1176400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0823600^2 + 93333240000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1176400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0823600^2 + 933333240000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1176400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0823600^2 + 9333333240000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1176400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0823600^2 + 93333333240000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1176400^2 \end{aligned}$$

421)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0822759^2 + 842000^2 & := & 1177241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0822759^2 + 9262000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1177241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0822759^2 + 93462000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1177241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0822759^2 + 935462000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1177241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0822759^2 + 9355462000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1177241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0822759^2 + 93555462000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1177241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0822759^2 + 935555462000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1177241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0822759^2 + 9355555462000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1177241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0822759^2 + 93555555462000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1177241^2 \end{aligned}$$

422)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0821916^2 + 844000^2 & := & 1178084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0821916^2 + 9284000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1178084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0821916^2 + 93684000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1178084^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0821916^2 + 937684000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1178084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0821916^2 + 9377684000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1178084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0821916^2 + 93777684000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1178084^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0821916^2 + 937777684000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1178084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0821916^2 + 9377777684000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1178084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0821916^2 + 93777777684000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1178084^2 \end{aligned}$$

423)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0821071^2 + 846000^2 & := & 1178929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0821071^2 + 9306000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1178929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0821071^2 + 93906000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1178929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0821071^2 + 939906000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1178929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0821071^2 + 9399906000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1178929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0821071^2 + 93999906000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1178929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0821071^2 + 939999906000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1178929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0821071^2 + 9399999906000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1178929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0821071^2 + 93999999906000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1178929^2 \end{aligned}$$

424)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0820224^2 + 848000^2 & := & 1179776^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0820224^2 + 9328000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1179776^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0820224^2 + 94128000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1179776^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0820224^2 + 942128000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1179776^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0820224^2 + 9422128000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1179776^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0820224^2 + 94222128000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1179776^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0820224^2 + 942222128000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1179776^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0820224^2 + 9422222128000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1179776^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0820224^2 + 94222222128000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1179776^2 \end{aligned}$$

425)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0819375^2 + 850000^2 & := & 1180625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0819375^2 + 9350000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1180625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0819375^2 + 94350000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1180625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0819375^2 + 944350000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1180625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0819375^2 + 9444350000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1180625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0819375^2 + 94444350000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1180625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0819375^2 + 944444350000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1180625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0819375^2 + 9444444350000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1180625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0819375^2 + 94444444350000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1180625^2 \end{aligned}$$

426)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0818524^2 + 852000^2 & := & 1181476^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0818524^2 + 9372000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1181476^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0818524^2 + 94572000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1181476^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0818524^2 + 946572000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1181476^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0818524^2 + 9466572000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1181476^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0818524^2 + 94666572000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1181476^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0818524^2 + 946666572000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1181476^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0818524^2 + 9466666572000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1181476^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0818524^2 + 94666666572000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1181476^2 \end{aligned}$$

427)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0817671^2 + 854000^2 & := & 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0817671^2 + 9394000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0817671^2 + 94794000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0817671^2 + 948794000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0817671^2 + 9488794000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0817671^2 + 94888794000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0817671^2 + 948888794000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0817671^2 + 9488888794000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0817671^2 + 94888888794000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1182329^2 \end{aligned}$$

428)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0816816^2 + 856000^2 & := & 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0816816^2 + 9416000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0816816^2 + 95016000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0816816^2 + 951016000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0816816^2 + 9511016000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0816816^2 + 95111016000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0816816^2 + 951111016000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0816816^2 + 9511111016000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0816816^2 + 95111111016000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1183184^2 \end{aligned}$$

429)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0815959^2 + 858000^2 & := & 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0815959^2 + 9438000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0815959^2 + 95238000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0815959^2 + 953238000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0815959^2 + 9533238000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0815959^2 + 95333238000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0815959^2 + 953333238000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0815959^2 + 9533333238000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0815959^2 + 95333333238000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1184041^2 \end{aligned}$$

430)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0815100^2 + 860000^2 & := & 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0815100^2 + 9460000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0815100^2 + 95460000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0815100^2 + 955460000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0815100^2 + 9555460000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0815100^2 + 95555460000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0815100^2 + 955555460000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0815100^2 + 9555555460000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0815100^2 + 95555555460000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1184900^2 \end{aligned}$$

431)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0814239^2 + 862000^2 & := & 1185761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0814239^2 + 9482000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1185761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0814239^2 + 95682000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1185761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0814239^2 + 957682000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1185761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0814239^2 + 9577682000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1185761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0814239^2 + 95777682000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1185761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0814239^2 + 957777682000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1185761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0814239^2 + 9577777682000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1185761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0814239^2 + 95777777682000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1185761^2 \end{aligned}$$

432)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0813376^2 + 864000^2 & := & 1186624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0813376^2 + 9504000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1186624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0813376^2 + 95904000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1186624^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0813376^2 + 959904000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1186624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0813376^2 + 9599904000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1186624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0813376^2 + 95999904000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1186624^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0813376^2 + 959999904000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1186624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0813376^2 + 9599999904000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1186624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0813376^2 + 95999999904000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1186624^2 \end{aligned}$$

433)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0812511^2 + 866000^2 & := & 1187489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0812511^2 + 9526000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1187489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0812511^2 + 96126000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1187489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0812511^2 + 962126000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1187489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0812511^2 + 9622126000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1187489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0812511^2 + 96222126000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1187489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0812511^2 + 962222126000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1187489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0812511^2 + 9622222126000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1187489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0812511^2 + 96222222126000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1187489^2 \end{aligned}$$

434)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0811644^2 + 868000^2 & := & 1188356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0811644^2 + 9548000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1188356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0811644^2 + 96348000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1188356^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0811644^2 + 964348000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1188356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0811644^2 + 9644348000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1188356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0811644^2 + 96444348000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1188356^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0811644^2 + 964444348000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1188356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0811644^2 + 9644444348000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1188356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0811644^2 + 96444444348000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1188356^2 \end{aligned}$$

435)

$$\begin{aligned} &0810775^2 + 870000^2 && := 1189225^2 \\ &12\ 0810775^2 + 9570000^2 && := 12\ 1189225^2 \\ &1232\ 0810775^2 + 96570000^2 && := 1232\ 1189225^2 \\ &123432\ 0810775^2 + 966570000^2 && := 123432\ 1189225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0810775^2 + 9666570000^2 && := 12345432\ 1189225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0810775^2 + 96666570000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1189225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0810775^2 + 966666570000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1189225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0810775^2 + 9666666570000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1189225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0810775^2 + 96666666570000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1189225^2 \end{aligned}$$

436)

$$\begin{aligned} &0809904^2 + 872000^2 && := 1190096^2 \\ &12\ 0809904^2 + 9592000^2 && := 12\ 1190096^2 \\ &1232\ 0809904^2 + 96792000^2 && := 1232\ 1190096^2 \\ &123432\ 0809904^2 + 968792000^2 && := 123432\ 1190096^2 \\ &12345432\ 0809904^2 + 9688792000^2 && := 12345432\ 1190096^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0809904^2 + 96888792000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1190096^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0809904^2 + 968888792000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1190096^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0809904^2 + 9688888792000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1190096^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0809904^2 + 96888888792000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1190096^2 \end{aligned}$$

437)

$$\begin{aligned} &0809031^2 + 874000^2 && := 1190969^2 \\ &12\ 0809031^2 + 9614000^2 && := 12\ 1190969^2 \\ &1232\ 0809031^2 + 97014000^2 && := 1232\ 1190969^2 \\ &123432\ 0809031^2 + 971014000^2 && := 123432\ 1190969^2 \\ &12345432\ 0809031^2 + 9711014000^2 && := 12345432\ 1190969^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0809031^2 + 97111014000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1190969^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0809031^2 + 971111014000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1190969^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0809031^2 + 9711111014000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1190969^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0809031^2 + 97111111014000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1190969^2 \end{aligned}$$

438)

$$\begin{aligned} &0808156^2 + 876000^2 && := 1191844^2 \\ &12\ 0808156^2 + 9636000^2 && := 12\ 1191844^2 \\ &1232\ 0808156^2 + 97236000^2 && := 1232\ 1191844^2 \\ &123432\ 0808156^2 + 973236000^2 && := 123432\ 1191844^2 \\ &12345432\ 0808156^2 + 9733236000^2 && := 12345432\ 1191844^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0808156^2 + 97333236000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1191844^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0808156^2 + 973333236000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1191844^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0808156^2 + 9733333236000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1191844^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0808156^2 + 97333333236000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1191844^2 \end{aligned}$$

439)

$$\begin{aligned} &0807279^2 + 878000^2 && := 1192721^2 \\ &12\ 0807279^2 + 9658000^2 && := 12\ 1192721^2 \\ &1232\ 0807279^2 + 97458000^2 && := 1232\ 1192721^2 \\ &123432\ 0807279^2 + 975458000^2 && := 123432\ 1192721^2 \\ &12345432\ 0807279^2 + 9755458000^2 && := 12345432\ 1192721^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0807279^2 + 97555458000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1192721^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0807279^2 + 975555458000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1192721^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0807279^2 + 9755555458000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1192721^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0807279^2 + 97555555458000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1192721^2 \end{aligned}$$

440)

$$\begin{aligned} &0806400^2 + 880000^2 && := 1193600^2 \\ &12\ 0806400^2 + 9680000^2 && := 12\ 1193600^2 \\ &1232\ 0806400^2 + 97680000^2 && := 1232\ 1193600^2 \\ &123432\ 0806400^2 + 977680000^2 && := 123432\ 1193600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0806400^2 + 9777680000^2 && := 12345432\ 1193600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0806400^2 + 97777680000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1193600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0806400^2 + 977777680000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1193600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0806400^2 + 9777777680000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1193600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0806400^2 + 97777777680000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1193600^2 \end{aligned}$$

441)

$$\begin{aligned} &0805519^2 + 882000^2 && := 1194481^2 \\ &12\ 0805519^2 + 9702000^2 && := 12\ 1194481^2 \\ &1232\ 0805519^2 + 97902000^2 && := 1232\ 1194481^2 \\ &123432\ 0805519^2 + 979902000^2 && := 123432\ 1194481^2 \\ &12345432\ 0805519^2 + 9799902000^2 && := 12345432\ 1194481^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0805519^2 + 97999902000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1194481^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0805519^2 + 979999902000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1194481^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0805519^2 + 9799999902000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1194481^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0805519^2 + 97999999902000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1194481^2 \end{aligned}$$

442)

$$\begin{aligned} &0804636^2 + 884000^2 && := 1195364^2 \\ &12\ 0804636^2 + 9724000^2 && := 12\ 1195364^2 \\ &1232\ 0804636^2 + 98124000^2 && := 1232\ 1195364^2 \\ &123432\ 0804636^2 + 982124000^2 && := 123432\ 1195364^2 \\ &12345432\ 0804636^2 + 9822124000^2 && := 12345432\ 1195364^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0804636^2 + 98222124000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1195364^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0804636^2 + 982222124000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1195364^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0804636^2 + 9822222124000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1195364^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0804636^2 + 98222222124000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1195364^2 \end{aligned}$$

443)

$$\begin{aligned} &0803751^2 + 886000^2 && := 1196249^2 \\ &12\ 0803751^2 + 9746000^2 && := 12\ 1196249^2 \\ &1232\ 0803751^2 + 98346000^2 && := 1232\ 1196249^2 \\ &123432\ 0803751^2 + 984346000^2 && := 123432\ 1196249^2 \\ &12345432\ 0803751^2 + 9844346000^2 && := 12345432\ 1196249^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0803751^2 + 98444346000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1196249^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0803751^2 + 984444346000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1196249^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0803751^2 + 9844444346000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1196249^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0803751^2 + 98444444346000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1196249^2 \end{aligned}$$

444)

$$\begin{aligned} &0802864^2 + 888000^2 && := 1197136^2 \\ &12\ 0802864^2 + 9768000^2 && := 12\ 1197136^2 \\ &1232\ 0802864^2 + 98568000^2 && := 1232\ 1197136^2 \\ &123432\ 0802864^2 + 986568000^2 && := 123432\ 1197136^2 \\ &12345432\ 0802864^2 + 9866568000^2 && := 12345432\ 1197136^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0802864^2 + 98666568000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1197136^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0802864^2 + 986666568000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1197136^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0802864^2 + 9866666568000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1197136^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0802864^2 + 98666666568000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1197136^2 \end{aligned}$$

445)

$$\begin{aligned} &0801975^2 + 890000^2 && := 1198025^2 \\ &12\ 0801975^2 + 9790000^2 && := 12\ 1198025^2 \\ &1232\ 0801975^2 + 98790000^2 && := 1232\ 1198025^2 \\ &123432\ 0801975^2 + 988790000^2 && := 123432\ 1198025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0801975^2 + 9888790000^2 && := 12345432\ 1198025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0801975^2 + 98888790000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1198025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0801975^2 + 988888790000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1198025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0801975^2 + 9888888790000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1198025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0801975^2 + 98888888790000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1198025^2 \end{aligned}$$

446)

$$\begin{aligned} &0801084^2 + 892000^2 && := 1198916^2 \\ &12\ 0801084^2 + 9812000^2 && := 12\ 1198916^2 \\ &1232\ 0801084^2 + 99012000^2 && := 1232\ 1198916^2 \\ &123432\ 0801084^2 + 991012000^2 && := 123432\ 1198916^2 \\ &12345432\ 0801084^2 + 9911012000^2 && := 12345432\ 1198916^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0801084^2 + 99111012000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1198916^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0801084^2 + 991111012000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1198916^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0801084^2 + 9911111012000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1198916^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0801084^2 + 99111111012000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1198916^2 \end{aligned}$$

447)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0800191^2 + 894000^2 & := & 1199809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0800191^2 + 9834000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1199809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0800191^2 + 99234000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1199809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0800191^2 + 993234000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1199809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0800191^2 + 9933234000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1199809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0800191^2 + 99333234000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1199809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0800191^2 + 993333234000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1199809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0800191^2 + 9933333234000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1199809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0800191^2 + 99333333234000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1199809^2 \end{aligned}$$

448)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0799296^2 + 896000^2 & := & 1200704^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0799296^2 + 9856000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1200704^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0799296^2 + 99456000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1200704^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0799296^2 + 995456000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1200704^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0799296^2 + 9955456000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1200704^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0799296^2 + 99555456000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1200704^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0799296^2 + 995555456000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1200704^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0799296^2 + 9955555456000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1200704^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0799296^2 + 99555555456000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1200704^2 \end{aligned}$$

449)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0798399^2 + 898000^2 & := & 1201601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0798399^2 + 9878000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1201601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0798399^2 + 99678000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1201601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0798399^2 + 997678000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1201601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0798399^2 + 9977678000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1201601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0798399^2 + 99777678000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1201601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0798399^2 + 997777678000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1201601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0798399^2 + 9977777678000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1201601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0798399^2 + 99777777678000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1201601^2 \end{aligned}$$

450)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0797500^2 + 900000^2 & := & 1202500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0797500^2 + 9900000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1202500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0797500^2 + 99900000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1202500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0797500^2 + 999900000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1202500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0797500^2 + 9999900000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1202500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0797500^2 + 99999900000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1202500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0797500^2 + 999999900000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1202500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0797500^2 + 9999999900000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1202500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0797500^2 + 99999999900000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1202500^2 \end{aligned}$$

451)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0796599^2 + 902000^2 & := & 1203401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0796599^2 + 9922000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1203401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0796599^2 + 100122000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1203401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0796599^2 + 1002122000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1203401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0796599^2 + 10022122000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1203401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0796599^2 + 100222122000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1203401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0796599^2 + 1002222122000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1203401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0796599^2 + 10022222122000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1203401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0796599^2 + 100222222122000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1203401^2 \end{aligned}$$

452)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0795696^2 + 904000^2 & := & 1204304^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0795696^2 + 9944000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1204304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0795696^2 + 100344000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1204304^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0795696^2 + 1004344000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1204304^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0795696^2 + 10044344000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1204304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0795696^2 + 100444344000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1204304^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0795696^2 + 1004444344000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1204304^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0795696^2 + 10044444344000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1204304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0795696^2 + 100444444344000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1204304^2 \end{aligned}$$

453)

$$\begin{aligned} &0794791^2 + 906000^2 && := 1205209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0794791^2 + 9966000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1205209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0794791^2 + 100566000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1205209^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0794791^2 + 1006566000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1205209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0794791^2 + 10066566000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1205209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0794791^2 + 100666566000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1205209^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0794791^2 + 1006666566000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1205209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0794791^2 + 10066666566000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1205209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0794791^2 + 100666666566000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1205209^2 \end{aligned}$$

454)

$$\begin{aligned} &0793884^2 + 908000^2 && := 1206116^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0793884^2 + 9988000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1206116^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0793884^2 + 100788000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1206116^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0793884^2 + 1008788000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1206116^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0793884^2 + 10088788000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1206116^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0793884^2 + 100888788000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1206116^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0793884^2 + 1008888788000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1206116^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0793884^2 + 10088888788000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1206116^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0793884^2 + 100888888788000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1206116^2 \end{aligned}$$

455)

$$\begin{aligned} &0792975^2 + 910000^2 && := 1207025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0792975^2 + 10010000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1207025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0792975^2 + 101010000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1207025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0792975^2 + 1011010000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1207025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0792975^2 + 10111010000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1207025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0792975^2 + 101111010000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1207025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0792975^2 + 1011111010000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1207025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0792975^2 + 10111111010000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1207025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0792975^2 + 101111111010000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1207025^2 \end{aligned}$$

456)

$$\begin{aligned} &0792064^2 + 912000^2 && := 1207936^2 \\ &12\ 0792064^2 + 10032000^2 && := 12\ 1207936^2 \\ &1232\ 0792064^2 + 101232000^2 && := 1232\ 1207936^2 \\ &123432\ 0792064^2 + 1013232000^2 && := 123432\ 1207936^2 \\ &12345432\ 0792064^2 + 10133232000^2 && := 12345432\ 1207936^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0792064^2 + 101333232000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1207936^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0792064^2 + 1013333232000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1207936^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0792064^2 + 10133333232000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1207936^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0792064^2 + 101333333232000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1207936^2 \end{aligned}$$

457)

$$\begin{aligned} &0791151^2 + 914000^2 && := 1208849^2 \\ &12\ 0791151^2 + 10054000^2 && := 12\ 1208849^2 \\ &1232\ 0791151^2 + 101454000^2 && := 1232\ 1208849^2 \\ &123432\ 0791151^2 + 1015454000^2 && := 123432\ 1208849^2 \\ &12345432\ 0791151^2 + 10155454000^2 && := 12345432\ 1208849^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0791151^2 + 101555454000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1208849^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0791151^2 + 1015555454000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1208849^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0791151^2 + 10155555454000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1208849^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0791151^2 + 101555555454000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1208849^2 \end{aligned}$$

458)

$$\begin{aligned} &0790236^2 + 916000^2 && := 1209764^2 \\ &12\ 0790236^2 + 10076000^2 && := 12\ 1209764^2 \\ &1232\ 0790236^2 + 101676000^2 && := 1232\ 1209764^2 \\ &123432\ 0790236^2 + 1017676000^2 && := 123432\ 1209764^2 \\ &12345432\ 0790236^2 + 10177676000^2 && := 12345432\ 1209764^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0790236^2 + 101777676000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1209764^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0790236^2 + 1017777676000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1209764^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0790236^2 + 10177777676000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1209764^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0790236^2 + 101777777676000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1209764^2 \end{aligned}$$

459)

$$\begin{aligned} &0789319^2 + 918000^2 && := 1210681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0789319^2 + 10098000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1210681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0789319^2 + 101898000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1210681^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0789319^2 + 1019898000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1210681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0789319^2 + 10199898000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1210681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0789319^2 + 101999898000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1210681^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0789319^2 + 1019999898000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1210681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0789319^2 + 10199999898000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1210681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0789319^2 + 101999999898000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1210681^2 \end{aligned}$$

460)

$$\begin{aligned} &0788400^2 + 920000^2 && := 1211600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0788400^2 + 10120000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1211600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0788400^2 + 102120000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1211600^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0788400^2 + 1022120000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1211600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0788400^2 + 10222120000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1211600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0788400^2 + 102222120000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1211600^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0788400^2 + 1022222120000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1211600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0788400^2 + 10222222120000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1211600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0788400^2 + 102222222120000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1211600^2 \end{aligned}$$

461)

$$\begin{aligned} &0787479^2 + 922000^2 && := 1212521^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0787479^2 + 10142000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1212521^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0787479^2 + 102342000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1212521^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0787479^2 + 1024342000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1212521^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0787479^2 + 10244342000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1212521^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0787479^2 + 102444342000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1212521^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0787479^2 + 1024444342000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1212521^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0787479^2 + 10244444342000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1212521^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0787479^2 + 102444444342000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1212521^2 \end{aligned}$$

462)

$$\begin{aligned} &0786556^2 + 924000^2 && := 1213444^2 \\ &12\ 0786556^2 + 10164000^2 && := 12\ 1213444^2 \\ &1232\ 0786556^2 + 102564000^2 && := 1232\ 1213444^2 \\ &123432\ 0786556^2 + 1026564000^2 && := 123432\ 1213444^2 \\ &12345432\ 0786556^2 + 10266564000^2 && := 12345432\ 1213444^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0786556^2 + 102666564000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1213444^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0786556^2 + 1026666564000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1213444^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0786556^2 + 10266666564000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1213444^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0786556^2 + 102666666564000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1213444^2 \end{aligned}$$

463)

$$\begin{aligned} &0785631^2 + 926000^2 && := 1214369^2 \\ &12\ 0785631^2 + 10186000^2 && := 12\ 1214369^2 \\ &1232\ 0785631^2 + 102786000^2 && := 1232\ 1214369^2 \\ &123432\ 0785631^2 + 1028786000^2 && := 123432\ 1214369^2 \\ &12345432\ 0785631^2 + 10288786000^2 && := 12345432\ 1214369^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0785631^2 + 102888786000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1214369^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0785631^2 + 1028888786000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1214369^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0785631^2 + 10288888786000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1214369^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0785631^2 + 102888888786000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1214369^2 \end{aligned}$$

464)

$$\begin{aligned} &0784704^2 + 928000^2 && := 1215296^2 \\ &12\ 0784704^2 + 10208000^2 && := 12\ 1215296^2 \\ &1232\ 0784704^2 + 103008000^2 && := 1232\ 1215296^2 \\ &123432\ 0784704^2 + 1031008000^2 && := 123432\ 1215296^2 \\ &12345432\ 0784704^2 + 10311008000^2 && := 12345432\ 1215296^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0784704^2 + 103111008000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1215296^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0784704^2 + 1031111008000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1215296^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0784704^2 + 10311111008000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1215296^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0784704^2 + 103111111008000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1215296^2 \end{aligned}$$

465)

$$\begin{aligned} &0783775^2 + 930000^2 && := 1216225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0783775^2 + 10230000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1216225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0783775^2 + 103230000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1216225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0783775^2 + 1033230000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1216225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0783775^2 + 10333230000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1216225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0783775^2 + 103333230000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1216225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0783775^2 + 1033333230000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1216225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0783775^2 + 10333333230000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1216225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0783775^2 + 103333333230000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1216225^2 \end{aligned}$$

466)

$$\begin{aligned} &0782844^2 + 932000^2 && := 1217156^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0782844^2 + 10252000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1217156^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0782844^2 + 103452000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1217156^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0782844^2 + 1035452000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1217156^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0782844^2 + 10355452000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1217156^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0782844^2 + 103555452000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1217156^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0782844^2 + 1035555452000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1217156^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0782844^2 + 10355555452000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1217156^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0782844^2 + 103555555452000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1217156^2 \end{aligned}$$

467)

$$\begin{aligned} &0781911^2 + 934000^2 && := 1218089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0781911^2 + 10274000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1218089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0781911^2 + 103674000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1218089^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0781911^2 + 1037674000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1218089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0781911^2 + 10377674000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1218089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0781911^2 + 103777674000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1218089^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0781911^2 + 1037777674000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1218089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0781911^2 + 10377777674000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1218089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0781911^2 + 103777777674000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1218089^2 \end{aligned}$$

468)

$$\begin{aligned} &0780976^2 + 936000^2 && := 1219024^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0780976^2 + 10296000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1219024^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0780976^2 + 103896000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1219024^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0780976^2 + 1039896000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1219024^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0780976^2 + 10399896000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1219024^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0780976^2 + 103999896000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1219024^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0780976^2 + 1039999896000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1219024^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0780976^2 + 10399999896000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1219024^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0780976^2 + 103999999896000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1219024^2 \end{aligned}$$

469)

$$\begin{aligned} &0780039^2 + 938000^2 && := 1219961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0780039^2 + 10318000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1219961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0780039^2 + 104118000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1219961^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0780039^2 + 1042118000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1219961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0780039^2 + 10422118000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1219961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0780039^2 + 104222118000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1219961^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0780039^2 + 1042222118000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1219961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0780039^2 + 10422222118000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1219961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0780039^2 + 104222222118000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1219961^2 \end{aligned}$$

470)

$$\begin{aligned} &0779100^2 + 940000^2 && := 1220900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0779100^2 + 10340000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1220900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0779100^2 + 104340000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1220900^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0779100^2 + 1044340000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1220900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0779100^2 + 10444340000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1220900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0779100^2 + 104444340000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1220900^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0779100^2 + 1044444340000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1220900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0779100^2 + 10444444340000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1220900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0779100^2 + 104444444340000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1220900^2 \end{aligned}$$

471)

$$\begin{aligned} 0778159^2 + 942000^2 &:= 1221841^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 0778159^2 + 10362000^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 1221841^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 0778159^2 + 104562000^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 1221841^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 0778159^2 + 1046562000^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 1221841^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 0778159^2 + 10466562000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 1221841^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 0778159^2 + 104666562000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1221841^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 0778159^2 + 1046666562000^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1221841^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 0778159^2 + 10466666562000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1221841^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0778159^2 + 104666666562000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1221841^2 \end{aligned}$$

472)

$$\begin{aligned} 0777216^2 + 944000^2 &:= 1222784^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 0777216^2 + 10384000^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 1222784^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 0777216^2 + 104784000^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 1222784^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 0777216^2 + 1048784000^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 1222784^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 0777216^2 + 10488784000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 1222784^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 0777216^2 + 104888784000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1222784^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 0777216^2 + 1048888784000^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1222784^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 0777216^2 + 10488888784000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1222784^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0777216^2 + 104888888784000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1222784^2 \end{aligned}$$

473)

$$\begin{aligned} 0776271^2 + 946000^2 &:= 1223729^2 \\ \mathbf{12} 0776271^2 + 10406000^2 &:= \mathbf{12} 1223729^2 \\ \mathbf{1232} 0776271^2 + 105006000^2 &:= \mathbf{1232} 1223729^2 \\ \mathbf{123432} 0776271^2 + 1051006000^2 &:= \mathbf{123432} 1223729^2 \\ \mathbf{12345432} 0776271^2 + 10511006000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345432} 1223729^2 \\ \mathbf{1234565432} 0776271^2 + 105111006000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1223729^2 \\ \mathbf{123456765432} 0776271^2 + 1051111006000^2 &:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1223729^2 \\ \mathbf{12345678765432} 0776271^2 + 10511111006000^2 &:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1223729^2 \\ \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0776271^2 + 105111111006000^2 &:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1223729^2 \end{aligned}$$

474)

$$\begin{aligned} &0775324^2 + 948000^2 && := 1224676^2 \\ &12\ 0775324^2 + 10428000^2 && := 12\ 1224676^2 \\ &1232\ 0775324^2 + 105228000^2 && := 1232\ 1224676^2 \\ &123432\ 0775324^2 + 1053228000^2 && := 123432\ 1224676^2 \\ &12345432\ 0775324^2 + 10533228000^2 && := 12345432\ 1224676^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0775324^2 + 105333228000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1224676^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0775324^2 + 1053333228000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1224676^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0775324^2 + 10533333228000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1224676^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0775324^2 + 105333333228000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1224676^2 \end{aligned}$$

475)

$$\begin{aligned} &0774375^2 + 950000^2 && := 1225625^2 \\ &12\ 0774375^2 + 10450000^2 && := 12\ 1225625^2 \\ &1232\ 0774375^2 + 105450000^2 && := 1232\ 1225625^2 \\ &123432\ 0774375^2 + 1055450000^2 && := 123432\ 1225625^2 \\ &12345432\ 0774375^2 + 10555450000^2 && := 12345432\ 1225625^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0774375^2 + 105555450000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1225625^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0774375^2 + 1055555450000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1225625^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0774375^2 + 10555555450000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1225625^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0774375^2 + 105555555450000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1225625^2 \end{aligned}$$

476)

$$\begin{aligned} &0773424^2 + 952000^2 && := 1226576^2 \\ &12\ 0773424^2 + 10472000^2 && := 12\ 1226576^2 \\ &1232\ 0773424^2 + 105672000^2 && := 1232\ 1226576^2 \\ &123432\ 0773424^2 + 1057672000^2 && := 123432\ 1226576^2 \\ &12345432\ 0773424^2 + 10577672000^2 && := 12345432\ 1226576^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0773424^2 + 105777672000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1226576^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0773424^2 + 1057777672000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1226576^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0773424^2 + 10577777672000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1226576^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0773424^2 + 105777777672000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1226576^2 \end{aligned}$$

477)

$$\begin{aligned} &0772471^2 + 954000^2 && := 1227529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0772471^2 + 10494000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1227529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0772471^2 + 105894000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1227529^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0772471^2 + 1059894000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1227529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0772471^2 + 10599894000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1227529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0772471^2 + 105999894000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1227529^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0772471^2 + 1059999894000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1227529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0772471^2 + 10599999894000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1227529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0772471^2 + 105999999894000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1227529^2 \end{aligned}$$

478)

$$\begin{aligned} &0771516^2 + 956000^2 && := 1228484^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0771516^2 + 10516000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1228484^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0771516^2 + 106116000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1228484^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0771516^2 + 1062116000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1228484^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0771516^2 + 10622116000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1228484^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0771516^2 + 106222116000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1228484^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0771516^2 + 1062222116000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1228484^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0771516^2 + 10622222116000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1228484^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0771516^2 + 106222222116000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1228484^2 \end{aligned}$$

479)

$$\begin{aligned} &0770559^2 + 958000^2 && := 1229441^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0770559^2 + 10538000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1229441^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0770559^2 + 106338000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1229441^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0770559^2 + 1064338000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1229441^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0770559^2 + 10644338000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1229441^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0770559^2 + 106444338000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1229441^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0770559^2 + 1064444338000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1229441^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0770559^2 + 10644444338000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1229441^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0770559^2 + 106444444338000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1229441^2 \end{aligned}$$

480)

$$\begin{aligned} &0769600^2 + 960000^2 && := 1230400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0769600^2 + 10560000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1230400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0769600^2 + 106560000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1230400^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0769600^2 + 1066560000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1230400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0769600^2 + 10666560000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1230400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0769600^2 + 106666560000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1230400^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0769600^2 + 1066666560000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1230400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0769600^2 + 10666666560000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1230400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0769600^2 + 106666666560000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1230400^2 \end{aligned}$$

481)

$$\begin{aligned} &0768639^2 + 962000^2 && := 1231361^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0768639^2 + 10582000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1231361^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0768639^2 + 106782000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1231361^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0768639^2 + 1068782000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1231361^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0768639^2 + 10688782000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1231361^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0768639^2 + 106888782000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1231361^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0768639^2 + 1068888782000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1231361^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0768639^2 + 10688888782000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1231361^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0768639^2 + 106888888782000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1231361^2 \end{aligned}$$

482)

$$\begin{aligned} &0767676^2 + 964000^2 && := 1232324^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0767676^2 + 10604000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1232324^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0767676^2 + 107004000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1232324^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0767676^2 + 1071004000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1232324^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0767676^2 + 10711004000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1232324^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0767676^2 + 107111004000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1232324^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0767676^2 + 1071111004000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1232324^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0767676^2 + 10711111004000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1232324^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0767676^2 + 107111111004000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1232324^2 \end{aligned}$$

483)

$$\begin{aligned} &0766711^2 + 966000^2 && := 1233289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0766711^2 + 10626000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1233289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0766711^2 + 107226000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1233289^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0766711^2 + 1073226000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1233289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0766711^2 + 10733226000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1233289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0766711^2 + 107333226000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1233289^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0766711^2 + 1073333226000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1233289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0766711^2 + 10733333226000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1233289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0766711^2 + 107333333226000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1233289^2 \end{aligned}$$

484)

$$\begin{aligned} &0765744^2 + 968000^2 && := 1234256^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0765744^2 + 10648000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1234256^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0765744^2 + 107448000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1234256^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0765744^2 + 1075448000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1234256^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0765744^2 + 10755448000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1234256^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0765744^2 + 107555448000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1234256^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0765744^2 + 1075555448000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1234256^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0765744^2 + 10755555448000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1234256^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0765744^2 + 107555555448000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1234256^2 \end{aligned}$$

485)

$$\begin{aligned} &0764775^2 + 970000^2 && := 1235225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0764775^2 + 10670000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1235225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0764775^2 + 107670000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1235225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0764775^2 + 1077670000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1235225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0764775^2 + 10777670000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1235225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0764775^2 + 107777670000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1235225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0764775^2 + 1077777670000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1235225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0764775^2 + 10777777670000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1235225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0764775^2 + 107777777670000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1235225^2 \end{aligned}$$

486)

$$\begin{aligned} &0763804^2 + 972000^2 && := 1236196^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0763804^2 + 10692000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1236196^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0763804^2 + 107892000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1236196^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0763804^2 + 1079892000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1236196^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0763804^2 + 10799892000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1236196^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0763804^2 + 107999892000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1236196^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0763804^2 + 1079999892000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1236196^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0763804^2 + 10799999892000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1236196^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0763804^2 + 107999999892000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1236196^2 \end{aligned}$$

487)

$$\begin{aligned} &0762831^2 + 974000^2 && := 1237169^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0762831^2 + 10714000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1237169^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0762831^2 + 108114000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1237169^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0762831^2 + 1082114000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1237169^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0762831^2 + 10822114000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1237169^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0762831^2 + 108222114000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1237169^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0762831^2 + 1082222114000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1237169^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0762831^2 + 10822222114000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1237169^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0762831^2 + 108222222114000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1237169^2 \end{aligned}$$

488)

$$\begin{aligned} &0761856^2 + 976000^2 && := 1238144^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0761856^2 + 10736000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1238144^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0761856^2 + 108336000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1238144^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0761856^2 + 1084336000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1238144^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0761856^2 + 10844336000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1238144^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0761856^2 + 108444336000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1238144^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0761856^2 + 1084444336000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1238144^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0761856^2 + 10844444336000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1238144^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0761856^2 + 108444444336000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1238144^2 \end{aligned}$$

489)

$$\begin{aligned} &0760879^2 + 978000^2 && := 1239121^2 \\ &12\ 0760879^2 + 10758000^2 && := 12\ 1239121^2 \\ &1232\ 0760879^2 + 108558000^2 && := 1232\ 1239121^2 \\ &123432\ 0760879^2 + 1086558000^2 && := 123432\ 1239121^2 \\ &12345432\ 0760879^2 + 10866558000^2 && := 12345432\ 1239121^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0760879^2 + 108666558000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1239121^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0760879^2 + 1086666558000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1239121^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0760879^2 + 10866666558000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1239121^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0760879^2 + 108666666558000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1239121^2 \end{aligned}$$

490)

$$\begin{aligned} &0759900^2 + 980000^2 && := 1240100^2 \\ &12\ 0759900^2 + 10780000^2 && := 12\ 1240100^2 \\ &1232\ 0759900^2 + 108780000^2 && := 1232\ 1240100^2 \\ &123432\ 0759900^2 + 1088780000^2 && := 123432\ 1240100^2 \\ &12345432\ 0759900^2 + 10888780000^2 && := 12345432\ 1240100^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0759900^2 + 108888780000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1240100^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0759900^2 + 1088888780000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1240100^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0759900^2 + 10888888780000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1240100^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0759900^2 + 108888888780000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1240100^2 \end{aligned}$$

491)

$$\begin{aligned} &0758919^2 + 982000^2 && := 1241081^2 \\ &12\ 0758919^2 + 10802000^2 && := 12\ 1241081^2 \\ &1232\ 0758919^2 + 109002000^2 && := 1232\ 1241081^2 \\ &123432\ 0758919^2 + 1091002000^2 && := 123432\ 1241081^2 \\ &12345432\ 0758919^2 + 10911002000^2 && := 12345432\ 1241081^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0758919^2 + 109111002000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1241081^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0758919^2 + 1091111002000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1241081^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0758919^2 + 10911111002000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1241081^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0758919^2 + 109111111002000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1241081^2 \end{aligned}$$

492)

$$\begin{aligned} &0757936^2 + 984000^2 && := 1242064^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0757936^2 + 10824000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1242064^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0757936^2 + 109224000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1242064^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0757936^2 + 1093224000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1242064^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0757936^2 + 10933224000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1242064^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0757936^2 + 109333224000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1242064^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0757936^2 + 1093333224000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1242064^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0757936^2 + 10933333224000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1242064^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0757936^2 + 109333333224000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1242064^2 \end{aligned}$$

493)

$$\begin{aligned} &0756951^2 + 986000^2 && := 1243049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0756951^2 + 10846000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1243049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0756951^2 + 109446000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1243049^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0756951^2 + 1095446000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1243049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0756951^2 + 10955446000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1243049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0756951^2 + 109555446000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1243049^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0756951^2 + 1095555446000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1243049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0756951^2 + 10955555446000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1243049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0756951^2 + 109555555446000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1243049^2 \end{aligned}$$

494)

$$\begin{aligned} &0755964^2 + 988000^2 && := 1244036^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0755964^2 + 10868000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1244036^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0755964^2 + 109668000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1244036^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0755964^2 + 1097668000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1244036^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0755964^2 + 10977668000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1244036^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0755964^2 + 109777668000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1244036^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0755964^2 + 1097777668000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1244036^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0755964^2 + 10977777668000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1244036^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0755964^2 + 109777777668000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1244036^2 \end{aligned}$$

495)

$$\begin{aligned} &0754975^2 + 990000^2 && := 1245025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0754975^2 + 10890000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1245025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0754975^2 + 109890000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1245025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0754975^2 + 1099890000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1245025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0754975^2 + 10999890000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1245025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0754975^2 + 109999890000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1245025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0754975^2 + 1099999890000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1245025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0754975^2 + 10999999890000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1245025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0754975^2 + 109999999890000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1245025^2 \end{aligned}$$

496)

$$\begin{aligned} &0753984^2 + 992000^2 && := 1246016^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0753984^2 + 10912000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1246016^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0753984^2 + 110112000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1246016^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0753984^2 + 1102112000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1246016^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0753984^2 + 11022112000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1246016^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0753984^2 + 110222112000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1246016^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0753984^2 + 1102222112000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1246016^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0753984^2 + 11022222112000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1246016^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0753984^2 + 110222222112000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1246016^2 \end{aligned}$$

497)

$$\begin{aligned} &0752991^2 + 994000^2 && := 1247009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0752991^2 + 10934000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1247009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0752991^2 + 110334000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1247009^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0752991^2 + 1104334000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1247009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0752991^2 + 11044334000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1247009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0752991^2 + 110444334000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1247009^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0752991^2 + 1104444334000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1247009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0752991^2 + 11044444334000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1247009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0752991^2 + 110444444334000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1247009^2 \end{aligned}$$

498)

$$\begin{aligned} &0751996^2 + 996000^2 &&:= 1248004^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0751996^2 + 10956000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12} 1248004^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0751996^2 + 110556000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1232} 1248004^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0751996^2 + 1106556000^2 &&:= \mathbf{123432} 1248004^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0751996^2 + 11066556000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345432} 1248004^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0751996^2 + 110666556000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1248004^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0751996^2 + 1106666556000^2 &&:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1248004^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0751996^2 + 11066666556000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1248004^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0751996^2 + 110666666556000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1248004^2 \end{aligned}$$

499)

$$\begin{aligned} &0750999^2 + 998000^2 &&:= 1249001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0750999^2 + 10978000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12} 1249001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0750999^2 + 110778000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1232} 1249001^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0750999^2 + 1108778000^2 &&:= \mathbf{123432} 1249001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0750999^2 + 11088778000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345432} 1249001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0750999^2 + 110888778000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1249001^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0750999^2 + 1108888778000^2 &&:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1249001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0750999^2 + 11088888778000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1249001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0750999^2 + 110888888778000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1249001^2 \end{aligned}$$

500)

$$\begin{aligned} &0750000^2 + 1000000^2 &&:= 1250000^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0750000^2 + 11000000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12} 1250000^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0750000^2 + 111000000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1232} 1250000^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0750000^2 + 1111000000^2 &&:= \mathbf{123432} 1250000^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0750000^2 + 11111000000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345432} 1250000^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0750000^2 + 111111000000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234565432} 1250000^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0750000^2 + 1111111000000^2 &&:= \mathbf{123456765432} 1250000^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0750000^2 + 11111111000000^2 &&:= \mathbf{12345678765432} 1250000^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0750000^2 + 111111111000000^2 &&:= \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1250000^2 \end{aligned}$$

501)

$$\begin{aligned} &0748999^2 + 1002000^2 && := 1251001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0748999^2 + 11022000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1251001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0748999^2 + 111222000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1251001^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0748999^2 + 1113222000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1251001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0748999^2 + 11133222000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1251001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0748999^2 + 111333222000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1251001^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0748999^2 + 1113333222000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1251001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0748999^2 + 11133333222000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1251001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0748999^2 + 111333333222000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1251001^2 \end{aligned}$$

502)

$$\begin{aligned} &0747996^2 + 1004000^2 && := 1252004^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0747996^2 + 11044000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1252004^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0747996^2 + 111444000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1252004^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0747996^2 + 1115444000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1252004^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0747996^2 + 11155444000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1252004^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0747996^2 + 111555444000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1252004^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0747996^2 + 1115555444000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1252004^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0747996^2 + 11155555444000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1252004^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0747996^2 + 111555555444000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1252004^2 \end{aligned}$$

503)

$$\begin{aligned} &0746991^2 + 1006000^2 && := 1253009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0746991^2 + 11066000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1253009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0746991^2 + 111666000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1253009^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0746991^2 + 1117666000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1253009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0746991^2 + 11177666000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1253009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0746991^2 + 111777666000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1253009^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0746991^2 + 1117777666000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1253009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0746991^2 + 11177777666000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1253009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0746991^2 + 111777777666000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1253009^2 \end{aligned}$$

504)

$$\begin{aligned} &0745984^2 + 1008000^2 && := 1254016^2 \\ &12\ 0745984^2 + 11088000^2 && := 12\ 1254016^2 \\ &1232\ 0745984^2 + 111888000^2 && := 1232\ 1254016^2 \\ &123432\ 0745984^2 + 1119888000^2 && := 123432\ 1254016^2 \\ &12345432\ 0745984^2 + 11199888000^2 && := 12345432\ 1254016^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0745984^2 + 111999888000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1254016^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0745984^2 + 1119999888000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1254016^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0745984^2 + 11199999888000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1254016^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0745984^2 + 111999999888000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1254016^2 \end{aligned}$$

505)

$$\begin{aligned} &0744975^2 + 1010000^2 && := 1255025^2 \\ &12\ 0744975^2 + 11110000^2 && := 12\ 1255025^2 \\ &1232\ 0744975^2 + 112110000^2 && := 1232\ 1255025^2 \\ &123432\ 0744975^2 + 1122110000^2 && := 123432\ 1255025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0744975^2 + 11222110000^2 && := 12345432\ 1255025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0744975^2 + 112222110000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1255025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0744975^2 + 1122222110000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1255025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0744975^2 + 11222222110000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1255025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0744975^2 + 112222222110000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1255025^2 \end{aligned}$$

506)

$$\begin{aligned} &0743964^2 + 1012000^2 && := 1256036^2 \\ &12\ 0743964^2 + 11132000^2 && := 12\ 1256036^2 \\ &1232\ 0743964^2 + 112332000^2 && := 1232\ 1256036^2 \\ &123432\ 0743964^2 + 1124332000^2 && := 123432\ 1256036^2 \\ &12345432\ 0743964^2 + 11244332000^2 && := 12345432\ 1256036^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0743964^2 + 112444332000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1256036^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0743964^2 + 1124444332000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1256036^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0743964^2 + 11244444332000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1256036^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0743964^2 + 112444444332000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1256036^2 \end{aligned}$$

507)

$$\begin{aligned} &0742951^2 + 1014000^2 && := 1257049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0742951^2 + 11154000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1257049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0742951^2 + 112554000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1257049^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0742951^2 + 1126554000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1257049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0742951^2 + 11266554000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1257049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0742951^2 + 112666554000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1257049^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0742951^2 + 1126666554000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1257049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0742951^2 + 11266666554000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1257049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0742951^2 + 112666666554000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1257049^2 \end{aligned}$$

508)

$$\begin{aligned} &0741936^2 + 1016000^2 && := 1258064^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0741936^2 + 11176000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1258064^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0741936^2 + 112776000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1258064^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0741936^2 + 1128776000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1258064^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0741936^2 + 11288776000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1258064^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0741936^2 + 112888776000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1258064^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0741936^2 + 1128888776000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1258064^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0741936^2 + 11288888776000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1258064^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0741936^2 + 112888888776000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1258064^2 \end{aligned}$$

509)

$$\begin{aligned} &0740919^2 + 1018000^2 && := 1259081^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0740919^2 + 11198000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1259081^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0740919^2 + 112998000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1259081^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0740919^2 + 1130998000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1259081^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0740919^2 + 11310998000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1259081^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0740919^2 + 113110998000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1259081^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0740919^2 + 1131110998000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1259081^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0740919^2 + 11311110998000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1259081^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0740919^2 + 113111110998000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1259081^2 \end{aligned}$$

510)

$$\begin{aligned} &0739900^2 + 1020000^2 && := 1260100^2 \\ &12\ 0739900^2 + 11220000^2 && := 12\ 1260100^2 \\ &1232\ 0739900^2 + 113220000^2 && := 1232\ 1260100^2 \\ &123432\ 0739900^2 + 1133220000^2 && := 123432\ 1260100^2 \\ &12345432\ 0739900^2 + 11333220000^2 && := 12345432\ 1260100^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0739900^2 + 113333220000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1260100^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0739900^2 + 1133333220000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1260100^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0739900^2 + 11333333220000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1260100^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0739900^2 + 113333333220000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1260100^2 \end{aligned}$$

511)

$$\begin{aligned} &0738879^2 + 1022000^2 && := 1261121^2 \\ &12\ 0738879^2 + 11242000^2 && := 12\ 1261121^2 \\ &1232\ 0738879^2 + 113442000^2 && := 1232\ 1261121^2 \\ &123432\ 0738879^2 + 1135442000^2 && := 123432\ 1261121^2 \\ &12345432\ 0738879^2 + 11355442000^2 && := 12345432\ 1261121^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0738879^2 + 113555442000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1261121^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0738879^2 + 1135555442000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1261121^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0738879^2 + 11355555442000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1261121^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0738879^2 + 113555555442000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1261121^2 \end{aligned}$$

512)

$$\begin{aligned} &0737856^2 + 1024000^2 && := 1262144^2 \\ &12\ 0737856^2 + 11264000^2 && := 12\ 1262144^2 \\ &1232\ 0737856^2 + 113664000^2 && := 1232\ 1262144^2 \\ &123432\ 0737856^2 + 1137664000^2 && := 123432\ 1262144^2 \\ &12345432\ 0737856^2 + 11377664000^2 && := 12345432\ 1262144^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0737856^2 + 113777664000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1262144^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0737856^2 + 1137777664000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1262144^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0737856^2 + 11377777664000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1262144^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0737856^2 + 113777777664000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1262144^2 \end{aligned}$$

513)

$$\begin{aligned} &0736831^2 + 1026000^2 && := 1263169^2 \\ &12\ 0736831^2 + 11286000^2 && := 12\ 1263169^2 \\ &1232\ 0736831^2 + 113886000^2 && := 1232\ 1263169^2 \\ &123432\ 0736831^2 + 1139886000^2 && := 123432\ 1263169^2 \\ &12345432\ 0736831^2 + 11399886000^2 && := 12345432\ 1263169^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0736831^2 + 113999886000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1263169^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0736831^2 + 1139999886000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1263169^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0736831^2 + 11399999886000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1263169^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0736831^2 + 113999999886000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1263169^2 \end{aligned}$$

514)

$$\begin{aligned} &0735804^2 + 1028000^2 && := 1264196^2 \\ &12\ 0735804^2 + 11308000^2 && := 12\ 1264196^2 \\ &1232\ 0735804^2 + 114108000^2 && := 1232\ 1264196^2 \\ &123432\ 0735804^2 + 1142108000^2 && := 123432\ 1264196^2 \\ &12345432\ 0735804^2 + 11422108000^2 && := 12345432\ 1264196^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0735804^2 + 114222108000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1264196^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0735804^2 + 1142222108000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1264196^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0735804^2 + 11422222108000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1264196^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0735804^2 + 114222222108000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1264196^2 \end{aligned}$$

515)

$$\begin{aligned} &0734775^2 + 1030000^2 && := 1265225^2 \\ &12\ 0734775^2 + 11330000^2 && := 12\ 1265225^2 \\ &1232\ 0734775^2 + 114330000^2 && := 1232\ 1265225^2 \\ &123432\ 0734775^2 + 1144330000^2 && := 123432\ 1265225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0734775^2 + 11444330000^2 && := 12345432\ 1265225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0734775^2 + 114444330000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1265225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0734775^2 + 1144444330000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1265225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0734775^2 + 11444444330000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1265225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0734775^2 + 114444444330000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1265225^2 \end{aligned}$$

516)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0733744^2 + 1032000^2 & := & 1266256^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0733744^2 + 11352000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1266256^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0733744^2 + 114552000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1266256^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0733744^2 + 1146552000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1266256^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0733744^2 + 11466552000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1266256^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0733744^2 + 114666552000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1266256^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0733744^2 + 1146666552000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1266256^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0733744^2 + 11466666552000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1266256^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0733744^2 + 114666666552000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1266256^2 \end{aligned}$$

517)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0732711^2 + 1034000^2 & := & 1267289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0732711^2 + 11374000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1267289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0732711^2 + 114774000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1267289^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0732711^2 + 1148774000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1267289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0732711^2 + 11488774000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1267289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0732711^2 + 114888774000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1267289^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0732711^2 + 1148888774000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1267289^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0732711^2 + 11488888774000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1267289^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0732711^2 + 114888888774000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1267289^2 \end{aligned}$$

518)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0731676^2 + 1036000^2 & := & 1268324^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0731676^2 + 11396000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1268324^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0731676^2 + 114996000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1268324^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0731676^2 + 1150996000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1268324^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0731676^2 + 11510996000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1268324^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0731676^2 + 115110996000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1268324^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0731676^2 + 1151110996000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1268324^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0731676^2 + 11511110996000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1268324^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0731676^2 + 115111110996000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1268324^2 \end{aligned}$$

519)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0730639^2 + 1038000^2 & := & 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0730639^2 + 11418000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0730639^2 + 115218000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0730639^2 + 1153218000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0730639^2 + 11533218000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0730639^2 + 115333218000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0730639^2 + 1153333218000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0730639^2 + 11533333218000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0730639^2 + 115333333218000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1269361^2 \end{aligned}$$

520)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0729600^2 + 1040000^2 & := & 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0729600^2 + 11440000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0729600^2 + 115440000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0729600^2 + 1155440000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0729600^2 + 11555440000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0729600^2 + 115555440000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0729600^2 + 1155555440000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0729600^2 + 11555555440000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0729600^2 + 115555555440000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1270400^2 \end{aligned}$$

521)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0728559^2 + 1042000^2 & := & 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0728559^2 + 11462000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0728559^2 + 115662000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0728559^2 + 1157662000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0728559^2 + 11577662000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0728559^2 + 115777662000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0728559^2 + 1157777662000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0728559^2 + 11577777662000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0728559^2 + 115777777662000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1271441^2 \end{aligned}$$

522)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0727516^2 + 1044000^2 & := & 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0727516^2 + 11484000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0727516^2 + 115884000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0727516^2 + 1159884000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0727516^2 + 11599884000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0727516^2 + 115999884000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0727516^2 + 1159999884000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0727516^2 + 11599999884000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0727516^2 + 115999999884000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1272484^2 \end{aligned}$$

523)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0726471^2 + 1046000^2 & := & 1273529^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0726471^2 + 11506000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1273529^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0726471^2 + 116106000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1273529^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0726471^2 + 1162106000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1273529^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0726471^2 + 11622106000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1273529^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0726471^2 + 116222106000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1273529^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0726471^2 + 1162222106000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1273529^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0726471^2 + 11622222106000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1273529^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0726471^2 + 116222222106000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1273529^2 \end{aligned}$$

524)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0725424^2 + 1048000^2 & := & 1274576^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0725424^2 + 11528000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1274576^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0725424^2 + 116328000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1274576^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0725424^2 + 1164328000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1274576^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0725424^2 + 11644328000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1274576^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0725424^2 + 116444328000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1274576^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0725424^2 + 1164444328000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1274576^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0725424^2 + 11644444328000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1274576^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0725424^2 + 116444444328000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1274576^2 \end{aligned}$$

525)

$$\begin{aligned} &0724375^2 + 1050000^2 && := 1275625^2 \\ &12\ 0724375^2 + 11550000^2 && := 12\ 1275625^2 \\ &1232\ 0724375^2 + 116550000^2 && := 1232\ 1275625^2 \\ &123432\ 0724375^2 + 1166550000^2 && := 123432\ 1275625^2 \\ &12345432\ 0724375^2 + 11666550000^2 && := 12345432\ 1275625^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0724375^2 + 116666550000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1275625^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0724375^2 + 1166666550000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1275625^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0724375^2 + 11666666550000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1275625^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0724375^2 + 116666666550000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1275625^2 \end{aligned}$$

526)

$$\begin{aligned} &0723324^2 + 1052000^2 && := 1276676^2 \\ &12\ 0723324^2 + 11572000^2 && := 12\ 1276676^2 \\ &1232\ 0723324^2 + 116772000^2 && := 1232\ 1276676^2 \\ &123432\ 0723324^2 + 1168772000^2 && := 123432\ 1276676^2 \\ &12345432\ 0723324^2 + 11688772000^2 && := 12345432\ 1276676^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0723324^2 + 116888772000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1276676^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0723324^2 + 1168888772000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1276676^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0723324^2 + 11688888772000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1276676^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0723324^2 + 116888888772000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1276676^2 \end{aligned}$$

527)

$$\begin{aligned} &0722271^2 + 1054000^2 && := 1277729^2 \\ &12\ 0722271^2 + 11594000^2 && := 12\ 1277729^2 \\ &1232\ 0722271^2 + 116994000^2 && := 1232\ 1277729^2 \\ &123432\ 0722271^2 + 1170994000^2 && := 123432\ 1277729^2 \\ &12345432\ 0722271^2 + 11710994000^2 && := 12345432\ 1277729^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0722271^2 + 117110994000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1277729^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0722271^2 + 1171110994000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1277729^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0722271^2 + 11711110994000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1277729^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0722271^2 + 117111110994000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1277729^2 \end{aligned}$$

528)

$$\begin{aligned} &0721216^2 + 1056000^2 && := 1278784^2 \\ &12\ 0721216^2 + 11616000^2 && := 12\ 1278784^2 \\ &1232\ 0721216^2 + 117216000^2 && := 1232\ 1278784^2 \\ &123432\ 0721216^2 + 1173216000^2 && := 123432\ 1278784^2 \\ &12345432\ 0721216^2 + 11733216000^2 && := 12345432\ 1278784^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0721216^2 + 117333216000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1278784^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0721216^2 + 1173333216000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1278784^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0721216^2 + 11733333216000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1278784^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0721216^2 + 117333333216000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1278784^2 \end{aligned}$$

529)

$$\begin{aligned} &0720159^2 + 1058000^2 && := 1279841^2 \\ &12\ 0720159^2 + 11638000^2 && := 12\ 1279841^2 \\ &1232\ 0720159^2 + 117438000^2 && := 1232\ 1279841^2 \\ &123432\ 0720159^2 + 1175438000^2 && := 123432\ 1279841^2 \\ &12345432\ 0720159^2 + 11755438000^2 && := 12345432\ 1279841^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0720159^2 + 117555438000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1279841^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0720159^2 + 1175555438000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1279841^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0720159^2 + 11755555438000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1279841^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0720159^2 + 117555555438000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1279841^2 \end{aligned}$$

530)

$$\begin{aligned} &0719100^2 + 1060000^2 && := 1280900^2 \\ &12\ 0719100^2 + 11660000^2 && := 12\ 1280900^2 \\ &1232\ 0719100^2 + 117660000^2 && := 1232\ 1280900^2 \\ &123432\ 0719100^2 + 1177660000^2 && := 123432\ 1280900^2 \\ &12345432\ 0719100^2 + 11777660000^2 && := 12345432\ 1280900^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0719100^2 + 117777660000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1280900^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0719100^2 + 1177777660000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1280900^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0719100^2 + 11777777660000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1280900^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0719100^2 + 117777777660000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1280900^2 \end{aligned}$$

531)

$$\begin{aligned} &0718039^2 + 1062000^2 && := 1281961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0718039^2 + 11682000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1281961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0718039^2 + 117882000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1281961^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0718039^2 + 1179882000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1281961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0718039^2 + 11799882000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1281961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0718039^2 + 117999882000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1281961^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0718039^2 + 1179999882000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1281961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0718039^2 + 11799999882000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1281961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0718039^2 + 117999999882000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1281961^2 \end{aligned}$$

532)

$$\begin{aligned} &0716976^2 + 1064000^2 && := 1283024^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0716976^2 + 11704000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1283024^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0716976^2 + 118104000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1283024^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0716976^2 + 1182104000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1283024^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0716976^2 + 11822104000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1283024^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0716976^2 + 118222104000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1283024^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0716976^2 + 1182222104000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1283024^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0716976^2 + 11822222104000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1283024^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0716976^2 + 118222222104000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1283024^2 \end{aligned}$$

533)

$$\begin{aligned} &0715911^2 + 1066000^2 && := 1284089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0715911^2 + 11726000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1284089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0715911^2 + 118326000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1284089^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0715911^2 + 1184326000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1284089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0715911^2 + 11844326000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1284089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0715911^2 + 118444326000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1284089^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0715911^2 + 1184444326000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1284089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0715911^2 + 11844444326000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1284089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0715911^2 + 118444444326000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1284089^2 \end{aligned}$$

534)

$$\begin{aligned} &0714844^2 + 1068000^2 && := 1285156^2 \\ &12\ 0714844^2 + 11748000^2 && := 12\ 1285156^2 \\ &1232\ 0714844^2 + 118548000^2 && := 1232\ 1285156^2 \\ &123432\ 0714844^2 + 1186548000^2 && := 123432\ 1285156^2 \\ &12345432\ 0714844^2 + 11866548000^2 && := 12345432\ 1285156^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0714844^2 + 118666548000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1285156^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0714844^2 + 1186666548000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1285156^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0714844^2 + 11866666548000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1285156^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0714844^2 + 118666666548000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1285156^2 \end{aligned}$$

535)

$$\begin{aligned} &0713775^2 + 1070000^2 && := 1286225^2 \\ &12\ 0713775^2 + 11770000^2 && := 12\ 1286225^2 \\ &1232\ 0713775^2 + 118770000^2 && := 1232\ 1286225^2 \\ &123432\ 0713775^2 + 1188770000^2 && := 123432\ 1286225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0713775^2 + 11888770000^2 && := 12345432\ 1286225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0713775^2 + 118888770000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1286225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0713775^2 + 1188888770000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1286225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0713775^2 + 11888888770000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1286225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0713775^2 + 118888888770000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1286225^2 \end{aligned}$$

536)

$$\begin{aligned} &0712704^2 + 1072000^2 && := 1287296^2 \\ &12\ 0712704^2 + 11792000^2 && := 12\ 1287296^2 \\ &1232\ 0712704^2 + 118992000^2 && := 1232\ 1287296^2 \\ &123432\ 0712704^2 + 1190992000^2 && := 123432\ 1287296^2 \\ &12345432\ 0712704^2 + 11910992000^2 && := 12345432\ 1287296^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0712704^2 + 119110992000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1287296^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0712704^2 + 1191110992000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1287296^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0712704^2 + 11911110992000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1287296^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0712704^2 + 119111110992000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1287296^2 \end{aligned}$$

537)

$$\begin{aligned} &0711631^2 + 1074000^2 && := 1288369^2 \\ &12\ 0711631^2 + 11814000^2 && := 12\ 1288369^2 \\ &1232\ 0711631^2 + 119214000^2 && := 1232\ 1288369^2 \\ &123432\ 0711631^2 + 1193214000^2 && := 123432\ 1288369^2 \\ &12345432\ 0711631^2 + 11933214000^2 && := 12345432\ 1288369^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0711631^2 + 119333214000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1288369^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0711631^2 + 1193333214000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1288369^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0711631^2 + 11933333214000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1288369^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0711631^2 + 119333333214000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1288369^2 \end{aligned}$$

538)

$$\begin{aligned} &0710556^2 + 1076000^2 && := 1289444^2 \\ &12\ 0710556^2 + 11836000^2 && := 12\ 1289444^2 \\ &1232\ 0710556^2 + 119436000^2 && := 1232\ 1289444^2 \\ &123432\ 0710556^2 + 1195436000^2 && := 123432\ 1289444^2 \\ &12345432\ 0710556^2 + 11955436000^2 && := 12345432\ 1289444^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0710556^2 + 119555436000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1289444^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0710556^2 + 1195555436000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1289444^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0710556^2 + 11955555436000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1289444^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0710556^2 + 119555555436000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1289444^2 \end{aligned}$$

539)

$$\begin{aligned} &0709479^2 + 1078000^2 && := 1290521^2 \\ &12\ 0709479^2 + 11858000^2 && := 12\ 1290521^2 \\ &1232\ 0709479^2 + 119658000^2 && := 1232\ 1290521^2 \\ &123432\ 0709479^2 + 1197658000^2 && := 123432\ 1290521^2 \\ &12345432\ 0709479^2 + 11977658000^2 && := 12345432\ 1290521^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0709479^2 + 119777658000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1290521^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0709479^2 + 1197777658000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1290521^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0709479^2 + 11977777658000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1290521^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0709479^2 + 119777777658000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1290521^2 \end{aligned}$$

540)

$$\begin{aligned} &0708400^2 + 1080000^2 && := 1291600^2 \\ &12\ 0708400^2 + 11880000^2 && := 12\ 1291600^2 \\ &1232\ 0708400^2 + 119880000^2 && := 1232\ 1291600^2 \\ &123432\ 0708400^2 + 1199880000^2 && := 123432\ 1291600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0708400^2 + 11999880000^2 && := 12345432\ 1291600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0708400^2 + 119999880000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1291600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0708400^2 + 1199999880000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1291600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0708400^2 + 11999999880000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1291600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0708400^2 + 119999999880000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1291600^2 \end{aligned}$$

541)

$$\begin{aligned} &0707319^2 + 1082000^2 && := 1292681^2 \\ &12\ 0707319^2 + 11902000^2 && := 12\ 1292681^2 \\ &1232\ 0707319^2 + 120102000^2 && := 1232\ 1292681^2 \\ &123432\ 0707319^2 + 1202102000^2 && := 123432\ 1292681^2 \\ &12345432\ 0707319^2 + 12022102000^2 && := 12345432\ 1292681^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0707319^2 + 120222102000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1292681^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0707319^2 + 1202222102000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1292681^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0707319^2 + 12022222102000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1292681^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0707319^2 + 120222222102000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1292681^2 \end{aligned}$$

542)

$$\begin{aligned} &0706236^2 + 1084000^2 && := 1293764^2 \\ &12\ 0706236^2 + 11924000^2 && := 12\ 1293764^2 \\ &1232\ 0706236^2 + 120324000^2 && := 1232\ 1293764^2 \\ &123432\ 0706236^2 + 1204324000^2 && := 123432\ 1293764^2 \\ &12345432\ 0706236^2 + 12044324000^2 && := 12345432\ 1293764^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0706236^2 + 120444324000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1293764^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0706236^2 + 1204444324000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1293764^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0706236^2 + 12044444324000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1293764^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0706236^2 + 120444444324000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1293764^2 \end{aligned}$$

543)

$$\begin{aligned} &0705151^2 + 1086000^2 && := 1294849^2 \\ &12\ 0705151^2 + 11946000^2 && := 12\ 1294849^2 \\ &1232\ 0705151^2 + 120546000^2 && := 1232\ 1294849^2 \\ &123432\ 0705151^2 + 1206546000^2 && := 123432\ 1294849^2 \\ &12345432\ 0705151^2 + 12066546000^2 && := 12345432\ 1294849^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0705151^2 + 120666546000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1294849^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0705151^2 + 1206666546000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1294849^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0705151^2 + 12066666546000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1294849^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0705151^2 + 120666666546000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1294849^2 \end{aligned}$$

544)

$$\begin{aligned} &0704064^2 + 1088000^2 && := 1295936^2 \\ &12\ 0704064^2 + 11968000^2 && := 12\ 1295936^2 \\ &1232\ 0704064^2 + 120768000^2 && := 1232\ 1295936^2 \\ &123432\ 0704064^2 + 1208768000^2 && := 123432\ 1295936^2 \\ &12345432\ 0704064^2 + 12088768000^2 && := 12345432\ 1295936^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0704064^2 + 120888768000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1295936^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0704064^2 + 1208888768000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1295936^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0704064^2 + 12088888768000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1295936^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0704064^2 + 120888888768000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1295936^2 \end{aligned}$$

545)

$$\begin{aligned} &0702975^2 + 1090000^2 && := 1297025^2 \\ &12\ 0702975^2 + 11990000^2 && := 12\ 1297025^2 \\ &1232\ 0702975^2 + 120990000^2 && := 1232\ 1297025^2 \\ &123432\ 0702975^2 + 1210990000^2 && := 123432\ 1297025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0702975^2 + 12110990000^2 && := 12345432\ 1297025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0702975^2 + 121110990000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1297025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0702975^2 + 1211110990000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1297025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0702975^2 + 12111110990000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1297025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0702975^2 + 121111110990000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1297025^2 \end{aligned}$$

546)

$$\begin{aligned} &0701884^2 + 1092000^2 &&:= 1298116^2 \\ &12\ 0701884^2 + 12012000^2 &&:= 12\ 1298116^2 \\ &1232\ 0701884^2 + 121212000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1298116^2 \\ &123432\ 0701884^2 + 1213212000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1298116^2 \\ &12345432\ 0701884^2 + 12133212000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1298116^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0701884^2 + 121333212000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1298116^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0701884^2 + 1213333212000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1298116^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0701884^2 + 12133333212000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1298116^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0701884^2 + 121333333212000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1298116^2 \end{aligned}$$

547)

$$\begin{aligned} &0700791^2 + 1094000^2 &&:= 1299209^2 \\ &12\ 0700791^2 + 12034000^2 &&:= 12\ 1299209^2 \\ &1232\ 0700791^2 + 121434000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1299209^2 \\ &123432\ 0700791^2 + 1215434000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1299209^2 \\ &12345432\ 0700791^2 + 12155434000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1299209^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0700791^2 + 121555434000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1299209^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0700791^2 + 1215555434000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1299209^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0700791^2 + 12155555434000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1299209^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0700791^2 + 121555555434000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1299209^2 \end{aligned}$$

548)

$$\begin{aligned} &0699696^2 + 1096000^2 &&:= 1300304^2 \\ &12\ 0699696^2 + 12056000^2 &&:= 12\ 1300304^2 \\ &1232\ 0699696^2 + 121656000^2 &&:= 1232\ 1300304^2 \\ &123432\ 0699696^2 + 1217656000^2 &&:= 123432\ 1300304^2 \\ &12345432\ 0699696^2 + 12177656000^2 &&:= 12345432\ 1300304^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0699696^2 + 121777656000^2 &&:= 1234565432\ 1300304^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0699696^2 + 1217777656000^2 &&:= 123456765432\ 1300304^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0699696^2 + 12177777656000^2 &&:= 12345678765432\ 1300304^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0699696^2 + 121777777656000^2 &&:= 1234567898765432\ 1300304^2 \end{aligned}$$

549)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0698599^2 + 1098000^2 & := & 1301401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0698599^2 + 12078000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1301401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0698599^2 + 121878000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1301401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0698599^2 + 1219878000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1301401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0698599^2 + 12199878000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1301401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0698599^2 + 121999878000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1301401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0698599^2 + 1219999878000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1301401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0698599^2 + 12199999878000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1301401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0698599^2 + 121999999878000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1301401^2 \end{aligned}$$

550)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0697500^2 + 1100000^2 & := & 1302500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0697500^2 + 12100000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1302500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0697500^2 + 122100000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1302500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0697500^2 + 1222100000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1302500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0697500^2 + 12222100000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1302500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0697500^2 + 122222100000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1302500^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0697500^2 + 1222222100000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1302500^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0697500^2 + 12222222100000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1302500^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0697500^2 + 122222222100000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1302500^2 \end{aligned}$$

551)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0696399^2 + 1102000^2 & := & 1303601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0696399^2 + 12122000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1303601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0696399^2 + 122322000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1303601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0696399^2 + 1224322000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1303601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0696399^2 + 12244322000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1303601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0696399^2 + 122444322000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1303601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0696399^2 + 1224444322000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1303601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0696399^2 + 12244444322000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1303601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0696399^2 + 122444444322000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1303601^2 \end{aligned}$$

552)

$$\begin{aligned} &0695296^2 + 1104000^2 && := 1304704^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0695296^2 + 12144000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1304704^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0695296^2 + 122544000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1304704^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0695296^2 + 1226544000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1304704^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0695296^2 + 12266544000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1304704^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0695296^2 + 122666544000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1304704^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0695296^2 + 1226666544000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1304704^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0695296^2 + 12266666544000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1304704^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0695296^2 + 122666666544000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1304704^2 \end{aligned}$$

553)

$$\begin{aligned} &0694191^2 + 1106000^2 && := 1305809^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0694191^2 + 12166000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1305809^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0694191^2 + 122766000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1305809^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0694191^2 + 1228766000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1305809^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0694191^2 + 12288766000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1305809^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0694191^2 + 122888766000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1305809^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0694191^2 + 1228888766000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1305809^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0694191^2 + 12288888766000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1305809^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0694191^2 + 122888888766000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1305809^2 \end{aligned}$$

554)

$$\begin{aligned} &0693084^2 + 1108000^2 && := 1306916^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0693084^2 + 12188000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1306916^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0693084^2 + 122988000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1306916^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0693084^2 + 1230988000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1306916^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0693084^2 + 12310988000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1306916^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0693084^2 + 123110988000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1306916^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0693084^2 + 1231110988000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1306916^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0693084^2 + 12311110988000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1306916^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0693084^2 + 123111110988000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1306916^2 \end{aligned}$$

555)

$$\begin{aligned} &0691975^2 + 1110000^2 &:=& 1308025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0691975^2 + 12210000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1308025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0691975^2 + 123210000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1308025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0691975^2 + 1233210000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1308025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0691975^2 + 12333210000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1308025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0691975^2 + 123333210000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1308025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0691975^2 + 1233333210000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1308025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0691975^2 + 12333333210000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1308025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0691975^2 + 123333333210000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1308025^2 \end{aligned}$$

556)

$$\begin{aligned} &0690864^2 + 1112000^2 &:=& 1309136^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0690864^2 + 12232000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1309136^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0690864^2 + 123432000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1309136^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0690864^2 + 1235432000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1309136^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0690864^2 + 12355432000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1309136^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0690864^2 + 123555432000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1309136^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0690864^2 + 1235555432000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1309136^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0690864^2 + 12355555432000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1309136^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0690864^2 + 123555555432000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1309136^2 \end{aligned}$$

557)

$$\begin{aligned} &0689751^2 + 1114000^2 &:=& 1310249^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0689751^2 + 12254000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1310249^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0689751^2 + 123654000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1310249^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0689751^2 + 1237654000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1310249^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0689751^2 + 12377654000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1310249^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0689751^2 + 123777654000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1310249^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0689751^2 + 1237777654000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1310249^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0689751^2 + 12377777654000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1310249^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0689751^2 + 123777777654000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1310249^2 \end{aligned}$$

558)

$$\begin{aligned} &0688636^2 + 1116000^2 && := 1311364^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0688636^2 + 12276000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1311364^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0688636^2 + 123876000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1311364^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0688636^2 + 1239876000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1311364^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0688636^2 + 12399876000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1311364^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0688636^2 + 123999876000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1311364^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0688636^2 + 1239999876000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1311364^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0688636^2 + 12399999876000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1311364^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0688636^2 + 123999999876000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1311364^2 \end{aligned}$$

559)

$$\begin{aligned} &0687519^2 + 1118000^2 && := 1312481^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0687519^2 + 12298000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1312481^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0687519^2 + 124098000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1312481^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0687519^2 + 1242098000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1312481^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0687519^2 + 12422098000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1312481^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0687519^2 + 124222098000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1312481^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0687519^2 + 1242222098000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1312481^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0687519^2 + 12422222098000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1312481^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0687519^2 + 124222222098000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1312481^2 \end{aligned}$$

560)

$$\begin{aligned} &0686400^2 + 1120000^2 && := 1313600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0686400^2 + 12320000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1313600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0686400^2 + 124320000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1313600^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0686400^2 + 1244320000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1313600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0686400^2 + 12444320000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1313600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0686400^2 + 124444320000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1313600^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0686400^2 + 1244444320000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1313600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0686400^2 + 12444444320000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1313600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0686400^2 + 124444444320000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1313600^2 \end{aligned}$$

561)

$$\begin{aligned} &0685279^2 + 1122000^2 && := 1314721^2 \\ &12\ 0685279^2 + 12342000^2 && := 12\ 1314721^2 \\ &1232\ 0685279^2 + 124542000^2 && := 1232\ 1314721^2 \\ &123432\ 0685279^2 + 1246542000^2 && := 123432\ 1314721^2 \\ &12345432\ 0685279^2 + 12466542000^2 && := 12345432\ 1314721^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0685279^2 + 124666542000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1314721^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0685279^2 + 1246666542000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1314721^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0685279^2 + 12466666542000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1314721^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0685279^2 + 124666666542000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1314721^2 \end{aligned}$$

562)

$$\begin{aligned} &0684156^2 + 1124000^2 && := 1315844^2 \\ &12\ 0684156^2 + 12364000^2 && := 12\ 1315844^2 \\ &1232\ 0684156^2 + 124764000^2 && := 1232\ 1315844^2 \\ &123432\ 0684156^2 + 1248764000^2 && := 123432\ 1315844^2 \\ &12345432\ 0684156^2 + 12488764000^2 && := 12345432\ 1315844^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0684156^2 + 124888764000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1315844^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0684156^2 + 1248888764000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1315844^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0684156^2 + 12488888764000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1315844^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0684156^2 + 124888888764000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1315844^2 \end{aligned}$$

563)

$$\begin{aligned} &0683031^2 + 1126000^2 && := 1316969^2 \\ &12\ 0683031^2 + 12386000^2 && := 12\ 1316969^2 \\ &1232\ 0683031^2 + 124986000^2 && := 1232\ 1316969^2 \\ &123432\ 0683031^2 + 1250986000^2 && := 123432\ 1316969^2 \\ &12345432\ 0683031^2 + 12510986000^2 && := 12345432\ 1316969^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0683031^2 + 125110986000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1316969^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0683031^2 + 1251110986000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1316969^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0683031^2 + 12511110986000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1316969^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0683031^2 + 125111110986000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1316969^2 \end{aligned}$$

564)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0681904^2 + 1128000^2 & := & 1318096^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0681904^2 + 12408000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1318096^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0681904^2 + 125208000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1318096^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0681904^2 + 1253208000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1318096^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0681904^2 + 12533208000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1318096^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0681904^2 + 125333208000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1318096^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0681904^2 + 1253333208000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1318096^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0681904^2 + 12533333208000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1318096^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0681904^2 + 125333333208000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1318096^2 \end{aligned}$$

565)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0680775^2 + 1130000^2 & := & 1319225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0680775^2 + 12430000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1319225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0680775^2 + 125430000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1319225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0680775^2 + 1255430000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1319225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0680775^2 + 12555430000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1319225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0680775^2 + 125555430000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1319225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0680775^2 + 1255555430000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1319225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0680775^2 + 12555555430000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1319225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0680775^2 + 125555555430000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1319225^2 \end{aligned}$$

566)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0679644^2 + 1132000^2 & := & 1320356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0679644^2 + 12452000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1320356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0679644^2 + 125652000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1320356^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0679644^2 + 1257652000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1320356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0679644^2 + 12577652000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1320356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0679644^2 + 125777652000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1320356^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0679644^2 + 1257777652000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1320356^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0679644^2 + 12577777652000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1320356^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0679644^2 + 125777777652000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1320356^2 \end{aligned}$$

567)

$$\begin{aligned} &0678511^2 + 1134000^2 && := 1321489^2 \\ &12\ 0678511^2 + 12474000^2 && := 12\ 1321489^2 \\ &1232\ 0678511^2 + 125874000^2 && := 1232\ 1321489^2 \\ &123432\ 0678511^2 + 1259874000^2 && := 123432\ 1321489^2 \\ &12345432\ 0678511^2 + 12599874000^2 && := 12345432\ 1321489^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0678511^2 + 125999874000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1321489^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0678511^2 + 1259999874000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1321489^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0678511^2 + 12599999874000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1321489^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0678511^2 + 125999999874000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1321489^2 \end{aligned}$$

568)

$$\begin{aligned} &0677376^2 + 1136000^2 && := 1322624^2 \\ &12\ 0677376^2 + 12496000^2 && := 12\ 1322624^2 \\ &1232\ 0677376^2 + 126096000^2 && := 1232\ 1322624^2 \\ &123432\ 0677376^2 + 1262096000^2 && := 123432\ 1322624^2 \\ &12345432\ 0677376^2 + 12622096000^2 && := 12345432\ 1322624^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0677376^2 + 126222096000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1322624^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0677376^2 + 1262222096000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1322624^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0677376^2 + 12622222096000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1322624^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0677376^2 + 126222222096000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1322624^2 \end{aligned}$$

569)

$$\begin{aligned} &0676239^2 + 1138000^2 && := 1323761^2 \\ &12\ 0676239^2 + 12518000^2 && := 12\ 1323761^2 \\ &1232\ 0676239^2 + 126318000^2 && := 1232\ 1323761^2 \\ &123432\ 0676239^2 + 1264318000^2 && := 123432\ 1323761^2 \\ &12345432\ 0676239^2 + 12644318000^2 && := 12345432\ 1323761^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0676239^2 + 126444318000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1323761^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0676239^2 + 1264444318000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1323761^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0676239^2 + 12644444318000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1323761^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0676239^2 + 126444444318000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1323761^2 \end{aligned}$$

570)

$$\begin{aligned} &0675100^2 + 1140000^2 && := 1324900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0675100^2 + 12540000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1324900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0675100^2 + 126540000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1324900^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0675100^2 + 1266540000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1324900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0675100^2 + 12666540000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1324900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0675100^2 + 126666540000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1324900^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0675100^2 + 1266666540000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1324900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0675100^2 + 12666666540000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1324900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0675100^2 + 126666666540000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1324900^2 \end{aligned}$$

571)

$$\begin{aligned} &0673959^2 + 1142000^2 && := 1326041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0673959^2 + 12562000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1326041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0673959^2 + 126762000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1326041^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0673959^2 + 1268762000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1326041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0673959^2 + 12688762000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1326041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0673959^2 + 126888762000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1326041^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0673959^2 + 1268888762000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1326041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0673959^2 + 12688888762000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1326041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0673959^2 + 126888888762000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1326041^2 \end{aligned}$$

572)

$$\begin{aligned} &0672816^2 + 1144000^2 && := 1327184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0672816^2 + 12584000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1327184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0672816^2 + 126984000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1327184^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0672816^2 + 1270984000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1327184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0672816^2 + 12710984000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1327184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0672816^2 + 127110984000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1327184^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0672816^2 + 1271110984000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1327184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0672816^2 + 12711110984000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1327184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0672816^2 + 127111110984000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1327184^2 \end{aligned}$$

573)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0671671^2 + 1146000^2 & := & 1328329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0671671^2 + 12606000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1328329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0671671^2 + 127206000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1328329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0671671^2 + 1273206000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1328329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0671671^2 + 12733206000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1328329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0671671^2 + 127333206000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1328329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0671671^2 + 1273333206000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1328329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0671671^2 + 12733333206000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1328329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0671671^2 + 127333333206000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1328329^2 \end{aligned}$$

574)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0670524^2 + 1148000^2 & := & 1329476^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0670524^2 + 12628000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1329476^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0670524^2 + 127428000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1329476^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0670524^2 + 1275428000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1329476^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0670524^2 + 12755428000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1329476^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0670524^2 + 127555428000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1329476^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0670524^2 + 1275555428000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1329476^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0670524^2 + 12755555428000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1329476^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0670524^2 + 127555555428000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1329476^2 \end{aligned}$$

575)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0669375^2 + 1150000^2 & := & 1330625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0669375^2 + 12650000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1330625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0669375^2 + 127650000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1330625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0669375^2 + 1277650000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1330625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0669375^2 + 12777650000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1330625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0669375^2 + 127777650000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1330625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0669375^2 + 1277777650000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1330625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0669375^2 + 12777777650000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1330625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0669375^2 + 127777777650000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1330625^2 \end{aligned}$$

576)

$$\begin{aligned} &0668224^2 + 1152000^2 && := 1331776^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0668224^2 + 12672000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1331776^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0668224^2 + 127872000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1331776^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0668224^2 + 1279872000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1331776^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0668224^2 + 12799872000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1331776^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0668224^2 + 127999872000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1331776^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0668224^2 + 1279999872000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1331776^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0668224^2 + 12799999872000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1331776^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0668224^2 + 127999999872000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1331776^2 \end{aligned}$$

577)

$$\begin{aligned} &0667071^2 + 1154000^2 && := 1332929^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0667071^2 + 12694000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1332929^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0667071^2 + 128094000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1332929^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0667071^2 + 1282094000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1332929^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0667071^2 + 12822094000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1332929^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0667071^2 + 128222094000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1332929^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0667071^2 + 1282222094000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1332929^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0667071^2 + 12822222094000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1332929^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0667071^2 + 128222222094000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1332929^2 \end{aligned}$$

578)

$$\begin{aligned} &0665916^2 + 1156000^2 && := 1334084^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0665916^2 + 12716000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1334084^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0665916^2 + 128316000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1334084^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0665916^2 + 1284316000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1334084^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0665916^2 + 12844316000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1334084^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0665916^2 + 128444316000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1334084^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0665916^2 + 1284444316000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1334084^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0665916^2 + 12844444316000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1334084^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0665916^2 + 128444444316000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1334084^2 \end{aligned}$$

579)

$$\begin{aligned} &0664759^2 + 1158000^2 && := 1335241^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0664759^2 + 12738000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1335241^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0664759^2 + 128538000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1335241^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0664759^2 + 1286538000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1335241^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0664759^2 + 12866538000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1335241^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0664759^2 + 128666538000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1335241^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0664759^2 + 1286666538000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1335241^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0664759^2 + 12866666538000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1335241^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0664759^2 + 128666666538000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1335241^2 \end{aligned}$$

580)

$$\begin{aligned} &0663600^2 + 1160000^2 && := 1336400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0663600^2 + 12760000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1336400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0663600^2 + 128760000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1336400^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0663600^2 + 1288760000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1336400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0663600^2 + 12888760000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1336400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0663600^2 + 128888760000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1336400^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0663600^2 + 1288888760000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1336400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0663600^2 + 12888888760000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1336400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0663600^2 + 128888888760000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1336400^2 \end{aligned}$$

581)

$$\begin{aligned} &0662439^2 + 1162000^2 && := 1337561^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0662439^2 + 12782000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1337561^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0662439^2 + 128982000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1337561^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0662439^2 + 1290982000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1337561^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0662439^2 + 12910982000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1337561^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0662439^2 + 129110982000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1337561^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0662439^2 + 1291110982000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1337561^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0662439^2 + 12911110982000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1337561^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0662439^2 + 129111110982000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1337561^2 \end{aligned}$$

582)

$$\begin{aligned} &0661276^2 + 1164000^2 &:=& 1338724^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0661276^2 + 12804000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1338724^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0661276^2 + 129204000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1338724^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0661276^2 + 1293204000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1338724^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0661276^2 + 12933204000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1338724^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0661276^2 + 129333204000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1338724^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0661276^2 + 1293333204000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1338724^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0661276^2 + 12933333204000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1338724^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0661276^2 + 129333333204000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1338724^2 \end{aligned}$$

583)

$$\begin{aligned} &0660111^2 + 1166000^2 &:=& 1339889^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0660111^2 + 12826000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1339889^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0660111^2 + 129426000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1339889^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0660111^2 + 1295426000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1339889^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0660111^2 + 12955426000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1339889^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0660111^2 + 129555426000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1339889^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0660111^2 + 1295555426000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1339889^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0660111^2 + 12955555426000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1339889^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0660111^2 + 129555555426000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1339889^2 \end{aligned}$$

584)

$$\begin{aligned} &0658944^2 + 1168000^2 &:=& 1341056^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0658944^2 + 12848000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1341056^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0658944^2 + 129648000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1341056^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0658944^2 + 1297648000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1341056^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0658944^2 + 12977648000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1341056^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0658944^2 + 129777648000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1341056^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0658944^2 + 1297777648000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1341056^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0658944^2 + 12977777648000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1341056^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0658944^2 + 129777777648000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1341056^2 \end{aligned}$$

585)

$$\begin{aligned} &0657775^2 + 1170000^2 && := 1342225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0657775^2 + 12870000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1342225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0657775^2 + 129870000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1342225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0657775^2 + 1299870000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1342225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0657775^2 + 12999870000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1342225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0657775^2 + 129999870000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1342225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0657775^2 + 1299999870000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1342225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0657775^2 + 12999999870000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1342225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0657775^2 + 129999999870000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1342225^2 \end{aligned}$$

586)

$$\begin{aligned} &0656604^2 + 1172000^2 && := 1343396^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0656604^2 + 12892000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1343396^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0656604^2 + 130092000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1343396^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0656604^2 + 1302092000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1343396^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0656604^2 + 13022092000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1343396^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0656604^2 + 130222092000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1343396^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0656604^2 + 1302222092000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1343396^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0656604^2 + 13022222092000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1343396^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0656604^2 + 130222222092000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1343396^2 \end{aligned}$$

587)

$$\begin{aligned} &0655431^2 + 1174000^2 && := 1344569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0655431^2 + 12914000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1344569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0655431^2 + 130314000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1344569^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0655431^2 + 1304314000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1344569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0655431^2 + 13044314000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1344569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0655431^2 + 130444314000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1344569^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0655431^2 + 1304444314000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1344569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0655431^2 + 13044444314000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1344569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0655431^2 + 130444444314000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1344569^2 \end{aligned}$$

588)

$$\begin{aligned} &0654256^2 + 1176000^2 && := 1345744^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0654256^2 + 12936000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1345744^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0654256^2 + 130536000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1345744^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0654256^2 + 1306536000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1345744^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0654256^2 + 13066536000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1345744^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0654256^2 + 130666536000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1345744^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0654256^2 + 1306666536000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1345744^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0654256^2 + 13066666536000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1345744^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0654256^2 + 130666666536000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1345744^2 \end{aligned}$$

589)

$$\begin{aligned} &0653079^2 + 1178000^2 && := 1346921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0653079^2 + 12958000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1346921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0653079^2 + 130758000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1346921^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0653079^2 + 1308758000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1346921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0653079^2 + 13088758000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1346921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0653079^2 + 130888758000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1346921^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0653079^2 + 1308888758000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1346921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0653079^2 + 13088888758000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1346921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0653079^2 + 130888888758000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1346921^2 \end{aligned}$$

590)

$$\begin{aligned} &0651900^2 + 1180000^2 && := 1348100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0651900^2 + 12980000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1348100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0651900^2 + 130980000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1348100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0651900^2 + 1310980000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1348100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0651900^2 + 13110980000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1348100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0651900^2 + 131110980000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1348100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0651900^2 + 1311110980000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1348100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0651900^2 + 13111110980000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1348100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0651900^2 + 131111110980000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1348100^2 \end{aligned}$$

591)

$$\begin{aligned} &0650719^2 + 1182000^2 && := 1349281^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0650719^2 + 13002000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1349281^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0650719^2 + 131202000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1349281^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0650719^2 + 1313202000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1349281^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0650719^2 + 13133202000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1349281^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0650719^2 + 131333202000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1349281^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0650719^2 + 1313333202000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1349281^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0650719^2 + 13133333202000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1349281^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0650719^2 + 131333333202000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1349281^2 \end{aligned}$$

592)

$$\begin{aligned} &0649536^2 + 1184000^2 && := 1350464^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0649536^2 + 13024000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1350464^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0649536^2 + 131424000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1350464^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0649536^2 + 1315424000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1350464^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0649536^2 + 13155424000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1350464^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0649536^2 + 131555424000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1350464^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0649536^2 + 1315555424000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1350464^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0649536^2 + 13155555424000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1350464^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0649536^2 + 131555555424000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1350464^2 \end{aligned}$$

593)

$$\begin{aligned} &0648351^2 + 1186000^2 && := 1351649^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0648351^2 + 13046000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1351649^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0648351^2 + 131646000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1351649^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0648351^2 + 1317646000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1351649^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0648351^2 + 13177646000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1351649^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0648351^2 + 131777646000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1351649^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0648351^2 + 1317777646000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1351649^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0648351^2 + 13177777646000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1351649^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0648351^2 + 131777777646000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1351649^2 \end{aligned}$$

594)

$$\begin{aligned} &0647164^2 + 1188000^2 && := 1352836^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0647164^2 + 13068000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1352836^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0647164^2 + 131868000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1352836^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0647164^2 + 1319868000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1352836^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0647164^2 + 13199868000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1352836^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0647164^2 + 131999868000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1352836^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0647164^2 + 1319999868000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1352836^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0647164^2 + 13199999868000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1352836^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0647164^2 + 131999999868000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1352836^2 \end{aligned}$$

595)

$$\begin{aligned} &0645975^2 + 1190000^2 && := 1354025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0645975^2 + 13090000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1354025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0645975^2 + 132090000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1354025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0645975^2 + 1322090000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1354025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0645975^2 + 13222090000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1354025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0645975^2 + 132222090000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1354025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0645975^2 + 1322222090000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1354025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0645975^2 + 13222222090000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1354025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0645975^2 + 132222222090000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1354025^2 \end{aligned}$$

596)

$$\begin{aligned} &0644784^2 + 1192000^2 && := 1355216^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0644784^2 + 13112000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1355216^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0644784^2 + 132312000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1355216^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0644784^2 + 1324312000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1355216^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0644784^2 + 13244312000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1355216^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0644784^2 + 132444312000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1355216^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0644784^2 + 1324444312000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1355216^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0644784^2 + 13244444312000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1355216^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0644784^2 + 132444444312000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1355216^2 \end{aligned}$$

597)

$$\begin{aligned} &0643591^2 + 1194000^2 && := 1356409^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0643591^2 + 13134000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1356409^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0643591^2 + 132534000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1356409^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0643591^2 + 1326534000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1356409^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0643591^2 + 13266534000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1356409^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0643591^2 + 132666534000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1356409^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0643591^2 + 1326666534000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1356409^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0643591^2 + 13266666534000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1356409^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0643591^2 + 132666666534000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1356409^2 \end{aligned}$$

598)

$$\begin{aligned} &0642396^2 + 1196000^2 && := 1357604^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0642396^2 + 13156000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1357604^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0642396^2 + 132756000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1357604^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0642396^2 + 1328756000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1357604^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0642396^2 + 13288756000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1357604^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0642396^2 + 132888756000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1357604^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0642396^2 + 1328888756000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1357604^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0642396^2 + 13288888756000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1357604^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0642396^2 + 132888888756000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1357604^2 \end{aligned}$$

599)

$$\begin{aligned} &0641199^2 + 1198000^2 && := 1358801^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0641199^2 + 13178000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1358801^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0641199^2 + 132978000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1358801^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0641199^2 + 1330978000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1358801^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0641199^2 + 13310978000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1358801^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0641199^2 + 133110978000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1358801^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0641199^2 + 1331110978000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1358801^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0641199^2 + 13311110978000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1358801^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0641199^2 + 133111110978000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1358801^2 \end{aligned}$$

600)

$$\begin{aligned} &0640000^2 + 1200000^2 && := 1360000^2 \\ &12\ 0640000^2 + 13200000^2 && := 12\ 1360000^2 \\ &1232\ 0640000^2 + 133200000^2 && := 1232\ 1360000^2 \\ &123432\ 0640000^2 + 1333200000^2 && := 123432\ 1360000^2 \\ &12345432\ 0640000^2 + 13333200000^2 && := 12345432\ 1360000^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0640000^2 + 133333200000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1360000^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0640000^2 + 1333333200000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1360000^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0640000^2 + 13333333200000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1360000^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0640000^2 + 133333333200000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1360000^2 \end{aligned}$$

601)

$$\begin{aligned} &0638799^2 + 1202000^2 && := 1361201^2 \\ &12\ 0638799^2 + 13222000^2 && := 12\ 1361201^2 \\ &1232\ 0638799^2 + 133422000^2 && := 1232\ 1361201^2 \\ &123432\ 0638799^2 + 1335422000^2 && := 123432\ 1361201^2 \\ &12345432\ 0638799^2 + 13355422000^2 && := 12345432\ 1361201^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0638799^2 + 133555422000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1361201^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0638799^2 + 1335555422000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1361201^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0638799^2 + 13355555422000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1361201^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0638799^2 + 133555555422000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1361201^2 \end{aligned}$$

602)

$$\begin{aligned} &0637596^2 + 1204000^2 && := 1362404^2 \\ &12\ 0637596^2 + 13244000^2 && := 12\ 1362404^2 \\ &1232\ 0637596^2 + 133644000^2 && := 1232\ 1362404^2 \\ &123432\ 0637596^2 + 1337644000^2 && := 123432\ 1362404^2 \\ &12345432\ 0637596^2 + 13377644000^2 && := 12345432\ 1362404^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0637596^2 + 133777644000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1362404^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0637596^2 + 1337777644000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1362404^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0637596^2 + 13377777644000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1362404^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0637596^2 + 133777777644000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1362404^2 \end{aligned}$$

603)

$$\begin{aligned}0636391^2 + 1206000^2 &:= 1363609^2 \\12\ 0636391^2 + 13266000^2 &:= 12\ 1363609^2 \\1232\ 0636391^2 + 133866000^2 &:= 1232\ 1363609^2 \\123432\ 0636391^2 + 1339866000^2 &:= 123432\ 1363609^2 \\12345432\ 0636391^2 + 13399866000^2 &:= 12345432\ 1363609^2 \\1234565432\ 0636391^2 + 133999866000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 1363609^2 \\123456765432\ 0636391^2 + 1339999866000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 1363609^2 \\12345678765432\ 0636391^2 + 13399999866000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 1363609^2 \\1234567898765432\ 0636391^2 + 133999999866000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 1363609^2\end{aligned}$$

604)

$$\begin{aligned}0635184^2 + 1208000^2 &:= 1364816^2 \\12\ 0635184^2 + 13288000^2 &:= 12\ 1364816^2 \\1232\ 0635184^2 + 134088000^2 &:= 1232\ 1364816^2 \\123432\ 0635184^2 + 1342088000^2 &:= 123432\ 1364816^2 \\12345432\ 0635184^2 + 13422088000^2 &:= 12345432\ 1364816^2 \\1234565432\ 0635184^2 + 134222088000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 1364816^2 \\123456765432\ 0635184^2 + 1342222088000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 1364816^2 \\12345678765432\ 0635184^2 + 13422222088000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 1364816^2 \\1234567898765432\ 0635184^2 + 134222222088000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 1364816^2\end{aligned}$$

605)

$$\begin{aligned}0633975^2 + 1210000^2 &:= 1366025^2 \\12\ 0633975^2 + 13310000^2 &:= 12\ 1366025^2 \\1232\ 0633975^2 + 134310000^2 &:= 1232\ 1366025^2 \\123432\ 0633975^2 + 1344310000^2 &:= 123432\ 1366025^2 \\12345432\ 0633975^2 + 13444310000^2 &:= 12345432\ 1366025^2 \\1234565432\ 0633975^2 + 134444310000^2 &:= 1234565432\ 1366025^2 \\123456765432\ 0633975^2 + 1344444310000^2 &:= 123456765432\ 1366025^2 \\12345678765432\ 0633975^2 + 13444444310000^2 &:= 12345678765432\ 1366025^2 \\1234567898765432\ 0633975^2 + 134444444310000^2 &:= 1234567898765432\ 1366025^2\end{aligned}$$

606)

$$\begin{aligned} &0632764^2 + 1212000^2 && := 1367236^2 \\ &12\ 0632764^2 + 13332000^2 && := 12\ 1367236^2 \\ &1232\ 0632764^2 + 134532000^2 && := 1232\ 1367236^2 \\ &123432\ 0632764^2 + 1346532000^2 && := 123432\ 1367236^2 \\ &12345432\ 0632764^2 + 13466532000^2 && := 12345432\ 1367236^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0632764^2 + 134666532000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1367236^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0632764^2 + 1346666532000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1367236^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0632764^2 + 13466666532000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1367236^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0632764^2 + 134666666532000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1367236^2 \end{aligned}$$

607)

$$\begin{aligned} &0631551^2 + 1214000^2 && := 1368449^2 \\ &12\ 0631551^2 + 13354000^2 && := 12\ 1368449^2 \\ &1232\ 0631551^2 + 134754000^2 && := 1232\ 1368449^2 \\ &123432\ 0631551^2 + 1348754000^2 && := 123432\ 1368449^2 \\ &12345432\ 0631551^2 + 13488754000^2 && := 12345432\ 1368449^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0631551^2 + 134888754000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1368449^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0631551^2 + 1348888754000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1368449^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0631551^2 + 13488888754000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1368449^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0631551^2 + 134888888754000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1368449^2 \end{aligned}$$

608)

$$\begin{aligned} &0630336^2 + 1216000^2 && := 1369664^2 \\ &12\ 0630336^2 + 13376000^2 && := 12\ 1369664^2 \\ &1232\ 0630336^2 + 134976000^2 && := 1232\ 1369664^2 \\ &123432\ 0630336^2 + 1350976000^2 && := 123432\ 1369664^2 \\ &12345432\ 0630336^2 + 13510976000^2 && := 12345432\ 1369664^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0630336^2 + 135110976000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1369664^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0630336^2 + 1351110976000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1369664^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0630336^2 + 13511110976000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1369664^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0630336^2 + 135111110976000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1369664^2 \end{aligned}$$

609)

$$\begin{aligned} &0629119^2 + 1218000^2 && := 1370881^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0629119^2 + 13398000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1370881^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0629119^2 + 135198000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1370881^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0629119^2 + 1353198000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1370881^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0629119^2 + 13533198000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1370881^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0629119^2 + 135333198000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1370881^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0629119^2 + 1353333198000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1370881^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0629119^2 + 13533333198000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1370881^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0629119^2 + 135333333198000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1370881^2 \end{aligned}$$

610)

$$\begin{aligned} &0627900^2 + 1220000^2 && := 1372100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0627900^2 + 13420000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1372100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0627900^2 + 135420000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1372100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0627900^2 + 1355420000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1372100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0627900^2 + 13555420000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1372100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0627900^2 + 135555420000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1372100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0627900^2 + 1355555420000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1372100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0627900^2 + 13555555420000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1372100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0627900^2 + 135555555420000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1372100^2 \end{aligned}$$

611)

$$\begin{aligned} &0626679^2 + 1222000^2 && := 1373321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0626679^2 + 13442000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1373321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0626679^2 + 135642000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1373321^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0626679^2 + 1357642000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1373321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0626679^2 + 13577642000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1373321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0626679^2 + 135777642000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1373321^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0626679^2 + 1357777642000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1373321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0626679^2 + 13577777642000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1373321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0626679^2 + 135777777642000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1373321^2 \end{aligned}$$

612)

$$\begin{aligned} &0625456^2 + 1224000^2 && := 1374544^2 \\ &12\ 0625456^2 + 13464000^2 && := 12\ 1374544^2 \\ &1232\ 0625456^2 + 135864000^2 && := 1232\ 1374544^2 \\ &123432\ 0625456^2 + 1359864000^2 && := 123432\ 1374544^2 \\ &12345432\ 0625456^2 + 13599864000^2 && := 12345432\ 1374544^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0625456^2 + 135999864000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1374544^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0625456^2 + 1359999864000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1374544^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0625456^2 + 13599999864000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1374544^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0625456^2 + 135999999864000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1374544^2 \end{aligned}$$

613)

$$\begin{aligned} &0624231^2 + 1226000^2 && := 1375769^2 \\ &12\ 0624231^2 + 13486000^2 && := 12\ 1375769^2 \\ &1232\ 0624231^2 + 136086000^2 && := 1232\ 1375769^2 \\ &123432\ 0624231^2 + 1362086000^2 && := 123432\ 1375769^2 \\ &12345432\ 0624231^2 + 13622086000^2 && := 12345432\ 1375769^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0624231^2 + 136222086000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1375769^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0624231^2 + 1362222086000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1375769^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0624231^2 + 13622222086000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1375769^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0624231^2 + 136222222086000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1375769^2 \end{aligned}$$

614)

$$\begin{aligned} &0623004^2 + 1228000^2 && := 1376996^2 \\ &12\ 0623004^2 + 13508000^2 && := 12\ 1376996^2 \\ &1232\ 0623004^2 + 136308000^2 && := 1232\ 1376996^2 \\ &123432\ 0623004^2 + 1364308000^2 && := 123432\ 1376996^2 \\ &12345432\ 0623004^2 + 13644308000^2 && := 12345432\ 1376996^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0623004^2 + 136444308000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1376996^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0623004^2 + 1364444308000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1376996^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0623004^2 + 13644444308000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1376996^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0623004^2 + 136444444308000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1376996^2 \end{aligned}$$

615)

$$\begin{aligned} &0621775^2 + 1230000^2 && := 1378225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0621775^2 + 13530000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1378225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0621775^2 + 136530000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1378225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0621775^2 + 1366530000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1378225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0621775^2 + 13666530000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1378225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0621775^2 + 136666530000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1378225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0621775^2 + 1366666530000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1378225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0621775^2 + 13666666530000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1378225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0621775^2 + 136666666530000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1378225^2 \end{aligned}$$

616)

$$\begin{aligned} &0620544^2 + 1232000^2 && := 1379456^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0620544^2 + 13552000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1379456^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0620544^2 + 136752000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1379456^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0620544^2 + 1368752000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1379456^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0620544^2 + 13688752000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1379456^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0620544^2 + 136888752000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1379456^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0620544^2 + 1368888752000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1379456^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0620544^2 + 13688888752000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1379456^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0620544^2 + 136888888752000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1379456^2 \end{aligned}$$

617)

$$\begin{aligned} &0619311^2 + 1234000^2 && := 1380689^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0619311^2 + 13574000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1380689^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0619311^2 + 136974000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1380689^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0619311^2 + 1370974000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1380689^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0619311^2 + 13710974000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1380689^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0619311^2 + 137110974000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1380689^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0619311^2 + 1371110974000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1380689^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0619311^2 + 13711110974000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1380689^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0619311^2 + 137111110974000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1380689^2 \end{aligned}$$

618)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0618076^2 + 1236000^2 & := & 1381924^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0618076^2 + 13596000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1381924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0618076^2 + 137196000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1381924^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0618076^2 + 1373196000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1381924^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0618076^2 + 13733196000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1381924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0618076^2 + 137333196000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1381924^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0618076^2 + 1373333196000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1381924^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0618076^2 + 13733333196000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1381924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0618076^2 + 137333333196000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1381924^2 \end{aligned}$$

619)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0616839^2 + 1238000^2 & := & 1383161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0616839^2 + 13618000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1383161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0616839^2 + 137418000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1383161^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0616839^2 + 1375418000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1383161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0616839^2 + 13755418000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1383161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0616839^2 + 137555418000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1383161^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0616839^2 + 1375555418000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1383161^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0616839^2 + 13755555418000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1383161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0616839^2 + 137555555418000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1383161^2 \end{aligned}$$

620)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0615600^2 + 1240000^2 & := & 1384400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0615600^2 + 13640000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1384400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0615600^2 + 137640000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1384400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0615600^2 + 1377640000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1384400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0615600^2 + 13777640000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1384400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0615600^2 + 137777640000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1384400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0615600^2 + 1377777640000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1384400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0615600^2 + 13777777640000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1384400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0615600^2 + 137777777640000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1384400^2 \end{aligned}$$

621)

$$\begin{aligned} &0614359^2 + 1242000^2 && := 1385641^2 \\ &12\ 0614359^2 + 13662000^2 && := 12\ 1385641^2 \\ &1232\ 0614359^2 + 137862000^2 && := 1232\ 1385641^2 \\ &123432\ 0614359^2 + 1379862000^2 && := 123432\ 1385641^2 \\ &12345432\ 0614359^2 + 13799862000^2 && := 12345432\ 1385641^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0614359^2 + 137999862000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1385641^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0614359^2 + 1379999862000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1385641^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0614359^2 + 13799999862000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1385641^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0614359^2 + 137999999862000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1385641^2 \end{aligned}$$

622)

$$\begin{aligned} &0613116^2 + 1244000^2 && := 1386884^2 \\ &12\ 0613116^2 + 13684000^2 && := 12\ 1386884^2 \\ &1232\ 0613116^2 + 138084000^2 && := 1232\ 1386884^2 \\ &123432\ 0613116^2 + 1382084000^2 && := 123432\ 1386884^2 \\ &12345432\ 0613116^2 + 13822084000^2 && := 12345432\ 1386884^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0613116^2 + 138222084000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1386884^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0613116^2 + 1382222084000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1386884^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0613116^2 + 13822222084000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1386884^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0613116^2 + 138222222084000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1386884^2 \end{aligned}$$

623)

$$\begin{aligned} &0611871^2 + 1246000^2 && := 1388129^2 \\ &12\ 0611871^2 + 13706000^2 && := 12\ 1388129^2 \\ &1232\ 0611871^2 + 138306000^2 && := 1232\ 1388129^2 \\ &123432\ 0611871^2 + 1384306000^2 && := 123432\ 1388129^2 \\ &12345432\ 0611871^2 + 13844306000^2 && := 12345432\ 1388129^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0611871^2 + 138444306000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1388129^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0611871^2 + 1384444306000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1388129^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0611871^2 + 13844444306000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1388129^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0611871^2 + 138444444306000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1388129^2 \end{aligned}$$

624)

$$\begin{aligned} &0610624^2 + 1248000^2 && := 1389376^2 \\ &12\ 0610624^2 + 13728000^2 && := 12\ 1389376^2 \\ &1232\ 0610624^2 + 138528000^2 && := 1232\ 1389376^2 \\ &123432\ 0610624^2 + 1386528000^2 && := 123432\ 1389376^2 \\ &12345432\ 0610624^2 + 13866528000^2 && := 12345432\ 1389376^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0610624^2 + 138666528000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1389376^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0610624^2 + 1386666528000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1389376^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0610624^2 + 13866666528000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1389376^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0610624^2 + 138666666528000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1389376^2 \end{aligned}$$

625)

$$\begin{aligned} &0609375^2 + 1250000^2 && := 1390625^2 \\ &12\ 0609375^2 + 13750000^2 && := 12\ 1390625^2 \\ &1232\ 0609375^2 + 138750000^2 && := 1232\ 1390625^2 \\ &123432\ 0609375^2 + 1388750000^2 && := 123432\ 1390625^2 \\ &12345432\ 0609375^2 + 13888750000^2 && := 12345432\ 1390625^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0609375^2 + 138888750000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1390625^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0609375^2 + 1388888750000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1390625^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0609375^2 + 13888888750000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1390625^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0609375^2 + 138888888750000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1390625^2 \end{aligned}$$

626)

$$\begin{aligned} &0608124^2 + 1252000^2 && := 1391876^2 \\ &12\ 0608124^2 + 13772000^2 && := 12\ 1391876^2 \\ &1232\ 0608124^2 + 138972000^2 && := 1232\ 1391876^2 \\ &123432\ 0608124^2 + 1390972000^2 && := 123432\ 1391876^2 \\ &12345432\ 0608124^2 + 13910972000^2 && := 12345432\ 1391876^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0608124^2 + 139110972000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1391876^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0608124^2 + 1391110972000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1391876^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0608124^2 + 13911110972000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1391876^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0608124^2 + 139111110972000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1391876^2 \end{aligned}$$

627)

$$\begin{aligned} &0606871^2 + 1254000^2 && := 1393129^2 \\ &12\ 0606871^2 + 13794000^2 && := 12\ 1393129^2 \\ &1232\ 0606871^2 + 139194000^2 && := 1232\ 1393129^2 \\ &123432\ 0606871^2 + 1393194000^2 && := 123432\ 1393129^2 \\ &12345432\ 0606871^2 + 13933194000^2 && := 12345432\ 1393129^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0606871^2 + 139333194000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1393129^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0606871^2 + 1393333194000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1393129^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0606871^2 + 13933333194000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1393129^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0606871^2 + 139333333194000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1393129^2 \end{aligned}$$

628)

$$\begin{aligned} &0605616^2 + 1256000^2 && := 1394384^2 \\ &12\ 0605616^2 + 13816000^2 && := 12\ 1394384^2 \\ &1232\ 0605616^2 + 139416000^2 && := 1232\ 1394384^2 \\ &123432\ 0605616^2 + 1395416000^2 && := 123432\ 1394384^2 \\ &12345432\ 0605616^2 + 13955416000^2 && := 12345432\ 1394384^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0605616^2 + 139555416000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1394384^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0605616^2 + 1395555416000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1394384^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0605616^2 + 13955555416000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1394384^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0605616^2 + 139555555416000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1394384^2 \end{aligned}$$

629)

$$\begin{aligned} &0604359^2 + 1258000^2 && := 1395641^2 \\ &12\ 0604359^2 + 13838000^2 && := 12\ 1395641^2 \\ &1232\ 0604359^2 + 139638000^2 && := 1232\ 1395641^2 \\ &123432\ 0604359^2 + 1397638000^2 && := 123432\ 1395641^2 \\ &12345432\ 0604359^2 + 13977638000^2 && := 12345432\ 1395641^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0604359^2 + 139777638000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1395641^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0604359^2 + 1397777638000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1395641^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0604359^2 + 13977777638000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1395641^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0604359^2 + 139777777638000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1395641^2 \end{aligned}$$

630)

$$\begin{aligned} &0603100^2 + 1260000^2 && := 1396900^2 \\ &12\ 0603100^2 + 13860000^2 && := 12\ 1396900^2 \\ &1232\ 0603100^2 + 139860000^2 && := 1232\ 1396900^2 \\ &123432\ 0603100^2 + 1399860000^2 && := 123432\ 1396900^2 \\ &12345432\ 0603100^2 + 13999860000^2 && := 12345432\ 1396900^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0603100^2 + 139999860000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1396900^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0603100^2 + 1399999860000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1396900^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0603100^2 + 13999999860000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1396900^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0603100^2 + 139999999860000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1396900^2 \end{aligned}$$

631)

$$\begin{aligned} &0601839^2 + 1262000^2 && := 1398161^2 \\ &12\ 0601839^2 + 13882000^2 && := 12\ 1398161^2 \\ &1232\ 0601839^2 + 140082000^2 && := 1232\ 1398161^2 \\ &123432\ 0601839^2 + 1402082000^2 && := 123432\ 1398161^2 \\ &12345432\ 0601839^2 + 14022082000^2 && := 12345432\ 1398161^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0601839^2 + 140222082000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1398161^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0601839^2 + 1402222082000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1398161^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0601839^2 + 14022222082000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1398161^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0601839^2 + 140222222082000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1398161^2 \end{aligned}$$

632)

$$\begin{aligned} &0600576^2 + 1264000^2 && := 1399424^2 \\ &12\ 0600576^2 + 13904000^2 && := 12\ 1399424^2 \\ &1232\ 0600576^2 + 140304000^2 && := 1232\ 1399424^2 \\ &123432\ 0600576^2 + 1404304000^2 && := 123432\ 1399424^2 \\ &12345432\ 0600576^2 + 14044304000^2 && := 12345432\ 1399424^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0600576^2 + 140444304000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1399424^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0600576^2 + 1404444304000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1399424^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0600576^2 + 14044444304000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1399424^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0600576^2 + 140444444304000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1399424^2 \end{aligned}$$

633)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0599311^2 + 1266000^2 & := & 1400689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0599311^2 + 13926000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1400689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0599311^2 + 140526000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1400689^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0599311^2 + 1406526000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1400689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0599311^2 + 14066526000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1400689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0599311^2 + 140666526000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1400689^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0599311^2 + 1406666526000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1400689^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0599311^2 + 14066666526000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1400689^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0599311^2 + 140666666526000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1400689^2 \end{aligned}$$

634)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0598044^2 + 1268000^2 & := & 1401956^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0598044^2 + 13948000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1401956^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0598044^2 + 140748000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1401956^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0598044^2 + 1408748000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1401956^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0598044^2 + 14088748000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1401956^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0598044^2 + 140888748000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1401956^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0598044^2 + 1408888748000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1401956^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0598044^2 + 14088888748000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1401956^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0598044^2 + 140888888748000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1401956^2 \end{aligned}$$

635)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0596775^2 + 1270000^2 & := & 1403225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0596775^2 + 13970000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1403225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0596775^2 + 140970000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1403225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0596775^2 + 1410970000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1403225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0596775^2 + 14110970000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1403225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0596775^2 + 141110970000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1403225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0596775^2 + 1411110970000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1403225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0596775^2 + 14111110970000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1403225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0596775^2 + 141111110970000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1403225^2 \end{aligned}$$

636)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0595504^2 + 1272000^2 & := & 1404496^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0595504^2 + 13992000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1404496^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0595504^2 + 141192000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1404496^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0595504^2 + 1413192000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1404496^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0595504^2 + 14133192000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1404496^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0595504^2 + 141333192000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1404496^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0595504^2 + 1413333192000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1404496^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0595504^2 + 14133333192000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1404496^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0595504^2 + 141333333192000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1404496^2 \end{aligned}$$

637)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0594231^2 + 1274000^2 & := & 1405769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0594231^2 + 14014000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1405769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0594231^2 + 141414000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1405769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0594231^2 + 1415414000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1405769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0594231^2 + 14155414000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1405769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0594231^2 + 141555414000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1405769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0594231^2 + 1415555414000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1405769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0594231^2 + 14155555414000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1405769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0594231^2 + 141555555414000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1405769^2 \end{aligned}$$

638)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0592956^2 + 1276000^2 & := & 1407044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0592956^2 + 14036000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1407044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0592956^2 + 141636000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1407044^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0592956^2 + 1417636000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1407044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0592956^2 + 14177636000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1407044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0592956^2 + 141777636000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1407044^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0592956^2 + 1417777636000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1407044^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0592956^2 + 14177777636000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1407044^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0592956^2 + 141777777636000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1407044^2 \end{aligned}$$

639)

$$\begin{aligned} &0591679^2 + 1278000^2 && := 1408321^2 \\ &12\ 0591679^2 + 14058000^2 && := 12\ 1408321^2 \\ &1232\ 0591679^2 + 141858000^2 && := 1232\ 1408321^2 \\ &123432\ 0591679^2 + 1419858000^2 && := 123432\ 1408321^2 \\ &12345432\ 0591679^2 + 14199858000^2 && := 12345432\ 1408321^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0591679^2 + 141999858000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1408321^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0591679^2 + 1419999858000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1408321^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0591679^2 + 14199999858000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1408321^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0591679^2 + 141999999858000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1408321^2 \end{aligned}$$

640)

$$\begin{aligned} &0590400^2 + 1280000^2 && := 1409600^2 \\ &12\ 0590400^2 + 14080000^2 && := 12\ 1409600^2 \\ &1232\ 0590400^2 + 142080000^2 && := 1232\ 1409600^2 \\ &123432\ 0590400^2 + 1422080000^2 && := 123432\ 1409600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0590400^2 + 14222080000^2 && := 12345432\ 1409600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0590400^2 + 142222080000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1409600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0590400^2 + 1422222080000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1409600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0590400^2 + 14222222080000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1409600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0590400^2 + 142222222080000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1409600^2 \end{aligned}$$

641)

$$\begin{aligned} &0589119^2 + 1282000^2 && := 1410881^2 \\ &12\ 0589119^2 + 14102000^2 && := 12\ 1410881^2 \\ &1232\ 0589119^2 + 142302000^2 && := 1232\ 1410881^2 \\ &123432\ 0589119^2 + 1424302000^2 && := 123432\ 1410881^2 \\ &12345432\ 0589119^2 + 14244302000^2 && := 12345432\ 1410881^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0589119^2 + 142444302000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1410881^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0589119^2 + 1424444302000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1410881^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0589119^2 + 14244444302000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1410881^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0589119^2 + 142444444302000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1410881^2 \end{aligned}$$

642)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0587836^2 + 1284000^2 & := & 1412164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0587836^2 + 14124000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1412164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0587836^2 + 142524000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1412164^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0587836^2 + 1426524000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1412164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0587836^2 + 14266524000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1412164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0587836^2 + 142666524000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1412164^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0587836^2 + 1426666524000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1412164^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0587836^2 + 14266666524000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1412164^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0587836^2 + 142666666524000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1412164^2 \end{aligned}$$

643)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0586551^2 + 1286000^2 & := & 1413449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0586551^2 + 14146000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1413449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0586551^2 + 142746000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1413449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0586551^2 + 1428746000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1413449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0586551^2 + 14288746000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1413449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0586551^2 + 142888746000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1413449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0586551^2 + 1428888746000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1413449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0586551^2 + 14288888746000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1413449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0586551^2 + 142888888746000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1413449^2 \end{aligned}$$

644)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0585264^2 + 1288000^2 & := & 1414736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0585264^2 + 14168000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1414736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0585264^2 + 142968000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1414736^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0585264^2 + 1430968000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1414736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0585264^2 + 14310968000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1414736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0585264^2 + 143110968000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1414736^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0585264^2 + 1431110968000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1414736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0585264^2 + 14311110968000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1414736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0585264^2 + 143111110968000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1414736^2 \end{aligned}$$

645)

$$\begin{aligned} &0583975^2 + 1290000^2 && := 1416025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0583975^2 + 14190000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1416025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0583975^2 + 143190000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1416025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0583975^2 + 1433190000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1416025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0583975^2 + 14333190000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1416025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0583975^2 + 143333190000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1416025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0583975^2 + 1433333190000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1416025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0583975^2 + 14333333190000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1416025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0583975^2 + 143333333190000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1416025^2 \end{aligned}$$

646)

$$\begin{aligned} &0582684^2 + 1292000^2 && := 1417316^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0582684^2 + 14212000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1417316^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0582684^2 + 143412000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1417316^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0582684^2 + 1435412000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1417316^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0582684^2 + 14355412000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1417316^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0582684^2 + 143555412000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1417316^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0582684^2 + 1435555412000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1417316^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0582684^2 + 14355555412000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1417316^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0582684^2 + 143555555412000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1417316^2 \end{aligned}$$

647)

$$\begin{aligned} &0581391^2 + 1294000^2 && := 1418609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0581391^2 + 14234000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1418609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0581391^2 + 143634000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1418609^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0581391^2 + 1437634000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1418609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0581391^2 + 14377634000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1418609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0581391^2 + 143777634000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1418609^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0581391^2 + 1437777634000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1418609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0581391^2 + 14377777634000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1418609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0581391^2 + 143777777634000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1418609^2 \end{aligned}$$

648)

$$\begin{aligned} &0580096^2 + 1296000^2 && := 1419904^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0580096^2 + 14256000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1419904^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0580096^2 + 143856000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1419904^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0580096^2 + 1439856000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1419904^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0580096^2 + 14399856000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1419904^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0580096^2 + 143999856000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1419904^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0580096^2 + 1439999856000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1419904^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0580096^2 + 14399999856000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1419904^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0580096^2 + 143999999856000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1419904^2 \end{aligned}$$

649)

$$\begin{aligned} &0578799^2 + 1298000^2 && := 1421201^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0578799^2 + 14278000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1421201^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0578799^2 + 144078000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1421201^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0578799^2 + 1442078000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1421201^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0578799^2 + 14422078000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1421201^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0578799^2 + 144222078000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1421201^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0578799^2 + 1442222078000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1421201^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0578799^2 + 14422222078000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1421201^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0578799^2 + 144222222078000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1421201^2 \end{aligned}$$

650)

$$\begin{aligned} &0577500^2 + 1300000^2 && := 1422500^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0577500^2 + 14300000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1422500^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0577500^2 + 144300000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1422500^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0577500^2 + 1444300000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1422500^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0577500^2 + 14444300000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1422500^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0577500^2 + 144444300000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1422500^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0577500^2 + 1444444300000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1422500^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0577500^2 + 14444444300000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1422500^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0577500^2 + 144444444300000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1422500^2 \end{aligned}$$

651)

$$\begin{aligned} &0576199^2 + 1302000^2 && := 1423801^2 \\ &12\ 0576199^2 + 14322000^2 && := 12\ 1423801^2 \\ &1232\ 0576199^2 + 144522000^2 && := 1232\ 1423801^2 \\ &123432\ 0576199^2 + 1446522000^2 && := 123432\ 1423801^2 \\ &12345432\ 0576199^2 + 14466522000^2 && := 12345432\ 1423801^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0576199^2 + 144666522000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1423801^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0576199^2 + 1446666522000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1423801^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0576199^2 + 14466666522000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1423801^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0576199^2 + 144666666522000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1423801^2 \end{aligned}$$

652)

$$\begin{aligned} &0574896^2 + 1304000^2 && := 1425104^2 \\ &12\ 0574896^2 + 14344000^2 && := 12\ 1425104^2 \\ &1232\ 0574896^2 + 144744000^2 && := 1232\ 1425104^2 \\ &123432\ 0574896^2 + 1448744000^2 && := 123432\ 1425104^2 \\ &12345432\ 0574896^2 + 14488744000^2 && := 12345432\ 1425104^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0574896^2 + 144888744000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1425104^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0574896^2 + 1448888744000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1425104^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0574896^2 + 14488888744000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1425104^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0574896^2 + 144888888744000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1425104^2 \end{aligned}$$

653)

$$\begin{aligned} &0573591^2 + 1306000^2 && := 1426409^2 \\ &12\ 0573591^2 + 14366000^2 && := 12\ 1426409^2 \\ &1232\ 0573591^2 + 144966000^2 && := 1232\ 1426409^2 \\ &123432\ 0573591^2 + 1450966000^2 && := 123432\ 1426409^2 \\ &12345432\ 0573591^2 + 14510966000^2 && := 12345432\ 1426409^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0573591^2 + 145110966000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1426409^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0573591^2 + 1451110966000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1426409^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0573591^2 + 14511110966000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1426409^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0573591^2 + 145111110966000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1426409^2 \end{aligned}$$

654)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0572284^2 + 1308000^2 & := & 1427716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0572284^2 + 14388000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1427716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0572284^2 + 145188000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1427716^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0572284^2 + 1453188000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1427716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0572284^2 + 14533188000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1427716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0572284^2 + 145333188000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1427716^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0572284^2 + 1453333188000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1427716^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0572284^2 + 14533333188000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1427716^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0572284^2 + 145333333188000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1427716^2 \end{aligned}$$

655)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0570975^2 + 1310000^2 & := & 1429025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0570975^2 + 14410000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1429025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0570975^2 + 145410000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1429025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0570975^2 + 1455410000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1429025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0570975^2 + 14555410000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1429025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0570975^2 + 145555410000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1429025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0570975^2 + 1455555410000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1429025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0570975^2 + 14555555410000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1429025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0570975^2 + 145555555410000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1429025^2 \end{aligned}$$

656)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0569664^2 + 1312000^2 & := & 1430336^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0569664^2 + 14432000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1430336^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0569664^2 + 145632000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1430336^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0569664^2 + 1457632000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1430336^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0569664^2 + 14577632000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1430336^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0569664^2 + 145777632000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1430336^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0569664^2 + 1457777632000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1430336^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0569664^2 + 14577777632000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1430336^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0569664^2 + 145777777632000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1430336^2 \end{aligned}$$

657)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0568351^2 + 1314000^2 & := & 1431649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0568351^2 + 14454000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1431649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0568351^2 + 145854000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1431649^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0568351^2 + 1459854000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1431649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0568351^2 + 14599854000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1431649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0568351^2 + 145999854000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1431649^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0568351^2 + 1459999854000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1431649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0568351^2 + 14599999854000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1431649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0568351^2 + 145999999854000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1431649^2 \end{aligned}$$

658)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0567036^2 + 1316000^2 & := & 1432964^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0567036^2 + 14476000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1432964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0567036^2 + 146076000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1432964^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0567036^2 + 1462076000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1432964^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0567036^2 + 14622076000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1432964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0567036^2 + 146222076000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1432964^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0567036^2 + 1462222076000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1432964^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0567036^2 + 14622222076000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1432964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0567036^2 + 146222222076000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1432964^2 \end{aligned}$$

659)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0565719^2 + 1318000^2 & := & 1434281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0565719^2 + 14498000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1434281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0565719^2 + 146298000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1434281^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0565719^2 + 1464298000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1434281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0565719^2 + 14644298000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1434281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0565719^2 + 146444298000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1434281^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0565719^2 + 1464444298000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1434281^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0565719^2 + 14644444298000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1434281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0565719^2 + 146444444298000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1434281^2 \end{aligned}$$

660)

$$\begin{aligned} &0564400^2 + 1320000^2 && := 1435600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0564400^2 + 14520000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1435600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0564400^2 + 146520000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1435600^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0564400^2 + 1466520000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1435600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0564400^2 + 14666520000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1435600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0564400^2 + 146666520000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1435600^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0564400^2 + 1466666520000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1435600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0564400^2 + 14666666520000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1435600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0564400^2 + 146666666520000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1435600^2 \end{aligned}$$

661)

$$\begin{aligned} &0563079^2 + 1322000^2 && := 1436921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0563079^2 + 14542000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1436921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0563079^2 + 146742000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1436921^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0563079^2 + 1468742000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1436921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0563079^2 + 14688742000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1436921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0563079^2 + 146888742000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1436921^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0563079^2 + 1468888742000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1436921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0563079^2 + 14688888742000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1436921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0563079^2 + 146888888742000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1436921^2 \end{aligned}$$

662)

$$\begin{aligned} &0561756^2 + 1324000^2 && := 1438244^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0561756^2 + 14564000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1438244^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0561756^2 + 146964000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1438244^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0561756^2 + 1470964000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1438244^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0561756^2 + 14710964000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1438244^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0561756^2 + 147110964000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1438244^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0561756^2 + 1471110964000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1438244^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0561756^2 + 14711110964000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1438244^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0561756^2 + 147111110964000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1438244^2 \end{aligned}$$

663)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0560431^2 + 1326000^2 & := & 1439569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0560431^2 + 14586000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1439569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0560431^2 + 147186000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1439569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0560431^2 + 1473186000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1439569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0560431^2 + 14733186000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1439569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0560431^2 + 147333186000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1439569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0560431^2 + 1473333186000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1439569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0560431^2 + 14733333186000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1439569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0560431^2 + 147333333186000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1439569^2 \end{aligned}$$

664)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0559104^2 + 1328000^2 & := & 1440896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0559104^2 + 14608000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1440896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0559104^2 + 147408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1440896^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0559104^2 + 1475408000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1440896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0559104^2 + 14755408000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1440896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0559104^2 + 147555408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1440896^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0559104^2 + 1475555408000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1440896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0559104^2 + 14755555408000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1440896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0559104^2 + 147555555408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1440896^2 \end{aligned}$$

665)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0557775^2 + 1330000^2 & := & 1442225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0557775^2 + 14630000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1442225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0557775^2 + 147630000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1442225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0557775^2 + 1477630000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1442225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0557775^2 + 14777630000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1442225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0557775^2 + 147777630000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1442225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0557775^2 + 1477777630000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1442225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0557775^2 + 14777777630000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1442225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0557775^2 + 147777777630000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1442225^2 \end{aligned}$$

666)

$$\begin{aligned} &0556444^2 + 1332000^2 && := 1443556^2 \\ &12\ 0556444^2 + 14652000^2 && := 12\ 1443556^2 \\ &1232\ 0556444^2 + 147852000^2 && := 1232\ 1443556^2 \\ &123432\ 0556444^2 + 1479852000^2 && := 123432\ 1443556^2 \\ &12345432\ 0556444^2 + 14799852000^2 && := 12345432\ 1443556^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0556444^2 + 147999852000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1443556^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0556444^2 + 1479999852000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1443556^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0556444^2 + 14799999852000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1443556^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0556444^2 + 147999999852000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1443556^2 \end{aligned}$$

667)

$$\begin{aligned} &0555111^2 + 1334000^2 && := 1444889^2 \\ &12\ 0555111^2 + 14674000^2 && := 12\ 1444889^2 \\ &1232\ 0555111^2 + 148074000^2 && := 1232\ 1444889^2 \\ &123432\ 0555111^2 + 1482074000^2 && := 123432\ 1444889^2 \\ &12345432\ 0555111^2 + 14822074000^2 && := 12345432\ 1444889^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0555111^2 + 148222074000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1444889^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0555111^2 + 1482222074000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1444889^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0555111^2 + 14822222074000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1444889^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0555111^2 + 148222222074000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1444889^2 \end{aligned}$$

668)

$$\begin{aligned} &0553776^2 + 1336000^2 && := 1446224^2 \\ &12\ 0553776^2 + 14696000^2 && := 12\ 1446224^2 \\ &1232\ 0553776^2 + 148296000^2 && := 1232\ 1446224^2 \\ &123432\ 0553776^2 + 1484296000^2 && := 123432\ 1446224^2 \\ &12345432\ 0553776^2 + 14844296000^2 && := 12345432\ 1446224^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0553776^2 + 148444296000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1446224^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0553776^2 + 1484444296000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1446224^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0553776^2 + 14844444296000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1446224^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0553776^2 + 148444444296000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1446224^2 \end{aligned}$$

669)

$$\begin{aligned} &0552439^2 + 1338000^2 && := 1447561^2 \\ &12\ 0552439^2 + 14718000^2 && := 12\ 1447561^2 \\ &1232\ 0552439^2 + 148518000^2 && := 1232\ 1447561^2 \\ &123432\ 0552439^2 + 1486518000^2 && := 123432\ 1447561^2 \\ &12345432\ 0552439^2 + 14866518000^2 && := 12345432\ 1447561^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0552439^2 + 148666518000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1447561^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0552439^2 + 1486666518000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1447561^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0552439^2 + 14866666518000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1447561^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0552439^2 + 148666666518000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1447561^2 \end{aligned}$$

670)

$$\begin{aligned} &0551100^2 + 1340000^2 && := 1448900^2 \\ &12\ 0551100^2 + 14740000^2 && := 12\ 1448900^2 \\ &1232\ 0551100^2 + 148740000^2 && := 1232\ 1448900^2 \\ &123432\ 0551100^2 + 1488740000^2 && := 123432\ 1448900^2 \\ &12345432\ 0551100^2 + 14888740000^2 && := 12345432\ 1448900^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0551100^2 + 148888740000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1448900^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0551100^2 + 1488888740000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1448900^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0551100^2 + 14888888740000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1448900^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0551100^2 + 148888888740000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1448900^2 \end{aligned}$$

671)

$$\begin{aligned} &0549759^2 + 1342000^2 && := 1450241^2 \\ &12\ 0549759^2 + 14762000^2 && := 12\ 1450241^2 \\ &1232\ 0549759^2 + 148962000^2 && := 1232\ 1450241^2 \\ &123432\ 0549759^2 + 1490962000^2 && := 123432\ 1450241^2 \\ &12345432\ 0549759^2 + 14910962000^2 && := 12345432\ 1450241^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0549759^2 + 149110962000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1450241^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0549759^2 + 1491110962000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1450241^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0549759^2 + 14911110962000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1450241^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0549759^2 + 149111110962000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1450241^2 \end{aligned}$$

672)

$$\begin{aligned} &0548416^2 + 1344000^2 && := 1451584^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0548416^2 + 14784000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1451584^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0548416^2 + 149184000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1451584^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0548416^2 + 1493184000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1451584^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0548416^2 + 14933184000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1451584^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0548416^2 + 149333184000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1451584^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0548416^2 + 1493333184000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1451584^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0548416^2 + 14933333184000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1451584^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0548416^2 + 149333333184000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1451584^2 \end{aligned}$$

673)

$$\begin{aligned} &0547071^2 + 1346000^2 && := 1452929^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0547071^2 + 14806000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1452929^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0547071^2 + 149406000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1452929^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0547071^2 + 1495406000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1452929^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0547071^2 + 14955406000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1452929^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0547071^2 + 149555406000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1452929^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0547071^2 + 1495555406000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1452929^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0547071^2 + 14955555406000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1452929^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0547071^2 + 149555555406000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1452929^2 \end{aligned}$$

674)

$$\begin{aligned} &0545724^2 + 1348000^2 && := 1454276^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0545724^2 + 14828000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1454276^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0545724^2 + 149628000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1454276^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0545724^2 + 1497628000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1454276^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0545724^2 + 14977628000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1454276^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0545724^2 + 149777628000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1454276^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0545724^2 + 1497777628000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1454276^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0545724^2 + 14977777628000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1454276^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0545724^2 + 149777777628000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1454276^2 \end{aligned}$$

675)

$$\begin{aligned} &0544375^2 + 1350000^2 && := 1455625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0544375^2 + 14850000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1455625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0544375^2 + 149850000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1455625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0544375^2 + 1499850000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1455625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0544375^2 + 14999850000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1455625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0544375^2 + 149999850000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1455625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0544375^2 + 1499999850000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1455625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0544375^2 + 14999999850000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1455625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0544375^2 + 149999999850000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1455625^2 \end{aligned}$$

676)

$$\begin{aligned} &0543024^2 + 1352000^2 && := 1456976^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0543024^2 + 14872000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1456976^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0543024^2 + 150072000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1456976^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0543024^2 + 1502072000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1456976^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0543024^2 + 15022072000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1456976^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0543024^2 + 150222072000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1456976^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0543024^2 + 1502222072000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1456976^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0543024^2 + 15022222072000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1456976^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0543024^2 + 150222222072000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1456976^2 \end{aligned}$$

677)

$$\begin{aligned} &0541671^2 + 1354000^2 && := 1458329^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0541671^2 + 14894000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1458329^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0541671^2 + 150294000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1458329^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0541671^2 + 1504294000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1458329^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0541671^2 + 15044294000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1458329^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0541671^2 + 150444294000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1458329^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0541671^2 + 1504444294000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1458329^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0541671^2 + 15044444294000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1458329^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0541671^2 + 150444444294000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1458329^2 \end{aligned}$$

678)

$$\begin{aligned} &0540316^2 + 1356000^2 && := 1459684^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0540316^2 + 14916000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1459684^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0540316^2 + 150516000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1459684^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0540316^2 + 1506516000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1459684^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0540316^2 + 15066516000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1459684^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0540316^2 + 150666516000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1459684^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0540316^2 + 1506666516000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1459684^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0540316^2 + 15066666516000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1459684^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0540316^2 + 150666666516000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1459684^2 \end{aligned}$$

679)

$$\begin{aligned} &0538959^2 + 1358000^2 && := 1461041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0538959^2 + 14938000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1461041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0538959^2 + 150738000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1461041^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0538959^2 + 1508738000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1461041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0538959^2 + 15088738000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1461041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0538959^2 + 150888738000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1461041^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0538959^2 + 1508888738000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1461041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0538959^2 + 15088888738000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1461041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0538959^2 + 150888888738000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1461041^2 \end{aligned}$$

680)

$$\begin{aligned} &0537600^2 + 1360000^2 && := 1462400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0537600^2 + 14960000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1462400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0537600^2 + 150960000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1462400^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0537600^2 + 1510960000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1462400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0537600^2 + 15110960000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1462400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0537600^2 + 151110960000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1462400^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0537600^2 + 1511110960000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1462400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0537600^2 + 15111110960000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1462400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0537600^2 + 151111110960000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1462400^2 \end{aligned}$$

681)

$$\begin{aligned} &0536239^2 + 1362000^2 && := 1463761^2 \\ &12\ 0536239^2 + 14982000^2 && := 12\ 1463761^2 \\ &1232\ 0536239^2 + 151182000^2 && := 1232\ 1463761^2 \\ &123432\ 0536239^2 + 1513182000^2 && := 123432\ 1463761^2 \\ &12345432\ 0536239^2 + 15133182000^2 && := 12345432\ 1463761^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0536239^2 + 151333182000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1463761^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0536239^2 + 1513333182000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1463761^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0536239^2 + 15133333182000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1463761^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0536239^2 + 151333333182000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1463761^2 \end{aligned}$$

682)

$$\begin{aligned} &0534876^2 + 1364000^2 && := 1465124^2 \\ &12\ 0534876^2 + 15004000^2 && := 12\ 1465124^2 \\ &1232\ 0534876^2 + 151404000^2 && := 1232\ 1465124^2 \\ &123432\ 0534876^2 + 1515404000^2 && := 123432\ 1465124^2 \\ &12345432\ 0534876^2 + 15155404000^2 && := 12345432\ 1465124^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0534876^2 + 151555404000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1465124^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0534876^2 + 1515555404000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1465124^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0534876^2 + 15155555404000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1465124^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0534876^2 + 151555555404000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1465124^2 \end{aligned}$$

683)

$$\begin{aligned} &0533511^2 + 1366000^2 && := 1466489^2 \\ &12\ 0533511^2 + 15026000^2 && := 12\ 1466489^2 \\ &1232\ 0533511^2 + 151626000^2 && := 1232\ 1466489^2 \\ &123432\ 0533511^2 + 1517626000^2 && := 123432\ 1466489^2 \\ &12345432\ 0533511^2 + 15177626000^2 && := 12345432\ 1466489^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0533511^2 + 151777626000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1466489^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0533511^2 + 1517777626000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1466489^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0533511^2 + 15177777626000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1466489^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0533511^2 + 151777777626000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1466489^2 \end{aligned}$$

684)

$$\begin{aligned} &0532144^2 + 1368000^2 && := 1467856^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0532144^2 + 15048000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1467856^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0532144^2 + 151848000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1467856^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0532144^2 + 1519848000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1467856^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0532144^2 + 15199848000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1467856^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0532144^2 + 151999848000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1467856^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0532144^2 + 1519999848000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1467856^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0532144^2 + 15199999848000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1467856^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0532144^2 + 151999999848000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1467856^2 \end{aligned}$$

685)

$$\begin{aligned} &0530775^2 + 1370000^2 && := 1469225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0530775^2 + 15070000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1469225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0530775^2 + 152070000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1469225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0530775^2 + 1522070000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1469225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0530775^2 + 15222070000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1469225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0530775^2 + 152222070000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1469225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0530775^2 + 1522222070000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1469225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0530775^2 + 15222222070000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1469225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0530775^2 + 152222222070000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1469225^2 \end{aligned}$$

686)

$$\begin{aligned} &0529404^2 + 1372000^2 && := 1470596^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0529404^2 + 15092000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1470596^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0529404^2 + 152292000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1470596^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0529404^2 + 1524292000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1470596^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0529404^2 + 15244292000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1470596^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0529404^2 + 152444292000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1470596^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0529404^2 + 1524444292000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1470596^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0529404^2 + 15244444292000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1470596^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0529404^2 + 152444444292000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1470596^2 \end{aligned}$$

687)

$$\begin{aligned} &0528031^2 + 1374000^2 && := 1471969^2 \\ &12\ 0528031^2 + 15114000^2 && := 12\ 1471969^2 \\ &1232\ 0528031^2 + 152514000^2 && := 1232\ 1471969^2 \\ &123432\ 0528031^2 + 1526514000^2 && := 123432\ 1471969^2 \\ &12345432\ 0528031^2 + 15266514000^2 && := 12345432\ 1471969^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0528031^2 + 152666514000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1471969^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0528031^2 + 1526666514000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1471969^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0528031^2 + 15266666514000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1471969^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0528031^2 + 152666666514000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1471969^2 \end{aligned}$$

688)

$$\begin{aligned} &0526656^2 + 1376000^2 && := 1473344^2 \\ &12\ 0526656^2 + 15136000^2 && := 12\ 1473344^2 \\ &1232\ 0526656^2 + 152736000^2 && := 1232\ 1473344^2 \\ &123432\ 0526656^2 + 1528736000^2 && := 123432\ 1473344^2 \\ &12345432\ 0526656^2 + 15288736000^2 && := 12345432\ 1473344^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0526656^2 + 152888736000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1473344^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0526656^2 + 1528888736000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1473344^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0526656^2 + 15288888736000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1473344^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0526656^2 + 152888888736000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1473344^2 \end{aligned}$$

689)

$$\begin{aligned} &0525279^2 + 1378000^2 && := 1474721^2 \\ &12\ 0525279^2 + 15158000^2 && := 12\ 1474721^2 \\ &1232\ 0525279^2 + 152958000^2 && := 1232\ 1474721^2 \\ &123432\ 0525279^2 + 1530958000^2 && := 123432\ 1474721^2 \\ &12345432\ 0525279^2 + 15310958000^2 && := 12345432\ 1474721^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0525279^2 + 153110958000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1474721^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0525279^2 + 1531110958000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1474721^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0525279^2 + 15311110958000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1474721^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0525279^2 + 153111110958000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1474721^2 \end{aligned}$$

690)

$$\begin{aligned} &0523900^2 + 1380000^2 && := 1476100^2 \\ &12\ 0523900^2 + 15180000^2 && := 12\ 1476100^2 \\ &1232\ 0523900^2 + 153180000^2 && := 1232\ 1476100^2 \\ &123432\ 0523900^2 + 1533180000^2 && := 123432\ 1476100^2 \\ &12345432\ 0523900^2 + 15333180000^2 && := 12345432\ 1476100^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0523900^2 + 153333180000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1476100^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0523900^2 + 1533333180000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1476100^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0523900^2 + 15333333180000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1476100^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0523900^2 + 153333333180000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1476100^2 \end{aligned}$$

691)

$$\begin{aligned} &0522519^2 + 1382000^2 && := 1477481^2 \\ &12\ 0522519^2 + 15202000^2 && := 12\ 1477481^2 \\ &1232\ 0522519^2 + 153402000^2 && := 1232\ 1477481^2 \\ &123432\ 0522519^2 + 1535402000^2 && := 123432\ 1477481^2 \\ &12345432\ 0522519^2 + 15355402000^2 && := 12345432\ 1477481^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0522519^2 + 153555402000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1477481^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0522519^2 + 1535555402000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1477481^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0522519^2 + 15355555402000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1477481^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0522519^2 + 153555555402000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1477481^2 \end{aligned}$$

692)

$$\begin{aligned} &0521136^2 + 1384000^2 && := 1478864^2 \\ &12\ 0521136^2 + 15224000^2 && := 12\ 1478864^2 \\ &1232\ 0521136^2 + 153624000^2 && := 1232\ 1478864^2 \\ &123432\ 0521136^2 + 1537624000^2 && := 123432\ 1478864^2 \\ &12345432\ 0521136^2 + 15377624000^2 && := 12345432\ 1478864^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0521136^2 + 153777624000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1478864^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0521136^2 + 1537777624000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1478864^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0521136^2 + 15377777624000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1478864^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0521136^2 + 153777777624000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1478864^2 \end{aligned}$$

693)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0519751^2 + 1386000^2 & := & 1480249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0519751^2 + 15246000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1480249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0519751^2 + 153846000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1480249^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0519751^2 + 1539846000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1480249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0519751^2 + 15399846000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1480249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0519751^2 + 153999846000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1480249^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0519751^2 + 1539999846000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1480249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0519751^2 + 15399999846000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1480249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0519751^2 + 153999999846000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1480249^2 \end{aligned}$$

694)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0518364^2 + 1388000^2 & := & 1481636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0518364^2 + 15268000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1481636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0518364^2 + 154068000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1481636^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0518364^2 + 1542068000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1481636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0518364^2 + 15422068000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1481636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0518364^2 + 154222068000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1481636^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0518364^2 + 1542222068000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1481636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0518364^2 + 15422222068000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1481636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0518364^2 + 154222222068000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1481636^2 \end{aligned}$$

695)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0516975^2 + 1390000^2 & := & 1483025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0516975^2 + 15290000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1483025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0516975^2 + 154290000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1483025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0516975^2 + 1544290000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1483025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0516975^2 + 15444290000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1483025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0516975^2 + 154444290000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1483025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0516975^2 + 1544444290000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1483025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0516975^2 + 15444444290000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1483025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0516975^2 + 154444444290000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1483025^2 \end{aligned}$$

696)

$$\begin{aligned} &0515584^2 + 1392000^2 && := 1484416^2 \\ &12\ 0515584^2 + 15312000^2 && := 12\ 1484416^2 \\ &1232\ 0515584^2 + 154512000^2 && := 1232\ 1484416^2 \\ &123432\ 0515584^2 + 1546512000^2 && := 123432\ 1484416^2 \\ &12345432\ 0515584^2 + 15466512000^2 && := 12345432\ 1484416^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0515584^2 + 154666512000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1484416^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0515584^2 + 1546666512000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1484416^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0515584^2 + 15466666512000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1484416^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0515584^2 + 154666666512000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1484416^2 \end{aligned}$$

697)

$$\begin{aligned} &0514191^2 + 1394000^2 && := 1485809^2 \\ &12\ 0514191^2 + 15334000^2 && := 12\ 1485809^2 \\ &1232\ 0514191^2 + 154734000^2 && := 1232\ 1485809^2 \\ &123432\ 0514191^2 + 1548734000^2 && := 123432\ 1485809^2 \\ &12345432\ 0514191^2 + 15488734000^2 && := 12345432\ 1485809^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0514191^2 + 154888734000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1485809^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0514191^2 + 1548888734000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1485809^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0514191^2 + 15488888734000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1485809^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0514191^2 + 154888888734000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1485809^2 \end{aligned}$$

698)

$$\begin{aligned} &0512796^2 + 1396000^2 && := 1487204^2 \\ &12\ 0512796^2 + 15356000^2 && := 12\ 1487204^2 \\ &1232\ 0512796^2 + 154956000^2 && := 1232\ 1487204^2 \\ &123432\ 0512796^2 + 1550956000^2 && := 123432\ 1487204^2 \\ &12345432\ 0512796^2 + 15510956000^2 && := 12345432\ 1487204^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0512796^2 + 155110956000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1487204^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0512796^2 + 1551110956000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1487204^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0512796^2 + 15511110956000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1487204^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0512796^2 + 155111110956000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1487204^2 \end{aligned}$$

699)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0511399^2 + 1398000^2 & := & 1488601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0511399^2 + 15378000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1488601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0511399^2 + 155178000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1488601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0511399^2 + 1553178000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1488601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0511399^2 + 15533178000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1488601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0511399^2 + 155333178000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1488601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0511399^2 + 1553333178000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1488601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0511399^2 + 15533333178000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1488601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0511399^2 + 155333333178000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1488601^2 \end{aligned}$$

700)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0510000^2 + 1400000^2 & := & 1490000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0510000^2 + 15400000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1490000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0510000^2 + 155400000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1490000^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0510000^2 + 1555400000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1490000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0510000^2 + 15555400000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1490000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0510000^2 + 155555400000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1490000^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0510000^2 + 1555555400000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1490000^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0510000^2 + 15555555400000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1490000^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0510000^2 + 155555555400000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1490000^2 \end{aligned}$$

701)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0508599^2 + 1402000^2 & := & 1491401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0508599^2 + 15422000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1491401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0508599^2 + 155622000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1491401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0508599^2 + 1557622000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1491401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0508599^2 + 15577622000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1491401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0508599^2 + 155777622000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1491401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0508599^2 + 1557777622000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1491401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0508599^2 + 15577777622000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1491401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0508599^2 + 155777777622000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1491401^2 \end{aligned}$$

702)

$$\begin{aligned} &0507196^2 + 1404000^2 && := 1492804^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0507196^2 + 15444000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1492804^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0507196^2 + 155844000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1492804^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0507196^2 + 1559844000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1492804^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0507196^2 + 15599844000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1492804^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0507196^2 + 155999844000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1492804^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0507196^2 + 1559999844000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1492804^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0507196^2 + 15599999844000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1492804^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0507196^2 + 155999999844000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1492804^2 \end{aligned}$$

703)

$$\begin{aligned} &0505791^2 + 1406000^2 && := 1494209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0505791^2 + 15466000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1494209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0505791^2 + 156066000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1494209^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0505791^2 + 1562066000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1494209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0505791^2 + 15622066000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1494209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0505791^2 + 156222066000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1494209^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0505791^2 + 1562222066000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1494209^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0505791^2 + 15622222066000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1494209^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0505791^2 + 156222222066000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1494209^2 \end{aligned}$$

704)

$$\begin{aligned} &0504384^2 + 1408000^2 && := 1495616^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0504384^2 + 15488000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1495616^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0504384^2 + 156288000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1495616^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0504384^2 + 1564288000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1495616^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0504384^2 + 15644288000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1495616^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0504384^2 + 156444288000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1495616^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0504384^2 + 1564444288000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1495616^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0504384^2 + 15644444288000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1495616^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0504384^2 + 156444444288000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1495616^2 \end{aligned}$$

705)

$$\begin{aligned} &0502975^2 + 1410000^2 && := 1497025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0502975^2 + 15510000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1497025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0502975^2 + 156510000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1497025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0502975^2 + 1566510000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1497025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0502975^2 + 15666510000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1497025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0502975^2 + 156666510000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1497025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0502975^2 + 1566666510000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1497025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0502975^2 + 15666666510000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1497025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0502975^2 + 156666666510000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1497025^2 \end{aligned}$$

706)

$$\begin{aligned} &0501564^2 + 1412000^2 && := 1498436^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0501564^2 + 15532000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1498436^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0501564^2 + 156732000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1498436^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0501564^2 + 1568732000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1498436^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0501564^2 + 15688732000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1498436^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0501564^2 + 156888732000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1498436^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0501564^2 + 1568888732000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1498436^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0501564^2 + 15688888732000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1498436^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0501564^2 + 156888888732000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1498436^2 \end{aligned}$$

707)

$$\begin{aligned} &0500151^2 + 1414000^2 && := 1499849^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0500151^2 + 15554000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1499849^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0500151^2 + 156954000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1499849^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0500151^2 + 1570954000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1499849^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0500151^2 + 15710954000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1499849^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0500151^2 + 157110954000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1499849^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0500151^2 + 1571110954000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1499849^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0500151^2 + 15711110954000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1499849^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0500151^2 + 157111110954000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1499849^2 \end{aligned}$$

708)

$$\begin{aligned} &0498736^2 + 1416000^2 && := 1501264^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0498736^2 + 15576000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1501264^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0498736^2 + 157176000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1501264^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0498736^2 + 1573176000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1501264^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0498736^2 + 15733176000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1501264^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0498736^2 + 157333176000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1501264^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0498736^2 + 1573333176000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1501264^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0498736^2 + 15733333176000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1501264^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0498736^2 + 157333333176000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1501264^2 \end{aligned}$$

709)

$$\begin{aligned} &0497319^2 + 1418000^2 && := 1502681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0497319^2 + 15598000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1502681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0497319^2 + 157398000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1502681^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0497319^2 + 1575398000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1502681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0497319^2 + 15755398000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1502681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0497319^2 + 157555398000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1502681^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0497319^2 + 1575555398000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1502681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0497319^2 + 15755555398000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1502681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0497319^2 + 157555555398000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1502681^2 \end{aligned}$$

710)

$$\begin{aligned} &0495900^2 + 1420000^2 && := 1504100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0495900^2 + 15620000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1504100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0495900^2 + 157620000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1504100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0495900^2 + 1577620000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1504100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0495900^2 + 15777620000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1504100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0495900^2 + 157777620000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1504100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0495900^2 + 1577777620000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1504100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0495900^2 + 15777777620000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1504100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0495900^2 + 157777777620000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1504100^2 \end{aligned}$$

711)

$$\begin{aligned} &0494479^2 + 1422000^2 && := 1505521^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0494479^2 + 15642000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1505521^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0494479^2 + 157842000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1505521^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0494479^2 + 1579842000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1505521^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0494479^2 + 15799842000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1505521^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0494479^2 + 157999842000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1505521^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0494479^2 + 1579999842000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1505521^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0494479^2 + 15799999842000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1505521^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0494479^2 + 157999999842000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1505521^2 \end{aligned}$$

712)

$$\begin{aligned} &0493056^2 + 1424000^2 && := 1506944^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0493056^2 + 15664000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1506944^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0493056^2 + 158064000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1506944^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0493056^2 + 1582064000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1506944^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0493056^2 + 15822064000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1506944^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0493056^2 + 158222064000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1506944^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0493056^2 + 1582222064000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1506944^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0493056^2 + 15822222064000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1506944^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0493056^2 + 158222222064000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1506944^2 \end{aligned}$$

713)

$$\begin{aligned} &0491631^2 + 1426000^2 && := 1508369^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0491631^2 + 15686000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1508369^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0491631^2 + 158286000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1508369^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0491631^2 + 1584286000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1508369^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0491631^2 + 15844286000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1508369^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0491631^2 + 158444286000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1508369^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0491631^2 + 1584444286000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1508369^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0491631^2 + 15844444286000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1508369^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0491631^2 + 158444444286000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1508369^2 \end{aligned}$$

714)

$$\begin{aligned} &0490204^2 + 1428000^2 && := 1509796^2 \\ &12\ 0490204^2 + 15708000^2 && := 12\ 1509796^2 \\ &1232\ 0490204^2 + 158508000^2 && := 1232\ 1509796^2 \\ &123432\ 0490204^2 + 1586508000^2 && := 123432\ 1509796^2 \\ &12345432\ 0490204^2 + 15866508000^2 && := 12345432\ 1509796^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0490204^2 + 158666508000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1509796^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0490204^2 + 1586666508000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1509796^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0490204^2 + 15866666508000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1509796^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0490204^2 + 158666666508000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1509796^2 \end{aligned}$$

715)

$$\begin{aligned} &0488775^2 + 1430000^2 && := 1511225^2 \\ &12\ 0488775^2 + 15730000^2 && := 12\ 1511225^2 \\ &1232\ 0488775^2 + 158730000^2 && := 1232\ 1511225^2 \\ &123432\ 0488775^2 + 1588730000^2 && := 123432\ 1511225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0488775^2 + 15888730000^2 && := 12345432\ 1511225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0488775^2 + 158888730000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1511225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0488775^2 + 1588888730000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1511225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0488775^2 + 15888888730000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1511225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0488775^2 + 158888888730000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1511225^2 \end{aligned}$$

716)

$$\begin{aligned} &0487344^2 + 1432000^2 && := 1512656^2 \\ &12\ 0487344^2 + 15752000^2 && := 12\ 1512656^2 \\ &1232\ 0487344^2 + 158952000^2 && := 1232\ 1512656^2 \\ &123432\ 0487344^2 + 1590952000^2 && := 123432\ 1512656^2 \\ &12345432\ 0487344^2 + 15910952000^2 && := 12345432\ 1512656^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0487344^2 + 159110952000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1512656^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0487344^2 + 1591110952000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1512656^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0487344^2 + 15911110952000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1512656^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0487344^2 + 159111110952000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1512656^2 \end{aligned}$$

717)

$$\begin{aligned} &0485911^2 + 1434000^2 && := 1514089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0485911^2 + 15774000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1514089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0485911^2 + 159174000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1514089^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0485911^2 + 1593174000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1514089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0485911^2 + 15933174000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1514089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0485911^2 + 159333174000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1514089^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0485911^2 + 1593333174000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1514089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0485911^2 + 15933333174000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1514089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0485911^2 + 159333333174000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1514089^2 \end{aligned}$$

718)

$$\begin{aligned} &0484476^2 + 1436000^2 && := 1515524^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0484476^2 + 15796000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1515524^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0484476^2 + 159396000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1515524^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0484476^2 + 1595396000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1515524^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0484476^2 + 15955396000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1515524^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0484476^2 + 159555396000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1515524^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0484476^2 + 1595555396000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1515524^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0484476^2 + 15955555396000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1515524^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0484476^2 + 159555555396000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1515524^2 \end{aligned}$$

719)

$$\begin{aligned} &0483039^2 + 1438000^2 && := 1516961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0483039^2 + 15818000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1516961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0483039^2 + 159618000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1516961^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0483039^2 + 1597618000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1516961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0483039^2 + 15977618000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1516961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0483039^2 + 159777618000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1516961^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0483039^2 + 1597777618000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1516961^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0483039^2 + 15977777618000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1516961^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0483039^2 + 159777777618000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1516961^2 \end{aligned}$$

720)

$$\begin{aligned} &0481600^2 + 1440000^2 && := 1518400^2 \\ &12\ 0481600^2 + 15840000^2 && := 12\ 1518400^2 \\ &1232\ 0481600^2 + 159840000^2 && := 1232\ 1518400^2 \\ &123432\ 0481600^2 + 1599840000^2 && := 123432\ 1518400^2 \\ &12345432\ 0481600^2 + 15999840000^2 && := 12345432\ 1518400^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0481600^2 + 159999840000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1518400^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0481600^2 + 1599999840000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1518400^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0481600^2 + 15999999840000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1518400^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0481600^2 + 159999999840000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1518400^2 \end{aligned}$$

721)

$$\begin{aligned} &0480159^2 + 1442000^2 && := 1519841^2 \\ &12\ 0480159^2 + 15862000^2 && := 12\ 1519841^2 \\ &1232\ 0480159^2 + 160062000^2 && := 1232\ 1519841^2 \\ &123432\ 0480159^2 + 1602062000^2 && := 123432\ 1519841^2 \\ &12345432\ 0480159^2 + 16022062000^2 && := 12345432\ 1519841^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0480159^2 + 160222062000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1519841^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0480159^2 + 1602222062000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1519841^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0480159^2 + 16022222062000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1519841^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0480159^2 + 160222222062000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1519841^2 \end{aligned}$$

722)

$$\begin{aligned} &0478716^2 + 1444000^2 && := 1521284^2 \\ &12\ 0478716^2 + 15884000^2 && := 12\ 1521284^2 \\ &1232\ 0478716^2 + 160284000^2 && := 1232\ 1521284^2 \\ &123432\ 0478716^2 + 1604284000^2 && := 123432\ 1521284^2 \\ &12345432\ 0478716^2 + 16044284000^2 && := 12345432\ 1521284^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0478716^2 + 160444284000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1521284^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0478716^2 + 1604444284000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1521284^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0478716^2 + 16044444284000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1521284^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0478716^2 + 160444444284000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1521284^2 \end{aligned}$$

723)

$$\begin{aligned} &0477271^2 + 1446000^2 && := 1522729^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0477271^2 + 15906000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1522729^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0477271^2 + 160506000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1522729^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0477271^2 + 1606506000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1522729^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0477271^2 + 16066506000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1522729^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0477271^2 + 160666506000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1522729^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0477271^2 + 1606666506000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1522729^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0477271^2 + 16066666506000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1522729^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0477271^2 + 160666666506000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1522729^2 \end{aligned}$$

724)

$$\begin{aligned} &0475824^2 + 1448000^2 && := 1524176^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0475824^2 + 15928000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1524176^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0475824^2 + 160728000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1524176^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0475824^2 + 1608728000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1524176^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0475824^2 + 16088728000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1524176^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0475824^2 + 160888728000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1524176^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0475824^2 + 1608888728000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1524176^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0475824^2 + 16088888728000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1524176^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0475824^2 + 160888888728000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1524176^2 \end{aligned}$$

725)

$$\begin{aligned} &0474375^2 + 1450000^2 && := 1525625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0474375^2 + 15950000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1525625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0474375^2 + 160950000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1525625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0474375^2 + 1610950000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1525625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0474375^2 + 16110950000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1525625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0474375^2 + 161110950000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1525625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0474375^2 + 1611110950000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1525625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0474375^2 + 16111110950000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1525625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0474375^2 + 161111110950000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1525625^2 \end{aligned}$$

726)

$$\begin{aligned} &0472924^2 + 1452000^2 && := 1527076^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0472924^2 + 15972000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1527076^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0472924^2 + 161172000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1527076^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0472924^2 + 1613172000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1527076^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0472924^2 + 16133172000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1527076^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0472924^2 + 161333172000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1527076^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0472924^2 + 1613333172000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1527076^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0472924^2 + 16133333172000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1527076^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0472924^2 + 161333333172000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1527076^2 \end{aligned}$$

727)

$$\begin{aligned} &0471471^2 + 1454000^2 && := 1528529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0471471^2 + 15994000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1528529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0471471^2 + 161394000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1528529^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0471471^2 + 1615394000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1528529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0471471^2 + 16155394000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1528529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0471471^2 + 161555394000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1528529^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0471471^2 + 1615555394000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1528529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0471471^2 + 16155555394000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1528529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0471471^2 + 161555555394000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1528529^2 \end{aligned}$$

728)

$$\begin{aligned} &0470016^2 + 1456000^2 && := 1529984^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0470016^2 + 16016000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1529984^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0470016^2 + 161616000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1529984^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0470016^2 + 1617616000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1529984^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0470016^2 + 16177616000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1529984^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0470016^2 + 161777616000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1529984^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0470016^2 + 1617777616000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1529984^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0470016^2 + 16177777616000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1529984^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0470016^2 + 161777777616000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1529984^2 \end{aligned}$$

729)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0468559^2 + 1458000^2 & := & 1531441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0468559^2 + 16038000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1531441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0468559^2 + 161838000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1531441^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0468559^2 + 1619838000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1531441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0468559^2 + 16199838000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1531441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0468559^2 + 161999838000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1531441^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0468559^2 + 1619999838000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1531441^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0468559^2 + 16199999838000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1531441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0468559^2 + 161999999838000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1531441^2 \end{aligned}$$

730)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0467100^2 + 1460000^2 & := & 1532900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0467100^2 + 16060000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1532900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0467100^2 + 162060000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1532900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0467100^2 + 1622060000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1532900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0467100^2 + 16222060000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1532900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0467100^2 + 162222060000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1532900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0467100^2 + 1622222060000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1532900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0467100^2 + 16222222060000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1532900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0467100^2 + 162222222060000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1532900^2 \end{aligned}$$

731)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0465639^2 + 1462000^2 & := & 1534361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0465639^2 + 16082000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1534361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0465639^2 + 162282000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1534361^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0465639^2 + 1624282000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1534361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0465639^2 + 16244282000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1534361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0465639^2 + 162444282000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1534361^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0465639^2 + 1624444282000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1534361^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0465639^2 + 16244444282000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1534361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0465639^2 + 162444444282000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1534361^2 \end{aligned}$$

732)

$$\begin{aligned} &0464176^2 + 1464000^2 && := 1535824^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0464176^2 + 16104000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1535824^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0464176^2 + 162504000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1535824^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0464176^2 + 1626504000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1535824^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0464176^2 + 16266504000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1535824^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0464176^2 + 162666504000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1535824^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0464176^2 + 1626666504000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1535824^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0464176^2 + 16266666504000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1535824^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0464176^2 + 162666666504000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1535824^2 \end{aligned}$$

733)

$$\begin{aligned} &0462711^2 + 1466000^2 && := 1537289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0462711^2 + 16126000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1537289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0462711^2 + 162726000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1537289^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0462711^2 + 1628726000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1537289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0462711^2 + 16288726000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1537289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0462711^2 + 162888726000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1537289^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0462711^2 + 1628888726000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1537289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0462711^2 + 16288888726000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1537289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0462711^2 + 162888888726000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1537289^2 \end{aligned}$$

734)

$$\begin{aligned} &0461244^2 + 1468000^2 && := 1538756^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0461244^2 + 16148000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1538756^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0461244^2 + 162948000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1538756^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0461244^2 + 1630948000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1538756^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0461244^2 + 16310948000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1538756^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0461244^2 + 163110948000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1538756^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0461244^2 + 1631110948000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1538756^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0461244^2 + 16311110948000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1538756^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0461244^2 + 163111110948000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1538756^2 \end{aligned}$$

735)

$$\begin{aligned} &0459775^2 + 1470000^2 && := 1540225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0459775^2 + 16170000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1540225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0459775^2 + 163170000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1540225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0459775^2 + 1633170000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1540225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0459775^2 + 16333170000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1540225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0459775^2 + 163333170000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1540225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0459775^2 + 1633333170000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1540225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0459775^2 + 16333333170000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1540225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0459775^2 + 163333333170000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1540225^2 \end{aligned}$$

736)

$$\begin{aligned} &0458304^2 + 1472000^2 && := 1541696^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0458304^2 + 16192000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1541696^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0458304^2 + 163392000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1541696^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0458304^2 + 1635392000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1541696^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0458304^2 + 16355392000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1541696^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0458304^2 + 163555392000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1541696^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0458304^2 + 1635555392000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1541696^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0458304^2 + 16355555392000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1541696^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0458304^2 + 163555555392000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1541696^2 \end{aligned}$$

737)

$$\begin{aligned} &0456831^2 + 1474000^2 && := 1543169^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0456831^2 + 16214000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1543169^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0456831^2 + 163614000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1543169^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0456831^2 + 1637614000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1543169^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0456831^2 + 16377614000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1543169^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0456831^2 + 163777614000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1543169^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0456831^2 + 1637777614000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1543169^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0456831^2 + 16377777614000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1543169^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0456831^2 + 163777777614000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1543169^2 \end{aligned}$$

738)

$$\begin{aligned} &0455356^2 + 1476000^2 && := 1544644^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0455356^2 + 16236000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1544644^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0455356^2 + 163836000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1544644^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0455356^2 + 1639836000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1544644^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0455356^2 + 16399836000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1544644^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0455356^2 + 163999836000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1544644^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0455356^2 + 1639999836000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1544644^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0455356^2 + 16399999836000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1544644^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0455356^2 + 163999999836000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1544644^2 \end{aligned}$$

739)

$$\begin{aligned} &0453879^2 + 1478000^2 && := 1546121^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0453879^2 + 16258000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1546121^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0453879^2 + 164058000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1546121^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0453879^2 + 1642058000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1546121^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0453879^2 + 16422058000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1546121^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0453879^2 + 164222058000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1546121^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0453879^2 + 1642222058000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1546121^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0453879^2 + 16422222058000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1546121^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0453879^2 + 164222222058000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1546121^2 \end{aligned}$$

740)

$$\begin{aligned} &0452400^2 + 1480000^2 && := 1547600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0452400^2 + 16280000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1547600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0452400^2 + 164280000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1547600^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0452400^2 + 1644280000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1547600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0452400^2 + 16444280000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1547600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0452400^2 + 164444280000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1547600^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0452400^2 + 1644444280000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1547600^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0452400^2 + 16444444280000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1547600^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0452400^2 + 164444444280000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1547600^2 \end{aligned}$$

741)

$$\begin{aligned} &0450919^2 + 1482000^2 && := 1549081^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0450919^2 + 16302000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1549081^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0450919^2 + 164502000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1549081^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0450919^2 + 1646502000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1549081^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0450919^2 + 16466502000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1549081^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0450919^2 + 164666502000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1549081^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0450919^2 + 1646666502000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1549081^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0450919^2 + 16466666502000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1549081^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0450919^2 + 164666666502000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1549081^2 \end{aligned}$$

742)

$$\begin{aligned} &0449436^2 + 1484000^2 && := 1550564^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0449436^2 + 16324000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1550564^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0449436^2 + 164724000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1550564^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0449436^2 + 1648724000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1550564^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0449436^2 + 16488724000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1550564^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0449436^2 + 164888724000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1550564^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0449436^2 + 1648888724000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1550564^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0449436^2 + 16488888724000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1550564^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0449436^2 + 164888888724000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1550564^2 \end{aligned}$$

743)

$$\begin{aligned} &0447951^2 + 1486000^2 && := 1552049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0447951^2 + 16346000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1552049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0447951^2 + 164946000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1552049^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0447951^2 + 1650946000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1552049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0447951^2 + 16510946000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1552049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0447951^2 + 165110946000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1552049^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0447951^2 + 1651110946000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1552049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0447951^2 + 16511110946000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1552049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0447951^2 + 165111110946000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1552049^2 \end{aligned}$$

744)

$$\begin{aligned} &0446464^2 + 1488000^2 && := 1553536^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0446464^2 + 16368000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1553536^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0446464^2 + 165168000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1553536^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0446464^2 + 1653168000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1553536^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0446464^2 + 16533168000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1553536^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0446464^2 + 165333168000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1553536^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0446464^2 + 1653333168000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1553536^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0446464^2 + 16533333168000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1553536^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0446464^2 + 165333333168000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1553536^2 \end{aligned}$$

745)

$$\begin{aligned} &0444975^2 + 1490000^2 && := 1555025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0444975^2 + 16390000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1555025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0444975^2 + 165390000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1555025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0444975^2 + 1655390000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1555025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0444975^2 + 16555390000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1555025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0444975^2 + 165555390000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1555025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0444975^2 + 1655555390000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1555025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0444975^2 + 16555555390000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1555025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0444975^2 + 165555555390000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1555025^2 \end{aligned}$$

746)

$$\begin{aligned} &0443484^2 + 1492000^2 && := 1556516^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0443484^2 + 16412000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1556516^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0443484^2 + 165612000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1556516^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0443484^2 + 1657612000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1556516^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0443484^2 + 16577612000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1556516^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0443484^2 + 165777612000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1556516^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0443484^2 + 1657777612000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1556516^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0443484^2 + 16577777612000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1556516^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0443484^2 + 165777777612000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1556516^2 \end{aligned}$$

747)

$$\begin{aligned} &0441991^2 + 1494000^2 && := 1558009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0441991^2 + 16434000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1558009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0441991^2 + 165834000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1558009^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0441991^2 + 1659834000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1558009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0441991^2 + 16599834000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1558009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0441991^2 + 165999834000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1558009^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0441991^2 + 1659999834000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1558009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0441991^2 + 16599999834000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1558009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0441991^2 + 165999999834000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1558009^2 \end{aligned}$$

748)

$$\begin{aligned} &0440496^2 + 1496000^2 && := 1559504^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0440496^2 + 16456000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1559504^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0440496^2 + 166056000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1559504^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0440496^2 + 1662056000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1559504^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0440496^2 + 16622056000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1559504^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0440496^2 + 166222056000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1559504^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0440496^2 + 1662222056000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1559504^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0440496^2 + 16622222056000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1559504^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0440496^2 + 166222222056000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1559504^2 \end{aligned}$$

749)

$$\begin{aligned} &0438999^2 + 1498000^2 && := 1561001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0438999^2 + 16478000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1561001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0438999^2 + 166278000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1561001^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0438999^2 + 1664278000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1561001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0438999^2 + 16644278000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1561001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0438999^2 + 166444278000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1561001^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0438999^2 + 1664444278000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1561001^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0438999^2 + 16644444278000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1561001^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0438999^2 + 166444444278000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1561001^2 \end{aligned}$$

750)

$$\begin{aligned} &0437500^2 + 1500000^2 && := 1562500^2 \\ &12\ 0437500^2 + 16500000^2 && := 12\ 1562500^2 \\ &1232\ 0437500^2 + 166500000^2 && := 1232\ 1562500^2 \\ &123432\ 0437500^2 + 1666500000^2 && := 123432\ 1562500^2 \\ &12345432\ 0437500^2 + 16666500000^2 && := 12345432\ 1562500^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0437500^2 + 166666500000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1562500^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0437500^2 + 1666666500000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1562500^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0437500^2 + 16666666500000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1562500^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0437500^2 + 166666666500000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1562500^2 \end{aligned}$$

751)

$$\begin{aligned} &0435999^2 + 1502000^2 && := 1564001^2 \\ &12\ 0435999^2 + 16522000^2 && := 12\ 1564001^2 \\ &1232\ 0435999^2 + 166722000^2 && := 1232\ 1564001^2 \\ &123432\ 0435999^2 + 1668722000^2 && := 123432\ 1564001^2 \\ &12345432\ 0435999^2 + 16688722000^2 && := 12345432\ 1564001^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0435999^2 + 166888722000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1564001^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0435999^2 + 1668888722000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1564001^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0435999^2 + 16688888722000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1564001^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0435999^2 + 166888888722000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1564001^2 \end{aligned}$$

752)

$$\begin{aligned} &0434496^2 + 1504000^2 && := 1565504^2 \\ &12\ 0434496^2 + 16544000^2 && := 12\ 1565504^2 \\ &1232\ 0434496^2 + 166944000^2 && := 1232\ 1565504^2 \\ &123432\ 0434496^2 + 1670944000^2 && := 123432\ 1565504^2 \\ &12345432\ 0434496^2 + 16710944000^2 && := 12345432\ 1565504^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0434496^2 + 167110944000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1565504^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0434496^2 + 1671110944000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1565504^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0434496^2 + 16711110944000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1565504^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0434496^2 + 167111110944000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1565504^2 \end{aligned}$$

753)

$$\begin{aligned} &0432991^2 + 1506000^2 && := 1567009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0432991^2 + 16566000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1567009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0432991^2 + 167166000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1567009^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0432991^2 + 1673166000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1567009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0432991^2 + 16733166000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1567009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0432991^2 + 167333166000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1567009^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0432991^2 + 1673333166000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1567009^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0432991^2 + 16733333166000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1567009^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0432991^2 + 167333333166000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1567009^2 \end{aligned}$$

754)

$$\begin{aligned} &0431484^2 + 1508000^2 && := 1568516^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0431484^2 + 16588000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1568516^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0431484^2 + 167388000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1568516^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0431484^2 + 1675388000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1568516^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0431484^2 + 16755388000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1568516^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0431484^2 + 167555388000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1568516^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0431484^2 + 1675555388000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1568516^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0431484^2 + 16755555388000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1568516^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0431484^2 + 167555555388000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1568516^2 \end{aligned}$$

755)

$$\begin{aligned} &0429975^2 + 1510000^2 && := 1570025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0429975^2 + 16610000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1570025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0429975^2 + 167610000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1570025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0429975^2 + 1677610000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1570025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0429975^2 + 16777610000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1570025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0429975^2 + 167777610000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1570025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0429975^2 + 1677777610000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1570025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0429975^2 + 16777777610000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1570025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0429975^2 + 167777777610000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1570025^2 \end{aligned}$$

756)

$$\begin{aligned} &0428464^2 + 1512000^2 && := 1571536^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0428464^2 + 16632000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1571536^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0428464^2 + 167832000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1571536^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0428464^2 + 1679832000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1571536^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0428464^2 + 16799832000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1571536^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0428464^2 + 167999832000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1571536^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0428464^2 + 1679999832000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1571536^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0428464^2 + 16799999832000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1571536^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0428464^2 + 167999999832000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1571536^2 \end{aligned}$$

757)

$$\begin{aligned} &0426951^2 + 1514000^2 && := 1573049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0426951^2 + 16654000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1573049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0426951^2 + 168054000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1573049^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0426951^2 + 1682054000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1573049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0426951^2 + 16822054000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1573049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0426951^2 + 168222054000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1573049^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0426951^2 + 1682222054000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1573049^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0426951^2 + 16822222054000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1573049^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0426951^2 + 168222222054000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1573049^2 \end{aligned}$$

758)

$$\begin{aligned} &0425436^2 + 1516000^2 && := 1574564^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0425436^2 + 16676000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1574564^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0425436^2 + 168276000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1574564^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0425436^2 + 1684276000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1574564^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0425436^2 + 16844276000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1574564^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0425436^2 + 168444276000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1574564^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0425436^2 + 1684444276000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1574564^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0425436^2 + 16844444276000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1574564^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0425436^2 + 168444444276000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1574564^2 \end{aligned}$$

759)

$$\begin{aligned} &0423919^2 + 1518000^2 && := 1576081^2 \\ &12\ 0423919^2 + 16698000^2 && := 12\ 1576081^2 \\ &1232\ 0423919^2 + 168498000^2 && := 1232\ 1576081^2 \\ &123432\ 0423919^2 + 1686498000^2 && := 123432\ 1576081^2 \\ &12345432\ 0423919^2 + 16866498000^2 && := 12345432\ 1576081^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0423919^2 + 168666498000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1576081^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0423919^2 + 1686666498000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1576081^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0423919^2 + 16866666498000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1576081^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0423919^2 + 168666666498000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1576081^2 \end{aligned}$$

760)

$$\begin{aligned} &0422400^2 + 1520000^2 && := 1577600^2 \\ &12\ 0422400^2 + 16720000^2 && := 12\ 1577600^2 \\ &1232\ 0422400^2 + 168720000^2 && := 1232\ 1577600^2 \\ &123432\ 0422400^2 + 1688720000^2 && := 123432\ 1577600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0422400^2 + 16888720000^2 && := 12345432\ 1577600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0422400^2 + 168888720000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1577600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0422400^2 + 1688888720000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1577600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0422400^2 + 16888888720000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1577600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0422400^2 + 168888888720000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1577600^2 \end{aligned}$$

761)

$$\begin{aligned} &0420879^2 + 1522000^2 && := 1579121^2 \\ &12\ 0420879^2 + 16742000^2 && := 12\ 1579121^2 \\ &1232\ 0420879^2 + 168942000^2 && := 1232\ 1579121^2 \\ &123432\ 0420879^2 + 1690942000^2 && := 123432\ 1579121^2 \\ &12345432\ 0420879^2 + 16910942000^2 && := 12345432\ 1579121^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0420879^2 + 169110942000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1579121^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0420879^2 + 1691110942000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1579121^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0420879^2 + 16911110942000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1579121^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0420879^2 + 169111110942000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1579121^2 \end{aligned}$$

762)

$$\begin{aligned} &0419356^2 + 1524000^2 && := 1580644^2 \\ &12\ 0419356^2 + 16764000^2 && := 12\ 1580644^2 \\ &1232\ 0419356^2 + 169164000^2 && := 1232\ 1580644^2 \\ &123432\ 0419356^2 + 1693164000^2 && := 123432\ 1580644^2 \\ &12345432\ 0419356^2 + 16933164000^2 && := 12345432\ 1580644^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0419356^2 + 169333164000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1580644^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0419356^2 + 1693333164000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1580644^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0419356^2 + 16933333164000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1580644^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0419356^2 + 169333333164000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1580644^2 \end{aligned}$$

763)

$$\begin{aligned} &0417831^2 + 1526000^2 && := 1582169^2 \\ &12\ 0417831^2 + 16786000^2 && := 12\ 1582169^2 \\ &1232\ 0417831^2 + 169386000^2 && := 1232\ 1582169^2 \\ &123432\ 0417831^2 + 1695386000^2 && := 123432\ 1582169^2 \\ &12345432\ 0417831^2 + 16955386000^2 && := 12345432\ 1582169^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0417831^2 + 169555386000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1582169^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0417831^2 + 1695555386000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1582169^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0417831^2 + 16955555386000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1582169^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0417831^2 + 169555555386000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1582169^2 \end{aligned}$$

764)

$$\begin{aligned} &0416304^2 + 1528000^2 && := 1583696^2 \\ &12\ 0416304^2 + 16808000^2 && := 12\ 1583696^2 \\ &1232\ 0416304^2 + 169608000^2 && := 1232\ 1583696^2 \\ &123432\ 0416304^2 + 1697608000^2 && := 123432\ 1583696^2 \\ &12345432\ 0416304^2 + 16977608000^2 && := 12345432\ 1583696^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0416304^2 + 169777608000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1583696^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0416304^2 + 1697777608000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1583696^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0416304^2 + 16977777608000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1583696^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0416304^2 + 169777777608000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1583696^2 \end{aligned}$$

765)

$$\begin{aligned} &0414775^2 + 1530000^2 && := 1585225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0414775^2 + 16830000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1585225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0414775^2 + 169830000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1585225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0414775^2 + 1699830000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1585225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0414775^2 + 16999830000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1585225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0414775^2 + 169999830000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1585225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0414775^2 + 1699999830000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1585225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0414775^2 + 16999999830000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1585225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0414775^2 + 169999999830000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1585225^2 \end{aligned}$$

766)

$$\begin{aligned} &0413244^2 + 1532000^2 && := 1586756^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0413244^2 + 16852000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1586756^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0413244^2 + 170052000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1586756^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0413244^2 + 1702052000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1586756^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0413244^2 + 17022052000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1586756^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0413244^2 + 170222052000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1586756^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0413244^2 + 1702222052000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1586756^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0413244^2 + 17022222052000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1586756^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0413244^2 + 170222222052000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1586756^2 \end{aligned}$$

767)

$$\begin{aligned} &0411711^2 + 1534000^2 && := 1588289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0411711^2 + 16874000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1588289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0411711^2 + 170274000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1588289^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0411711^2 + 1704274000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1588289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0411711^2 + 17044274000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1588289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0411711^2 + 170444274000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1588289^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0411711^2 + 1704444274000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1588289^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0411711^2 + 17044444274000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1588289^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0411711^2 + 170444444274000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1588289^2 \end{aligned}$$

768)

$$\begin{aligned} &0410176^2 + 1536000^2 && := 1589824^2 \\ &12\ 0410176^2 + 16896000^2 && := 12\ 1589824^2 \\ &1232\ 0410176^2 + 170496000^2 && := 1232\ 1589824^2 \\ &123432\ 0410176^2 + 1706496000^2 && := 123432\ 1589824^2 \\ &12345432\ 0410176^2 + 17066496000^2 && := 12345432\ 1589824^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0410176^2 + 170666496000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1589824^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0410176^2 + 1706666496000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1589824^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0410176^2 + 17066666496000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1589824^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0410176^2 + 170666666496000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1589824^2 \end{aligned}$$

769)

$$\begin{aligned} &0408639^2 + 1538000^2 && := 1591361^2 \\ &12\ 0408639^2 + 16918000^2 && := 12\ 1591361^2 \\ &1232\ 0408639^2 + 170718000^2 && := 1232\ 1591361^2 \\ &123432\ 0408639^2 + 1708718000^2 && := 123432\ 1591361^2 \\ &12345432\ 0408639^2 + 17088718000^2 && := 12345432\ 1591361^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0408639^2 + 170888718000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1591361^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0408639^2 + 1708888718000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1591361^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0408639^2 + 17088888718000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1591361^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0408639^2 + 170888888718000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1591361^2 \end{aligned}$$

770)

$$\begin{aligned} &0407100^2 + 1540000^2 && := 1592900^2 \\ &12\ 0407100^2 + 16940000^2 && := 12\ 1592900^2 \\ &1232\ 0407100^2 + 170940000^2 && := 1232\ 1592900^2 \\ &123432\ 0407100^2 + 1710940000^2 && := 123432\ 1592900^2 \\ &12345432\ 0407100^2 + 17110940000^2 && := 12345432\ 1592900^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0407100^2 + 171110940000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1592900^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0407100^2 + 1711110940000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1592900^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0407100^2 + 17111110940000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1592900^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0407100^2 + 171111110940000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1592900^2 \end{aligned}$$

771)

$$\begin{aligned} &0405559^2 + 1542000^2 && := 1594441^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0405559^2 + 16962000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1594441^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0405559^2 + 171162000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1594441^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0405559^2 + 1713162000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1594441^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0405559^2 + 17133162000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1594441^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0405559^2 + 171333162000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1594441^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0405559^2 + 1713333162000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1594441^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0405559^2 + 17133333162000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1594441^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0405559^2 + 171333333162000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1594441^2 \end{aligned}$$

772)

$$\begin{aligned} &0404016^2 + 1544000^2 && := 1595984^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0404016^2 + 16984000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1595984^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0404016^2 + 171384000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1595984^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0404016^2 + 1715384000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1595984^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0404016^2 + 17155384000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1595984^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0404016^2 + 171555384000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1595984^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0404016^2 + 1715555384000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1595984^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0404016^2 + 17155555384000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1595984^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0404016^2 + 171555555384000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1595984^2 \end{aligned}$$

773)

$$\begin{aligned} &0402471^2 + 1546000^2 && := 1597529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0402471^2 + 17006000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1597529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0402471^2 + 171606000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1597529^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0402471^2 + 1717606000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1597529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0402471^2 + 17177606000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1597529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0402471^2 + 171777606000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1597529^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0402471^2 + 1717777606000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1597529^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0402471^2 + 17177777606000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1597529^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0402471^2 + 171777777606000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1597529^2 \end{aligned}$$

774)

$$\begin{aligned} &0400924^2 + 1548000^2 && := 1599076^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0400924^2 + 17028000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1599076^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0400924^2 + 171828000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1599076^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0400924^2 + 1719828000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1599076^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0400924^2 + 17199828000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1599076^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0400924^2 + 171999828000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1599076^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0400924^2 + 1719999828000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1599076^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0400924^2 + 17199999828000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1599076^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0400924^2 + 171999999828000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1599076^2 \end{aligned}$$

775)

$$\begin{aligned} &0399375^2 + 1550000^2 && := 1600625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0399375^2 + 17050000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1600625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0399375^2 + 172050000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1600625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0399375^2 + 1722050000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1600625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0399375^2 + 17222050000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1600625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0399375^2 + 172222050000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1600625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0399375^2 + 1722222050000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1600625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0399375^2 + 17222222050000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1600625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0399375^2 + 172222222050000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1600625^2 \end{aligned}$$

776)

$$\begin{aligned} &0397824^2 + 1552000^2 && := 1602176^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0397824^2 + 17072000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1602176^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0397824^2 + 172272000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1602176^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0397824^2 + 1724272000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1602176^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0397824^2 + 17244272000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1602176^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0397824^2 + 172444272000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1602176^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0397824^2 + 1724444272000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1602176^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0397824^2 + 17244444272000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1602176^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0397824^2 + 172444444272000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1602176^2 \end{aligned}$$

777)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0396271^2 + 1554000^2 & := & 1603729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0396271^2 + 17094000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1603729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0396271^2 + 172494000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1603729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0396271^2 + 1726494000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1603729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0396271^2 + 17266494000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1603729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0396271^2 + 172666494000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1603729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0396271^2 + 1726666494000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1603729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0396271^2 + 17266666494000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1603729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0396271^2 + 172666666494000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1603729^2 \end{aligned}$$

778)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0394716^2 + 1556000^2 & := & 1605284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0394716^2 + 17116000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1605284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0394716^2 + 172716000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1605284^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0394716^2 + 1728716000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1605284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0394716^2 + 17288716000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1605284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0394716^2 + 172888716000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1605284^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0394716^2 + 1728888716000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1605284^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0394716^2 + 17288888716000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1605284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0394716^2 + 172888888716000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1605284^2 \end{aligned}$$

779)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0393159^2 + 1558000^2 & := & 1606841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0393159^2 + 17138000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1606841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0393159^2 + 172938000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1606841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0393159^2 + 1730938000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1606841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0393159^2 + 17310938000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1606841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0393159^2 + 173110938000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1606841^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0393159^2 + 1731110938000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1606841^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0393159^2 + 17311110938000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1606841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0393159^2 + 173111110938000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1606841^2 \end{aligned}$$

780)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0391600^2 + 1560000^2 & := & 1608400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0391600^2 + 17160000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1608400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0391600^2 + 173160000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1608400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0391600^2 + 1733160000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1608400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0391600^2 + 17333160000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1608400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0391600^2 + 173333160000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1608400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0391600^2 + 1733333160000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1608400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0391600^2 + 17333333160000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1608400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0391600^2 + 173333333160000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1608400^2 \end{aligned}$$

781)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0390039^2 + 1562000^2 & := & 1609961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0390039^2 + 17182000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1609961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0390039^2 + 173382000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1609961^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0390039^2 + 1735382000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1609961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0390039^2 + 17355382000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1609961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0390039^2 + 173555382000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1609961^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0390039^2 + 1735555382000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1609961^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0390039^2 + 17355555382000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1609961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0390039^2 + 173555555382000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1609961^2 \end{aligned}$$

782)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0388476^2 + 1564000^2 & := & 1611524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0388476^2 + 17204000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1611524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0388476^2 + 173604000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1611524^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0388476^2 + 1737604000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1611524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0388476^2 + 17377604000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1611524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0388476^2 + 173777604000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1611524^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0388476^2 + 1737777604000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1611524^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0388476^2 + 17377777604000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1611524^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0388476^2 + 173777777604000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1611524^2 \end{aligned}$$

783)

$$\begin{aligned} &0386911^2 + 1566000^2 && := 1613089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0386911^2 + 17226000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1613089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0386911^2 + 173826000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1613089^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0386911^2 + 1739826000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1613089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0386911^2 + 17399826000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1613089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0386911^2 + 173999826000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1613089^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0386911^2 + 1739999826000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1613089^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0386911^2 + 17399999826000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1613089^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0386911^2 + 173999999826000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1613089^2 \end{aligned}$$

784)

$$\begin{aligned} &0385344^2 + 1568000^2 && := 1614656^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0385344^2 + 17248000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1614656^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0385344^2 + 174048000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1614656^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0385344^2 + 1742048000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1614656^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0385344^2 + 17422048000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1614656^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0385344^2 + 174222048000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1614656^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0385344^2 + 1742222048000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1614656^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0385344^2 + 17422222048000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1614656^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0385344^2 + 174222222048000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1614656^2 \end{aligned}$$

785)

$$\begin{aligned} &0383775^2 + 1570000^2 && := 1616225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0383775^2 + 17270000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1616225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0383775^2 + 174270000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1616225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0383775^2 + 1744270000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1616225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0383775^2 + 17444270000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1616225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0383775^2 + 174444270000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1616225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0383775^2 + 1744444270000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1616225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0383775^2 + 17444444270000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1616225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0383775^2 + 174444444270000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1616225^2 \end{aligned}$$

786)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0382204^2 + 1572000^2 & := & 1617796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0382204^2 + 17292000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1617796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0382204^2 + 174492000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1617796^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0382204^2 + 1746492000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1617796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0382204^2 + 17466492000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1617796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0382204^2 + 174666492000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1617796^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0382204^2 + 1746666492000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1617796^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0382204^2 + 17466666492000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1617796^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0382204^2 + 174666666492000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1617796^2 \end{aligned}$$

787)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0380631^2 + 1574000^2 & := & 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0380631^2 + 17314000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0380631^2 + 174714000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0380631^2 + 1748714000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0380631^2 + 17488714000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0380631^2 + 174888714000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0380631^2 + 1748888714000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0380631^2 + 17488888714000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0380631^2 + 174888888714000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1619369^2 \end{aligned}$$

788)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0379056^2 + 1576000^2 & := & 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0379056^2 + 17336000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0379056^2 + 174936000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0379056^2 + 1750936000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0379056^2 + 17510936000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0379056^2 + 175110936000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0379056^2 + 1751110936000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0379056^2 + 17511110936000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0379056^2 + 175111110936000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1620944^2 \end{aligned}$$

789)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0377479^2 + 1578000^2 & := & 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0377479^2 + 17358000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0377479^2 + 175158000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0377479^2 + 1753158000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0377479^2 + 17533158000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0377479^2 + 175333158000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0377479^2 + 1753333158000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0377479^2 + 17533333158000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0377479^2 + 175333333158000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1622521^2 \end{aligned}$$

790)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0375900^2 + 1580000^2 & := & 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0375900^2 + 17380000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0375900^2 + 175380000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0375900^2 + 1755380000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0375900^2 + 17555380000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0375900^2 + 175555380000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0375900^2 + 1755555380000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0375900^2 + 17555555380000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0375900^2 + 175555555380000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1624100^2 \end{aligned}$$

791)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0374319^2 + 1582000^2 & := & 1625681^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0374319^2 + 17402000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1625681^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0374319^2 + 175602000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1625681^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0374319^2 + 1757602000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1625681^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0374319^2 + 17577602000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1625681^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0374319^2 + 175777602000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1625681^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0374319^2 + 1757777602000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1625681^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0374319^2 + 17577777602000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1625681^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0374319^2 + 175777777602000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1625681^2 \end{aligned}$$

792)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0372736^2 + 1584000^2 & := & 1627264^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0372736^2 + 17424000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1627264^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0372736^2 + 175824000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1627264^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0372736^2 + 1759824000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1627264^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0372736^2 + 17599824000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1627264^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0372736^2 + 175999824000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1627264^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0372736^2 + 1759999824000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1627264^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0372736^2 + 17599999824000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1627264^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0372736^2 + 175999999824000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1627264^2 \end{aligned}$$

793)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0371151^2 + 1586000^2 & := & 1628849^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0371151^2 + 17446000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1628849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0371151^2 + 176046000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1628849^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0371151^2 + 1762046000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1628849^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0371151^2 + 17622046000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1628849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0371151^2 + 176222046000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1628849^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0371151^2 + 1762222046000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1628849^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0371151^2 + 17622222046000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1628849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0371151^2 + 176222222046000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1628849^2 \end{aligned}$$

794)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0369564^2 + 1588000^2 & := & 1630436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0369564^2 + 17468000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1630436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0369564^2 + 176268000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1630436^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0369564^2 + 1764268000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1630436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0369564^2 + 17644268000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1630436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0369564^2 + 176444268000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1630436^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0369564^2 + 1764444268000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1630436^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0369564^2 + 17644444268000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1630436^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0369564^2 + 176444444268000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1630436^2 \end{aligned}$$

795)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0367975^2 + 1590000^2 & := & 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0367975^2 + 17490000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0367975^2 + 176490000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0367975^2 + 1766490000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0367975^2 + 17666490000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0367975^2 + 176666490000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0367975^2 + 1766666490000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0367975^2 + 17666666490000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0367975^2 + 176666666490000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1632025^2 \end{aligned}$$

796)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0366384^2 + 1592000^2 & := & 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0366384^2 + 17512000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0366384^2 + 176712000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0366384^2 + 1768712000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0366384^2 + 17688712000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0366384^2 + 176888712000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0366384^2 + 1768888712000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0366384^2 + 17688888712000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0366384^2 + 176888888712000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1633616^2 \end{aligned}$$

797)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0364791^2 + 1594000^2 & := & 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0364791^2 + 17534000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0364791^2 + 176934000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0364791^2 + 1770934000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0364791^2 + 17710934000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0364791^2 + 177110934000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0364791^2 + 1771110934000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0364791^2 + 17711110934000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0364791^2 + 177111110934000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1635209^2 \end{aligned}$$

798)

$$\begin{aligned} &0363196^2 + 1596000^2 && := 1636804^2 \\ &12\ 0363196^2 + 17556000^2 && := 12\ 1636804^2 \\ &1232\ 0363196^2 + 177156000^2 && := 1232\ 1636804^2 \\ &123432\ 0363196^2 + 1773156000^2 && := 123432\ 1636804^2 \\ &12345432\ 0363196^2 + 17733156000^2 && := 12345432\ 1636804^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0363196^2 + 177333156000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1636804^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0363196^2 + 1773333156000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1636804^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0363196^2 + 17733333156000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1636804^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0363196^2 + 177333333156000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1636804^2 \end{aligned}$$

799)

$$\begin{aligned} &0361599^2 + 1598000^2 && := 1638401^2 \\ &12\ 0361599^2 + 17578000^2 && := 12\ 1638401^2 \\ &1232\ 0361599^2 + 177378000^2 && := 1232\ 1638401^2 \\ &123432\ 0361599^2 + 1775378000^2 && := 123432\ 1638401^2 \\ &12345432\ 0361599^2 + 17755378000^2 && := 12345432\ 1638401^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0361599^2 + 177555378000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1638401^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0361599^2 + 1775555378000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1638401^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0361599^2 + 17755555378000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1638401^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0361599^2 + 177555555378000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1638401^2 \end{aligned}$$

800)

$$\begin{aligned} &0360000^2 + 1600000^2 && := 1640000^2 \\ &12\ 0360000^2 + 17600000^2 && := 12\ 1640000^2 \\ &1232\ 0360000^2 + 177600000^2 && := 1232\ 1640000^2 \\ &123432\ 0360000^2 + 1777600000^2 && := 123432\ 1640000^2 \\ &12345432\ 0360000^2 + 17777600000^2 && := 12345432\ 1640000^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0360000^2 + 177777600000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1640000^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0360000^2 + 1777777600000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1640000^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0360000^2 + 17777777600000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1640000^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0360000^2 + 177777777600000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1640000^2 \end{aligned}$$

801)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0358399^2 + 1602000^2 & := & 1641601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0358399^2 + 17622000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1641601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0358399^2 + 177822000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1641601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0358399^2 + 1779822000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1641601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0358399^2 + 17799822000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1641601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0358399^2 + 177999822000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1641601^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0358399^2 + 1779999822000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1641601^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0358399^2 + 17799999822000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1641601^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0358399^2 + 177999999822000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1641601^2 \end{aligned}$$

802)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0356796^2 + 1604000^2 & := & 1643204^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0356796^2 + 17644000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1643204^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0356796^2 + 178044000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1643204^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0356796^2 + 1782044000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1643204^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0356796^2 + 17822044000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1643204^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0356796^2 + 178222044000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1643204^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0356796^2 + 1782222044000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1643204^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0356796^2 + 17822222044000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1643204^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0356796^2 + 178222222044000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1643204^2 \end{aligned}$$

803)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0355191^2 + 1606000^2 & := & 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0355191^2 + 17666000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0355191^2 + 178266000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0355191^2 + 1784266000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0355191^2 + 17844266000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0355191^2 + 178444266000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0355191^2 + 1784444266000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0355191^2 + 17844444266000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0355191^2 + 178444444266000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1644809^2 \end{aligned}$$

804)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0353584^2 + 1608000^2 & := & 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0353584^2 + 17688000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0353584^2 + 178488000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0353584^2 + 1786488000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0353584^2 + 17866488000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0353584^2 + 178666488000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0353584^2 + 1786666488000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0353584^2 + 17866666488000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0353584^2 + 178666666488000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1646416^2 \end{aligned}$$

805)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0351975^2 + 1610000^2 & := & 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0351975^2 + 17710000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0351975^2 + 178710000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0351975^2 + 1788710000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0351975^2 + 17888710000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0351975^2 + 178888710000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0351975^2 + 1788888710000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0351975^2 + 17888888710000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0351975^2 + 178888888710000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1648025^2 \end{aligned}$$

806)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0350364^2 + 1612000^2 & := & 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0350364^2 + 17732000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0350364^2 + 178932000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0350364^2 + 1790932000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0350364^2 + 17910932000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0350364^2 + 179110932000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0350364^2 + 1791110932000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0350364^2 + 17911110932000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0350364^2 + 179111110932000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1649636^2 \end{aligned}$$

807)

$$\begin{aligned} &0348751^2 + 1614000^2 && := 1651249^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0348751^2 + 17754000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1651249^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0348751^2 + 179154000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1651249^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0348751^2 + 1793154000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1651249^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0348751^2 + 17933154000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1651249^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0348751^2 + 179333154000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1651249^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0348751^2 + 1793333154000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1651249^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0348751^2 + 17933333154000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1651249^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0348751^2 + 179333333154000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1651249^2 \end{aligned}$$

808)

$$\begin{aligned} &0347136^2 + 1616000^2 && := 1652864^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0347136^2 + 17776000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1652864^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0347136^2 + 179376000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1652864^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0347136^2 + 1795376000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1652864^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0347136^2 + 17955376000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1652864^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0347136^2 + 179555376000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1652864^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0347136^2 + 1795555376000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1652864^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0347136^2 + 17955555376000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1652864^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0347136^2 + 179555555376000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1652864^2 \end{aligned}$$

809)

$$\begin{aligned} &0345519^2 + 1618000^2 && := 1654481^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0345519^2 + 17798000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1654481^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0345519^2 + 179598000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1654481^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0345519^2 + 1797598000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1654481^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0345519^2 + 17977598000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1654481^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0345519^2 + 179777598000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1654481^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0345519^2 + 1797777598000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1654481^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0345519^2 + 17977777598000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1654481^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0345519^2 + 179777777598000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1654481^2 \end{aligned}$$

810)

$$\begin{aligned} &0343900^2 + 1620000^2 && := 1656100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0343900^2 + 17820000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1656100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0343900^2 + 179820000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1656100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0343900^2 + 1799820000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1656100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0343900^2 + 17999820000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1656100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0343900^2 + 179999820000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1656100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0343900^2 + 1799999820000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1656100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0343900^2 + 17999999820000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1656100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0343900^2 + 179999999820000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1656100^2 \end{aligned}$$

811)

$$\begin{aligned} &0342279^2 + 1622000^2 && := 1657721^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0342279^2 + 17842000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1657721^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0342279^2 + 180042000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1657721^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0342279^2 + 1802042000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1657721^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0342279^2 + 18022042000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1657721^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0342279^2 + 180222042000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1657721^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0342279^2 + 1802222042000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1657721^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0342279^2 + 18022222042000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1657721^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0342279^2 + 180222222042000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1657721^2 \end{aligned}$$

812)

$$\begin{aligned} &0340656^2 + 1624000^2 && := 1659344^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0340656^2 + 17864000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1659344^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0340656^2 + 180264000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1659344^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0340656^2 + 1804264000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1659344^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0340656^2 + 18044264000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1659344^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0340656^2 + 180444264000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1659344^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0340656^2 + 1804444264000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1659344^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0340656^2 + 18044444264000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1659344^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0340656^2 + 180444444264000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1659344^2 \end{aligned}$$

813)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0339031^2 + 1626000^2 & := & 1660969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0339031^2 + 17886000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1660969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0339031^2 + 180486000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1660969^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0339031^2 + 1806486000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1660969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0339031^2 + 18066486000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1660969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0339031^2 + 180666486000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1660969^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0339031^2 + 1806666486000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1660969^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0339031^2 + 18066666486000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1660969^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0339031^2 + 180666666486000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1660969^2 \end{aligned}$$

814)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0337404^2 + 1628000^2 & := & 1662596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0337404^2 + 17908000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1662596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0337404^2 + 180708000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1662596^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0337404^2 + 1808708000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1662596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0337404^2 + 18088708000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1662596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0337404^2 + 180888708000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1662596^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0337404^2 + 1808888708000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1662596^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0337404^2 + 18088888708000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1662596^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0337404^2 + 180888888708000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1662596^2 \end{aligned}$$

815)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0335775^2 + 1630000^2 & := & 1664225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0335775^2 + 17930000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1664225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0335775^2 + 180930000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1664225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0335775^2 + 1810930000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1664225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0335775^2 + 18110930000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1664225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0335775^2 + 181110930000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1664225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0335775^2 + 1811110930000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1664225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0335775^2 + 18111110930000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1664225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0335775^2 + 181111110930000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1664225^2 \end{aligned}$$

816)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0334144^2 + 1632000^2 & := & 1665856^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0334144^2 + 17952000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1665856^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0334144^2 + 181152000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1665856^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0334144^2 + 1813152000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1665856^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0334144^2 + 18133152000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1665856^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0334144^2 + 181333152000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1665856^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0334144^2 + 1813333152000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1665856^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0334144^2 + 18133333152000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1665856^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0334144^2 + 181333333152000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1665856^2 \end{aligned}$$

817)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0332511^2 + 1634000^2 & := & 1667489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0332511^2 + 17974000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1667489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0332511^2 + 181374000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1667489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0332511^2 + 1815374000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1667489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0332511^2 + 18155374000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1667489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0332511^2 + 181555374000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1667489^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0332511^2 + 1815555374000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1667489^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0332511^2 + 18155555374000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1667489^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0332511^2 + 181555555374000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1667489^2 \end{aligned}$$

818)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0330876^2 + 1636000^2 & := & 1669124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0330876^2 + 17996000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1669124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0330876^2 + 181596000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1669124^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0330876^2 + 1817596000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1669124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0330876^2 + 18177596000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1669124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0330876^2 + 181777596000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1669124^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0330876^2 + 1817777596000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1669124^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0330876^2 + 18177777596000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1669124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0330876^2 + 181777777596000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1669124^2 \end{aligned}$$

819)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0329239^2 + 1638000^2 & := & 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0329239^2 + 18018000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0329239^2 + 181818000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0329239^2 + 1819818000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0329239^2 + 18199818000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0329239^2 + 181999818000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0329239^2 + 1819999818000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0329239^2 + 18199999818000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0329239^2 + 181999999818000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1670761^2 \end{aligned}$$

820)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0327600^2 + 1640000^2 & := & 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0327600^2 + 18040000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0327600^2 + 182040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0327600^2 + 1822040000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0327600^2 + 18222040000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0327600^2 + 182222040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0327600^2 + 1822222040000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0327600^2 + 18222222040000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0327600^2 + 182222222040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1672400^2 \end{aligned}$$

821)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0325959^2 + 1642000^2 & := & 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0325959^2 + 18062000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0325959^2 + 182262000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0325959^2 + 1824262000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0325959^2 + 18244262000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0325959^2 + 182444262000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0325959^2 + 1824444262000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0325959^2 + 18244444262000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0325959^2 + 182444444262000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1674041^2 \end{aligned}$$

822)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0324316^2 + 1644000^2 & := & 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0324316^2 + 18084000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0324316^2 + 182484000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0324316^2 + 1826484000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0324316^2 + 18266484000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0324316^2 + 182666484000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0324316^2 + 1826666484000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0324316^2 + 18266666484000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0324316^2 + 182666666484000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1675684^2 \end{aligned}$$

823)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0322671^2 + 1646000^2 & := & 1677329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0322671^2 + 18106000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1677329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0322671^2 + 182706000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1677329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0322671^2 + 1828706000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1677329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0322671^2 + 18288706000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1677329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0322671^2 + 182888706000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1677329^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0322671^2 + 1828888706000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1677329^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0322671^2 + 18288888706000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1677329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0322671^2 + 182888888706000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1677329^2 \end{aligned}$$

824)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0321024^2 + 1648000^2 & := & 1678976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0321024^2 + 18128000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1678976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0321024^2 + 182928000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1678976^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0321024^2 + 1830928000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1678976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0321024^2 + 18310928000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1678976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0321024^2 + 183110928000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1678976^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0321024^2 + 1831110928000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1678976^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0321024^2 + 18311110928000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1678976^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0321024^2 + 183111110928000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1678976^2 \end{aligned}$$

825)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0319375^2 + 1650000^2 & := & 1680625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0319375^2 + 18150000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1680625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0319375^2 + 183150000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1680625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0319375^2 + 1833150000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1680625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0319375^2 + 18333150000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1680625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0319375^2 + 183333150000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1680625^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0319375^2 + 1833333150000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1680625^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0319375^2 + 18333333150000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1680625^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0319375^2 + 183333333150000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1680625^2 \end{aligned}$$

826)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0317724^2 + 1652000^2 & := & 1682276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0317724^2 + 18172000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1682276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0317724^2 + 183372000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1682276^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0317724^2 + 1835372000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1682276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0317724^2 + 18355372000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1682276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0317724^2 + 183555372000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1682276^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0317724^2 + 1835555372000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1682276^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0317724^2 + 18355555372000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1682276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0317724^2 + 183555555372000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1682276^2 \end{aligned}$$

827)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0316071^2 + 1654000^2 & := & 1683929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0316071^2 + 18194000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1683929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0316071^2 + 183594000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1683929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0316071^2 + 1837594000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1683929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0316071^2 + 18377594000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1683929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0316071^2 + 183777594000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1683929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0316071^2 + 1837777594000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1683929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0316071^2 + 18377777594000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1683929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0316071^2 + 183777777594000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1683929^2 \end{aligned}$$

828)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0314416^2 + 1656000^2 & := & 1685584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0314416^2 + 18216000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1685584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0314416^2 + 183816000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1685584^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0314416^2 + 1839816000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1685584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0314416^2 + 18399816000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1685584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0314416^2 + 183999816000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1685584^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0314416^2 + 1839999816000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1685584^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0314416^2 + 18399999816000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1685584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0314416^2 + 183999999816000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1685584^2 \end{aligned}$$

829)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0312759^2 + 1658000^2 & := & 1687241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0312759^2 + 18238000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1687241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0312759^2 + 184038000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1687241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0312759^2 + 1842038000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1687241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0312759^2 + 18422038000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1687241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0312759^2 + 184222038000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1687241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0312759^2 + 1842222038000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1687241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0312759^2 + 18422222038000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1687241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0312759^2 + 184222222038000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1687241^2 \end{aligned}$$

830)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0311100^2 + 1660000^2 & := & 1688900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0311100^2 + 18260000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1688900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0311100^2 + 184260000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1688900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0311100^2 + 1844260000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1688900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0311100^2 + 18444260000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1688900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0311100^2 + 184444260000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1688900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0311100^2 + 1844444260000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1688900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0311100^2 + 18444444260000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1688900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0311100^2 + 184444444260000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1688900^2 \end{aligned}$$

831)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0309439^2 + 1662000^2 & := & 1690561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0309439^2 + 18282000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1690561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0309439^2 + 184482000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1690561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0309439^2 + 1846482000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1690561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0309439^2 + 18466482000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1690561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0309439^2 + 184666482000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1690561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0309439^2 + 1846666482000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1690561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0309439^2 + 18466666482000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1690561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0309439^2 + 184666666482000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1690561^2 \end{aligned}$$

832)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0307776^2 + 1664000^2 & := & 1692224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0307776^2 + 18304000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1692224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0307776^2 + 184704000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1692224^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0307776^2 + 1848704000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1692224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0307776^2 + 18488704000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1692224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0307776^2 + 184888704000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1692224^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0307776^2 + 1848888704000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1692224^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0307776^2 + 18488888704000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1692224^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0307776^2 + 184888888704000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1692224^2 \end{aligned}$$

833)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0306111^2 + 1666000^2 & := & 1693889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0306111^2 + 18326000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1693889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0306111^2 + 184926000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1693889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0306111^2 + 1850926000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1693889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0306111^2 + 18510926000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1693889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0306111^2 + 185110926000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1693889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0306111^2 + 1851110926000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1693889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0306111^2 + 18511110926000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1693889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0306111^2 + 185111110926000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1693889^2 \end{aligned}$$

834)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0304444^2 + 1668000^2 & := & 1695556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0304444^2 + 18348000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1695556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0304444^2 + 185148000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1695556^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0304444^2 + 1853148000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1695556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0304444^2 + 18533148000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1695556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0304444^2 + 185333148000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1695556^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0304444^2 + 1853333148000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1695556^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0304444^2 + 18533333148000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1695556^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0304444^2 + 185333333148000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1695556^2 \end{aligned}$$

835)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0302775^2 + 1670000^2 & := & 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0302775^2 + 18370000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0302775^2 + 185370000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0302775^2 + 1855370000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0302775^2 + 18555370000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0302775^2 + 185555370000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0302775^2 + 1855555370000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0302775^2 + 18555555370000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0302775^2 + 185555555370000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1697225^2 \end{aligned}$$

836)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0301104^2 + 1672000^2 & := & 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0301104^2 + 18392000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0301104^2 + 185592000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0301104^2 + 1857592000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0301104^2 + 18577592000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0301104^2 + 185777592000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0301104^2 + 1857777592000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0301104^2 + 18577777592000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0301104^2 + 185777777592000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1698896^2 \end{aligned}$$

837)

$$\begin{aligned} &0299431^2 + 1674000^2 && := 1700569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0299431^2 + 18414000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1700569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0299431^2 + 185814000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1700569^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0299431^2 + 1859814000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1700569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0299431^2 + 18599814000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1700569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0299431^2 + 185999814000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1700569^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0299431^2 + 1859999814000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1700569^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0299431^2 + 18599999814000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1700569^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0299431^2 + 185999999814000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1700569^2 \end{aligned}$$

838)

$$\begin{aligned} &0297756^2 + 1676000^2 && := 1702244^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0297756^2 + 18436000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1702244^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0297756^2 + 186036000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1702244^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0297756^2 + 1862036000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1702244^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0297756^2 + 18622036000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1702244^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0297756^2 + 186222036000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1702244^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0297756^2 + 1862222036000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1702244^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0297756^2 + 18622222036000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1702244^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0297756^2 + 186222222036000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1702244^2 \end{aligned}$$

839)

$$\begin{aligned} &0296079^2 + 1678000^2 && := 1703921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0296079^2 + 18458000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1703921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0296079^2 + 186258000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1703921^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0296079^2 + 1864258000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1703921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0296079^2 + 18644258000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1703921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0296079^2 + 186444258000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1703921^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0296079^2 + 1864444258000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1703921^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0296079^2 + 18644444258000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1703921^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0296079^2 + 186444444258000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1703921^2 \end{aligned}$$

840)

$$\begin{aligned} &0294400^2 + 1680000^2 && := 1705600^2 \\ &12\ 0294400^2 + 18480000^2 && := 12\ 1705600^2 \\ &1232\ 0294400^2 + 186480000^2 && := 1232\ 1705600^2 \\ &123432\ 0294400^2 + 1866480000^2 && := 123432\ 1705600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0294400^2 + 18666480000^2 && := 12345432\ 1705600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0294400^2 + 186666480000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1705600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0294400^2 + 1866666480000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1705600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0294400^2 + 18666666480000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1705600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0294400^2 + 186666666480000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1705600^2 \end{aligned}$$

841)

$$\begin{aligned} &0292719^2 + 1682000^2 && := 1707281^2 \\ &12\ 0292719^2 + 18502000^2 && := 12\ 1707281^2 \\ &1232\ 0292719^2 + 186702000^2 && := 1232\ 1707281^2 \\ &123432\ 0292719^2 + 1868702000^2 && := 123432\ 1707281^2 \\ &12345432\ 0292719^2 + 18688702000^2 && := 12345432\ 1707281^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0292719^2 + 186888702000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1707281^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0292719^2 + 1868888702000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1707281^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0292719^2 + 18688888702000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1707281^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0292719^2 + 186888888702000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1707281^2 \end{aligned}$$

842)

$$\begin{aligned} &0291036^2 + 1684000^2 && := 1708964^2 \\ &12\ 0291036^2 + 18524000^2 && := 12\ 1708964^2 \\ &1232\ 0291036^2 + 186924000^2 && := 1232\ 1708964^2 \\ &123432\ 0291036^2 + 1870924000^2 && := 123432\ 1708964^2 \\ &12345432\ 0291036^2 + 18710924000^2 && := 12345432\ 1708964^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0291036^2 + 187110924000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1708964^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0291036^2 + 1871110924000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1708964^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0291036^2 + 18711110924000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1708964^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0291036^2 + 187111110924000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1708964^2 \end{aligned}$$

843)

$$\begin{aligned} &0289351^2 + 1686000^2 && := 1710649^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0289351^2 + 18546000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1710649^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0289351^2 + 187146000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1710649^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0289351^2 + 1873146000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1710649^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0289351^2 + 18733146000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1710649^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0289351^2 + 187333146000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1710649^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0289351^2 + 1873333146000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1710649^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0289351^2 + 18733333146000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1710649^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0289351^2 + 187333333146000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1710649^2 \end{aligned}$$

844)

$$\begin{aligned} &0287664^2 + 1688000^2 && := 1712336^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0287664^2 + 18568000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1712336^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0287664^2 + 187368000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1712336^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0287664^2 + 1875368000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1712336^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0287664^2 + 18755368000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1712336^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0287664^2 + 187555368000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1712336^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0287664^2 + 1875555368000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1712336^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0287664^2 + 18755555368000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1712336^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0287664^2 + 187555555368000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1712336^2 \end{aligned}$$

845)

$$\begin{aligned} &0285975^2 + 1690000^2 && := 1714025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0285975^2 + 18590000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1714025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0285975^2 + 187590000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1714025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0285975^2 + 1877590000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1714025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0285975^2 + 18777590000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1714025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0285975^2 + 187777590000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1714025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0285975^2 + 1877777590000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1714025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0285975^2 + 18777777590000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1714025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0285975^2 + 187777777590000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1714025^2 \end{aligned}$$

846)

$$\begin{aligned} &0284284^2 + 1692000^2 && := 1715716^2 \\ &12\ 0284284^2 + 18612000^2 && := 12\ 1715716^2 \\ &1232\ 0284284^2 + 187812000^2 && := 1232\ 1715716^2 \\ &123432\ 0284284^2 + 1879812000^2 && := 123432\ 1715716^2 \\ &12345432\ 0284284^2 + 18799812000^2 && := 12345432\ 1715716^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0284284^2 + 187999812000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1715716^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0284284^2 + 1879999812000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1715716^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0284284^2 + 18799999812000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1715716^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0284284^2 + 187999999812000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1715716^2 \end{aligned}$$

847)

$$\begin{aligned} &0282591^2 + 1694000^2 && := 1717409^2 \\ &12\ 0282591^2 + 18634000^2 && := 12\ 1717409^2 \\ &1232\ 0282591^2 + 188034000^2 && := 1232\ 1717409^2 \\ &123432\ 0282591^2 + 1882034000^2 && := 123432\ 1717409^2 \\ &12345432\ 0282591^2 + 18822034000^2 && := 12345432\ 1717409^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0282591^2 + 188222034000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1717409^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0282591^2 + 1882222034000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1717409^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0282591^2 + 18822222034000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1717409^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0282591^2 + 188222222034000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1717409^2 \end{aligned}$$

848)

$$\begin{aligned} &0280896^2 + 1696000^2 && := 1719104^2 \\ &12\ 0280896^2 + 18656000^2 && := 12\ 1719104^2 \\ &1232\ 0280896^2 + 188256000^2 && := 1232\ 1719104^2 \\ &123432\ 0280896^2 + 1884256000^2 && := 123432\ 1719104^2 \\ &12345432\ 0280896^2 + 18844256000^2 && := 12345432\ 1719104^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0280896^2 + 188444256000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1719104^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0280896^2 + 1884444256000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1719104^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0280896^2 + 18844444256000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1719104^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0280896^2 + 188444444256000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1719104^2 \end{aligned}$$

849)

$$\begin{aligned} &0279199^2 + 1698000^2 && := 1720801^2 \\ &12\ 0279199^2 + 18678000^2 && := 12\ 1720801^2 \\ &1232\ 0279199^2 + 188478000^2 && := 1232\ 1720801^2 \\ &123432\ 0279199^2 + 1886478000^2 && := 123432\ 1720801^2 \\ &12345432\ 0279199^2 + 18866478000^2 && := 12345432\ 1720801^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0279199^2 + 188666478000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1720801^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0279199^2 + 1886666478000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1720801^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0279199^2 + 18866666478000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1720801^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0279199^2 + 188666666478000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1720801^2 \end{aligned}$$

850)

$$\begin{aligned} &0277500^2 + 1700000^2 && := 1722500^2 \\ &12\ 0277500^2 + 18700000^2 && := 12\ 1722500^2 \\ &1232\ 0277500^2 + 188700000^2 && := 1232\ 1722500^2 \\ &123432\ 0277500^2 + 1888700000^2 && := 123432\ 1722500^2 \\ &12345432\ 0277500^2 + 18888700000^2 && := 12345432\ 1722500^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0277500^2 + 188888700000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1722500^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0277500^2 + 1888888700000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1722500^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0277500^2 + 18888888700000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1722500^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0277500^2 + 188888888700000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1722500^2 \end{aligned}$$

851)

$$\begin{aligned} &0275799^2 + 1702000^2 && := 1724201^2 \\ &12\ 0275799^2 + 18722000^2 && := 12\ 1724201^2 \\ &1232\ 0275799^2 + 188922000^2 && := 1232\ 1724201^2 \\ &123432\ 0275799^2 + 1890922000^2 && := 123432\ 1724201^2 \\ &12345432\ 0275799^2 + 18910922000^2 && := 12345432\ 1724201^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0275799^2 + 189110922000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1724201^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0275799^2 + 1891110922000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1724201^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0275799^2 + 18911110922000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1724201^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0275799^2 + 189111110922000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1724201^2 \end{aligned}$$

852)

$$\begin{aligned} &0274096^2 + 1704000^2 && := 1725904^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0274096^2 + 18744000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1725904^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0274096^2 + 189144000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1725904^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0274096^2 + 1893144000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1725904^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0274096^2 + 18933144000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1725904^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0274096^2 + 189333144000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1725904^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0274096^2 + 1893333144000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1725904^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0274096^2 + 18933333144000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1725904^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0274096^2 + 189333333144000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1725904^2 \end{aligned}$$

853)

$$\begin{aligned} &0272391^2 + 1706000^2 && := 1727609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0272391^2 + 18766000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1727609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0272391^2 + 189366000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1727609^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0272391^2 + 1895366000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1727609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0272391^2 + 18955366000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1727609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0272391^2 + 189555366000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1727609^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0272391^2 + 189555366000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1727609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0272391^2 + 1895555366000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1727609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0272391^2 + 18955555366000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1727609^2 \end{aligned}$$

854)

$$\begin{aligned} &0270684^2 + 1708000^2 && := 1729316^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0270684^2 + 18788000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1729316^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0270684^2 + 189588000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1729316^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0270684^2 + 1897588000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1729316^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0270684^2 + 18977588000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1729316^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0270684^2 + 189777588000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1729316^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0270684^2 + 1897777588000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1729316^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0270684^2 + 18977777588000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1729316^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0270684^2 + 189777777588000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1729316^2 \end{aligned}$$

855)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0268975^2 + 1710000^2 & := & 1731025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0268975^2 + 18810000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1731025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0268975^2 + 189810000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1731025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0268975^2 + 1899810000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1731025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0268975^2 + 18999810000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1731025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0268975^2 + 189999810000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1731025^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0268975^2 + 1899999810000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1731025^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0268975^2 + 18999999810000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1731025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0268975^2 + 189999999810000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1731025^2 \end{aligned}$$

856)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0267264^2 + 1712000^2 & := & 1732736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0267264^2 + 18832000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1732736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0267264^2 + 190032000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1732736^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0267264^2 + 1902032000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1732736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0267264^2 + 19022032000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1732736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0267264^2 + 190222032000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1732736^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0267264^2 + 1902222032000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1732736^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0267264^2 + 19022222032000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1732736^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0267264^2 + 190222222032000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1732736^2 \end{aligned}$$

857)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0265551^2 + 1714000^2 & := & 1734449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0265551^2 + 18854000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1734449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0265551^2 + 190254000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1734449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0265551^2 + 1904254000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1734449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0265551^2 + 19044254000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1734449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0265551^2 + 190444254000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1734449^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0265551^2 + 1904444254000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1734449^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0265551^2 + 19044444254000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1734449^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0265551^2 + 190444444254000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1734449^2 \end{aligned}$$

858)

$$\begin{aligned} &0263836^2 + 1716000^2 && := 1736164^2 \\ &12\ 0263836^2 + 18876000^2 && := 12\ 1736164^2 \\ &1232\ 0263836^2 + 190476000^2 && := 1232\ 1736164^2 \\ &123432\ 0263836^2 + 1906476000^2 && := 123432\ 1736164^2 \\ &12345432\ 0263836^2 + 19066476000^2 && := 12345432\ 1736164^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0263836^2 + 190666476000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1736164^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0263836^2 + 1906666476000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1736164^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0263836^2 + 19066666476000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1736164^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0263836^2 + 190666666476000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1736164^2 \end{aligned}$$

859)

$$\begin{aligned} &0262119^2 + 1718000^2 && := 1737881^2 \\ &12\ 0262119^2 + 18898000^2 && := 12\ 1737881^2 \\ &1232\ 0262119^2 + 190698000^2 && := 1232\ 1737881^2 \\ &123432\ 0262119^2 + 1908698000^2 && := 123432\ 1737881^2 \\ &12345432\ 0262119^2 + 19088698000^2 && := 12345432\ 1737881^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0262119^2 + 190888698000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1737881^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0262119^2 + 1908888698000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1737881^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0262119^2 + 19088888698000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1737881^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0262119^2 + 190888888698000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1737881^2 \end{aligned}$$

860)

$$\begin{aligned} &0260400^2 + 1720000^2 && := 1739600^2 \\ &12\ 0260400^2 + 18920000^2 && := 12\ 1739600^2 \\ &1232\ 0260400^2 + 190920000^2 && := 1232\ 1739600^2 \\ &123432\ 0260400^2 + 1910920000^2 && := 123432\ 1739600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0260400^2 + 19110920000^2 && := 12345432\ 1739600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0260400^2 + 191110920000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1739600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0260400^2 + 1911110920000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1739600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0260400^2 + 19111110920000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1739600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0260400^2 + 191111110920000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1739600^2 \end{aligned}$$

861)

$$\begin{aligned} &0258679^2 + 1722000^2 && := 1741321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0258679^2 + 18942000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1741321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0258679^2 + 191142000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1741321^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0258679^2 + 1913142000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1741321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0258679^2 + 19133142000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1741321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0258679^2 + 191333142000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1741321^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0258679^2 + 1913333142000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1741321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0258679^2 + 19133333142000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1741321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0258679^2 + 191333333142000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1741321^2 \end{aligned}$$

862)

$$\begin{aligned} &0256956^2 + 1724000^2 && := 1743044^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0256956^2 + 18964000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1743044^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0256956^2 + 191364000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1743044^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0256956^2 + 1915364000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1743044^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0256956^2 + 19155364000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1743044^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0256956^2 + 191555364000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1743044^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0256956^2 + 1915555364000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1743044^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0256956^2 + 19155555364000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1743044^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0256956^2 + 191555555364000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1743044^2 \end{aligned}$$

863)

$$\begin{aligned} &0255231^2 + 1726000^2 && := 1744769^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0255231^2 + 18986000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1744769^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0255231^2 + 191586000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1744769^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0255231^2 + 1917586000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1744769^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0255231^2 + 19177586000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1744769^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0255231^2 + 191777586000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1744769^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0255231^2 + 1917777586000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1744769^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0255231^2 + 19177777586000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1744769^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0255231^2 + 191777777586000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1744769^2 \end{aligned}$$

864)

$$\begin{aligned} &0253504^2 + 1728000^2 && := 1746496^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0253504^2 + 19008000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1746496^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0253504^2 + 191808000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1746496^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0253504^2 + 1919808000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1746496^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0253504^2 + 19199808000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1746496^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0253504^2 + 191999808000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1746496^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0253504^2 + 1919999808000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1746496^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0253504^2 + 19199999808000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1746496^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0253504^2 + 191999999808000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1746496^2 \end{aligned}$$

865)

$$\begin{aligned} &0251775^2 + 1730000^2 && := 1748225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0251775^2 + 19030000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1748225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0251775^2 + 192030000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1748225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0251775^2 + 1922030000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1748225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0251775^2 + 19222030000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1748225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0251775^2 + 192222030000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1748225^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0251775^2 + 1922222030000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1748225^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0251775^2 + 19222222030000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1748225^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0251775^2 + 192222222030000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1748225^2 \end{aligned}$$

866)

$$\begin{aligned} &0250044^2 + 1732000^2 && := 1749956^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0250044^2 + 19052000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1749956^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0250044^2 + 192252000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1749956^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0250044^2 + 1924252000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1749956^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0250044^2 + 19244252000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1749956^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0250044^2 + 192444252000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1749956^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0250044^2 + 1924444252000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1749956^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0250044^2 + 19244444252000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1749956^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0250044^2 + 192444444252000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1749956^2 \end{aligned}$$

867)

$$\begin{aligned} &0248311^2 + 1734000^2 && := 1751689^2 \\ &12\ 0248311^2 + 19074000^2 && := 12\ 1751689^2 \\ &1232\ 0248311^2 + 192474000^2 && := 1232\ 1751689^2 \\ &123432\ 0248311^2 + 1926474000^2 && := 123432\ 1751689^2 \\ &12345432\ 0248311^2 + 19266474000^2 && := 12345432\ 1751689^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0248311^2 + 192666474000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1751689^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0248311^2 + 1926666474000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1751689^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0248311^2 + 19266666474000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1751689^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0248311^2 + 192666666474000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1751689^2 \end{aligned}$$

868)

$$\begin{aligned} &0246576^2 + 1736000^2 && := 1753424^2 \\ &12\ 0246576^2 + 19096000^2 && := 12\ 1753424^2 \\ &1232\ 0246576^2 + 192696000^2 && := 1232\ 1753424^2 \\ &123432\ 0246576^2 + 1928696000^2 && := 123432\ 1753424^2 \\ &12345432\ 0246576^2 + 19288696000^2 && := 12345432\ 1753424^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0246576^2 + 192888696000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1753424^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0246576^2 + 1928888696000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1753424^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0246576^2 + 19288888696000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1753424^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0246576^2 + 192888888696000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1753424^2 \end{aligned}$$

869)

$$\begin{aligned} &0244839^2 + 1738000^2 && := 1755161^2 \\ &12\ 0244839^2 + 19118000^2 && := 12\ 1755161^2 \\ &1232\ 0244839^2 + 192918000^2 && := 1232\ 1755161^2 \\ &123432\ 0244839^2 + 1930918000^2 && := 123432\ 1755161^2 \\ &12345432\ 0244839^2 + 19310918000^2 && := 12345432\ 1755161^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0244839^2 + 193110918000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1755161^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0244839^2 + 1931110918000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1755161^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0244839^2 + 19311110918000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1755161^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0244839^2 + 193111110918000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1755161^2 \end{aligned}$$

870)

$$\begin{aligned} &0243100^2 + 1740000^2 && := 1756900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0243100^2 + 19140000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1756900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0243100^2 + 193140000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1756900^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0243100^2 + 1933140000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1756900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0243100^2 + 19333140000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1756900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0243100^2 + 193333140000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1756900^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0243100^2 + 1933333140000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1756900^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0243100^2 + 19333333140000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1756900^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0243100^2 + 193333333140000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1756900^2 \end{aligned}$$

871)

$$\begin{aligned} &0241359^2 + 1742000^2 && := 1758641^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0241359^2 + 19162000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1758641^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0241359^2 + 193362000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1758641^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0241359^2 + 1935362000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1758641^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0241359^2 + 19355362000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1758641^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0241359^2 + 193555362000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1758641^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0241359^2 + 1935555362000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1758641^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0241359^2 + 19355555362000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1758641^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0241359^2 + 193555555362000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1758641^2 \end{aligned}$$

872)

$$\begin{aligned} &0239616^2 + 1744000^2 && := 1760384^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0239616^2 + 19184000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1760384^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0239616^2 + 193584000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1760384^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0239616^2 + 1937584000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1760384^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0239616^2 + 19377584000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1760384^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0239616^2 + 193777584000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1760384^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0239616^2 + 1937777584000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1760384^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0239616^2 + 19377777584000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1760384^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0239616^2 + 193777777584000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1760384^2 \end{aligned}$$

873)

$$\begin{aligned} &0237871^2 + 1746000^2 && := 1762129^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0237871^2 + 19206000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1762129^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0237871^2 + 193806000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1762129^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0237871^2 + 1939806000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1762129^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0237871^2 + 19399806000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1762129^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0237871^2 + 193999806000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1762129^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0237871^2 + 1939999806000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1762129^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0237871^2 + 19399999806000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1762129^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0237871^2 + 193999999806000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1762129^2 \end{aligned}$$

874)

$$\begin{aligned} &0236124^2 + 1748000^2 && := 1763876^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0236124^2 + 19228000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1763876^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0236124^2 + 194028000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1763876^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0236124^2 + 1942028000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1763876^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0236124^2 + 19422028000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1763876^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0236124^2 + 194222028000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1763876^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0236124^2 + 1942222028000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1763876^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0236124^2 + 19422222028000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1763876^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0236124^2 + 194222222028000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1763876^2 \end{aligned}$$

875)

$$\begin{aligned} &0234375^2 + 1750000^2 && := 1765625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0234375^2 + 19250000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1765625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0234375^2 + 194250000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1765625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0234375^2 + 1944250000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1765625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0234375^2 + 19444250000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1765625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0234375^2 + 194444250000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1765625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0234375^2 + 1944444250000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1765625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0234375^2 + 19444444250000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1765625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0234375^2 + 194444444250000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1765625^2 \end{aligned}$$

876)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0232624^2 + 1752000^2 & := & 1767376^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0232624^2 + 19272000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1767376^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0232624^2 + 194472000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1767376^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0232624^2 + 1946472000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1767376^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0232624^2 + 19466472000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1767376^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0232624^2 + 194666472000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1767376^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0232624^2 + 1946666472000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1767376^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0232624^2 + 19466666472000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1767376^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0232624^2 + 194666666472000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1767376^2 \end{aligned}$$

877)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0230871^2 + 1754000^2 & := & 1769129^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0230871^2 + 19294000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1769129^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0230871^2 + 194694000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1769129^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0230871^2 + 1948694000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1769129^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0230871^2 + 19488694000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1769129^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0230871^2 + 194888694000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1769129^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0230871^2 + 1948888694000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1769129^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0230871^2 + 19488888694000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1769129^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0230871^2 + 194888888694000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1769129^2 \end{aligned}$$

878)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0229116^2 + 1756000^2 & := & 1770884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0229116^2 + 19316000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1770884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0229116^2 + 194916000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1770884^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0229116^2 + 1950916000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1770884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0229116^2 + 19510916000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1770884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0229116^2 + 195110916000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1770884^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0229116^2 + 1951110916000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1770884^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0229116^2 + 19511110916000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1770884^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0229116^2 + 195111110916000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1770884^2 \end{aligned}$$

879)

$$\begin{aligned} &0227359^2 + 1758000^2 && := 1772641^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0227359^2 + 19338000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1772641^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0227359^2 + 195138000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1772641^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0227359^2 + 1953138000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1772641^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0227359^2 + 19533138000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1772641^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0227359^2 + 195333138000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1772641^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0227359^2 + 1953333138000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1772641^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0227359^2 + 19533333138000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1772641^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0227359^2 + 195333333138000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1772641^2 \end{aligned}$$

880)

$$\begin{aligned} &0225600^2 + 1760000^2 && := 1774400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0225600^2 + 19360000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1774400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0225600^2 + 195360000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1774400^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0225600^2 + 1955360000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1774400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0225600^2 + 19555360000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1774400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0225600^2 + 195555360000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1774400^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0225600^2 + 1955555360000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1774400^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0225600^2 + 19555555360000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1774400^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0225600^2 + 195555555360000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1774400^2 \end{aligned}$$

881)

$$\begin{aligned} &0223839^2 + 1762000^2 && := 1776161^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0223839^2 + 19382000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1776161^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0223839^2 + 195582000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1776161^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0223839^2 + 1957582000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1776161^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0223839^2 + 19577582000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1776161^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0223839^2 + 195777582000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1776161^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0223839^2 + 1957777582000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1776161^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0223839^2 + 19577777582000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1776161^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0223839^2 + 195777777582000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1776161^2 \end{aligned}$$

882)

$$\begin{aligned} &0222076^2 + 1764000^2 && := 1777924^2 \\ &12\ 0222076^2 + 19404000^2 && := 12\ 1777924^2 \\ &1232\ 0222076^2 + 195804000^2 && := 1232\ 1777924^2 \\ &123432\ 0222076^2 + 1959804000^2 && := 123432\ 1777924^2 \\ &12345432\ 0222076^2 + 19599804000^2 && := 12345432\ 1777924^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0222076^2 + 195999804000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1777924^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0222076^2 + 1959999804000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1777924^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0222076^2 + 19599999804000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1777924^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0222076^2 + 195999999804000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1777924^2 \end{aligned}$$

883)

$$\begin{aligned} &0220311^2 + 1766000^2 && := 1779689^2 \\ &12\ 0220311^2 + 19426000^2 && := 12\ 1779689^2 \\ &1232\ 0220311^2 + 196026000^2 && := 1232\ 1779689^2 \\ &123432\ 0220311^2 + 1962026000^2 && := 123432\ 1779689^2 \\ &12345432\ 0220311^2 + 19622026000^2 && := 12345432\ 1779689^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0220311^2 + 196222026000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1779689^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0220311^2 + 1962222026000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1779689^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0220311^2 + 19622222026000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1779689^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0220311^2 + 196222222026000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1779689^2 \end{aligned}$$

884)

$$\begin{aligned} &0218544^2 + 1768000^2 && := 1781456^2 \\ &12\ 0218544^2 + 19448000^2 && := 12\ 1781456^2 \\ &1232\ 0218544^2 + 196248000^2 && := 1232\ 1781456^2 \\ &123432\ 0218544^2 + 1964248000^2 && := 123432\ 1781456^2 \\ &12345432\ 0218544^2 + 19644248000^2 && := 12345432\ 1781456^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0218544^2 + 196444248000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1781456^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0218544^2 + 1964444248000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1781456^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0218544^2 + 19644444248000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1781456^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0218544^2 + 196444444248000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1781456^2 \end{aligned}$$

885)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0216775^2 + 1770000^2 & := & 1783225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0216775^2 + 19470000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1783225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0216775^2 + 196470000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1783225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0216775^2 + 1966470000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1783225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0216775^2 + 19666470000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1783225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0216775^2 + 196666470000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1783225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0216775^2 + 1966666470000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1783225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0216775^2 + 19666666470000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1783225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0216775^2 + 196666666470000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1783225^2 \end{aligned}$$

886)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0215004^2 + 1772000^2 & := & 1784996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0215004^2 + 19492000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1784996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0215004^2 + 196692000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1784996^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0215004^2 + 1968692000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1784996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0215004^2 + 19688692000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1784996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0215004^2 + 196888692000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1784996^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0215004^2 + 1968888692000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1784996^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0215004^2 + 19688888692000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1784996^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0215004^2 + 196888888692000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1784996^2 \end{aligned}$$

887)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0213231^2 + 1774000^2 & := & 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0213231^2 + 19514000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0213231^2 + 196914000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0213231^2 + 1970914000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0213231^2 + 19710914000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0213231^2 + 197110914000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0213231^2 + 1971110914000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0213231^2 + 19711110914000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0213231^2 + 197111110914000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1786769^2 \end{aligned}$$

888)

$$\begin{aligned} &0211456^2 + 1776000^2 &:=& 1788544^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0211456^2 + 19536000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1788544^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0211456^2 + 197136000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1788544^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0211456^2 + 1973136000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1788544^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0211456^2 + 19733136000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1788544^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0211456^2 + 197333136000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1788544^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0211456^2 + 1973333136000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1788544^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0211456^2 + 19733333136000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1788544^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0211456^2 + 197333333136000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1788544^2 \end{aligned}$$

889)

$$\begin{aligned} &0209679^2 + 1778000^2 &:=& 1790321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0209679^2 + 19558000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1790321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0209679^2 + 197358000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1790321^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0209679^2 + 1975358000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1790321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0209679^2 + 19755358000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1790321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0209679^2 + 197555358000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1790321^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0209679^2 + 1975555358000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1790321^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0209679^2 + 19755555358000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1790321^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0209679^2 + 197555555358000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1790321^2 \end{aligned}$$

890)

$$\begin{aligned} &0207900^2 + 1780000^2 &:=& 1792100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0207900^2 + 19580000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12} 1792100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0207900^2 + 197580000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1232} 1792100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0207900^2 + 1977580000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123432} 1792100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0207900^2 + 19777580000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345432} 1792100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0207900^2 + 197777580000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234565432} 1792100^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0207900^2 + 1977777580000^2 &:=& \mathbf{123456765432} 1792100^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0207900^2 + 19777777580000^2 &:=& \mathbf{12345678765432} 1792100^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0207900^2 + 197777777580000^2 &:=& \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1792100^2 \end{aligned}$$

891)

$$\begin{aligned} &0206119^2 + 1782000^2 && := 1793881^2 \\ &12\ 0206119^2 + 19602000^2 && := 12\ 1793881^2 \\ &1232\ 0206119^2 + 197802000^2 && := 1232\ 1793881^2 \\ &123432\ 0206119^2 + 1979802000^2 && := 123432\ 1793881^2 \\ &12345432\ 0206119^2 + 19799802000^2 && := 12345432\ 1793881^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0206119^2 + 197999802000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1793881^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0206119^2 + 1979999802000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1793881^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0206119^2 + 19799999802000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1793881^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0206119^2 + 197999999802000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1793881^2 \end{aligned}$$

892)

$$\begin{aligned} &0204336^2 + 1784000^2 && := 1795664^2 \\ &12\ 0204336^2 + 19624000^2 && := 12\ 1795664^2 \\ &1232\ 0204336^2 + 198024000^2 && := 1232\ 1795664^2 \\ &123432\ 0204336^2 + 1982024000^2 && := 123432\ 1795664^2 \\ &12345432\ 0204336^2 + 19822024000^2 && := 12345432\ 1795664^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0204336^2 + 198222024000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1795664^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0204336^2 + 1982222024000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1795664^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0204336^2 + 19822222024000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1795664^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0204336^2 + 198222222024000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1795664^2 \end{aligned}$$

893)

$$\begin{aligned} &0202551^2 + 1786000^2 && := 1797449^2 \\ &12\ 0202551^2 + 19646000^2 && := 12\ 1797449^2 \\ &1232\ 0202551^2 + 198246000^2 && := 1232\ 1797449^2 \\ &123432\ 0202551^2 + 1984246000^2 && := 123432\ 1797449^2 \\ &12345432\ 0202551^2 + 19844246000^2 && := 12345432\ 1797449^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0202551^2 + 198444246000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1797449^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0202551^2 + 1984444246000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1797449^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0202551^2 + 19844444246000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1797449^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0202551^2 + 198444444246000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1797449^2 \end{aligned}$$

894)

$$\begin{aligned} &0200764^2 + 1788000^2 && := 1799236^2 \\ &12\ 0200764^2 + 19668000^2 && := 12\ 1799236^2 \\ &1232\ 0200764^2 + 198468000^2 && := 1232\ 1799236^2 \\ &123432\ 0200764^2 + 1986468000^2 && := 123432\ 1799236^2 \\ &12345432\ 0200764^2 + 19866468000^2 && := 12345432\ 1799236^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0200764^2 + 198666468000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1799236^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0200764^2 + 1986666468000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1799236^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0200764^2 + 19866666468000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1799236^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0200764^2 + 198666666468000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1799236^2 \end{aligned}$$

895)

$$\begin{aligned} &0198975^2 + 1790000^2 && := 1801025^2 \\ &12\ 0198975^2 + 19690000^2 && := 12\ 1801025^2 \\ &1232\ 0198975^2 + 198690000^2 && := 1232\ 1801025^2 \\ &123432\ 0198975^2 + 1988690000^2 && := 123432\ 1801025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0198975^2 + 19888690000^2 && := 12345432\ 1801025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0198975^2 + 198888690000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1801025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0198975^2 + 1988888690000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1801025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0198975^2 + 19888888690000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1801025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0198975^2 + 198888888690000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1801025^2 \end{aligned}$$

896)

$$\begin{aligned} &0197184^2 + 1792000^2 && := 1802816^2 \\ &12\ 0197184^2 + 19712000^2 && := 12\ 1802816^2 \\ &1232\ 0197184^2 + 198912000^2 && := 1232\ 1802816^2 \\ &123432\ 0197184^2 + 1990912000^2 && := 123432\ 1802816^2 \\ &12345432\ 0197184^2 + 19910912000^2 && := 12345432\ 1802816^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0197184^2 + 199110912000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1802816^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0197184^2 + 1991110912000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1802816^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0197184^2 + 19911110912000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1802816^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0197184^2 + 199111110912000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1802816^2 \end{aligned}$$

897)

$$\begin{aligned} &0195391^2 + 1794000^2 && := 1804609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0195391^2 + 19734000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1804609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0195391^2 + 199134000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1804609^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0195391^2 + 1993134000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1804609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0195391^2 + 19933134000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1804609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0195391^2 + 199333134000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1804609^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0195391^2 + 1993333134000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1804609^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0195391^2 + 19933333134000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1804609^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0195391^2 + 199333333134000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1804609^2 \end{aligned}$$

898)

$$\begin{aligned} &0193596^2 + 1796000^2 && := 1806404^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0193596^2 + 19756000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1806404^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0193596^2 + 199356000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1806404^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0193596^2 + 1995356000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1806404^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0193596^2 + 19955356000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1806404^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0193596^2 + 199555356000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1806404^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0193596^2 + 1995555356000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1806404^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0193596^2 + 19955555356000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1806404^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0193596^2 + 199555555356000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1806404^2 \end{aligned}$$

899)

$$\begin{aligned} &0191799^2 + 1798000^2 && := 1808201^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0191799^2 + 19778000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1808201^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0191799^2 + 199578000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1808201^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0191799^2 + 1997578000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1808201^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0191799^2 + 19977578000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1808201^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0191799^2 + 199777578000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1808201^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0191799^2 + 1997777578000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1808201^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0191799^2 + 19977777578000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1808201^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0191799^2 + 199777777578000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1808201^2 \end{aligned}$$

900)

$$\begin{aligned} &0190000^2 + 1800000^2 && := 1810000^2 \\ &12\ 0190000^2 + 19800000^2 && := 12\ 1810000^2 \\ &1232\ 0190000^2 + 199800000^2 && := 1232\ 1810000^2 \\ &123432\ 0190000^2 + 1999800000^2 && := 123432\ 1810000^2 \\ &12345432\ 0190000^2 + 19999800000^2 && := 12345432\ 1810000^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0190000^2 + 199999800000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1810000^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0190000^2 + 1999999800000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1810000^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0190000^2 + 19999999800000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1810000^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0190000^2 + 199999999800000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1810000^2 \end{aligned}$$

901)

$$\begin{aligned} &0188199^2 + 1802000^2 && := 1811801^2 \\ &12\ 0188199^2 + 19822000^2 && := 12\ 1811801^2 \\ &1232\ 0188199^2 + 200022000^2 && := 1232\ 1811801^2 \\ &123432\ 0188199^2 + 2002022000^2 && := 123432\ 1811801^2 \\ &12345432\ 0188199^2 + 20022022000^2 && := 12345432\ 1811801^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0188199^2 + 200222022000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1811801^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0188199^2 + 2002222022000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1811801^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0188199^2 + 20022222022000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1811801^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0188199^2 + 200222222022000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1811801^2 \end{aligned}$$

902)

$$\begin{aligned} &0186396^2 + 1804000^2 && := 1813604^2 \\ &12\ 0186396^2 + 19844000^2 && := 12\ 1813604^2 \\ &1232\ 0186396^2 + 200244000^2 && := 1232\ 1813604^2 \\ &123432\ 0186396^2 + 2004244000^2 && := 123432\ 1813604^2 \\ &12345432\ 0186396^2 + 20044244000^2 && := 12345432\ 1813604^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0186396^2 + 200444244000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1813604^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0186396^2 + 2004444244000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1813604^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0186396^2 + 20044444244000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1813604^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0186396^2 + 200444444244000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1813604^2 \end{aligned}$$

903)

$$\begin{aligned} &0184591^2 + 1806000^2 && := 1815409^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0184591^2 + 19866000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1815409^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0184591^2 + 200466000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1815409^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0184591^2 + 2006466000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1815409^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0184591^2 + 20066466000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1815409^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0184591^2 + 200666466000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1815409^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0184591^2 + 2006666466000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1815409^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0184591^2 + 20066666466000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1815409^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0184591^2 + 200666666466000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1815409^2 \end{aligned}$$

904)

$$\begin{aligned} &0182784^2 + 1808000^2 && := 1817216^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0182784^2 + 19888000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1817216^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0182784^2 + 200688000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1817216^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0182784^2 + 2008688000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1817216^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0182784^2 + 20088688000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1817216^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0182784^2 + 200888688000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1817216^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0182784^2 + 2008888688000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1817216^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0182784^2 + 20088888688000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1817216^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0182784^2 + 200888888688000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1817216^2 \end{aligned}$$

905)

$$\begin{aligned} &0180975^2 + 1810000^2 && := 1819025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0180975^2 + 19910000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1819025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0180975^2 + 200910000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1819025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0180975^2 + 2010910000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1819025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0180975^2 + 20110910000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1819025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0180975^2 + 201110910000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1819025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0180975^2 + 2011110910000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1819025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0180975^2 + 20111110910000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1819025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0180975^2 + 201111110910000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1819025^2 \end{aligned}$$

906)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0179164^2 + 1812000^2 & := & 1820836^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0179164^2 + 19932000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1820836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0179164^2 + 201132000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1820836^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0179164^2 + 2013132000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1820836^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0179164^2 + 20133132000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1820836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0179164^2 + 201333132000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1820836^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0179164^2 + 2013333132000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1820836^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0179164^2 + 20133333132000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1820836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0179164^2 + 201333333132000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1820836^2 \end{aligned}$$

907)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0177351^2 + 1814000^2 & := & 1822649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0177351^2 + 19954000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1822649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0177351^2 + 201354000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1822649^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0177351^2 + 2015354000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1822649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0177351^2 + 20155354000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1822649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0177351^2 + 201555354000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1822649^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0177351^2 + 2015555354000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1822649^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0177351^2 + 20155555354000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1822649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0177351^2 + 201555555354000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1822649^2 \end{aligned}$$

908)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0175536^2 + 1816000^2 & := & 1824464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0175536^2 + 19976000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1824464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0175536^2 + 201576000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1824464^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0175536^2 + 2017576000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1824464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0175536^2 + 20177576000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1824464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0175536^2 + 201777576000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1824464^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0175536^2 + 2017777576000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1824464^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0175536^2 + 20177777576000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1824464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0175536^2 + 201777777576000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1824464^2 \end{aligned}$$

909)

$$\begin{aligned} &0173719^2 + 1818000^2 && := 1826281^2 \\ &12\ 0173719^2 + 19998000^2 && := 12\ 1826281^2 \\ &1232\ 0173719^2 + 201798000^2 && := 1232\ 1826281^2 \\ &123432\ 0173719^2 + 2019798000^2 && := 123432\ 1826281^2 \\ &12345432\ 0173719^2 + 20199798000^2 && := 12345432\ 1826281^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0173719^2 + 201999798000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1826281^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0173719^2 + 2019999798000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1826281^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0173719^2 + 20199999798000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1826281^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0173719^2 + 201999999798000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1826281^2 \end{aligned}$$

910)

$$\begin{aligned} &0171900^2 + 1820000^2 && := 1828100^2 \\ &12\ 0171900^2 + 20020000^2 && := 12\ 1828100^2 \\ &1232\ 0171900^2 + 202020000^2 && := 1232\ 1828100^2 \\ &123432\ 0171900^2 + 2022020000^2 && := 123432\ 1828100^2 \\ &12345432\ 0171900^2 + 20222020000^2 && := 12345432\ 1828100^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0171900^2 + 202222020000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1828100^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0171900^2 + 2022222020000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1828100^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0171900^2 + 20222222020000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1828100^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0171900^2 + 202222222020000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1828100^2 \end{aligned}$$

911)

$$\begin{aligned} &0170079^2 + 1822000^2 && := 1829921^2 \\ &12\ 0170079^2 + 20042000^2 && := 12\ 1829921^2 \\ &1232\ 0170079^2 + 202242000^2 && := 1232\ 1829921^2 \\ &123432\ 0170079^2 + 2024242000^2 && := 123432\ 1829921^2 \\ &12345432\ 0170079^2 + 20244242000^2 && := 12345432\ 1829921^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0170079^2 + 202444242000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1829921^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0170079^2 + 2024444242000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1829921^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0170079^2 + 20244444242000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1829921^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0170079^2 + 202444444242000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1829921^2 \end{aligned}$$

912)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0168256^2 + 1824000^2 & := & 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0168256^2 + 20064000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0168256^2 + 202464000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0168256^2 + 2026464000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0168256^2 + 20266464000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0168256^2 + 202666464000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0168256^2 + 2026666464000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0168256^2 + 20266666464000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0168256^2 + 202666666464000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1831744^2 \end{aligned}$$

913)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0166431^2 + 1826000^2 & := & 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0166431^2 + 20086000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0166431^2 + 202686000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0166431^2 + 2028686000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0166431^2 + 20288686000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0166431^2 + 202888686000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0166431^2 + 2028888686000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0166431^2 + 20288888686000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0166431^2 + 202888888686000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1833569^2 \end{aligned}$$

914)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0164604^2 + 1828000^2 & := & 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0164604^2 + 20108000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0164604^2 + 202908000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0164604^2 + 2030908000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0164604^2 + 20310908000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0164604^2 + 203110908000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0164604^2 + 2031110908000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0164604^2 + 20311110908000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0164604^2 + 203111110908000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1835396^2 \end{aligned}$$

915)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0162775^2 + 1830000^2 & := & 1837225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0162775^2 + 20130000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1837225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0162775^2 + 203130000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1837225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0162775^2 + 2033130000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1837225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0162775^2 + 20333130000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1837225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0162775^2 + 203333130000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1837225^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0162775^2 + 2033333130000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1837225^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0162775^2 + 20333333130000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1837225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0162775^2 + 203333333130000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1837225^2 \end{aligned}$$

916)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0160944^2 + 1832000^2 & := & 1839056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0160944^2 + 20152000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1839056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0160944^2 + 203352000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1839056^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0160944^2 + 2035352000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1839056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0160944^2 + 20355352000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1839056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0160944^2 + 203555352000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1839056^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0160944^2 + 2035555352000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1839056^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0160944^2 + 20355555352000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1839056^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0160944^2 + 203555555352000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1839056^2 \end{aligned}$$

917)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0159111^2 + 1834000^2 & := & 1840889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0159111^2 + 20174000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1840889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0159111^2 + 203574000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1840889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0159111^2 + 2037574000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1840889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0159111^2 + 20377574000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1840889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0159111^2 + 203777574000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1840889^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0159111^2 + 2037777574000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1840889^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0159111^2 + 20377777574000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1840889^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0159111^2 + 203777777574000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1840889^2 \end{aligned}$$

918)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0157276^2 + 1836000^2 & := & 1842724^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0157276^2 + 20196000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1842724^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0157276^2 + 203796000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1842724^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0157276^2 + 2039796000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1842724^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0157276^2 + 20399796000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1842724^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0157276^2 + 203999796000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1842724^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0157276^2 + 2039999796000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1842724^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0157276^2 + 20399999796000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1842724^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0157276^2 + 203999999796000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1842724^2 \end{aligned}$$

919)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0155439^2 + 1838000^2 & := & 1844561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0155439^2 + 20218000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1844561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0155439^2 + 204018000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1844561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0155439^2 + 2042018000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1844561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0155439^2 + 20422018000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1844561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0155439^2 + 204222018000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1844561^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0155439^2 + 2042222018000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1844561^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0155439^2 + 20422222018000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1844561^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0155439^2 + 204222222018000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1844561^2 \end{aligned}$$

920)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0153600^2 + 1840000^2 & := & 1846400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0153600^2 + 20240000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1846400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0153600^2 + 204240000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1846400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0153600^2 + 2044240000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1846400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0153600^2 + 20444240000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1846400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0153600^2 + 204444240000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1846400^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0153600^2 + 2044444240000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1846400^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0153600^2 + 20444444240000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1846400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0153600^2 + 204444444240000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1846400^2 \end{aligned}$$

921)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0151759^2 + 1842000^2 & := & 1848241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0151759^2 + 20262000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1848241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0151759^2 + 204462000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1848241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0151759^2 + 2046462000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1848241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0151759^2 + 20466462000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1848241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0151759^2 + 204666462000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1848241^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0151759^2 + 2046666462000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1848241^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0151759^2 + 20466666462000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1848241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0151759^2 + 204666666462000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1848241^2 \end{aligned}$$

922)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0149916^2 + 1844000^2 & := & 1850084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0149916^2 + 20284000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1850084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0149916^2 + 204684000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1850084^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0149916^2 + 2048684000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1850084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0149916^2 + 20488684000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1850084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0149916^2 + 204888684000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1850084^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0149916^2 + 2048888684000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1850084^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0149916^2 + 20488888684000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1850084^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0149916^2 + 204888888684000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1850084^2 \end{aligned}$$

923)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0148071^2 + 1846000^2 & := & 1851929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0148071^2 + 20306000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1851929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0148071^2 + 204906000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1851929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0148071^2 + 2050906000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1851929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0148071^2 + 20510906000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1851929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0148071^2 + 205110906000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1851929^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0148071^2 + 2051110906000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1851929^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0148071^2 + 20511110906000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1851929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0148071^2 + 205111110906000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1851929^2 \end{aligned}$$

924)

$$\begin{aligned} &0146224^2 + 1848000^2 && := 1853776^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0146224^2 + 20328000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1853776^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0146224^2 + 205128000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1853776^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0146224^2 + 2053128000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1853776^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0146224^2 + 20533128000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1853776^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0146224^2 + 205333128000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1853776^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0146224^2 + 2053333128000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1853776^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0146224^2 + 20533333128000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1853776^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0146224^2 + 205333333128000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1853776^2 \end{aligned}$$

925)

$$\begin{aligned} &0144375^2 + 1850000^2 && := 1855625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0144375^2 + 20350000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1855625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0144375^2 + 205350000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1855625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0144375^2 + 2055350000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1855625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0144375^2 + 20555350000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1855625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0144375^2 + 205555350000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1855625^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0144375^2 + 2055555350000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1855625^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0144375^2 + 20555555350000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1855625^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0144375^2 + 205555555350000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1855625^2 \end{aligned}$$

926)

$$\begin{aligned} &0142524^2 + 1852000^2 && := 1857476^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0142524^2 + 20372000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1857476^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0142524^2 + 205572000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1857476^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0142524^2 + 2057572000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1857476^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0142524^2 + 20577572000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1857476^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0142524^2 + 205777572000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1857476^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0142524^2 + 2057777572000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1857476^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0142524^2 + 20577777572000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1857476^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0142524^2 + 205777777572000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1857476^2 \end{aligned}$$

927)

$$\begin{aligned} &0140671^2 + 1854000^2 && := 1859329^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0140671^2 + 20394000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1859329^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0140671^2 + 205794000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1859329^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0140671^2 + 2059794000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1859329^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0140671^2 + 20599794000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1859329^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0140671^2 + 205999794000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1859329^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0140671^2 + 2059999794000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1859329^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0140671^2 + 20599999794000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1859329^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0140671^2 + 205999999794000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1859329^2 \end{aligned}$$

928)

$$\begin{aligned} &0138816^2 + 1856000^2 && := 1861184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0138816^2 + 20416000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1861184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0138816^2 + 206016000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1861184^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0138816^2 + 2062016000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1861184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0138816^2 + 20622016000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1861184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0138816^2 + 206222016000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1861184^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0138816^2 + 2062222016000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1861184^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0138816^2 + 20622222016000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1861184^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0138816^2 + 206222222016000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1861184^2 \end{aligned}$$

929)

$$\begin{aligned} &0136959^2 + 1858000^2 && := 1863041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0136959^2 + 20438000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1863041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0136959^2 + 206238000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1863041^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0136959^2 + 2064238000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1863041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0136959^2 + 20644238000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1863041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0136959^2 + 206444238000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1863041^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0136959^2 + 2064444238000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1863041^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0136959^2 + 20644444238000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1863041^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0136959^2 + 206444444238000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1863041^2 \end{aligned}$$

930)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0135100^2 + 1860000^2 & := & 1864900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0135100^2 + 20460000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1864900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0135100^2 + 206460000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1864900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0135100^2 + 2066460000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1864900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0135100^2 + 20666460000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1864900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0135100^2 + 206666460000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1864900^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0135100^2 + 2066666460000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1864900^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0135100^2 + 20666666460000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1864900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0135100^2 + 206666666460000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1864900^2 \end{aligned}$$

931)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0133239^2 + 1862000^2 & := & 1866761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0133239^2 + 20482000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1866761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0133239^2 + 206682000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1866761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0133239^2 + 2068682000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1866761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0133239^2 + 20688682000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1866761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0133239^2 + 206888682000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1866761^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0133239^2 + 2068888682000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1866761^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0133239^2 + 20688888682000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1866761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0133239^2 + 206888888682000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1866761^2 \end{aligned}$$

932)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0131376^2 + 1864000^2 & := & 1868624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0131376^2 + 20504000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1868624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0131376^2 + 206904000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1868624^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0131376^2 + 2070904000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1868624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0131376^2 + 20710904000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1868624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0131376^2 + 207110904000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1868624^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0131376^2 + 2071110904000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1868624^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0131376^2 + 20711110904000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1868624^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0131376^2 + 207111110904000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1868624^2 \end{aligned}$$

933)

$$\begin{aligned} &0129511^2 + 1866000^2 && := 1870489^2 \\ &12\ 0129511^2 + 20526000^2 && := 12\ 1870489^2 \\ &1232\ 0129511^2 + 207126000^2 && := 1232\ 1870489^2 \\ &123432\ 0129511^2 + 2073126000^2 && := 123432\ 1870489^2 \\ &12345432\ 0129511^2 + 20733126000^2 && := 12345432\ 1870489^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0129511^2 + 207333126000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1870489^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0129511^2 + 2073333126000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1870489^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0129511^2 + 20733333126000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1870489^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0129511^2 + 207333333126000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1870489^2 \end{aligned}$$

934)

$$\begin{aligned} &0127644^2 + 1868000^2 && := 1872356^2 \\ &12\ 0127644^2 + 20548000^2 && := 12\ 1872356^2 \\ &1232\ 0127644^2 + 207348000^2 && := 1232\ 1872356^2 \\ &123432\ 0127644^2 + 2075348000^2 && := 123432\ 1872356^2 \\ &12345432\ 0127644^2 + 20755348000^2 && := 12345432\ 1872356^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0127644^2 + 207555348000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1872356^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0127644^2 + 2075555348000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1872356^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0127644^2 + 20755555348000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1872356^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0127644^2 + 207555555348000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1872356^2 \end{aligned}$$

935)

$$\begin{aligned} &0125775^2 + 1870000^2 && := 1874225^2 \\ &12\ 0125775^2 + 20570000^2 && := 12\ 1874225^2 \\ &1232\ 0125775^2 + 207570000^2 && := 1232\ 1874225^2 \\ &123432\ 0125775^2 + 2077570000^2 && := 123432\ 1874225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0125775^2 + 20777570000^2 && := 12345432\ 1874225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0125775^2 + 207777570000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1874225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0125775^2 + 2077777570000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1874225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0125775^2 + 20777777570000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1874225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0125775^2 + 207777777570000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1874225^2 \end{aligned}$$

936)

$$\begin{aligned} &0123904^2 + 1872000^2 && := 1876096^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0123904^2 + 20592000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1876096^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0123904^2 + 207792000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1876096^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0123904^2 + 2079792000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1876096^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0123904^2 + 20799792000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1876096^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0123904^2 + 207999792000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1876096^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0123904^2 + 2079999792000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1876096^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0123904^2 + 20799999792000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1876096^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0123904^2 + 207999999792000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1876096^2 \end{aligned}$$

937)

$$\begin{aligned} &0122031^2 + 1874000^2 && := 1877969^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0122031^2 + 20614000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1877969^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0122031^2 + 208014000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1877969^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0122031^2 + 2082014000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1877969^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0122031^2 + 20822014000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1877969^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0122031^2 + 208222014000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1877969^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0122031^2 + 2082222014000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1877969^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0122031^2 + 20822222014000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1877969^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0122031^2 + 208222222014000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1877969^2 \end{aligned}$$

938)

$$\begin{aligned} &0120156^2 + 1876000^2 && := 1879844^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0120156^2 + 20636000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1879844^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0120156^2 + 208236000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1879844^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0120156^2 + 2084236000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1879844^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0120156^2 + 20844236000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1879844^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0120156^2 + 208444236000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1879844^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0120156^2 + 2084444236000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1879844^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0120156^2 + 20844444236000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1879844^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0120156^2 + 208444444236000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1879844^2 \end{aligned}$$

939)

$$\begin{aligned} &0118279^2 + 1878000^2 && := 1881721^2 \\ &12\ 0118279^2 + 20658000^2 && := 12\ 1881721^2 \\ &1232\ 0118279^2 + 208458000^2 && := 1232\ 1881721^2 \\ &123432\ 0118279^2 + 2086458000^2 && := 123432\ 1881721^2 \\ &12345432\ 0118279^2 + 20866458000^2 && := 12345432\ 1881721^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0118279^2 + 208666458000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1881721^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0118279^2 + 2086666458000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1881721^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0118279^2 + 20866666458000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1881721^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0118279^2 + 208666666458000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1881721^2 \end{aligned}$$

940)

$$\begin{aligned} &0116400^2 + 1880000^2 && := 1883600^2 \\ &12\ 0116400^2 + 20680000^2 && := 12\ 1883600^2 \\ &1232\ 0116400^2 + 208680000^2 && := 1232\ 1883600^2 \\ &123432\ 0116400^2 + 2088680000^2 && := 123432\ 1883600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0116400^2 + 20888680000^2 && := 12345432\ 1883600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0116400^2 + 208888680000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1883600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0116400^2 + 2088888680000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1883600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0116400^2 + 20888888680000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1883600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0116400^2 + 208888888680000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1883600^2 \end{aligned}$$

941)

$$\begin{aligned} &0114519^2 + 1882000^2 && := 1885481^2 \\ &12\ 0114519^2 + 20702000^2 && := 12\ 1885481^2 \\ &1232\ 0114519^2 + 208902000^2 && := 1232\ 1885481^2 \\ &123432\ 0114519^2 + 2090902000^2 && := 123432\ 1885481^2 \\ &12345432\ 0114519^2 + 20910902000^2 && := 12345432\ 1885481^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0114519^2 + 209110902000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1885481^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0114519^2 + 2091110902000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1885481^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0114519^2 + 20911110902000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1885481^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0114519^2 + 209111110902000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1885481^2 \end{aligned}$$

942)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0112636^2 + 1884000^2 & := & 1887364^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0112636^2 + 20724000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1887364^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0112636^2 + 209124000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1887364^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0112636^2 + 2093124000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1887364^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0112636^2 + 20933124000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1887364^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0112636^2 + 209333124000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1887364^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0112636^2 + 2093333124000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1887364^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0112636^2 + 20933333124000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1887364^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0112636^2 + 209333333124000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1887364^2 \end{aligned}$$

943)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0110751^2 + 1886000^2 & := & 1889249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0110751^2 + 20746000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1889249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0110751^2 + 209346000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1889249^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0110751^2 + 2095346000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1889249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0110751^2 + 20955346000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1889249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0110751^2 + 209555346000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1889249^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0110751^2 + 2095555346000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1889249^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0110751^2 + 20955555346000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1889249^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0110751^2 + 209555555346000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1889249^2 \end{aligned}$$

944)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0108864^2 + 1888000^2 & := & 1891136^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0108864^2 + 20768000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1891136^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0108864^2 + 209568000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1891136^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0108864^2 + 2097568000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1891136^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0108864^2 + 20977568000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1891136^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0108864^2 + 209777568000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1891136^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0108864^2 + 2097777568000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1891136^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0108864^2 + 20977777568000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1891136^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0108864^2 + 209777777568000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1891136^2 \end{aligned}$$

945)

$$\begin{aligned} &0106975^2 + 1890000^2 && := 1893025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0106975^2 + 20790000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1893025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0106975^2 + 209790000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1893025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0106975^2 + 2099790000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1893025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0106975^2 + 20999790000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1893025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0106975^2 + 209999790000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1893025^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0106975^2 + 2099999790000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1893025^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0106975^2 + 20999999790000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1893025^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0106975^2 + 209999999790000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1893025^2 \end{aligned}$$

946)

$$\begin{aligned} &0105084^2 + 1892000^2 && := 1894916^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0105084^2 + 20812000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1894916^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0105084^2 + 210012000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1894916^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0105084^2 + 2102012000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1894916^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0105084^2 + 21022012000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1894916^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0105084^2 + 210222012000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1894916^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0105084^2 + 2102222012000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1894916^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0105084^2 + 21022222012000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1894916^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0105084^2 + 210222222012000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1894916^2 \end{aligned}$$

947)

$$\begin{aligned} &0103191^2 + 1894000^2 && := 1896809^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0103191^2 + 20834000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1896809^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0103191^2 + 210234000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1896809^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0103191^2 + 2104234000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1896809^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0103191^2 + 21044234000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1896809^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0103191^2 + 210444234000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1896809^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0103191^2 + 2104444234000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1896809^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0103191^2 + 21044444234000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1896809^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0103191^2 + 210444444234000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1896809^2 \end{aligned}$$

948)

$$\begin{aligned} &0101296^2 + 1896000^2 && := 1898704^2 \\ &12\ 0101296^2 + 20856000^2 && := 12\ 1898704^2 \\ &1232\ 0101296^2 + 210456000^2 && := 1232\ 1898704^2 \\ &123432\ 0101296^2 + 2106456000^2 && := 123432\ 1898704^2 \\ &12345432\ 0101296^2 + 21066456000^2 && := 12345432\ 1898704^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0101296^2 + 210666456000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1898704^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0101296^2 + 2106666456000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1898704^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0101296^2 + 21066666456000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1898704^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0101296^2 + 210666666456000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1898704^2 \end{aligned}$$

949)

$$\begin{aligned} &0099399^2 + 1898000^2 && := 1900601^2 \\ &12\ 0099399^2 + 20878000^2 && := 12\ 1900601^2 \\ &1232\ 0099399^2 + 210678000^2 && := 1232\ 1900601^2 \\ &123432\ 0099399^2 + 2108678000^2 && := 123432\ 1900601^2 \\ &12345432\ 0099399^2 + 21088678000^2 && := 12345432\ 1900601^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0099399^2 + 210888678000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1900601^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0099399^2 + 2108888678000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1900601^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0099399^2 + 21088888678000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1900601^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0099399^2 + 210888888678000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1900601^2 \end{aligned}$$

950)

$$\begin{aligned} &0097500^2 + 1900000^2 && := 1902500^2 \\ &12\ 0097500^2 + 20900000^2 && := 12\ 1902500^2 \\ &1232\ 0097500^2 + 210900000^2 && := 1232\ 1902500^2 \\ &123432\ 0097500^2 + 2110900000^2 && := 123432\ 1902500^2 \\ &12345432\ 0097500^2 + 21110900000^2 && := 12345432\ 1902500^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0097500^2 + 211110900000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1902500^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0097500^2 + 2111110900000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1902500^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0097500^2 + 21111110900000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1902500^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0097500^2 + 211111110900000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1902500^2 \end{aligned}$$

951)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0095599^2 + 1902000^2 & := & 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0095599^2 + 20922000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0095599^2 + 211122000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0095599^2 + 2113122000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0095599^2 + 21133122000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0095599^2 + 211333122000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0095599^2 + 2113333122000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0095599^2 + 21133333122000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0095599^2 + 211333333122000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1904401^2 \end{aligned}$$

952)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0093696^2 + 1904000^2 & := & 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0093696^2 + 20944000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0093696^2 + 211344000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0093696^2 + 2115344000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0093696^2 + 21155344000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0093696^2 + 211555344000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0093696^2 + 2115555344000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0093696^2 + 21155555344000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0093696^2 + 211555555344000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1906304^2 \end{aligned}$$

953)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0091791^2 + 1906000^2 & := & 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0091791^2 + 20966000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0091791^2 + 211566000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0091791^2 + 2117566000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0091791^2 + 21177566000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0091791^2 + 211777566000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0091791^2 + 2117777566000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0091791^2 + 21177777566000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0091791^2 + 211777777566000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1908209^2 \end{aligned}$$

954)

$$\begin{aligned} &0089884^2 + 1908000^2 && := 1910116^2 \\ &12\ 0089884^2 + 20988000^2 && := 12\ 1910116^2 \\ &1232\ 0089884^2 + 211788000^2 && := 1232\ 1910116^2 \\ &123432\ 0089884^2 + 2119788000^2 && := 123432\ 1910116^2 \\ &12345432\ 0089884^2 + 21199788000^2 && := 12345432\ 1910116^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0089884^2 + 211999788000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1910116^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0089884^2 + 2119999788000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1910116^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0089884^2 + 21199999788000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1910116^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0089884^2 + 211999999788000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1910116^2 \end{aligned}$$

955)

$$\begin{aligned} &0087975^2 + 1910000^2 && := 1912025^2 \\ &12\ 0087975^2 + 21010000^2 && := 12\ 1912025^2 \\ &1232\ 0087975^2 + 212010000^2 && := 1232\ 1912025^2 \\ &123432\ 0087975^2 + 2122010000^2 && := 123432\ 1912025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0087975^2 + 21222010000^2 && := 12345432\ 1912025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0087975^2 + 212222010000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1912025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0087975^2 + 2122222010000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1912025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0087975^2 + 21222222010000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1912025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0087975^2 + 212222222010000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1912025^2 \end{aligned}$$

956)

$$\begin{aligned} &0086064^2 + 1912000^2 && := 1913936^2 \\ &12\ 0086064^2 + 21032000^2 && := 12\ 1913936^2 \\ &1232\ 0086064^2 + 212232000^2 && := 1232\ 1913936^2 \\ &123432\ 0086064^2 + 2124232000^2 && := 123432\ 1913936^2 \\ &12345432\ 0086064^2 + 21244232000^2 && := 12345432\ 1913936^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0086064^2 + 212444232000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1913936^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0086064^2 + 2124444232000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1913936^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0086064^2 + 21244444232000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1913936^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0086064^2 + 212444444232000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1913936^2 \end{aligned}$$

957)

$$\begin{aligned} &0084151^2 + 1914000^2 && := 1915849^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0084151^2 + 21054000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1915849^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0084151^2 + 212454000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1915849^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0084151^2 + 2126454000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1915849^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0084151^2 + 21266454000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1915849^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0084151^2 + 212666454000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1915849^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0084151^2 + 2126666454000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1915849^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0084151^2 + 21266666454000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1915849^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0084151^2 + 212666666454000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1915849^2 \end{aligned}$$

958)

$$\begin{aligned} &0082236^2 + 1916000^2 && := 1917764^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0082236^2 + 21076000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1917764^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0082236^2 + 212676000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1917764^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0082236^2 + 2128676000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1917764^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0082236^2 + 21288676000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1917764^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0082236^2 + 212888676000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1917764^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0082236^2 + 2128888676000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1917764^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0082236^2 + 21288888676000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1917764^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0082236^2 + 212888888676000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1917764^2 \end{aligned}$$

959)

$$\begin{aligned} &0080319^2 + 1918000^2 && := 1919681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12} 0080319^2 + 21098000^2 && := \mathbf{12} 1919681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1232} 0080319^2 + 212898000^2 && := \mathbf{1232} 1919681^2 \\ &\mathbf{123432} 0080319^2 + 2130898000^2 && := \mathbf{123432} 1919681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345432} 0080319^2 + 21310898000^2 && := \mathbf{12345432} 1919681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234565432} 0080319^2 + 213110898000^2 && := \mathbf{1234565432} 1919681^2 \\ &\mathbf{123456765432} 0080319^2 + 2131110898000^2 && := \mathbf{123456765432} 1919681^2 \\ &\mathbf{12345678765432} 0080319^2 + 21311110898000^2 && := \mathbf{12345678765432} 1919681^2 \\ &\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0080319^2 + 213111110898000^2 && := \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1919681^2 \end{aligned}$$

960)

$$\begin{aligned} &0078400^2 + 1920000^2 && := 1921600^2 \\ &12\ 0078400^2 + 21120000^2 && := 12\ 1921600^2 \\ &1232\ 0078400^2 + 213120000^2 && := 1232\ 1921600^2 \\ &123432\ 0078400^2 + 2133120000^2 && := 123432\ 1921600^2 \\ &12345432\ 0078400^2 + 21333120000^2 && := 12345432\ 1921600^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0078400^2 + 213333120000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1921600^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0078400^2 + 2133333120000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1921600^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0078400^2 + 21333333120000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1921600^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0078400^2 + 213333333120000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1921600^2 \end{aligned}$$

961)

$$\begin{aligned} &0076479^2 + 1922000^2 && := 1923521^2 \\ &12\ 0076479^2 + 21142000^2 && := 12\ 1923521^2 \\ &1232\ 0076479^2 + 213342000^2 && := 1232\ 1923521^2 \\ &123432\ 0076479^2 + 2135342000^2 && := 123432\ 1923521^2 \\ &12345432\ 0076479^2 + 21355342000^2 && := 12345432\ 1923521^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0076479^2 + 213555342000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1923521^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0076479^2 + 2135555342000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1923521^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0076479^2 + 21355555342000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1923521^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0076479^2 + 213555555342000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1923521^2 \end{aligned}$$

962)

$$\begin{aligned} &0074556^2 + 1924000^2 && := 1925444^2 \\ &12\ 0074556^2 + 21164000^2 && := 12\ 1925444^2 \\ &1232\ 0074556^2 + 213564000^2 && := 1232\ 1925444^2 \\ &123432\ 0074556^2 + 2137564000^2 && := 123432\ 1925444^2 \\ &12345432\ 0074556^2 + 21377564000^2 && := 12345432\ 1925444^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0074556^2 + 213777564000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1925444^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0074556^2 + 2137777564000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1925444^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0074556^2 + 21377777564000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1925444^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0074556^2 + 213777777564000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1925444^2 \end{aligned}$$

963)

$$\begin{aligned} &0072631^2 + 1926000^2 && := 1927369^2 \\ &12\ 0072631^2 + 21186000^2 && := 12\ 1927369^2 \\ &1232\ 0072631^2 + 213786000^2 && := 1232\ 1927369^2 \\ &123432\ 0072631^2 + 2139786000^2 && := 123432\ 1927369^2 \\ &12345432\ 0072631^2 + 21399786000^2 && := 12345432\ 1927369^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0072631^2 + 213999786000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1927369^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0072631^2 + 2139999786000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1927369^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0072631^2 + 21399999786000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1927369^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0072631^2 + 213999999786000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1927369^2 \end{aligned}$$

964)

$$\begin{aligned} &0070704^2 + 1928000^2 && := 1929296^2 \\ &12\ 0070704^2 + 21208000^2 && := 12\ 1929296^2 \\ &1232\ 0070704^2 + 214008000^2 && := 1232\ 1929296^2 \\ &123432\ 0070704^2 + 2142008000^2 && := 123432\ 1929296^2 \\ &12345432\ 0070704^2 + 21422008000^2 && := 12345432\ 1929296^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0070704^2 + 214222008000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1929296^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0070704^2 + 2142222008000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1929296^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0070704^2 + 21422222008000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1929296^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0070704^2 + 214222222008000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1929296^2 \end{aligned}$$

965)

$$\begin{aligned} &0068775^2 + 1930000^2 && := 1931225^2 \\ &12\ 0068775^2 + 21230000^2 && := 12\ 1931225^2 \\ &1232\ 0068775^2 + 214230000^2 && := 1232\ 1931225^2 \\ &123432\ 0068775^2 + 2144230000^2 && := 123432\ 1931225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0068775^2 + 21444230000^2 && := 12345432\ 1931225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0068775^2 + 214444230000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1931225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0068775^2 + 2144444230000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1931225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0068775^2 + 21444444230000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1931225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0068775^2 + 214444444230000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1931225^2 \end{aligned}$$

966)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0066844^2 + 1932000^2 & := & 1933156^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0066844^2 + 21252000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1933156^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0066844^2 + 214452000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1933156^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0066844^2 + 2146452000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1933156^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0066844^2 + 21466452000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1933156^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0066844^2 + 214666452000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1933156^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0066844^2 + 2146666452000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1933156^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0066844^2 + 21466666452000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1933156^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0066844^2 + 214666666452000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1933156^2 \end{aligned}$$

967)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0064911^2 + 1934000^2 & := & 1935089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0064911^2 + 21274000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1935089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0064911^2 + 214674000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1935089^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0064911^2 + 2148674000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1935089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0064911^2 + 21488674000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1935089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0064911^2 + 214888674000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1935089^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0064911^2 + 2148888674000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1935089^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0064911^2 + 21488888674000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1935089^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0064911^2 + 214888888674000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1935089^2 \end{aligned}$$

968)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0062976^2 + 1936000^2 & := & 1937024^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0062976^2 + 21296000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1937024^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0062976^2 + 214896000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1937024^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0062976^2 + 2150896000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1937024^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0062976^2 + 21510896000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1937024^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0062976^2 + 215110896000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1937024^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0062976^2 + 2151110896000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1937024^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0062976^2 + 21511110896000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1937024^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0062976^2 + 215111110896000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1937024^2 \end{aligned}$$

969)

$$\begin{aligned} &0061039^2 + 1938000^2 && := 1938961^2 \\ &12\ 0061039^2 + 21318000^2 && := 12\ 1938961^2 \\ &1232\ 0061039^2 + 215118000^2 && := 1232\ 1938961^2 \\ &123432\ 0061039^2 + 2153118000^2 && := 123432\ 1938961^2 \\ &12345432\ 0061039^2 + 21533118000^2 && := 12345432\ 1938961^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0061039^2 + 215333118000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1938961^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0061039^2 + 2153333118000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1938961^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0061039^2 + 21533333118000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1938961^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0061039^2 + 215333333118000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1938961^2 \end{aligned}$$

970)

$$\begin{aligned} &0059100^2 + 1940000^2 && := 1940900^2 \\ &12\ 0059100^2 + 21340000^2 && := 12\ 1940900^2 \\ &1232\ 0059100^2 + 215340000^2 && := 1232\ 1940900^2 \\ &123432\ 0059100^2 + 2155340000^2 && := 123432\ 1940900^2 \\ &12345432\ 0059100^2 + 21555340000^2 && := 12345432\ 1940900^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0059100^2 + 215555340000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1940900^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0059100^2 + 2155555340000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1940900^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0059100^2 + 21555555340000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1940900^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0059100^2 + 215555555340000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1940900^2 \end{aligned}$$

971)

$$\begin{aligned} &0057159^2 + 1942000^2 && := 1942841^2 \\ &12\ 0057159^2 + 21362000^2 && := 12\ 1942841^2 \\ &1232\ 0057159^2 + 215562000^2 && := 1232\ 1942841^2 \\ &123432\ 0057159^2 + 2157562000^2 && := 123432\ 1942841^2 \\ &12345432\ 0057159^2 + 21577562000^2 && := 12345432\ 1942841^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0057159^2 + 215777562000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1942841^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0057159^2 + 2157777562000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1942841^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0057159^2 + 21577777562000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1942841^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0057159^2 + 215777777562000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1942841^2 \end{aligned}$$

972)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0055216^2 + 1944000^2 & := & 1944784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0055216^2 + 21384000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1944784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0055216^2 + 215784000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1944784^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0055216^2 + 2159784000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1944784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0055216^2 + 21599784000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1944784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0055216^2 + 215999784000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1944784^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0055216^2 + 2159999784000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1944784^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0055216^2 + 21599999784000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1944784^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0055216^2 + 215999999784000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1944784^2 \end{aligned}$$

973)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0053271^2 + 1946000^2 & := & 1946729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0053271^2 + 21406000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1946729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0053271^2 + 216006000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1946729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0053271^2 + 2162006000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1946729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0053271^2 + 21622006000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1946729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0053271^2 + 216222006000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1946729^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0053271^2 + 2162222006000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1946729^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0053271^2 + 21622222006000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1946729^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0053271^2 + 216222222006000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1946729^2 \end{aligned}$$

974)

$$\begin{aligned} & 0051324^2 + 1948000^2 & := & 1948676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12} 0051324^2 + 21428000^2 & := & \mathbf{12} 1948676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1232} 0051324^2 + 216228000^2 & := & \mathbf{1232} 1948676^2 \\ & \mathbf{123432} 0051324^2 + 2164228000^2 & := & \mathbf{123432} 1948676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345432} 0051324^2 + 21644228000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345432} 1948676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234565432} 0051324^2 + 216444228000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234565432} 1948676^2 \\ & \mathbf{123456765432} 0051324^2 + 2164444228000^2 & := & \mathbf{123456765432} 1948676^2 \\ & \mathbf{12345678765432} 0051324^2 + 21644444228000^2 & := & \mathbf{12345678765432} 1948676^2 \\ & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 0051324^2 + 216444444228000^2 & := & \mathbf{1234567898765432} 1948676^2 \end{aligned}$$

975)

$$\begin{aligned} &0049375^2 + 1950000^2 && := 1950625^2 \\ &12\ 0049375^2 + 21450000^2 && := 12\ 1950625^2 \\ &1232\ 0049375^2 + 216450000^2 && := 1232\ 1950625^2 \\ &123432\ 0049375^2 + 2166450000^2 && := 123432\ 1950625^2 \\ &12345432\ 0049375^2 + 21666450000^2 && := 12345432\ 1950625^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0049375^2 + 216666450000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1950625^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0049375^2 + 2166666450000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1950625^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0049375^2 + 21666666450000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1950625^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0049375^2 + 216666666450000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1950625^2 \end{aligned}$$

976)

$$\begin{aligned} &0047424^2 + 1952000^2 && := 1952576^2 \\ &12\ 0047424^2 + 21472000^2 && := 12\ 1952576^2 \\ &1232\ 0047424^2 + 216672000^2 && := 1232\ 1952576^2 \\ &123432\ 0047424^2 + 2168672000^2 && := 123432\ 1952576^2 \\ &12345432\ 0047424^2 + 21688672000^2 && := 12345432\ 1952576^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0047424^2 + 216888672000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1952576^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0047424^2 + 2168888672000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1952576^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0047424^2 + 21688888672000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1952576^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0047424^2 + 216888888672000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1952576^2 \end{aligned}$$

977)

$$\begin{aligned} &0045471^2 + 1954000^2 && := 1954529^2 \\ &12\ 0045471^2 + 21494000^2 && := 12\ 1954529^2 \\ &1232\ 0045471^2 + 216894000^2 && := 1232\ 1954529^2 \\ &123432\ 0045471^2 + 2170894000^2 && := 123432\ 1954529^2 \\ &12345432\ 0045471^2 + 21710894000^2 && := 12345432\ 1954529^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0045471^2 + 217110894000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1954529^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0045471^2 + 2171110894000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1954529^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0045471^2 + 21711110894000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1954529^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0045471^2 + 217111110894000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1954529^2 \end{aligned}$$

978)

$$\begin{aligned} &0043516^2 + 1956000^2 && := 1956484^2 \\ &12\ 0043516^2 + 21516000^2 && := 12\ 1956484^2 \\ &1232\ 0043516^2 + 217116000^2 && := 1232\ 1956484^2 \\ &123432\ 0043516^2 + 2173116000^2 && := 123432\ 1956484^2 \\ &12345432\ 0043516^2 + 21733116000^2 && := 12345432\ 1956484^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0043516^2 + 217333116000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1956484^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0043516^2 + 2173333116000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1956484^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0043516^2 + 21733333116000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1956484^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0043516^2 + 217333333116000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1956484^2 \end{aligned}$$

979)

$$\begin{aligned} &0041559^2 + 1958000^2 && := 1958441^2 \\ &12\ 0041559^2 + 21538000^2 && := 12\ 1958441^2 \\ &1232\ 0041559^2 + 217338000^2 && := 1232\ 1958441^2 \\ &123432\ 0041559^2 + 2175338000^2 && := 123432\ 1958441^2 \\ &12345432\ 0041559^2 + 21755338000^2 && := 12345432\ 1958441^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0041559^2 + 217555338000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1958441^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0041559^2 + 2175555338000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1958441^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0041559^2 + 21755555338000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1958441^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0041559^2 + 217555555338000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1958441^2 \end{aligned}$$

980)

$$\begin{aligned} &0039600^2 + 1960000^2 && := 1960400^2 \\ &12\ 0039600^2 + 21560000^2 && := 12\ 1960400^2 \\ &1232\ 0039600^2 + 217560000^2 && := 1232\ 1960400^2 \\ &123432\ 0039600^2 + 2177560000^2 && := 123432\ 1960400^2 \\ &12345432\ 0039600^2 + 21777560000^2 && := 12345432\ 1960400^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0039600^2 + 217777560000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1960400^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0039600^2 + 2177777560000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1960400^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0039600^2 + 21777777560000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1960400^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0039600^2 + 217777777560000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1960400^2 \end{aligned}$$

981)

$$\begin{aligned} &0037639^2 + 1962000^2 && := 1962361^2 \\ &12\ 0037639^2 + 21582000^2 && := 12\ 1962361^2 \\ &1232\ 0037639^2 + 217782000^2 && := 1232\ 1962361^2 \\ &123432\ 0037639^2 + 2179782000^2 && := 123432\ 1962361^2 \\ &12345432\ 0037639^2 + 21799782000^2 && := 12345432\ 1962361^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0037639^2 + 217999782000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1962361^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0037639^2 + 2179999782000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1962361^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0037639^2 + 21799999782000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1962361^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0037639^2 + 217999999782000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1962361^2 \end{aligned}$$

982)

$$\begin{aligned} &0035676^2 + 1964000^2 && := 1964324^2 \\ &12\ 0035676^2 + 21604000^2 && := 12\ 1964324^2 \\ &1232\ 0035676^2 + 218004000^2 && := 1232\ 1964324^2 \\ &123432\ 0035676^2 + 2182004000^2 && := 123432\ 1964324^2 \\ &12345432\ 0035676^2 + 21822004000^2 && := 12345432\ 1964324^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0035676^2 + 218222004000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1964324^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0035676^2 + 2182222004000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1964324^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0035676^2 + 21822222004000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1964324^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0035676^2 + 218222222004000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1964324^2 \end{aligned}$$

983)

$$\begin{aligned} &0033711^2 + 1966000^2 && := 1966289^2 \\ &12\ 0033711^2 + 21626000^2 && := 12\ 1966289^2 \\ &1232\ 0033711^2 + 218226000^2 && := 1232\ 1966289^2 \\ &123432\ 0033711^2 + 2184226000^2 && := 123432\ 1966289^2 \\ &12345432\ 0033711^2 + 21844226000^2 && := 12345432\ 1966289^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0033711^2 + 218444226000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1966289^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0033711^2 + 2184444226000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1966289^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0033711^2 + 21844444226000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1966289^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0033711^2 + 218444444226000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1966289^2 \end{aligned}$$

984)

$$\begin{aligned} &0031744^2 + 1968000^2 && := 1968256^2 \\ &12\ 0031744^2 + 21648000^2 && := 12\ 1968256^2 \\ &1232\ 0031744^2 + 218448000^2 && := 1232\ 1968256^2 \\ &123432\ 0031744^2 + 2186448000^2 && := 123432\ 1968256^2 \\ &12345432\ 0031744^2 + 21866448000^2 && := 12345432\ 1968256^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0031744^2 + 218666448000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1968256^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0031744^2 + 2186666448000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1968256^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0031744^2 + 21866666448000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1968256^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0031744^2 + 218666666448000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1968256^2 \end{aligned}$$

985)

$$\begin{aligned} &0029775^2 + 1970000^2 && := 1970225^2 \\ &12\ 0029775^2 + 21670000^2 && := 12\ 1970225^2 \\ &1232\ 0029775^2 + 218670000^2 && := 1232\ 1970225^2 \\ &123432\ 0029775^2 + 2188670000^2 && := 123432\ 1970225^2 \\ &12345432\ 0029775^2 + 21888670000^2 && := 12345432\ 1970225^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0029775^2 + 218888670000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1970225^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0029775^2 + 2188888670000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1970225^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0029775^2 + 21888888670000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1970225^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0029775^2 + 218888888670000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1970225^2 \end{aligned}$$

986)

$$\begin{aligned} &0027804^2 + 1972000^2 && := 1972196^2 \\ &12\ 0027804^2 + 21692000^2 && := 12\ 1972196^2 \\ &1232\ 0027804^2 + 218892000^2 && := 1232\ 1972196^2 \\ &123432\ 0027804^2 + 2190892000^2 && := 123432\ 1972196^2 \\ &12345432\ 0027804^2 + 21910892000^2 && := 12345432\ 1972196^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0027804^2 + 219110892000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1972196^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0027804^2 + 2191110892000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1972196^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0027804^2 + 21911110892000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1972196^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0027804^2 + 219111110892000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1972196^2 \end{aligned}$$

987)

$$\begin{aligned} &0025831^2 + 1974000^2 && := 1974169^2 \\ &12\ 0025831^2 + 21714000^2 && := 12\ 1974169^2 \\ &1232\ 0025831^2 + 219114000^2 && := 1232\ 1974169^2 \\ &123432\ 0025831^2 + 2193114000^2 && := 123432\ 1974169^2 \\ &12345432\ 0025831^2 + 21933114000^2 && := 12345432\ 1974169^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0025831^2 + 219333114000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1974169^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0025831^2 + 2193333114000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1974169^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0025831^2 + 21933333114000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1974169^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0025831^2 + 219333333114000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1974169^2 \end{aligned}$$

988)

$$\begin{aligned} &0023856^2 + 1976000^2 && := 1976144^2 \\ &12\ 0023856^2 + 21736000^2 && := 12\ 1976144^2 \\ &1232\ 0023856^2 + 219336000^2 && := 1232\ 1976144^2 \\ &123432\ 0023856^2 + 2195336000^2 && := 123432\ 1976144^2 \\ &12345432\ 0023856^2 + 21955336000^2 && := 12345432\ 1976144^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0023856^2 + 219555336000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1976144^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0023856^2 + 2195555336000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1976144^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0023856^2 + 21955555336000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1976144^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0023856^2 + 219555555336000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1976144^2 \end{aligned}$$

989)

$$\begin{aligned} &0021879^2 + 1978000^2 && := 1978121^2 \\ &12\ 0021879^2 + 21758000^2 && := 12\ 1978121^2 \\ &1232\ 0021879^2 + 219558000^2 && := 1232\ 1978121^2 \\ &123432\ 0021879^2 + 2197558000^2 && := 123432\ 1978121^2 \\ &12345432\ 0021879^2 + 21977558000^2 && := 12345432\ 1978121^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0021879^2 + 219777558000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1978121^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0021879^2 + 2197777558000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1978121^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0021879^2 + 21977777558000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1978121^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0021879^2 + 219777777558000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1978121^2 \end{aligned}$$

990)

$$\begin{aligned} &0019900^2 + 1980000^2 && := 1980100^2 \\ &12\ 0019900^2 + 21780000^2 && := 12\ 1980100^2 \\ &1232\ 0019900^2 + 219780000^2 && := 1232\ 1980100^2 \\ &123432\ 0019900^2 + 2199780000^2 && := 123432\ 1980100^2 \\ &12345432\ 0019900^2 + 21999780000^2 && := 12345432\ 1980100^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0019900^2 + 219999780000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1980100^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0019900^2 + 2199999780000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1980100^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0019900^2 + 21999999780000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1980100^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0019900^2 + 219999999780000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1980100^2 \end{aligned}$$

991)

$$\begin{aligned} &0017919^2 + 1982000^2 && := 1982081^2 \\ &12\ 0017919^2 + 21802000^2 && := 12\ 1982081^2 \\ &1232\ 0017919^2 + 220002000^2 && := 1232\ 1982081^2 \\ &123432\ 0017919^2 + 2202002000^2 && := 123432\ 1982081^2 \\ &12345432\ 0017919^2 + 22022002000^2 && := 12345432\ 1982081^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0017919^2 + 220222002000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1982081^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0017919^2 + 2202222002000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1982081^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0017919^2 + 22022222002000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1982081^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0017919^2 + 220222222002000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1982081^2 \end{aligned}$$

992)

$$\begin{aligned} &0015936^2 + 1984000^2 && := 1984064^2 \\ &12\ 0015936^2 + 21824000^2 && := 12\ 1984064^2 \\ &1232\ 0015936^2 + 220224000^2 && := 1232\ 1984064^2 \\ &123432\ 0015936^2 + 2204224000^2 && := 123432\ 1984064^2 \\ &12345432\ 0015936^2 + 22044224000^2 && := 12345432\ 1984064^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0015936^2 + 220444224000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1984064^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0015936^2 + 2204444224000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1984064^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0015936^2 + 22044444224000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1984064^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0015936^2 + 220444444224000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1984064^2 \end{aligned}$$

993)

$$\begin{aligned} &0013951^2 + 1986000^2 && := 1986049^2 \\ &12\ 0013951^2 + 21846000^2 && := 12\ 1986049^2 \\ &1232\ 0013951^2 + 220446000^2 && := 1232\ 1986049^2 \\ &123432\ 0013951^2 + 2206446000^2 && := 123432\ 1986049^2 \\ &12345432\ 0013951^2 + 22066446000^2 && := 12345432\ 1986049^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0013951^2 + 220666446000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1986049^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0013951^2 + 2206666446000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1986049^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0013951^2 + 22066666446000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1986049^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0013951^2 + 220666666446000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1986049^2 \end{aligned}$$

994)

$$\begin{aligned} &0011964^2 + 1988000^2 && := 1988036^2 \\ &12\ 0011964^2 + 21868000^2 && := 12\ 1988036^2 \\ &1232\ 0011964^2 + 220668000^2 && := 1232\ 1988036^2 \\ &123432\ 0011964^2 + 2208668000^2 && := 123432\ 1988036^2 \\ &12345432\ 0011964^2 + 22088668000^2 && := 12345432\ 1988036^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0011964^2 + 220888668000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1988036^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0011964^2 + 2208888668000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1988036^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0011964^2 + 22088888668000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1988036^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0011964^2 + 220888888668000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1988036^2 \end{aligned}$$

995)

$$\begin{aligned} &0009975^2 + 1990000^2 && := 1990025^2 \\ &12\ 0009975^2 + 21890000^2 && := 12\ 1990025^2 \\ &1232\ 0009975^2 + 220890000^2 && := 1232\ 1990025^2 \\ &123432\ 0009975^2 + 2210890000^2 && := 123432\ 1990025^2 \\ &12345432\ 0009975^2 + 22110890000^2 && := 12345432\ 1990025^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0009975^2 + 221110890000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1990025^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0009975^2 + 2211110890000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1990025^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0009975^2 + 22111110890000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1990025^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0009975^2 + 221111110890000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1990025^2 \end{aligned}$$

996)

$$\begin{aligned} &0007984^2 + 1992000^2 && := 1992016^2 \\ &12\ 0007984^2 + 21912000^2 && := 12\ 1992016^2 \\ &1232\ 0007984^2 + 221112000^2 && := 1232\ 1992016^2 \\ &123432\ 0007984^2 + 2213112000^2 && := 123432\ 1992016^2 \\ &12345432\ 0007984^2 + 22133112000^2 && := 12345432\ 1992016^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0007984^2 + 221333112000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1992016^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0007984^2 + 2213333112000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1992016^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0007984^2 + 22133333112000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1992016^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0007984^2 + 221333333112000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1992016^2 \end{aligned}$$

997)

$$\begin{aligned} &0005991^2 + 1994000^2 && := 1994009^2 \\ &12\ 0005991^2 + 21934000^2 && := 12\ 1994009^2 \\ &1232\ 0005991^2 + 221334000^2 && := 1232\ 1994009^2 \\ &123432\ 0005991^2 + 2215334000^2 && := 123432\ 1994009^2 \\ &12345432\ 0005991^2 + 22155334000^2 && := 12345432\ 1994009^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0005991^2 + 221555334000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1994009^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0005991^2 + 2215555334000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1994009^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0005991^2 + 22155555334000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1994009^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0005991^2 + 221555555334000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1994009^2 \end{aligned}$$

998)

$$\begin{aligned} &0003996^2 + 1996000^2 && := 1996004^2 \\ &12\ 0003996^2 + 21956000^2 && := 12\ 1996004^2 \\ &1232\ 0003996^2 + 221556000^2 && := 1232\ 1996004^2 \\ &123432\ 0003996^2 + 2217556000^2 && := 123432\ 1996004^2 \\ &12345432\ 0003996^2 + 22177556000^2 && := 12345432\ 1996004^2 \\ &1234565432\ 0003996^2 + 221777556000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1996004^2 \\ &123456765432\ 0003996^2 + 2217777556000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1996004^2 \\ &12345678765432\ 0003996^2 + 22177777556000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1996004^2 \\ &1234567898765432\ 0003996^2 + 221777777556000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1996004^2 \end{aligned}$$

999)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0001999^2 + 1998000^2 && := 1998001^2 \\
 &12\ 0001999^2 + 21978000^2 && := 12\ 1998001^2 \\
 &1232\ 0001999^2 + 221778000^2 && := 1232\ 1998001^2 \\
 &123432\ 0001999^2 + 2219778000^2 && := 123432\ 1998001^2 \\
 &12345432\ 0001999^2 + 22199778000^2 && := 12345432\ 1998001^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 0001999^2 + 221999778000^2 && := 1234565432\ 1998001^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 0001999^2 + 2219999778000^2 && := 123456765432\ 1998001^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 0001999^2 + 22199999778000^2 && := 12345678765432\ 1998001^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 0001999^2 + 221999999778000^2 && := 1234567898765432\ 1998001^2
 \end{aligned}$$

4.3.2 Second Way

Let's consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 (vi) \ m = &1000, 101000, 10101000, 1010101000, 101010101000, 10101010101000, 1010101010101000 \\
 &1010101010101000, 101010101010101000.
 \end{aligned}$$

in (1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 999$; below are 999 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns**:

1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999999^2 + 2000^2 && := 1000001^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999999^2 + 202000^2 && := 1020\ 1000001^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999999^2 + 20202000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000001^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999999^2 + 2020202000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000001^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999999^2 + 202020202000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000001^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999999^2 + 20202020202000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000001^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999999^2 + 2020202020202000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000001^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999999^2 + 202020202020202000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000001^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999999^2 + 20202020202020202000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000001^2
 \end{aligned}$$

2)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999996^2 + 4000^2 && := 1000004^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999996^2 + 404000^2 && := 1020\ 1000004^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999996^2 + 40404000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000004^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999996^2 + 4040404000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000004^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999996^2 + 404040404000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000004^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999996^2 + 40404040404000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000004^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999996^2 + 4040404040404000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000004^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999996^2 + 404040404040404000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000004^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999996^2 + 40404040404040404000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000004^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 3)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999991^2 + 6000^2 && := 1000009^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999991^2 + 606000^2 && := 1020\ 1000009^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999991^2 + 60606000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000009^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999991^2 + 6060606000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000009^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999991^2 + 606060606000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000009^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999991^2 + 60606060606000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000009^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999991^2 + 6060606060606000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000009^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999991^2 + 606060606060606000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000009^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999991^2 + 60606060606060606000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000009^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 4)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999984^2 + 8000^2 && := 1000016^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999984^2 + 808000^2 && := 1020\ 1000016^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999984^2 + 80808000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000016^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999984^2 + 8080808000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000016^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999984^2 + 808080808000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000016^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999984^2 + 80808080808000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000016^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999984^2 + 8080808080808000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000016^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999984^2 + 808080808080808000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000016^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999984^2 + 80808080808080808000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000016^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 5)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999975^2 + 10000^2 && := 1000025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999975^2 + 1010000^2 && := 1020\ 1000025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999975^2 + 101010000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999975^2 + 10101010000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999975^2 + 1010101010000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999975^2 + 101010101010000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999975^2 + 10101010101010000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999975^2 + 1010101010101010000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999975^2 + 101010101010101010000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 6)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999964^2 + 12000^2 && := 1000036^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999964^2 + 1212000^2 && := 1020\ 1000036^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999964^2 + 121212000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000036^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999964^2 + 12121212000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000036^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999964^2 + 1212121212000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000036^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999964^2 + 121212121212000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000036^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999964^2 + 12121212121212000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000036^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999964^2 + 1212121212121212000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000036^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999964^2 + 121212121212121212000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000036^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 7)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999951^2 + 14000^2 && := 1000049^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999951^2 + 1414000^2 && := 1020\ 1000049^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999951^2 + 141414000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000049^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999951^2 + 14141414000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000049^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999951^2 + 1414141414000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000049^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999951^2 + 141414141414000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000049^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999951^2 + 14141414141414000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000049^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999951^2 + 1414141414141414000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000049^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999951^2 + 141414141414141414000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000049^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 8)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999936^2 + 16000^2 && := 1000064^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999936^2 + 1616000^2 && := 1020\ 1000064^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999936^2 + 161616000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000064^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999936^2 + 16161616000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000064^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999936^2 + 1616161616000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000064^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999936^2 + 161616161616000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000064^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999936^2 + 16161616161616000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000064^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999936^2 + 1616161616161616000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000064^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999936^2 + 161616161616161616000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000064^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 9)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999919^2 + 18000^2 && := 1000081^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999919^2 + 1818000^2 && := 1020\ 1000081^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999919^2 + 181818000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000081^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999919^2 + 18181818000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000081^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999919^2 + 1818181818000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000081^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999919^2 + 181818181818000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000081^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999919^2 + 18181818181818000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000081^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999919^2 + 1818181818181818000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000081^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999919^2 + 181818181818181818000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000081^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 10)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999900^2 + 20000^2 && := 1000100^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999900^2 + 2020000^2 && := 1020\ 1000100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999900^2 + 202020000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999900^2 + 20202020000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999900^2 + 2020202020000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999900^2 + 202020202020000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999900^2 + 20202020202020000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999900^2 + 2020202020202020000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999900^2 + 202020202020202020000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000100^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 11)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999879^2 + 22000^2 && := 1000121^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999879^2 + 2222000^2 && := 1020\ 1000121^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999879^2 + 222222000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000121^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999879^2 + 22222222000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000121^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999879^2 + 2222222222000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000121^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999879^2 + 222222222222000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000121^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999879^2 + 22222222222222000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000121^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999879^2 + 2222222222222222000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000121^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999879^2 + 222222222222222222000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000121^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 12)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999856^2 + 24000^2 && := 1000144^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999856^2 + 2424000^2 && := 1020\ 1000144^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999856^2 + 242424000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000144^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999856^2 + 24242424000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000144^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999856^2 + 2424242424000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000144^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999856^2 + 242424242424000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000144^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999856^2 + 24242424242424000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000144^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999856^2 + 2424242424242424000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000144^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999856^2 + 242424242424242424000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000144^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 13)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999831^2 + 26000^2 && := 1000169^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999831^2 + 2626000^2 && := 1020\ 1000169^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999831^2 + 262626000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000169^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999831^2 + 26262626000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000169^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999831^2 + 2626262626000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000169^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999831^2 + 262626262626000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000169^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999831^2 + 26262626262626000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000169^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999831^2 + 2626262626262626000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000169^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999831^2 + 262626262626262626000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000169^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 14)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999804^2 + 28000^2 && := 1000196^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999804^2 + 2828000^2 && := 1020\ 1000196^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999804^2 + 282828000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000196^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999804^2 + 28282828000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000196^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999804^2 + 2828282828000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000196^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999804^2 + 282828282828000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000196^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999804^2 + 28282828282828000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000196^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999804^2 + 2828282828282828000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000196^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999804^2 + 282828282828282828000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000196^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 15)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999775^2 + 30000^2 && := 1000225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999775^2 + 3030000^2 && := 1020\ 1000225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999775^2 + 303030000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999775^2 + 30303030000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999775^2 + 3030303030000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999775^2 + 303030303030000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999775^2 + 30303030303030000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999775^2 + 3030303030303030000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999775^2 + 303030303030303030000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 16)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999744^2 + 32000^2 && := 1000256^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999744^2 + 3232000^2 && := 1020\ 1000256^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999744^2 + 323232000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000256^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999744^2 + 32323232000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000256^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999744^2 + 3232323232000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000256^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999744^2 + 323232323232000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000256^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999744^2 + 32323232323232000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000256^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999744^2 + 3232323232323232000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000256^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999744^2 + 323232323232323232000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000256^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 17)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999711^2 + 34000^2 && := 1000289^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999711^2 + 3434000^2 && := 1020\ 1000289^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999711^2 + 343434000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000289^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999711^2 + 34343434000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000289^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999711^2 + 3434343434000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000289^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999711^2 + 343434343434000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000289^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999711^2 + 34343434343434000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000289^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999711^2 + 3434343434343434000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000289^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999711^2 + 343434343434343434000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000289^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 18)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999676^2 + 36000^2 && := 1000324^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999676^2 + 3636000^2 && := 1020\ 1000324^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999676^2 + 363636000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000324^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999676^2 + 36363636000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000324^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999676^2 + 3636363636000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000324^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999676^2 + 363636363636000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000324^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999676^2 + 36363636363636000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000324^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999676^2 + 3636363636363636000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000324^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999676^2 + 363636363636363636000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000324^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 19)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999639^2 + 38000^2 && := 1000361^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999639^2 + 3838000^2 && := 1020\ 1000361^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999639^2 + 383838000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000361^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999639^2 + 38383838000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000361^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999639^2 + 3838383838000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000361^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999639^2 + 383838383838000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000361^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999639^2 + 38383838383838000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000361^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999639^2 + 3838383838383838000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000361^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999639^2 + 383838383838383838000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000361^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 20)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999600^2 + 40000^2 && := 1000400^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999600^2 + 4040000^2 && := 1020\ 1000400^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999600^2 + 404040000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000400^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999600^2 + 40404040000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000400^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999600^2 + 4040404040000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000400^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999600^2 + 404040404040000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000400^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999600^2 + 40404040404040000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000400^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999600^2 + 4040404040404040000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000400^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999600^2 + 404040404040404040000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000400^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 21)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999559^2 + 42000^2 && := 1000441^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999559^2 + 4242000^2 && := 1020\ 1000441^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999559^2 + 424242000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000441^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999559^2 + 42424242000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000441^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999559^2 + 4242424242000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000441^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999559^2 + 424242424242000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000441^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999559^2 + 42424242424242000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000441^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999559^2 + 4242424242424242000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000441^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999559^2 + 424242424242424242000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000441^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 22)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999516^2 + 44000^2 && := 1000484^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999516^2 + 4444000^2 && := 1020\ 1000484^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999516^2 + 444444000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000484^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999516^2 + 44444444000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000484^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999516^2 + 4444444444000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000484^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999516^2 + 444444444444000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000484^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999516^2 + 44444444444444000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000484^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999516^2 + 4444444444444444000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000484^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999516^2 + 444444444444444444000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000484^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 23)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999471^2 + 46000^2 && := 1000529^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999471^2 + 4646000^2 && := 1020\ 1000529^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999471^2 + 464646000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000529^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999471^2 + 46464646000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000529^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999471^2 + 4646464646000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000529^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999471^2 + 464646464646000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000529^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999471^2 + 46464646464646000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000529^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999471^2 + 4646464646464646000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000529^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999471^2 + 464646464646464646000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000529^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 24)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999424^2 + 48000^2 && := 1000576^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999424^2 + 4848000^2 && := 1020\ 1000576^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999424^2 + 484848000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000576^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999424^2 + 48484848000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000576^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999424^2 + 4848484848000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000576^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999424^2 + 484848484848000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000576^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999424^2 + 48484848484848000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000576^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999424^2 + 4848484848484848000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000576^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999424^2 + 484848484848484848000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000576^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 25)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999375^2 + 50000^2 && := 1000625^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999375^2 + 5050000^2 && := 1020\ 1000625^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999375^2 + 505050000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000625^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999375^2 + 50505050000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000625^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999375^2 + 5050505050000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000625^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999375^2 + 505050505050000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000625^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999375^2 + 50505050505050000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000625^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999375^2 + 5050505050505050000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000625^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999375^2 + 505050505050505050000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000625^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 26)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999324^2 + 52000^2 && := 1000676^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999324^2 + 5252000^2 && := 1020\ 1000676^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999324^2 + 525252000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000676^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999324^2 + 52525252000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000676^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999324^2 + 5252525252000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000676^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999324^2 + 525252525252000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000676^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999324^2 + 52525252525252000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000676^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999324^2 + 5252525252525252000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000676^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999324^2 + 5252525252525252000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000676^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 27)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999271^2 + 54000^2 && := 1000729^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999271^2 + 5454000^2 && := 1020\ 1000729^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999271^2 + 545454000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000729^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999271^2 + 54545454000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000729^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999271^2 + 5454545454000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000729^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999271^2 + 545454545454000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000729^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999271^2 + 54545454545454000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000729^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999271^2 + 5454545454545454000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000729^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999271^2 + 545454545454545454000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000729^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 28)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999216^2 + 56000^2 && := 1000784^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999216^2 + 5656000^2 && := 1020\ 1000784^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999216^2 + 565656000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000784^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999216^2 + 56565656000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000784^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999216^2 + 5656565656000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000784^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999216^2 + 565656565656000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000784^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999216^2 + 56565656565656000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000784^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999216^2 + 5656565656565656000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000784^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999216^2 + 565656565656565656000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000784^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 29)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999159^2 + 58000^2 && := 1000841^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999159^2 + 5858000^2 && := 1020\ 1000841^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999159^2 + 585858000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000841^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999159^2 + 58585858000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000841^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999159^2 + 5858585858000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000841^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999159^2 + 585858585858000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000841^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999159^2 + 58585858585858000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000841^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999159^2 + 5858585858585858000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000841^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999159^2 + 585858585858585858000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000841^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 30)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999100^2 + 60000^2 && := 1000900^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999100^2 + 6060000^2 && := 1020\ 1000900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999100^2 + 606060000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999100^2 + 60606060000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999100^2 + 6060606060000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999100^2 + 606060606060000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999100^2 + 60606060606060000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999100^2 + 6060606060606060000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999100^2 + 606060606060606060000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 31)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0999039^2 + 62000^2 && := 1000961^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999039^2 + 6262000^2 && := 1020\ 1000961^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999039^2 + 626262000^2 && := 10203020\ 1000961^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999039^2 + 62626262000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1000961^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999039^2 + 6262626262000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1000961^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999039^2 + 626262626262000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1000961^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999039^2 + 62626262626262000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1000961^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999039^2 + 6262626262626262000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1000961^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999039^2 + 626262626262626262000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1000961^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 32)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998976^2 + 64000^2 && := 1001024^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998976^2 + 6464000^2 && := 1020\ 1001024^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998976^2 + 646464000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001024^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998976^2 + 64646464000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001024^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998976^2 + 6464646464000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001024^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998976^2 + 646464646464000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001024^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998976^2 + 64646464646464000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001024^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998976^2 + 6464646464646464000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001024^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998976^2 + 646464646464646464000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001024^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 33)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998911^2 + 66000^2 && := 1001089^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998911^2 + 6666000^2 && := 1020\ 1001089^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998911^2 + 666666000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001089^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998911^2 + 66666666000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001089^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998911^2 + 6666666666000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001089^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998911^2 + 666666666666000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001089^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998911^2 + 66666666666666000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001089^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998911^2 + 6666666666666666000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001089^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998911^2 + 666666666666666666000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001089^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 34)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998844^2 + 68000^2 && := 1001156^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998844^2 + 6868000^2 && := 1020\ 1001156^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998844^2 + 686868000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001156^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998844^2 + 68686868000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001156^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998844^2 + 6868686868000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001156^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998844^2 + 686868686868000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001156^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998844^2 + 68686868686868000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001156^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998844^2 + 6868686868686868000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001156^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998844^2 + 686868686868686868000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001156^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 35)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998775^2 + 70000^2 && := 1001225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998775^2 + 7070000^2 && := 1020\ 1001225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998775^2 + 707070000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998775^2 + 70707070000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998775^2 + 7070707070000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998775^2 + 707070707070000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998775^2 + 70707070707070000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998775^2 + 7070707070707070000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998775^2 + 707070707070707070000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 36)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998704^2 + 72000^2 && := 1001296^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998704^2 + 7272000^2 && := 1020\ 1001296^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998704^2 + 727272000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001296^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998704^2 + 72727272000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001296^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998704^2 + 7272727272000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001296^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998704^2 + 727272727272000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001296^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998704^2 + 72727272727272000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001296^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998704^2 + 7272727272727272000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001296^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998704^2 + 727272727272727272000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001296^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 37)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998631^2 + 74000^2 && := 1001369^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998631^2 + 7474000^2 && := 1020\ 1001369^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998631^2 + 747474000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001369^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998631^2 + 74747474000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001369^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998631^2 + 7474747474000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001369^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998631^2 + 747474747474000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001369^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998631^2 + 74747474747474000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001369^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998631^2 + 7474747474747474000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001369^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998631^2 + 747474747474747474000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001369^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 38)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998556^2 + 76000^2 && := 1001444^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998556^2 + 7676000^2 && := 1020\ 1001444^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998556^2 + 767676000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001444^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998556^2 + 76767676000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001444^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998556^2 + 7676767676000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001444^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998556^2 + 767676767676000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001444^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998556^2 + 76767676767676000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001444^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998556^2 + 7676767676767676000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001444^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998556^2 + 767676767676767676000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001444^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 39)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998479^2 + 78000^2 && := 1001521^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998479^2 + 7878000^2 && := 1020\ 1001521^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998479^2 + 787878000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001521^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998479^2 + 78787878000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001521^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998479^2 + 7878787878000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001521^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998479^2 + 787878787878000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001521^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998479^2 + 78787878787878000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001521^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998479^2 + 7878787878787878000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001521^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998479^2 + 787878787878787878000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001521^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 40)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998400^2 + 80000^2 && := 1001600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998400^2 + 8080000^2 && := 1020\ 1001600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998400^2 + 808080000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998400^2 + 80808080000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998400^2 + 8080808080000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998400^2 + 808080808080000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998400^2 + 80808080808080000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998400^2 + 8080808080808080000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998400^2 + 808080808080808080000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 41)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998319^2 + 82000^2 && := 1001681^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998319^2 + 8282000^2 && := 1020\ 1001681^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998319^2 + 828282000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001681^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998319^2 + 82828282000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001681^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998319^2 + 8282828282000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001681^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998319^2 + 828282828282000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001681^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998319^2 + 82828282828282000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001681^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998319^2 + 8282828282828282000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001681^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998319^2 + 828282828282828282000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001681^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 42)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0998236^2 + 84000^2 && := 1001764^2 \\
 &1020\ 0998236^2 + 8484000^2 && := 1020\ 1001764^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0998236^2 + 848484000^2 && := 10203020\ 1001764^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0998236^2 + 84848484000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1001764^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0998236^2 + 8484848484000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1001764^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0998236^2 + 848484848484000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1001764^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0998236^2 + 84848484848484000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1001764^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0998236^2 + 8484848484848484000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1001764^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0998236^2 + 848484848484848484000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1001764^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 43)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0998151^2 + 86000^2 && := 1001849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0998151^2 + 8686000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1001849^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0998151^2 + 868686000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1001849^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0998151^2 + 86868686000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1001849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0998151^2 + 8686868686000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1001849^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0998151^2 + 868686868686000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1001849^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0998151^2 + 86868686868686000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1001849^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0998151^2 + 8686868686868686000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1001849^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0998151^2 + 868686868686868686000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1001849^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 44)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0998064^2 + 88000^2 && := 1001936^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0998064^2 + 8888000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1001936^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0998064^2 + 888888000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1001936^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0998064^2 + 88888888000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1001936^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0998064^2 + 8888888888000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1001936^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0998064^2 + 888888888888000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1001936^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0998064^2 + 88888888888888000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1001936^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0998064^2 + 8888888888888888000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1001936^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0998064^2 + 888888888888888888000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1001936^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 45)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0997975^2 + 90000^2 && := 1002025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0997975^2 + 9090000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1002025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0997975^2 + 909090000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1002025^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0997975^2 + 90909090000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1002025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0997975^2 + 9090909090000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1002025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0997975^2 + 909090909090000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1002025^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0997975^2 + 90909090909090000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1002025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0997975^2 + 9090909090909090000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1002025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0997975^2 + 909090909090909090000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1002025^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 46)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0997884^2 + 92000^2 && := 1002116^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0997884^2 + 9292000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1002116^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0997884^2 + 929292000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1002116^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0997884^2 + 92929292000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1002116^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0997884^2 + 9292929292000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1002116^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0997884^2 + 929292929292000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1002116^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0997884^2 + 92929292929292000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1002116^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0997884^2 + 9292929292929292000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1002116^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0997884^2 + 929292929292929292000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1002116^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 47)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0997791^2 + 94000^2 && := 1002209^2 \\
 &1020\ 0997791^2 + 9494000^2 && := 1020\ 1002209^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0997791^2 + 949494000^2 && := 10203020\ 1002209^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0997791^2 + 94949494000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1002209^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0997791^2 + 9494949494000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1002209^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0997791^2 + 949494949494000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1002209^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0997791^2 + 94949494949494000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1002209^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0997791^2 + 9494949494949494000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1002209^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0997791^2 + 949494949494949494000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1002209^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 48)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0997696^2 + 96000^2 && := 1002304^2 \\
 &1020\ 0997696^2 + 9696000^2 && := 1020\ 1002304^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0997696^2 + 969696000^2 && := 10203020\ 1002304^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0997696^2 + 96969696000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1002304^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0997696^2 + 9696969696000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1002304^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0997696^2 + 969696969696000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1002304^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0997696^2 + 96969696969696000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1002304^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0997696^2 + 9696969696969696000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1002304^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0997696^2 + 969696969696969696000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1002304^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 49)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0997599^2 + 98000^2 && := 1002401^2 \\
 &1020\ 0997599^2 + 9898000^2 && := 1020\ 1002401^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0997599^2 + 989898000^2 && := 10203020\ 1002401^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0997599^2 + 98989898000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1002401^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0997599^2 + 9898989898000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1002401^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0997599^2 + 989898989898000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1002401^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0997599^2 + 98989898989898000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1002401^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0997599^2 + 9898989898989898000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1002401^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0997599^2 + 989898989898989898000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1002401^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 50)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0997500^2 + 100000^2 && := 1002500^2 \\
 &1020\ 0997500^2 + 10100000^2 && := 1020\ 1002500^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0997500^2 + 1010100000^2 && := 10203020\ 1002500^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0997500^2 + 101010100000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1002500^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0997500^2 + 10101010100000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1002500^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0997500^2 + 1010101010100000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1002500^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0997500^2 + 101010101010100000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1002500^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0997500^2 + 10101010101010100000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1002500^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0997500^2 + 1010101010101010100000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1002500^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 51)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0997399^2 + 102000^2 && := 1002601^2 \\
 &1020\ 0997399^2 + 10302000^2 && := 1020\ 1002601^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0997399^2 + 1030302000^2 && := 10203020\ 1002601^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0997399^2 + 103030302000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1002601^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0997399^2 + 10303030302000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1002601^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0997399^2 + 1030303030302000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1002601^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0997399^2 + 103030303030302000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1002601^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0997399^2 + 10303030303030302000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1002601^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0997399^2 + 1030303030303030302000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1002601^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 52)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0997296^2 + 104000^2 && := 1002704^2 \\
 &1020\ 0997296^2 + 10504000^2 && := 1020\ 1002704^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0997296^2 + 1050504000^2 && := 10203020\ 1002704^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0997296^2 + 105050504000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1002704^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0997296^2 + 10505050504000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1002704^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0997296^2 + 1050505050504000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1002704^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0997296^2 + 105050505050504000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1002704^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0997296^2 + 10505050505050504000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1002704^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0997296^2 + 1050505050505050504000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1002704^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 53)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0997191^2 + 106000^2 && := 1002809^2 \\
 &1020\ 0997191^2 + 10706000^2 && := 1020\ 1002809^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0997191^2 + 1070706000^2 && := 10203020\ 1002809^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0997191^2 + 107070706000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1002809^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0997191^2 + 10707070706000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1002809^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0997191^2 + 1070707070706000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1002809^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0997191^2 + 107070707070706000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1002809^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0997191^2 + 10707070707070706000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1002809^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0997191^2 + 1070707070707070706000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1002809^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 54)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0997084^2 + 108000^2 && := 1002916^2 \\
 &1020\ 0997084^2 + 10908000^2 && := 1020\ 1002916^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0997084^2 + 1090908000^2 && := 10203020\ 1002916^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0997084^2 + 109090908000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1002916^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0997084^2 + 10909090908000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1002916^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0997084^2 + 1090909090908000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1002916^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0997084^2 + 109090909090908000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1002916^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0997084^2 + 10909090909090908000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1002916^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0997084^2 + 1090909090909090908000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1002916^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 55)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996975^2 + 110000^2 && := 1003025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996975^2 + 11110000^2 && := 1020\ 1003025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996975^2 + 1111110000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996975^2 + 111111110000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996975^2 + 11111111110000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996975^2 + 1111111111110000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996975^2 + 111111111111110000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996975^2 + 11111111111111110000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996975^2 + 1111111111111111110000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 56)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996864^2 + 112000^2 && := 1003136^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996864^2 + 11312000^2 && := 1020\ 1003136^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996864^2 + 1131312000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003136^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996864^2 + 113131312000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003136^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996864^2 + 11313131312000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003136^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996864^2 + 1131313131312000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003136^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996864^2 + 113131313131312000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003136^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996864^2 + 11313131313131312000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003136^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996864^2 + 1131313131313131312000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003136^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 57)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996751^2 + 114000^2 && := 1003249^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996751^2 + 11514000^2 && := 1020\ 1003249^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996751^2 + 1151514000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003249^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996751^2 + 115151514000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003249^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996751^2 + 11515151514000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003249^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996751^2 + 1151515151514000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003249^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996751^2 + 115151515151514000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003249^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996751^2 + 11515151515151514000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003249^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996751^2 + 1151515151515151514000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003249^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 58)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996636^2 + 116000^2 && := 1003364^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996636^2 + 11716000^2 && := 1020\ 1003364^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996636^2 + 1171716000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003364^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996636^2 + 117171716000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003364^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996636^2 + 11717171716000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003364^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996636^2 + 1171717171716000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003364^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996636^2 + 117171717171716000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003364^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996636^2 + 11717171717171716000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003364^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996636^2 + 1171717171717171716000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003364^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 59)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996519^2 + 118000^2 && := 1003481^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996519^2 + 11918000^2 && := 1020\ 1003481^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996519^2 + 1191918000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003481^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996519^2 + 119191918000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003481^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996519^2 + 11919191918000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003481^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996519^2 + 1191919191918000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003481^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996519^2 + 119191919191918000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003481^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996519^2 + 11919191919191918000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003481^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996519^2 + 1191919191919191918000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003481^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 60)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996400^2 + 120000^2 && := 1003600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996400^2 + 12120000^2 && := 1020\ 1003600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996400^2 + 1212120000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996400^2 + 121212120000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996400^2 + 12121212120000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996400^2 + 1212121212120000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996400^2 + 121212121212120000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996400^2 + 12121212121212120000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996400^2 + 1212121212121212120000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 61)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996279^2 + 122000^2 && := 1003721^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996279^2 + 12322000^2 && := 1020\ 1003721^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996279^2 + 1232322000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003721^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996279^2 + 123232322000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003721^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996279^2 + 12323232322000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003721^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996279^2 + 1232323232322000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003721^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996279^2 + 123232323232322000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003721^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996279^2 + 12323232323232322000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003721^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996279^2 + 12323232323232322000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003721^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 62)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996156^2 + 124000^2 && := 1003844^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996156^2 + 12524000^2 && := 1020\ 1003844^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996156^2 + 1252524000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003844^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996156^2 + 125252524000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003844^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996156^2 + 12525252524000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003844^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996156^2 + 1252525252524000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003844^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996156^2 + 125252525252524000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003844^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996156^2 + 12525252525252524000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003844^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996156^2 + 12525252525252524000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003844^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 63)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0996031^2 + 126000^2 && := 1003969^2 \\
 &1020\ 0996031^2 + 12726000^2 && := 1020\ 1003969^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0996031^2 + 1272726000^2 && := 10203020\ 1003969^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0996031^2 + 127272726000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1003969^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0996031^2 + 12727272726000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1003969^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0996031^2 + 1272727272726000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1003969^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0996031^2 + 127272727272726000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1003969^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0996031^2 + 12727272727272726000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1003969^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0996031^2 + 1272727272727272726000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1003969^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 64)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0995904^2 + 128000^2 && := 1004096^2 \\
 &1020\ 0995904^2 + 12928000^2 && := 1020\ 1004096^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0995904^2 + 1292928000^2 && := 10203020\ 1004096^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0995904^2 + 129292928000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1004096^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0995904^2 + 12929292928000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1004096^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0995904^2 + 1292929292928000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1004096^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0995904^2 + 129292929292928000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1004096^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0995904^2 + 12929292929292928000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1004096^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0995904^2 + 1292929292929292928000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1004096^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 65)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0995775^2 + 130000^2 && := 1004225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0995775^2 + 13130000^2 && := 1020\ 1004225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0995775^2 + 1313130000^2 && := 10203020\ 1004225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0995775^2 + 131313130000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1004225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0995775^2 + 13131313130000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1004225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0995775^2 + 1313131313130000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1004225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0995775^2 + 131313131313130000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1004225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0995775^2 + 13131313131313130000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1004225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0995775^2 + 1313131313131313130000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1004225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 66)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0995644^2 + 132000^2 && := 1004356^2 \\
 &1020\ 0995644^2 + 13332000^2 && := 1020\ 1004356^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0995644^2 + 1333332000^2 && := 10203020\ 1004356^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0995644^2 + 133333332000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1004356^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0995644^2 + 13333333332000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1004356^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0995644^2 + 1333333333332000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1004356^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0995644^2 + 133333333333332000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1004356^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0995644^2 + 13333333333333332000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1004356^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0995644^2 + 1333333333333333332000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1004356^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 67)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0995511^2 + 134000^2 && := 1004489^2 \\
 &1020\ 0995511^2 + 13534000^2 && := 1020\ 1004489^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0995511^2 + 1353534000^2 && := 10203020\ 1004489^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0995511^2 + 135353534000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1004489^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0995511^2 + 13535353534000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1004489^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0995511^2 + 1353535353534000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1004489^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0995511^2 + 135353535353534000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1004489^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0995511^2 + 13535353535353534000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1004489^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0995511^2 + 1353535353535353534000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1004489^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 68)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0995376^2 + 136000^2 && := 1004624^2 \\
 &1020\ 0995376^2 + 13736000^2 && := 1020\ 1004624^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0995376^2 + 1373736000^2 && := 10203020\ 1004624^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0995376^2 + 137373736000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1004624^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0995376^2 + 13737373736000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1004624^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0995376^2 + 1373737373736000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1004624^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0995376^2 + 137373737373736000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1004624^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0995376^2 + 13737373737373736000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1004624^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0995376^2 + 1373737373737373736000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1004624^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 69)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0995239^2 + 138000^2 && := 1004761^2 \\
 &1020\ 0995239^2 + 13938000^2 && := 1020\ 1004761^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0995239^2 + 1393938000^2 && := 10203020\ 1004761^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0995239^2 + 139393938000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1004761^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0995239^2 + 13939393938000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1004761^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0995239^2 + 1393939393938000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1004761^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0995239^2 + 139393939393938000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1004761^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0995239^2 + 13939393939393938000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1004761^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0995239^2 + 1393939393939393938000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1004761^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 70)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0995100^2 + 140000^2 && := 1004900^2 \\
 &1020\ 0995100^2 + 14140000^2 && := 1020\ 1004900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0995100^2 + 1414140000^2 && := 10203020\ 1004900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0995100^2 + 141414140000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1004900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0995100^2 + 14141414140000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1004900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0995100^2 + 1414141414140000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1004900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0995100^2 + 141414141414140000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1004900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0995100^2 + 14141414141414140000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1004900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0995100^2 + 1414141414141414140000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1004900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 71)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0994959^2 + 142000^2 && := 1005041^2 \\
 &1020\ 0994959^2 + 14342000^2 && := 1020\ 1005041^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0994959^2 + 1434342000^2 && := 10203020\ 1005041^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0994959^2 + 143434342000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1005041^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0994959^2 + 14343434342000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1005041^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0994959^2 + 1434343434342000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1005041^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0994959^2 + 143434343434342000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1005041^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0994959^2 + 14343434343434342000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1005041^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0994959^2 + 1434343434343434342000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1005041^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 72)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0994816^2 + 144000^2 && := 1005184^2 \\
 &1020\ 0994816^2 + 14544000^2 && := 1020\ 1005184^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0994816^2 + 1454544000^2 && := 10203020\ 1005184^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0994816^2 + 145454544000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1005184^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0994816^2 + 14545454544000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1005184^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0994816^2 + 1454545454544000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1005184^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0994816^2 + 145454545454544000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1005184^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0994816^2 + 14545454545454544000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1005184^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0994816^2 + 1454545454545454544000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1005184^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 73)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0994671^2 + 146000^2 && := 1005329^2 \\
 &1020\ 0994671^2 + 14746000^2 && := 1020\ 1005329^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0994671^2 + 1474746000^2 && := 10203020\ 1005329^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0994671^2 + 147474746000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1005329^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0994671^2 + 14747474746000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1005329^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0994671^2 + 1474747474746000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1005329^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0994671^2 + 147474747474746000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1005329^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0994671^2 + 14747474747474746000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1005329^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0994671^2 + 1474747474747474746000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1005329^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 74)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0994524^2 + 148000^2 && := 1005476^2 \\
 &1020\ 0994524^2 + 14948000^2 && := 1020\ 1005476^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0994524^2 + 1494948000^2 && := 10203020\ 1005476^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0994524^2 + 149494948000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1005476^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0994524^2 + 14949494948000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1005476^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0994524^2 + 1494949494948000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1005476^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0994524^2 + 149494949494948000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1005476^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0994524^2 + 14949494949494948000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1005476^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0994524^2 + 14949494949494948000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1005476^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 75)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0994375^2 + 150000^2 && := 1005625^2 \\ &1020\ 0994375^2 + 15150000^2 && := 1020\ 1005625^2 \\ &10203020\ 0994375^2 + 1515150000^2 && := 10203020\ 1005625^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0994375^2 + 151515150000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1005625^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0994375^2 + 15151515150000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1005625^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0994375^2 + 1515151515150000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1005625^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0994375^2 + 151515151515150000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1005625^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0994375^2 + 15151515151515150000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1005625^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0994375^2 + 1515151515151515150000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1005625^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 76)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0994224^2 + 152000^2 && := 1005776^2 \\ &1020\ 0994224^2 + 15352000^2 && := 1020\ 1005776^2 \\ &10203020\ 0994224^2 + 1535352000^2 && := 10203020\ 1005776^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0994224^2 + 153535352000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1005776^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0994224^2 + 15353535352000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1005776^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0994224^2 + 1535353535352000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1005776^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0994224^2 + 153535353535352000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1005776^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0994224^2 + 15353535353535352000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1005776^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0994224^2 + 1535353535353535352000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1005776^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 77)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0994071^2 + 154000^2 && := 1005929^2 \\ &1020\ 0994071^2 + 15554000^2 && := 1020\ 1005929^2 \\ &10203020\ 0994071^2 + 1555554000^2 && := 10203020\ 1005929^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0994071^2 + 155555554000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1005929^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0994071^2 + 15555555554000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1005929^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0994071^2 + 1555555555554000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1005929^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0994071^2 + 155555555555554000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1005929^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0994071^2 + 15555555555555554000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1005929^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0994071^2 + 1555555555555555554000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1005929^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 78)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0993916^2 + 156000^2 && := 1006084^2 \\ &1020\ 0993916^2 + 15756000^2 && := 1020\ 1006084^2 \\ &10203020\ 0993916^2 + 1575756000^2 && := 10203020\ 1006084^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0993916^2 + 157575756000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1006084^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0993916^2 + 15757575756000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1006084^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0993916^2 + 1575757575756000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1006084^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0993916^2 + 157575757575756000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1006084^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0993916^2 + 15757575757575756000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1006084^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0993916^2 + 1575757575757575756000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1006084^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 79)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0993759^2 + 158000^2$ | $:= 1006241^2$ |
| $1020\ 0993759^2 + 15958000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1006241^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0993759^2 + 1595958000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1006241^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0993759^2 + 159595958000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1006241^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0993759^2 + 15959595958000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1006241^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0993759^2 + 1595959595958000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1006241^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0993759^2 + 159595959595958000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1006241^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0993759^2 + 15959595959595958000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1006241^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0993759^2 + 1595959595959595958000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1006241^2$ |
- 80)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0993600^2 + 160000^2$ | $:= 1006400^2$ |
| $1020\ 0993600^2 + 16160000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1006400^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0993600^2 + 1616160000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1006400^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0993600^2 + 161616160000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1006400^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0993600^2 + 16161616160000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1006400^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0993600^2 + 1616161616160000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1006400^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0993600^2 + 161616161616160000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1006400^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0993600^2 + 16161616161616160000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1006400^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0993600^2 + 1616161616161616160000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1006400^2$ |
- 81)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0993439^2 + 162000^2$ | $:= 1006561^2$ |
| $1020\ 0993439^2 + 16362000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1006561^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0993439^2 + 1636362000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1006561^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0993439^2 + 163636362000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1006561^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0993439^2 + 16363636362000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1006561^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0993439^2 + 1636363636362000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1006561^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0993439^2 + 163636363636362000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1006561^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0993439^2 + 16363636363636362000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1006561^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0993439^2 + 1636363636363636362000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1006561^2$ |
- 82)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0993276^2 + 164000^2$ | $:= 1006724^2$ |
| $1020\ 0993276^2 + 16564000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1006724^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0993276^2 + 1656564000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1006724^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0993276^2 + 165656564000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1006724^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0993276^2 + 16565656564000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1006724^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0993276^2 + 1656565656564000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1006724^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0993276^2 + 165656565656564000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1006724^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0993276^2 + 16565656565656564000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1006724^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0993276^2 + 1656565656565656564000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1006724^2$ |

- 83)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0993111^2 + 166000^2$ | $:= 1006889^2$ |
| $1020\ 0993111^2 + 16766000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1006889^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0993111^2 + 1676766000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1006889^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0993111^2 + 167676766000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1006889^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0993111^2 + 16767676766000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1006889^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0993111^2 + 1676767676766000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1006889^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0993111^2 + 167676767676766000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1006889^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0993111^2 + 16767676767676766000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1006889^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0993111^2 + 1676767676767676766000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1006889^2$ |
- 84)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0992944^2 + 168000^2$ | $:= 1007056^2$ |
| $1020\ 0992944^2 + 16968000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1007056^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0992944^2 + 1696968000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1007056^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0992944^2 + 169696968000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1007056^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0992944^2 + 16969696968000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1007056^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0992944^2 + 1696969696968000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1007056^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0992944^2 + 169696969696968000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1007056^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0992944^2 + 16969696969696968000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1007056^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0992944^2 + 1696969696969696968000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1007056^2$ |
- 85)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0992775^2 + 170000^2$ | $:= 1007225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0992775^2 + 17170000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1007225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0992775^2 + 1717170000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1007225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0992775^2 + 171717170000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1007225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0992775^2 + 17171717170000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1007225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0992775^2 + 1717171717170000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1007225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0992775^2 + 171717171717170000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1007225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0992775^2 + 17171717171717170000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1007225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0992775^2 + 1717171717171717170000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1007225^2$ |
- 86)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0992604^2 + 172000^2$ | $:= 1007396^2$ |
| $1020\ 0992604^2 + 17372000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1007396^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0992604^2 + 1737372000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1007396^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0992604^2 + 173737372000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1007396^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0992604^2 + 17373737372000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1007396^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0992604^2 + 1737373737372000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1007396^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0992604^2 + 173737373737372000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1007396^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0992604^2 + 17373737373737372000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1007396^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0992604^2 + 1737373737373737372000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1007396^2$ |

- 87)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0992431^2 + 174000^2 && := 1007569^2 \\
 &1020\ 0992431^2 + 17574000^2 && := 1020\ 1007569^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0992431^2 + 1757574000^2 && := 10203020\ 1007569^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0992431^2 + 175757574000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1007569^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0992431^2 + 17575757574000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1007569^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0992431^2 + 1757575757574000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1007569^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0992431^2 + 175757575757574000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1007569^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0992431^2 + 17575757575757574000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1007569^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0992431^2 + 1757575757575757574000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1007569^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 88)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0992256^2 + 176000^2 && := 1007744^2 \\
 &1020\ 0992256^2 + 17776000^2 && := 1020\ 1007744^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0992256^2 + 1777776000^2 && := 10203020\ 1007744^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0992256^2 + 177777776000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1007744^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0992256^2 + 17777777776000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1007744^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0992256^2 + 1777777777776000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1007744^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0992256^2 + 177777777777776000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1007744^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0992256^2 + 17777777777777776000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1007744^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0992256^2 + 1777777777777777776000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1007744^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 89)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0992079^2 + 178000^2 && := 1007921^2 \\
 &1020\ 0992079^2 + 17978000^2 && := 1020\ 1007921^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0992079^2 + 1797978000^2 && := 10203020\ 1007921^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0992079^2 + 179797978000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1007921^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0992079^2 + 17979797978000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1007921^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0992079^2 + 1797979797978000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1007921^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0992079^2 + 179797979797978000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1007921^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0992079^2 + 17979797979797978000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1007921^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0992079^2 + 1797979797979797978000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1007921^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 90)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0991900^2 + 180000^2 && := 1008100^2 \\
 &1020\ 0991900^2 + 18180000^2 && := 1020\ 1008100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0991900^2 + 1818180000^2 && := 10203020\ 1008100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0991900^2 + 181818180000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1008100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0991900^2 + 18181818180000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1008100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0991900^2 + 1818181818180000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1008100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0991900^2 + 181818181818180000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1008100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0991900^2 + 18181818181818180000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1008100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0991900^2 + 1818181818181818180000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1008100^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 91)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0991719^2 + 182000^2 && := 1008281^2 \\
 &1020\ 0991719^2 + 18382000^2 && := 1020\ 1008281^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0991719^2 + 1838382000^2 && := 10203020\ 1008281^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0991719^2 + 183838382000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1008281^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0991719^2 + 18383838382000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1008281^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0991719^2 + 1838383838382000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1008281^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0991719^2 + 183838383838382000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1008281^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0991719^2 + 18383838383838382000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1008281^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0991719^2 + 1838383838383838382000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1008281^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 92)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0991536^2 + 184000^2 && := 1008464^2 \\
 &1020\ 0991536^2 + 18584000^2 && := 1020\ 1008464^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0991536^2 + 1858584000^2 && := 10203020\ 1008464^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0991536^2 + 185858584000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1008464^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0991536^2 + 18585858584000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1008464^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0991536^2 + 1858585858584000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1008464^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0991536^2 + 185858585858584000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1008464^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0991536^2 + 18585858585858584000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1008464^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0991536^2 + 1858585858585858584000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1008464^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 93)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0991351^2 + 186000^2 && := 1008649^2 \\
 &1020\ 0991351^2 + 18786000^2 && := 1020\ 1008649^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0991351^2 + 1878786000^2 && := 10203020\ 1008649^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0991351^2 + 187878786000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1008649^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0991351^2 + 18787878786000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1008649^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0991351^2 + 1878787878786000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1008649^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0991351^2 + 187878787878786000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1008649^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0991351^2 + 18787878787878786000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1008649^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0991351^2 + 1878787878787878786000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1008649^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 94)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0991164^2 + 188000^2 && := 1008836^2 \\
 &1020\ 0991164^2 + 18988000^2 && := 1020\ 1008836^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0991164^2 + 1898988000^2 && := 10203020\ 1008836^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0991164^2 + 189898988000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1008836^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0991164^2 + 18989898988000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1008836^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0991164^2 + 1898989898988000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1008836^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0991164^2 + 189898989898988000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1008836^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0991164^2 + 18989898989898988000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1008836^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0991164^2 + 18989898989898988000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1008836^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 95)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0990975^2 + 190000^2$ | $:= 1009025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0990975^2 + 19190000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1009025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0990975^2 + 1919190000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1009025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0990975^2 + 191919190000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1009025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0990975^2 + 19191919190000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1009025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0990975^2 + 1919191919190000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1009025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0990975^2 + 191919191919190000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1009025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0990975^2 + 19191919191919190000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1009025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0990975^2 + 1919191919191919190000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1009025^2$ |
- 96)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0990784^2 + 192000^2$ | $:= 1009216^2$ |
| $1020\ 0990784^2 + 19392000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1009216^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0990784^2 + 1939392000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1009216^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0990784^2 + 193939392000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1009216^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0990784^2 + 19393939392000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1009216^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0990784^2 + 1939393939392000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1009216^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0990784^2 + 193939393939392000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1009216^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0990784^2 + 19393939393939392000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1009216^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0990784^2 + 1939393939393939392000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1009216^2$ |
- 97)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0990591^2 + 194000^2$ | $:= 1009409^2$ |
| $1020\ 0990591^2 + 19594000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1009409^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0990591^2 + 1959594000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1009409^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0990591^2 + 195959594000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1009409^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0990591^2 + 19595959594000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1009409^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0990591^2 + 1959595959594000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1009409^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0990591^2 + 195959595959594000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1009409^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0990591^2 + 19595959595959594000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1009409^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0990591^2 + 1959595959595959594000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1009409^2$ |
- 98)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0990396^2 + 196000^2$ | $:= 1009604^2$ |
| $1020\ 0990396^2 + 19796000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1009604^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0990396^2 + 1979796000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1009604^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0990396^2 + 197979796000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1009604^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0990396^2 + 19797979796000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1009604^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0990396^2 + 1979797979796000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1009604^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0990396^2 + 197979797979796000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1009604^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0990396^2 + 19797979797979796000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1009604^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0990396^2 + 1979797979797979796000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1009604^2$ |

- 99)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0990199^2 + 198000^2 && := 1009801^2 \\
 &1020\ 0990199^2 + 19998000^2 && := 1020\ 1009801^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0990199^2 + 1999998000^2 && := 10203020\ 1009801^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0990199^2 + 199999998000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1009801^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0990199^2 + 19999999998000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1009801^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0990199^2 + 199999999998000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1009801^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0990199^2 + 19999999999998000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1009801^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0990199^2 + 1999999999999998000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1009801^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0990199^2 + 199999999999999998000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1009801^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 100)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0990000^2 + 200000^2 && := 1010000^2 \\
 &1020\ 0990000^2 + 20200000^2 && := 1020\ 1010000^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0990000^2 + 2020200000^2 && := 10203020\ 1010000^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0990000^2 + 202020200000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1010000^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0990000^2 + 20202020200000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1010000^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0990000^2 + 2020202020200000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1010000^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0990000^2 + 202020202020200000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1010000^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0990000^2 + 20202020202020200000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1010000^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0990000^2 + 2020202020202020200000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1010000^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 101)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0989799^2 + 202000^2 && := 1010201^2 \\
 &1020\ 0989799^2 + 20402000^2 && := 1020\ 1010201^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0989799^2 + 2040402000^2 && := 10203020\ 1010201^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0989799^2 + 204040402000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1010201^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0989799^2 + 20404040402000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1010201^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0989799^2 + 2040404040402000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1010201^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0989799^2 + 204040404040402000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1010201^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0989799^2 + 20404040404040402000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1010201^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 102)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0989596^2 + 204000^2 && := 1010404^2 \\
 &1020\ 0989596^2 + 20604000^2 && := 1020\ 1010404^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0989596^2 + 2060604000^2 && := 10203020\ 1010404^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0989596^2 + 206060604000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1010404^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0989596^2 + 20606060604000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1010404^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0989596^2 + 2060606060604000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1010404^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0989596^2 + 206060606060604000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1010404^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0989596^2 + 20606060606060604000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1010404^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0989596^2 + 2060606060606060604000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1010404^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 103)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0989391^2 + 206000^2 && := 1010609^2 \\
 &1020\ 0989391^2 + 20806000^2 && := 1020\ 1010609^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0989391^2 + 2080806000^2 && := 10203020\ 1010609^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0989391^2 + 208080806000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1010609^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0989391^2 + 20808080806000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1010609^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0989391^2 + 2080808080806000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1010609^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0989391^2 + 208080808080806000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1010609^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0989391^2 + 20808080808080806000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1010609^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0989391^2 + 2080808080808080806000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1010609^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 104)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0989184^2 + 208000^2 && := 1010816^2 \\
 &1020\ 0989184^2 + 21008000^2 && := 1020\ 1010816^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0989184^2 + 2101008000^2 && := 10203020\ 1010816^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0989184^2 + 210101008000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1010816^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0989184^2 + 21010101008000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1010816^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0989184^2 + 2101010101008000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1010816^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0989184^2 + 210101010101008000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1010816^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0989184^2 + 21010101010101008000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1010816^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0989184^2 + 2101010101010101008000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1010816^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 105)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0988975^2 + 210000^2 && := 1011025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0988975^2 + 21210000^2 && := 1020\ 1011025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0988975^2 + 2121210000^2 && := 10203020\ 1011025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0988975^2 + 212121210000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1011025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0988975^2 + 21212121210000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1011025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0988975^2 + 2121212121210000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1011025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0988975^2 + 212121212121210000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1011025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0988975^2 + 21212121212121210000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1011025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0988975^2 + 21212121212121210000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1011025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 106)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0988764^2 + 212000^2 && := 1011236^2 \\
 &1020\ 0988764^2 + 21412000^2 && := 1020\ 1011236^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0988764^2 + 2141412000^2 && := 10203020\ 1011236^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0988764^2 + 214141412000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1011236^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0988764^2 + 21414141412000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1011236^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0988764^2 + 2141414141412000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1011236^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0988764^2 + 214141414141412000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1011236^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0988764^2 + 21414141414141412000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1011236^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0988764^2 + 21414141414141412000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1011236^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 107)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0988551^2 + 214000^2 && := 1011449^2 \\
 &1020\ 0988551^2 + 21614000^2 && := 1020\ 1011449^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0988551^2 + 2161614000^2 && := 10203020\ 1011449^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0988551^2 + 216161614000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1011449^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0988551^2 + 21616161614000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1011449^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0988551^2 + 2161616161614000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1011449^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0988551^2 + 216161616161614000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1011449^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0988551^2 + 21616161616161614000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1011449^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0988551^2 + 2161616161616161614000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1011449^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 108)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0988336^2 + 216000^2 && := 1011664^2 \\
 &1020\ 0988336^2 + 21816000^2 && := 1020\ 1011664^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0988336^2 + 2181816000^2 && := 10203020\ 1011664^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0988336^2 + 218181816000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1011664^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0988336^2 + 21818181816000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1011664^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0988336^2 + 2181818181816000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1011664^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0988336^2 + 218181818181816000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1011664^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0988336^2 + 21818181818181816000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1011664^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0988336^2 + 2181818181818181816000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1011664^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 109)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0988119^2 + 218000^2 && := 1011881^2 \\
 &1020\ 0988119^2 + 22018000^2 && := 1020\ 1011881^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0988119^2 + 2202018000^2 && := 10203020\ 1011881^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0988119^2 + 220202018000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1011881^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0988119^2 + 22020202018000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1011881^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0988119^2 + 2202020202018000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1011881^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0988119^2 + 220202020202018000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1011881^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0988119^2 + 22020202020202018000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1011881^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0988119^2 + 2202020202020202018000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1011881^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 110)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0987900^2 + 220000^2 && := 1012100^2 \\
 &1020\ 0987900^2 + 22220000^2 && := 1020\ 1012100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0987900^2 + 2222220000^2 && := 10203020\ 1012100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0987900^2 + 22222220000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1012100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0987900^2 + 222222220000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1012100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0987900^2 + 2222222220000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1012100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0987900^2 + 22222222220000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1012100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0987900^2 + 222222222220000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1012100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0987900^2 + 2222222222220000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1012100^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 111)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0987679^2 + 222000^2 && := 1012321^2 \\
 &1020\ 0987679^2 + 22422000^2 && := 1020\ 1012321^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0987679^2 + 2242422000^2 && := 10203020\ 1012321^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0987679^2 + 224242422000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1012321^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0987679^2 + 22424242422000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1012321^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0987679^2 + 2242424242422000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1012321^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0987679^2 + 224242424242422000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1012321^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0987679^2 + 22424242424242422000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1012321^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0987679^2 + 2242424242424242422000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1012321^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 112)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0987456^2 + 224000^2 && := 1012544^2 \\
 &1020\ 0987456^2 + 22624000^2 && := 1020\ 1012544^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0987456^2 + 2262624000^2 && := 10203020\ 1012544^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0987456^2 + 226262624000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1012544^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0987456^2 + 22626262624000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1012544^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0987456^2 + 2262626262624000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1012544^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0987456^2 + 226262626262624000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1012544^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0987456^2 + 22626262626262624000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1012544^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0987456^2 + 22626262626262624000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1012544^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 113)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0987231^2 + 226000^2 && := 1012769^2 \\
 &1020\ 0987231^2 + 22826000^2 && := 1020\ 1012769^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0987231^2 + 2282826000^2 && := 10203020\ 1012769^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0987231^2 + 228282826000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1012769^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0987231^2 + 22828282826000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1012769^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0987231^2 + 2282828282826000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1012769^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0987231^2 + 228282828282826000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1012769^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0987231^2 + 22828282828282826000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1012769^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0987231^2 + 22828282828282826000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1012769^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 114)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0987004^2 + 228000^2 && := 1012996^2 \\
 &1020\ 0987004^2 + 23028000^2 && := 1020\ 1012996^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0987004^2 + 2303028000^2 && := 10203020\ 1012996^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0987004^2 + 230303028000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1012996^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0987004^2 + 23030303028000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1012996^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0987004^2 + 2303030303028000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1012996^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0987004^2 + 230303030303028000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1012996^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0987004^2 + 23030303030303028000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1012996^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0987004^2 + 23030303030303028000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1012996^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 115)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0986775^2 + 230000^2 && := 1013225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0986775^2 + 23230000^2 && := 1020\ 1013225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0986775^2 + 2323230000^2 && := 10203020\ 1013225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0986775^2 + 232323230000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1013225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0986775^2 + 23232323230000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1013225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0986775^2 + 2323232323230000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1013225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0986775^2 + 232323232323230000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1013225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0986775^2 + 23232323232323230000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1013225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0986775^2 + 2323232323232323230000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1013225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 116)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0986544^2 + 232000^2 && := 1013456^2 \\
 &1020\ 0986544^2 + 23432000^2 && := 1020\ 1013456^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0986544^2 + 2343432000^2 && := 10203020\ 1013456^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0986544^2 + 234343432000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1013456^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0986544^2 + 23434343432000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1013456^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0986544^2 + 2343434343432000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1013456^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0986544^2 + 234343434343432000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1013456^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0986544^2 + 23434343434343432000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1013456^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0986544^2 + 2343434343434343432000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1013456^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 117)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0986311^2 + 234000^2 && := 1013689^2 \\
 &1020\ 0986311^2 + 23634000^2 && := 1020\ 1013689^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0986311^2 + 2363634000^2 && := 10203020\ 1013689^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0986311^2 + 236363634000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1013689^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0986311^2 + 23636363634000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1013689^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0986311^2 + 2363636363634000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1013689^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0986311^2 + 236363636363634000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1013689^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0986311^2 + 23636363636363634000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1013689^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0986311^2 + 2363636363636363634000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1013689^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 118)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0986076^2 + 236000^2 && := 1013924^2 \\
 &1020\ 0986076^2 + 23836000^2 && := 1020\ 1013924^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0986076^2 + 2383836000^2 && := 10203020\ 1013924^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0986076^2 + 238383836000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1013924^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0986076^2 + 23838383836000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1013924^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0986076^2 + 2383838383836000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1013924^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0986076^2 + 238383838383836000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1013924^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0986076^2 + 23838383838383836000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1013924^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0986076^2 + 23838383838383836000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1013924^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 119)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0985839^2 + 238000^2 && := 1014161^2 \\
 &1020\ 0985839^2 + 24038000^2 && := 1020\ 1014161^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0985839^2 + 2404038000^2 && := 10203020\ 1014161^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0985839^2 + 240404038000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1014161^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0985839^2 + 24040404038000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1014161^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0985839^2 + 2404040404038000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1014161^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0985839^2 + 240404040404038000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1014161^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0985839^2 + 24040404040404038000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1014161^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0985839^2 + 2404040404040404038000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1014161^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 120)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0985600^2 + 240000^2 && := 1014400^2 \\
 &1020\ 0985600^2 + 24240000^2 && := 1020\ 1014400^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0985600^2 + 2424240000^2 && := 10203020\ 1014400^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0985600^2 + 242424240000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1014400^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0985600^2 + 24242424240000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1014400^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0985600^2 + 2424242424240000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1014400^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0985600^2 + 242424242424240000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1014400^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0985600^2 + 24242424242424240000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1014400^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0985600^2 + 2424242424242424240000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1014400^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 121)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0985359^2 + 242000^2 && := 1014641^2 \\
 &1020\ 0985359^2 + 24442000^2 && := 1020\ 1014641^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0985359^2 + 2444442000^2 && := 10203020\ 1014641^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0985359^2 + 244444442000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1014641^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0985359^2 + 24444444442000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1014641^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0985359^2 + 2444444444442000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1014641^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0985359^2 + 244444444444442000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1014641^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0985359^2 + 24444444444444442000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1014641^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0985359^2 + 2444444444444444442000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1014641^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 122)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0985116^2 + 244000^2 && := 1014884^2 \\
 &1020\ 0985116^2 + 24644000^2 && := 1020\ 1014884^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0985116^2 + 2464644000^2 && := 10203020\ 1014884^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0985116^2 + 246464644000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1014884^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0985116^2 + 24646464644000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1014884^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0985116^2 + 2464646464644000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1014884^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0985116^2 + 246464646464644000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1014884^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0985116^2 + 24646464646464644000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1014884^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0985116^2 + 24646464646464644000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1014884^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 123)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0984871^2 + 246000^2 && := 1015129^2 \\
 &1020\ 0984871^2 + 24846000^2 && := 1020\ 1015129^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0984871^2 + 2484846000^2 && := 10203020\ 1015129^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0984871^2 + 248484846000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1015129^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0984871^2 + 24848484846000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1015129^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0984871^2 + 2484848484846000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1015129^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0984871^2 + 248484848484846000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1015129^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0984871^2 + 24848484848484846000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1015129^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0984871^2 + 2484848484848484846000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1015129^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 124)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0984624^2 + 248000^2 && := 1015376^2 \\
 &1020\ 0984624^2 + 25048000^2 && := 1020\ 1015376^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0984624^2 + 2505048000^2 && := 10203020\ 1015376^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0984624^2 + 250505048000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1015376^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0984624^2 + 25050505048000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1015376^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0984624^2 + 2505050505048000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1015376^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0984624^2 + 250505050505048000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1015376^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0984624^2 + 25050505050505048000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1015376^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0984624^2 + 2505050505050505048000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1015376^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 125)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0984375^2 + 250000^2 && := 1015625^2 \\
 &1020\ 0984375^2 + 25250000^2 && := 1020\ 1015625^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0984375^2 + 2525250000^2 && := 10203020\ 1015625^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0984375^2 + 252525250000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1015625^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0984375^2 + 25252525250000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1015625^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0984375^2 + 2525252525250000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1015625^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0984375^2 + 252525252525250000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1015625^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0984375^2 + 25252525252525250000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1015625^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0984375^2 + 2525252525252525250000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1015625^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 126)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0984124^2 + 252000^2 && := 1015876^2 \\
 &1020\ 0984124^2 + 25452000^2 && := 1020\ 1015876^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0984124^2 + 2545452000^2 && := 10203020\ 1015876^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0984124^2 + 254545452000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1015876^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0984124^2 + 25454545452000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1015876^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0984124^2 + 2545454545452000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1015876^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0984124^2 + 254545454545452000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1015876^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0984124^2 + 25454545454545452000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1015876^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0984124^2 + 2545454545454545452000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1015876^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 127)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0983871^2 + 254000^2 && := 1016129^2 \\
 &1020\ 0983871^2 + 25654000^2 && := 1020\ 1016129^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0983871^2 + 2565654000^2 && := 10203020\ 1016129^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0983871^2 + 256565654000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1016129^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0983871^2 + 25656565654000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1016129^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0983871^2 + 2565656565654000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1016129^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0983871^2 + 256565656565654000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1016129^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0983871^2 + 25656565656565654000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1016129^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0983871^2 + 2565656565656565654000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1016129^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 128)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0983616^2 + 256000^2 && := 1016384^2 \\
 &1020\ 0983616^2 + 25856000^2 && := 1020\ 1016384^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0983616^2 + 2585856000^2 && := 10203020\ 1016384^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0983616^2 + 258585856000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1016384^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0983616^2 + 25858585856000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1016384^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0983616^2 + 2585858585856000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1016384^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0983616^2 + 258585858585856000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1016384^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0983616^2 + 25858585858585856000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1016384^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0983616^2 + 2585858585858585856000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1016384^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 129)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0983359^2 + 258000^2 && := 1016641^2 \\
 &1020\ 0983359^2 + 26058000^2 && := 1020\ 1016641^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0983359^2 + 2606058000^2 && := 10203020\ 1016641^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0983359^2 + 260606058000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1016641^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0983359^2 + 26060606058000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1016641^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0983359^2 + 2606060606058000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1016641^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0983359^2 + 260606060606058000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1016641^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0983359^2 + 26060606060606058000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1016641^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0983359^2 + 2606060606060606058000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1016641^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 130)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0983100^2 + 260000^2 && := 1016900^2 \\
 &1020\ 0983100^2 + 26260000^2 && := 1020\ 1016900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0983100^2 + 2626260000^2 && := 10203020\ 1016900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0983100^2 + 262626260000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1016900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0983100^2 + 26262626260000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1016900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0983100^2 + 2626262626260000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1016900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0983100^2 + 262626262626260000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1016900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0983100^2 + 26262626262626260000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1016900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0983100^2 + 26262626262626260000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1016900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 131)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0982839^2 + 262000^2 && := 1017161^2 \\
 &1020\ 0982839^2 + 26462000^2 && := 1020\ 1017161^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0982839^2 + 2646462000^2 && := 10203020\ 1017161^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0982839^2 + 264646462000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1017161^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0982839^2 + 26464646462000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1017161^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0982839^2 + 2646464646462000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1017161^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0982839^2 + 264646464646462000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1017161^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0982839^2 + 26464646464646462000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1017161^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0982839^2 + 2646464646464646462000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1017161^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 132)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0982576^2 + 264000^2 && := 1017424^2 \\
 &1020\ 0982576^2 + 26664000^2 && := 1020\ 1017424^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0982576^2 + 2666664000^2 && := 10203020\ 1017424^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0982576^2 + 266666664000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1017424^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0982576^2 + 26666666664000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1017424^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0982576^2 + 2666666666664000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1017424^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0982576^2 + 266666666666664000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1017424^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0982576^2 + 26666666666666664000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1017424^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0982576^2 + 2666666666666666664000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1017424^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 133)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0982311^2 + 266000^2 && := 1017689^2 \\
 &1020\ 0982311^2 + 26866000^2 && := 1020\ 1017689^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0982311^2 + 2686866000^2 && := 10203020\ 1017689^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0982311^2 + 268686866000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1017689^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0982311^2 + 26868686866000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1017689^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0982311^2 + 2686868686866000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1017689^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0982311^2 + 268686868686866000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1017689^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0982311^2 + 26868686868686866000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1017689^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0982311^2 + 26868686868686866000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1017689^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 134)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0982044^2 + 268000^2 && := 1017956^2 \\
 &1020\ 0982044^2 + 27068000^2 && := 1020\ 1017956^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0982044^2 + 2707068000^2 && := 10203020\ 1017956^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0982044^2 + 270707068000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1017956^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0982044^2 + 27070707068000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1017956^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0982044^2 + 2707070707068000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1017956^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0982044^2 + 270707070707068000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1017956^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0982044^2 + 27070707070707068000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1017956^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0982044^2 + 27070707070707068000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1017956^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 135)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0981775^2 + 270000^2 && := 1018225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0981775^2 + 27270000^2 && := 1020\ 1018225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0981775^2 + 2727270000^2 && := 10203020\ 1018225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0981775^2 + 272727270000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1018225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0981775^2 + 27272727270000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1018225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0981775^2 + 2727272727270000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1018225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0981775^2 + 272727272727270000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1018225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0981775^2 + 27272727272727270000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1018225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0981775^2 + 2727272727272727270000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1018225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 136)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0981504^2 + 272000^2 && := 1018496^2 \\
 &1020\ 0981504^2 + 27472000^2 && := 1020\ 1018496^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0981504^2 + 2747472000^2 && := 10203020\ 1018496^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0981504^2 + 274747472000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1018496^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0981504^2 + 27474747472000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1018496^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0981504^2 + 2747474747472000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1018496^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0981504^2 + 274747474747472000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1018496^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0981504^2 + 27474747474747472000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1018496^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0981504^2 + 2747474747474747472000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1018496^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 137)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0981231^2 + 274000^2 && := 1018769^2 \\
 &1020\ 0981231^2 + 27674000^2 && := 1020\ 1018769^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0981231^2 + 2767674000^2 && := 10203020\ 1018769^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0981231^2 + 276767674000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1018769^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0981231^2 + 27676767674000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1018769^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0981231^2 + 2767676767674000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1018769^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0981231^2 + 276767676767674000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1018769^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0981231^2 + 27676767676767674000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1018769^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0981231^2 + 2767676767676767674000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1018769^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 138)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0980956^2 + 276000^2 && := 1019044^2 \\
 &1020\ 0980956^2 + 27876000^2 && := 1020\ 1019044^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0980956^2 + 2787876000^2 && := 10203020\ 1019044^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0980956^2 + 278787876000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1019044^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0980956^2 + 27878787876000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1019044^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0980956^2 + 2787878787876000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1019044^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0980956^2 + 278787878787876000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1019044^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0980956^2 + 27878787878787876000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1019044^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0980956^2 + 2787878787878787876000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1019044^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 139)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0980679^2 + 278000^2 && := 1019321^2 \\
 &1020\ 0980679^2 + 28078000^2 && := 1020\ 1019321^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0980679^2 + 2808078000^2 && := 10203020\ 1019321^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0980679^2 + 280808078000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1019321^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0980679^2 + 28080808078000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1019321^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0980679^2 + 2808080808078000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1019321^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0980679^2 + 280808080808078000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1019321^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0980679^2 + 28080808080808078000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1019321^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0980679^2 + 2808080808080808078000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1019321^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 140)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0980400^2 + 280000^2 && := 1019600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0980400^2 + 28280000^2 && := 1020\ 1019600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0980400^2 + 2828280000^2 && := 10203020\ 1019600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0980400^2 + 282828280000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1019600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0980400^2 + 28282828280000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1019600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0980400^2 + 2828282828280000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1019600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0980400^2 + 282828282828280000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1019600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0980400^2 + 28282828282828280000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1019600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0980400^2 + 2828282828282828280000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1019600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 141)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0980119^2 + 282000^2 && := 1019881^2 \\
 &1020\ 0980119^2 + 28482000^2 && := 1020\ 1019881^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0980119^2 + 2848482000^2 && := 10203020\ 1019881^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0980119^2 + 284848482000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1019881^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0980119^2 + 28484848482000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1019881^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0980119^2 + 2848484848482000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1019881^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0980119^2 + 284848484848482000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1019881^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0980119^2 + 28484848484848482000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1019881^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0980119^2 + 2848484848484848482000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1019881^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 142)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0979836^2 + 284000^2 && := 1020164^2 \\
 &1020\ 0979836^2 + 28684000^2 && := 1020\ 1020164^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0979836^2 + 2868684000^2 && := 10203020\ 1020164^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0979836^2 + 286868684000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1020164^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0979836^2 + 28686868684000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1020164^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0979836^2 + 2868686868684000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1020164^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0979836^2 + 286868686868684000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1020164^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0979836^2 + 28686868686868684000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1020164^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0979836^2 + 2868686868686868684000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1020164^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 143)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0979551^2 + 286000^2 && := 1020449^2 \\
 &1020\ 0979551^2 + 28886000^2 && := 1020\ 1020449^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0979551^2 + 2888886000^2 && := 10203020\ 1020449^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0979551^2 + 288888886000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1020449^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0979551^2 + 28888888886000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1020449^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0979551^2 + 2888888888886000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1020449^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0979551^2 + 288888888888886000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1020449^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0979551^2 + 28888888888888886000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1020449^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0979551^2 + 2888888888888888886000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1020449^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 144)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0979264^2 + 288000^2 && := 1020736^2 \\
 &1020\ 0979264^2 + 29088000^2 && := 1020\ 1020736^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0979264^2 + 2909088000^2 && := 10203020\ 1020736^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0979264^2 + 290909088000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1020736^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0979264^2 + 29090909088000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1020736^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0979264^2 + 2909090909088000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1020736^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0979264^2 + 290909090909088000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1020736^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0979264^2 + 29090909090909088000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1020736^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0979264^2 + 2909090909090909088000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1020736^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 145)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0978975^2 + 290000^2 && := 1021025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0978975^2 + 29290000^2 && := 1020\ 1021025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0978975^2 + 2929290000^2 && := 10203020\ 1021025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0978975^2 + 292929290000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1021025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0978975^2 + 29292929290000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1021025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0978975^2 + 2929292929290000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1021025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0978975^2 + 292929292929290000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1021025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0978975^2 + 29292929292929290000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1021025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0978975^2 + 2929292929292929290000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1021025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 146)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0978684^2 + 292000^2 && := 1021316^2 \\
 &1020\ 0978684^2 + 29492000^2 && := 1020\ 1021316^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0978684^2 + 2949492000^2 && := 10203020\ 1021316^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0978684^2 + 294949492000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1021316^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0978684^2 + 29494949492000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1021316^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0978684^2 + 2949494949492000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1021316^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0978684^2 + 294949494949492000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1021316^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0978684^2 + 29494949494949492000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1021316^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0978684^2 + 2949494949494949492000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1021316^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 147)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0978391^2 + 294000^2 && := 1021609^2 \\
 &1020\ 0978391^2 + 29694000^2 && := 1020\ 1021609^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0978391^2 + 2969694000^2 && := 10203020\ 1021609^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0978391^2 + 296969694000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1021609^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0978391^2 + 29696969694000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1021609^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0978391^2 + 2969696969694000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1021609^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0978391^2 + 296969696969694000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1021609^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0978391^2 + 29696969696969694000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1021609^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0978391^2 + 2969696969696969694000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1021609^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 148)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0978096^2 + 296000^2 && := 1021904^2 \\
 &1020\ 0978096^2 + 29896000^2 && := 1020\ 1021904^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0978096^2 + 2989896000^2 && := 10203020\ 1021904^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0978096^2 + 298989896000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1021904^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0978096^2 + 29898989896000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1021904^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0978096^2 + 2989898989896000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1021904^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0978096^2 + 298989898989896000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1021904^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0978096^2 + 29898989898989896000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1021904^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0978096^2 + 2989898989898989896000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1021904^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 149)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0977799^2 + 298000^2 && := 1022201^2 \\
 &1020\ 0977799^2 + 30098000^2 && := 1020\ 1022201^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0977799^2 + 3010098000^2 && := 10203020\ 1022201^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0977799^2 + 301010098000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1022201^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0977799^2 + 30101010098000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1022201^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0977799^2 + 3010101010098000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1022201^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0977799^2 + 301010101010098000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1022201^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0977799^2 + 30101010101010098000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1022201^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0977799^2 + 30101010101010098000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1022201^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 150)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0977500^2 + 300000^2 && := 1022500^2 \\
 &1020\ 0977500^2 + 30300000^2 && := 1020\ 1022500^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0977500^2 + 3030300000^2 && := 10203020\ 1022500^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0977500^2 + 303030300000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1022500^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0977500^2 + 30303030300000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1022500^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0977500^2 + 3030303030300000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1022500^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0977500^2 + 303030303030300000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1022500^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0977500^2 + 30303030303030300000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1022500^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0977500^2 + 30303030303030300000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1022500^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 151)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0977199^2 + 302000^2 && := 1022801^2 \\
 &1020\ 0977199^2 + 30502000^2 && := 1020\ 1022801^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0977199^2 + 3050502000^2 && := 10203020\ 1022801^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0977199^2 + 305050502000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1022801^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0977199^2 + 30505050502000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1022801^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0977199^2 + 3050505050502000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1022801^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0977199^2 + 305050505050502000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1022801^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0977199^2 + 30505050505050502000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1022801^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0977199^2 + 3050505050505050502000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1022801^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 152)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0976896^2 + 304000^2 && := 1023104^2 \\
 &1020\ 0976896^2 + 30704000^2 && := 1020\ 1023104^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0976896^2 + 3070704000^2 && := 10203020\ 1023104^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0976896^2 + 307070704000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1023104^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0976896^2 + 30707070704000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1023104^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0976896^2 + 3070707070704000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1023104^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0976896^2 + 307070707070704000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1023104^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0976896^2 + 30707070707070704000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1023104^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0976896^2 + 3070707070707070704000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1023104^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 153)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0976591^2 + 306000^2 && := 1023409^2 \\
 &1020\ 0976591^2 + 30906000^2 && := 1020\ 1023409^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0976591^2 + 3090906000^2 && := 10203020\ 1023409^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0976591^2 + 309090906000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1023409^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0976591^2 + 30909090906000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1023409^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0976591^2 + 3090909090906000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1023409^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0976591^2 + 309090909090906000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1023409^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0976591^2 + 30909090909090906000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1023409^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0976591^2 + 3090909090909090906000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1023409^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 154)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0976284^2 + 308000^2 && := 1023716^2 \\
 &1020\ 0976284^2 + 31108000^2 && := 1020\ 1023716^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0976284^2 + 3111108000^2 && := 10203020\ 1023716^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0976284^2 + 311111108000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1023716^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0976284^2 + 31111111108000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1023716^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0976284^2 + 3111111111108000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1023716^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0976284^2 + 311111111111108000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1023716^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0976284^2 + 31111111111111108000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1023716^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0976284^2 + 3111111111111111108000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1023716^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 155)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0975975^2 + 310000^2$ | $:= 1024025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0975975^2 + 31310000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1024025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0975975^2 + 3131310000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1024025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0975975^2 + 313131310000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1024025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0975975^2 + 31313131310000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1024025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0975975^2 + 3131313131310000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1024025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0975975^2 + 313131313131310000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1024025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0975975^2 + 31313131313131310000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1024025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0975975^2 + 3131313131313131310000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1024025^2$ |
- 156)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0975664^2 + 312000^2$ | $:= 1024336^2$ |
| $1020\ 0975664^2 + 31512000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1024336^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0975664^2 + 3151512000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1024336^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0975664^2 + 315151512000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1024336^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0975664^2 + 31515151512000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1024336^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0975664^2 + 3151515151512000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1024336^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0975664^2 + 315151515151512000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1024336^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0975664^2 + 31515151515151512000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1024336^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0975664^2 + 3151515151515151512000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1024336^2$ |
- 157)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0975351^2 + 314000^2$ | $:= 1024649^2$ |
| $1020\ 0975351^2 + 31714000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1024649^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0975351^2 + 3171714000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1024649^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0975351^2 + 317171714000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1024649^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0975351^2 + 31717171714000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1024649^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0975351^2 + 3171717171714000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1024649^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0975351^2 + 317171717171714000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1024649^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0975351^2 + 31717171717171714000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1024649^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0975351^2 + 3171717171717171714000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1024649^2$ |
- 158)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0975036^2 + 316000^2$ | $:= 1024964^2$ |
| $1020\ 0975036^2 + 31916000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1024964^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0975036^2 + 3191916000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1024964^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0975036^2 + 319191916000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1024964^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0975036^2 + 31919191916000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1024964^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0975036^2 + 3191919191916000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1024964^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0975036^2 + 319191919191916000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1024964^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0975036^2 + 31919191919191916000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1024964^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0975036^2 + 3191919191919191916000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1024964^2$ |

- 159)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0974719^2 + 318000^2 && := 1025281^2 \\
 &1020\ 0974719^2 + 32118000^2 && := 1020\ 1025281^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0974719^2 + 3212118000^2 && := 10203020\ 1025281^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0974719^2 + 321212118000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1025281^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0974719^2 + 32121212118000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1025281^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0974719^2 + 3212121212118000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1025281^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0974719^2 + 321212121212118000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1025281^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0974719^2 + 32121212121212118000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1025281^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0974719^2 + 3212121212121212118000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1025281^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 160)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0974400^2 + 320000^2 && := 1025600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0974400^2 + 32320000^2 && := 1020\ 1025600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0974400^2 + 3232320000^2 && := 10203020\ 1025600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0974400^2 + 323232320000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1025600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0974400^2 + 32323232320000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1025600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0974400^2 + 3232323232320000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1025600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0974400^2 + 323232323232320000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1025600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0974400^2 + 32323232323232320000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1025600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0974400^2 + 3232323232323232320000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1025600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 161)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0974079^2 + 322000^2 && := 1025921^2 \\
 &1020\ 0974079^2 + 32522000^2 && := 1020\ 1025921^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0974079^2 + 3252522000^2 && := 10203020\ 1025921^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0974079^2 + 325252522000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1025921^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0974079^2 + 32525252522000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1025921^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0974079^2 + 3252525252522000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1025921^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0974079^2 + 325252525252522000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1025921^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0974079^2 + 325252525252522000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1025921^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0974079^2 + 32525252525252522000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1025921^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 162)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0973756^2 + 324000^2 && := 1026244^2 \\
 &1020\ 0973756^2 + 32724000^2 && := 1020\ 1026244^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0973756^2 + 3272724000^2 && := 10203020\ 1026244^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0973756^2 + 327272724000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1026244^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0973756^2 + 32727272724000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1026244^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0973756^2 + 3272727272724000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1026244^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0973756^2 + 327272727272724000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1026244^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0973756^2 + 32727272727272724000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1026244^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0973756^2 + 32727272727272724000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1026244^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 163)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0973431^2 + 326000^2 && := 1026569^2 \\
 &1020\ 0973431^2 + 32926000^2 && := 1020\ 1026569^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0973431^2 + 3292926000^2 && := 10203020\ 1026569^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0973431^2 + 329292926000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1026569^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0973431^2 + 32929292926000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1026569^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0973431^2 + 3292929292926000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1026569^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0973431^2 + 329292929292926000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1026569^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0973431^2 + 32929292929292926000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1026569^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0973431^2 + 3292929292929292926000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1026569^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 164)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0973104^2 + 328000^2 && := 1026896^2 \\
 &1020\ 0973104^2 + 33128000^2 && := 1020\ 1026896^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0973104^2 + 3313128000^2 && := 10203020\ 1026896^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0973104^2 + 331313128000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1026896^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0973104^2 + 33131313128000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1026896^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0973104^2 + 3313131313128000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1026896^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0973104^2 + 331313131313128000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1026896^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0973104^2 + 33131313131313128000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1026896^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0973104^2 + 3313131313131313128000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1026896^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 165)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0972775^2 + 330000^2 && := 1027225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0972775^2 + 33330000^2 && := 1020\ 1027225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0972775^2 + 3333330000^2 && := 10203020\ 1027225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0972775^2 + 333333330000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1027225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0972775^2 + 33333333330000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1027225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0972775^2 + 3333333333330000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1027225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0972775^2 + 333333333333330000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1027225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0972775^2 + 33333333333333330000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1027225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0972775^2 + 3333333333333333330000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1027225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 166)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0972444^2 + 332000^2 && := 1027556^2 \\
 &1020\ 0972444^2 + 33532000^2 && := 1020\ 1027556^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0972444^2 + 3353532000^2 && := 10203020\ 1027556^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0972444^2 + 335353532000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1027556^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0972444^2 + 33535353532000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1027556^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0972444^2 + 3353535353532000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1027556^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0972444^2 + 335353535353532000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1027556^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0972444^2 + 33535353535353532000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1027556^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0972444^2 + 3353535353535353532000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1027556^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 167)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0972111^2 + 334000^2 && := 1027889^2 \\
 &1020\ 0972111^2 + 33734000^2 && := 1020\ 1027889^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0972111^2 + 3373734000^2 && := 10203020\ 1027889^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0972111^2 + 337373734000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1027889^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0972111^2 + 33737373734000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1027889^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0972111^2 + 3373737373734000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1027889^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0972111^2 + 337373737373734000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1027889^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0972111^2 + 33737373737373734000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1027889^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0972111^2 + 3373737373737373734000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1027889^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 168)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0971776^2 + 336000^2 && := 1028224^2 \\
 &1020\ 0971776^2 + 33936000^2 && := 1020\ 1028224^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0971776^2 + 3393936000^2 && := 10203020\ 1028224^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0971776^2 + 339393936000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1028224^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0971776^2 + 33939393936000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1028224^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0971776^2 + 3393939393936000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1028224^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0971776^2 + 339393939393936000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1028224^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0971776^2 + 33939393939393936000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1028224^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0971776^2 + 3393939393939393936000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1028224^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 169)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0971439^2 + 338000^2 && := 1028561^2 \\
 &1020\ 0971439^2 + 34138000^2 && := 1020\ 1028561^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0971439^2 + 3414138000^2 && := 10203020\ 1028561^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0971439^2 + 341414138000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1028561^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0971439^2 + 34141414138000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1028561^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0971439^2 + 3414141414138000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1028561^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0971439^2 + 341414141414138000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1028561^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0971439^2 + 34141414141414138000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1028561^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0971439^2 + 3414141414141414138000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1028561^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 170)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0971100^2 + 340000^2 && := 1028900^2 \\
 &1020\ 0971100^2 + 34340000^2 && := 1020\ 1028900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0971100^2 + 3434340000^2 && := 10203020\ 1028900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0971100^2 + 343434340000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1028900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0971100^2 + 34343434340000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1028900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0971100^2 + 3434343434340000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1028900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0971100^2 + 343434343434340000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1028900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0971100^2 + 34343434343434340000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1028900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0971100^2 + 34343434343434340000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1028900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 171)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0970759^2 + 342000^2 && := 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0970759^2 + 34542000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0970759^2 + 3454542000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0970759^2 + 345454542000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0970759^2 + 34545454542000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0970759^2 + 3454545454542000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0970759^2 + 345454545454542000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0970759^2 + 345454545454542000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1029241^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0970759^2 + 34545454545454542000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1029241^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 172)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0970416^2 + 344000^2 && := 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0970416^2 + 34744000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0970416^2 + 3474744000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0970416^2 + 347474744000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0970416^2 + 34747474744000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0970416^2 + 3474747474744000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0970416^2 + 347474747474744000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0970416^2 + 347474747474744000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1029584^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0970416^2 + 34747474747474744000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1029584^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 173)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0970071^2 + 346000^2 && := 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0970071^2 + 34946000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0970071^2 + 3494946000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0970071^2 + 349494946000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0970071^2 + 34949494946000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0970071^2 + 3494949494946000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0970071^2 + 349494949494946000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0970071^2 + 349494949494946000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1029929^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0970071^2 + 34949494949494946000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1029929^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 174)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0969724^2 + 348000^2 && := 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0969724^2 + 35148000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0969724^2 + 3515148000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0969724^2 + 351515148000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0969724^2 + 35151515148000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0969724^2 + 3515151515148000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0969724^2 + 351515151515148000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0969724^2 + 35151515151515148000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1030276^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0969724^2 + 3515151515151515148000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1030276^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 175)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0969375^2 + 350000^2$ | $:= 1030625^2$ |
| $1020\ 0969375^2 + 35350000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1030625^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0969375^2 + 3535350000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1030625^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0969375^2 + 353535350000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1030625^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0969375^2 + 35353535350000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1030625^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0969375^2 + 3535353535350000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1030625^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0969375^2 + 353535353535350000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1030625^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0969375^2 + 35353535353535350000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1030625^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0969375^2 + 3535353535353535350000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1030625^2$ |
- 176)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0969024^2 + 352000^2$ | $:= 1030976^2$ |
| $1020\ 0969024^2 + 35552000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1030976^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0969024^2 + 3555552000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1030976^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0969024^2 + 35555552000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1030976^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0969024^2 + 3555555552000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1030976^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0969024^2 + 355555555552000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1030976^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0969024^2 + 35555555555552000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1030976^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0969024^2 + 3555555555555552000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1030976^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0969024^2 + 355555555555555552000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1030976^2$ |
- 177)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0968671^2 + 354000^2$ | $:= 1031329^2$ |
| $1020\ 0968671^2 + 35754000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1031329^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0968671^2 + 3575754000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1031329^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0968671^2 + 357575754000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1031329^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0968671^2 + 35757575754000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1031329^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0968671^2 + 3575757575754000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1031329^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0968671^2 + 357575757575754000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1031329^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0968671^2 + 35757575757575754000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1031329^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0968671^2 + 3575757575757575754000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1031329^2$ |
- 178)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0968316^2 + 356000^2$ | $:= 1031684^2$ |
| $1020\ 0968316^2 + 35956000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1031684^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0968316^2 + 3595956000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1031684^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0968316^2 + 359595956000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1031684^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0968316^2 + 35959595956000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1031684^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0968316^2 + 3595959595956000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1031684^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0968316^2 + 359595959595956000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1031684^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0968316^2 + 35959595959595956000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1031684^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0968316^2 + 3595959595959595956000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1031684^2$ |

- 179)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0967959^2 + 358000^2 && := 1032041^2 \\
 &1020\ 0967959^2 + 36158000^2 && := 1020\ 1032041^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0967959^2 + 3616158000^2 && := 10203020\ 1032041^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0967959^2 + 361616158000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1032041^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0967959^2 + 36161616158000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1032041^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0967959^2 + 3616161616158000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1032041^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0967959^2 + 361616161616158000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1032041^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0967959^2 + 36161616161616158000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1032041^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0967959^2 + 3616161616161616158000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1032041^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 180)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0967600^2 + 360000^2 && := 1032400^2 \\
 &1020\ 0967600^2 + 36360000^2 && := 1020\ 1032400^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0967600^2 + 3636360000^2 && := 10203020\ 1032400^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0967600^2 + 363636360000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1032400^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0967600^2 + 36363636360000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1032400^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0967600^2 + 3636363636360000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1032400^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0967600^2 + 363636363636360000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1032400^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0967600^2 + 36363636363636360000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1032400^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0967600^2 + 3636363636363636360000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1032400^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 181)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0967239^2 + 362000^2 && := 1032761^2 \\
 &1020\ 0967239^2 + 36562000^2 && := 1020\ 1032761^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0967239^2 + 3656562000^2 && := 10203020\ 1032761^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0967239^2 + 365656562000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1032761^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0967239^2 + 36565656562000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1032761^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0967239^2 + 3656565656562000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1032761^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0967239^2 + 365656565656562000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1032761^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0967239^2 + 36565656565656562000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1032761^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 182)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0966876^2 + 364000^2 && := 1033124^2 \\
 &1020\ 0966876^2 + 36764000^2 && := 1020\ 1033124^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0966876^2 + 3676764000^2 && := 10203020\ 1033124^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0966876^2 + 367676764000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1033124^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0966876^2 + 36767676764000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1033124^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0966876^2 + 3676767676764000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1033124^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0966876^2 + 367676767676764000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1033124^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0966876^2 + 36767676767676764000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1033124^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0966876^2 + 3676767676767676764000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1033124^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 183)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0966511^2 + 366000^2$ | $:= 1033489^2$ |
| $1020\ 0966511^2 + 36966000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1033489^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0966511^2 + 3696966000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1033489^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0966511^2 + 369696966000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1033489^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0966511^2 + 36969696966000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1033489^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0966511^2 + 3696969696966000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1033489^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0966511^2 + 369696969696966000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1033489^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0966511^2 + 36969696969696966000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1033489^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0966511^2 + 3696969696969696966000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1033489^2$ |
- 184)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0966144^2 + 368000^2$ | $:= 1033856^2$ |
| $1020\ 0966144^2 + 37168000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1033856^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0966144^2 + 3717168000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1033856^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0966144^2 + 371717168000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1033856^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0966144^2 + 37171717168000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1033856^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0966144^2 + 3717171717168000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1033856^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0966144^2 + 371717171717168000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1033856^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0966144^2 + 37171717171717168000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1033856^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0966144^2 + 37171717171717168000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1033856^2$ |
- 185)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0965775^2 + 370000^2$ | $:= 1034225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0965775^2 + 37370000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1034225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0965775^2 + 3737370000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1034225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0965775^2 + 373737370000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1034225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0965775^2 + 37373737370000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1034225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0965775^2 + 3737373737370000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1034225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0965775^2 + 373737373737370000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1034225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0965775^2 + 37373737373737370000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1034225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0965775^2 + 3737373737373737370000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1034225^2$ |
- 186)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0965404^2 + 372000^2$ | $:= 1034596^2$ |
| $1020\ 0965404^2 + 37572000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1034596^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0965404^2 + 3757572000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1034596^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0965404^2 + 375757572000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1034596^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0965404^2 + 37575757572000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1034596^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0965404^2 + 3757575757572000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1034596^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0965404^2 + 375757575757572000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1034596^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0965404^2 + 37575757575757572000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1034596^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0965404^2 + 3757575757575757572000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1034596^2$ |

- 187)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0965031^2 + 374000^2 && := 1034969^2 \\ &1020\ 0965031^2 + 37774000^2 && := 1020\ 1034969^2 \\ &10203020\ 0965031^2 + 3777774000^2 && := 10203020\ 1034969^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0965031^2 + 377777774000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1034969^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0965031^2 + 37777777774000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1034969^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0965031^2 + 3777777777774000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1034969^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0965031^2 + 377777777777774000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1034969^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0965031^2 + 37777777777777774000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1034969^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0965031^2 + 3777777777777777774000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1034969^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 188)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0964656^2 + 376000^2 && := 1035344^2 \\ &1020\ 0964656^2 + 37976000^2 && := 1020\ 1035344^2 \\ &10203020\ 0964656^2 + 3797976000^2 && := 10203020\ 1035344^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0964656^2 + 379797976000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1035344^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0964656^2 + 37979797976000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1035344^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0964656^2 + 3797979797976000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1035344^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0964656^2 + 379797979797976000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1035344^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0964656^2 + 37979797979797976000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1035344^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0964656^2 + 3797979797979797976000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1035344^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 189)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0964279^2 + 378000^2 && := 1035721^2 \\ &1020\ 0964279^2 + 38178000^2 && := 1020\ 1035721^2 \\ &10203020\ 0964279^2 + 3818178000^2 && := 10203020\ 1035721^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0964279^2 + 381818178000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1035721^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0964279^2 + 38181818178000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1035721^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0964279^2 + 3818181818178000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1035721^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0964279^2 + 381818181818178000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1035721^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0964279^2 + 38181818181818178000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1035721^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0964279^2 + 3818181818181818178000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1035721^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 190)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0963900^2 + 380000^2 && := 1036100^2 \\ &1020\ 0963900^2 + 38380000^2 && := 1020\ 1036100^2 \\ &10203020\ 0963900^2 + 3838380000^2 && := 10203020\ 1036100^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0963900^2 + 383838380000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1036100^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0963900^2 + 38383838380000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1036100^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0963900^2 + 3838383838380000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1036100^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0963900^2 + 383838383838380000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1036100^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0963900^2 + 38383838383838380000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1036100^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0963900^2 + 3838383838383838380000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1036100^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 191)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0963519^2 + 382000^2 && := 1036481^2 \\
 &1020\ 0963519^2 + 38582000^2 && := 1020\ 1036481^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0963519^2 + 3858582000^2 && := 10203020\ 1036481^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0963519^2 + 385858582000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1036481^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0963519^2 + 38585858582000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1036481^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0963519^2 + 3858585858582000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1036481^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0963519^2 + 385858585858582000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1036481^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0963519^2 + 38585858585858582000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1036481^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0963519^2 + 3858585858585858582000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1036481^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 192)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0963136^2 + 384000^2 && := 1036864^2 \\
 &1020\ 0963136^2 + 38784000^2 && := 1020\ 1036864^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0963136^2 + 3878784000^2 && := 10203020\ 1036864^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0963136^2 + 387878784000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1036864^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0963136^2 + 38787878784000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1036864^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0963136^2 + 3878787878784000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1036864^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0963136^2 + 387878787878784000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1036864^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0963136^2 + 38787878787878784000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1036864^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0963136^2 + 3878787878787878784000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1036864^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 193)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0962751^2 + 386000^2 && := 1037249^2 \\
 &1020\ 0962751^2 + 38986000^2 && := 1020\ 1037249^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0962751^2 + 3898986000^2 && := 10203020\ 1037249^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0962751^2 + 389898986000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1037249^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0962751^2 + 38989898986000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1037249^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0962751^2 + 3898989898986000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1037249^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0962751^2 + 389898989898986000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1037249^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0962751^2 + 38989898989898986000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1037249^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0962751^2 + 3898989898989898986000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1037249^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 194)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0962364^2 + 388000^2 && := 1037636^2 \\
 &1020\ 0962364^2 + 39188000^2 && := 1020\ 1037636^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0962364^2 + 3919188000^2 && := 10203020\ 1037636^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0962364^2 + 391919188000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1037636^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0962364^2 + 39191919188000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1037636^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0962364^2 + 3919191919188000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1037636^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0962364^2 + 391919191919188000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1037636^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0962364^2 + 39191919191919188000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1037636^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0962364^2 + 3919191919191919188000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1037636^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 195)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0961975^2 + 390000^2$ | $:= 1038025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0961975^2 + 39390000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1038025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0961975^2 + 3939390000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1038025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0961975^2 + 393939390000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1038025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0961975^2 + 39393939390000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1038025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0961975^2 + 3939393939390000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1038025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0961975^2 + 393939393939390000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1038025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0961975^2 + 39393939393939390000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1038025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0961975^2 + 3939393939393939390000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1038025^2$ |
- 196)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0961584^2 + 392000^2$ | $:= 1038416^2$ |
| $1020\ 0961584^2 + 39592000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1038416^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0961584^2 + 3959592000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1038416^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0961584^2 + 395959592000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1038416^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0961584^2 + 39595959592000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1038416^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0961584^2 + 3959595959592000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1038416^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0961584^2 + 395959595959592000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1038416^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0961584^2 + 39595959595959592000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1038416^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0961584^2 + 3959595959595959592000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1038416^2$ |
- 197)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0961191^2 + 394000^2$ | $:= 1038809^2$ |
| $1020\ 0961191^2 + 39794000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1038809^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0961191^2 + 3979794000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1038809^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0961191^2 + 397979794000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1038809^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0961191^2 + 39797979794000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1038809^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0961191^2 + 3979797979794000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1038809^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0961191^2 + 397979797979794000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1038809^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0961191^2 + 39797979797979794000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1038809^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0961191^2 + 3979797979797979794000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1038809^2$ |
- 198)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0960796^2 + 396000^2$ | $:= 1039204^2$ |
| $1020\ 0960796^2 + 39996000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1039204^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0960796^2 + 3999996000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1039204^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0960796^2 + 399999996000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1039204^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0960796^2 + 39999999996000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1039204^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0960796^2 + 3999999999996000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1039204^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0960796^2 + 399999999999996000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1039204^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0960796^2 + 39999999999999996000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1039204^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0960796^2 + 3999999999999999996000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1039204^2$ |

- 199)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0960399^2 + 398000^2 && := 1039601^2 \\
 &1020\ 0960399^2 + 40198000^2 && := 1020\ 1039601^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0960399^2 + 4020198000^2 && := 10203020\ 1039601^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0960399^2 + 402020198000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1039601^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0960399^2 + 40202020198000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1039601^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0960399^2 + 4020202020198000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1039601^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0960399^2 + 402020202020198000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1039601^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0960399^2 + 40202020202020198000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1039601^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0960399^2 + 4020202020202020198000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1039601^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 200)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0960000^2 + 400000^2 && := 1040000^2 \\
 &1020\ 0960000^2 + 40400000^2 && := 1020\ 1040000^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0960000^2 + 4040400000^2 && := 10203020\ 1040000^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0960000^2 + 404040400000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1040000^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0960000^2 + 40404040400000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1040000^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0960000^2 + 4040404040400000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1040000^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0960000^2 + 404040404040400000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1040000^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0960000^2 + 40404040404040400000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1040000^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0960000^2 + 4040404040404040400000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1040000^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 201)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0959599^2 + 402000^2 && := 1040401^2 \\
 &1020\ 0959599^2 + 40602000^2 && := 1020\ 1040401^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0959599^2 + 4060602000^2 && := 10203020\ 1040401^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0959599^2 + 406060602000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1040401^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0959599^2 + 40606060602000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1040401^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0959599^2 + 4060606060602000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1040401^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0959599^2 + 406060606060602000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1040401^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0959599^2 + 40606060606060602000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1040401^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 202)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0959196^2 + 404000^2 && := 1040804^2 \\
 &1020\ 0959196^2 + 40804000^2 && := 1020\ 1040804^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0959196^2 + 4080804000^2 && := 10203020\ 1040804^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0959196^2 + 408080804000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1040804^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0959196^2 + 40808080804000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1040804^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0959196^2 + 4080808080804000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1040804^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0959196^2 + 408080808080804000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1040804^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0959196^2 + 40808080808080804000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1040804^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0959196^2 + 4080808080808080804000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1040804^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 203)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0958791^2 + 406000^2 && := 1041209^2 \\
 &1020\ 0958791^2 + 41006000^2 && := 1020\ 1041209^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0958791^2 + 4101006000^2 && := 10203020\ 1041209^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0958791^2 + 410101006000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1041209^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0958791^2 + 41010101006000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1041209^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0958791^2 + 4101010101006000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1041209^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0958791^2 + 410101010101006000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1041209^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0958791^2 + 41010101010101006000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1041209^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0958791^2 + 4101010101010101006000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1041209^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 204)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0958384^2 + 408000^2 && := 1041616^2 \\
 &1020\ 0958384^2 + 41208000^2 && := 1020\ 1041616^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0958384^2 + 4121208000^2 && := 10203020\ 1041616^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0958384^2 + 412121208000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1041616^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0958384^2 + 41212121208000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1041616^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0958384^2 + 4121212121208000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1041616^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0958384^2 + 412121212121208000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1041616^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0958384^2 + 41212121212121208000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1041616^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0958384^2 + 41212121212121208000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1041616^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 205)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0957975^2 + 410000^2 && := 1042025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0957975^2 + 41410000^2 && := 1020\ 1042025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0957975^2 + 4141410000^2 && := 10203020\ 1042025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0957975^2 + 414141410000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1042025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0957975^2 + 41414141410000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1042025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0957975^2 + 4141414141410000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1042025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0957975^2 + 414141414141410000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1042025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0957975^2 + 41414141414141410000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1042025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0957975^2 + 4141414141414141410000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1042025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 206)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0957564^2 + 412000^2 && := 1042436^2 \\
 &1020\ 0957564^2 + 41612000^2 && := 1020\ 1042436^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0957564^2 + 4161612000^2 && := 10203020\ 1042436^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0957564^2 + 416161612000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1042436^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0957564^2 + 41616161612000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1042436^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0957564^2 + 4161616161612000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1042436^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0957564^2 + 416161616161612000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1042436^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0957564^2 + 41616161616161612000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1042436^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0957564^2 + 4161616161616161612000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1042436^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 207)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0957151^2 + 414000^2 && := 1042849^2 \\
 &1020\ 0957151^2 + 41814000^2 && := 1020\ 1042849^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0957151^2 + 4181814000^2 && := 10203020\ 1042849^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0957151^2 + 418181814000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1042849^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0957151^2 + 41818181814000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1042849^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0957151^2 + 4181818181814000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1042849^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0957151^2 + 418181818181814000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1042849^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0957151^2 + 41818181818181814000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1042849^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0957151^2 + 4181818181818181814000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1042849^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 208)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0956736^2 + 416000^2 && := 1043264^2 \\
 &1020\ 0956736^2 + 42016000^2 && := 1020\ 1043264^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0956736^2 + 4202016000^2 && := 10203020\ 1043264^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0956736^2 + 420202016000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1043264^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0956736^2 + 42020202016000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1043264^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0956736^2 + 4202020202016000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1043264^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0956736^2 + 420202020202016000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1043264^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0956736^2 + 42020202020202016000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1043264^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0956736^2 + 4202020202020202016000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1043264^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 209)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0956319^2 + 418000^2 && := 1043681^2 \\
 &1020\ 0956319^2 + 42218000^2 && := 1020\ 1043681^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0956319^2 + 4222218000^2 && := 10203020\ 1043681^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0956319^2 + 42222218000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1043681^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0956319^2 + 422222218000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1043681^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0956319^2 + 4222222218000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1043681^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0956319^2 + 42222222218000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1043681^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0956319^2 + 422222222218000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1043681^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0956319^2 + 4222222222218000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1043681^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 210)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0955900^2 + 420000^2 && := 1044100^2 \\
 &1020\ 0955900^2 + 42420000^2 && := 1020\ 1044100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0955900^2 + 4242420000^2 && := 10203020\ 1044100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0955900^2 + 424242420000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1044100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0955900^2 + 42424242420000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1044100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0955900^2 + 4242424242420000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1044100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0955900^2 + 424242424242420000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1044100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0955900^2 + 42424242424242420000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1044100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0955900^2 + 42424242424242420000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1044100^2
 \end{aligned}$$

211)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0955479^2 + 422000^2 && := 1044521^2 \\
 &1020\ 0955479^2 + 42622000^2 && := 1020\ 1044521^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0955479^2 + 4262622000^2 && := 10203020\ 1044521^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0955479^2 + 426262622000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1044521^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0955479^2 + 42626262622000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1044521^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0955479^2 + 4262626262622000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1044521^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0955479^2 + 426262626262622000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1044521^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0955479^2 + 426262626262622000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1044521^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0955479^2 + 42626262626262622000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1044521^2
 \end{aligned}$$

212)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0955056^2 + 424000^2 && := 1044944^2 \\
 &1020\ 0955056^2 + 42824000^2 && := 1020\ 1044944^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0955056^2 + 4282824000^2 && := 10203020\ 1044944^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0955056^2 + 428282824000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1044944^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0955056^2 + 42828282824000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1044944^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0955056^2 + 4282828282824000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1044944^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0955056^2 + 428282828282824000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1044944^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0955056^2 + 42828282828282824000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1044944^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0955056^2 + 4282828282828282824000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1044944^2
 \end{aligned}$$

213)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0954631^2 + 426000^2 && := 1045369^2 \\
 &1020\ 0954631^2 + 43026000^2 && := 1020\ 1045369^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0954631^2 + 4303026000^2 && := 10203020\ 1045369^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0954631^2 + 430303026000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1045369^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0954631^2 + 43030303026000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1045369^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0954631^2 + 4303030303026000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1045369^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0954631^2 + 430303030303026000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1045369^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0954631^2 + 43030303030303026000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1045369^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0954631^2 + 43030303030303026000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1045369^2
 \end{aligned}$$

214)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0954204^2 + 428000^2 && := 1045796^2 \\
 &1020\ 0954204^2 + 43228000^2 && := 1020\ 1045796^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0954204^2 + 4323228000^2 && := 10203020\ 1045796^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0954204^2 + 432323228000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1045796^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0954204^2 + 43232323228000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1045796^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0954204^2 + 4323232323228000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1045796^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0954204^2 + 432323232323228000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1045796^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0954204^2 + 43232323232323228000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1045796^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0954204^2 + 43232323232323228000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1045796^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 215)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0953775^2 + 430000^2 && := 1046225^2 \\ &1020\ 0953775^2 + 43430000^2 && := 1020\ 1046225^2 \\ &10203020\ 0953775^2 + 4343430000^2 && := 10203020\ 1046225^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0953775^2 + 434343430000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1046225^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0953775^2 + 43434343430000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1046225^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0953775^2 + 4343434343430000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1046225^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0953775^2 + 434343434343430000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1046225^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0953775^2 + 43434343434343430000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1046225^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0953775^2 + 4343434343434343430000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1046225^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 216)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0953344^2 + 432000^2 && := 1046656^2 \\ &1020\ 0953344^2 + 43632000^2 && := 1020\ 1046656^2 \\ &10203020\ 0953344^2 + 4363632000^2 && := 10203020\ 1046656^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0953344^2 + 436363632000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1046656^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0953344^2 + 43636363632000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1046656^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0953344^2 + 4363636363632000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1046656^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0953344^2 + 436363636363632000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1046656^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0953344^2 + 43636363636363632000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1046656^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0953344^2 + 4363636363636363632000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1046656^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 217)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0952911^2 + 434000^2 && := 1047089^2 \\ &1020\ 0952911^2 + 43834000^2 && := 1020\ 1047089^2 \\ &10203020\ 0952911^2 + 4383834000^2 && := 10203020\ 1047089^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0952911^2 + 438383834000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1047089^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0952911^2 + 43838383834000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1047089^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0952911^2 + 4383838383834000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1047089^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0952911^2 + 438383838383834000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1047089^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0952911^2 + 43838383838383834000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1047089^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0952911^2 + 4383838383838383834000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1047089^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 218)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0952476^2 + 436000^2 && := 1047524^2 \\ &1020\ 0952476^2 + 44036000^2 && := 1020\ 1047524^2 \\ &10203020\ 0952476^2 + 4404036000^2 && := 10203020\ 1047524^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0952476^2 + 440404036000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1047524^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0952476^2 + 44040404036000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1047524^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0952476^2 + 4404040404036000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1047524^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0952476^2 + 440404040404036000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1047524^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0952476^2 + 44040404040404036000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1047524^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0952476^2 + 4404040404040404036000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1047524^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 219)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0952039^2 + 438000^2 && := 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0952039^2 + 44238000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0952039^2 + 4424238000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0952039^2 + 442424238000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0952039^2 + 44242424238000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0952039^2 + 4424242424238000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0952039^2 + 442424242424238000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0952039^2 + 442424242424238000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1047961^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0952039^2 + 44242424242424238000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1047961^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 220)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0951600^2 + 440000^2 && := 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0951600^2 + 44440000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0951600^2 + 4444440000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0951600^2 + 444444440000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0951600^2 + 44444444440000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0951600^2 + 4444444444440000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0951600^2 + 444444444444440000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0951600^2 + 44444444444444440000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1048400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0951600^2 + 4444444444444444440000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1048400^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 221)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0951159^2 + 442000^2 && := 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0951159^2 + 44642000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0951159^2 + 4464642000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0951159^2 + 446464642000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0951159^2 + 44646464642000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0951159^2 + 4464646464642000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0951159^2 + 446464646464642000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0951159^2 + 44646464646464642000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1048841^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0951159^2 + 4464646464646464642000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1048841^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 222)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0950716^2 + 444000^2 && := 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0950716^2 + 44844000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0950716^2 + 4484844000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0950716^2 + 448484844000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0950716^2 + 44848484844000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0950716^2 + 4484848484844000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0950716^2 + 448484848484844000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0950716^2 + 44848484848484844000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1049284^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0950716^2 + 4484848484848484844000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1049284^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 223)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0950271^2 + 446000^2 && := 1049729^2 \\ &1020\ 0950271^2 + 45046000^2 && := 1020\ 1049729^2 \\ &10203020\ 0950271^2 + 4505046000^2 && := 10203020\ 1049729^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0950271^2 + 450505046000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1049729^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0950271^2 + 45050505046000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1049729^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0950271^2 + 4505050505046000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1049729^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0950271^2 + 450505050505046000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1049729^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0950271^2 + 45050505050505046000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1049729^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0950271^2 + 4505050505050505046000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1049729^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 224)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0949824^2 + 448000^2 && := 1050176^2 \\ &1020\ 0949824^2 + 45248000^2 && := 1020\ 1050176^2 \\ &10203020\ 0949824^2 + 4525248000^2 && := 10203020\ 1050176^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0949824^2 + 452525248000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1050176^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0949824^2 + 45252525248000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1050176^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0949824^2 + 4525252525248000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1050176^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0949824^2 + 452525252525248000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1050176^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0949824^2 + 45252525252525248000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1050176^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0949824^2 + 4525252525252525248000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1050176^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 225)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0949375^2 + 450000^2 && := 1050625^2 \\ &1020\ 0949375^2 + 45450000^2 && := 1020\ 1050625^2 \\ &10203020\ 0949375^2 + 4545450000^2 && := 10203020\ 1050625^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0949375^2 + 454545450000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1050625^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0949375^2 + 45454545450000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1050625^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0949375^2 + 4545454545450000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1050625^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0949375^2 + 454545454545450000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1050625^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0949375^2 + 45454545454545450000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1050625^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0949375^2 + 4545454545454545450000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1050625^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 226)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0948924^2 + 452000^2 && := 1051076^2 \\ &1020\ 0948924^2 + 45652000^2 && := 1020\ 1051076^2 \\ &10203020\ 0948924^2 + 4565652000^2 && := 10203020\ 1051076^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0948924^2 + 456565652000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1051076^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0948924^2 + 45656565652000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1051076^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0948924^2 + 4565656565652000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1051076^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0948924^2 + 456565656565652000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1051076^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0948924^2 + 45656565656565652000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1051076^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0948924^2 + 4565656565656565652000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1051076^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 227)
- $$0948471^2 + 454000^2 := 1051529^2$$
- $$1020\ 0948471^2 + 45854000^2 := 1020\ 1051529^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0948471^2 + 4585854000^2 := 10203020\ 1051529^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0948471^2 + 458585854000^2 := 102030403020\ 1051529^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0948471^2 + 45858585854000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1051529^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0948471^2 + 4585858585854000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1051529^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0948471^2 + 458585858585854000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1051529^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0948471^2 + 45858585858585854000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1051529^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0948471^2 + 4585858585858585854000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1051529^2$$
- 228)
- $$0948016^2 + 456000^2 := 1051984^2$$
- $$1020\ 0948016^2 + 46056000^2 := 1020\ 1051984^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0948016^2 + 4606056000^2 := 10203020\ 1051984^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0948016^2 + 460606056000^2 := 102030403020\ 1051984^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0948016^2 + 46060606056000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1051984^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0948016^2 + 4606060606056000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1051984^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0948016^2 + 460606060606056000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1051984^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0948016^2 + 46060606060606056000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1051984^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0948016^2 + 4606060606060606056000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1051984^2$$
- 229)
- $$0947559^2 + 458000^2 := 1052441^2$$
- $$1020\ 0947559^2 + 46258000^2 := 1020\ 1052441^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0947559^2 + 4626258000^2 := 10203020\ 1052441^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0947559^2 + 462626258000^2 := 102030403020\ 1052441^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0947559^2 + 46262626258000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1052441^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0947559^2 + 4626262626258000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1052441^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0947559^2 + 462626262626258000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1052441^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0947559^2 + 46262626262626258000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1052441^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0947559^2 + 4626262626262626258000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1052441^2$$
- 230)
- $$0947100^2 + 460000^2 := 1052900^2$$
- $$1020\ 0947100^2 + 46460000^2 := 1020\ 1052900^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0947100^2 + 4646460000^2 := 10203020\ 1052900^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0947100^2 + 464646460000^2 := 102030403020\ 1052900^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0947100^2 + 46464646460000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1052900^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0947100^2 + 4646464646460000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1052900^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0947100^2 + 464646464646460000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1052900^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0947100^2 + 46464646464646460000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1052900^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0947100^2 + 4646464646464646460000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1052900^2$$

231)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0946639^2 + 462000^2 && := 1053361^2 \\
 &1020\ 0946639^2 + 46662000^2 && := 1020\ 1053361^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0946639^2 + 4666662000^2 && := 10203020\ 1053361^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0946639^2 + 46666662000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1053361^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0946639^2 + 4666666662000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1053361^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0946639^2 + 466666666662000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1053361^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0946639^2 + 46666666666662000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1053361^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0946639^2 + 4666666666666662000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1053361^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0946639^2 + 466666666666666662000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1053361^2
 \end{aligned}$$

232)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0946176^2 + 464000^2 && := 1053824^2 \\
 &1020\ 0946176^2 + 46864000^2 && := 1020\ 1053824^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0946176^2 + 4686864000^2 && := 10203020\ 1053824^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0946176^2 + 468686864000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1053824^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0946176^2 + 46868686864000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1053824^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0946176^2 + 4686868686864000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1053824^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0946176^2 + 468686868686864000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1053824^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0946176^2 + 46868686868686864000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1053824^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0946176^2 + 4686868686868686864000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1053824^2
 \end{aligned}$$

233)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0945711^2 + 466000^2 && := 1054289^2 \\
 &1020\ 0945711^2 + 47066000^2 && := 1020\ 1054289^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0945711^2 + 4707066000^2 && := 10203020\ 1054289^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0945711^2 + 470707066000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1054289^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0945711^2 + 47070707066000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1054289^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0945711^2 + 4707070707066000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1054289^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0945711^2 + 470707070707066000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1054289^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0945711^2 + 47070707070707066000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1054289^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0945711^2 + 47070707070707066000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1054289^2
 \end{aligned}$$

234)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0945244^2 + 468000^2 && := 1054756^2 \\
 &1020\ 0945244^2 + 47268000^2 && := 1020\ 1054756^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0945244^2 + 4727268000^2 && := 10203020\ 1054756^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0945244^2 + 472727268000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1054756^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0945244^2 + 47272727268000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1054756^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0945244^2 + 4727272727268000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1054756^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0945244^2 + 472727272727268000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1054756^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0945244^2 + 47272727272727268000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1054756^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0945244^2 + 47272727272727268000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1054756^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 235)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0944775^2 + 470000^2 && := 1055225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0944775^2 + 47470000^2 && := 1020\ 1055225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0944775^2 + 4747470000^2 && := 10203020\ 1055225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0944775^2 + 474747470000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1055225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0944775^2 + 47474747470000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1055225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0944775^2 + 4747474747470000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1055225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0944775^2 + 474747474747470000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1055225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0944775^2 + 47474747474747470000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1055225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0944775^2 + 4747474747474747470000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1055225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 236)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0944304^2 + 472000^2 && := 1055696^2 \\
 &1020\ 0944304^2 + 47672000^2 && := 1020\ 1055696^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0944304^2 + 4767672000^2 && := 10203020\ 1055696^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0944304^2 + 476767672000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1055696^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0944304^2 + 47676767672000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1055696^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0944304^2 + 4767676767672000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1055696^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0944304^2 + 476767676767672000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1055696^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0944304^2 + 47676767676767672000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1055696^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0944304^2 + 4767676767676767672000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1055696^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 237)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0943831^2 + 474000^2 && := 1056169^2 \\
 &1020\ 0943831^2 + 47874000^2 && := 1020\ 1056169^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0943831^2 + 4787874000^2 && := 10203020\ 1056169^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0943831^2 + 478787874000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1056169^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0943831^2 + 47878787874000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1056169^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0943831^2 + 4787878787874000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1056169^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0943831^2 + 478787878787874000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1056169^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0943831^2 + 47878787878787874000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1056169^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0943831^2 + 4787878787878787874000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1056169^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 238)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0943356^2 + 476000^2 && := 1056644^2 \\
 &1020\ 0943356^2 + 48076000^2 && := 1020\ 1056644^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0943356^2 + 4808076000^2 && := 10203020\ 1056644^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0943356^2 + 480808076000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1056644^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0943356^2 + 48080808076000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1056644^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0943356^2 + 4808080808076000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1056644^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0943356^2 + 480808080808076000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1056644^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0943356^2 + 48080808080808076000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1056644^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0943356^2 + 4808080808080808076000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1056644^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 239)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0942879^2 + 478000^2 && := 1057121^2 \\
 &1020\ 0942879^2 + 48278000^2 && := 1020\ 1057121^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0942879^2 + 4828278000^2 && := 10203020\ 1057121^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0942879^2 + 482828278000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1057121^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0942879^2 + 48282828278000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1057121^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0942879^2 + 4828282828278000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1057121^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0942879^2 + 482828282828278000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1057121^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0942879^2 + 48282828282828278000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1057121^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0942879^2 + 4828282828282828278000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1057121^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 240)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0942400^2 + 480000^2 && := 1057600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0942400^2 + 48480000^2 && := 1020\ 1057600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0942400^2 + 4848480000^2 && := 10203020\ 1057600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0942400^2 + 484848480000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1057600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0942400^2 + 48484848480000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1057600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0942400^2 + 4848484848480000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1057600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0942400^2 + 484848484848480000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1057600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0942400^2 + 48484848484848480000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1057600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0942400^2 + 4848484848484848480000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1057600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 241)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0941919^2 + 482000^2 && := 1058081^2 \\
 &1020\ 0941919^2 + 48682000^2 && := 1020\ 1058081^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0941919^2 + 4868682000^2 && := 10203020\ 1058081^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0941919^2 + 486868682000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1058081^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0941919^2 + 48686868682000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1058081^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0941919^2 + 4868686868682000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1058081^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0941919^2 + 486868686868682000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1058081^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0941919^2 + 48686868686868682000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1058081^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0941919^2 + 4868686868686868682000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1058081^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 242)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0941436^2 + 484000^2 && := 1058564^2 \\
 &1020\ 0941436^2 + 48884000^2 && := 1020\ 1058564^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0941436^2 + 4888884000^2 && := 10203020\ 1058564^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0941436^2 + 488888884000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1058564^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0941436^2 + 48888888884000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1058564^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0941436^2 + 4888888888884000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1058564^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0941436^2 + 488888888888884000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1058564^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0941436^2 + 48888888888888884000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1058564^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0941436^2 + 4888888888888888884000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1058564^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 243)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0940951^2 + 486000^2 && := 1059049^2 \\
 &1020\ 0940951^2 + 49086000^2 && := 1020\ 1059049^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0940951^2 + 4909086000^2 && := 10203020\ 1059049^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0940951^2 + 490909086000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1059049^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0940951^2 + 49090909086000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1059049^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0940951^2 + 4909090909086000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1059049^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0940951^2 + 490909090909086000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1059049^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0940951^2 + 49090909090909086000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1059049^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0940951^2 + 4909090909090909086000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1059049^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 244)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0940464^2 + 488000^2 && := 1059536^2 \\
 &1020\ 0940464^2 + 49288000^2 && := 1020\ 1059536^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0940464^2 + 4929288000^2 && := 10203020\ 1059536^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0940464^2 + 492929288000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1059536^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0940464^2 + 49292929288000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1059536^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0940464^2 + 4929292929288000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1059536^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0940464^2 + 492929292929288000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1059536^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0940464^2 + 49292929292929288000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1059536^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0940464^2 + 4929292929292929288000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1059536^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 245)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0939975^2 + 490000^2 && := 1060025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0939975^2 + 49490000^2 && := 1020\ 1060025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0939975^2 + 4949490000^2 && := 10203020\ 1060025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0939975^2 + 494949490000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1060025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0939975^2 + 49494949490000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1060025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0939975^2 + 4949494949490000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1060025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0939975^2 + 494949494949490000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1060025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0939975^2 + 49494949494949490000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1060025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0939975^2 + 4949494949494949490000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1060025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 246)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0939484^2 + 492000^2 && := 1060516^2 \\
 &1020\ 0939484^2 + 49692000^2 && := 1020\ 1060516^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0939484^2 + 4969692000^2 && := 10203020\ 1060516^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0939484^2 + 496969692000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1060516^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0939484^2 + 49696969692000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1060516^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0939484^2 + 4969696969692000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1060516^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0939484^2 + 496969696969692000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1060516^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0939484^2 + 49696969696969692000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1060516^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0939484^2 + 4969696969696969692000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1060516^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 247)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0938991^2 + 494000^2 && := 1061009^2 \\
 &1020\ 0938991^2 + 49894000^2 && := 1020\ 1061009^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0938991^2 + 4989894000^2 && := 10203020\ 1061009^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0938991^2 + 498989894000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1061009^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0938991^2 + 49898989894000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1061009^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0938991^2 + 4989898989894000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1061009^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0938991^2 + 498989898989894000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1061009^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0938991^2 + 49898989898989894000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1061009^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0938991^2 + 4989898989898989894000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1061009^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 248)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0938496^2 + 496000^2 && := 1061504^2 \\
 &1020\ 0938496^2 + 50096000^2 && := 1020\ 1061504^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0938496^2 + 5010096000^2 && := 10203020\ 1061504^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0938496^2 + 501010096000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1061504^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0938496^2 + 50101010096000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1061504^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0938496^2 + 5010101010096000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1061504^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0938496^2 + 501010101010096000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1061504^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0938496^2 + 50101010101010096000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1061504^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0938496^2 + 5010101010101010096000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1061504^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 249)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0937999^2 + 498000^2 && := 1062001^2 \\
 &1020\ 0937999^2 + 50298000^2 && := 1020\ 1062001^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0937999^2 + 5030298000^2 && := 10203020\ 1062001^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0937999^2 + 503030298000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1062001^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0937999^2 + 50303030298000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1062001^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0937999^2 + 5030303030298000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1062001^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0937999^2 + 503030303030298000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1062001^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0937999^2 + 50303030303030298000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1062001^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0937999^2 + 5030303030303030298000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1062001^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 250)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0937500^2 + 500000^2 && := 1062500^2 \\
 &1020\ 0937500^2 + 50500000^2 && := 1020\ 1062500^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0937500^2 + 5050500000^2 && := 10203020\ 1062500^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0937500^2 + 505050500000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1062500^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0937500^2 + 50505050500000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1062500^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0937500^2 + 5050505050500000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1062500^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0937500^2 + 505050505050500000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1062500^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0937500^2 + 50505050505050500000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1062500^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0937500^2 + 5050505050505050500000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1062500^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 251)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0936999^2 + 502000^2 && := 1063001^2 \\
 &1020\ 0936999^2 + 50702000^2 && := 1020\ 1063001^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0936999^2 + 5070702000^2 && := 10203020\ 1063001^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0936999^2 + 507070702000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1063001^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0936999^2 + 50707070702000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1063001^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0936999^2 + 5070707070702000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1063001^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0936999^2 + 507070707070702000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1063001^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0936999^2 + 50707070707070702000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1063001^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0936999^2 + 5070707070707070702000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1063001^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 252)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0936496^2 + 504000^2 && := 1063504^2 \\
 &1020\ 0936496^2 + 50904000^2 && := 1020\ 1063504^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0936496^2 + 5090904000^2 && := 10203020\ 1063504^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0936496^2 + 509090904000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1063504^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0936496^2 + 50909090904000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1063504^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0936496^2 + 5090909090904000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1063504^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0936496^2 + 509090909090904000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1063504^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0936496^2 + 50909090909090904000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1063504^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0936496^2 + 5090909090909090904000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1063504^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 253)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0935991^2 + 506000^2 && := 1064009^2 \\
 &1020\ 0935991^2 + 51106000^2 && := 1020\ 1064009^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0935991^2 + 5111106000^2 && := 10203020\ 1064009^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0935991^2 + 511111106000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1064009^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0935991^2 + 51111111106000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1064009^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0935991^2 + 5111111111106000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1064009^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0935991^2 + 511111111111106000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1064009^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0935991^2 + 51111111111111106000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1064009^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0935991^2 + 5111111111111111106000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1064009^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 254)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0935484^2 + 508000^2 && := 1064516^2 \\
 &1020\ 0935484^2 + 51308000^2 && := 1020\ 1064516^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0935484^2 + 5131308000^2 && := 10203020\ 1064516^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0935484^2 + 513131308000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1064516^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0935484^2 + 51313131308000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1064516^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0935484^2 + 5131313131308000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1064516^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0935484^2 + 513131313131308000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1064516^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0935484^2 + 51313131313131308000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1064516^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0935484^2 + 5131313131313131308000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1064516^2
 \end{aligned}$$

255)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0934975^2 + 510000^2 && := 1065025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0934975^2 + 51510000^2 && := 1020\ 1065025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0934975^2 + 5151510000^2 && := 10203020\ 1065025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0934975^2 + 515151510000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1065025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0934975^2 + 51515151510000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1065025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0934975^2 + 5151515151510000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1065025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0934975^2 + 515151515151510000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1065025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0934975^2 + 51515151515151510000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1065025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0934975^2 + 5151515151515151510000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1065025^2
 \end{aligned}$$

256)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0934464^2 + 512000^2 && := 1065536^2 \\
 &1020\ 0934464^2 + 51712000^2 && := 1020\ 1065536^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0934464^2 + 5171712000^2 && := 10203020\ 1065536^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0934464^2 + 517171712000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1065536^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0934464^2 + 51717171712000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1065536^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0934464^2 + 5171717171712000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1065536^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0934464^2 + 517171717171712000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1065536^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0934464^2 + 51717171717171712000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1065536^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0934464^2 + 5171717171717171712000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1065536^2
 \end{aligned}$$

257)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0933951^2 + 514000^2 && := 1066049^2 \\
 &1020\ 0933951^2 + 51914000^2 && := 1020\ 1066049^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0933951^2 + 5191914000^2 && := 10203020\ 1066049^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0933951^2 + 519191914000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1066049^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0933951^2 + 51919191914000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1066049^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0933951^2 + 5191919191914000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1066049^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0933951^2 + 519191919191914000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1066049^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0933951^2 + 51919191919191914000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1066049^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0933951^2 + 5191919191919191914000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1066049^2
 \end{aligned}$$

258)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0933436^2 + 516000^2 && := 1066564^2 \\
 &1020\ 0933436^2 + 52116000^2 && := 1020\ 1066564^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0933436^2 + 5212116000^2 && := 10203020\ 1066564^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0933436^2 + 521212116000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1066564^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0933436^2 + 52121212116000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1066564^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0933436^2 + 5212121212116000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1066564^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0933436^2 + 521212121212116000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1066564^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0933436^2 + 52121212121212116000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1066564^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0933436^2 + 52121212121212116000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1066564^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 259)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0932919^2 + 518000^2 && := 1067081^2 \\
 &1020\ 0932919^2 + 52318000^2 && := 1020\ 1067081^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0932919^2 + 5232318000^2 && := 10203020\ 1067081^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0932919^2 + 523232318000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1067081^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0932919^2 + 52323232318000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1067081^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0932919^2 + 5232323232318000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1067081^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0932919^2 + 523232323232318000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1067081^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0932919^2 + 52323232323232318000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1067081^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0932919^2 + 5232323232323232318000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1067081^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 260)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0932400^2 + 520000^2 && := 1067600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0932400^2 + 52520000^2 && := 1020\ 1067600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0932400^2 + 5252520000^2 && := 10203020\ 1067600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0932400^2 + 525252520000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1067600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0932400^2 + 52525252520000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1067600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0932400^2 + 5252525252520000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1067600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0932400^2 + 525252525252520000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1067600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0932400^2 + 52525252525252520000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1067600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0932400^2 + 5252525252525252520000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1067600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 261)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0931879^2 + 522000^2 && := 1068121^2 \\
 &1020\ 0931879^2 + 52722000^2 && := 1020\ 1068121^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0931879^2 + 5272722000^2 && := 10203020\ 1068121^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0931879^2 + 527272722000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1068121^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0931879^2 + 52727272722000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1068121^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0931879^2 + 5272727272722000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1068121^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0931879^2 + 527272727272722000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1068121^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0931879^2 + 52727272727272722000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1068121^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0931879^2 + 5272727272727272722000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1068121^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 262)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0931356^2 + 524000^2 && := 1068644^2 \\
 &1020\ 0931356^2 + 52924000^2 && := 1020\ 1068644^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0931356^2 + 5292924000^2 && := 10203020\ 1068644^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0931356^2 + 529292924000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1068644^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0931356^2 + 52929292924000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1068644^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0931356^2 + 5292929292924000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1068644^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0931356^2 + 529292929292924000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1068644^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0931356^2 + 52929292929292924000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1068644^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0931356^2 + 5292929292929292924000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1068644^2
 \end{aligned}$$

263)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0930831^2 + 526000^2 && := 1069169^2 \\
 &1020\ 0930831^2 + 53126000^2 && := 1020\ 1069169^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0930831^2 + 5313126000^2 && := 10203020\ 1069169^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0930831^2 + 531313126000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1069169^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0930831^2 + 53131313126000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1069169^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0930831^2 + 5313131313126000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1069169^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0930831^2 + 531313131313126000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1069169^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0930831^2 + 53131313131313126000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1069169^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0930831^2 + 5313131313131313126000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1069169^2
 \end{aligned}$$

264)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0930304^2 + 528000^2 && := 1069696^2 \\
 &1020\ 0930304^2 + 53328000^2 && := 1020\ 1069696^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0930304^2 + 5333328000^2 && := 10203020\ 1069696^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0930304^2 + 533333328000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1069696^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0930304^2 + 53333333328000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1069696^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0930304^2 + 5333333333328000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1069696^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0930304^2 + 533333333333328000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1069696^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0930304^2 + 53333333333333328000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1069696^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0930304^2 + 5333333333333333328000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1069696^2
 \end{aligned}$$

265)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0929775^2 + 530000^2 && := 1070225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0929775^2 + 53530000^2 && := 1020\ 1070225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0929775^2 + 5353530000^2 && := 10203020\ 1070225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0929775^2 + 535353530000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1070225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0929775^2 + 53535353530000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1070225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0929775^2 + 5353535353530000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1070225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0929775^2 + 535353535353530000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1070225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0929775^2 + 53535353535353530000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1070225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0929775^2 + 5353535353535353530000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1070225^2
 \end{aligned}$$

266)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0929244^2 + 532000^2 && := 1070756^2 \\
 &1020\ 0929244^2 + 53732000^2 && := 1020\ 1070756^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0929244^2 + 5373732000^2 && := 10203020\ 1070756^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0929244^2 + 537373732000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1070756^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0929244^2 + 53737373732000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1070756^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0929244^2 + 5373737373732000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1070756^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0929244^2 + 537373737373732000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1070756^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0929244^2 + 53737373737373732000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1070756^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0929244^2 + 5373737373737373732000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1070756^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 267)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0928711^2 + 534000^2 && := 1071289^2 \\
 &1020\ 0928711^2 + 53934000^2 && := 1020\ 1071289^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0928711^2 + 5393934000^2 && := 10203020\ 1071289^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0928711^2 + 539393934000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1071289^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0928711^2 + 53939393934000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1071289^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0928711^2 + 5393939393934000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1071289^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0928711^2 + 539393939393934000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1071289^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0928711^2 + 53939393939393934000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1071289^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0928711^2 + 5393939393939393934000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1071289^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 268)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0928176^2 + 536000^2 && := 1071824^2 \\
 &1020\ 0928176^2 + 54136000^2 && := 1020\ 1071824^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0928176^2 + 5414136000^2 && := 10203020\ 1071824^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0928176^2 + 541414136000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1071824^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0928176^2 + 54141414136000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1071824^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0928176^2 + 5414141414136000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1071824^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0928176^2 + 541414141414136000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1071824^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0928176^2 + 54141414141414136000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1071824^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0928176^2 + 5414141414141414136000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1071824^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 269)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0927639^2 + 538000^2 && := 1072361^2 \\
 &1020\ 0927639^2 + 54338000^2 && := 1020\ 1072361^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0927639^2 + 5434338000^2 && := 10203020\ 1072361^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0927639^2 + 543434338000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1072361^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0927639^2 + 54343434338000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1072361^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0927639^2 + 5434343434338000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1072361^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0927639^2 + 543434343434338000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1072361^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0927639^2 + 54343434343434338000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1072361^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0927639^2 + 5434343434343434338000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1072361^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 270)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0927100^2 + 540000^2 && := 1072900^2 \\
 &1020\ 0927100^2 + 54540000^2 && := 1020\ 1072900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0927100^2 + 5454540000^2 && := 10203020\ 1072900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0927100^2 + 545454540000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1072900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0927100^2 + 54545454540000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1072900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0927100^2 + 5454545454540000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1072900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0927100^2 + 545454545454540000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1072900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0927100^2 + 54545454545454540000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1072900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0927100^2 + 5454545454545454540000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1072900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 271)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0926559^2 + 542000^2 && := 1073441^2 \\
 &1020\ 0926559^2 + 54742000^2 && := 1020\ 1073441^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0926559^2 + 5474742000^2 && := 10203020\ 1073441^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0926559^2 + 547474742000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1073441^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0926559^2 + 54747474742000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1073441^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0926559^2 + 5474747474742000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1073441^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0926559^2 + 547474747474742000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1073441^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0926559^2 + 54747474747474742000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1073441^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0926559^2 + 5474747474747474742000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1073441^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 272)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0926016^2 + 544000^2 && := 1073984^2 \\
 &1020\ 0926016^2 + 54944000^2 && := 1020\ 1073984^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0926016^2 + 5494944000^2 && := 10203020\ 1073984^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0926016^2 + 549494944000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1073984^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0926016^2 + 54949494944000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1073984^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0926016^2 + 5494949494944000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1073984^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0926016^2 + 549494949494944000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1073984^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0926016^2 + 54949494949494944000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1073984^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0926016^2 + 5494949494949494944000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1073984^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 273)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0925471^2 + 546000^2 && := 1074529^2 \\
 &1020\ 0925471^2 + 55146000^2 && := 1020\ 1074529^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0925471^2 + 5515146000^2 && := 10203020\ 1074529^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0925471^2 + 551515146000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1074529^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0925471^2 + 55151515146000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1074529^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0925471^2 + 5515151515146000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1074529^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0925471^2 + 551515151515146000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1074529^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0925471^2 + 55151515151515146000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1074529^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0925471^2 + 5515151515151515146000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1074529^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 274)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0924924^2 + 548000^2 && := 1075076^2 \\
 &1020\ 0924924^2 + 55348000^2 && := 1020\ 1075076^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0924924^2 + 5535348000^2 && := 10203020\ 1075076^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0924924^2 + 553535348000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1075076^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0924924^2 + 55353535348000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1075076^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0924924^2 + 5535353535348000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1075076^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0924924^2 + 553535353535348000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1075076^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0924924^2 + 55353535353535348000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1075076^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0924924^2 + 5535353535353535348000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1075076^2
 \end{aligned}$$

275)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0924375^2 + 550000^2 && := 1075625^2 \\
 &1020\ 0924375^2 + 55550000^2 && := 1020\ 1075625^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0924375^2 + 5555550000^2 && := 10203020\ 1075625^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0924375^2 + 555555550000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1075625^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0924375^2 + 55555555550000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1075625^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0924375^2 + 5555555555550000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1075625^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0924375^2 + 555555555555550000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1075625^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0924375^2 + 55555555555555550000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1075625^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0924375^2 + 5555555555555555550000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1075625^2
 \end{aligned}$$

276)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0923824^2 + 552000^2 && := 1076176^2 \\
 &1020\ 0923824^2 + 55752000^2 && := 1020\ 1076176^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0923824^2 + 5575752000^2 && := 10203020\ 1076176^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0923824^2 + 557575752000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1076176^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0923824^2 + 55757575752000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1076176^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0923824^2 + 5575757575752000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1076176^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0923824^2 + 557575757575752000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1076176^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0923824^2 + 55757575757575752000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1076176^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0923824^2 + 5575757575757575752000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1076176^2
 \end{aligned}$$

277)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0923271^2 + 554000^2 && := 1076729^2 \\
 &1020\ 0923271^2 + 55954000^2 && := 1020\ 1076729^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0923271^2 + 5595954000^2 && := 10203020\ 1076729^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0923271^2 + 559595954000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1076729^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0923271^2 + 55959595954000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1076729^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0923271^2 + 5595959595954000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1076729^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0923271^2 + 559595959595954000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1076729^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0923271^2 + 55959595959595954000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1076729^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0923271^2 + 5595959595959595954000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1076729^2
 \end{aligned}$$

278)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0922716^2 + 556000^2 && := 1077284^2 \\
 &1020\ 0922716^2 + 56156000^2 && := 1020\ 1077284^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0922716^2 + 5616156000^2 && := 10203020\ 1077284^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0922716^2 + 561616156000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1077284^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0922716^2 + 56161616156000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1077284^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0922716^2 + 5616161616156000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1077284^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0922716^2 + 561616161616156000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1077284^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0922716^2 + 56161616161616156000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1077284^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0922716^2 + 5616161616161616156000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1077284^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 279)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0922159^2 + 558000^2 && := 1077841^2 \\ &1020\ 0922159^2 + 56358000^2 && := 1020\ 1077841^2 \\ &10203020\ 0922159^2 + 5636358000^2 && := 10203020\ 1077841^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0922159^2 + 563636358000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1077841^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0922159^2 + 56363636358000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1077841^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0922159^2 + 5636363636358000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1077841^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0922159^2 + 563636363636358000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1077841^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0922159^2 + 56363636363636358000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1077841^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0922159^2 + 5636363636363636358000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1077841^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 280)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0921600^2 + 560000^2 && := 1078400^2 \\ &1020\ 0921600^2 + 56560000^2 && := 1020\ 1078400^2 \\ &10203020\ 0921600^2 + 5656560000^2 && := 10203020\ 1078400^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0921600^2 + 565656560000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1078400^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0921600^2 + 56565656560000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1078400^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0921600^2 + 5656565656560000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1078400^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0921600^2 + 565656565656560000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1078400^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0921600^2 + 56565656565656560000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1078400^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0921600^2 + 5656565656565656560000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1078400^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 281)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0921039^2 + 562000^2 && := 1078961^2 \\ &1020\ 0921039^2 + 56762000^2 && := 1020\ 1078961^2 \\ &10203020\ 0921039^2 + 5676762000^2 && := 10203020\ 1078961^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0921039^2 + 567676762000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1078961^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0921039^2 + 56767676762000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1078961^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0921039^2 + 5676767676762000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1078961^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0921039^2 + 567676767676762000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1078961^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0921039^2 + 56767676767676762000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1078961^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0921039^2 + 5676767676767676762000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1078961^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 282)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0920476^2 + 564000^2 && := 1079524^2 \\ &1020\ 0920476^2 + 56964000^2 && := 1020\ 1079524^2 \\ &10203020\ 0920476^2 + 5696964000^2 && := 10203020\ 1079524^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0920476^2 + 569696964000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1079524^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0920476^2 + 56969696964000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1079524^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0920476^2 + 5696969696964000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1079524^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0920476^2 + 569696969696964000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1079524^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0920476^2 + 56969696969696964000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1079524^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0920476^2 + 5696969696969696964000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1079524^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 283)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0919911^2 + 566000^2$ | $:= 1080089^2$ |
| $1020\ 0919911^2 + 57166000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1080089^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0919911^2 + 5717166000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1080089^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0919911^2 + 571717166000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1080089^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0919911^2 + 57171717166000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1080089^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0919911^2 + 5717171717166000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1080089^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0919911^2 + 571717171717166000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1080089^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0919911^2 + 57171717171717166000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1080089^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0919911^2 + 5717171717171717166000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1080089^2$ |
- 284)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0919344^2 + 568000^2$ | $:= 1080656^2$ |
| $1020\ 0919344^2 + 57368000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1080656^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0919344^2 + 5737368000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1080656^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0919344^2 + 573737368000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1080656^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0919344^2 + 57373737368000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1080656^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0919344^2 + 5737373737368000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1080656^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0919344^2 + 573737373737368000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1080656^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0919344^2 + 57373737373737368000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1080656^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0919344^2 + 5737373737373737368000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1080656^2$ |
- 285)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0918775^2 + 570000^2$ | $:= 1081225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0918775^2 + 57570000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1081225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0918775^2 + 5757570000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1081225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0918775^2 + 575757570000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1081225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0918775^2 + 57575757570000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1081225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0918775^2 + 5757575757570000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1081225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0918775^2 + 575757575757570000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1081225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0918775^2 + 57575757575757570000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1081225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0918775^2 + 5757575757575757570000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1081225^2$ |
- 286)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0918204^2 + 572000^2$ | $:= 1081796^2$ |
| $1020\ 0918204^2 + 57772000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1081796^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0918204^2 + 5777772000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1081796^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0918204^2 + 57777772000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1081796^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0918204^2 + 577777772000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1081796^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0918204^2 + 5777777772000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1081796^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0918204^2 + 57777777772000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1081796^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0918204^2 + 577777777772000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1081796^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0918204^2 + 5777777777772000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1081796^2$ |

- 287)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0917631^2 + 574000^2 && := 1082369^2 \\
 &1020\ 0917631^2 + 57974000^2 && := 1020\ 1082369^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0917631^2 + 5797974000^2 && := 10203020\ 1082369^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0917631^2 + 579797974000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1082369^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0917631^2 + 57979797974000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1082369^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0917631^2 + 5797979797974000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1082369^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0917631^2 + 579797979797974000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1082369^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0917631^2 + 57979797979797974000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1082369^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0917631^2 + 5797979797979797974000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1082369^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 288)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0917056^2 + 576000^2 && := 1082944^2 \\
 &1020\ 0917056^2 + 58176000^2 && := 1020\ 1082944^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0917056^2 + 5818176000^2 && := 10203020\ 1082944^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0917056^2 + 581818176000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1082944^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0917056^2 + 58181818176000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1082944^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0917056^2 + 5818181818176000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1082944^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0917056^2 + 581818181818176000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1082944^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0917056^2 + 58181818181818176000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1082944^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0917056^2 + 5818181818181818176000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1082944^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 289)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0916479^2 + 578000^2 && := 1083521^2 \\
 &1020\ 0916479^2 + 58378000^2 && := 1020\ 1083521^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0916479^2 + 5838378000^2 && := 10203020\ 1083521^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0916479^2 + 583838378000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1083521^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0916479^2 + 58383838378000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1083521^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0916479^2 + 5838383838378000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1083521^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0916479^2 + 583838383838378000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1083521^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0916479^2 + 58383838383838378000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1083521^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0916479^2 + 5838383838383838378000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1083521^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 290)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0915900^2 + 580000^2 && := 1084100^2 \\
 &1020\ 0915900^2 + 58580000^2 && := 1020\ 1084100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0915900^2 + 5858580000^2 && := 10203020\ 1084100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0915900^2 + 585858580000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1084100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0915900^2 + 58585858580000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1084100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0915900^2 + 5858585858580000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1084100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0915900^2 + 585858585858580000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1084100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0915900^2 + 58585858585858580000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1084100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0915900^2 + 5858585858585858580000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1084100^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 291)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0915319^2 + 582000^2$ | $:= 1084681^2$ |
| $1020\ 0915319^2 + 58782000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1084681^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0915319^2 + 5878782000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1084681^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0915319^2 + 587878782000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1084681^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0915319^2 + 58787878782000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1084681^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0915319^2 + 5878787878782000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1084681^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0915319^2 + 587878787878782000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1084681^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0915319^2 + 58787878787878782000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1084681^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0915319^2 + 5878787878787878782000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1084681^2$ |
- 292)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0914736^2 + 584000^2$ | $:= 1085264^2$ |
| $1020\ 0914736^2 + 58984000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1085264^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0914736^2 + 5898984000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1085264^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0914736^2 + 589898984000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1085264^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0914736^2 + 58989898984000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1085264^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0914736^2 + 5898989898984000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1085264^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0914736^2 + 589898989898984000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1085264^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0914736^2 + 58989898989898984000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1085264^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0914736^2 + 5898989898989898984000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1085264^2$ |
- 293)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0914151^2 + 586000^2$ | $:= 1085849^2$ |
| $1020\ 0914151^2 + 59186000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1085849^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0914151^2 + 5919186000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1085849^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0914151^2 + 591919186000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1085849^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0914151^2 + 59191919186000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1085849^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0914151^2 + 5919191919186000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1085849^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0914151^2 + 591919191919186000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1085849^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0914151^2 + 59191919191919186000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1085849^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0914151^2 + 5919191919191919186000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1085849^2$ |
- 294)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0913564^2 + 588000^2$ | $:= 1086436^2$ |
| $1020\ 0913564^2 + 59388000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1086436^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0913564^2 + 5939388000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1086436^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0913564^2 + 593939388000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1086436^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0913564^2 + 59393939388000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1086436^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0913564^2 + 5939393939388000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1086436^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0913564^2 + 593939393939388000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1086436^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0913564^2 + 59393939393939388000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1086436^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0913564^2 + 5939393939393939388000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1086436^2$ |

- 295)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0912975^2 + 590000^2$ | $:= 1087025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0912975^2 + 59590000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1087025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0912975^2 + 5959590000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1087025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0912975^2 + 595959590000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1087025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0912975^2 + 59595959590000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1087025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0912975^2 + 5959595959590000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1087025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0912975^2 + 595959595959590000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1087025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0912975^2 + 59595959595959590000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1087025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0912975^2 + 5959595959595959590000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1087025^2$ |
- 296)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0912384^2 + 592000^2$ | $:= 1087616^2$ |
| $1020\ 0912384^2 + 59792000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1087616^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0912384^2 + 5979792000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1087616^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0912384^2 + 597979792000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1087616^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0912384^2 + 59797979792000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1087616^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0912384^2 + 5979797979792000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1087616^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0912384^2 + 597979797979792000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1087616^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0912384^2 + 59797979797979792000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1087616^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0912384^2 + 5979797979797979792000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1087616^2$ |
- 297)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0911791^2 + 594000^2$ | $:= 1088209^2$ |
| $1020\ 0911791^2 + 59994000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1088209^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0911791^2 + 5999994000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1088209^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0911791^2 + 59999994000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1088209^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0911791^2 + 599999994000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1088209^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0911791^2 + 5999999994000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1088209^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0911791^2 + 59999999994000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1088209^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0911791^2 + 599999999994000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1088209^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0911791^2 + 5999999999994000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1088209^2$ |
- 298)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0911196^2 + 596000^2$ | $:= 1088804^2$ |
| $1020\ 0911196^2 + 60196000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1088804^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0911196^2 + 6020196000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1088804^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0911196^2 + 602020196000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1088804^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0911196^2 + 60202020196000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1088804^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0911196^2 + 6020202020196000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1088804^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0911196^2 + 602020202020196000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1088804^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0911196^2 + 60202020202020196000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1088804^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0911196^2 + 6020202020202020196000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1088804^2$ |

- 299)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0910599^2 + 598000^2 && := 1089401^2 \\
 &1020\ 0910599^2 + 60398000^2 && := 1020\ 1089401^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0910599^2 + 6040398000^2 && := 10203020\ 1089401^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0910599^2 + 604040398000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1089401^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0910599^2 + 60404040398000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1089401^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0910599^2 + 6040404040398000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1089401^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0910599^2 + 604040404040398000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1089401^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0910599^2 + 60404040404040398000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1089401^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0910599^2 + 6040404040404040398000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1089401^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 300)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0910000^2 + 600000^2 && := 1090000^2 \\
 &1020\ 0910000^2 + 60600000^2 && := 1020\ 1090000^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0910000^2 + 6060600000^2 && := 10203020\ 1090000^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0910000^2 + 606060600000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1090000^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0910000^2 + 60606060600000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1090000^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0910000^2 + 6060606060600000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1090000^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0910000^2 + 606060606060600000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1090000^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0910000^2 + 60606060606060600000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1090000^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0910000^2 + 6060606060606060600000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1090000^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 301)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0909399^2 + 602000^2 && := 1090601^2 \\
 &1020\ 0909399^2 + 60802000^2 && := 1020\ 1090601^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0909399^2 + 6080802000^2 && := 10203020\ 1090601^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0909399^2 + 608080802000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1090601^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0909399^2 + 60808080802000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1090601^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0909399^2 + 6080808080802000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1090601^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0909399^2 + 608080808080802000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1090601^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0909399^2 + 60808080808080802000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1090601^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0909399^2 + 6080808080808080802000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1090601^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 302)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0908796^2 + 604000^2 && := 1091204^2 \\
 &1020\ 0908796^2 + 61004000^2 && := 1020\ 1091204^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0908796^2 + 6101004000^2 && := 10203020\ 1091204^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0908796^2 + 610101004000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1091204^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0908796^2 + 61010101004000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1091204^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0908796^2 + 6101010101004000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1091204^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0908796^2 + 610101010101004000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1091204^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0908796^2 + 61010101010101004000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1091204^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0908796^2 + 61010101010101004000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1091204^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 303)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0908191^2 + 606000^2$ | $:= 1091809^2$ |
| $1020\ 0908191^2 + 61206000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1091809^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0908191^2 + 6121206000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1091809^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0908191^2 + 612121206000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1091809^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0908191^2 + 61212121206000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1091809^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0908191^2 + 6121212121206000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1091809^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0908191^2 + 612121212121206000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1091809^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0908191^2 + 61212121212121206000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1091809^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0908191^2 + 6121212121212121206000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1091809^2$ |
- 304)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0907584^2 + 608000^2$ | $:= 1092416^2$ |
| $1020\ 0907584^2 + 61408000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1092416^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0907584^2 + 6141408000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1092416^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0907584^2 + 614141408000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1092416^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0907584^2 + 61414141408000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1092416^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0907584^2 + 6141414141408000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1092416^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0907584^2 + 614141414141408000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1092416^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0907584^2 + 61414141414141408000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1092416^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0907584^2 + 6141414141414141408000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1092416^2$ |
- 305)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0906975^2 + 610000^2$ | $:= 1093025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0906975^2 + 61610000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1093025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0906975^2 + 6161610000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1093025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0906975^2 + 616161610000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1093025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0906975^2 + 61616161610000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1093025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0906975^2 + 6161616161610000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1093025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0906975^2 + 616161616161610000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1093025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0906975^2 + 61616161616161610000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1093025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0906975^2 + 6161616161616161610000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1093025^2$ |
- 306)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0906364^2 + 612000^2$ | $:= 1093636^2$ |
| $1020\ 0906364^2 + 61812000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1093636^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0906364^2 + 6181812000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1093636^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0906364^2 + 618181812000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1093636^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0906364^2 + 61818181812000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1093636^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0906364^2 + 6181818181812000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1093636^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0906364^2 + 618181818181812000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1093636^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0906364^2 + 61818181818181812000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1093636^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0906364^2 + 6181818181818181812000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1093636^2$ |

- 307)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0905751^2 + 614000^2 && := 1094249^2 \\
 &1020\ 0905751^2 + 62014000^2 && := 1020\ 1094249^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0905751^2 + 6202014000^2 && := 10203020\ 1094249^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0905751^2 + 620202014000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1094249^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0905751^2 + 62020202014000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1094249^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0905751^2 + 6202020202014000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1094249^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0905751^2 + 620202020202014000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1094249^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0905751^2 + 62020202020202014000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1094249^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0905751^2 + 6202020202020202014000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1094249^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 308)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0905136^2 + 616000^2 && := 1094864^2 \\
 &1020\ 0905136^2 + 62216000^2 && := 1020\ 1094864^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0905136^2 + 6222216000^2 && := 10203020\ 1094864^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0905136^2 + 622222216000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1094864^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0905136^2 + 62222222216000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1094864^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0905136^2 + 6222222222216000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1094864^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0905136^2 + 622222222222216000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1094864^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0905136^2 + 62222222222222216000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1094864^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0905136^2 + 6222222222222222216000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1094864^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 309)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0904519^2 + 618000^2 && := 1095481^2 \\
 &1020\ 0904519^2 + 62418000^2 && := 1020\ 1095481^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0904519^2 + 6242418000^2 && := 10203020\ 1095481^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0904519^2 + 624242418000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1095481^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0904519^2 + 62424242418000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1095481^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0904519^2 + 6242424242418000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1095481^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0904519^2 + 624242424242418000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1095481^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0904519^2 + 62424242424242418000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1095481^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0904519^2 + 6242424242424242418000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1095481^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 310)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0903900^2 + 620000^2 && := 1096100^2 \\
 &1020\ 0903900^2 + 62620000^2 && := 1020\ 1096100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0903900^2 + 6262620000^2 && := 10203020\ 1096100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0903900^2 + 626262620000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1096100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0903900^2 + 62626262620000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1096100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0903900^2 + 6262626262620000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1096100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0903900^2 + 626262626262620000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1096100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0903900^2 + 62626262626262620000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1096100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0903900^2 + 62626262626262620000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1096100^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 311)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0903279^2 + 622000^2 && := 1096721^2 \\ &1020\ 0903279^2 + 62822000^2 && := 1020\ 1096721^2 \\ &10203020\ 0903279^2 + 6282822000^2 && := 10203020\ 1096721^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0903279^2 + 628282822000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1096721^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0903279^2 + 62828282822000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1096721^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0903279^2 + 6282828282822000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1096721^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0903279^2 + 628282828282822000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1096721^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0903279^2 + 628282828282822000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1096721^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0903279^2 + 628282828282822000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1096721^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 312)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0902656^2 + 624000^2 && := 1097344^2 \\ &1020\ 0902656^2 + 63024000^2 && := 1020\ 1097344^2 \\ &10203020\ 0902656^2 + 6303024000^2 && := 10203020\ 1097344^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0902656^2 + 630303024000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1097344^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0902656^2 + 63030303024000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1097344^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0902656^2 + 6303030303024000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1097344^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0902656^2 + 630303030303024000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1097344^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0902656^2 + 63030303030303024000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1097344^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0902656^2 + 6303030303030303024000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1097344^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 313)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0902031^2 + 626000^2 && := 1097969^2 \\ &1020\ 0902031^2 + 63226000^2 && := 1020\ 1097969^2 \\ &10203020\ 0902031^2 + 6323226000^2 && := 10203020\ 1097969^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0902031^2 + 632323226000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1097969^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0902031^2 + 63232323226000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1097969^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0902031^2 + 6323232323226000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1097969^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0902031^2 + 632323232323226000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1097969^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0902031^2 + 632323232323226000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1097969^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0902031^2 + 63232323232323226000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1097969^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 314)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0901404^2 + 628000^2 && := 1098596^2 \\ &1020\ 0901404^2 + 63428000^2 && := 1020\ 1098596^2 \\ &10203020\ 0901404^2 + 6343428000^2 && := 10203020\ 1098596^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0901404^2 + 634343428000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1098596^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0901404^2 + 63434343428000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1098596^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0901404^2 + 6343434343428000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1098596^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0901404^2 + 634343434343428000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1098596^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0901404^2 + 634343434343428000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1098596^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0901404^2 + 63434343434343428000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1098596^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 315)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0900775^2 + 630000^2 && := 1099225^2 \\ &1020\ 0900775^2 + 63630000^2 && := 1020\ 1099225^2 \\ &10203020\ 0900775^2 + 6363630000^2 && := 10203020\ 1099225^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0900775^2 + 636363630000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1099225^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0900775^2 + 63636363630000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1099225^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0900775^2 + 6363636363630000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1099225^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0900775^2 + 636363636363630000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1099225^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0900775^2 + 63636363636363630000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1099225^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0900775^2 + 6363636363636363630000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1099225^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 316)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0900144^2 + 632000^2 && := 1099856^2 \\ &1020\ 0900144^2 + 63832000^2 && := 1020\ 1099856^2 \\ &10203020\ 0900144^2 + 6383832000^2 && := 10203020\ 1099856^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0900144^2 + 638383832000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1099856^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0900144^2 + 63838383832000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1099856^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0900144^2 + 6383838383832000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1099856^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0900144^2 + 638383838383832000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1099856^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0900144^2 + 63838383838383832000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1099856^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0900144^2 + 6383838383838383832000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1099856^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 317)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0899511^2 + 634000^2 && := 1100489^2 \\ &1020\ 0899511^2 + 64034000^2 && := 1020\ 1100489^2 \\ &10203020\ 0899511^2 + 6404034000^2 && := 10203020\ 1100489^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0899511^2 + 640404034000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1100489^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0899511^2 + 64040404034000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1100489^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0899511^2 + 6404040404034000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1100489^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0899511^2 + 640404040404034000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1100489^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0899511^2 + 64040404040404034000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1100489^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0899511^2 + 64040404040404034000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1100489^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 318)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0898876^2 + 636000^2 && := 1101124^2 \\ &1020\ 0898876^2 + 64236000^2 && := 1020\ 1101124^2 \\ &10203020\ 0898876^2 + 6424236000^2 && := 10203020\ 1101124^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0898876^2 + 642424236000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1101124^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0898876^2 + 64242424236000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1101124^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0898876^2 + 6424242424236000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1101124^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0898876^2 + 642424242424236000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1101124^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0898876^2 + 64242424242424236000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1101124^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0898876^2 + 64242424242424236000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1101124^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 319)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0898239^2 + 638000^2 && := 1101761^2 \\ &1020\ 0898239^2 + 64438000^2 && := 1020\ 1101761^2 \\ &10203020\ 0898239^2 + 6444438000^2 && := 10203020\ 1101761^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0898239^2 + 644444438000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1101761^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0898239^2 + 64444444438000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1101761^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0898239^2 + 6444444444438000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1101761^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0898239^2 + 644444444444438000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1101761^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0898239^2 + 64444444444444438000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1101761^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0898239^2 + 6444444444444444438000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1101761^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 320)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0897600^2 + 640000^2 && := 1102400^2 \\ &1020\ 0897600^2 + 64640000^2 && := 1020\ 1102400^2 \\ &10203020\ 0897600^2 + 6464640000^2 && := 10203020\ 1102400^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0897600^2 + 646464640000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1102400^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0897600^2 + 64646464640000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1102400^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0897600^2 + 6464646464640000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1102400^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0897600^2 + 646464646464640000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1102400^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0897600^2 + 64646464646464640000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1102400^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0897600^2 + 6464646464646464640000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1102400^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 321)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0896959^2 + 642000^2 && := 1103041^2 \\ &1020\ 0896959^2 + 64842000^2 && := 1020\ 1103041^2 \\ &10203020\ 0896959^2 + 6484842000^2 && := 10203020\ 1103041^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0896959^2 + 648484842000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1103041^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0896959^2 + 64848484842000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1103041^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0896959^2 + 6484848484842000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1103041^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0896959^2 + 648484848484842000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1103041^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0896959^2 + 64848484848484842000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1103041^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0896959^2 + 6484848484848484842000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1103041^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 322)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0896316^2 + 644000^2 && := 1103684^2 \\ &1020\ 0896316^2 + 65044000^2 && := 1020\ 1103684^2 \\ &10203020\ 0896316^2 + 6505044000^2 && := 10203020\ 1103684^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0896316^2 + 650505044000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1103684^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0896316^2 + 65050505044000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1103684^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0896316^2 + 6505050505044000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1103684^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0896316^2 + 650505050505044000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1103684^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0896316^2 + 65050505050505044000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1103684^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0896316^2 + 6505050505050505044000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1103684^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 323)
- $$0895671^2 + 646000^2 := 1104329^2$$
- $$1020\ 0895671^2 + 65246000^2 := 1020\ 1104329^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0895671^2 + 6525246000^2 := 10203020\ 1104329^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0895671^2 + 652525246000^2 := 102030403020\ 1104329^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0895671^2 + 65252525246000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1104329^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0895671^2 + 6525252525246000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1104329^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0895671^2 + 652525252525246000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1104329^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0895671^2 + 65252525252525246000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1104329^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0895671^2 + 6525252525252525246000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1104329^2$$
- 324)
- $$0895024^2 + 648000^2 := 1104976^2$$
- $$1020\ 0895024^2 + 65448000^2 := 1020\ 1104976^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0895024^2 + 6545448000^2 := 10203020\ 1104976^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0895024^2 + 654545448000^2 := 102030403020\ 1104976^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0895024^2 + 65454545448000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1104976^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0895024^2 + 6545454545448000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1104976^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0895024^2 + 654545454545448000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1104976^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0895024^2 + 65454545454545448000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1104976^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0895024^2 + 6545454545454545448000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1104976^2$$
- 325)
- $$0894375^2 + 650000^2 := 1105625^2$$
- $$1020\ 0894375^2 + 65650000^2 := 1020\ 1105625^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0894375^2 + 6565650000^2 := 10203020\ 1105625^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0894375^2 + 656565650000^2 := 102030403020\ 1105625^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0894375^2 + 65656565650000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1105625^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0894375^2 + 6565656565650000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1105625^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0894375^2 + 656565656565650000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1105625^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0894375^2 + 65656565656565650000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1105625^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0894375^2 + 6565656565656565650000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1105625^2$$
- 326)
- $$0893724^2 + 652000^2 := 1106276^2$$
- $$1020\ 0893724^2 + 65852000^2 := 1020\ 1106276^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0893724^2 + 6585852000^2 := 10203020\ 1106276^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0893724^2 + 658585852000^2 := 102030403020\ 1106276^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0893724^2 + 65858585852000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1106276^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0893724^2 + 6585858585852000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1106276^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0893724^2 + 658585858585852000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1106276^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0893724^2 + 65858585858585852000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1106276^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0893724^2 + 6585858585858585852000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1106276^2$$

- 327)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0893071^2 + 654000^2 & := & 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0893071^2 + 66054000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0893071^2 + 6606054000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0893071^2 + 660606054000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0893071^2 + 66060606054000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0893071^2 + 6606060606054000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0893071^2 + 660606060606054000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0893071^2 + 66060606060606054000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1106929^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0893071^2 + 6606060606060606054000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1106929^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 328)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0892416^2 + 656000^2 & := & 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0892416^2 + 66256000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0892416^2 + 6626256000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0892416^2 + 662626256000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0892416^2 + 66262626256000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0892416^2 + 6626262626256000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0892416^2 + 662626262626256000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0892416^2 + 66262626262626256000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1107584^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0892416^2 + 6626262626262626256000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1107584^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 329)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0891759^2 + 658000^2 & := & 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0891759^2 + 66458000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0891759^2 + 6646458000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0891759^2 + 664646458000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0891759^2 + 66464646458000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0891759^2 + 6646464646458000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0891759^2 + 664646464646458000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0891759^2 + 66464646464646458000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1108241^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0891759^2 + 6646464646464646458000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1108241^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 330)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0891100^2 + 660000^2 & := & 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0891100^2 + 66660000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0891100^2 + 6666660000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0891100^2 + 666666660000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0891100^2 + 66666666660000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0891100^2 + 6666666666660000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0891100^2 + 666666666666660000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0891100^2 + 66666666666666660000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1108900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0891100^2 + 6666666666666666660000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1108900^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 331)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0890439^2 + 662000^2 && := 1109561^2 \\
 &1020\ 0890439^2 + 66862000^2 && := 1020\ 1109561^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0890439^2 + 6686862000^2 && := 10203020\ 1109561^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0890439^2 + 668686862000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1109561^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0890439^2 + 66868686862000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1109561^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0890439^2 + 6686868686862000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1109561^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0890439^2 + 668686868686862000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1109561^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0890439^2 + 66868686868686862000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1109561^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0890439^2 + 6686868686868686862000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1109561^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 332)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0889776^2 + 664000^2 && := 1110224^2 \\
 &1020\ 0889776^2 + 67064000^2 && := 1020\ 1110224^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0889776^2 + 6707064000^2 && := 10203020\ 1110224^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0889776^2 + 670707064000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1110224^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0889776^2 + 67070707064000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1110224^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0889776^2 + 6707070707064000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1110224^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0889776^2 + 670707070707064000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1110224^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0889776^2 + 67070707070707064000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1110224^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0889776^2 + 6707070707070707064000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1110224^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 333)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0889111^2 + 666000^2 && := 1110889^2 \\
 &1020\ 0889111^2 + 67266000^2 && := 1020\ 1110889^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0889111^2 + 6727266000^2 && := 10203020\ 1110889^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0889111^2 + 672727266000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1110889^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0889111^2 + 67272727266000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1110889^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0889111^2 + 6727272727266000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1110889^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0889111^2 + 672727272727266000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1110889^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0889111^2 + 67272727272727266000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1110889^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0889111^2 + 6727272727272727266000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1110889^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 334)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0888444^2 + 668000^2 && := 1111556^2 \\
 &1020\ 0888444^2 + 67468000^2 && := 1020\ 1111556^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0888444^2 + 6747468000^2 && := 10203020\ 1111556^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0888444^2 + 674747468000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1111556^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0888444^2 + 67474747468000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1111556^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0888444^2 + 6747474747468000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1111556^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0888444^2 + 674747474747468000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1111556^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0888444^2 + 67474747474747468000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1111556^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0888444^2 + 6747474747474747468000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1111556^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 335)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0887775^2 + 670000^2 && := 1112225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0887775^2 + 67670000^2 && := 1020\ 1112225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0887775^2 + 6767670000^2 && := 10203020\ 1112225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0887775^2 + 676767670000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1112225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0887775^2 + 67676767670000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1112225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0887775^2 + 6767676767670000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1112225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0887775^2 + 676767676767670000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1112225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0887775^2 + 67676767676767670000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1112225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0887775^2 + 6767676767676767670000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1112225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 336)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0887104^2 + 672000^2 && := 1112896^2 \\
 &1020\ 0887104^2 + 67872000^2 && := 1020\ 1112896^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0887104^2 + 6787872000^2 && := 10203020\ 1112896^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0887104^2 + 678787872000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1112896^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0887104^2 + 67878787872000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1112896^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0887104^2 + 6787878787872000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1112896^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0887104^2 + 678787878787872000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1112896^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0887104^2 + 67878787878787872000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1112896^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0887104^2 + 6787878787878787872000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1112896^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 337)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0886431^2 + 674000^2 && := 1113569^2 \\
 &1020\ 0886431^2 + 68074000^2 && := 1020\ 1113569^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0886431^2 + 6808074000^2 && := 10203020\ 1113569^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0886431^2 + 680808074000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1113569^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0886431^2 + 68080808074000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1113569^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0886431^2 + 6808080808074000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1113569^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0886431^2 + 680808080808074000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1113569^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0886431^2 + 68080808080808074000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1113569^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0886431^2 + 6808080808080808074000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1113569^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 338)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0885756^2 + 676000^2 && := 1114244^2 \\
 &1020\ 0885756^2 + 68276000^2 && := 1020\ 1114244^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0885756^2 + 6828276000^2 && := 10203020\ 1114244^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0885756^2 + 682828276000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1114244^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0885756^2 + 68282828276000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1114244^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0885756^2 + 6828282828276000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1114244^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0885756^2 + 682828282828276000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1114244^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0885756^2 + 68282828282828276000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1114244^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0885756^2 + 68282828282828276000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1114244^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 339)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0885079^2 + 678000^2 & := & 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0885079^2 + 68478000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0885079^2 + 6848478000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0885079^2 + 684848478000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0885079^2 + 68484848478000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0885079^2 + 6848484848478000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0885079^2 + 684848484848478000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0885079^2 + 68484848484848478000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1114921^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0885079^2 + 6848484848484848478000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1114921^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 340)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0884400^2 + 680000^2 & := & 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0884400^2 + 68680000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0884400^2 + 6868680000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0884400^2 + 686868680000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0884400^2 + 68686868680000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0884400^2 + 6868686868680000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0884400^2 + 686868686868680000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0884400^2 + 68686868686868680000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1115600^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0884400^2 + 6868686868686868680000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1115600^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 341)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0883719^2 + 682000^2 & := & 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0883719^2 + 68882000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0883719^2 + 6888882000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0883719^2 + 68888882000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0883719^2 + 688888882000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0883719^2 + 6888888882000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0883719^2 + 68888888882000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0883719^2 + 688888888882000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1116281^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0883719^2 + 6888888888882000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1116281^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 342)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0883036^2 + 684000^2 & := & 1116964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0883036^2 + 69084000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1116964^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0883036^2 + 6909084000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1116964^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0883036^2 + 690909084000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1116964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0883036^2 + 69090909084000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1116964^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0883036^2 + 6909090909084000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1116964^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0883036^2 + 690909090909084000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1116964^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0883036^2 + 69090909090909084000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1116964^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0883036^2 + 6909090909090909084000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1116964^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 343)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0882351^2 + 686000^2 && := 1117649^2 \\
 &1020\ 0882351^2 + 69286000^2 && := 1020\ 1117649^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0882351^2 + 6929286000^2 && := 10203020\ 1117649^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0882351^2 + 692929286000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1117649^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0882351^2 + 69292929286000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1117649^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0882351^2 + 6929292929286000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1117649^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0882351^2 + 692929292929286000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1117649^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0882351^2 + 69292929292929286000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1117649^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0882351^2 + 6929292929292929286000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1117649^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 344)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0881664^2 + 688000^2 && := 1118336^2 \\
 &1020\ 0881664^2 + 69488000^2 && := 1020\ 1118336^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0881664^2 + 6949488000^2 && := 10203020\ 1118336^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0881664^2 + 694949488000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1118336^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0881664^2 + 69494949488000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1118336^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0881664^2 + 6949494949488000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1118336^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0881664^2 + 694949494949488000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1118336^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0881664^2 + 69494949494949488000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1118336^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0881664^2 + 6949494949494949488000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1118336^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 345)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0880975^2 + 690000^2 && := 1119025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0880975^2 + 69690000^2 && := 1020\ 1119025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0880975^2 + 6969690000^2 && := 10203020\ 1119025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0880975^2 + 696969690000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1119025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0880975^2 + 69696969690000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1119025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0880975^2 + 6969696969690000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1119025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0880975^2 + 696969696969690000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1119025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0880975^2 + 69696969696969690000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1119025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0880975^2 + 6969696969696969690000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1119025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 346)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0880284^2 + 692000^2 && := 1119716^2 \\
 &1020\ 0880284^2 + 69892000^2 && := 1020\ 1119716^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0880284^2 + 6989892000^2 && := 10203020\ 1119716^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0880284^2 + 698989892000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1119716^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0880284^2 + 69898989892000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1119716^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0880284^2 + 6989898989892000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1119716^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0880284^2 + 698989898989892000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1119716^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0880284^2 + 69898989898989892000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1119716^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0880284^2 + 6989898989898989892000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1119716^2
 \end{aligned}$$

347)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0879591^2 + 694000^2 && := 1120409^2 \\
 &1020\ 0879591^2 + 70094000^2 && := 1020\ 1120409^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0879591^2 + 7010094000^2 && := 10203020\ 1120409^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0879591^2 + 701010094000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1120409^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0879591^2 + 70101010094000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1120409^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0879591^2 + 7010101010094000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1120409^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0879591^2 + 701010101010094000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1120409^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0879591^2 + 70101010101010094000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1120409^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0879591^2 + 7010101010101010094000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1120409^2
 \end{aligned}$$

348)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0878896^2 + 696000^2 && := 1121104^2 \\
 &1020\ 0878896^2 + 70296000^2 && := 1020\ 1121104^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0878896^2 + 7030296000^2 && := 10203020\ 1121104^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0878896^2 + 703030296000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1121104^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0878896^2 + 70303030296000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1121104^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0878896^2 + 7030303030296000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1121104^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0878896^2 + 703030303030296000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1121104^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0878896^2 + 70303030303030296000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1121104^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0878896^2 + 7030303030303030296000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1121104^2
 \end{aligned}$$

349)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0878199^2 + 698000^2 && := 1121801^2 \\
 &1020\ 0878199^2 + 70498000^2 && := 1020\ 1121801^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0878199^2 + 7050498000^2 && := 10203020\ 1121801^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0878199^2 + 705050498000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1121801^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0878199^2 + 70505050498000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1121801^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0878199^2 + 7050505050498000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1121801^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0878199^2 + 705050505050498000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1121801^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0878199^2 + 70505050505050498000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1121801^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0878199^2 + 7050505050505050498000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1121801^2
 \end{aligned}$$

350)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0877500^2 + 700000^2 && := 1122500^2 \\
 &1020\ 0877500^2 + 70700000^2 && := 1020\ 1122500^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0877500^2 + 7070700000^2 && := 10203020\ 1122500^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0877500^2 + 707070700000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1122500^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0877500^2 + 70707070700000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1122500^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0877500^2 + 7070707070700000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1122500^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0877500^2 + 707070707070700000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1122500^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0877500^2 + 707070707070700000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1122500^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0877500^2 + 70707070707070700000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1122500^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 351)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0876799^2 + 702000^2 && := 1123201^2 \\
 &1020\ 0876799^2 + 70902000^2 && := 1020\ 1123201^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0876799^2 + 7090902000^2 && := 10203020\ 1123201^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0876799^2 + 709090902000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1123201^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0876799^2 + 70909090902000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1123201^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0876799^2 + 7090909090902000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1123201^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0876799^2 + 709090909090902000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1123201^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0876799^2 + 70909090909090902000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1123201^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0876799^2 + 7090909090909090902000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1123201^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 352)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0876096^2 + 704000^2 && := 1123904^2 \\
 &1020\ 0876096^2 + 71104000^2 && := 1020\ 1123904^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0876096^2 + 7111104000^2 && := 10203020\ 1123904^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0876096^2 + 711111104000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1123904^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0876096^2 + 71111111104000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1123904^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0876096^2 + 7111111111104000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1123904^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0876096^2 + 711111111111104000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1123904^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0876096^2 + 71111111111111104000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1123904^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0876096^2 + 7111111111111111104000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1123904^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 353)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0875391^2 + 706000^2 && := 1124609^2 \\
 &1020\ 0875391^2 + 71306000^2 && := 1020\ 1124609^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0875391^2 + 7131306000^2 && := 10203020\ 1124609^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0875391^2 + 713131306000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1124609^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0875391^2 + 71313131306000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1124609^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0875391^2 + 7131313131306000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1124609^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0875391^2 + 713131313131306000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1124609^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0875391^2 + 71313131313131306000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1124609^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0875391^2 + 7131313131313131306000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1124609^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 354)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0874684^2 + 708000^2 && := 1125316^2 \\
 &1020\ 0874684^2 + 71508000^2 && := 1020\ 1125316^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0874684^2 + 7151508000^2 && := 10203020\ 1125316^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0874684^2 + 715151508000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1125316^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0874684^2 + 71515151508000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1125316^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0874684^2 + 7151515151508000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1125316^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0874684^2 + 715151515151508000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1125316^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0874684^2 + 71515151515151508000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1125316^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0874684^2 + 7151515151515151508000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1125316^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 355)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0873975^2 + 710000^2$ | $:= 1126025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0873975^2 + 71710000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1126025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0873975^2 + 7171710000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1126025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0873975^2 + 717171710000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1126025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0873975^2 + 71717171710000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1126025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0873975^2 + 7171717171710000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1126025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0873975^2 + 717171717171710000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1126025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0873975^2 + 71717171717171710000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1126025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0873975^2 + 7171717171717171710000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1126025^2$ |
- 356)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0873264^2 + 712000^2$ | $:= 1126736^2$ |
| $1020\ 0873264^2 + 71912000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1126736^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0873264^2 + 7191912000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1126736^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0873264^2 + 719191912000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1126736^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0873264^2 + 71919191912000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1126736^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0873264^2 + 7191919191912000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1126736^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0873264^2 + 719191919191912000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1126736^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0873264^2 + 71919191919191912000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1126736^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0873264^2 + 7191919191919191912000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1126736^2$ |
- 357)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0872551^2 + 714000^2$ | $:= 1127449^2$ |
| $1020\ 0872551^2 + 72114000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1127449^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0872551^2 + 7212114000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1127449^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0872551^2 + 721212114000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1127449^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0872551^2 + 72121212114000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1127449^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0872551^2 + 7212121212114000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1127449^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0872551^2 + 721212121212114000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1127449^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0872551^2 + 721212121212114000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1127449^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0872551^2 + 72121212121212114000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1127449^2$ |
- 358)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0871836^2 + 716000^2$ | $:= 1128164^2$ |
| $1020\ 0871836^2 + 72316000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1128164^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0871836^2 + 7232316000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1128164^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0871836^2 + 723232316000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1128164^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0871836^2 + 72323232316000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1128164^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0871836^2 + 7232323232316000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1128164^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0871836^2 + 723232323232316000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1128164^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0871836^2 + 72323232323232316000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1128164^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0871836^2 + 72323232323232316000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1128164^2$ |

- 359)
- $$0871119^2 + 718000^2 := 1128881^2$$
- $$1020\ 0871119^2 + 72518000^2 := 1020\ 1128881^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0871119^2 + 7252518000^2 := 10203020\ 1128881^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0871119^2 + 725252518000^2 := 102030403020\ 1128881^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0871119^2 + 72525252518000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1128881^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0871119^2 + 7252525252518000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1128881^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0871119^2 + 725252525252518000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1128881^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0871119^2 + 72525252525252518000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1128881^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0871119^2 + 7252525252525252518000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1128881^2$$
- 360)
- $$0870400^2 + 720000^2 := 1129600^2$$
- $$1020\ 0870400^2 + 72720000^2 := 1020\ 1129600^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0870400^2 + 7272720000^2 := 10203020\ 1129600^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0870400^2 + 727272720000^2 := 102030403020\ 1129600^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0870400^2 + 72727272720000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1129600^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0870400^2 + 7272727272720000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1129600^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0870400^2 + 727272727272720000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1129600^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0870400^2 + 72727272727272720000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1129600^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0870400^2 + 7272727272727272720000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1129600^2$$
- 361)
- $$0869679^2 + 722000^2 := 1130321^2$$
- $$1020\ 0869679^2 + 72922000^2 := 1020\ 1130321^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0869679^2 + 7292922000^2 := 10203020\ 1130321^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0869679^2 + 729292922000^2 := 102030403020\ 1130321^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0869679^2 + 72929292922000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1130321^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0869679^2 + 7292929292922000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1130321^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0869679^2 + 729292929292922000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1130321^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0869679^2 + 72929292929292922000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1130321^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0869679^2 + 7292929292929292922000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1130321^2$$
- 362)
- $$0868956^2 + 724000^2 := 1131044^2$$
- $$1020\ 0868956^2 + 73124000^2 := 1020\ 1131044^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0868956^2 + 7313124000^2 := 10203020\ 1131044^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0868956^2 + 731313124000^2 := 102030403020\ 1131044^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0868956^2 + 73131313124000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1131044^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0868956^2 + 7313131313124000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1131044^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0868956^2 + 731313131313124000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1131044^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0868956^2 + 73131313131313124000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1131044^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0868956^2 + 7313131313131313124000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1131044^2$$

363)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0868231^2 + 726000^2 && := 1131769^2 \\
 &1020\ 0868231^2 + 73326000^2 && := 1020\ 1131769^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0868231^2 + 7333326000^2 && := 10203020\ 1131769^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0868231^2 + 733333326000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1131769^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0868231^2 + 73333333326000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1131769^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0868231^2 + 7333333333326000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1131769^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0868231^2 + 733333333333326000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1131769^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0868231^2 + 73333333333333326000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1131769^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0868231^2 + 7333333333333333326000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1131769^2
 \end{aligned}$$

364)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0867504^2 + 728000^2 && := 1132496^2 \\
 &1020\ 0867504^2 + 73528000^2 && := 1020\ 1132496^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0867504^2 + 7353528000^2 && := 10203020\ 1132496^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0867504^2 + 735353528000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1132496^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0867504^2 + 73535353528000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1132496^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0867504^2 + 7353535353528000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1132496^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0867504^2 + 735353535353528000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1132496^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0867504^2 + 73535353535353528000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1132496^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0867504^2 + 7353535353535353528000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1132496^2
 \end{aligned}$$

365)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0866775^2 + 730000^2 && := 1133225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0866775^2 + 73730000^2 && := 1020\ 1133225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0866775^2 + 7373730000^2 && := 10203020\ 1133225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0866775^2 + 737373730000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1133225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0866775^2 + 73737373730000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1133225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0866775^2 + 7373737373730000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1133225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0866775^2 + 737373737373730000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1133225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0866775^2 + 73737373737373730000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1133225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0866775^2 + 7373737373737373730000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1133225^2
 \end{aligned}$$

366)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0866044^2 + 732000^2 && := 1133956^2 \\
 &1020\ 0866044^2 + 73932000^2 && := 1020\ 1133956^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0866044^2 + 7393932000^2 && := 10203020\ 1133956^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0866044^2 + 739393932000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1133956^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0866044^2 + 73939393932000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1133956^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0866044^2 + 7393939393932000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1133956^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0866044^2 + 739393939393932000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1133956^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0866044^2 + 73939393939393932000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1133956^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0866044^2 + 7393939393939393932000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1133956^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 367)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0865311^2 + 734000^2 && := 1134689^2 \\
 &1020\ 0865311^2 + 74134000^2 && := 1020\ 1134689^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0865311^2 + 7414134000^2 && := 10203020\ 1134689^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0865311^2 + 741414134000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1134689^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0865311^2 + 74141414134000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1134689^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0865311^2 + 7414141414134000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1134689^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0865311^2 + 741414141414134000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1134689^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0865311^2 + 74141414141414134000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1134689^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0865311^2 + 7414141414141414134000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1134689^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 368)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0864576^2 + 736000^2 && := 1135424^2 \\
 &1020\ 0864576^2 + 74336000^2 && := 1020\ 1135424^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0864576^2 + 7434336000^2 && := 10203020\ 1135424^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0864576^2 + 743434336000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1135424^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0864576^2 + 74343434336000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1135424^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0864576^2 + 7434343434336000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1135424^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0864576^2 + 743434343434336000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1135424^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0864576^2 + 74343434343434336000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1135424^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0864576^2 + 7434343434343434336000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1135424^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 369)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0863839^2 + 738000^2 && := 1136161^2 \\
 &1020\ 0863839^2 + 74538000^2 && := 1020\ 1136161^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0863839^2 + 7454538000^2 && := 10203020\ 1136161^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0863839^2 + 745454538000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1136161^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0863839^2 + 74545454538000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1136161^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0863839^2 + 7454545454538000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1136161^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0863839^2 + 745454545454538000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1136161^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0863839^2 + 74545454545454538000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1136161^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0863839^2 + 7454545454545454538000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1136161^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 370)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0863100^2 + 740000^2 && := 1136900^2 \\
 &1020\ 0863100^2 + 74740000^2 && := 1020\ 1136900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0863100^2 + 7474740000^2 && := 10203020\ 1136900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0863100^2 + 747474740000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1136900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0863100^2 + 74747474740000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1136900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0863100^2 + 7474747474740000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1136900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0863100^2 + 747474747474740000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1136900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0863100^2 + 74747474747474740000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1136900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0863100^2 + 7474747474747474740000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1136900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 371)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0862359^2 + 742000^2 && := 1137641^2 \\ &1020\ 0862359^2 + 74942000^2 && := 1020\ 1137641^2 \\ &10203020\ 0862359^2 + 7494942000^2 && := 10203020\ 1137641^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0862359^2 + 749494942000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1137641^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0862359^2 + 74949494942000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1137641^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0862359^2 + 7494949494942000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1137641^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0862359^2 + 749494949494942000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1137641^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0862359^2 + 74949494949494942000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1137641^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0862359^2 + 7494949494949494942000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1137641^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 372)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0861616^2 + 744000^2 && := 1138384^2 \\ &1020\ 0861616^2 + 75144000^2 && := 1020\ 1138384^2 \\ &10203020\ 0861616^2 + 7515144000^2 && := 10203020\ 1138384^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0861616^2 + 751515144000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1138384^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0861616^2 + 75151515144000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1138384^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0861616^2 + 7515151515144000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1138384^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0861616^2 + 751515151515144000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1138384^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0861616^2 + 75151515151515144000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1138384^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0861616^2 + 7515151515151515144000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1138384^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 373)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0860871^2 + 746000^2 && := 1139129^2 \\ &1020\ 0860871^2 + 75346000^2 && := 1020\ 1139129^2 \\ &10203020\ 0860871^2 + 7535346000^2 && := 10203020\ 1139129^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0860871^2 + 753535346000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1139129^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0860871^2 + 75353535346000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1139129^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0860871^2 + 7535353535346000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1139129^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0860871^2 + 753535353535346000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1139129^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0860871^2 + 75353535353535346000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1139129^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0860871^2 + 7535353535353535346000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1139129^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 374)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0860124^2 + 748000^2 && := 1139876^2 \\ &1020\ 0860124^2 + 75548000^2 && := 1020\ 1139876^2 \\ &10203020\ 0860124^2 + 7555548000^2 && := 10203020\ 1139876^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0860124^2 + 755555548000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1139876^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0860124^2 + 75555555548000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1139876^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0860124^2 + 7555555555548000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1139876^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0860124^2 + 755555555555548000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1139876^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0860124^2 + 75555555555555548000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1139876^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0860124^2 + 7555555555555555548000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1139876^2 \end{aligned}$$

375)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0859375^2 + 750000^2 && := 1140625^2 \\
 &1020\ 0859375^2 + 75750000^2 && := 1020\ 1140625^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0859375^2 + 7575750000^2 && := 10203020\ 1140625^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0859375^2 + 757575750000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1140625^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0859375^2 + 75757575750000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1140625^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0859375^2 + 7575757575750000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1140625^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0859375^2 + 757575757575750000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1140625^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0859375^2 + 75757575757575750000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1140625^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0859375^2 + 7575757575757575750000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1140625^2
 \end{aligned}$$

376)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0858624^2 + 752000^2 && := 1141376^2 \\
 &1020\ 0858624^2 + 75952000^2 && := 1020\ 1141376^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0858624^2 + 7595952000^2 && := 10203020\ 1141376^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0858624^2 + 759595952000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1141376^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0858624^2 + 75959595952000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1141376^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0858624^2 + 7595959595952000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1141376^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0858624^2 + 759595959595952000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1141376^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0858624^2 + 75959595959595952000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1141376^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0858624^2 + 7595959595959595952000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1141376^2
 \end{aligned}$$

377)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0857871^2 + 754000^2 && := 1142129^2 \\
 &1020\ 0857871^2 + 76154000^2 && := 1020\ 1142129^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0857871^2 + 7616154000^2 && := 10203020\ 1142129^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0857871^2 + 761616154000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1142129^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0857871^2 + 76161616154000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1142129^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0857871^2 + 7616161616154000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1142129^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0857871^2 + 761616161616154000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1142129^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0857871^2 + 76161616161616154000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1142129^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0857871^2 + 7616161616161616154000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1142129^2
 \end{aligned}$$

378)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0857116^2 + 756000^2 && := 1142884^2 \\
 &1020\ 0857116^2 + 76356000^2 && := 1020\ 1142884^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0857116^2 + 7636356000^2 && := 10203020\ 1142884^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0857116^2 + 763636356000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1142884^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0857116^2 + 76363636356000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1142884^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0857116^2 + 7636363636356000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1142884^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0857116^2 + 763636363636356000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1142884^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0857116^2 + 76363636363636356000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1142884^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0857116^2 + 7636363636363636356000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1142884^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 379)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0856359^2 + 758000^2 && := 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0856359^2 + 76558000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0856359^2 + 7656558000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0856359^2 + 765656558000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0856359^2 + 76565656558000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0856359^2 + 7656565656558000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0856359^2 + 765656565656558000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0856359^2 + 765656565656558000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1143641^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0856359^2 + 765656565656558000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1143641^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 380)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0855600^2 + 760000^2 && := 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0855600^2 + 76760000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0855600^2 + 7676760000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0855600^2 + 767676760000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0855600^2 + 76767676760000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0855600^2 + 7676767676760000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0855600^2 + 767676767676760000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0855600^2 + 76767676767676760000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1144400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0855600^2 + 76767676767676760000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1144400^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 381)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0854839^2 + 762000^2 && := 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0854839^2 + 76962000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0854839^2 + 7696962000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0854839^2 + 769696962000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0854839^2 + 76969696962000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0854839^2 + 7696969696962000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0854839^2 + 769696969696962000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0854839^2 + 769696969696962000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1145161^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0854839^2 + 769696969696962000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1145161^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 382)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0854076^2 + 764000^2 && := 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0854076^2 + 77164000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0854076^2 + 7717164000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0854076^2 + 771717164000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0854076^2 + 77171717164000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0854076^2 + 7717171717164000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0854076^2 + 771717171717164000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0854076^2 + 77171717171717164000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1145924^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0854076^2 + 77171717171717164000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1145924^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 383)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0853311^2 + 766000^2$ | $:= 1146689^2$ |
| $1020\ 0853311^2 + 77366000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1146689^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0853311^2 + 7737366000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1146689^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0853311^2 + 773737366000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1146689^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0853311^2 + 77373737366000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1146689^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0853311^2 + 7737373737366000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1146689^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0853311^2 + 773737373737366000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1146689^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0853311^2 + 77373737373737366000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1146689^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0853311^2 + 7737373737373737366000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1146689^2$ |
- 384)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0852544^2 + 768000^2$ | $:= 1147456^2$ |
| $1020\ 0852544^2 + 77568000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1147456^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0852544^2 + 7757568000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1147456^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0852544^2 + 775757568000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1147456^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0852544^2 + 77575757568000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1147456^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0852544^2 + 7757575757568000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1147456^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0852544^2 + 775757575757568000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1147456^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0852544^2 + 77575757575757568000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1147456^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0852544^2 + 7757575757575757568000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1147456^2$ |
- 385)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0851775^2 + 770000^2$ | $:= 1148225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0851775^2 + 77770000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1148225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0851775^2 + 7777770000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1148225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0851775^2 + 777777770000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1148225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0851775^2 + 77777777770000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1148225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0851775^2 + 7777777777770000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1148225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0851775^2 + 777777777777770000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1148225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0851775^2 + 77777777777777770000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1148225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0851775^2 + 7777777777777777770000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1148225^2$ |
- 386)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0851004^2 + 772000^2$ | $:= 1148996^2$ |
| $1020\ 0851004^2 + 77972000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1148996^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0851004^2 + 7797972000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1148996^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0851004^2 + 779797972000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1148996^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0851004^2 + 77979797972000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1148996^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0851004^2 + 7797979797972000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1148996^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0851004^2 + 779797979797972000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1148996^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0851004^2 + 77979797979797972000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1148996^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0851004^2 + 7797979797979797972000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1148996^2$ |

- 387)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0850231^2 + 774000^2$ | $:= 1149769^2$ |
| $1020\ 0850231^2 + 78174000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1149769^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0850231^2 + 7818174000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1149769^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0850231^2 + 781818174000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1149769^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0850231^2 + 78181818174000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1149769^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0850231^2 + 7818181818174000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1149769^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0850231^2 + 781818181818174000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1149769^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0850231^2 + 78181818181818174000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1149769^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0850231^2 + 7818181818181818174000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1149769^2$ |
- 388)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0849456^2 + 776000^2$ | $:= 1150544^2$ |
| $1020\ 0849456^2 + 78376000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1150544^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0849456^2 + 7838376000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1150544^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0849456^2 + 783838376000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1150544^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0849456^2 + 78383838376000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1150544^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0849456^2 + 7838383838376000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1150544^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0849456^2 + 783838383838376000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1150544^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0849456^2 + 78383838383838376000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1150544^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0849456^2 + 7838383838383838376000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1150544^2$ |
- 389)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0848679^2 + 778000^2$ | $:= 1151321^2$ |
| $1020\ 0848679^2 + 78578000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1151321^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0848679^2 + 7858578000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1151321^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0848679^2 + 785858578000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1151321^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0848679^2 + 78585858578000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1151321^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0848679^2 + 7858585858578000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1151321^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0848679^2 + 785858585858578000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1151321^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0848679^2 + 78585858585858578000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1151321^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0848679^2 + 7858585858585858578000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1151321^2$ |
- 390)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0847900^2 + 780000^2$ | $:= 1152100^2$ |
| $1020\ 0847900^2 + 78780000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1152100^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0847900^2 + 7878780000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1152100^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0847900^2 + 787878780000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1152100^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0847900^2 + 78787878780000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1152100^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0847900^2 + 7878787878780000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1152100^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0847900^2 + 787878787878780000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1152100^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0847900^2 + 78787878787878780000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1152100^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0847900^2 + 7878787878787878780000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1152100^2$ |

- 391)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0847119^2 + 782000^2$ | $:= 1152881^2$ |
| $1020\ 0847119^2 + 78982000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1152881^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0847119^2 + 7898982000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1152881^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0847119^2 + 789898982000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1152881^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0847119^2 + 78989898982000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1152881^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0847119^2 + 7898989898982000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1152881^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0847119^2 + 789898989898982000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1152881^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0847119^2 + 789898989898982000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1152881^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0847119^2 + 78989898989898982000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1152881^2$ |
- 392)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0846336^2 + 784000^2$ | $:= 1153664^2$ |
| $1020\ 0846336^2 + 79184000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1153664^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0846336^2 + 7919184000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1153664^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0846336^2 + 791919184000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1153664^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0846336^2 + 79191919184000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1153664^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0846336^2 + 7919191919184000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1153664^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0846336^2 + 791919191919184000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1153664^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0846336^2 + 79191919191919184000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1153664^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0846336^2 + 7919191919191919184000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1153664^2$ |
- 393)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0845551^2 + 786000^2$ | $:= 1154449^2$ |
| $1020\ 0845551^2 + 79386000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1154449^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0845551^2 + 7939386000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1154449^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0845551^2 + 793939386000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1154449^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0845551^2 + 79393939386000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1154449^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0845551^2 + 7939393939386000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1154449^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0845551^2 + 793939393939386000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1154449^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0845551^2 + 79393939393939386000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1154449^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0845551^2 + 7939393939393939386000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1154449^2$ |
- 394)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0844764^2 + 788000^2$ | $:= 1155236^2$ |
| $1020\ 0844764^2 + 79588000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1155236^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0844764^2 + 7959588000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1155236^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0844764^2 + 795959588000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1155236^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0844764^2 + 79595959588000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1155236^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0844764^2 + 7959595959588000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1155236^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0844764^2 + 795959595959588000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1155236^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0844764^2 + 79595959595959588000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1155236^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0844764^2 + 7959595959595959588000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1155236^2$ |

- 395)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0843975^2 + 790000^2$ | $:= 1156025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0843975^2 + 79790000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1156025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0843975^2 + 7979790000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1156025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0843975^2 + 797979790000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1156025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0843975^2 + 79797979790000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1156025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0843975^2 + 7979797979790000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1156025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0843975^2 + 797979797979790000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1156025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0843975^2 + 79797979797979790000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1156025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0843975^2 + 7979797979797979790000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1156025^2$ |
- 396)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0843184^2 + 792000^2$ | $:= 1156816^2$ |
| $1020\ 0843184^2 + 79992000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1156816^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0843184^2 + 7999992000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1156816^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0843184^2 + 799999992000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1156816^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0843184^2 + 79999999992000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1156816^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0843184^2 + 7999999999992000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1156816^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0843184^2 + 799999999999992000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1156816^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0843184^2 + 79999999999999992000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1156816^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0843184^2 + 7999999999999999992000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1156816^2$ |
- 397)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0842391^2 + 794000^2$ | $:= 1157609^2$ |
| $1020\ 0842391^2 + 80194000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1157609^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0842391^2 + 8020194000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1157609^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0842391^2 + 802020194000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1157609^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0842391^2 + 80202020194000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1157609^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0842391^2 + 8020202020194000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1157609^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0842391^2 + 802020202020194000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1157609^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0842391^2 + 80202020202020194000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1157609^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0842391^2 + 8020202020202020194000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1157609^2$ |
- 398)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0841596^2 + 796000^2$ | $:= 1158404^2$ |
| $1020\ 0841596^2 + 80396000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1158404^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0841596^2 + 8040396000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1158404^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0841596^2 + 804040396000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1158404^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0841596^2 + 80404040396000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1158404^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0841596^2 + 8040404040396000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1158404^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0841596^2 + 804040404040396000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1158404^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0841596^2 + 80404040404040396000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1158404^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0841596^2 + 8040404040404040396000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1158404^2$ |

- 399)
- $$0840799^2 + 798000^2 := 1159201^2$$
- $$1020\ 0840799^2 + 80598000^2 := 1020\ 1159201^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0840799^2 + 8060598000^2 := 10203020\ 1159201^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0840799^2 + 806060598000^2 := 102030403020\ 1159201^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0840799^2 + 80606060598000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1159201^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0840799^2 + 8060606060598000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1159201^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0840799^2 + 806060606060598000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1159201^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0840799^2 + 80606060606060598000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1159201^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0840799^2 + 8060606060606060598000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1159201^2$$
- 400)
- $$0840000^2 + 800000^2 := 1160000^2$$
- $$1020\ 0840000^2 + 80800000^2 := 1020\ 1160000^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0840000^2 + 8080800000^2 := 10203020\ 1160000^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0840000^2 + 808080800000^2 := 102030403020\ 1160000^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0840000^2 + 80808080800000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1160000^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0840000^2 + 8080808080800000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1160000^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0840000^2 + 808080808080800000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1160000^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0840000^2 + 80808080808080800000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1160000^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0840000^2 + 8080808080808080800000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1160000^2$$
- 401)
- $$0839199^2 + 802000^2 := 1160801^2$$
- $$1020\ 0839199^2 + 81002000^2 := 1020\ 1160801^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0839199^2 + 8101002000^2 := 10203020\ 1160801^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0839199^2 + 810101002000^2 := 102030403020\ 1160801^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0839199^2 + 81010101002000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1160801^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0839199^2 + 8101010101002000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1160801^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0839199^2 + 810101010101002000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1160801^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0839199^2 + 81010101010101002000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1160801^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0839199^2 + 81010101010101002000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1160801^2$$
- 402)
- $$0838396^2 + 804000^2 := 1161604^2$$
- $$1020\ 0838396^2 + 81204000^2 := 1020\ 1161604^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0838396^2 + 8121204000^2 := 10203020\ 1161604^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0838396^2 + 812121204000^2 := 102030403020\ 1161604^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0838396^2 + 81212121204000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1161604^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0838396^2 + 8121212121204000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1161604^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0838396^2 + 812121212121204000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1161604^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0838396^2 + 81212121212121204000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1161604^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0838396^2 + 81212121212121204000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1161604^2$$

- 403)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0837591^2 + 806000^2 && := 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0837591^2 + 81406000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0837591^2 + 8141406000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0837591^2 + 814141406000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0837591^2 + 81414141406000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0837591^2 + 8141414141406000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0837591^2 + 814141414141406000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0837591^2 + 81414141414141406000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1162409^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0837591^2 + 8141414141414141406000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1162409^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 404)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0836784^2 + 808000^2 && := 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0836784^2 + 81608000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0836784^2 + 8161608000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0836784^2 + 816161608000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0836784^2 + 81616161608000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0836784^2 + 8161616161608000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0836784^2 + 816161616161608000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0836784^2 + 81616161616161608000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1163216^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0836784^2 + 8161616161616161608000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1163216^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 405)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0835975^2 + 810000^2 && := 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0835975^2 + 81810000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0835975^2 + 8181810000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0835975^2 + 818181810000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0835975^2 + 81818181810000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0835975^2 + 8181818181810000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0835975^2 + 818181818181810000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0835975^2 + 81818181818181810000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1164025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0835975^2 + 8181818181818181810000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1164025^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 406)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0835164^2 + 812000^2 && := 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0835164^2 + 82012000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0835164^2 + 8202012000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0835164^2 + 820202012000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0835164^2 + 82020202012000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0835164^2 + 8202020202012000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0835164^2 + 820202020202012000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0835164^2 + 82020202020202012000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1164836^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0835164^2 + 8202020202020202012000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1164836^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 407)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0834351^2 + 814000^2 & := & 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0834351^2 + 82214000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0834351^2 + 8222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0834351^2 + 822222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0834351^2 + 82222222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0834351^2 + 8222222222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0834351^2 + 822222222222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0834351^2 + 82222222222222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1165649^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0834351^2 + 8222222222222222214000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1165649^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 408)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0833536^2 + 816000^2 & := & 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0833536^2 + 82416000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0833536^2 + 8242416000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0833536^2 + 824242416000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0833536^2 + 82424242416000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0833536^2 + 8242424242416000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0833536^2 + 824242424242416000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0833536^2 + 82424242424242416000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1166464^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0833536^2 + 8242424242424242416000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1166464^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 409)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0832719^2 + 818000^2 & := & 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0832719^2 + 82618000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0832719^2 + 8262618000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0832719^2 + 826262618000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0832719^2 + 82626262618000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0832719^2 + 8262626262618000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0832719^2 + 826262626262618000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0832719^2 + 82626262626262618000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1167281^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0832719^2 + 8262626262626262618000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1167281^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 410)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0831900^2 + 820000^2 & := & 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0831900^2 + 82820000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0831900^2 + 8282820000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0831900^2 + 828282820000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0831900^2 + 82828282820000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0831900^2 + 8282828282820000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0831900^2 + 828282828282820000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0831900^2 + 82828282828282820000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1168100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0831900^2 + 8282828282828282820000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1168100^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 411)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0831079^2 + 822000^2 && := 1168921^2 \\
 &1020\ 0831079^2 + 83022000^2 && := 1020\ 1168921^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0831079^2 + 8303022000^2 && := 10203020\ 1168921^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0831079^2 + 830303022000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1168921^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0831079^2 + 83030303022000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1168921^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0831079^2 + 8303030303022000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1168921^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0831079^2 + 830303030303022000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1168921^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0831079^2 + 83030303030303022000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1168921^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0831079^2 + 8303030303030303022000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1168921^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 412)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0830256^2 + 824000^2 && := 1169744^2 \\
 &1020\ 0830256^2 + 83224000^2 && := 1020\ 1169744^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0830256^2 + 8323224000^2 && := 10203020\ 1169744^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0830256^2 + 832323224000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1169744^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0830256^2 + 83232323224000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1169744^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0830256^2 + 8323232323224000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1169744^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0830256^2 + 832323232323224000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1169744^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0830256^2 + 83232323232323224000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1169744^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0830256^2 + 83232323232323224000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1169744^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 413)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0829431^2 + 826000^2 && := 1170569^2 \\
 &1020\ 0829431^2 + 83426000^2 && := 1020\ 1170569^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0829431^2 + 8343426000^2 && := 10203020\ 1170569^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0829431^2 + 834343426000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1170569^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0829431^2 + 83434343426000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1170569^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0829431^2 + 8343434343426000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1170569^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0829431^2 + 834343434343426000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1170569^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0829431^2 + 83434343434343426000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1170569^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0829431^2 + 8343434343434343426000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1170569^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 414)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0828604^2 + 828000^2 && := 1171396^2 \\
 &1020\ 0828604^2 + 83628000^2 && := 1020\ 1171396^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0828604^2 + 8363628000^2 && := 10203020\ 1171396^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0828604^2 + 836363628000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1171396^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0828604^2 + 83636363628000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1171396^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0828604^2 + 8363636363628000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1171396^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0828604^2 + 836363636363628000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1171396^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0828604^2 + 83636363636363628000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1171396^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0828604^2 + 83636363636363628000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1171396^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 415)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0827775^2 + 830000^2 && := 1172225^2 \\ &1020\ 0827775^2 + 83830000^2 && := 1020\ 1172225^2 \\ &10203020\ 0827775^2 + 8383830000^2 && := 10203020\ 1172225^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0827775^2 + 838383830000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1172225^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0827775^2 + 83838383830000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1172225^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0827775^2 + 8383838383830000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1172225^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0827775^2 + 838383838383830000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1172225^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0827775^2 + 83838383838383830000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1172225^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0827775^2 + 8383838383838383830000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1172225^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 416)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0826944^2 + 832000^2 && := 1173056^2 \\ &1020\ 0826944^2 + 84032000^2 && := 1020\ 1173056^2 \\ &10203020\ 0826944^2 + 8404032000^2 && := 10203020\ 1173056^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0826944^2 + 840404032000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1173056^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0826944^2 + 84040404032000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1173056^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0826944^2 + 8404040404032000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1173056^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0826944^2 + 840404040404032000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1173056^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0826944^2 + 84040404040404032000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1173056^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0826944^2 + 8404040404040404032000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1173056^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 417)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0826111^2 + 834000^2 && := 1173889^2 \\ &1020\ 0826111^2 + 84234000^2 && := 1020\ 1173889^2 \\ &10203020\ 0826111^2 + 8424234000^2 && := 10203020\ 1173889^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0826111^2 + 842424234000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1173889^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0826111^2 + 84242424234000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1173889^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0826111^2 + 8424242424234000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1173889^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0826111^2 + 842424242424234000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1173889^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0826111^2 + 84242424242424234000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1173889^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0826111^2 + 8424242424242424234000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1173889^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 418)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0825276^2 + 836000^2 && := 1174724^2 \\ &1020\ 0825276^2 + 84436000^2 && := 1020\ 1174724^2 \\ &10203020\ 0825276^2 + 8444436000^2 && := 10203020\ 1174724^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0825276^2 + 844444436000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1174724^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0825276^2 + 84444444436000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1174724^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0825276^2 + 8444444444436000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1174724^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0825276^2 + 844444444444436000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1174724^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0825276^2 + 84444444444444436000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1174724^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0825276^2 + 8444444444444444436000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1174724^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 419)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0824439^2 + 838000^2 && := 1175561^2 \\
 &1020\ 0824439^2 + 84638000^2 && := 1020\ 1175561^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0824439^2 + 8464638000^2 && := 10203020\ 1175561^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0824439^2 + 846464638000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1175561^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0824439^2 + 84646464638000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1175561^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0824439^2 + 8464646464638000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1175561^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0824439^2 + 846464646464638000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1175561^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0824439^2 + 846464646464638000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1175561^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0824439^2 + 84646464646464638000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1175561^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 420)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0823600^2 + 840000^2 && := 1176400^2 \\
 &1020\ 0823600^2 + 84840000^2 && := 1020\ 1176400^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0823600^2 + 8484840000^2 && := 10203020\ 1176400^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0823600^2 + 848484840000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1176400^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0823600^2 + 84848484840000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1176400^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0823600^2 + 8484848484840000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1176400^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0823600^2 + 848484848484840000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1176400^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0823600^2 + 848484848484840000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1176400^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0823600^2 + 84848484848484840000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1176400^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 421)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0822759^2 + 842000^2 && := 1177241^2 \\
 &1020\ 0822759^2 + 85042000^2 && := 1020\ 1177241^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0822759^2 + 8505042000^2 && := 10203020\ 1177241^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0822759^2 + 850505042000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1177241^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0822759^2 + 85050505042000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1177241^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0822759^2 + 8505050505042000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1177241^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0822759^2 + 850505050505042000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1177241^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0822759^2 + 85050505050505042000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1177241^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0822759^2 + 8505050505050505042000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1177241^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 422)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0821916^2 + 844000^2 && := 1178084^2 \\
 &1020\ 0821916^2 + 85244000^2 && := 1020\ 1178084^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0821916^2 + 8525244000^2 && := 10203020\ 1178084^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0821916^2 + 852525244000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1178084^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0821916^2 + 85252525244000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1178084^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0821916^2 + 8525252525244000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1178084^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0821916^2 + 852525252525244000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1178084^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0821916^2 + 852525252525244000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1178084^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0821916^2 + 85252525252525244000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1178084^2
 \end{aligned}$$

423)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0821071^2 + 846000^2 && := 1178929^2 \\
 &1020\ 0821071^2 + 85446000^2 && := 1020\ 1178929^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0821071^2 + 8545446000^2 && := 10203020\ 1178929^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0821071^2 + 854545446000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1178929^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0821071^2 + 85454545446000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1178929^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0821071^2 + 8545454545446000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1178929^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0821071^2 + 854545454545446000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1178929^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0821071^2 + 854545454545446000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1178929^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0821071^2 + 85454545454545446000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1178929^2
 \end{aligned}$$

424)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0820224^2 + 848000^2 && := 1179776^2 \\
 &1020\ 0820224^2 + 85648000^2 && := 1020\ 1179776^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0820224^2 + 8565648000^2 && := 10203020\ 1179776^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0820224^2 + 856565648000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1179776^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0820224^2 + 85656565648000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1179776^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0820224^2 + 8565656565648000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1179776^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0820224^2 + 856565656565648000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1179776^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0820224^2 + 856565656565648000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1179776^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0820224^2 + 85656565656565648000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1179776^2
 \end{aligned}$$

425)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0819375^2 + 850000^2 && := 1180625^2 \\
 &1020\ 0819375^2 + 85850000^2 && := 1020\ 1180625^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0819375^2 + 8585850000^2 && := 10203020\ 1180625^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0819375^2 + 858585850000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1180625^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0819375^2 + 85858585850000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1180625^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0819375^2 + 8585858585850000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1180625^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0819375^2 + 858585858585850000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1180625^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0819375^2 + 858585858585850000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1180625^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0819375^2 + 85858585858585850000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1180625^2
 \end{aligned}$$

426)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0818524^2 + 852000^2 && := 1181476^2 \\
 &1020\ 0818524^2 + 86052000^2 && := 1020\ 1181476^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0818524^2 + 8606052000^2 && := 10203020\ 1181476^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0818524^2 + 860606052000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1181476^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0818524^2 + 86060606052000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1181476^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0818524^2 + 8606060606052000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1181476^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0818524^2 + 860606060606052000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1181476^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0818524^2 + 860606060606052000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1181476^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0818524^2 + 86060606060606052000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1181476^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 427)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0817671^2 + 854000^2 && := 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0817671^2 + 86254000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0817671^2 + 8626254000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0817671^2 + 862626254000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0817671^2 + 86262626254000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0817671^2 + 8626262626254000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0817671^2 + 862626262626254000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0817671^2 + 862626262626254000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1182329^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0817671^2 + 86262626262626254000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1182329^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 428)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0816816^2 + 856000^2 && := 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0816816^2 + 86456000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0816816^2 + 8646456000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0816816^2 + 864646456000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0816816^2 + 86464646456000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0816816^2 + 8646464646456000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0816816^2 + 864646464646456000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0816816^2 + 864646464646456000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1183184^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0816816^2 + 86464646464646456000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1183184^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 429)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0815959^2 + 858000^2 && := 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0815959^2 + 86658000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0815959^2 + 8666658000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0815959^2 + 866666658000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0815959^2 + 86666666658000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0815959^2 + 8666666666658000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0815959^2 + 866666666666658000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0815959^2 + 86666666666666658000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1184041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0815959^2 + 8666666666666666658000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1184041^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 430)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0815100^2 + 860000^2 && := 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0815100^2 + 86860000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0815100^2 + 8686860000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0815100^2 + 868686860000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0815100^2 + 86868686860000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0815100^2 + 8686868686860000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0815100^2 + 868686868686860000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0815100^2 + 86868686868686860000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1184900^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0815100^2 + 8686868686868686860000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1184900^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 431)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0814239^2 + 862000^2 && := 1185761^2 \\
 &1020\ 0814239^2 + 87062000^2 && := 1020\ 1185761^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0814239^2 + 8707062000^2 && := 10203020\ 1185761^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0814239^2 + 870707062000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1185761^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0814239^2 + 87070707062000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1185761^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0814239^2 + 8707070707062000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1185761^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0814239^2 + 870707070707062000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1185761^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0814239^2 + 870707070707062000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1185761^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0814239^2 + 870707070707062000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1185761^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 432)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0813376^2 + 864000^2 && := 1186624^2 \\
 &1020\ 0813376^2 + 87264000^2 && := 1020\ 1186624^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0813376^2 + 8727264000^2 && := 10203020\ 1186624^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0813376^2 + 872727264000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1186624^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0813376^2 + 87272727264000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1186624^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0813376^2 + 8727272727264000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1186624^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0813376^2 + 872727272727264000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1186624^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0813376^2 + 872727272727264000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1186624^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0813376^2 + 872727272727264000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1186624^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 433)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0812511^2 + 866000^2 && := 1187489^2 \\
 &1020\ 0812511^2 + 87466000^2 && := 1020\ 1187489^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0812511^2 + 8747466000^2 && := 10203020\ 1187489^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0812511^2 + 874747466000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1187489^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0812511^2 + 87474747466000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1187489^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0812511^2 + 8747474747466000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1187489^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0812511^2 + 874747474747466000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1187489^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0812511^2 + 874747474747466000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1187489^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0812511^2 + 874747474747466000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1187489^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 434)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0811644^2 + 868000^2 && := 1188356^2 \\
 &1020\ 0811644^2 + 87668000^2 && := 1020\ 1188356^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0811644^2 + 8767668000^2 && := 10203020\ 1188356^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0811644^2 + 876767668000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1188356^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0811644^2 + 87676767668000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1188356^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0811644^2 + 8767676767668000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1188356^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0811644^2 + 876767676767668000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1188356^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0811644^2 + 876767676767668000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1188356^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0811644^2 + 876767676767668000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1188356^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 435)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0810775^2 + 870000^2 && := 1189225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0810775^2 + 87870000^2 && := 1020\ 1189225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0810775^2 + 8787870000^2 && := 10203020\ 1189225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0810775^2 + 878787870000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1189225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0810775^2 + 87878787870000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1189225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0810775^2 + 8787878787870000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1189225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0810775^2 + 878787878787870000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1189225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0810775^2 + 87878787878787870000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1189225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0810775^2 + 8787878787878787870000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1189225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 436)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0809904^2 + 872000^2 && := 1190096^2 \\
 &1020\ 0809904^2 + 88072000^2 && := 1020\ 1190096^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0809904^2 + 8808072000^2 && := 10203020\ 1190096^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0809904^2 + 880808072000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1190096^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0809904^2 + 88080808072000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1190096^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0809904^2 + 8808080808072000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1190096^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0809904^2 + 880808080808072000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1190096^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0809904^2 + 88080808080808072000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1190096^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0809904^2 + 8808080808080808072000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1190096^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 437)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0809031^2 + 874000^2 && := 1190969^2 \\
 &1020\ 0809031^2 + 88274000^2 && := 1020\ 1190969^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0809031^2 + 8828274000^2 && := 10203020\ 1190969^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0809031^2 + 882828274000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1190969^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0809031^2 + 88282828274000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1190969^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0809031^2 + 8828282828274000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1190969^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0809031^2 + 882828282828274000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1190969^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0809031^2 + 88282828282828274000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1190969^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0809031^2 + 8828282828282828274000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1190969^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 438)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0808156^2 + 876000^2 && := 1191844^2 \\
 &1020\ 0808156^2 + 88476000^2 && := 1020\ 1191844^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0808156^2 + 8848476000^2 && := 10203020\ 1191844^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0808156^2 + 884848476000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1191844^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0808156^2 + 88484848476000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1191844^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0808156^2 + 8848484848476000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1191844^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0808156^2 + 884848484848476000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1191844^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0808156^2 + 88484848484848476000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1191844^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0808156^2 + 8848484848484848476000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1191844^2
 \end{aligned}$$

439)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0807279^2 + 878000^2 && := 1192721^2 \\
 &1020\ 0807279^2 + 88678000^2 && := 1020\ 1192721^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0807279^2 + 8868678000^2 && := 10203020\ 1192721^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0807279^2 + 886868678000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1192721^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0807279^2 + 88686868678000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1192721^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0807279^2 + 8868686868678000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1192721^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0807279^2 + 886868686868678000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1192721^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0807279^2 + 88686868686868678000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1192721^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0807279^2 + 8868686868686868678000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1192721^2
 \end{aligned}$$

440)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0806400^2 + 880000^2 && := 1193600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0806400^2 + 88880000^2 && := 1020\ 1193600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0806400^2 + 8888880000^2 && := 10203020\ 1193600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0806400^2 + 888888880000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1193600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0806400^2 + 88888888880000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1193600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0806400^2 + 8888888888880000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1193600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0806400^2 + 888888888888880000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1193600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0806400^2 + 88888888888888880000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1193600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0806400^2 + 8888888888888888880000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1193600^2
 \end{aligned}$$

441)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0805519^2 + 882000^2 && := 1194481^2 \\
 &1020\ 0805519^2 + 89082000^2 && := 1020\ 1194481^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0805519^2 + 8909082000^2 && := 10203020\ 1194481^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0805519^2 + 890909082000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1194481^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0805519^2 + 89090909082000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1194481^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0805519^2 + 8909090909082000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1194481^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0805519^2 + 890909090909082000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1194481^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0805519^2 + 89090909090909082000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1194481^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0805519^2 + 8909090909090909082000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1194481^2
 \end{aligned}$$

442)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0804636^2 + 884000^2 && := 1195364^2 \\
 &1020\ 0804636^2 + 89284000^2 && := 1020\ 1195364^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0804636^2 + 8929284000^2 && := 10203020\ 1195364^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0804636^2 + 892929284000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1195364^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0804636^2 + 89292929284000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1195364^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0804636^2 + 8929292929284000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1195364^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0804636^2 + 892929292929284000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1195364^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0804636^2 + 89292929292929284000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1195364^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0804636^2 + 8929292929292929284000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1195364^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 443)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0803751^2 + 886000^2 && := 1196249^2 \\
 &1020\ 0803751^2 + 89486000^2 && := 1020\ 1196249^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0803751^2 + 8949486000^2 && := 10203020\ 1196249^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0803751^2 + 894949486000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1196249^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0803751^2 + 89494949486000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1196249^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0803751^2 + 8949494949486000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1196249^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0803751^2 + 894949494949486000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1196249^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0803751^2 + 89494949494949486000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1196249^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0803751^2 + 8949494949494949486000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1196249^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 444)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0802864^2 + 888000^2 && := 1197136^2 \\
 &1020\ 0802864^2 + 89688000^2 && := 1020\ 1197136^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0802864^2 + 8969688000^2 && := 10203020\ 1197136^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0802864^2 + 896969688000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1197136^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0802864^2 + 89696969688000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1197136^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0802864^2 + 8969696969688000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1197136^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0802864^2 + 896969696969688000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1197136^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0802864^2 + 89696969696969688000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1197136^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0802864^2 + 8969696969696969688000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1197136^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 445)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0801975^2 + 890000^2 && := 1198025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0801975^2 + 89890000^2 && := 1020\ 1198025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0801975^2 + 8989890000^2 && := 10203020\ 1198025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0801975^2 + 898989890000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1198025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0801975^2 + 89898989890000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1198025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0801975^2 + 8989898989890000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1198025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0801975^2 + 898989898989890000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1198025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0801975^2 + 89898989898989890000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1198025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0801975^2 + 8989898989898989890000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1198025^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 446)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0801084^2 + 892000^2 && := 1198916^2 \\
 &1020\ 0801084^2 + 90092000^2 && := 1020\ 1198916^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0801084^2 + 9010092000^2 && := 10203020\ 1198916^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0801084^2 + 901010092000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1198916^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0801084^2 + 90101010092000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1198916^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0801084^2 + 9010101010092000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1198916^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0801084^2 + 901010101010092000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1198916^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0801084^2 + 90101010101010092000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1198916^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0801084^2 + 9010101010101010092000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1198916^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 447)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0800191^2 + 894000^2 && := 1199809^2 \\
 &1020\ 0800191^2 + 90294000^2 && := 1020\ 1199809^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0800191^2 + 9030294000^2 && := 10203020\ 1199809^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0800191^2 + 903030294000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1199809^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0800191^2 + 90303030294000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1199809^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0800191^2 + 9030303030294000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1199809^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0800191^2 + 903030303030294000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1199809^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0800191^2 + 90303030303030294000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1199809^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0800191^2 + 9030303030303030294000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1199809^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 448)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0799296^2 + 896000^2 && := 1200704^2 \\
 &1020\ 0799296^2 + 90496000^2 && := 1020\ 1200704^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0799296^2 + 9050496000^2 && := 10203020\ 1200704^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0799296^2 + 905050496000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1200704^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0799296^2 + 90505050496000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1200704^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0799296^2 + 9050505050496000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1200704^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0799296^2 + 905050505050496000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1200704^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0799296^2 + 90505050505050496000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1200704^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0799296^2 + 9050505050505050496000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1200704^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 449)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0798399^2 + 898000^2 && := 1201601^2 \\
 &1020\ 0798399^2 + 90698000^2 && := 1020\ 1201601^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0798399^2 + 9070698000^2 && := 10203020\ 1201601^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0798399^2 + 907070698000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1201601^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0798399^2 + 90707070698000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1201601^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0798399^2 + 9070707070698000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1201601^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0798399^2 + 907070707070698000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1201601^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0798399^2 + 90707070707070698000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1201601^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0798399^2 + 9070707070707070698000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1201601^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 450)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0797500^2 + 900000^2 && := 1202500^2 \\
 &1020\ 0797500^2 + 90900000^2 && := 1020\ 1202500^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0797500^2 + 9090900000^2 && := 10203020\ 1202500^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0797500^2 + 909090900000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1202500^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0797500^2 + 90909090900000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1202500^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0797500^2 + 9090909090900000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1202500^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0797500^2 + 909090909090900000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1202500^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0797500^2 + 90909090909090900000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1202500^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0797500^2 + 9090909090909090900000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1202500^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 451)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0796599^2 + 902000^2 && := 1203401^2 \\
 &1020\ 0796599^2 + 91102000^2 && := 1020\ 1203401^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0796599^2 + 9111102000^2 && := 10203020\ 1203401^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0796599^2 + 911111102000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1203401^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0796599^2 + 91111111102000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1203401^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0796599^2 + 9111111111102000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1203401^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0796599^2 + 911111111111102000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1203401^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0796599^2 + 91111111111111102000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1203401^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0796599^2 + 9111111111111111102000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1203401^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 452)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0795696^2 + 904000^2 && := 1204304^2 \\
 &1020\ 0795696^2 + 91304000^2 && := 1020\ 1204304^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0795696^2 + 9131304000^2 && := 10203020\ 1204304^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0795696^2 + 913131304000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1204304^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0795696^2 + 91313131304000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1204304^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0795696^2 + 9131313131304000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1204304^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0795696^2 + 913131313131304000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1204304^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0795696^2 + 91313131313131304000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1204304^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0795696^2 + 9131313131313131304000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1204304^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 453)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0794791^2 + 906000^2 && := 1205209^2 \\
 &1020\ 0794791^2 + 91506000^2 && := 1020\ 1205209^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0794791^2 + 9151506000^2 && := 10203020\ 1205209^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0794791^2 + 915151506000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1205209^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0794791^2 + 91515151506000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1205209^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0794791^2 + 9151515151506000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1205209^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0794791^2 + 915151515151506000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1205209^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0794791^2 + 91515151515151506000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1205209^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0794791^2 + 9151515151515151506000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1205209^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 454)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0793884^2 + 908000^2 && := 1206116^2 \\
 &1020\ 0793884^2 + 91708000^2 && := 1020\ 1206116^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0793884^2 + 9171708000^2 && := 10203020\ 1206116^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0793884^2 + 917171708000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1206116^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0793884^2 + 91717171708000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1206116^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0793884^2 + 9171717171708000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1206116^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0793884^2 + 917171717171708000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1206116^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0793884^2 + 91717171717171708000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1206116^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0793884^2 + 9171717171717171708000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1206116^2
 \end{aligned}$$

455)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0792975^2 + 910000^2 && := 1207025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0792975^2 + 91910000^2 && := 1020\ 1207025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0792975^2 + 9191910000^2 && := 10203020\ 1207025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0792975^2 + 919191910000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1207025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0792975^2 + 91919191910000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1207025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0792975^2 + 9191919191910000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1207025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0792975^2 + 919191919191910000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1207025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0792975^2 + 91919191919191910000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1207025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0792975^2 + 9191919191919191910000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1207025^2
 \end{aligned}$$

456)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0792064^2 + 912000^2 && := 1207936^2 \\
 &1020\ 0792064^2 + 92112000^2 && := 1020\ 1207936^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0792064^2 + 9212112000^2 && := 10203020\ 1207936^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0792064^2 + 921212112000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1207936^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0792064^2 + 92121212112000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1207936^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0792064^2 + 9212121212112000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1207936^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0792064^2 + 921212121212112000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1207936^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0792064^2 + 92121212121212112000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1207936^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0792064^2 + 9212121212121212112000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1207936^2
 \end{aligned}$$

457)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0791151^2 + 914000^2 && := 1208849^2 \\
 &1020\ 0791151^2 + 92314000^2 && := 1020\ 1208849^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0791151^2 + 9232314000^2 && := 10203020\ 1208849^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0791151^2 + 923232314000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1208849^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0791151^2 + 92323232314000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1208849^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0791151^2 + 9232323232314000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1208849^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0791151^2 + 923232323232314000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1208849^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0791151^2 + 92323232323232314000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1208849^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0791151^2 + 9232323232323232314000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1208849^2
 \end{aligned}$$

458)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0790236^2 + 916000^2 && := 1209764^2 \\
 &1020\ 0790236^2 + 92516000^2 && := 1020\ 1209764^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0790236^2 + 9252516000^2 && := 10203020\ 1209764^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0790236^2 + 925252516000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1209764^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0790236^2 + 92525252516000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1209764^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0790236^2 + 9252525252516000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1209764^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0790236^2 + 925252525252516000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1209764^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0790236^2 + 92525252525252516000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1209764^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0790236^2 + 9252525252525252516000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1209764^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 459)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0789319^2 + 918000^2 && := 1210681^2 \\
 &1020\ 0789319^2 + 92718000^2 && := 1020\ 1210681^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0789319^2 + 9272718000^2 && := 10203020\ 1210681^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0789319^2 + 927272718000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1210681^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0789319^2 + 92727272718000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1210681^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0789319^2 + 9272727272718000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1210681^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0789319^2 + 927272727272718000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1210681^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0789319^2 + 92727272727272718000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1210681^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0789319^2 + 9272727272727272718000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1210681^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 460)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0788400^2 + 920000^2 && := 1211600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0788400^2 + 92920000^2 && := 1020\ 1211600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0788400^2 + 9292920000^2 && := 10203020\ 1211600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0788400^2 + 929292920000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1211600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0788400^2 + 92929292920000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1211600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0788400^2 + 9292929292920000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1211600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0788400^2 + 929292929292920000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1211600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0788400^2 + 92929292929292920000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1211600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0788400^2 + 9292929292929292920000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1211600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 461)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0787479^2 + 922000^2 && := 1212521^2 \\
 &1020\ 0787479^2 + 93122000^2 && := 1020\ 1212521^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0787479^2 + 9313122000^2 && := 10203020\ 1212521^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0787479^2 + 931313122000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1212521^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0787479^2 + 93131313122000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1212521^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0787479^2 + 9313131313122000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1212521^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0787479^2 + 931313131313122000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1212521^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0787479^2 + 93131313131313122000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1212521^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0787479^2 + 9313131313131313122000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1212521^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 462)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0786556^2 + 924000^2 && := 1213444^2 \\
 &1020\ 0786556^2 + 93324000^2 && := 1020\ 1213444^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0786556^2 + 9333324000^2 && := 10203020\ 1213444^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0786556^2 + 933333324000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1213444^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0786556^2 + 93333333324000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1213444^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0786556^2 + 9333333333324000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1213444^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0786556^2 + 933333333333324000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1213444^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0786556^2 + 93333333333333324000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1213444^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0786556^2 + 9333333333333333324000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1213444^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 463)
- $$0785631^2 + 926000^2 := 1214369^2$$
- $$1020\ 0785631^2 + 93526000^2 := 1020\ 1214369^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0785631^2 + 9353526000^2 := 10203020\ 1214369^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0785631^2 + 935353526000^2 := 102030403020\ 1214369^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0785631^2 + 93535353526000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1214369^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0785631^2 + 9353535353526000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1214369^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0785631^2 + 935353535353526000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1214369^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0785631^2 + 93535353535353526000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1214369^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0785631^2 + 9353535353535353526000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1214369^2$$
- 464)
- $$0784704^2 + 928000^2 := 1215296^2$$
- $$1020\ 0784704^2 + 93728000^2 := 1020\ 1215296^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0784704^2 + 9373728000^2 := 10203020\ 1215296^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0784704^2 + 937373728000^2 := 102030403020\ 1215296^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0784704^2 + 93737373728000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1215296^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0784704^2 + 9373737373728000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1215296^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0784704^2 + 937373737373728000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1215296^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0784704^2 + 93737373737373728000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1215296^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0784704^2 + 9373737373737373728000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1215296^2$$
- 465)
- $$0783775^2 + 930000^2 := 1216225^2$$
- $$1020\ 0783775^2 + 93930000^2 := 1020\ 1216225^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0783775^2 + 9393930000^2 := 10203020\ 1216225^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0783775^2 + 939393930000^2 := 102030403020\ 1216225^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0783775^2 + 93939393930000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1216225^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0783775^2 + 9393939393930000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1216225^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0783775^2 + 939393939393930000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1216225^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0783775^2 + 93939393939393930000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1216225^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0783775^2 + 9393939393939393930000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1216225^2$$
- 466)
- $$0782844^2 + 932000^2 := 1217156^2$$
- $$1020\ 0782844^2 + 94132000^2 := 1020\ 1217156^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0782844^2 + 9414132000^2 := 10203020\ 1217156^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0782844^2 + 941414132000^2 := 102030403020\ 1217156^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0782844^2 + 94141414132000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1217156^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0782844^2 + 9414141414132000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1217156^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0782844^2 + 941414141414132000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1217156^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0782844^2 + 94141414141414132000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1217156^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0782844^2 + 9414141414141414132000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1217156^2$$

467)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0781911^2 + 934000^2 && := 1218089^2 \\
 &1020\ 0781911^2 + 94334000^2 && := 1020\ 1218089^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0781911^2 + 9434334000^2 && := 10203020\ 1218089^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0781911^2 + 943434334000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1218089^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0781911^2 + 94343434334000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1218089^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0781911^2 + 9434343434334000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1218089^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0781911^2 + 943434343434334000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1218089^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0781911^2 + 943434343434334000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1218089^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0781911^2 + 94343434343434334000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1218089^2
 \end{aligned}$$

468)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0780976^2 + 936000^2 && := 1219024^2 \\
 &1020\ 0780976^2 + 94536000^2 && := 1020\ 1219024^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0780976^2 + 9454536000^2 && := 10203020\ 1219024^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0780976^2 + 945454536000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1219024^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0780976^2 + 94545454536000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1219024^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0780976^2 + 9454545454536000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1219024^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0780976^2 + 945454545454536000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1219024^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0780976^2 + 945454545454536000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1219024^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0780976^2 + 94545454545454536000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1219024^2
 \end{aligned}$$

469)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0780039^2 + 938000^2 && := 1219961^2 \\
 &1020\ 0780039^2 + 94738000^2 && := 1020\ 1219961^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0780039^2 + 9474738000^2 && := 10203020\ 1219961^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0780039^2 + 947474738000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1219961^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0780039^2 + 94747474738000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1219961^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0780039^2 + 9474747474738000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1219961^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0780039^2 + 947474747474738000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1219961^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0780039^2 + 947474747474738000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1219961^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0780039^2 + 94747474747474738000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1219961^2
 \end{aligned}$$

470)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0779100^2 + 940000^2 && := 1220900^2 \\
 &1020\ 0779100^2 + 94940000^2 && := 1020\ 1220900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0779100^2 + 9494940000^2 && := 10203020\ 1220900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0779100^2 + 949494940000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1220900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0779100^2 + 94949494940000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1220900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0779100^2 + 9494949494940000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1220900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0779100^2 + 949494949494940000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1220900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0779100^2 + 949494949494940000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1220900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0779100^2 + 949494949494940000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1220900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 471)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0778159^2 + 942000^2 && := 1221841^2 \\ &1020\ 0778159^2 + 95142000^2 && := 1020\ 1221841^2 \\ &10203020\ 0778159^2 + 9515142000^2 && := 10203020\ 1221841^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0778159^2 + 951515142000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1221841^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0778159^2 + 95151515142000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1221841^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0778159^2 + 9515151515142000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1221841^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0778159^2 + 951515151515142000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1221841^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0778159^2 + 95151515151515142000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1221841^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0778159^2 + 9515151515151515142000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1221841^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 472)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0777216^2 + 944000^2 && := 1222784^2 \\ &1020\ 0777216^2 + 95344000^2 && := 1020\ 1222784^2 \\ &10203020\ 0777216^2 + 9535344000^2 && := 10203020\ 1222784^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0777216^2 + 953535344000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1222784^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0777216^2 + 95353535344000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1222784^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0777216^2 + 9535353535344000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1222784^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0777216^2 + 953535353535344000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1222784^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0777216^2 + 95353535353535344000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1222784^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0777216^2 + 9535353535353535344000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1222784^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 473)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0776271^2 + 946000^2 && := 1223729^2 \\ &1020\ 0776271^2 + 95546000^2 && := 1020\ 1223729^2 \\ &10203020\ 0776271^2 + 9555546000^2 && := 10203020\ 1223729^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0776271^2 + 955555546000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1223729^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0776271^2 + 95555555546000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1223729^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0776271^2 + 9555555555546000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1223729^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0776271^2 + 955555555555546000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1223729^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0776271^2 + 95555555555555546000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1223729^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0776271^2 + 9555555555555555546000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1223729^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 474)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0775324^2 + 948000^2 && := 1224676^2 \\ &1020\ 0775324^2 + 95748000^2 && := 1020\ 1224676^2 \\ &10203020\ 0775324^2 + 9575748000^2 && := 10203020\ 1224676^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0775324^2 + 957575748000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1224676^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0775324^2 + 95757575748000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1224676^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0775324^2 + 9575757575748000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1224676^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0775324^2 + 957575757575748000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1224676^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0775324^2 + 95757575757575748000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1224676^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0775324^2 + 9575757575757575748000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1224676^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 475)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0774375^2 + 950000^2 && := 1225625^2 \\ &1020\ 0774375^2 + 95950000^2 && := 1020\ 1225625^2 \\ &10203020\ 0774375^2 + 9595950000^2 && := 10203020\ 1225625^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0774375^2 + 959595950000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1225625^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0774375^2 + 95959595950000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1225625^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0774375^2 + 9595959595950000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1225625^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0774375^2 + 959595959595950000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1225625^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0774375^2 + 95959595959595950000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1225625^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0774375^2 + 9595959595959595950000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1225625^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 476)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0773424^2 + 952000^2 && := 1226576^2 \\ &1020\ 0773424^2 + 96152000^2 && := 1020\ 1226576^2 \\ &10203020\ 0773424^2 + 9616152000^2 && := 10203020\ 1226576^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0773424^2 + 961616152000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1226576^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0773424^2 + 96161616152000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1226576^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0773424^2 + 9616161616152000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1226576^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0773424^2 + 961616161616152000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1226576^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0773424^2 + 96161616161616152000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1226576^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0773424^2 + 9616161616161616152000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1226576^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 477)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0772471^2 + 954000^2 && := 1227529^2 \\ &1020\ 0772471^2 + 96354000^2 && := 1020\ 1227529^2 \\ &10203020\ 0772471^2 + 9636354000^2 && := 10203020\ 1227529^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0772471^2 + 963636354000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1227529^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0772471^2 + 96363636354000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1227529^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0772471^2 + 9636363636354000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1227529^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0772471^2 + 963636363636354000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1227529^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0772471^2 + 96363636363636354000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1227529^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0772471^2 + 9636363636363636354000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1227529^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 478)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0771516^2 + 956000^2 && := 1228484^2 \\ &1020\ 0771516^2 + 96556000^2 && := 1020\ 1228484^2 \\ &10203020\ 0771516^2 + 9656556000^2 && := 10203020\ 1228484^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0771516^2 + 965656556000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1228484^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0771516^2 + 96565656556000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1228484^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0771516^2 + 9656565656556000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1228484^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0771516^2 + 965656565656556000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1228484^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0771516^2 + 96565656565656556000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1228484^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0771516^2 + 9656565656565656556000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1228484^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 479)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0770559^2 + 958000^2 && := 1229441^2 \\
 &1020\ 0770559^2 + 96758000^2 && := 1020\ 1229441^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0770559^2 + 9676758000^2 && := 10203020\ 1229441^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0770559^2 + 967676758000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1229441^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0770559^2 + 96767676758000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1229441^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0770559^2 + 9676767676758000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1229441^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0770559^2 + 967676767676758000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1229441^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0770559^2 + 96767676767676758000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1229441^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0770559^2 + 9676767676767676758000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1229441^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 480)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0769600^2 + 960000^2 && := 1230400^2 \\
 &1020\ 0769600^2 + 96960000^2 && := 1020\ 1230400^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0769600^2 + 9696960000^2 && := 10203020\ 1230400^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0769600^2 + 969696960000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1230400^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0769600^2 + 96969696960000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1230400^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0769600^2 + 9696969696960000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1230400^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0769600^2 + 969696969696960000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1230400^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0769600^2 + 96969696969696960000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1230400^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0769600^2 + 9696969696969696960000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1230400^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 481)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0768639^2 + 962000^2 && := 1231361^2 \\
 &1020\ 0768639^2 + 97162000^2 && := 1020\ 1231361^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0768639^2 + 9717162000^2 && := 10203020\ 1231361^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0768639^2 + 971717162000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1231361^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0768639^2 + 97171717162000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1231361^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0768639^2 + 9717171717162000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1231361^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0768639^2 + 971717171717162000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1231361^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0768639^2 + 97171717171717162000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1231361^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0768639^2 + 9717171717171717162000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1231361^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 482)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0767676^2 + 964000^2 && := 1232324^2 \\
 &1020\ 0767676^2 + 97364000^2 && := 1020\ 1232324^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0767676^2 + 9737364000^2 && := 10203020\ 1232324^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0767676^2 + 973737364000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1232324^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0767676^2 + 97373737364000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1232324^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0767676^2 + 9737373737364000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1232324^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0767676^2 + 973737373737364000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1232324^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0767676^2 + 97373737373737364000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1232324^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0767676^2 + 9737373737373737364000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1232324^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 483)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0766711^2 + 966000^2 && := 1233289^2 \\
 &1020\ 0766711^2 + 97566000^2 && := 1020\ 1233289^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0766711^2 + 9757566000^2 && := 10203020\ 1233289^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0766711^2 + 975757566000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1233289^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0766711^2 + 97575757566000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1233289^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0766711^2 + 9757575757566000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1233289^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0766711^2 + 975757575757566000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1233289^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0766711^2 + 97575757575757566000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1233289^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0766711^2 + 9757575757575757566000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1233289^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 484)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0765744^2 + 968000^2 && := 1234256^2 \\
 &1020\ 0765744^2 + 97768000^2 && := 1020\ 1234256^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0765744^2 + 9777768000^2 && := 10203020\ 1234256^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0765744^2 + 97777768000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1234256^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0765744^2 + 977777768000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1234256^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0765744^2 + 9777777768000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1234256^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0765744^2 + 97777777768000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1234256^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0765744^2 + 977777777768000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1234256^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0765744^2 + 9777777777768000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1234256^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 485)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0764775^2 + 970000^2 && := 1235225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0764775^2 + 97970000^2 && := 1020\ 1235225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0764775^2 + 9797970000^2 && := 10203020\ 1235225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0764775^2 + 979797970000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1235225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0764775^2 + 97979797970000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1235225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0764775^2 + 9797979797970000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1235225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0764775^2 + 979797979797970000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1235225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0764775^2 + 97979797979797970000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1235225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0764775^2 + 9797979797979797970000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1235225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 486)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0763804^2 + 972000^2 && := 1236196^2 \\
 &1020\ 0763804^2 + 98172000^2 && := 1020\ 1236196^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0763804^2 + 9818172000^2 && := 10203020\ 1236196^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0763804^2 + 981818172000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1236196^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0763804^2 + 98181818172000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1236196^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0763804^2 + 9818181818172000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1236196^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0763804^2 + 981818181818172000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1236196^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0763804^2 + 98181818181818172000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1236196^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0763804^2 + 9818181818181818172000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1236196^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 487)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0762831^2 + 974000^2 && := 1237169^2 \\
 &1020\ 0762831^2 + 98374000^2 && := 1020\ 1237169^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0762831^2 + 9838374000^2 && := 10203020\ 1237169^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0762831^2 + 983838374000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1237169^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0762831^2 + 98383838374000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1237169^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0762831^2 + 9838383838374000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1237169^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0762831^2 + 983838383838374000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1237169^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0762831^2 + 98383838383838374000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1237169^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0762831^2 + 9838383838383838374000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1237169^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 488)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0761856^2 + 976000^2 && := 1238144^2 \\
 &1020\ 0761856^2 + 98576000^2 && := 1020\ 1238144^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0761856^2 + 9858576000^2 && := 10203020\ 1238144^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0761856^2 + 985858576000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1238144^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0761856^2 + 98585858576000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1238144^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0761856^2 + 9858585858576000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1238144^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0761856^2 + 985858585858576000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1238144^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0761856^2 + 98585858585858576000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1238144^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0761856^2 + 9858585858585858576000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1238144^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 489)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0760879^2 + 978000^2 && := 1239121^2 \\
 &1020\ 0760879^2 + 98778000^2 && := 1020\ 1239121^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0760879^2 + 9878778000^2 && := 10203020\ 1239121^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0760879^2 + 987878778000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1239121^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0760879^2 + 98787878778000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1239121^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0760879^2 + 9878787878778000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1239121^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0760879^2 + 987878787878778000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1239121^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0760879^2 + 98787878787878778000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1239121^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0760879^2 + 9878787878787878778000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1239121^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 490)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0759900^2 + 980000^2 && := 1240100^2 \\
 &1020\ 0759900^2 + 98980000^2 && := 1020\ 1240100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0759900^2 + 9898980000^2 && := 10203020\ 1240100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0759900^2 + 989898980000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1240100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0759900^2 + 98989898980000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1240100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0759900^2 + 9898989898980000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1240100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0759900^2 + 989898989898980000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1240100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0759900^2 + 98989898989898980000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1240100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0759900^2 + 9898989898989898980000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1240100^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 491)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0758919^2 + 982000^2 && := 1241081^2 \\
 &1020\ 0758919^2 + 99182000^2 && := 1020\ 1241081^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0758919^2 + 9919182000^2 && := 10203020\ 1241081^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0758919^2 + 991919182000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1241081^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0758919^2 + 99191919182000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1241081^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0758919^2 + 9919191919182000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1241081^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0758919^2 + 991919191919182000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1241081^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0758919^2 + 99191919191919182000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1241081^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0758919^2 + 9919191919191919182000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1241081^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 492)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0757936^2 + 984000^2 && := 1242064^2 \\
 &1020\ 0757936^2 + 99384000^2 && := 1020\ 1242064^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0757936^2 + 9939384000^2 && := 10203020\ 1242064^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0757936^2 + 993939384000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1242064^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0757936^2 + 99393939384000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1242064^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0757936^2 + 9939393939384000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1242064^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0757936^2 + 993939393939384000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1242064^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0757936^2 + 99393939393939384000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1242064^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0757936^2 + 9939393939393939384000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1242064^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 493)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0756951^2 + 986000^2 && := 1243049^2 \\
 &1020\ 0756951^2 + 99586000^2 && := 1020\ 1243049^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0756951^2 + 9959586000^2 && := 10203020\ 1243049^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0756951^2 + 995959586000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1243049^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0756951^2 + 99595959586000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1243049^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0756951^2 + 9959595959586000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1243049^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0756951^2 + 995959595959586000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1243049^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0756951^2 + 99595959595959586000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1243049^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0756951^2 + 9959595959595959586000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1243049^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 494)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0755964^2 + 988000^2 && := 1244036^2 \\
 &1020\ 0755964^2 + 99788000^2 && := 1020\ 1244036^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0755964^2 + 9979788000^2 && := 10203020\ 1244036^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0755964^2 + 997979788000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1244036^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0755964^2 + 99797979788000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1244036^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0755964^2 + 9979797979788000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1244036^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0755964^2 + 997979797979788000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1244036^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0755964^2 + 99797979797979788000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1244036^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0755964^2 + 9979797979797979788000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1244036^2
 \end{aligned}$$

495)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0754975^2 + 990000^2 && := 1245025^2 \\
 &1020\ 0754975^2 + 99990000^2 && := 1020\ 1245025^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0754975^2 + 9999990000^2 && := 10203020\ 1245025^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0754975^2 + 999999990000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1245025^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0754975^2 + 99999999990000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1245025^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0754975^2 + 9999999999990000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1245025^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0754975^2 + 999999999999990000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1245025^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0754975^2 + 99999999999999990000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1245025^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0754975^2 + 9999999999999999990000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1245025^2
 \end{aligned}$$

496)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0753984^2 + 992000^2 && := 1246016^2 \\
 &1020\ 0753984^2 + 100192000^2 && := 1020\ 1246016^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0753984^2 + 10020192000^2 && := 10203020\ 1246016^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0753984^2 + 1002020192000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1246016^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0753984^2 + 100202020192000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1246016^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0753984^2 + 10020202020192000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1246016^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0753984^2 + 1002020202020192000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1246016^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0753984^2 + 100202020202020192000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1246016^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0753984^2 + 10020202020202020192000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1246016^2
 \end{aligned}$$

497)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0752991^2 + 994000^2 && := 1247009^2 \\
 &1020\ 0752991^2 + 100394000^2 && := 1020\ 1247009^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0752991^2 + 10040394000^2 && := 10203020\ 1247009^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0752991^2 + 1004040394000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1247009^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0752991^2 + 100404040394000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1247009^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0752991^2 + 10040404040394000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1247009^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0752991^2 + 1004040404040394000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1247009^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0752991^2 + 100404040404040394000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1247009^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0752991^2 + 10040404040404040394000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1247009^2
 \end{aligned}$$

498)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0751996^2 + 996000^2 && := 1248004^2 \\
 &1020\ 0751996^2 + 100596000^2 && := 1020\ 1248004^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0751996^2 + 10060596000^2 && := 10203020\ 1248004^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0751996^2 + 1006060596000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1248004^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0751996^2 + 100606060596000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1248004^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0751996^2 + 10060606060596000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1248004^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0751996^2 + 1006060606060596000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1248004^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0751996^2 + 100606060606060596000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1248004^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0751996^2 + 10060606060606060596000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1248004^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 499)
- $$0750999^2 + 998000^2 := 1249001^2$$
- $$1020\ 0750999^2 + 100798000^2 := 1020\ 1249001^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0750999^2 + 10080798000^2 := 10203020\ 1249001^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0750999^2 + 1008080798000^2 := 102030403020\ 1249001^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0750999^2 + 100808080798000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1249001^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0750999^2 + 10080808080798000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1249001^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0750999^2 + 1008080808080798000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1249001^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0750999^2 + 100808080808080798000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1249001^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0750999^2 + 10080808080808080798000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1249001^2$$
- 500)
- $$0750000^2 + 1000000^2 := 1250000^2$$
- $$1020\ 0750000^2 + 101000000^2 := 1020\ 1250000^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0750000^2 + 10101000000^2 := 10203020\ 1250000^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0750000^2 + 1010101000000^2 := 102030403020\ 1250000^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0750000^2 + 101010101000000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1250000^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0750000^2 + 10101010101000000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1250000^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0750000^2 + 1010101010101000000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1250000^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0750000^2 + 101010101010101000000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1250000^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0750000^2 + 10101010101010101000000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1250000^2$$
- 501)
- $$0748999^2 + 1002000^2 := 1251001^2$$
- $$1020\ 0748999^2 + 101202000^2 := 1020\ 1251001^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0748999^2 + 10121202000^2 := 10203020\ 1251001^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0748999^2 + 1012121202000^2 := 102030403020\ 1251001^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0748999^2 + 101212121202000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1251001^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0748999^2 + 10121212121202000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1251001^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0748999^2 + 1012121212121202000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1251001^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0748999^2 + 101212121212121202000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1251001^2$$
- 502)
- $$0747996^2 + 1004000^2 := 1252004^2$$
- $$1020\ 0747996^2 + 101404000^2 := 1020\ 1252004^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0747996^2 + 10141404000^2 := 10203020\ 1252004^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0747996^2 + 1014141404000^2 := 102030403020\ 1252004^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0747996^2 + 101414141404000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1252004^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0747996^2 + 10141414141404000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1252004^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0747996^2 + 1014141414141404000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1252004^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0747996^2 + 101414141414141404000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1252004^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0747996^2 + 10141414141414141404000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1252004^2$$

- 503)
- $$0746991^2 + 1006000^2 := 1253009^2$$
- $$1020\ 0746991^2 + 101606000^2 := 1020\ 1253009^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0746991^2 + 10161606000^2 := 10203020\ 1253009^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0746991^2 + 1016161606000^2 := 102030403020\ 1253009^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0746991^2 + 101616161606000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1253009^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0746991^2 + 10161616161606000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1253009^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0746991^2 + 1016161616161606000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1253009^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0746991^2 + 101616161616161606000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1253009^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0746991^2 + 10161616161616161606000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1253009^2$$
- 504)
- $$0745984^2 + 1008000^2 := 1254016^2$$
- $$1020\ 0745984^2 + 101808000^2 := 1020\ 1254016^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0745984^2 + 10181808000^2 := 10203020\ 1254016^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0745984^2 + 1018181808000^2 := 102030403020\ 1254016^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0745984^2 + 101818181808000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1254016^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0745984^2 + 10181818181808000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1254016^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0745984^2 + 1018181818181808000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1254016^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0745984^2 + 101818181818181808000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1254016^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0745984^2 + 10181818181818181808000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1254016^2$$
- 505)
- $$0744975^2 + 1010000^2 := 1255025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0744975^2 + 102010000^2 := 1020\ 1255025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0744975^2 + 10202010000^2 := 10203020\ 1255025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0744975^2 + 1020202010000^2 := 102030403020\ 1255025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0744975^2 + 102020202010000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1255025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0744975^2 + 10202020202010000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1255025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0744975^2 + 1020202020202010000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1255025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0744975^2 + 102020202020202010000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1255025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0744975^2 + 10202020202020202010000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1255025^2$$
- 506)
- $$0743964^2 + 1012000^2 := 1256036^2$$
- $$1020\ 0743964^2 + 102212000^2 := 1020\ 1256036^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0743964^2 + 10222212000^2 := 10203020\ 1256036^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0743964^2 + 1022222212000^2 := 102030403020\ 1256036^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0743964^2 + 102222222212000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1256036^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0743964^2 + 10222222222212000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1256036^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0743964^2 + 1022222222222212000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1256036^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0743964^2 + 102222222222222212000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1256036^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0743964^2 + 10222222222222222212000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1256036^2$$

- 507)
- $$0742951^2 + 1014000^2 := 1257049^2$$
- $$1020\ 0742951^2 + 102414000^2 := 1020\ 1257049^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0742951^2 + 10242414000^2 := 10203020\ 1257049^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0742951^2 + 1024242414000^2 := 102030403020\ 1257049^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0742951^2 + 102424242414000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1257049^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0742951^2 + 10242424242414000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1257049^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0742951^2 + 1024242424242414000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1257049^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0742951^2 + 102424242424242414000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1257049^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0742951^2 + 10242424242424242414000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1257049^2$$
- 508)
- $$0741936^2 + 1016000^2 := 1258064^2$$
- $$1020\ 0741936^2 + 102616000^2 := 1020\ 1258064^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0741936^2 + 10262616000^2 := 10203020\ 1258064^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0741936^2 + 1026262616000^2 := 102030403020\ 1258064^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0741936^2 + 102626262616000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1258064^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0741936^2 + 10262626262616000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1258064^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0741936^2 + 1026262626262616000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1258064^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0741936^2 + 102626262626262616000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1258064^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0741936^2 + 10262626262626262616000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1258064^2$$
- 509)
- $$0740919^2 + 1018000^2 := 1259081^2$$
- $$1020\ 0740919^2 + 102818000^2 := 1020\ 1259081^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0740919^2 + 10282818000^2 := 10203020\ 1259081^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0740919^2 + 1028282818000^2 := 102030403020\ 1259081^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0740919^2 + 102828282818000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1259081^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0740919^2 + 10282828282818000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1259081^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0740919^2 + 1028282828282818000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1259081^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0740919^2 + 102828282828282818000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1259081^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0740919^2 + 10282828282828282818000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1259081^2$$
- 510)
- $$0739900^2 + 1020000^2 := 1260100^2$$
- $$1020\ 0739900^2 + 103020000^2 := 1020\ 1260100^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0739900^2 + 10303020000^2 := 10203020\ 1260100^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0739900^2 + 1030303020000^2 := 102030403020\ 1260100^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0739900^2 + 103030303020000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1260100^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0739900^2 + 10303030303020000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1260100^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0739900^2 + 1030303030303020000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1260100^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0739900^2 + 103030303030303020000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1260100^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0739900^2 + 10303030303030303020000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1260100^2$$

- 511)
- $$0738879^2 + 1022000^2 := 1261121^2$$
- $$1020\ 0738879^2 + 103222000^2 := 1020\ 1261121^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0738879^2 + 10323222000^2 := 10203020\ 1261121^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0738879^2 + 1032323222000^2 := 102030403020\ 1261121^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0738879^2 + 103232323222000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1261121^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0738879^2 + 10323232323222000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1261121^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0738879^2 + 1032323232323222000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1261121^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0738879^2 + 103232323232323222000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1261121^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0738879^2 + 10323232323232323222000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1261121^2$$
- 512)
- $$0737856^2 + 1024000^2 := 1262144^2$$
- $$1020\ 0737856^2 + 103424000^2 := 1020\ 1262144^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0737856^2 + 10343424000^2 := 10203020\ 1262144^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0737856^2 + 1034343424000^2 := 102030403020\ 1262144^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0737856^2 + 103434343424000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1262144^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0737856^2 + 10343434343424000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1262144^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0737856^2 + 1034343434343424000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1262144^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0737856^2 + 103434343434343424000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1262144^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0737856^2 + 10343434343434343424000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1262144^2$$
- 513)
- $$0736831^2 + 1026000^2 := 1263169^2$$
- $$1020\ 0736831^2 + 103626000^2 := 1020\ 1263169^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0736831^2 + 10363626000^2 := 10203020\ 1263169^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0736831^2 + 1036363626000^2 := 102030403020\ 1263169^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0736831^2 + 103636363626000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1263169^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0736831^2 + 10363636363626000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1263169^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0736831^2 + 1036363636363626000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1263169^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0736831^2 + 103636363636363626000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1263169^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0736831^2 + 10363636363636363626000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1263169^2$$
- 514)
- $$0735804^2 + 1028000^2 := 1264196^2$$
- $$1020\ 0735804^2 + 103828000^2 := 1020\ 1264196^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0735804^2 + 10383828000^2 := 10203020\ 1264196^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0735804^2 + 1038383828000^2 := 102030403020\ 1264196^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0735804^2 + 103838383828000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1264196^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0735804^2 + 10383838383828000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1264196^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0735804^2 + 1038383838383828000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1264196^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0735804^2 + 103838383838383828000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1264196^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0735804^2 + 10383838383838383828000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1264196^2$$

- 515)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0734775^2 + 1030000^2 && := 1265225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0734775^2 + 104030000^2 && := 1020\ 1265225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0734775^2 + 10404030000^2 && := 10203020\ 1265225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0734775^2 + 1040404030000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1265225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0734775^2 + 104040404030000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1265225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0734775^2 + 10404040404030000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1265225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0734775^2 + 1040404040404030000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1265225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0734775^2 + 104040404040404030000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1265225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0734775^2 + 10404040404040404030000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1265225^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 516)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0733744^2 + 1032000^2 && := 1266256^2 \\
 &1020\ 0733744^2 + 104232000^2 && := 1020\ 1266256^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0733744^2 + 10424232000^2 && := 10203020\ 1266256^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0733744^2 + 1042424232000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1266256^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0733744^2 + 104242424232000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1266256^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0733744^2 + 10424242424232000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1266256^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0733744^2 + 1042424242424232000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1266256^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0733744^2 + 104242424242424232000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1266256^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0733744^2 + 10424242424242424232000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1266256^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 517)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0732711^2 + 1034000^2 && := 1267289^2 \\
 &1020\ 0732711^2 + 104434000^2 && := 1020\ 1267289^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0732711^2 + 10444434000^2 && := 10203020\ 1267289^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0732711^2 + 1044444434000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1267289^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0732711^2 + 104444444434000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1267289^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0732711^2 + 10444444444434000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1267289^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0732711^2 + 1044444444444434000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1267289^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0732711^2 + 104444444444444434000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1267289^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0732711^2 + 10444444444444444434000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1267289^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 518)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0731676^2 + 1036000^2 && := 1268324^2 \\
 &1020\ 0731676^2 + 104636000^2 && := 1020\ 1268324^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0731676^2 + 10464636000^2 && := 10203020\ 1268324^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0731676^2 + 1046464636000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1268324^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0731676^2 + 104646464636000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1268324^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0731676^2 + 10464646464636000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1268324^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0731676^2 + 1046464646464636000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1268324^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0731676^2 + 104646464646464636000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1268324^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0731676^2 + 10464646464646464636000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1268324^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 519)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0730639^2 + 1038000^2 & := & 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0730639^2 + 104838000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0730639^2 + 10484838000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0730639^2 + 1048484838000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0730639^2 + 104848484838000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0730639^2 + 10484848484838000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0730639^2 + 1048484848484838000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0730639^2 + 104848484848484838000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1269361^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0730639^2 + 10484848484848484838000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1269361^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 520)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0729600^2 + 1040000^2 & := & 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0729600^2 + 105040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0729600^2 + 10505040000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0729600^2 + 1050505040000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0729600^2 + 105050505040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0729600^2 + 10505050505040000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0729600^2 + 1050505050505040000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0729600^2 + 105050505050505040000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1270400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0729600^2 + 10505050505050505040000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1270400^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 521)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0728559^2 + 1042000^2 & := & 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0728559^2 + 105242000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0728559^2 + 10525242000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0728559^2 + 1052525242000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0728559^2 + 105252525242000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0728559^2 + 10525252525242000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0728559^2 + 1052525252525242000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0728559^2 + 105252525252525242000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1271441^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0728559^2 + 10525252525252525242000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1271441^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 522)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0727516^2 + 1044000^2 & := & 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0727516^2 + 105444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0727516^2 + 10545444000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0727516^2 + 1054545444000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0727516^2 + 105454545444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0727516^2 + 10545454545444000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0727516^2 + 1054545454545444000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0727516^2 + 105454545454545444000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1272484^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0727516^2 + 10545454545454545444000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1272484^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 523)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0726471^2 + 1046000^2$ | $:= 1273529^2$ |
| $1020\ 0726471^2 + 105646000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1273529^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0726471^2 + 10565646000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1273529^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0726471^2 + 1056565646000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1273529^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0726471^2 + 105656565646000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1273529^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0726471^2 + 10565656565646000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1273529^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0726471^2 + 1056565656565646000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1273529^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0726471^2 + 105656565656565646000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1273529^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0726471^2 + 10565656565656565646000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1273529^2$ |
- 524)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0725424^2 + 1048000^2$ | $:= 1274576^2$ |
| $1020\ 0725424^2 + 105848000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1274576^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0725424^2 + 10585848000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1274576^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0725424^2 + 1058585848000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1274576^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0725424^2 + 105858585848000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1274576^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0725424^2 + 10585858585848000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1274576^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0725424^2 + 1058585858585848000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1274576^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0725424^2 + 105858585858585848000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1274576^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0725424^2 + 10585858585858585848000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1274576^2$ |
- 525)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0724375^2 + 1050000^2$ | $:= 1275625^2$ |
| $1020\ 0724375^2 + 106050000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1275625^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0724375^2 + 10606050000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1275625^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0724375^2 + 1060606050000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1275625^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0724375^2 + 106060606050000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1275625^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0724375^2 + 10606060606050000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1275625^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0724375^2 + 1060606060606050000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1275625^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0724375^2 + 106060606060606050000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1275625^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0724375^2 + 106060606060606050000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1275625^2$ |
- 526)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0723324^2 + 1052000^2$ | $:= 1276676^2$ |
| $1020\ 0723324^2 + 106252000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1276676^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0723324^2 + 10626252000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1276676^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0723324^2 + 1062626252000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1276676^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0723324^2 + 106262626252000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1276676^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0723324^2 + 10626262626252000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1276676^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0723324^2 + 1062626262626252000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1276676^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0723324^2 + 106262626262626252000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1276676^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0723324^2 + 106262626262626252000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1276676^2$ |

- 527)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0722271^2 + 1054000^2 && := 1277729^2 \\ &1020\ 0722271^2 + 106454000^2 && := 1020\ 1277729^2 \\ &10203020\ 0722271^2 + 10646454000^2 && := 10203020\ 1277729^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0722271^2 + 1064646454000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1277729^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0722271^2 + 106464646454000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1277729^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0722271^2 + 10646464646454000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1277729^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0722271^2 + 1064646464646454000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1277729^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0722271^2 + 106464646464646454000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1277729^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0722271^2 + 10646464646464646454000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1277729^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 528)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0721216^2 + 1056000^2 && := 1278784^2 \\ &1020\ 0721216^2 + 106656000^2 && := 1020\ 1278784^2 \\ &10203020\ 0721216^2 + 10666656000^2 && := 10203020\ 1278784^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0721216^2 + 1066666656000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1278784^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0721216^2 + 106666666656000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1278784^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0721216^2 + 10666666666656000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1278784^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0721216^2 + 1066666666666656000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1278784^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0721216^2 + 106666666666666656000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1278784^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0721216^2 + 10666666666666666656000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1278784^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 529)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0720159^2 + 1058000^2 && := 1279841^2 \\ &1020\ 0720159^2 + 106858000^2 && := 1020\ 1279841^2 \\ &10203020\ 0720159^2 + 10686858000^2 && := 10203020\ 1279841^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0720159^2 + 1068686858000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1279841^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0720159^2 + 106868686858000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1279841^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0720159^2 + 10686868686858000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1279841^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0720159^2 + 1068686868686858000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1279841^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0720159^2 + 106868686868686858000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1279841^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0720159^2 + 10686868686868686858000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1279841^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 530)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0719100^2 + 1060000^2 && := 1280900^2 \\ &1020\ 0719100^2 + 107060000^2 && := 1020\ 1280900^2 \\ &10203020\ 0719100^2 + 10707060000^2 && := 10203020\ 1280900^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0719100^2 + 1070707060000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1280900^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0719100^2 + 107070707060000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1280900^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0719100^2 + 10707070707060000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1280900^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0719100^2 + 1070707070707060000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1280900^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0719100^2 + 107070707070707060000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1280900^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0719100^2 + 10707070707070707060000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1280900^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 531)
- $$0718039^2 + 1062000^2 := 1281961^2$$
- $$1020\ 0718039^2 + 107262000^2 := 1020\ 1281961^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0718039^2 + 10727262000^2 := 10203020\ 1281961^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0718039^2 + 1072727262000^2 := 102030403020\ 1281961^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0718039^2 + 107272727262000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1281961^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0718039^2 + 10727272727262000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1281961^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0718039^2 + 1072727272727262000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1281961^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0718039^2 + 107272727272727262000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1281961^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0718039^2 + 107272727272727262000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1281961^2$$
- 532)
- $$0716976^2 + 1064000^2 := 1283024^2$$
- $$1020\ 0716976^2 + 107464000^2 := 1020\ 1283024^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0716976^2 + 10747464000^2 := 10203020\ 1283024^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0716976^2 + 1074747464000^2 := 102030403020\ 1283024^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0716976^2 + 107474747464000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1283024^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0716976^2 + 10747474747464000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1283024^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0716976^2 + 1074747474747464000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1283024^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0716976^2 + 107474747474747464000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1283024^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0716976^2 + 107474747474747464000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1283024^2$$
- 533)
- $$0715911^2 + 1066000^2 := 1284089^2$$
- $$1020\ 0715911^2 + 107666000^2 := 1020\ 1284089^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0715911^2 + 10767666000^2 := 10203020\ 1284089^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0715911^2 + 1076767666000^2 := 102030403020\ 1284089^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0715911^2 + 107676767666000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1284089^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0715911^2 + 10767676767666000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1284089^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0715911^2 + 1076767676767666000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1284089^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0715911^2 + 107676767676767666000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1284089^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0715911^2 + 107676767676767666000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1284089^2$$
- 534)
- $$0714844^2 + 1068000^2 := 1285156^2$$
- $$1020\ 0714844^2 + 107868000^2 := 1020\ 1285156^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0714844^2 + 10787868000^2 := 10203020\ 1285156^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0714844^2 + 1078787868000^2 := 102030403020\ 1285156^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0714844^2 + 107878787868000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1285156^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0714844^2 + 10787878787868000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1285156^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0714844^2 + 1078787878787868000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1285156^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0714844^2 + 107878787878787868000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1285156^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0714844^2 + 107878787878787868000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1285156^2$$

- 535)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0713775^2 + 1070000^2$ | $:= 1286225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0713775^2 + 108070000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1286225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0713775^2 + 10808070000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1286225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0713775^2 + 1080808070000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1286225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0713775^2 + 108080808070000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1286225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0713775^2 + 10808080808070000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1286225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0713775^2 + 1080808080808070000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1286225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0713775^2 + 108080808080808070000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1286225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0713775^2 + 10808080808080808070000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1286225^2$ |
- 536)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0712704^2 + 1072000^2$ | $:= 1287296^2$ |
| $1020\ 0712704^2 + 108272000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1287296^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0712704^2 + 10828272000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1287296^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0712704^2 + 1082828272000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1287296^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0712704^2 + 108282828272000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1287296^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0712704^2 + 10828282828272000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1287296^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0712704^2 + 1082828282828272000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1287296^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0712704^2 + 108282828282828272000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1287296^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0712704^2 + 10828282828282828272000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1287296^2$ |
- 537)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0711631^2 + 1074000^2$ | $:= 1288369^2$ |
| $1020\ 0711631^2 + 108474000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1288369^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0711631^2 + 10848474000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1288369^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0711631^2 + 1084848474000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1288369^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0711631^2 + 108484848474000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1288369^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0711631^2 + 10848484848474000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1288369^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0711631^2 + 1084848484848474000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1288369^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0711631^2 + 108484848484848474000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1288369^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0711631^2 + 10848484848484848474000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1288369^2$ |
- 538)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0710556^2 + 1076000^2$ | $:= 1289444^2$ |
| $1020\ 0710556^2 + 108676000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1289444^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0710556^2 + 10868676000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1289444^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0710556^2 + 1086868676000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1289444^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0710556^2 + 108686868676000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1289444^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0710556^2 + 10868686868676000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1289444^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0710556^2 + 1086868686868676000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1289444^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0710556^2 + 108686868686868676000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1289444^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0710556^2 + 10868686868686868676000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1289444^2$ |

- 539)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0709479^2 + 1078000^2 && := 1290521^2 \\ &1020\ 0709479^2 + 108878000^2 && := 1020\ 1290521^2 \\ &10203020\ 0709479^2 + 10888878000^2 && := 10203020\ 1290521^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0709479^2 + 1088888878000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1290521^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0709479^2 + 108888888878000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1290521^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0709479^2 + 10888888888878000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1290521^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0709479^2 + 1088888888888878000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1290521^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0709479^2 + 108888888888888878000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1290521^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0709479^2 + 10888888888888888878000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1290521^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 540)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0708400^2 + 1080000^2 && := 1291600^2 \\ &1020\ 0708400^2 + 109080000^2 && := 1020\ 1291600^2 \\ &10203020\ 0708400^2 + 10909080000^2 && := 10203020\ 1291600^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0708400^2 + 1090909080000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1291600^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0708400^2 + 109090909080000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1291600^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0708400^2 + 10909090909080000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1291600^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0708400^2 + 1090909090909080000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1291600^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0708400^2 + 109090909090909080000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1291600^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0708400^2 + 10909090909090909080000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1291600^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 541)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0707319^2 + 1082000^2 && := 1292681^2 \\ &1020\ 0707319^2 + 109282000^2 && := 1020\ 1292681^2 \\ &10203020\ 0707319^2 + 10929282000^2 && := 10203020\ 1292681^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0707319^2 + 1092929282000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1292681^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0707319^2 + 109292929282000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1292681^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0707319^2 + 10929292929282000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1292681^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0707319^2 + 1092929292929282000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1292681^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0707319^2 + 109292929292929282000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1292681^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0707319^2 + 109292929292929282000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1292681^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 542)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0706236^2 + 1084000^2 && := 1293764^2 \\ &1020\ 0706236^2 + 109484000^2 && := 1020\ 1293764^2 \\ &10203020\ 0706236^2 + 10949484000^2 && := 10203020\ 1293764^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0706236^2 + 1094949484000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1293764^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0706236^2 + 109494949484000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1293764^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0706236^2 + 10949494949484000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1293764^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0706236^2 + 1094949494949484000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1293764^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0706236^2 + 109494949494949484000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1293764^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0706236^2 + 10949494949494949484000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1293764^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 543)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0705151^2 + 1086000^2$ | $:= 1294849^2$ |
| $1020\ 0705151^2 + 109686000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1294849^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0705151^2 + 10969686000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1294849^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0705151^2 + 1096969686000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1294849^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0705151^2 + 109696969686000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1294849^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0705151^2 + 10969696969686000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1294849^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0705151^2 + 1096969696969686000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1294849^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0705151^2 + 1096969696969686000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1294849^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0705151^2 + 109696969696969686000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1294849^2$ |
- 544)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0704064^2 + 1088000^2$ | $:= 1295936^2$ |
| $1020\ 0704064^2 + 109888000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1295936^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0704064^2 + 10989888000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1295936^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0704064^2 + 1098989888000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1295936^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0704064^2 + 109898989888000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1295936^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0704064^2 + 10989898989888000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1295936^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0704064^2 + 1098989898989888000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1295936^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0704064^2 + 1098989898989888000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1295936^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0704064^2 + 109898989898989888000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1295936^2$ |
- 545)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0702975^2 + 1090000^2$ | $:= 1297025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0702975^2 + 110090000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1297025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0702975^2 + 11010090000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1297025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0702975^2 + 1101010090000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1297025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0702975^2 + 110101010090000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1297025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0702975^2 + 11010101010090000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1297025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0702975^2 + 1101010101010090000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1297025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0702975^2 + 110101010101010090000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1297025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0702975^2 + 11010101010101010090000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1297025^2$ |
- 546)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0701884^2 + 1092000^2$ | $:= 1298116^2$ |
| $1020\ 0701884^2 + 110292000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1298116^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0701884^2 + 11030292000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1298116^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0701884^2 + 1103030292000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1298116^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0701884^2 + 110303030292000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1298116^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0701884^2 + 11030303030292000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1298116^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0701884^2 + 1103030303030292000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1298116^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0701884^2 + 110303030303030292000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1298116^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0701884^2 + 11030303030303030292000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1298116^2$ |

- 547)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0700791^2 + 1094000^2 && := 1299209^2 \\ &1020\ 0700791^2 + 110494000^2 && := 1020\ 1299209^2 \\ &10203020\ 0700791^2 + 11050494000^2 && := 10203020\ 1299209^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0700791^2 + 1105050494000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1299209^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0700791^2 + 110505050494000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1299209^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0700791^2 + 11050505050494000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1299209^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0700791^2 + 1105050505050494000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1299209^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0700791^2 + 110505050505050494000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1299209^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0700791^2 + 11050505050505050494000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1299209^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 548)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0699696^2 + 1096000^2 && := 1300304^2 \\ &1020\ 0699696^2 + 110696000^2 && := 1020\ 1300304^2 \\ &10203020\ 0699696^2 + 11070696000^2 && := 10203020\ 1300304^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0699696^2 + 1107070696000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1300304^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0699696^2 + 110707070696000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1300304^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0699696^2 + 11070707070696000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1300304^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0699696^2 + 1107070707070696000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1300304^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0699696^2 + 110707070707070696000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1300304^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0699696^2 + 11070707070707070696000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1300304^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 549)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0698599^2 + 1098000^2 && := 1301401^2 \\ &1020\ 0698599^2 + 110898000^2 && := 1020\ 1301401^2 \\ &10203020\ 0698599^2 + 11090898000^2 && := 10203020\ 1301401^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0698599^2 + 1109090898000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1301401^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0698599^2 + 110909090898000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1301401^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0698599^2 + 11090909090898000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1301401^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0698599^2 + 1109090909090898000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1301401^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0698599^2 + 110909090909090898000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1301401^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0698599^2 + 11090909090909090898000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1301401^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 550)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0697500^2 + 1100000^2 && := 1302500^2 \\ &1020\ 0697500^2 + 111100000^2 && := 1020\ 1302500^2 \\ &10203020\ 0697500^2 + 11111100000^2 && := 10203020\ 1302500^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0697500^2 + 1111111100000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1302500^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0697500^2 + 111111111100000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1302500^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0697500^2 + 11111111111100000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1302500^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0697500^2 + 1111111111111100000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1302500^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0697500^2 + 111111111111111100000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1302500^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0697500^2 + 11111111111111111100000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1302500^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 551)
- $$0696399^2 + 1102000^2 := 1303601^2$$
- $$1020\ 0696399^2 + 111302000^2 := 1020\ 1303601^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0696399^2 + 11131302000^2 := 10203020\ 1303601^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0696399^2 + 1113131302000^2 := 102030403020\ 1303601^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0696399^2 + 111313131302000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1303601^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0696399^2 + 11131313131302000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1303601^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0696399^2 + 1113131313131302000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1303601^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0696399^2 + 111313131313131302000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1303601^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0696399^2 + 11131313131313131302000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1303601^2$$
- 552)
- $$0695296^2 + 1104000^2 := 1304704^2$$
- $$1020\ 0695296^2 + 111504000^2 := 1020\ 1304704^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0695296^2 + 11151504000^2 := 10203020\ 1304704^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0695296^2 + 1115151504000^2 := 102030403020\ 1304704^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0695296^2 + 111515151504000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1304704^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0695296^2 + 11151515151504000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1304704^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0695296^2 + 1115151515151504000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1304704^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0695296^2 + 111515151515151504000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1304704^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0695296^2 + 11151515151515151504000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1304704^2$$
- 553)
- $$0694191^2 + 1106000^2 := 1305809^2$$
- $$1020\ 0694191^2 + 111706000^2 := 1020\ 1305809^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0694191^2 + 11171706000^2 := 10203020\ 1305809^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0694191^2 + 1117171706000^2 := 102030403020\ 1305809^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0694191^2 + 111717171706000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1305809^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0694191^2 + 11171717171706000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1305809^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0694191^2 + 1117171717171706000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1305809^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0694191^2 + 111717171717171706000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1305809^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0694191^2 + 11171717171717171706000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1305809^2$$
- 554)
- $$0693084^2 + 1108000^2 := 1306916^2$$
- $$1020\ 0693084^2 + 111908000^2 := 1020\ 1306916^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0693084^2 + 11191908000^2 := 10203020\ 1306916^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0693084^2 + 1119191908000^2 := 102030403020\ 1306916^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0693084^2 + 111919191908000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1306916^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0693084^2 + 11191919191908000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1306916^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0693084^2 + 1119191919191908000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1306916^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0693084^2 + 111919191919191908000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1306916^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0693084^2 + 11191919191919191908000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1306916^2$$

- 555)
- $$0691975^2 + 1110000^2 := 1308025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0691975^2 + 112110000^2 := 1020\ 1308025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0691975^2 + 11212110000^2 := 10203020\ 1308025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0691975^2 + 1121212110000^2 := 102030403020\ 1308025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0691975^2 + 112121212110000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1308025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0691975^2 + 11212121212110000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1308025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0691975^2 + 1121212121212110000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1308025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0691975^2 + 112121212121212110000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1308025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0691975^2 + 11212121212121212110000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1308025^2$$
- 556)
- $$0690864^2 + 1112000^2 := 1309136^2$$
- $$1020\ 0690864^2 + 112312000^2 := 1020\ 1309136^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0690864^2 + 11232312000^2 := 10203020\ 1309136^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0690864^2 + 1123232312000^2 := 102030403020\ 1309136^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0690864^2 + 112323232312000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1309136^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0690864^2 + 11232323232312000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1309136^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0690864^2 + 1123232323232312000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1309136^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0690864^2 + 112323232323232312000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1309136^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0690864^2 + 11232323232323232312000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1309136^2$$
- 557)
- $$0689751^2 + 1114000^2 := 1310249^2$$
- $$1020\ 0689751^2 + 112514000^2 := 1020\ 1310249^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0689751^2 + 11252514000^2 := 10203020\ 1310249^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0689751^2 + 1125252514000^2 := 102030403020\ 1310249^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0689751^2 + 112525252514000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1310249^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0689751^2 + 11252525252514000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1310249^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0689751^2 + 1125252525252514000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1310249^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0689751^2 + 112525252525252514000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1310249^2$$
- 558)
- $$0688636^2 + 1116000^2 := 1311364^2$$
- $$1020\ 0688636^2 + 112716000^2 := 1020\ 1311364^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0688636^2 + 11272716000^2 := 10203020\ 1311364^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0688636^2 + 1127272716000^2 := 102030403020\ 1311364^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0688636^2 + 112727272716000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1311364^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0688636^2 + 11272727272716000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1311364^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0688636^2 + 1127272727272716000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1311364^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0688636^2 + 112727272727272716000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1311364^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0688636^2 + 11272727272727272716000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1311364^2$$

- 559)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0687519^2 + 1118000^2 && := 1312481^2 \\
 &1020\ 0687519^2 + 112918000^2 && := 1020\ 1312481^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0687519^2 + 11292918000^2 && := 10203020\ 1312481^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0687519^2 + 1129292918000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1312481^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0687519^2 + 112929292918000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1312481^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0687519^2 + 11292929292918000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1312481^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0687519^2 + 1129292929292918000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1312481^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0687519^2 + 112929292929292918000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1312481^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0687519^2 + 11292929292929292918000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1312481^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 560)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0686400^2 + 1120000^2 && := 1313600^2 \\
 &1020\ 0686400^2 + 113120000^2 && := 1020\ 1313600^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0686400^2 + 11313120000^2 && := 10203020\ 1313600^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0686400^2 + 1131313120000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1313600^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0686400^2 + 113131313120000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1313600^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0686400^2 + 11313131313120000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1313600^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0686400^2 + 1131313131313120000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1313600^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0686400^2 + 113131313131313120000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1313600^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0686400^2 + 11313131313131313120000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1313600^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 561)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0685279^2 + 1122000^2 && := 1314721^2 \\
 &1020\ 0685279^2 + 113322000^2 && := 1020\ 1314721^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0685279^2 + 11333322000^2 && := 10203020\ 1314721^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0685279^2 + 1133333322000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1314721^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0685279^2 + 113333333322000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1314721^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0685279^2 + 11333333333322000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1314721^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0685279^2 + 1133333333333322000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1314721^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0685279^2 + 113333333333333322000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1314721^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0685279^2 + 11333333333333333322000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1314721^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 562)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0684156^2 + 1124000^2 && := 1315844^2 \\
 &1020\ 0684156^2 + 113524000^2 && := 1020\ 1315844^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0684156^2 + 11353524000^2 && := 10203020\ 1315844^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0684156^2 + 1135353524000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1315844^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0684156^2 + 113535353524000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1315844^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0684156^2 + 11353535353524000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1315844^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0684156^2 + 1135353535353524000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1315844^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0684156^2 + 113535353535353524000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1315844^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0684156^2 + 11353535353535353524000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1315844^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 563)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0683031^2 + 1126000^2$ | $:= 1316969^2$ |
| $1020\ 0683031^2 + 113726000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1316969^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0683031^2 + 11373726000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1316969^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0683031^2 + 1137373726000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1316969^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0683031^2 + 113737373726000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1316969^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0683031^2 + 11373737373726000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1316969^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0683031^2 + 1137373737373726000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1316969^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0683031^2 + 113737373737373726000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1316969^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0683031^2 + 11373737373737373726000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1316969^2$ |
- 564)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0681904^2 + 1128000^2$ | $:= 1318096^2$ |
| $1020\ 0681904^2 + 113928000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1318096^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0681904^2 + 11393928000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1318096^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0681904^2 + 1139393928000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1318096^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0681904^2 + 113939393928000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1318096^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0681904^2 + 11393939393928000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1318096^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0681904^2 + 1139393939393928000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1318096^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0681904^2 + 113939393939393928000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1318096^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0681904^2 + 11393939393939393928000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1318096^2$ |
- 565)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0680775^2 + 1130000^2$ | $:= 1319225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0680775^2 + 114130000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1319225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0680775^2 + 11414130000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1319225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0680775^2 + 1141414130000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1319225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0680775^2 + 114141414130000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1319225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0680775^2 + 11414141414130000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1319225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0680775^2 + 1141414141414130000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1319225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0680775^2 + 114141414141414130000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1319225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0680775^2 + 11414141414141414130000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1319225^2$ |
- 566)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0679644^2 + 1132000^2$ | $:= 1320356^2$ |
| $1020\ 0679644^2 + 114332000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1320356^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0679644^2 + 11434332000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1320356^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0679644^2 + 1143434332000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1320356^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0679644^2 + 114343434332000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1320356^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0679644^2 + 11434343434332000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1320356^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0679644^2 + 1143434343434332000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1320356^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0679644^2 + 114343434343434332000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1320356^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0679644^2 + 11434343434343434332000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1320356^2$ |

- 567)
- $$0678511^2 + 1134000^2 := 1321489^2$$
- $$1020\ 0678511^2 + 114534000^2 := 1020\ 1321489^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0678511^2 + 11454534000^2 := 10203020\ 1321489^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0678511^2 + 1145454534000^2 := 102030403020\ 1321489^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0678511^2 + 114545454534000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1321489^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0678511^2 + 11454545454534000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1321489^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0678511^2 + 1145454545454534000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1321489^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0678511^2 + 114545454545454534000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1321489^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0678511^2 + 11454545454545454534000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1321489^2$$
- 568)
- $$0677376^2 + 1136000^2 := 1322624^2$$
- $$1020\ 0677376^2 + 114736000^2 := 1020\ 1322624^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0677376^2 + 11474736000^2 := 10203020\ 1322624^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0677376^2 + 1147474736000^2 := 102030403020\ 1322624^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0677376^2 + 114747474736000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1322624^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0677376^2 + 11474747474736000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1322624^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0677376^2 + 1147474747474736000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1322624^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0677376^2 + 114747474747474736000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1322624^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0677376^2 + 11474747474747474736000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1322624^2$$
- 569)
- $$0676239^2 + 1138000^2 := 1323761^2$$
- $$1020\ 0676239^2 + 114938000^2 := 1020\ 1323761^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0676239^2 + 11494938000^2 := 10203020\ 1323761^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0676239^2 + 1149494938000^2 := 102030403020\ 1323761^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0676239^2 + 114949494938000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1323761^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0676239^2 + 11494949494938000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1323761^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0676239^2 + 1149494949494938000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1323761^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0676239^2 + 114949494949494938000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1323761^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0676239^2 + 11494949494949494938000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1323761^2$$
- 570)
- $$0675100^2 + 1140000^2 := 1324900^2$$
- $$1020\ 0675100^2 + 115140000^2 := 1020\ 1324900^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0675100^2 + 11515140000^2 := 10203020\ 1324900^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0675100^2 + 1151515140000^2 := 102030403020\ 1324900^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0675100^2 + 115151515140000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1324900^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0675100^2 + 11515151515140000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1324900^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0675100^2 + 1151515151515140000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1324900^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0675100^2 + 115151515151515140000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1324900^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0675100^2 + 11515151515151515140000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1324900^2$$

- 571)
- $$0673959^2 + 1142000^2 := 1326041^2$$
- $$1020\ 0673959^2 + 115342000^2 := 1020\ 1326041^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0673959^2 + 11535342000^2 := 10203020\ 1326041^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0673959^2 + 1153535342000^2 := 102030403020\ 1326041^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0673959^2 + 115353535342000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1326041^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0673959^2 + 11535353535342000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1326041^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0673959^2 + 1153535353535342000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1326041^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0673959^2 + 115353535353535342000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1326041^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0673959^2 + 11535353535353535342000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1326041^2$$
- 572)
- $$0672816^2 + 1144000^2 := 1327184^2$$
- $$1020\ 0672816^2 + 115544000^2 := 1020\ 1327184^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0672816^2 + 11555544000^2 := 10203020\ 1327184^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0672816^2 + 115555544000^2 := 102030403020\ 1327184^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0672816^2 + 1155555544000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1327184^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0672816^2 + 115555555544000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1327184^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0672816^2 + 11555555555544000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1327184^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0672816^2 + 1155555555555544000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1327184^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0672816^2 + 115555555555555544000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1327184^2$$
- 573)
- $$0671671^2 + 1146000^2 := 1328329^2$$
- $$1020\ 0671671^2 + 115746000^2 := 1020\ 1328329^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0671671^2 + 11575746000^2 := 10203020\ 1328329^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0671671^2 + 1157575746000^2 := 102030403020\ 1328329^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0671671^2 + 115757575746000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1328329^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0671671^2 + 11575757575746000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1328329^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0671671^2 + 1157575757575746000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1328329^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0671671^2 + 115757575757575746000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1328329^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0671671^2 + 11575757575757575746000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1328329^2$$
- 574)
- $$0670524^2 + 1148000^2 := 1329476^2$$
- $$1020\ 0670524^2 + 115948000^2 := 1020\ 1329476^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0670524^2 + 11595948000^2 := 10203020\ 1329476^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0670524^2 + 1159595948000^2 := 102030403020\ 1329476^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0670524^2 + 115959595948000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1329476^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0670524^2 + 11595959595948000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1329476^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0670524^2 + 1159595959595948000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1329476^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0670524^2 + 115959595959595948000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1329476^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0670524^2 + 11595959595959595948000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1329476^2$$

- 575)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0669375^2 + 1150000^2$ | $:= 1330625^2$ |
| $1020\ 0669375^2 + 116150000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1330625^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0669375^2 + 11616150000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1330625^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0669375^2 + 1161616150000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1330625^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0669375^2 + 116161616150000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1330625^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0669375^2 + 11616161616150000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1330625^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0669375^2 + 1161616161616150000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1330625^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0669375^2 + 116161616161616150000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1330625^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0669375^2 + 11616161616161616150000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1330625^2$ |
- 576)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0668224^2 + 1152000^2$ | $:= 1331776^2$ |
| $1020\ 0668224^2 + 116352000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1331776^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0668224^2 + 11636352000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1331776^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0668224^2 + 1163636352000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1331776^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0668224^2 + 116363636352000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1331776^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0668224^2 + 11636363636352000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1331776^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0668224^2 + 1163636363636352000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1331776^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0668224^2 + 116363636363636352000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1331776^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0668224^2 + 11636363636363636352000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1331776^2$ |
- 577)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0667071^2 + 1154000^2$ | $:= 1332929^2$ |
| $1020\ 0667071^2 + 116554000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1332929^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0667071^2 + 11656554000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1332929^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0667071^2 + 1165656554000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1332929^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0667071^2 + 116565656554000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1332929^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0667071^2 + 11656565656554000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1332929^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0667071^2 + 1165656565656554000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1332929^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0667071^2 + 116565656565656554000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1332929^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0667071^2 + 11656565656565656554000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1332929^2$ |
- 578)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0665916^2 + 1156000^2$ | $:= 1334084^2$ |
| $1020\ 0665916^2 + 116756000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1334084^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0665916^2 + 11676756000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1334084^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0665916^2 + 1167676756000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1334084^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0665916^2 + 116767676756000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1334084^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0665916^2 + 11676767676756000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1334084^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0665916^2 + 1167676767676756000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1334084^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0665916^2 + 116767676767676756000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1334084^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0665916^2 + 11676767676767676756000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1334084^2$ |

- 579)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0664759^2 + 1158000^2$ | $:= 1335241^2$ |
| $1020\ 0664759^2 + 116958000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1335241^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0664759^2 + 11696958000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1335241^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0664759^2 + 1169696958000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1335241^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0664759^2 + 116969696958000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1335241^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0664759^2 + 11696969696958000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1335241^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0664759^2 + 1169696969696958000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1335241^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0664759^2 + 116969696969696958000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1335241^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0664759^2 + 11696969696969696958000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1335241^2$ |
- 580)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0663600^2 + 1160000^2$ | $:= 1336400^2$ |
| $1020\ 0663600^2 + 117160000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1336400^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0663600^2 + 11717160000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1336400^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0663600^2 + 1171717160000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1336400^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0663600^2 + 117171717160000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1336400^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0663600^2 + 11717171717160000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1336400^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0663600^2 + 1171717171717160000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1336400^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0663600^2 + 117171717171717160000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1336400^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0663600^2 + 11717171717171717160000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1336400^2$ |
- 581)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0662439^2 + 1162000^2$ | $:= 1337561^2$ |
| $1020\ 0662439^2 + 117362000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1337561^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0662439^2 + 11737362000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1337561^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0662439^2 + 1173737362000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1337561^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0662439^2 + 117373737362000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1337561^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0662439^2 + 11737373737362000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1337561^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0662439^2 + 1173737373737362000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1337561^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0662439^2 + 117373737373737362000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1337561^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0662439^2 + 11737373737373737362000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1337561^2$ |
- 582)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0661276^2 + 1164000^2$ | $:= 1338724^2$ |
| $1020\ 0661276^2 + 117564000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1338724^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0661276^2 + 11757564000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1338724^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0661276^2 + 1175757564000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1338724^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0661276^2 + 117575757564000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1338724^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0661276^2 + 11757575757564000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1338724^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0661276^2 + 1175757575757564000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1338724^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0661276^2 + 117575757575757564000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1338724^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0661276^2 + 11757575757575757564000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1338724^2$ |

- 583)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0660111^2 + 1166000^2$ | $:= 1339889^2$ |
| $1020\ 0660111^2 + 117766000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1339889^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0660111^2 + 11777766000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1339889^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0660111^2 + 1177777766000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1339889^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0660111^2 + 117777777766000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1339889^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0660111^2 + 11777777777766000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1339889^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0660111^2 + 1177777777777766000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1339889^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0660111^2 + 117777777777777766000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1339889^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0660111^2 + 11777777777777777766000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1339889^2$ |
- 584)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0658944^2 + 1168000^2$ | $:= 1341056^2$ |
| $1020\ 0658944^2 + 117968000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1341056^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0658944^2 + 11797968000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1341056^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0658944^2 + 1179797968000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1341056^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0658944^2 + 117979797968000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1341056^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0658944^2 + 11797979797968000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1341056^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0658944^2 + 1179797979797968000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1341056^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0658944^2 + 117979797979797968000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1341056^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0658944^2 + 11797979797979797968000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1341056^2$ |
- 585)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0657775^2 + 1170000^2$ | $:= 1342225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0657775^2 + 118170000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1342225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0657775^2 + 11818170000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1342225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0657775^2 + 1181818170000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1342225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0657775^2 + 118181818170000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1342225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0657775^2 + 11818181818170000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1342225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0657775^2 + 1181818181818170000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1342225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0657775^2 + 118181818181818170000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1342225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0657775^2 + 11818181818181818170000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1342225^2$ |
- 586)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0656604^2 + 1172000^2$ | $:= 1343396^2$ |
| $1020\ 0656604^2 + 118372000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1343396^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0656604^2 + 11838372000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1343396^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0656604^2 + 1183838372000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1343396^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0656604^2 + 118383838372000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1343396^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0656604^2 + 11838383838372000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1343396^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0656604^2 + 1183838383838372000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1343396^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0656604^2 + 118383838383838372000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1343396^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0656604^2 + 11838383838383838372000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1343396^2$ |

- 587)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0655431^2 + 1174000^2$ | $:= 1344569^2$ |
| $1020\ 0655431^2 + 118574000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1344569^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0655431^2 + 11858574000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1344569^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0655431^2 + 1185858574000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1344569^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0655431^2 + 118585858574000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1344569^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0655431^2 + 11858585858574000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1344569^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0655431^2 + 1185858585858574000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1344569^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0655431^2 + 118585858585858574000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1344569^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0655431^2 + 11858585858585858574000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1344569^2$ |
- 588)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0654256^2 + 1176000^2$ | $:= 1345744^2$ |
| $1020\ 0654256^2 + 118776000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1345744^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0654256^2 + 11878776000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1345744^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0654256^2 + 1187878776000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1345744^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0654256^2 + 118787878776000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1345744^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0654256^2 + 11878787878776000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1345744^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0654256^2 + 1187878787878776000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1345744^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0654256^2 + 118787878787878776000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1345744^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0654256^2 + 11878787878787878776000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1345744^2$ |
- 589)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0653079^2 + 1178000^2$ | $:= 1346921^2$ |
| $1020\ 0653079^2 + 118978000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1346921^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0653079^2 + 11898978000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1346921^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0653079^2 + 1189898978000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1346921^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0653079^2 + 118989898978000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1346921^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0653079^2 + 11898989898978000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1346921^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0653079^2 + 1189898989898978000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1346921^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0653079^2 + 118989898989898978000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1346921^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0653079^2 + 11898989898989898978000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1346921^2$ |
- 590)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0651900^2 + 1180000^2$ | $:= 1348100^2$ |
| $1020\ 0651900^2 + 119180000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1348100^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0651900^2 + 11919180000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1348100^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0651900^2 + 1191919180000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1348100^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0651900^2 + 119191919180000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1348100^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0651900^2 + 11919191919180000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1348100^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0651900^2 + 1191919191919180000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1348100^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0651900^2 + 119191919191919180000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1348100^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0651900^2 + 11919191919191919180000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1348100^2$ |

- 591)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0650719^2 + 1182000^2$ | $:= 1349281^2$ |
| $1020\ 0650719^2 + 119382000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1349281^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0650719^2 + 11939382000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1349281^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0650719^2 + 1193939382000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1349281^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0650719^2 + 119393939382000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1349281^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0650719^2 + 11939393939382000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1349281^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0650719^2 + 1193939393939382000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1349281^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0650719^2 + 119393939393939382000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1349281^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0650719^2 + 11939393939393939382000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1349281^2$ |
- 592)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0649536^2 + 1184000^2$ | $:= 1350464^2$ |
| $1020\ 0649536^2 + 119584000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1350464^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0649536^2 + 11959584000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1350464^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0649536^2 + 1195959584000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1350464^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0649536^2 + 119595959584000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1350464^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0649536^2 + 11959595959584000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1350464^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0649536^2 + 1195959595959584000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1350464^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0649536^2 + 119595959595959584000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1350464^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0649536^2 + 11959595959595959584000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1350464^2$ |
- 593)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0648351^2 + 1186000^2$ | $:= 1351649^2$ |
| $1020\ 0648351^2 + 119786000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1351649^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0648351^2 + 11979786000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1351649^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0648351^2 + 1197979786000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1351649^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0648351^2 + 119797979786000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1351649^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0648351^2 + 11979797979786000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1351649^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0648351^2 + 1197979797979786000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1351649^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0648351^2 + 119797979797979786000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1351649^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0648351^2 + 11979797979797979786000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1351649^2$ |
- 594)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0647164^2 + 1188000^2$ | $:= 1352836^2$ |
| $1020\ 0647164^2 + 119988000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1352836^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0647164^2 + 11999988000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1352836^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0647164^2 + 1199999988000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1352836^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0647164^2 + 119999999988000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1352836^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0647164^2 + 11999999999988000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1352836^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0647164^2 + 1199999999999988000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1352836^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0647164^2 + 119999999999999988000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1352836^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0647164^2 + 11999999999999999988000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1352836^2$ |

- 595)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0645975^2 + 1190000^2$ | $:= 1354025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0645975^2 + 120190000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1354025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0645975^2 + 12020190000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1354025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0645975^2 + 1202020190000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1354025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0645975^2 + 120202020190000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1354025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0645975^2 + 12020202020190000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1354025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0645975^2 + 1202020202020190000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1354025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0645975^2 + 120202020202020190000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1354025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0645975^2 + 12020202020202020190000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1354025^2$ |
- 596)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0644784^2 + 1192000^2$ | $:= 1355216^2$ |
| $1020\ 0644784^2 + 120392000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1355216^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0644784^2 + 12040392000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1355216^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0644784^2 + 1204040392000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1355216^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0644784^2 + 120404040392000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1355216^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0644784^2 + 12040404040392000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1355216^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0644784^2 + 1204040404040392000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1355216^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0644784^2 + 120404040404040392000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1355216^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0644784^2 + 12040404040404040392000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1355216^2$ |
- 597)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0643591^2 + 1194000^2$ | $:= 1356409^2$ |
| $1020\ 0643591^2 + 120594000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1356409^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0643591^2 + 12060594000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1356409^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0643591^2 + 1206060594000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1356409^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0643591^2 + 120606060594000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1356409^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0643591^2 + 12060606060594000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1356409^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0643591^2 + 1206060606060594000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1356409^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0643591^2 + 120606060606060594000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1356409^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0643591^2 + 12060606060606060594000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1356409^2$ |
- 598)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0642396^2 + 1196000^2$ | $:= 1357604^2$ |
| $1020\ 0642396^2 + 120796000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1357604^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0642396^2 + 12080796000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1357604^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0642396^2 + 1208080796000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1357604^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0642396^2 + 120808080796000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1357604^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0642396^2 + 12080808080796000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1357604^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0642396^2 + 1208080808080796000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1357604^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0642396^2 + 120808080808080796000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1357604^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0642396^2 + 12080808080808080796000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1357604^2$ |

- 599)
- $$0641199^2 + 1198000^2 := 1358801^2$$
- $$1020\ 0641199^2 + 120998000^2 := 1020\ 1358801^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0641199^2 + 12100998000^2 := 10203020\ 1358801^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0641199^2 + 1210100998000^2 := 102030403020\ 1358801^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0641199^2 + 121010100998000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1358801^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0641199^2 + 12101010100998000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1358801^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0641199^2 + 1210101010100998000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1358801^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0641199^2 + 121010101010100998000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1358801^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0641199^2 + 12101010101010100998000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1358801^2$$
- 600)
- $$0640000^2 + 1200000^2 := 1360000^2$$
- $$1020\ 0640000^2 + 121200000^2 := 1020\ 1360000^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0640000^2 + 12121200000^2 := 10203020\ 1360000^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0640000^2 + 1212121200000^2 := 102030403020\ 1360000^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0640000^2 + 121212121200000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1360000^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0640000^2 + 12121212121200000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1360000^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0640000^2 + 1212121212121200000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1360000^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0640000^2 + 121212121212121200000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1360000^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0640000^2 + 12121212121212121200000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1360000^2$$
- 601)
- $$0638799^2 + 1202000^2 := 1361201^2$$
- $$1020\ 0638799^2 + 121402000^2 := 1020\ 1361201^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0638799^2 + 12141402000^2 := 10203020\ 1361201^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0638799^2 + 1214141402000^2 := 102030403020\ 1361201^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0638799^2 + 121414141402000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1361201^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0638799^2 + 12141414141402000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1361201^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0638799^2 + 1214141414141402000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1361201^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0638799^2 + 121414141414141402000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1361201^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0638799^2 + 12141414141414141402000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1361201^2$$
- 602)
- $$0637596^2 + 1204000^2 := 1362404^2$$
- $$1020\ 0637596^2 + 121604000^2 := 1020\ 1362404^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0637596^2 + 12161604000^2 := 10203020\ 1362404^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0637596^2 + 1216161604000^2 := 102030403020\ 1362404^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0637596^2 + 121616161604000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1362404^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0637596^2 + 12161616161604000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1362404^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0637596^2 + 1216161616161604000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1362404^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0637596^2 + 121616161616161604000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1362404^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0637596^2 + 12161616161616161604000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1362404^2$$

- 603)
- $$0636391^2 + 1206000^2 := 1363609^2$$
- $$1020\ 0636391^2 + 121806000^2 := 1020\ 1363609^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0636391^2 + 12181806000^2 := 10203020\ 1363609^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0636391^2 + 1218181806000^2 := 102030403020\ 1363609^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0636391^2 + 121818181806000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1363609^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0636391^2 + 12181818181806000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1363609^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0636391^2 + 1218181818181806000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1363609^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0636391^2 + 121818181818181806000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1363609^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0636391^2 + 12181818181818181806000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1363609^2$$
- 604)
- $$0635184^2 + 1208000^2 := 1364816^2$$
- $$1020\ 0635184^2 + 122008000^2 := 1020\ 1364816^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0635184^2 + 12202008000^2 := 10203020\ 1364816^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0635184^2 + 1220202008000^2 := 102030403020\ 1364816^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0635184^2 + 122020202008000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1364816^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0635184^2 + 12202020202008000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1364816^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0635184^2 + 1220202020202008000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1364816^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0635184^2 + 122020202020202008000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1364816^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0635184^2 + 12202020202020202008000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1364816^2$$
- 605)
- $$0633975^2 + 1210000^2 := 1366025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0633975^2 + 122210000^2 := 1020\ 1366025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0633975^2 + 12222210000^2 := 10203020\ 1366025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0633975^2 + 1222222210000^2 := 102030403020\ 1366025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0633975^2 + 122222222210000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1366025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0633975^2 + 12222222222210000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1366025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0633975^2 + 1222222222222210000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1366025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0633975^2 + 122222222222222210000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1366025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0633975^2 + 12222222222222222210000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1366025^2$$
- 606)
- $$0632764^2 + 1212000^2 := 1367236^2$$
- $$1020\ 0632764^2 + 122412000^2 := 1020\ 1367236^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0632764^2 + 12242412000^2 := 10203020\ 1367236^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0632764^2 + 1224242412000^2 := 102030403020\ 1367236^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0632764^2 + 122424242412000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1367236^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0632764^2 + 12242424242412000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1367236^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0632764^2 + 1224242424242412000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1367236^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0632764^2 + 122424242424242412000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1367236^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0632764^2 + 12242424242424242412000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1367236^2$$

- 607)
- $$0631551^2 + 1214000^2 := 1368449^2$$
- $$1020\ 0631551^2 + 122614000^2 := 1020\ 1368449^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0631551^2 + 12262614000^2 := 10203020\ 1368449^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0631551^2 + 1226262614000^2 := 102030403020\ 1368449^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0631551^2 + 122626262614000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1368449^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0631551^2 + 12262626262614000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1368449^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0631551^2 + 1226262626262614000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1368449^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0631551^2 + 122626262626262614000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1368449^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0631551^2 + 122626262626262614000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1368449^2$$
- 608)
- $$0630336^2 + 1216000^2 := 1369664^2$$
- $$1020\ 0630336^2 + 122816000^2 := 1020\ 1369664^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0630336^2 + 12282816000^2 := 10203020\ 1369664^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0630336^2 + 1228282816000^2 := 102030403020\ 1369664^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0630336^2 + 122828282816000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1369664^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0630336^2 + 12282828282816000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1369664^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0630336^2 + 1228282828282816000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1369664^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0630336^2 + 122828282828282816000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1369664^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0630336^2 + 122828282828282816000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1369664^2$$
- 609)
- $$0629119^2 + 1218000^2 := 1370881^2$$
- $$1020\ 0629119^2 + 123018000^2 := 1020\ 1370881^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0629119^2 + 12303018000^2 := 10203020\ 1370881^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0629119^2 + 1230303018000^2 := 102030403020\ 1370881^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0629119^2 + 123030303018000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1370881^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0629119^2 + 12303030303018000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1370881^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0629119^2 + 1230303030303018000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1370881^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0629119^2 + 123030303030303018000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1370881^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0629119^2 + 123030303030303018000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1370881^2$$
- 610)
- $$0627900^2 + 1220000^2 := 1372100^2$$
- $$1020\ 0627900^2 + 123220000^2 := 1020\ 1372100^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0627900^2 + 12323220000^2 := 10203020\ 1372100^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0627900^2 + 1232323220000^2 := 102030403020\ 1372100^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0627900^2 + 123232323220000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1372100^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0627900^2 + 12323232323220000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1372100^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0627900^2 + 1232323232323220000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1372100^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0627900^2 + 123232323232323220000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1372100^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0627900^2 + 123232323232323220000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1372100^2$$

- 611)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0626679^2 + 1222000^2 && := 1373321^2 \\
 &1020\ 0626679^2 + 123422000^2 && := 1020\ 1373321^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0626679^2 + 12343422000^2 && := 10203020\ 1373321^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0626679^2 + 1234343422000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1373321^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0626679^2 + 123434343422000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1373321^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0626679^2 + 12343434343422000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1373321^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0626679^2 + 1234343434343422000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1373321^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0626679^2 + 123434343434343422000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1373321^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0626679^2 + 12343434343434343422000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1373321^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 612)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0625456^2 + 1224000^2 && := 1374544^2 \\
 &1020\ 0625456^2 + 123624000^2 && := 1020\ 1374544^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0625456^2 + 12363624000^2 && := 10203020\ 1374544^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0625456^2 + 1236363624000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1374544^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0625456^2 + 123636363624000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1374544^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0625456^2 + 12363636363624000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1374544^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0625456^2 + 1236363636363624000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1374544^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0625456^2 + 123636363636363624000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1374544^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0625456^2 + 12363636363636363624000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1374544^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 613)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0624231^2 + 1226000^2 && := 1375769^2 \\
 &1020\ 0624231^2 + 123826000^2 && := 1020\ 1375769^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0624231^2 + 12383826000^2 && := 10203020\ 1375769^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0624231^2 + 1238383826000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1375769^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0624231^2 + 123838383826000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1375769^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0624231^2 + 12383838383826000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1375769^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0624231^2 + 1238383838383826000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1375769^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0624231^2 + 123838383838383826000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1375769^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0624231^2 + 12383838383838383826000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1375769^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 614)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0623004^2 + 1228000^2 && := 1376996^2 \\
 &1020\ 0623004^2 + 124028000^2 && := 1020\ 1376996^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0623004^2 + 12404028000^2 && := 10203020\ 1376996^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0623004^2 + 1240404028000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1376996^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0623004^2 + 124040404028000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1376996^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0623004^2 + 12404040404028000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1376996^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0623004^2 + 1240404040404028000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1376996^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0623004^2 + 124040404040404028000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1376996^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0623004^2 + 12404040404040404028000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1376996^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 615)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0621775^2 + 1230000^2$ | $:= 1378225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0621775^2 + 124230000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1378225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0621775^2 + 12424230000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1378225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0621775^2 + 1242424230000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1378225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0621775^2 + 124242424230000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1378225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0621775^2 + 12424242424230000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1378225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0621775^2 + 1242424242424230000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1378225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0621775^2 + 124242424242424230000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1378225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0621775^2 + 12424242424242424230000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1378225^2$ |
- 616)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0620544^2 + 1232000^2$ | $:= 1379456^2$ |
| $1020\ 0620544^2 + 124432000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1379456^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0620544^2 + 12444432000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1379456^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0620544^2 + 1244444432000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1379456^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0620544^2 + 124444444432000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1379456^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0620544^2 + 12444444444432000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1379456^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0620544^2 + 1244444444444432000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1379456^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0620544^2 + 124444444444444432000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1379456^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0620544^2 + 12444444444444444432000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1379456^2$ |
- 617)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0619311^2 + 1234000^2$ | $:= 1380689^2$ |
| $1020\ 0619311^2 + 124634000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1380689^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0619311^2 + 12464634000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1380689^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0619311^2 + 1246464634000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1380689^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0619311^2 + 124646464634000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1380689^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0619311^2 + 12464646464634000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1380689^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0619311^2 + 1246464646464634000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1380689^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0619311^2 + 124646464646464634000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1380689^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0619311^2 + 12464646464646464634000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1380689^2$ |
- 618)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0618076^2 + 1236000^2$ | $:= 1381924^2$ |
| $1020\ 0618076^2 + 124836000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1381924^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0618076^2 + 12484836000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1381924^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0618076^2 + 1248484836000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1381924^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0618076^2 + 124848484836000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1381924^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0618076^2 + 12484848484836000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1381924^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0618076^2 + 1248484848484836000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1381924^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0618076^2 + 124848484848484836000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1381924^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0618076^2 + 12484848484848484836000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1381924^2$ |

- 619)
- $$0616839^2 + 1238000^2 := 1383161^2$$
- $$1020\ 0616839^2 + 125038000^2 := 1020\ 1383161^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0616839^2 + 12505038000^2 := 10203020\ 1383161^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0616839^2 + 1250505038000^2 := 102030403020\ 1383161^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0616839^2 + 125050505038000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1383161^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0616839^2 + 12505050505038000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1383161^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0616839^2 + 1250505050505038000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1383161^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0616839^2 + 125050505050505038000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1383161^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0616839^2 + 12505050505050505038000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1383161^2$$
- 620)
- $$0615600^2 + 1240000^2 := 1384400^2$$
- $$1020\ 0615600^2 + 125240000^2 := 1020\ 1384400^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0615600^2 + 12525240000^2 := 10203020\ 1384400^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0615600^2 + 1252525240000^2 := 102030403020\ 1384400^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0615600^2 + 125252525240000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1384400^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0615600^2 + 12525252525240000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1384400^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0615600^2 + 1252525252525240000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1384400^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0615600^2 + 125252525252525240000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1384400^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0615600^2 + 12525252525252525240000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1384400^2$$
- 621)
- $$0614359^2 + 1242000^2 := 1385641^2$$
- $$1020\ 0614359^2 + 125442000^2 := 1020\ 1385641^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0614359^2 + 12545442000^2 := 10203020\ 1385641^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0614359^2 + 1254545442000^2 := 102030403020\ 1385641^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0614359^2 + 125454545442000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1385641^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0614359^2 + 12545454545442000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1385641^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0614359^2 + 1254545454545442000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1385641^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0614359^2 + 125454545454545442000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1385641^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0614359^2 + 125454545454545442000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1385641^2$$
- 622)
- $$0613116^2 + 1244000^2 := 1386884^2$$
- $$1020\ 0613116^2 + 125644000^2 := 1020\ 1386884^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0613116^2 + 12565644000^2 := 10203020\ 1386884^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0613116^2 + 1256565644000^2 := 102030403020\ 1386884^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0613116^2 + 125656565644000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1386884^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0613116^2 + 12565656565644000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1386884^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0613116^2 + 1256565656565644000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1386884^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0613116^2 + 125656565656565644000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1386884^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0613116^2 + 125656565656565644000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1386884^2$$

- 623)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0611871^2 + 1246000^2 && := 1388129^2 \\ &1020\ 0611871^2 + 125846000^2 && := 1020\ 1388129^2 \\ &10203020\ 0611871^2 + 12585846000^2 && := 10203020\ 1388129^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0611871^2 + 1258585846000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1388129^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0611871^2 + 125858585846000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1388129^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0611871^2 + 12585858585846000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1388129^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0611871^2 + 1258585858585846000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1388129^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0611871^2 + 125858585858585846000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1388129^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0611871^2 + 12585858585858585846000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1388129^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 624)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0610624^2 + 1248000^2 && := 1389376^2 \\ &1020\ 0610624^2 + 126048000^2 && := 1020\ 1389376^2 \\ &10203020\ 0610624^2 + 12606048000^2 && := 10203020\ 1389376^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0610624^2 + 1260606048000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1389376^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0610624^2 + 126060606048000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1389376^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0610624^2 + 12606060606048000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1389376^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0610624^2 + 1260606060606048000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1389376^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0610624^2 + 126060606060606048000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1389376^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0610624^2 + 12606060606060606048000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1389376^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 625)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0609375^2 + 1250000^2 && := 1390625^2 \\ &1020\ 0609375^2 + 126250000^2 && := 1020\ 1390625^2 \\ &10203020\ 0609375^2 + 12626250000^2 && := 10203020\ 1390625^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0609375^2 + 1262626250000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1390625^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0609375^2 + 126262626250000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1390625^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0609375^2 + 12626262626250000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1390625^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0609375^2 + 1262626262626250000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1390625^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0609375^2 + 126262626262626250000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1390625^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0609375^2 + 126262626262626250000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1390625^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 626)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0608124^2 + 1252000^2 && := 1391876^2 \\ &1020\ 0608124^2 + 126452000^2 && := 1020\ 1391876^2 \\ &10203020\ 0608124^2 + 12646452000^2 && := 10203020\ 1391876^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0608124^2 + 1264646452000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1391876^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0608124^2 + 126464646452000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1391876^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0608124^2 + 12646464646452000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1391876^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0608124^2 + 1264646464646452000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1391876^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0608124^2 + 126464646464646452000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1391876^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0608124^2 + 126464646464646452000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1391876^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 627)
- $$0606871^2 + 1254000^2 := 1393129^2$$
- $$1020\ 0606871^2 + 126654000^2 := 1020\ 1393129^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0606871^2 + 12666654000^2 := 10203020\ 1393129^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0606871^2 + 1266666654000^2 := 102030403020\ 1393129^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0606871^2 + 126666666654000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1393129^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0606871^2 + 12666666666654000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1393129^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0606871^2 + 1266666666666654000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1393129^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0606871^2 + 126666666666666654000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1393129^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0606871^2 + 12666666666666666654000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1393129^2$$
- 628)
- $$0605616^2 + 1256000^2 := 1394384^2$$
- $$1020\ 0605616^2 + 126856000^2 := 1020\ 1394384^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0605616^2 + 12686856000^2 := 10203020\ 1394384^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0605616^2 + 1268686856000^2 := 102030403020\ 1394384^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0605616^2 + 126868686856000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1394384^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0605616^2 + 12686868686856000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1394384^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0605616^2 + 1268686868686856000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1394384^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0605616^2 + 126868686868686856000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1394384^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0605616^2 + 12686868686868686856000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1394384^2$$
- 629)
- $$0604359^2 + 1258000^2 := 1395641^2$$
- $$1020\ 0604359^2 + 127058000^2 := 1020\ 1395641^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0604359^2 + 12707058000^2 := 10203020\ 1395641^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0604359^2 + 1270707058000^2 := 102030403020\ 1395641^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0604359^2 + 127070707058000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1395641^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0604359^2 + 12707070707058000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1395641^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0604359^2 + 1270707070707058000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1395641^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0604359^2 + 127070707070707058000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1395641^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0604359^2 + 127070707070707058000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1395641^2$$
- 630)
- $$0603100^2 + 1260000^2 := 1396900^2$$
- $$1020\ 0603100^2 + 127260000^2 := 1020\ 1396900^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0603100^2 + 12727260000^2 := 10203020\ 1396900^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0603100^2 + 1272727260000^2 := 102030403020\ 1396900^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0603100^2 + 127272727260000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1396900^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0603100^2 + 12727272727260000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1396900^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0603100^2 + 1272727272727260000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1396900^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0603100^2 + 127272727272727260000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1396900^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0603100^2 + 127272727272727260000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1396900^2$$

- 631)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0601839^2 + 1262000^2 && := 1398161^2 \\ &1020\ 0601839^2 + 127462000^2 && := 1020\ 1398161^2 \\ &10203020\ 0601839^2 + 12747462000^2 && := 10203020\ 1398161^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0601839^2 + 1274747462000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1398161^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0601839^2 + 127474747462000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1398161^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0601839^2 + 12747474747462000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1398161^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0601839^2 + 1274747474747462000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1398161^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0601839^2 + 127474747474747462000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1398161^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0601839^2 + 12747474747474747462000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1398161^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 632)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0600576^2 + 1264000^2 && := 1399424^2 \\ &1020\ 0600576^2 + 127664000^2 && := 1020\ 1399424^2 \\ &10203020\ 0600576^2 + 12767664000^2 && := 10203020\ 1399424^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0600576^2 + 1276767664000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1399424^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0600576^2 + 127676767664000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1399424^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0600576^2 + 12767676767664000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1399424^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0600576^2 + 1276767676767664000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1399424^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0600576^2 + 127676767676767664000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1399424^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0600576^2 + 12767676767676767664000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1399424^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 633)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0599311^2 + 1266000^2 && := 1400689^2 \\ &1020\ 0599311^2 + 127866000^2 && := 1020\ 1400689^2 \\ &10203020\ 0599311^2 + 12787866000^2 && := 10203020\ 1400689^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0599311^2 + 1278787866000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1400689^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0599311^2 + 127878787866000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1400689^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0599311^2 + 12787878787866000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1400689^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0599311^2 + 1278787878787866000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1400689^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0599311^2 + 127878787878787866000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1400689^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0599311^2 + 12787878787878787866000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1400689^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 634)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0598044^2 + 1268000^2 && := 1401956^2 \\ &1020\ 0598044^2 + 128068000^2 && := 1020\ 1401956^2 \\ &10203020\ 0598044^2 + 12808068000^2 && := 10203020\ 1401956^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0598044^2 + 1280808068000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1401956^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0598044^2 + 128080808068000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1401956^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0598044^2 + 12808080808068000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1401956^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0598044^2 + 1280808080808068000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1401956^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0598044^2 + 128080808080808068000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1401956^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0598044^2 + 12808080808080808068000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1401956^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 635)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0596775^2 + 1270000^2$ | $:= 1403225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0596775^2 + 128270000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1403225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0596775^2 + 12828270000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1403225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0596775^2 + 1282828270000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1403225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0596775^2 + 128282828270000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1403225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0596775^2 + 12828282828270000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1403225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0596775^2 + 1282828282828270000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1403225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0596775^2 + 1282828282828270000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1403225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0596775^2 + 128282828282828270000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1403225^2$ |
- 636)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0595504^2 + 1272000^2$ | $:= 1404496^2$ |
| $1020\ 0595504^2 + 128472000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1404496^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0595504^2 + 12848472000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1404496^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0595504^2 + 1284848472000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1404496^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0595504^2 + 128484848472000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1404496^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0595504^2 + 12848484848472000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1404496^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0595504^2 + 1284848484848472000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1404496^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0595504^2 + 128484848484848472000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1404496^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0595504^2 + 12848484848484848472000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1404496^2$ |
- 637)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0594231^2 + 1274000^2$ | $:= 1405769^2$ |
| $1020\ 0594231^2 + 128674000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1405769^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0594231^2 + 12868674000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1405769^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0594231^2 + 1286868674000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1405769^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0594231^2 + 128686868674000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1405769^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0594231^2 + 12868686868674000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1405769^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0594231^2 + 1286868686868674000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1405769^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0594231^2 + 128686868686868674000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1405769^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0594231^2 + 12868686868686868674000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1405769^2$ |
- 638)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0592956^2 + 1276000^2$ | $:= 1407044^2$ |
| $1020\ 0592956^2 + 128876000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1407044^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0592956^2 + 12888876000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1407044^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0592956^2 + 1288888876000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1407044^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0592956^2 + 128888888876000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1407044^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0592956^2 + 12888888888876000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1407044^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0592956^2 + 1288888888888876000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1407044^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0592956^2 + 128888888888888876000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1407044^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0592956^2 + 12888888888888888876000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1407044^2$ |

- 639)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0591679^2 + 1278000^2$ | $:= 1408321^2$ |
| $1020\ 0591679^2 + 129078000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1408321^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0591679^2 + 12909078000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1408321^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0591679^2 + 1290909078000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1408321^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0591679^2 + 129090909078000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1408321^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0591679^2 + 12909090909078000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1408321^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0591679^2 + 1290909090909078000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1408321^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0591679^2 + 129090909090909078000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1408321^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0591679^2 + 12909090909090909078000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1408321^2$ |
- 640)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0590400^2 + 1280000^2$ | $:= 1409600^2$ |
| $1020\ 0590400^2 + 129280000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1409600^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0590400^2 + 12929280000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1409600^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0590400^2 + 1292929280000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1409600^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0590400^2 + 129292929280000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1409600^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0590400^2 + 12929292929280000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1409600^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0590400^2 + 1292929292929280000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1409600^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0590400^2 + 129292929292929280000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1409600^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0590400^2 + 12929292929292929280000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1409600^2$ |
- 641)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0589119^2 + 1282000^2$ | $:= 1410881^2$ |
| $1020\ 0589119^2 + 129482000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1410881^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0589119^2 + 12949482000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1410881^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0589119^2 + 1294949482000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1410881^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0589119^2 + 129494949482000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1410881^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0589119^2 + 12949494949482000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1410881^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0589119^2 + 1294949494949482000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1410881^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0589119^2 + 129494949494949482000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1410881^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0589119^2 + 12949494949494949482000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1410881^2$ |
- 642)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0587836^2 + 1284000^2$ | $:= 1412164^2$ |
| $1020\ 0587836^2 + 129684000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1412164^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0587836^2 + 12969684000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1412164^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0587836^2 + 1296969684000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1412164^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0587836^2 + 129696969684000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1412164^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0587836^2 + 12969696969684000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1412164^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0587836^2 + 1296969696969684000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1412164^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0587836^2 + 129696969696969684000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1412164^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0587836^2 + 12969696969696969684000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1412164^2$ |

- 643)
- $$0586551^2 + 1286000^2 := 1413449^2$$
- $$1020\ 0586551^2 + 129886000^2 := 1020\ 1413449^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0586551^2 + 12989886000^2 := 10203020\ 1413449^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0586551^2 + 1298989886000^2 := 102030403020\ 1413449^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0586551^2 + 129898989886000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1413449^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0586551^2 + 12989898989886000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1413449^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0586551^2 + 1298989898989886000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1413449^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0586551^2 + 1298989898989886000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1413449^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0586551^2 + 1298989898989886000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1413449^2$$
- 644)
- $$0585264^2 + 1288000^2 := 1414736^2$$
- $$1020\ 0585264^2 + 130088000^2 := 1020\ 1414736^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0585264^2 + 13010088000^2 := 10203020\ 1414736^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0585264^2 + 1301010088000^2 := 102030403020\ 1414736^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0585264^2 + 130101010088000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1414736^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0585264^2 + 13010101010088000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1414736^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0585264^2 + 1301010101010088000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1414736^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0585264^2 + 130101010101010088000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1414736^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0585264^2 + 130101010101010088000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1414736^2$$
- 645)
- $$0583975^2 + 1290000^2 := 1416025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0583975^2 + 130290000^2 := 1020\ 1416025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0583975^2 + 13030290000^2 := 10203020\ 1416025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0583975^2 + 1303030290000^2 := 102030403020\ 1416025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0583975^2 + 130303030290000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1416025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0583975^2 + 13030303030290000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1416025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0583975^2 + 1303030303030290000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1416025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0583975^2 + 130303030303030290000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1416025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0583975^2 + 130303030303030290000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1416025^2$$
- 646)
- $$0582684^2 + 1292000^2 := 1417316^2$$
- $$1020\ 0582684^2 + 130492000^2 := 1020\ 1417316^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0582684^2 + 13050492000^2 := 10203020\ 1417316^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0582684^2 + 1305050492000^2 := 102030403020\ 1417316^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0582684^2 + 130505050492000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1417316^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0582684^2 + 13050505050492000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1417316^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0582684^2 + 1305050505050492000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1417316^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0582684^2 + 130505050505050492000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1417316^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0582684^2 + 130505050505050492000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1417316^2$$

- 647)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0581391^2 + 1294000^2 && := 1418609^2 \\ &1020\ 0581391^2 + 130694000^2 && := 1020\ 1418609^2 \\ &10203020\ 0581391^2 + 13070694000^2 && := 10203020\ 1418609^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0581391^2 + 1307070694000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1418609^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0581391^2 + 130707070694000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1418609^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0581391^2 + 13070707070694000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1418609^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0581391^2 + 1307070707070694000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1418609^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0581391^2 + 130707070707070694000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1418609^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0581391^2 + 13070707070707070694000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1418609^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 648)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0580096^2 + 1296000^2 && := 1419904^2 \\ &1020\ 0580096^2 + 130896000^2 && := 1020\ 1419904^2 \\ &10203020\ 0580096^2 + 13090896000^2 && := 10203020\ 1419904^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0580096^2 + 1309090896000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1419904^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0580096^2 + 130909090896000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1419904^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0580096^2 + 13090909090896000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1419904^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0580096^2 + 1309090909090896000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1419904^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0580096^2 + 130909090909090896000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1419904^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0580096^2 + 13090909090909090896000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1419904^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 649)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0578799^2 + 1298000^2 && := 1421201^2 \\ &1020\ 0578799^2 + 131098000^2 && := 1020\ 1421201^2 \\ &10203020\ 0578799^2 + 13111098000^2 && := 10203020\ 1421201^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0578799^2 + 1311111098000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1421201^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0578799^2 + 131111111098000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1421201^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0578799^2 + 13111111111098000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1421201^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0578799^2 + 1311111111111098000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1421201^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0578799^2 + 131111111111111098000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1421201^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0578799^2 + 13111111111111111098000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1421201^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 650)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0577500^2 + 1300000^2 && := 1422500^2 \\ &1020\ 0577500^2 + 131300000^2 && := 1020\ 1422500^2 \\ &10203020\ 0577500^2 + 13131300000^2 && := 10203020\ 1422500^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0577500^2 + 1313131300000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1422500^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0577500^2 + 131313131300000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1422500^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0577500^2 + 13131313131300000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1422500^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0577500^2 + 1313131313131300000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1422500^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0577500^2 + 131313131313131300000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1422500^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0577500^2 + 13131313131313131300000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1422500^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 651)
- $$0576199^2 + 1302000^2 := 1423801^2$$
- $$1020\ 0576199^2 + 131502000^2 := 1020\ 1423801^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0576199^2 + 13151502000^2 := 10203020\ 1423801^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0576199^2 + 1315151502000^2 := 102030403020\ 1423801^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0576199^2 + 131515151502000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1423801^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0576199^2 + 13151515151502000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1423801^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0576199^2 + 1315151515151502000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1423801^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0576199^2 + 131515151515151502000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1423801^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0576199^2 + 13151515151515151502000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1423801^2$$
- 652)
- $$0574896^2 + 1304000^2 := 1425104^2$$
- $$1020\ 0574896^2 + 131704000^2 := 1020\ 1425104^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0574896^2 + 13171704000^2 := 10203020\ 1425104^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0574896^2 + 1317171704000^2 := 102030403020\ 1425104^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0574896^2 + 131717171704000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1425104^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0574896^2 + 13171717171704000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1425104^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0574896^2 + 1317171717171704000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1425104^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0574896^2 + 131717171717171704000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1425104^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0574896^2 + 13171717171717171704000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1425104^2$$
- 653)
- $$0573591^2 + 1306000^2 := 1426409^2$$
- $$1020\ 0573591^2 + 131906000^2 := 1020\ 1426409^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0573591^2 + 13191906000^2 := 10203020\ 1426409^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0573591^2 + 1319191906000^2 := 102030403020\ 1426409^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0573591^2 + 131919191906000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1426409^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0573591^2 + 13191919191906000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1426409^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0573591^2 + 1319191919191906000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1426409^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0573591^2 + 131919191919191906000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1426409^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0573591^2 + 13191919191919191906000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1426409^2$$
- 654)
- $$0572284^2 + 1308000^2 := 1427716^2$$
- $$1020\ 0572284^2 + 132108000^2 := 1020\ 1427716^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0572284^2 + 13212108000^2 := 10203020\ 1427716^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0572284^2 + 1321212108000^2 := 102030403020\ 1427716^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0572284^2 + 132121212108000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1427716^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0572284^2 + 13212121212108000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1427716^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0572284^2 + 1321212121212108000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1427716^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0572284^2 + 132121212121212108000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1427716^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0572284^2 + 13212121212121212108000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1427716^2$$

- 655)
- $$0570975^2 + 1310000^2 := 1429025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0570975^2 + 132310000^2 := 1020\ 1429025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0570975^2 + 13232310000^2 := 10203020\ 1429025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0570975^2 + 1323232310000^2 := 102030403020\ 1429025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0570975^2 + 132323232310000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1429025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0570975^2 + 13232323232310000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1429025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0570975^2 + 1323232323232310000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1429025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0570975^2 + 132323232323232310000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1429025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0570975^2 + 13232323232323232310000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1429025^2$$
- 656)
- $$0569664^2 + 1312000^2 := 1430336^2$$
- $$1020\ 0569664^2 + 132512000^2 := 1020\ 1430336^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0569664^2 + 13252512000^2 := 10203020\ 1430336^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0569664^2 + 1325252512000^2 := 102030403020\ 1430336^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0569664^2 + 132525252512000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1430336^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0569664^2 + 13252525252512000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1430336^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0569664^2 + 1325252525252512000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1430336^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0569664^2 + 132525252525252512000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1430336^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0569664^2 + 13252525252525252512000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1430336^2$$
- 657)
- $$0568351^2 + 1314000^2 := 1431649^2$$
- $$1020\ 0568351^2 + 132714000^2 := 1020\ 1431649^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0568351^2 + 13272714000^2 := 10203020\ 1431649^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0568351^2 + 1327272714000^2 := 102030403020\ 1431649^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0568351^2 + 132727272714000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1431649^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0568351^2 + 13272727272714000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1431649^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0568351^2 + 1327272727272714000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1431649^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0568351^2 + 132727272727272714000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1431649^2$$
- 658)
- $$0567036^2 + 1316000^2 := 1432964^2$$
- $$1020\ 0567036^2 + 132916000^2 := 1020\ 1432964^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0567036^2 + 13292916000^2 := 10203020\ 1432964^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0567036^2 + 1329292916000^2 := 102030403020\ 1432964^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0567036^2 + 132929292916000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1432964^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0567036^2 + 13292929292916000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1432964^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0567036^2 + 1329292929292916000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1432964^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0567036^2 + 132929292929292916000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1432964^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0567036^2 + 13292929292929292916000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1432964^2$$

- 659)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0565719^2 + 1318000^2$ | $:= 1434281^2$ |
| $1020\ 0565719^2 + 133118000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1434281^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0565719^2 + 13313118000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1434281^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0565719^2 + 1331313118000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1434281^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0565719^2 + 133131313118000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1434281^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0565719^2 + 13313131313118000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1434281^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0565719^2 + 1331313131313118000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1434281^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0565719^2 + 133131313131313118000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1434281^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0565719^2 + 13313131313131313118000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1434281^2$ |
- 660)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0564400^2 + 1320000^2$ | $:= 1435600^2$ |
| $1020\ 0564400^2 + 133320000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1435600^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0564400^2 + 13333320000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1435600^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0564400^2 + 1333333320000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1435600^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0564400^2 + 133333333320000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1435600^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0564400^2 + 13333333333320000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1435600^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0564400^2 + 1333333333333320000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1435600^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0564400^2 + 133333333333333320000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1435600^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0564400^2 + 13333333333333333320000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1435600^2$ |
- 661)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0563079^2 + 1322000^2$ | $:= 1436921^2$ |
| $1020\ 0563079^2 + 133522000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1436921^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0563079^2 + 13353522000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1436921^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0563079^2 + 1335353522000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1436921^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0563079^2 + 133535353522000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1436921^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0563079^2 + 13353535353522000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1436921^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0563079^2 + 1335353535353522000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1436921^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0563079^2 + 133535353535353522000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1436921^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0563079^2 + 13353535353535353522000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1436921^2$ |
- 662)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0561756^2 + 1324000^2$ | $:= 1438244^2$ |
| $1020\ 0561756^2 + 133724000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1438244^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0561756^2 + 13373724000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1438244^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0561756^2 + 1337373724000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1438244^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0561756^2 + 133737373724000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1438244^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0561756^2 + 13373737373724000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1438244^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0561756^2 + 1337373737373724000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1438244^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0561756^2 + 133737373737373724000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1438244^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0561756^2 + 13373737373737373724000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1438244^2$ |

- 663)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0560431^2 + 1326000^2$ | $:= 1439569^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0560431^2 + 133926000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1439569^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0560431^2 + 13393926000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1439569^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0560431^2 + 1339393926000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1439569^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0560431^2 + 133939393926000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1439569^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0560431^2 + 13393939393926000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1439569^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0560431^2 + 1339393939393926000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1439569^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0560431^2 + 133939393939393926000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1439569^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0560431^2 + 13393939393939393926000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1439569^2$ |
- 664)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0559104^2 + 1328000^2$ | $:= 1440896^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0559104^2 + 134128000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1440896^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0559104^2 + 13414128000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1440896^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0559104^2 + 1341414128000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1440896^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0559104^2 + 134141414128000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1440896^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0559104^2 + 13414141414128000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1440896^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0559104^2 + 1341414141414128000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1440896^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0559104^2 + 134141414141414128000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1440896^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0559104^2 + 13414141414141414128000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1440896^2$ |
- 665)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0557775^2 + 1330000^2$ | $:= 1442225^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0557775^2 + 134330000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1442225^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0557775^2 + 13434330000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1442225^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0557775^2 + 1343434330000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1442225^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0557775^2 + 134343434330000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1442225^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0557775^2 + 13434343434330000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1442225^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0557775^2 + 1343434343434330000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1442225^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0557775^2 + 134343434343434330000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1442225^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0557775^2 + 13434343434343434330000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1442225^2$ |
- 666)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0556444^2 + 1332000^2$ | $:= 1443556^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0556444^2 + 134532000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1443556^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0556444^2 + 13454532000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1443556^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0556444^2 + 1345454532000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1443556^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0556444^2 + 134545454532000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1443556^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0556444^2 + 13454545454532000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1443556^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0556444^2 + 1345454545454532000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1443556^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0556444^2 + 134545454545454532000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1443556^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0556444^2 + 13454545454545454532000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1443556^2$ |

- 667)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0555111^2 + 1334000^2$ | $:= 1444889^2$ |
| $1020\ 0555111^2 + 134734000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1444889^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0555111^2 + 13474734000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1444889^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0555111^2 + 1347474734000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1444889^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0555111^2 + 134747474734000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1444889^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0555111^2 + 13474747474734000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1444889^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0555111^2 + 1347474747474734000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1444889^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0555111^2 + 134747474747474734000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1444889^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0555111^2 + 13474747474747474734000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1444889^2$ |
- 668)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0553776^2 + 1336000^2$ | $:= 1446224^2$ |
| $1020\ 0553776^2 + 134936000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1446224^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0553776^2 + 13494936000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1446224^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0553776^2 + 1349494936000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1446224^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0553776^2 + 134949494936000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1446224^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0553776^2 + 13494949494936000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1446224^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0553776^2 + 1349494949494936000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1446224^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0553776^2 + 134949494949494936000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1446224^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0553776^2 + 13494949494949494936000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1446224^2$ |
- 669)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0552439^2 + 1338000^2$ | $:= 1447561^2$ |
| $1020\ 0552439^2 + 135138000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1447561^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0552439^2 + 13515138000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1447561^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0552439^2 + 1351515138000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1447561^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0552439^2 + 135151515138000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1447561^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0552439^2 + 13515151515138000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1447561^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0552439^2 + 1351515151515138000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1447561^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0552439^2 + 135151515151515138000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1447561^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0552439^2 + 13515151515151515138000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1447561^2$ |
- 670)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0551100^2 + 1340000^2$ | $:= 1448900^2$ |
| $1020\ 0551100^2 + 135340000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1448900^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0551100^2 + 13535340000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1448900^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0551100^2 + 1353535340000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1448900^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0551100^2 + 135353535340000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1448900^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0551100^2 + 13535353535340000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1448900^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0551100^2 + 1353535353535340000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1448900^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0551100^2 + 135353535353535340000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1448900^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0551100^2 + 13535353535353535340000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1448900^2$ |

- 671)
- $$0549759^2 + 1342000^2 := 1450241^2$$
- $$1020\ 0549759^2 + 135542000^2 := 1020\ 1450241^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0549759^2 + 13555542000^2 := 10203020\ 1450241^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0549759^2 + 1355555542000^2 := 102030403020\ 1450241^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0549759^2 + 135555555542000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1450241^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0549759^2 + 13555555555542000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1450241^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0549759^2 + 1355555555555542000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1450241^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0549759^2 + 135555555555555542000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1450241^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0549759^2 + 13555555555555555542000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1450241^2$$
- 672)
- $$0548416^2 + 1344000^2 := 1451584^2$$
- $$1020\ 0548416^2 + 135744000^2 := 1020\ 1451584^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0548416^2 + 13575744000^2 := 10203020\ 1451584^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0548416^2 + 1357575744000^2 := 102030403020\ 1451584^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0548416^2 + 135757575744000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1451584^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0548416^2 + 13575757575744000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1451584^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0548416^2 + 1357575757575744000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1451584^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0548416^2 + 135757575757575744000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1451584^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0548416^2 + 13575757575757575744000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1451584^2$$
- 673)
- $$0547071^2 + 1346000^2 := 1452929^2$$
- $$1020\ 0547071^2 + 135946000^2 := 1020\ 1452929^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0547071^2 + 13595946000^2 := 10203020\ 1452929^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0547071^2 + 1359595946000^2 := 102030403020\ 1452929^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0547071^2 + 135959595946000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1452929^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0547071^2 + 13595959595946000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1452929^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0547071^2 + 1359595959595946000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1452929^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0547071^2 + 135959595959595946000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1452929^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0547071^2 + 13595959595959595946000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1452929^2$$
- 674)
- $$0545724^2 + 1348000^2 := 1454276^2$$
- $$1020\ 0545724^2 + 136148000^2 := 1020\ 1454276^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0545724^2 + 13616148000^2 := 10203020\ 1454276^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0545724^2 + 1361616148000^2 := 102030403020\ 1454276^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0545724^2 + 136161616148000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1454276^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0545724^2 + 13616161616148000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1454276^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0545724^2 + 1361616161616148000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1454276^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0545724^2 + 136161616161616148000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1454276^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0545724^2 + 13616161616161616148000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1454276^2$$

- 675)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0544375^2 + 1350000^2$ | $:= 1455625^2$ |
| $1020\ 0544375^2 + 136350000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1455625^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0544375^2 + 13636350000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1455625^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0544375^2 + 1363636350000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1455625^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0544375^2 + 136363636350000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1455625^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0544375^2 + 13636363636350000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1455625^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0544375^2 + 1363636363636350000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1455625^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0544375^2 + 136363636363636350000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1455625^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0544375^2 + 13636363636363636350000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1455625^2$ |
- 676)
- | | |
|--|--|
| $0543024^2 + 1352000^2$ | $:= 1456976^2$ |
| $1020\ 0543024^2 + 136552000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1456976^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0543024^2 + 13656552000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1456976^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0543024^2 + 1365656552000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1456976^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0543024^2 + 13656565652000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1456976^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0543024^2 + 1365656565652000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1456976^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0543024^2 + 136565656565652000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1456976^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0543024^2 + 13656565656565652000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1456976^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0543024^2 + 1365656565656565652000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1456976^2$ |
- 677)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0541671^2 + 1354000^2$ | $:= 1458329^2$ |
| $1020\ 0541671^2 + 136754000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1458329^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0541671^2 + 13676754000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1458329^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0541671^2 + 1367676754000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1458329^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0541671^2 + 136767676754000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1458329^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0541671^2 + 13676767676754000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1458329^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0541671^2 + 1367676767676754000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1458329^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0541671^2 + 136767676767676754000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1458329^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0541671^2 + 13676767676767676754000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1458329^2$ |
- 678)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0540316^2 + 1356000^2$ | $:= 1459684^2$ |
| $1020\ 0540316^2 + 136956000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1459684^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0540316^2 + 13696956000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1459684^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0540316^2 + 1369696956000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1459684^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0540316^2 + 136969696956000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1459684^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0540316^2 + 13696969696956000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1459684^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0540316^2 + 1369696969696956000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1459684^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0540316^2 + 136969696969696956000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1459684^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0540316^2 + 13696969696969696956000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1459684^2$ |

- 679)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0538959^2 + 1358000^2 && := 1461041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0538959^2 + 137158000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1461041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0538959^2 + 13717158000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1461041^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0538959^2 + 1371717158000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1461041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0538959^2 + 137171717158000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1461041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0538959^2 + 13717171717158000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1461041^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0538959^2 + 1371717171717158000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1461041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0538959^2 + 137171717171717158000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1461041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0538959^2 + 13717171717171717158000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1461041^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 680)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0537600^2 + 1360000^2 && := 1462400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0537600^2 + 137360000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1462400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0537600^2 + 13737360000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1462400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0537600^2 + 1373737360000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1462400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0537600^2 + 137373737360000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1462400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0537600^2 + 13737373737360000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1462400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0537600^2 + 1373737373737360000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1462400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0537600^2 + 137373737373737360000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1462400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0537600^2 + 13737373737373737360000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1462400^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 681)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0536239^2 + 1362000^2 && := 1463761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0536239^2 + 137562000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1463761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0536239^2 + 13757562000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1463761^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0536239^2 + 1375757562000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1463761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0536239^2 + 137575757562000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1463761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0536239^2 + 13757575757562000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1463761^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0536239^2 + 1375757575757562000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1463761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0536239^2 + 137575757575757562000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1463761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0536239^2 + 13757575757575757562000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1463761^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 682)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0534876^2 + 1364000^2 && := 1465124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0534876^2 + 137764000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1465124^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0534876^2 + 13777764000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1465124^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0534876^2 + 1377777764000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1465124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0534876^2 + 137777777764000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1465124^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0534876^2 + 13777777777764000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1465124^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0534876^2 + 1377777777777764000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1465124^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0534876^2 + 137777777777777764000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1465124^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0534876^2 + 13777777777777777764000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1465124^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 683)
- $$0533511^2 + 1366000^2 := 1466489^2$$
- $$1020\ 0533511^2 + 137966000^2 := 1020\ 1466489^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0533511^2 + 13797966000^2 := 10203020\ 1466489^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0533511^2 + 1379797966000^2 := 102030403020\ 1466489^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0533511^2 + 137979797966000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1466489^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0533511^2 + 13797979797966000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1466489^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0533511^2 + 1379797979797966000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1466489^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0533511^2 + 137979797979797966000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1466489^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0533511^2 + 13797979797979797966000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1466489^2$$
- 684)
- $$0532144^2 + 1368000^2 := 1467856^2$$
- $$1020\ 0532144^2 + 138168000^2 := 1020\ 1467856^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0532144^2 + 13818168000^2 := 10203020\ 1467856^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0532144^2 + 1381818168000^2 := 102030403020\ 1467856^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0532144^2 + 138181818168000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1467856^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0532144^2 + 13818181818168000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1467856^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0532144^2 + 1381818181818168000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1467856^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0532144^2 + 138181818181818168000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1467856^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0532144^2 + 13818181818181818168000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1467856^2$$
- 685)
- $$0530775^2 + 1370000^2 := 1469225^2$$
- $$1020\ 0530775^2 + 138370000^2 := 1020\ 1469225^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0530775^2 + 13838370000^2 := 10203020\ 1469225^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0530775^2 + 1383838370000^2 := 102030403020\ 1469225^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0530775^2 + 138383838370000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1469225^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0530775^2 + 13838383838370000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1469225^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0530775^2 + 1383838383838370000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1469225^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0530775^2 + 138383838383838370000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1469225^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0530775^2 + 13838383838383838370000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1469225^2$$
- 686)
- $$0529404^2 + 1372000^2 := 1470596^2$$
- $$1020\ 0529404^2 + 138572000^2 := 1020\ 1470596^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0529404^2 + 13858572000^2 := 10203020\ 1470596^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0529404^2 + 1385858572000^2 := 102030403020\ 1470596^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0529404^2 + 138585858572000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1470596^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0529404^2 + 13858585858572000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1470596^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0529404^2 + 1385858585858572000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1470596^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0529404^2 + 138585858585858572000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1470596^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0529404^2 + 13858585858585858572000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1470596^2$$

- 687)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0528031^2 + 1374000^2$ | $:= 1471969^2$ |
| $1020\ 0528031^2 + 138774000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1471969^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0528031^2 + 13878774000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1471969^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0528031^2 + 1387878774000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1471969^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0528031^2 + 138787878774000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1471969^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0528031^2 + 13878787878774000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1471969^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0528031^2 + 1387878787878774000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1471969^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0528031^2 + 138787878787878774000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1471969^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0528031^2 + 13878787878787878774000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1471969^2$ |
- 688)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0526656^2 + 1376000^2$ | $:= 1473344^2$ |
| $1020\ 0526656^2 + 138976000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1473344^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0526656^2 + 13898976000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1473344^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0526656^2 + 1389898976000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1473344^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0526656^2 + 138989898976000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1473344^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0526656^2 + 13898989898976000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1473344^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0526656^2 + 1389898989898976000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1473344^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0526656^2 + 138989898989898976000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1473344^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0526656^2 + 13898989898989898976000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1473344^2$ |
- 689)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0525279^2 + 1378000^2$ | $:= 1474721^2$ |
| $1020\ 0525279^2 + 139178000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1474721^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0525279^2 + 13919178000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1474721^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0525279^2 + 1391919178000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1474721^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0525279^2 + 139191919178000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1474721^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0525279^2 + 13919191919178000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1474721^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0525279^2 + 1391919191919178000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1474721^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0525279^2 + 139191919191919178000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1474721^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0525279^2 + 13919191919191919178000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1474721^2$ |
- 690)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0523900^2 + 1380000^2$ | $:= 1476100^2$ |
| $1020\ 0523900^2 + 139380000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1476100^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0523900^2 + 13939380000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1476100^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0523900^2 + 1393939380000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1476100^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0523900^2 + 139393939380000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1476100^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0523900^2 + 13939393939380000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1476100^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0523900^2 + 1393939393939380000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1476100^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0523900^2 + 139393939393939380000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1476100^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0523900^2 + 13939393939393939380000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1476100^2$ |

- 691)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0522519^2 + 1382000^2 && := 1477481^2 \\
 &1020\ 0522519^2 + 139582000^2 && := 1020\ 1477481^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0522519^2 + 13959582000^2 && := 10203020\ 1477481^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0522519^2 + 1395959582000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1477481^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0522519^2 + 139595959582000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1477481^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0522519^2 + 13959595959582000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1477481^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0522519^2 + 1395959595959582000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1477481^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0522519^2 + 139595959595959582000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1477481^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0522519^2 + 13959595959595959582000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1477481^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 692)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0521136^2 + 1384000^2 && := 1478864^2 \\
 &1020\ 0521136^2 + 139784000^2 && := 1020\ 1478864^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0521136^2 + 13979784000^2 && := 10203020\ 1478864^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0521136^2 + 1397979784000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1478864^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0521136^2 + 139797979784000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1478864^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0521136^2 + 13979797979784000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1478864^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0521136^2 + 1397979797979784000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1478864^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0521136^2 + 139797979797979784000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1478864^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0521136^2 + 13979797979797979784000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1478864^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 693)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0519751^2 + 1386000^2 && := 1480249^2 \\
 &1020\ 0519751^2 + 139986000^2 && := 1020\ 1480249^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0519751^2 + 13999986000^2 && := 10203020\ 1480249^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0519751^2 + 1399999986000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1480249^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0519751^2 + 139999999986000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1480249^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0519751^2 + 13999999999986000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1480249^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0519751^2 + 1399999999999986000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1480249^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0519751^2 + 139999999999999986000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1480249^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0519751^2 + 13999999999999999986000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1480249^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 694)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0518364^2 + 1388000^2 && := 1481636^2 \\
 &1020\ 0518364^2 + 140188000^2 && := 1020\ 1481636^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0518364^2 + 14020188000^2 && := 10203020\ 1481636^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0518364^2 + 1402020188000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1481636^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0518364^2 + 140202020188000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1481636^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0518364^2 + 14020202020188000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1481636^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0518364^2 + 1402020202020188000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1481636^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0518364^2 + 140202020202020188000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1481636^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0518364^2 + 14020202020202020188000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1481636^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 695)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0516975^2 + 1390000^2$ | $:= 1483025^2$ |
| $1020 0516975^2 + 140390000^2$ | $:= 1020 1483025^2$ |
| $10203020 0516975^2 + 14040390000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1483025^2$ |
| $102030403020 0516975^2 + 1404040390000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1483025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0516975^2 + 140404040390000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1483025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0516975^2 + 14040404040390000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1483025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0516975^2 + 1404040404040390000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1483025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0516975^2 + 140404040404040390000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1483025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0516975^2 + 14040404040404040390000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1483025^2$ |
- 696)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0515584^2 + 1392000^2$ | $:= 1484416^2$ |
| $1020 0515584^2 + 140592000^2$ | $:= 1020 1484416^2$ |
| $10203020 0515584^2 + 14060592000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1484416^2$ |
| $102030403020 0515584^2 + 1406060592000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1484416^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0515584^2 + 140606060592000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1484416^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0515584^2 + 14060606060592000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1484416^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0515584^2 + 1406060606060592000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1484416^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0515584^2 + 140606060606060592000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1484416^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0515584^2 + 14060606060606060592000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1484416^2$ |
- 697)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0514191^2 + 1394000^2$ | $:= 1485809^2$ |
| $1020 0514191^2 + 140794000^2$ | $:= 1020 1485809^2$ |
| $10203020 0514191^2 + 14080794000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1485809^2$ |
| $102030403020 0514191^2 + 1408080794000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1485809^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0514191^2 + 140808080794000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1485809^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0514191^2 + 14080808080794000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1485809^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0514191^2 + 1408080808080794000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1485809^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0514191^2 + 140808080808080794000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1485809^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0514191^2 + 14080808080808080794000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1485809^2$ |
- 698)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0512796^2 + 1396000^2$ | $:= 1487204^2$ |
| $1020 0512796^2 + 140996000^2$ | $:= 1020 1487204^2$ |
| $10203020 0512796^2 + 14100996000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1487204^2$ |
| $102030403020 0512796^2 + 1410100996000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1487204^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0512796^2 + 141010100996000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1487204^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0512796^2 + 14101010100996000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1487204^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0512796^2 + 1410101010100996000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1487204^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0512796^2 + 141010101010100996000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1487204^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0512796^2 + 14101010101010100996000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1487204^2$ |

- 699)
- $$0511399^2 + 1398000^2 := 1488601^2$$
- $$1020 0511399^2 + 141198000^2 := 1020 1488601^2$$
- $$10203020 0511399^2 + 14121198000^2 := 10203020 1488601^2$$
- $$102030403020 0511399^2 + 1412121198000^2 := 102030403020 1488601^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0511399^2 + 141212121198000^2 := 1020304050403020 1488601^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0511399^2 + 14121212121198000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1488601^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0511399^2 + 1412121212121198000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1488601^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0511399^2 + 141212121212121198000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1488601^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0511399^2 + 14121212121212121198000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1488601^2$$
- 700)
- $$0510000^2 + 1400000^2 := 1490000^2$$
- $$1020 0510000^2 + 141400000^2 := 1020 1490000^2$$
- $$10203020 0510000^2 + 14141400000^2 := 10203020 1490000^2$$
- $$102030403020 0510000^2 + 1414141400000^2 := 102030403020 1490000^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0510000^2 + 141414141400000^2 := 1020304050403020 1490000^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0510000^2 + 14141414141400000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1490000^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0510000^2 + 1414141414141400000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1490000^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0510000^2 + 141414141414141400000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1490000^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0510000^2 + 14141414141414141400000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1490000^2$$
- 701)
- $$0508599^2 + 1402000^2 := 1491401^2$$
- $$1020 0508599^2 + 141602000^2 := 1020 1491401^2$$
- $$10203020 0508599^2 + 14161602000^2 := 10203020 1491401^2$$
- $$102030403020 0508599^2 + 1416161602000^2 := 102030403020 1491401^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0508599^2 + 141616161602000^2 := 1020304050403020 1491401^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0508599^2 + 14161616161602000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1491401^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0508599^2 + 1416161616161602000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1491401^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0508599^2 + 141616161616161602000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1491401^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0508599^2 + 14161616161616161602000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1491401^2$$
- 702)
- $$0507196^2 + 1404000^2 := 1492804^2$$
- $$1020 0507196^2 + 141804000^2 := 1020 1492804^2$$
- $$10203020 0507196^2 + 14181804000^2 := 10203020 1492804^2$$
- $$102030403020 0507196^2 + 1418181804000^2 := 102030403020 1492804^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0507196^2 + 141818181804000^2 := 1020304050403020 1492804^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0507196^2 + 14181818181804000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1492804^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0507196^2 + 1418181818181804000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1492804^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0507196^2 + 141818181818181804000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1492804^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0507196^2 + 14181818181818181804000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1492804^2$$

- 703)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0505791^2 + 1406000^2 && := 1494209^2 \\ &1020\ 0505791^2 + 142006000^2 && := 1020\ 1494209^2 \\ &10203020\ 0505791^2 + 14202006000^2 && := 10203020\ 1494209^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0505791^2 + 1420202006000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1494209^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0505791^2 + 142020202006000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1494209^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0505791^2 + 14202020202006000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1494209^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0505791^2 + 1420202020202006000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1494209^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0505791^2 + 142020202020202006000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1494209^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0505791^2 + 14202020202020202006000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1494209^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 704)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0504384^2 + 1408000^2 && := 1495616^2 \\ &1020\ 0504384^2 + 142208000^2 && := 1020\ 1495616^2 \\ &10203020\ 0504384^2 + 14222208000^2 && := 10203020\ 1495616^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0504384^2 + 1422222208000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1495616^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0504384^2 + 142222222208000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1495616^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0504384^2 + 14222222222208000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1495616^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0504384^2 + 1422222222222208000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1495616^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0504384^2 + 142222222222222208000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1495616^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0504384^2 + 14222222222222222208000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1495616^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 705)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0502975^2 + 1410000^2 && := 1497025^2 \\ &1020\ 0502975^2 + 142410000^2 && := 1020\ 1497025^2 \\ &10203020\ 0502975^2 + 14242410000^2 && := 10203020\ 1497025^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0502975^2 + 1424242410000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1497025^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0502975^2 + 142424242410000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1497025^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0502975^2 + 14242424242410000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1497025^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0502975^2 + 1424242424242410000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1497025^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0502975^2 + 142424242424242410000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1497025^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 706)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0501564^2 + 1412000^2 && := 1498436^2 \\ &1020\ 0501564^2 + 142612000^2 && := 1020\ 1498436^2 \\ &10203020\ 0501564^2 + 14262612000^2 && := 10203020\ 1498436^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0501564^2 + 1426262612000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1498436^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0501564^2 + 142626262612000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1498436^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0501564^2 + 14262626262612000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1498436^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0501564^2 + 1426262626262612000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1498436^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0501564^2 + 142626262626262612000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1498436^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0501564^2 + 142626262626262612000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1498436^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 707)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0500151^2 + 1414000^2$ | $:= 1499849^2$ |
| $1020\ 0500151^2 + 142814000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1499849^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0500151^2 + 14282814000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1499849^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0500151^2 + 1428282814000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1499849^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0500151^2 + 142828282814000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1499849^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0500151^2 + 14282828282814000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1499849^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0500151^2 + 1428282828282814000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1499849^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0500151^2 + 142828282828282814000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1499849^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0500151^2 + 14282828282828282814000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1499849^2$ |
- 708)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0498736^2 + 1416000^2$ | $:= 1501264^2$ |
| $1020\ 0498736^2 + 143016000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1501264^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0498736^2 + 14303016000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1501264^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0498736^2 + 1430303016000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1501264^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0498736^2 + 143030303016000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1501264^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0498736^2 + 14303030303016000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1501264^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0498736^2 + 1430303030303016000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1501264^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0498736^2 + 143030303030303016000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1501264^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0498736^2 + 14303030303030303016000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1501264^2$ |
- 709)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0497319^2 + 1418000^2$ | $:= 1502681^2$ |
| $1020\ 0497319^2 + 143218000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1502681^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0497319^2 + 14323218000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1502681^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0497319^2 + 1432323218000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1502681^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0497319^2 + 143232323218000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1502681^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0497319^2 + 14323232323218000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1502681^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0497319^2 + 1432323232323218000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1502681^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0497319^2 + 143232323232323218000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1502681^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0497319^2 + 14323232323232323218000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1502681^2$ |
- 710)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0495900^2 + 1420000^2$ | $:= 1504100^2$ |
| $1020\ 0495900^2 + 143420000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1504100^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0495900^2 + 14343420000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1504100^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0495900^2 + 1434343420000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1504100^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0495900^2 + 143434343420000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1504100^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0495900^2 + 14343434343420000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1504100^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0495900^2 + 1434343434343420000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1504100^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0495900^2 + 143434343434343420000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1504100^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0495900^2 + 14343434343434343420000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1504100^2$ |

- 711)
- $$0494479^2 + 1422000^2 := 1505521^2$$
- $$1020\ 0494479^2 + 143622000^2 := 1020\ 1505521^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0494479^2 + 14363622000^2 := 10203020\ 1505521^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0494479^2 + 1436363622000^2 := 102030403020\ 1505521^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0494479^2 + 143636363622000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1505521^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0494479^2 + 14363636363622000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1505521^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0494479^2 + 1436363636363622000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1505521^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0494479^2 + 143636363636363622000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1505521^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0494479^2 + 14363636363636363622000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1505521^2$$
- 712)
- $$0493056^2 + 1424000^2 := 1506944^2$$
- $$1020\ 0493056^2 + 143824000^2 := 1020\ 1506944^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0493056^2 + 14383824000^2 := 10203020\ 1506944^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0493056^2 + 1438383824000^2 := 102030403020\ 1506944^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0493056^2 + 143838383824000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1506944^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0493056^2 + 14383838383824000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1506944^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0493056^2 + 1438383838383824000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1506944^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0493056^2 + 143838383838383824000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1506944^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0493056^2 + 14383838383838383824000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1506944^2$$
- 713)
- $$0491631^2 + 1426000^2 := 1508369^2$$
- $$1020\ 0491631^2 + 144026000^2 := 1020\ 1508369^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0491631^2 + 14404026000^2 := 10203020\ 1508369^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0491631^2 + 1440404026000^2 := 102030403020\ 1508369^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0491631^2 + 144040404026000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1508369^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0491631^2 + 14404040404026000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1508369^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0491631^2 + 1440404040404026000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1508369^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0491631^2 + 144040404040404026000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1508369^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0491631^2 + 14404040404040404026000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1508369^2$$
- 714)
- $$0490204^2 + 1428000^2 := 1509796^2$$
- $$1020\ 0490204^2 + 144228000^2 := 1020\ 1509796^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0490204^2 + 14424228000^2 := 10203020\ 1509796^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0490204^2 + 1442424228000^2 := 102030403020\ 1509796^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0490204^2 + 144242424228000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1509796^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0490204^2 + 14424242424228000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1509796^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0490204^2 + 1442424242424228000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1509796^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0490204^2 + 144242424242424228000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1509796^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0490204^2 + 14424242424242424228000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1509796^2$$

- 715)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0488775^2 + 1430000^2$ | $:= 1511225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0488775^2 + 144430000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1511225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0488775^2 + 14444430000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1511225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0488775^2 + 1444444430000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1511225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0488775^2 + 144444444430000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1511225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0488775^2 + 14444444444430000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1511225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0488775^2 + 1444444444444430000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1511225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0488775^2 + 144444444444444430000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1511225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0488775^2 + 14444444444444444430000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1511225^2$ |
- 716)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0487344^2 + 1432000^2$ | $:= 1512656^2$ |
| $1020\ 0487344^2 + 144632000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1512656^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0487344^2 + 14464632000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1512656^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0487344^2 + 1446464632000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1512656^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0487344^2 + 144646464632000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1512656^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0487344^2 + 14464646464632000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1512656^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0487344^2 + 1446464646464632000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1512656^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0487344^2 + 144646464646464632000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1512656^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0487344^2 + 14464646464646464632000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1512656^2$ |
- 717)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0485911^2 + 1434000^2$ | $:= 1514089^2$ |
| $1020\ 0485911^2 + 144834000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1514089^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0485911^2 + 14484834000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1514089^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0485911^2 + 1448484834000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1514089^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0485911^2 + 144848484834000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1514089^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0485911^2 + 14484848484834000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1514089^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0485911^2 + 1448484848484834000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1514089^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0485911^2 + 144848484848484834000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1514089^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0485911^2 + 14484848484848484834000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1514089^2$ |
- 718)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0484476^2 + 1436000^2$ | $:= 1515524^2$ |
| $1020\ 0484476^2 + 145036000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1515524^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0484476^2 + 14505036000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1515524^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0484476^2 + 1450505036000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1515524^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0484476^2 + 145050505036000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1515524^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0484476^2 + 14505050505036000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1515524^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0484476^2 + 1450505050505036000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1515524^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0484476^2 + 145050505050505036000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1515524^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0484476^2 + 14505050505050505036000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1515524^2$ |

- 719)
- $$0483039^2 + 1438000^2 := 1516961^2$$
- $$1020\ 0483039^2 + 145238000^2 := 1020\ 1516961^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0483039^2 + 14525238000^2 := 10203020\ 1516961^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0483039^2 + 1452525238000^2 := 102030403020\ 1516961^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0483039^2 + 145252525238000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1516961^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0483039^2 + 14525252525238000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1516961^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0483039^2 + 1452525252525238000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1516961^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0483039^2 + 145252525252525238000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1516961^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0483039^2 + 14525252525252525238000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1516961^2$$
- 720)
- $$0481600^2 + 1440000^2 := 1518400^2$$
- $$1020\ 0481600^2 + 145440000^2 := 1020\ 1518400^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0481600^2 + 14545440000^2 := 10203020\ 1518400^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0481600^2 + 1454545440000^2 := 102030403020\ 1518400^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0481600^2 + 145454545440000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1518400^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0481600^2 + 14545454545440000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1518400^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0481600^2 + 1454545454545440000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1518400^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0481600^2 + 145454545454545440000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1518400^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0481600^2 + 14545454545454545440000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1518400^2$$
- 721)
- $$0480159^2 + 1442000^2 := 1519841^2$$
- $$1020\ 0480159^2 + 145642000^2 := 1020\ 1519841^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0480159^2 + 14565642000^2 := 10203020\ 1519841^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0480159^2 + 1456565642000^2 := 102030403020\ 1519841^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0480159^2 + 145656565642000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1519841^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0480159^2 + 14565656565642000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1519841^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0480159^2 + 1456565656565642000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1519841^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0480159^2 + 145656565656565642000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1519841^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0480159^2 + 14565656565656565642000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1519841^2$$
- 722)
- $$0478716^2 + 1444000^2 := 1521284^2$$
- $$1020\ 0478716^2 + 145844000^2 := 1020\ 1521284^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0478716^2 + 14585844000^2 := 10203020\ 1521284^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0478716^2 + 1458585844000^2 := 102030403020\ 1521284^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0478716^2 + 145858585844000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1521284^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0478716^2 + 14585858585844000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1521284^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0478716^2 + 1458585858585844000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1521284^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0478716^2 + 145858585858585844000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1521284^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0478716^2 + 14585858585858585844000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1521284^2$$

- 723)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0477271^2 + 1446000^2$ | $:= 1522729^2$ |
| $1020\ 0477271^2 + 146046000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1522729^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0477271^2 + 14606046000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1522729^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0477271^2 + 1460606046000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1522729^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0477271^2 + 146060606046000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1522729^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0477271^2 + 14606060606046000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1522729^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0477271^2 + 1460606060606046000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1522729^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0477271^2 + 146060606060606046000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1522729^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0477271^2 + 14606060606060606046000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1522729^2$ |
- 724)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0475824^2 + 1448000^2$ | $:= 1524176^2$ |
| $1020\ 0475824^2 + 146248000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1524176^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0475824^2 + 14626248000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1524176^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0475824^2 + 1462626248000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1524176^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0475824^2 + 146262626248000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1524176^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0475824^2 + 14626262626248000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1524176^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0475824^2 + 1462626262626248000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1524176^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0475824^2 + 146262626262626248000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1524176^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0475824^2 + 14626262626262626248000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1524176^2$ |
- 725)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0474375^2 + 1450000^2$ | $:= 1525625^2$ |
| $1020\ 0474375^2 + 146450000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1525625^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0474375^2 + 14646450000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1525625^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0474375^2 + 1464646450000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1525625^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0474375^2 + 146464646450000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1525625^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0474375^2 + 14646464646450000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1525625^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0474375^2 + 1464646464646450000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1525625^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0474375^2 + 146464646464646450000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1525625^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0474375^2 + 14646464646464646450000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1525625^2$ |
- 726)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0472924^2 + 1452000^2$ | $:= 1527076^2$ |
| $1020\ 0472924^2 + 146652000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1527076^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0472924^2 + 14666652000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1527076^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0472924^2 + 1466666652000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1527076^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0472924^2 + 146666666652000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1527076^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0472924^2 + 14666666666652000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1527076^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0472924^2 + 1466666666666652000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1527076^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0472924^2 + 146666666666666652000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1527076^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0472924^2 + 14666666666666666652000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1527076^2$ |

- 727)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0471471^2 + 1454000^2$ | $:= 1528529^2$ |
| $1020\ 0471471^2 + 146854000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1528529^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0471471^2 + 14686854000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1528529^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0471471^2 + 1468686854000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1528529^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0471471^2 + 146868686854000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1528529^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0471471^2 + 14686868686854000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1528529^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0471471^2 + 1468686868686854000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1528529^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0471471^2 + 146868686868686854000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1528529^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0471471^2 + 14686868686868686854000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1528529^2$ |
- 728)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0470016^2 + 1456000^2$ | $:= 1529984^2$ |
| $1020\ 0470016^2 + 147056000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1529984^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0470016^2 + 14707056000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1529984^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0470016^2 + 1470707056000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1529984^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0470016^2 + 147070707056000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1529984^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0470016^2 + 14707070707056000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1529984^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0470016^2 + 1470707070707056000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1529984^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0470016^2 + 147070707070707056000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1529984^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0470016^2 + 14707070707070707056000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1529984^2$ |
- 729)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0468559^2 + 1458000^2$ | $:= 1531441^2$ |
| $1020\ 0468559^2 + 147258000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1531441^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0468559^2 + 14727258000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1531441^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0468559^2 + 1472727258000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1531441^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0468559^2 + 147272727258000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1531441^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0468559^2 + 14727272727258000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1531441^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0468559^2 + 1472727272727258000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1531441^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0468559^2 + 147272727272727258000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1531441^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0468559^2 + 14727272727272727258000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1531441^2$ |
- 730)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0467100^2 + 1460000^2$ | $:= 1532900^2$ |
| $1020\ 0467100^2 + 147460000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1532900^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0467100^2 + 14747460000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1532900^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0467100^2 + 1474747460000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1532900^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0467100^2 + 147474747460000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1532900^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0467100^2 + 14747474747460000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1532900^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0467100^2 + 1474747474747460000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1532900^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0467100^2 + 147474747474747460000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1532900^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0467100^2 + 14747474747474747460000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1532900^2$ |

- 731)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0465639^2 + 1462000^2$ | $:= 1534361^2$ |
| 1020 $0465639^2 + 147662000^2$ | $:=$ 1020 1534361^2 |
| 10203020 $0465639^2 + 14767662000^2$ | $:=$ 10203020 1534361^2 |
| 102030403020 $0465639^2 + 1476767662000^2$ | $:=$ 102030403020 1534361^2 |
| 1020304050403020 $0465639^2 + 147676767662000^2$ | $:=$ 1020304050403020 1534361^2 |
| 10203040506050403020 $0465639^2 + 14767676767662000^2$ | $:=$ 10203040506050403020 1534361^2 |
| 102030405060706050403020 $0465639^2 + 1476767676767662000^2$ | $:=$ 102030405060706050403020 1534361^2 |
| 1020304050607080706050403020 $0465639^2 + 147676767676767662000^2$ | $:=$ 1020304050607080706050403020 1534361^2 |
| 10203040506070809080706050403020 $0465639^2 + 14767676767676767662000^2$ | $:=$ 10203040506070809080706050403020 1534361^2 |
- 732)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0464176^2 + 1464000^2$ | $:= 1535824^2$ |
| 1020 $0464176^2 + 147864000^2$ | $:=$ 1020 1535824^2 |
| 10203020 $0464176^2 + 14787864000^2$ | $:=$ 10203020 1535824^2 |
| 102030403020 $0464176^2 + 1478787864000^2$ | $:=$ 102030403020 1535824^2 |
| 1020304050403020 $0464176^2 + 147878787864000^2$ | $:=$ 1020304050403020 1535824^2 |
| 10203040506050403020 $0464176^2 + 14787878787864000^2$ | $:=$ 10203040506050403020 1535824^2 |
| 102030405060706050403020 $0464176^2 + 1478787878787864000^2$ | $:=$ 102030405060706050403020 1535824^2 |
| 1020304050607080706050403020 $0464176^2 + 147878787878787864000^2$ | $:=$ 1020304050607080706050403020 1535824^2 |
| 10203040506070809080706050403020 $0464176^2 + 14787878787878787864000^2$ | $:=$ 10203040506070809080706050403020 1535824^2 |
- 733)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0462711^2 + 1466000^2$ | $:= 1537289^2$ |
| 1020 $0462711^2 + 148066000^2$ | $:=$ 1020 1537289^2 |
| 10203020 $0462711^2 + 14808066000^2$ | $:=$ 10203020 1537289^2 |
| 102030403020 $0462711^2 + 1480808066000^2$ | $:=$ 102030403020 1537289^2 |
| 1020304050403020 $0462711^2 + 148080808066000^2$ | $:=$ 1020304050403020 1537289^2 |
| 10203040506050403020 $0462711^2 + 14808080808066000^2$ | $:=$ 10203040506050403020 1537289^2 |
| 102030405060706050403020 $0462711^2 + 1480808080808066000^2$ | $:=$ 102030405060706050403020 1537289^2 |
| 1020304050607080706050403020 $0462711^2 + 148080808080808066000^2$ | $:=$ 1020304050607080706050403020 1537289^2 |
| 10203040506070809080706050403020 $0462711^2 + 14808080808080808066000^2$ | $:=$ 10203040506070809080706050403020 1537289^2 |
- 734)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0461244^2 + 1468000^2$ | $:= 1538756^2$ |
| 1020 $0461244^2 + 148268000^2$ | $:=$ 1020 1538756^2 |
| 10203020 $0461244^2 + 14828268000^2$ | $:=$ 10203020 1538756^2 |
| 102030403020 $0461244^2 + 1482828268000^2$ | $:=$ 102030403020 1538756^2 |
| 1020304050403020 $0461244^2 + 148282828268000^2$ | $:=$ 1020304050403020 1538756^2 |
| 10203040506050403020 $0461244^2 + 14828282828268000^2$ | $:=$ 10203040506050403020 1538756^2 |
| 102030405060706050403020 $0461244^2 + 1482828282828268000^2$ | $:=$ 102030405060706050403020 1538756^2 |
| 1020304050607080706050403020 $0461244^2 + 148282828282828268000^2$ | $:=$ 1020304050607080706050403020 1538756^2 |
| 10203040506070809080706050403020 $0461244^2 + 14828282828282828268000^2$ | $:=$ 10203040506070809080706050403020 1538756^2 |

- 735)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0459775^2 + 1470000^2 && := 1540225^2 \\ &1020\ 0459775^2 + 148470000^2 && := 1020\ 1540225^2 \\ &10203020\ 0459775^2 + 14848470000^2 && := 10203020\ 1540225^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0459775^2 + 1484848470000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1540225^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0459775^2 + 148484848470000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1540225^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0459775^2 + 14848484848470000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1540225^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0459775^2 + 1484848484848470000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1540225^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0459775^2 + 148484848484848470000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1540225^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0459775^2 + 14848484848484848470000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1540225^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 736)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0458304^2 + 1472000^2 && := 1541696^2 \\ &1020\ 0458304^2 + 148672000^2 && := 1020\ 1541696^2 \\ &10203020\ 0458304^2 + 14868672000^2 && := 10203020\ 1541696^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0458304^2 + 1486868672000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1541696^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0458304^2 + 148686868672000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1541696^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0458304^2 + 14868686868672000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1541696^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0458304^2 + 1486868686868672000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1541696^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0458304^2 + 148686868686868672000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1541696^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0458304^2 + 14868686868686868672000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1541696^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 737)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0456831^2 + 1474000^2 && := 1543169^2 \\ &1020\ 0456831^2 + 148874000^2 && := 1020\ 1543169^2 \\ &10203020\ 0456831^2 + 14888874000^2 && := 10203020\ 1543169^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0456831^2 + 1488888874000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1543169^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0456831^2 + 148888888874000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1543169^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0456831^2 + 14888888888874000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1543169^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0456831^2 + 1488888888888874000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1543169^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0456831^2 + 148888888888888874000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1543169^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0456831^2 + 14888888888888888874000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1543169^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 738)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0455356^2 + 1476000^2 && := 1544644^2 \\ &1020\ 0455356^2 + 149076000^2 && := 1020\ 1544644^2 \\ &10203020\ 0455356^2 + 14909076000^2 && := 10203020\ 1544644^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0455356^2 + 1490909076000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1544644^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0455356^2 + 149090909076000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1544644^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0455356^2 + 14909090909076000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1544644^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0455356^2 + 1490909090909076000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1544644^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0455356^2 + 149090909090909076000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1544644^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0455356^2 + 14909090909090909076000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1544644^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 739)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0453879^2 + 1478000^2 && := 1546121^2 \\ &1020\ 0453879^2 + 149278000^2 && := 1020\ 1546121^2 \\ &10203020\ 0453879^2 + 14929278000^2 && := 10203020\ 1546121^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0453879^2 + 1492929278000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1546121^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0453879^2 + 149292929278000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1546121^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0453879^2 + 14929292929278000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1546121^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0453879^2 + 1492929292929278000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1546121^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0453879^2 + 149292929292929278000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1546121^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0453879^2 + 14929292929292929278000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1546121^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 740)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0452400^2 + 1480000^2 && := 1547600^2 \\ &1020\ 0452400^2 + 149480000^2 && := 1020\ 1547600^2 \\ &10203020\ 0452400^2 + 14949480000^2 && := 10203020\ 1547600^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0452400^2 + 1494949480000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1547600^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0452400^2 + 149494949480000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1547600^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0452400^2 + 14949494949480000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1547600^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0452400^2 + 1494949494949480000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1547600^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0452400^2 + 149494949494949480000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1547600^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0452400^2 + 14949494949494949480000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1547600^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 741)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0450919^2 + 1482000^2 && := 1549081^2 \\ &1020\ 0450919^2 + 149682000^2 && := 1020\ 1549081^2 \\ &10203020\ 0450919^2 + 14969682000^2 && := 10203020\ 1549081^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0450919^2 + 1496969682000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1549081^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0450919^2 + 149696969682000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1549081^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0450919^2 + 14969696969682000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1549081^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0450919^2 + 1496969696969682000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1549081^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0450919^2 + 149696969696969682000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1549081^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0450919^2 + 14969696969696969682000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1549081^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 742)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0449436^2 + 1484000^2 && := 1550564^2 \\ &1020\ 0449436^2 + 149884000^2 && := 1020\ 1550564^2 \\ &10203020\ 0449436^2 + 14989884000^2 && := 10203020\ 1550564^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0449436^2 + 1498989884000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1550564^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0449436^2 + 149898989884000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1550564^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0449436^2 + 14989898989884000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1550564^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0449436^2 + 1498989898989884000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1550564^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0449436^2 + 149898989898989884000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1550564^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0449436^2 + 14989898989898989884000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1550564^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 743)
- $$0447951^2 + 1486000^2 := 1552049^2$$
- $$1020\ 0447951^2 + 150086000^2 := 1020\ 1552049^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0447951^2 + 15010086000^2 := 10203020\ 1552049^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0447951^2 + 1501010086000^2 := 102030403020\ 1552049^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0447951^2 + 150101010086000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1552049^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0447951^2 + 15010101010086000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1552049^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0447951^2 + 1501010101010086000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1552049^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0447951^2 + 150101010101010086000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1552049^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0447951^2 + 15010101010101010086000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1552049^2$$
- 744)
- $$0446464^2 + 1488000^2 := 1553536^2$$
- $$1020\ 0446464^2 + 150288000^2 := 1020\ 1553536^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0446464^2 + 15030288000^2 := 10203020\ 1553536^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0446464^2 + 1503030288000^2 := 102030403020\ 1553536^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0446464^2 + 150303030288000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1553536^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0446464^2 + 15030303030288000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1553536^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0446464^2 + 1503030303030288000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1553536^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0446464^2 + 150303030303030288000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1553536^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0446464^2 + 15030303030303030288000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1553536^2$$
- 745)
- $$0444975^2 + 1490000^2 := 1555025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0444975^2 + 150490000^2 := 1020\ 1555025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0444975^2 + 15050490000^2 := 10203020\ 1555025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0444975^2 + 1505050490000^2 := 102030403020\ 1555025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0444975^2 + 150505050490000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1555025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0444975^2 + 15050505050490000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1555025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0444975^2 + 1505050505050490000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1555025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0444975^2 + 150505050505050490000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1555025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0444975^2 + 15050505050505050490000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1555025^2$$
- 746)
- $$0443484^2 + 1492000^2 := 1556516^2$$
- $$1020\ 0443484^2 + 150692000^2 := 1020\ 1556516^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0443484^2 + 15070692000^2 := 10203020\ 1556516^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0443484^2 + 1507070692000^2 := 102030403020\ 1556516^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0443484^2 + 150707070692000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1556516^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0443484^2 + 15070707070692000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1556516^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0443484^2 + 1507070707070692000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1556516^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0443484^2 + 150707070707070692000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1556516^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0443484^2 + 15070707070707070692000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1556516^2$$

- 747)
- $$0441991^2 + 1494000^2 := 1558009^2$$
- $$1020\ 0441991^2 + 150894000^2 := 1020\ 1558009^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0441991^2 + 15090894000^2 := 10203020\ 1558009^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0441991^2 + 1509090894000^2 := 102030403020\ 1558009^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0441991^2 + 150909090894000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1558009^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0441991^2 + 15090909090894000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1558009^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0441991^2 + 1509090909090894000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1558009^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0441991^2 + 150909090909090894000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1558009^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0441991^2 + 15090909090909090894000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1558009^2$$
- 748)
- $$0440496^2 + 1496000^2 := 1559504^2$$
- $$1020\ 0440496^2 + 151096000^2 := 1020\ 1559504^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0440496^2 + 15111096000^2 := 10203020\ 1559504^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0440496^2 + 1511111096000^2 := 102030403020\ 1559504^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0440496^2 + 151111111096000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1559504^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0440496^2 + 15111111111096000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1559504^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0440496^2 + 1511111111111096000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1559504^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0440496^2 + 151111111111111096000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1559504^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0440496^2 + 15111111111111111096000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1559504^2$$
- 749)
- $$0438999^2 + 1498000^2 := 1561001^2$$
- $$1020\ 0438999^2 + 151298000^2 := 1020\ 1561001^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0438999^2 + 15131298000^2 := 10203020\ 1561001^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0438999^2 + 1513131298000^2 := 102030403020\ 1561001^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0438999^2 + 151313131298000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1561001^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0438999^2 + 15131313131298000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1561001^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0438999^2 + 1513131313131298000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1561001^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0438999^2 + 151313131313131298000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1561001^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0438999^2 + 15131313131313131298000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1561001^2$$
- 750)
- $$0437500^2 + 1500000^2 := 1562500^2$$
- $$1020\ 0437500^2 + 151500000^2 := 1020\ 1562500^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0437500^2 + 15151500000^2 := 10203020\ 1562500^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0437500^2 + 1515151500000^2 := 102030403020\ 1562500^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0437500^2 + 151515151500000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1562500^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0437500^2 + 15151515151500000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1562500^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0437500^2 + 1515151515151500000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1562500^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0437500^2 + 151515151515151500000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1562500^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0437500^2 + 15151515151515151500000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1562500^2$$

- 751)
- $$0435999^2 + 1502000^2 := 1564001^2$$
- $$1020\ 0435999^2 + 151702000^2 := 1020\ 1564001^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0435999^2 + 15171702000^2 := 10203020\ 1564001^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0435999^2 + 1517171702000^2 := 102030403020\ 1564001^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0435999^2 + 151717171702000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1564001^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0435999^2 + 15171717171702000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1564001^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0435999^2 + 1517171717171702000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1564001^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0435999^2 + 151717171717171702000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1564001^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0435999^2 + 15171717171717171702000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1564001^2$$
- 752)
- $$0434496^2 + 1504000^2 := 1565504^2$$
- $$1020\ 0434496^2 + 151904000^2 := 1020\ 1565504^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0434496^2 + 15191904000^2 := 10203020\ 1565504^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0434496^2 + 1519191904000^2 := 102030403020\ 1565504^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0434496^2 + 151919191904000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1565504^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0434496^2 + 15191919191904000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1565504^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0434496^2 + 1519191919191904000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1565504^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0434496^2 + 151919191919191904000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1565504^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0434496^2 + 15191919191919191904000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1565504^2$$
- 753)
- $$0432991^2 + 1506000^2 := 1567009^2$$
- $$1020\ 0432991^2 + 152106000^2 := 1020\ 1567009^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0432991^2 + 15212106000^2 := 10203020\ 1567009^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0432991^2 + 1521212106000^2 := 102030403020\ 1567009^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0432991^2 + 152121212106000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1567009^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0432991^2 + 15212121212106000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1567009^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0432991^2 + 1521212121212106000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1567009^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0432991^2 + 152121212121212106000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1567009^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0432991^2 + 152121212121212106000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1567009^2$$
- 754)
- $$0431484^2 + 1508000^2 := 1568516^2$$
- $$1020\ 0431484^2 + 152308000^2 := 1020\ 1568516^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0431484^2 + 15232308000^2 := 10203020\ 1568516^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0431484^2 + 1523232308000^2 := 102030403020\ 1568516^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0431484^2 + 152323232308000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1568516^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0431484^2 + 15232323232308000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1568516^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0431484^2 + 1523232323232308000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1568516^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0431484^2 + 152323232323232308000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1568516^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0431484^2 + 152323232323232308000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1568516^2$$

- 755)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0429975^2 + 1510000^2 && := 1570025^2 \\ &1020\ 0429975^2 + 152510000^2 && := 1020\ 1570025^2 \\ &10203020\ 0429975^2 + 15252510000^2 && := 10203020\ 1570025^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0429975^2 + 1525252510000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1570025^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0429975^2 + 152525252510000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1570025^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0429975^2 + 15252525252510000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1570025^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0429975^2 + 1525252525252510000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1570025^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0429975^2 + 152525252525252510000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1570025^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0429975^2 + 15252525252525252510000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1570025^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 756)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0428464^2 + 1512000^2 && := 1571536^2 \\ &1020\ 0428464^2 + 152712000^2 && := 1020\ 1571536^2 \\ &10203020\ 0428464^2 + 15272712000^2 && := 10203020\ 1571536^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0428464^2 + 1527272712000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1571536^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0428464^2 + 152727272712000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1571536^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0428464^2 + 15272727272712000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1571536^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0428464^2 + 1527272727272712000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1571536^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0428464^2 + 152727272727272712000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1571536^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0428464^2 + 15272727272727272712000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1571536^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 757)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0426951^2 + 1514000^2 && := 1573049^2 \\ &1020\ 0426951^2 + 152914000^2 && := 1020\ 1573049^2 \\ &10203020\ 0426951^2 + 15292914000^2 && := 10203020\ 1573049^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0426951^2 + 1529292914000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1573049^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0426951^2 + 152929292914000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1573049^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0426951^2 + 15292929292914000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1573049^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0426951^2 + 1529292929292914000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1573049^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0426951^2 + 152929292929292914000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1573049^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0426951^2 + 15292929292929292914000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1573049^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 758)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0425436^2 + 1516000^2 && := 1574564^2 \\ &1020\ 0425436^2 + 153116000^2 && := 1020\ 1574564^2 \\ &10203020\ 0425436^2 + 15313116000^2 && := 10203020\ 1574564^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0425436^2 + 1531313116000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1574564^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0425436^2 + 153131313116000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1574564^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0425436^2 + 15313131313116000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1574564^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0425436^2 + 1531313131313116000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1574564^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0425436^2 + 153131313131313116000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1574564^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0425436^2 + 15313131313131313116000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1574564^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 759)
- $$0423919^2 + 1518000^2 := 1576081^2$$
- $$1020\ 0423919^2 + 153318000^2 := 1020\ 1576081^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0423919^2 + 15333318000^2 := 10203020\ 1576081^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0423919^2 + 1533333318000^2 := 102030403020\ 1576081^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0423919^2 + 153333333318000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1576081^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0423919^2 + 15333333333318000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1576081^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0423919^2 + 1533333333333318000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1576081^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0423919^2 + 153333333333333318000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1576081^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0423919^2 + 15333333333333333318000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1576081^2$$
- 760)
- $$0422400^2 + 1520000^2 := 1577600^2$$
- $$1020\ 0422400^2 + 153520000^2 := 1020\ 1577600^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0422400^2 + 15353520000^2 := 10203020\ 1577600^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0422400^2 + 1535353520000^2 := 102030403020\ 1577600^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0422400^2 + 153535353520000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1577600^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0422400^2 + 15353535353520000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1577600^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0422400^2 + 1535353535353520000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1577600^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0422400^2 + 153535353535353520000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1577600^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0422400^2 + 15353535353535353520000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1577600^2$$
- 761)
- $$0420879^2 + 1522000^2 := 1579121^2$$
- $$1020\ 0420879^2 + 153722000^2 := 1020\ 1579121^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0420879^2 + 15373722000^2 := 10203020\ 1579121^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0420879^2 + 1537373722000^2 := 102030403020\ 1579121^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0420879^2 + 153737373722000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1579121^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0420879^2 + 15373737373722000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1579121^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0420879^2 + 1537373737373722000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1579121^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0420879^2 + 153737373737373722000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1579121^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0420879^2 + 15373737373737373722000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1579121^2$$
- 762)
- $$0419356^2 + 1524000^2 := 1580644^2$$
- $$1020\ 0419356^2 + 153924000^2 := 1020\ 1580644^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0419356^2 + 15393924000^2 := 10203020\ 1580644^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0419356^2 + 1539393924000^2 := 102030403020\ 1580644^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0419356^2 + 153939393924000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1580644^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0419356^2 + 15393939393924000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1580644^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0419356^2 + 1539393939393924000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1580644^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0419356^2 + 153939393939393924000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1580644^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0419356^2 + 15393939393939393924000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1580644^2$$

- 763)
- $$0417831^2 + 1526000^2 := 1582169^2$$
- $$1020\ 0417831^2 + 154126000^2 := 1020\ 1582169^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0417831^2 + 15414126000^2 := 10203020\ 1582169^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0417831^2 + 1541414126000^2 := 102030403020\ 1582169^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0417831^2 + 154141414126000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1582169^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0417831^2 + 15414141414126000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1582169^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0417831^2 + 1541414141414126000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1582169^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0417831^2 + 154141414141414126000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1582169^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0417831^2 + 15414141414141414126000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1582169^2$$
- 764)
- $$0416304^2 + 1528000^2 := 1583696^2$$
- $$1020\ 0416304^2 + 154328000^2 := 1020\ 1583696^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0416304^2 + 15434328000^2 := 10203020\ 1583696^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0416304^2 + 1543434328000^2 := 102030403020\ 1583696^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0416304^2 + 154343434328000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1583696^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0416304^2 + 15434343434328000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1583696^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0416304^2 + 1543434343434328000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1583696^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0416304^2 + 154343434343434328000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1583696^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0416304^2 + 15434343434343434328000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1583696^2$$
- 765)
- $$0414775^2 + 1530000^2 := 1585225^2$$
- $$1020\ 0414775^2 + 154530000^2 := 1020\ 1585225^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0414775^2 + 15454530000^2 := 10203020\ 1585225^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0414775^2 + 1545454530000^2 := 102030403020\ 1585225^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0414775^2 + 154545454530000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1585225^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0414775^2 + 15454545454530000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1585225^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0414775^2 + 1545454545454530000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1585225^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0414775^2 + 154545454545454530000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1585225^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0414775^2 + 154545454545454530000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1585225^2$$
- 766)
- $$0413244^2 + 1532000^2 := 1586756^2$$
- $$1020\ 0413244^2 + 154732000^2 := 1020\ 1586756^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0413244^2 + 15474732000^2 := 10203020\ 1586756^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0413244^2 + 1547474732000^2 := 102030403020\ 1586756^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0413244^2 + 154747474732000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1586756^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0413244^2 + 15474747474732000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1586756^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0413244^2 + 1547474747474732000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1586756^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0413244^2 + 154747474747474732000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1586756^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0413244^2 + 15474747474747474732000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1586756^2$$

- 767)
- $$0411711^2 + 1534000^2 := 1588289^2$$
- $$1020\ 0411711^2 + 154934000^2 := 1020\ 1588289^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0411711^2 + 15494934000^2 := 10203020\ 1588289^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0411711^2 + 1549494934000^2 := 102030403020\ 1588289^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0411711^2 + 154949494934000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1588289^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0411711^2 + 15494949494934000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1588289^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0411711^2 + 1549494949494934000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1588289^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0411711^2 + 154949494949494934000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1588289^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0411711^2 + 15494949494949494934000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1588289^2$$
- 768)
- $$0410176^2 + 1536000^2 := 1589824^2$$
- $$1020\ 0410176^2 + 155136000^2 := 1020\ 1589824^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0410176^2 + 15515136000^2 := 10203020\ 1589824^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0410176^2 + 1551515136000^2 := 102030403020\ 1589824^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0410176^2 + 155151515136000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1589824^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0410176^2 + 15515151515136000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1589824^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0410176^2 + 1551515151515136000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1589824^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0410176^2 + 155151515151515136000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1589824^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0410176^2 + 15515151515151515136000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1589824^2$$
- 769)
- $$0408639^2 + 1538000^2 := 1591361^2$$
- $$1020\ 0408639^2 + 155338000^2 := 1020\ 1591361^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0408639^2 + 15535338000^2 := 10203020\ 1591361^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0408639^2 + 1553535338000^2 := 102030403020\ 1591361^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0408639^2 + 155353535338000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1591361^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0408639^2 + 15535353535338000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1591361^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0408639^2 + 1553535353535338000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1591361^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0408639^2 + 155353535353535338000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1591361^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0408639^2 + 155353535353535338000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1591361^2$$
- 770)
- $$0407100^2 + 1540000^2 := 1592900^2$$
- $$1020\ 0407100^2 + 155540000^2 := 1020\ 1592900^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0407100^2 + 15555540000^2 := 10203020\ 1592900^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0407100^2 + 1555555540000^2 := 102030403020\ 1592900^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0407100^2 + 155555555540000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1592900^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0407100^2 + 15555555555540000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1592900^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0407100^2 + 1555555555555540000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1592900^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0407100^2 + 155555555555555540000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1592900^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0407100^2 + 15555555555555555540000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1592900^2$$

- 771)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0405559^2 + 1542000^2 && := 1594441^2 \\ &1020\ 0405559^2 + 155742000^2 && := 1020\ 1594441^2 \\ &10203020\ 0405559^2 + 15575742000^2 && := 10203020\ 1594441^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0405559^2 + 1557575742000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1594441^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0405559^2 + 155757575742000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1594441^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0405559^2 + 15575757575742000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1594441^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0405559^2 + 1557575757575742000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1594441^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0405559^2 + 155757575757575742000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1594441^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0405559^2 + 15575757575757575742000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1594441^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 772)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0404016^2 + 1544000^2 && := 1595984^2 \\ &1020\ 0404016^2 + 155944000^2 && := 1020\ 1595984^2 \\ &10203020\ 0404016^2 + 15595944000^2 && := 10203020\ 1595984^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0404016^2 + 1559595944000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1595984^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0404016^2 + 155959595944000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1595984^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0404016^2 + 15595959595944000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1595984^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0404016^2 + 1559595959595944000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1595984^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0404016^2 + 155959595959595944000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1595984^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0404016^2 + 15595959595959595944000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1595984^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 773)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0402471^2 + 1546000^2 && := 1597529^2 \\ &1020\ 0402471^2 + 156146000^2 && := 1020\ 1597529^2 \\ &10203020\ 0402471^2 + 15616146000^2 && := 10203020\ 1597529^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0402471^2 + 1561616146000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1597529^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0402471^2 + 156161616146000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1597529^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0402471^2 + 15616161616146000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1597529^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0402471^2 + 1561616161616146000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1597529^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0402471^2 + 156161616161616146000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1597529^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0402471^2 + 15616161616161616146000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1597529^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 774)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0400924^2 + 1548000^2 && := 1599076^2 \\ &1020\ 0400924^2 + 156348000^2 && := 1020\ 1599076^2 \\ &10203020\ 0400924^2 + 15636348000^2 && := 10203020\ 1599076^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0400924^2 + 1563636348000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1599076^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0400924^2 + 156363636348000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1599076^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0400924^2 + 15636363636348000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1599076^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0400924^2 + 1563636363636348000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1599076^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0400924^2 + 156363636363636348000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1599076^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0400924^2 + 15636363636363636348000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1599076^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 775)
- $$0399375^2 + 1550000^2 := 1600625^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0399375^2 + 156550000^2 := 1020 \ 1600625^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0399375^2 + 15656550000^2 := 10203020 \ 1600625^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0399375^2 + 1565656550000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1600625^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0399375^2 + 156565656550000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1600625^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0399375^2 + 15656565656550000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1600625^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0399375^2 + 1565656565656550000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1600625^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0399375^2 + 156565656565656550000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1600625^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0399375^2 + 15656565656565656550000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1600625^2$$
- 776)
- $$0397824^2 + 1552000^2 := 1602176^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0397824^2 + 156752000^2 := 1020 \ 1602176^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0397824^2 + 15676752000^2 := 10203020 \ 1602176^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0397824^2 + 1567676752000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1602176^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0397824^2 + 156767676752000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1602176^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0397824^2 + 15676767676752000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1602176^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0397824^2 + 1567676767676752000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1602176^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0397824^2 + 156767676767676752000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1602176^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0397824^2 + 15676767676767676752000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1602176^2$$
- 777)
- $$0396271^2 + 1554000^2 := 1603729^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0396271^2 + 156954000^2 := 1020 \ 1603729^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0396271^2 + 15696954000^2 := 10203020 \ 1603729^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0396271^2 + 1569696954000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1603729^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0396271^2 + 156969696954000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1603729^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0396271^2 + 15696969696954000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1603729^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0396271^2 + 1569696969696954000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1603729^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0396271^2 + 156969696969696954000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1603729^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0396271^2 + 15696969696969696954000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1603729^2$$
- 778)
- $$0394716^2 + 1556000^2 := 1605284^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0394716^2 + 157156000^2 := 1020 \ 1605284^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0394716^2 + 15717156000^2 := 10203020 \ 1605284^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0394716^2 + 1571717156000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1605284^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0394716^2 + 157171717156000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1605284^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0394716^2 + 15717171717156000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1605284^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0394716^2 + 1571717171717156000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1605284^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0394716^2 + 157171717171717156000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1605284^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0394716^2 + 157171717171717156000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1605284^2$$

- 779)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0393159^2 + 1558000^2 && := 1606841^2 \\
 &1020\ 0393159^2 + 157358000^2 && := 1020\ 1606841^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0393159^2 + 15737358000^2 && := 10203020\ 1606841^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0393159^2 + 1573737358000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1606841^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0393159^2 + 157373737358000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1606841^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0393159^2 + 15737373737358000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1606841^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0393159^2 + 1573737373737358000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1606841^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0393159^2 + 157373737373737358000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1606841^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0393159^2 + 15737373737373737358000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1606841^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 780)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0391600^2 + 1560000^2 && := 1608400^2 \\
 &1020\ 0391600^2 + 157560000^2 && := 1020\ 1608400^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0391600^2 + 15757560000^2 && := 10203020\ 1608400^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0391600^2 + 1575757560000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1608400^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0391600^2 + 157575757560000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1608400^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0391600^2 + 15757575757560000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1608400^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0391600^2 + 1575757575757560000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1608400^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0391600^2 + 157575757575757560000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1608400^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0391600^2 + 15757575757575757560000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1608400^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 781)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0390039^2 + 1562000^2 && := 1609961^2 \\
 &1020\ 0390039^2 + 157762000^2 && := 1020\ 1609961^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0390039^2 + 15777762000^2 && := 10203020\ 1609961^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0390039^2 + 1577777762000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1609961^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0390039^2 + 157777777762000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1609961^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0390039^2 + 15777777777762000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1609961^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0390039^2 + 1577777777777762000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1609961^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0390039^2 + 157777777777777762000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1609961^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0390039^2 + 15777777777777777762000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1609961^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 782)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0388476^2 + 1564000^2 && := 1611524^2 \\
 &1020\ 0388476^2 + 157964000^2 && := 1020\ 1611524^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0388476^2 + 15797964000^2 && := 10203020\ 1611524^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0388476^2 + 1579797964000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1611524^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0388476^2 + 157979797964000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1611524^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0388476^2 + 15797979797964000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1611524^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0388476^2 + 1579797979797964000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1611524^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0388476^2 + 157979797979797964000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1611524^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0388476^2 + 15797979797979797964000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1611524^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 783)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0386911^2 + 1566000^2$ | $:= 1613089^2$ |
| $1020\ 0386911^2 + 158166000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1613089^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0386911^2 + 15818166000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1613089^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0386911^2 + 1581818166000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1613089^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0386911^2 + 158181818166000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1613089^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0386911^2 + 15818181818166000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1613089^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0386911^2 + 1581818181818166000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1613089^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0386911^2 + 158181818181818166000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1613089^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0386911^2 + 15818181818181818166000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1613089^2$ |
- 784)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0385344^2 + 1568000^2$ | $:= 1614656^2$ |
| $1020\ 0385344^2 + 158368000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1614656^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0385344^2 + 15838368000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1614656^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0385344^2 + 1583838368000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1614656^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0385344^2 + 158383838368000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1614656^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0385344^2 + 15838383838368000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1614656^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0385344^2 + 1583838383838368000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1614656^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0385344^2 + 158383838383838368000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1614656^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0385344^2 + 15838383838383838368000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1614656^2$ |
- 785)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0383775^2 + 1570000^2$ | $:= 1616225^2$ |
| $1020\ 0383775^2 + 158570000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1616225^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0383775^2 + 15858570000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1616225^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0383775^2 + 1585858570000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1616225^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0383775^2 + 158585858570000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1616225^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0383775^2 + 15858585858570000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1616225^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0383775^2 + 1585858585858570000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1616225^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0383775^2 + 158585858585858570000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1616225^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0383775^2 + 15858585858585858570000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1616225^2$ |
- 786)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0382204^2 + 1572000^2$ | $:= 1617796^2$ |
| $1020\ 0382204^2 + 158772000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1617796^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0382204^2 + 15878772000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1617796^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0382204^2 + 1587878772000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1617796^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0382204^2 + 158787878772000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1617796^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0382204^2 + 15878787878772000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1617796^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0382204^2 + 1587878787878772000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1617796^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0382204^2 + 158787878787878772000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1617796^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0382204^2 + 15878787878787878772000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1617796^2$ |

- 787)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0380631^2 + 1574000^2 && := 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0380631^2 + 158974000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0380631^2 + 15898974000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0380631^2 + 1589898974000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0380631^2 + 158989898974000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0380631^2 + 15898989898974000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0380631^2 + 1589898989898974000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0380631^2 + 1589898989898974000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1619369^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0380631^2 + 1589898989898974000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1619369^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 788)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0379056^2 + 1576000^2 && := 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0379056^2 + 159176000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0379056^2 + 15919176000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0379056^2 + 1591919176000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0379056^2 + 159191919176000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0379056^2 + 15919191919176000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0379056^2 + 1591919191919176000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0379056^2 + 159191919191919176000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1620944^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0379056^2 + 15919191919191919176000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1620944^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 789)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0377479^2 + 1578000^2 && := 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0377479^2 + 159378000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0377479^2 + 15939378000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0377479^2 + 1593939378000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0377479^2 + 159393939378000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0377479^2 + 15939393939378000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0377479^2 + 1593939393939378000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0377479^2 + 159393939393939378000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1622521^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0377479^2 + 15939393939393939378000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1622521^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 790)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0375900^2 + 1580000^2 && := 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0375900^2 + 159580000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0375900^2 + 15959580000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0375900^2 + 1595959580000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0375900^2 + 159595959580000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0375900^2 + 15959595959580000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0375900^2 + 1595959595959580000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0375900^2 + 159595959595959580000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1624100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0375900^2 + 15959595959595959580000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1624100^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 791)
- $$0374319^2 + 1582000^2 := 1625681^2$$
- $$1020\ 0374319^2 + 159782000^2 := 1020\ 1625681^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0374319^2 + 15979782000^2 := 10203020\ 1625681^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0374319^2 + 1597979782000^2 := 102030403020\ 1625681^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0374319^2 + 159797979782000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1625681^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0374319^2 + 15979797979782000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1625681^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0374319^2 + 1597979797979782000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1625681^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0374319^2 + 159797979797979782000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1625681^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0374319^2 + 159797979797979782000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1625681^2$$
- 792)
- $$0372736^2 + 1584000^2 := 1627264^2$$
- $$1020\ 0372736^2 + 159984000^2 := 1020\ 1627264^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0372736^2 + 15999984000^2 := 10203020\ 1627264^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0372736^2 + 159999984000^2 := 102030403020\ 1627264^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0372736^2 + 1599999984000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1627264^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0372736^2 + 15999999984000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1627264^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0372736^2 + 159999999984000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1627264^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0372736^2 + 1599999999984000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1627264^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0372736^2 + 15999999999984000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1627264^2$$
- 793)
- $$0371151^2 + 1586000^2 := 1628849^2$$
- $$1020\ 0371151^2 + 160186000^2 := 1020\ 1628849^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0371151^2 + 16020186000^2 := 10203020\ 1628849^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0371151^2 + 1602020186000^2 := 102030403020\ 1628849^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0371151^2 + 160202020186000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1628849^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0371151^2 + 16020202020186000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1628849^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0371151^2 + 1602020202020186000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1628849^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0371151^2 + 160202020202020186000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1628849^2$$
- 794)
- $$0369564^2 + 1588000^2 := 1630436^2$$
- $$1020\ 0369564^2 + 160388000^2 := 1020\ 1630436^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0369564^2 + 16040388000^2 := 10203020\ 1630436^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0369564^2 + 1604040388000^2 := 102030403020\ 1630436^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0369564^2 + 160404040388000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1630436^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0369564^2 + 16040404040388000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1630436^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0369564^2 + 1604040404040388000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1630436^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0369564^2 + 160404040404040388000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1630436^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0369564^2 + 16040404040404040388000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1630436^2$$

- 795)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0367975^2 + 1590000^2 & := & 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0367975^2 + 160590000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0367975^2 + 16060590000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0367975^2 + 1606060590000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0367975^2 + 160606060590000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0367975^2 + 16060606060590000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0367975^2 + 1606060606060590000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0367975^2 + 160606060606060590000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1632025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0367975^2 + 16060606060606060590000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1632025^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 796)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0366384^2 + 1592000^2 & := & 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0366384^2 + 160792000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0366384^2 + 16080792000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0366384^2 + 1608080792000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0366384^2 + 160808080792000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0366384^2 + 16080808080792000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0366384^2 + 1608080808080792000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0366384^2 + 160808080808080792000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1633616^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0366384^2 + 16080808080808080792000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1633616^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 797)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0364791^2 + 1594000^2 & := & 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0364791^2 + 160994000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0364791^2 + 16100994000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0364791^2 + 1610100994000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0364791^2 + 161010100994000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0364791^2 + 16101010100994000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0364791^2 + 1610101010100994000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0364791^2 + 161010101010100994000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1635209^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0364791^2 + 16101010101010100994000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1635209^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 798)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0363196^2 + 1596000^2 & := & 1636804^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} \ 0363196^2 + 161196000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} \ 1636804^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} \ 0363196^2 + 16121196000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} \ 1636804^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 0363196^2 + 1612121196000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} \ 1636804^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 0363196^2 + 161212121196000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} \ 1636804^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 0363196^2 + 16121212121196000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \ 1636804^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 0363196^2 + 1612121212121196000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \ 1636804^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 0363196^2 + 161212121212121196000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \ 1636804^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 0363196^2 + 16121212121212121196000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \ 1636804^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 799)
- $$0361599^2 + 1598000^2 := 1638401^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0361599^2 + 161398000^2 := 1020 \ 1638401^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0361599^2 + 16141398000^2 := 10203020 \ 1638401^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0361599^2 + 1614141398000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1638401^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0361599^2 + 161414141398000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1638401^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0361599^2 + 16141414141398000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1638401^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0361599^2 + 1614141414141398000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1638401^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0361599^2 + 161414141414141398000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1638401^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0361599^2 + 16141414141414141398000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1638401^2$$
- 800)
- $$0360000^2 + 1600000^2 := 1640000^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0360000^2 + 161600000^2 := 1020 \ 1640000^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0360000^2 + 16161600000^2 := 10203020 \ 1640000^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0360000^2 + 1616161600000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1640000^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0360000^2 + 161616161600000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1640000^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0360000^2 + 16161616161600000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1640000^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0360000^2 + 1616161616161600000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1640000^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0360000^2 + 161616161616161600000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1640000^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0360000^2 + 16161616161616161600000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1640000^2$$
- 801)
- $$0358399^2 + 1602000^2 := 1641601^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0358399^2 + 161802000^2 := 1020 \ 1641601^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0358399^2 + 16181802000^2 := 10203020 \ 1641601^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0358399^2 + 1618181802000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1641601^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0358399^2 + 161818181802000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1641601^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0358399^2 + 16181818181802000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1641601^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0358399^2 + 1618181818181802000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1641601^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0358399^2 + 161818181818181802000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1641601^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0358399^2 + 16181818181818181802000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1641601^2$$
- 802)
- $$0356796^2 + 1604000^2 := 1643204^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0356796^2 + 162004000^2 := 1020 \ 1643204^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0356796^2 + 16202004000^2 := 10203020 \ 1643204^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0356796^2 + 1620202004000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1643204^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0356796^2 + 162020202004000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1643204^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0356796^2 + 16202020202004000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1643204^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0356796^2 + 1620202020202004000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1643204^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0356796^2 + 162020202020202004000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1643204^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0356796^2 + 16202020202020202004000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1643204^2$$

- 803)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0355191^2 + 1606000^2 & := & 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0355191^2 + 162206000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0355191^2 + 16222206000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0355191^2 + 1622222206000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0355191^2 + 162222222206000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0355191^2 + 16222222222206000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0355191^2 + 1622222222222206000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0355191^2 + 162222222222222206000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1644809^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0355191^2 + 16222222222222222206000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1644809^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 804)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0353584^2 + 1608000^2 & := & 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0353584^2 + 162408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0353584^2 + 16242408000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0353584^2 + 1624242408000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0353584^2 + 162424242408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0353584^2 + 16242424242408000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0353584^2 + 1624242424242408000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0353584^2 + 162424242424242408000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1646416^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0353584^2 + 16242424242424242408000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1646416^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 805)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0351975^2 + 1610000^2 & := & 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0351975^2 + 162610000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0351975^2 + 16262610000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0351975^2 + 1626262610000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0351975^2 + 162626262610000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0351975^2 + 16262626262610000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0351975^2 + 1626262626262610000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0351975^2 + 162626262626262610000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1648025^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0351975^2 + 16262626262626262610000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1648025^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 806)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0350364^2 + 1612000^2 & := & 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0350364^2 + 162812000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0350364^2 + 16282812000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0350364^2 + 1628282812000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0350364^2 + 162828282812000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0350364^2 + 16282828282812000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0350364^2 + 1628282828282812000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0350364^2 + 162828282828282812000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1649636^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0350364^2 + 16282828282828282812000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1649636^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 807)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0348751^2 + 1614000^2$ | $:= 1651249^2$ |
| $1020\ 0348751^2 + 163014000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1651249^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0348751^2 + 16303014000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1651249^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0348751^2 + 1630303014000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1651249^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0348751^2 + 163030303014000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1651249^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0348751^2 + 16303030303014000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1651249^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0348751^2 + 1630303030303014000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1651249^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0348751^2 + 163030303030303014000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1651249^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0348751^2 + 16303030303030303014000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1651249^2$ |
- 808)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0347136^2 + 1616000^2$ | $:= 1652864^2$ |
| $1020\ 0347136^2 + 163216000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1652864^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0347136^2 + 16323216000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1652864^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0347136^2 + 1632323216000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1652864^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0347136^2 + 163232323216000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1652864^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0347136^2 + 16323232323216000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1652864^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0347136^2 + 1632323232323216000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1652864^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0347136^2 + 163232323232323216000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1652864^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0347136^2 + 16323232323232323216000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1652864^2$ |
- 809)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0345519^2 + 1618000^2$ | $:= 1654481^2$ |
| $1020\ 0345519^2 + 163418000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1654481^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0345519^2 + 16343418000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1654481^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0345519^2 + 1634343418000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1654481^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0345519^2 + 163434343418000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1654481^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0345519^2 + 16343434343418000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1654481^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0345519^2 + 1634343434343418000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1654481^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0345519^2 + 163434343434343418000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1654481^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0345519^2 + 16343434343434343418000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1654481^2$ |
- 810)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0343900^2 + 1620000^2$ | $:= 1656100^2$ |
| $1020\ 0343900^2 + 163620000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1656100^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0343900^2 + 16363620000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1656100^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0343900^2 + 1636363620000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1656100^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0343900^2 + 163636363620000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1656100^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0343900^2 + 16363636363620000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1656100^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0343900^2 + 1636363636363620000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1656100^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0343900^2 + 163636363636363620000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1656100^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0343900^2 + 16363636363636363620000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1656100^2$ |

- 811)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0342279^2 + 1622000^2 && := 1657721^2 \\
 &1020\ 0342279^2 + 163822000^2 && := 1020\ 1657721^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0342279^2 + 16383822000^2 && := 10203020\ 1657721^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0342279^2 + 1638383822000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1657721^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0342279^2 + 163838383822000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1657721^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0342279^2 + 16383838383822000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1657721^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0342279^2 + 1638383838383822000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1657721^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0342279^2 + 163838383838383822000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1657721^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0342279^2 + 16383838383838383822000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1657721^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 812)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0340656^2 + 1624000^2 && := 1659344^2 \\
 &1020\ 0340656^2 + 164024000^2 && := 1020\ 1659344^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0340656^2 + 16404024000^2 && := 10203020\ 1659344^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0340656^2 + 1640404024000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1659344^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0340656^2 + 164040404024000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1659344^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0340656^2 + 16404040404024000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1659344^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0340656^2 + 1640404040404024000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1659344^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0340656^2 + 164040404040404024000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1659344^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0340656^2 + 16404040404040404024000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1659344^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 813)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0339031^2 + 1626000^2 && := 1660969^2 \\
 &1020\ 0339031^2 + 164226000^2 && := 1020\ 1660969^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0339031^2 + 16424226000^2 && := 10203020\ 1660969^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0339031^2 + 1642424226000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1660969^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0339031^2 + 164242424226000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1660969^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0339031^2 + 16424242424226000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1660969^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0339031^2 + 1642424242424226000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1660969^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0339031^2 + 164242424242424226000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1660969^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0339031^2 + 164242424242424226000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1660969^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 814)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0337404^2 + 1628000^2 && := 1662596^2 \\
 &1020\ 0337404^2 + 164428000^2 && := 1020\ 1662596^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0337404^2 + 16444428000^2 && := 10203020\ 1662596^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0337404^2 + 1644444428000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1662596^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0337404^2 + 164444444428000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1662596^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0337404^2 + 16444444444428000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1662596^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0337404^2 + 1644444444444428000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1662596^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0337404^2 + 164444444444444428000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1662596^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0337404^2 + 16444444444444444428000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1662596^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 815)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0335775^2 + 1630000^2$ | $:= 1664225^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0335775^2 + 164630000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1664225^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0335775^2 + 16464630000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1664225^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0335775^2 + 1646464630000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1664225^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0335775^2 + 164646464630000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1664225^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0335775^2 + 16464646464630000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1664225^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0335775^2 + 1646464646464630000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1664225^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0335775^2 + 164646464646464630000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1664225^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0335775^2 + 16464646464646464630000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1664225^2$ |
- 816)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0334144^2 + 1632000^2$ | $:= 1665856^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0334144^2 + 164832000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1665856^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0334144^2 + 16484832000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1665856^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0334144^2 + 1648484832000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1665856^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0334144^2 + 164848484832000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1665856^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0334144^2 + 16484848484832000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1665856^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0334144^2 + 1648484848484832000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1665856^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0334144^2 + 164848484848484832000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1665856^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0334144^2 + 16484848484848484832000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1665856^2$ |
- 817)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0332511^2 + 1634000^2$ | $:= 1667489^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0332511^2 + 165034000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1667489^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0332511^2 + 16505034000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1667489^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0332511^2 + 1650505034000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1667489^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0332511^2 + 165050505034000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1667489^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0332511^2 + 16505050505034000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1667489^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0332511^2 + 1650505050505034000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1667489^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0332511^2 + 165050505050505034000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1667489^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0332511^2 + 16505050505050505034000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1667489^2$ |
- 818)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0330876^2 + 1636000^2$ | $:= 1669124^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0330876^2 + 165236000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1669124^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0330876^2 + 16525236000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1669124^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0330876^2 + 1652525236000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1669124^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0330876^2 + 165252525236000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1669124^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0330876^2 + 16525252525236000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1669124^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0330876^2 + 1652525252525236000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1669124^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0330876^2 + 165252525252525236000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1669124^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0330876^2 + 16525252525252525236000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1669124^2$ |

- 819)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0329239^2 + 1638000^2 && := 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0329239^2 + 165438000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0329239^2 + 16545438000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0329239^2 + 1654545438000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0329239^2 + 165454545438000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0329239^2 + 16545454545438000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0329239^2 + 1654545454545438000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0329239^2 + 165454545454545438000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1670761^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0329239^2 + 16545454545454545438000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1670761^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 820)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0327600^2 + 1640000^2 && := 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0327600^2 + 165640000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0327600^2 + 16565640000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0327600^2 + 1656565640000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0327600^2 + 165656565640000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0327600^2 + 16565656565640000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0327600^2 + 1656565656565640000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0327600^2 + 165656565656565640000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1672400^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0327600^2 + 16565656565656565640000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1672400^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 821)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0325959^2 + 1642000^2 && := 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0325959^2 + 165842000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0325959^2 + 16585842000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0325959^2 + 1658585842000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0325959^2 + 165858585842000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0325959^2 + 16585858585842000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0325959^2 + 1658585858585842000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0325959^2 + 165858585858585842000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1674041^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0325959^2 + 16585858585858585842000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1674041^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 822)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0324316^2 + 1644000^2 && := 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0324316^2 + 166044000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0324316^2 + 16606044000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0324316^2 + 1660606044000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0324316^2 + 166060606044000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0324316^2 + 16606060606044000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0324316^2 + 1660606060606044000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0324316^2 + 166060606060606044000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1675684^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0324316^2 + 16606060606060606044000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1675684^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 823)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0322671^2 + 1646000^2 && := 1677329^2 \\
 &1020\ 0322671^2 + 166246000^2 && := 1020\ 1677329^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0322671^2 + 16626246000^2 && := 10203020\ 1677329^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0322671^2 + 1662626246000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1677329^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0322671^2 + 166262626246000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1677329^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0322671^2 + 16626262626246000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1677329^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0322671^2 + 1662626262626246000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1677329^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0322671^2 + 1662626262626246000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1677329^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0322671^2 + 166262626262626246000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1677329^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 824)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0321024^2 + 1648000^2 && := 1678976^2 \\
 &1020\ 0321024^2 + 166448000^2 && := 1020\ 1678976^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0321024^2 + 16646448000^2 && := 10203020\ 1678976^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0321024^2 + 1664646448000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1678976^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0321024^2 + 166464646448000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1678976^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0321024^2 + 16646464646448000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1678976^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0321024^2 + 1664646464646448000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1678976^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0321024^2 + 1664646464646448000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1678976^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0321024^2 + 166464646464646448000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1678976^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 825)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0319375^2 + 1650000^2 && := 1680625^2 \\
 &1020\ 0319375^2 + 166650000^2 && := 1020\ 1680625^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0319375^2 + 16666650000^2 && := 10203020\ 1680625^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0319375^2 + 1666666650000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1680625^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0319375^2 + 166666666650000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1680625^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0319375^2 + 16666666666650000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1680625^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0319375^2 + 1666666666666650000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1680625^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0319375^2 + 166666666666666650000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1680625^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0319375^2 + 16666666666666666650000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1680625^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 826)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0317724^2 + 1652000^2 && := 1682276^2 \\
 &1020\ 0317724^2 + 166852000^2 && := 1020\ 1682276^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0317724^2 + 16686852000^2 && := 10203020\ 1682276^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0317724^2 + 1668686852000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1682276^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0317724^2 + 166868686852000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1682276^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0317724^2 + 16686868686852000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1682276^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0317724^2 + 1668686868686852000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1682276^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0317724^2 + 1668686868686852000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1682276^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0317724^2 + 166868686868686852000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1682276^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 827)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0316071^2 + 1654000^2 && := 1683929^2 \\
 &1020\ 0316071^2 + 167054000^2 && := 1020\ 1683929^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0316071^2 + 16707054000^2 && := 10203020\ 1683929^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0316071^2 + 1670707054000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1683929^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0316071^2 + 167070707054000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1683929^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0316071^2 + 16707070707054000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1683929^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0316071^2 + 1670707070707054000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1683929^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0316071^2 + 167070707070707054000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1683929^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0316071^2 + 16707070707070707054000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1683929^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 828)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0314416^2 + 1656000^2 && := 1685584^2 \\
 &1020\ 0314416^2 + 167256000^2 && := 1020\ 1685584^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0314416^2 + 16727256000^2 && := 10203020\ 1685584^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0314416^2 + 1672727256000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1685584^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0314416^2 + 167272727256000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1685584^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0314416^2 + 16727272727256000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1685584^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0314416^2 + 1672727272727256000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1685584^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0314416^2 + 167272727272727256000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1685584^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0314416^2 + 167272727272727256000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1685584^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 829)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0312759^2 + 1658000^2 && := 1687241^2 \\
 &1020\ 0312759^2 + 167458000^2 && := 1020\ 1687241^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0312759^2 + 16747458000^2 && := 10203020\ 1687241^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0312759^2 + 1674747458000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1687241^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0312759^2 + 167474747458000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1687241^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0312759^2 + 16747474747458000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1687241^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0312759^2 + 1674747474747458000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1687241^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0312759^2 + 167474747474747458000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1687241^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0312759^2 + 16747474747474747458000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1687241^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 830)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0311100^2 + 1660000^2 && := 1688900^2 \\
 &1020\ 0311100^2 + 167660000^2 && := 1020\ 1688900^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0311100^2 + 16767660000^2 && := 10203020\ 1688900^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0311100^2 + 1676767660000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1688900^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0311100^2 + 167676767660000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1688900^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0311100^2 + 16767676767660000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1688900^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0311100^2 + 1676767676767660000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1688900^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0311100^2 + 167676767676767660000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1688900^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0311100^2 + 16767676767676767660000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1688900^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 831)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0309439^2 + 1662000^2 && := 1690561^2 \\
 &1020\ 0309439^2 + 167862000^2 && := 1020\ 1690561^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0309439^2 + 16787862000^2 && := 10203020\ 1690561^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0309439^2 + 1678787862000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1690561^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0309439^2 + 167878787862000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1690561^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0309439^2 + 16787878787862000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1690561^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0309439^2 + 1678787878787862000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1690561^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0309439^2 + 167878787878787862000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1690561^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0309439^2 + 16787878787878787862000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1690561^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 832)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0307776^2 + 1664000^2 && := 1692224^2 \\
 &1020\ 0307776^2 + 168064000^2 && := 1020\ 1692224^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0307776^2 + 16808064000^2 && := 10203020\ 1692224^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0307776^2 + 1680808064000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1692224^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0307776^2 + 168080808064000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1692224^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0307776^2 + 16808080808064000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1692224^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0307776^2 + 1680808080808064000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1692224^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0307776^2 + 168080808080808064000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1692224^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0307776^2 + 16808080808080808064000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1692224^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 833)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0306111^2 + 1666000^2 && := 1693889^2 \\
 &1020\ 0306111^2 + 168266000^2 && := 1020\ 1693889^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0306111^2 + 16828266000^2 && := 10203020\ 1693889^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0306111^2 + 1682828266000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1693889^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0306111^2 + 168282828266000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1693889^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0306111^2 + 16828282828266000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1693889^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0306111^2 + 1682828282828266000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1693889^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0306111^2 + 168282828282828266000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1693889^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0306111^2 + 168282828282828266000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1693889^2
 \end{aligned}$$
- 834)
- $$\begin{aligned}
 &0304444^2 + 1668000^2 && := 1695556^2 \\
 &1020\ 0304444^2 + 168468000^2 && := 1020\ 1695556^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0304444^2 + 16848468000^2 && := 10203020\ 1695556^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0304444^2 + 1684848468000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1695556^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0304444^2 + 168484848468000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1695556^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0304444^2 + 16848484848468000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1695556^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0304444^2 + 1684848484848468000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1695556^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0304444^2 + 168484848484848468000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1695556^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0304444^2 + 16848484848484848468000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1695556^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- 835)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0302775^2 + 1670000^2 && := 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0302775^2 + 168670000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0302775^2 + 16868670000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0302775^2 + 1686868670000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0302775^2 + 168686868670000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0302775^2 + 16868686868670000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0302775^2 + 1686868686868670000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0302775^2 + 168686868686868670000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1697225^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0302775^2 + 16868686868686868670000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1697225^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 836)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0301104^2 + 1672000^2 && := 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0301104^2 + 168872000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0301104^2 + 16888872000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0301104^2 + 1688888872000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0301104^2 + 168888888872000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0301104^2 + 16888888888872000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0301104^2 + 1688888888888872000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0301104^2 + 168888888888888872000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1698896^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0301104^2 + 16888888888888888872000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1698896^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 837)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0299431^2 + 1674000^2 && := 1700569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0299431^2 + 169074000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1700569^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0299431^2 + 16909074000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1700569^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0299431^2 + 1690909074000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1700569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0299431^2 + 169090909074000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1700569^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0299431^2 + 16909090909074000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1700569^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0299431^2 + 1690909090909074000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1700569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0299431^2 + 169090909090909074000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1700569^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0299431^2 + 16909090909090909074000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1700569^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 838)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0297756^2 + 1676000^2 && := 1702244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0297756^2 + 169276000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1702244^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0297756^2 + 16929276000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1702244^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0297756^2 + 1692929276000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1702244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0297756^2 + 169292929276000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1702244^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0297756^2 + 16929292929276000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1702244^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0297756^2 + 1692929292929276000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1702244^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0297756^2 + 169292929292929276000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1702244^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0297756^2 + 16929292929292929276000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1702244^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 839)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0296079^2 + 1678000^2 && := 1703921^2 \\ &1020\ 0296079^2 + 169478000^2 && := 1020\ 1703921^2 \\ &10203020\ 0296079^2 + 16949478000^2 && := 10203020\ 1703921^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0296079^2 + 1694949478000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1703921^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0296079^2 + 169494949478000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1703921^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0296079^2 + 16949494949478000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1703921^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0296079^2 + 1694949494949478000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1703921^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0296079^2 + 169494949494949478000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1703921^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0296079^2 + 16949494949494949478000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1703921^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 840)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0294400^2 + 1680000^2 && := 1705600^2 \\ &1020\ 0294400^2 + 169680000^2 && := 1020\ 1705600^2 \\ &10203020\ 0294400^2 + 16969680000^2 && := 10203020\ 1705600^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0294400^2 + 1696969680000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1705600^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0294400^2 + 169696969680000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1705600^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0294400^2 + 16969696969680000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1705600^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0294400^2 + 1696969696969680000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1705600^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0294400^2 + 169696969696969680000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1705600^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0294400^2 + 16969696969696969680000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1705600^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 841)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0292719^2 + 1682000^2 && := 1707281^2 \\ &1020\ 0292719^2 + 169882000^2 && := 1020\ 1707281^2 \\ &10203020\ 0292719^2 + 16989882000^2 && := 10203020\ 1707281^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0292719^2 + 1698989882000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1707281^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0292719^2 + 169898989882000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1707281^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0292719^2 + 16989898989882000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1707281^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0292719^2 + 1698989898989882000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1707281^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0292719^2 + 169898989898989882000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1707281^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0292719^2 + 16989898989898989882000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1707281^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 842)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0291036^2 + 1684000^2 && := 1708964^2 \\ &1020\ 0291036^2 + 170084000^2 && := 1020\ 1708964^2 \\ &10203020\ 0291036^2 + 17010084000^2 && := 10203020\ 1708964^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0291036^2 + 1701010084000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1708964^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0291036^2 + 170101010084000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1708964^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0291036^2 + 17010101010084000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1708964^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0291036^2 + 1701010101010084000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1708964^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0291036^2 + 170101010101010084000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1708964^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0291036^2 + 17010101010101010084000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1708964^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 843)
- $$0289351^2 + 1686000^2 := 1710649^2$$
- $$1020\ 0289351^2 + 170286000^2 := 1020\ 1710649^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0289351^2 + 17030286000^2 := 10203020\ 1710649^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0289351^2 + 1703030286000^2 := 102030403020\ 1710649^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0289351^2 + 170303030286000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1710649^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0289351^2 + 17030303030286000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1710649^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0289351^2 + 1703030303030286000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1710649^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0289351^2 + 170303030303030286000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1710649^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0289351^2 + 17030303030303030286000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1710649^2$$
- 844)
- $$0287664^2 + 1688000^2 := 1712336^2$$
- $$1020\ 0287664^2 + 170488000^2 := 1020\ 1712336^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0287664^2 + 17050488000^2 := 10203020\ 1712336^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0287664^2 + 1705050488000^2 := 102030403020\ 1712336^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0287664^2 + 170505050488000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1712336^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0287664^2 + 17050505050488000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1712336^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0287664^2 + 1705050505050488000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1712336^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0287664^2 + 170505050505050488000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1712336^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0287664^2 + 17050505050505050488000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1712336^2$$
- 845)
- $$0285975^2 + 1690000^2 := 1714025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0285975^2 + 170690000^2 := 1020\ 1714025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0285975^2 + 17070690000^2 := 10203020\ 1714025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0285975^2 + 1707070690000^2 := 102030403020\ 1714025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0285975^2 + 170707070690000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1714025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0285975^2 + 17070707070690000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1714025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0285975^2 + 1707070707070690000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1714025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0285975^2 + 170707070707070690000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1714025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0285975^2 + 17070707070707070690000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1714025^2$$
- 846)
- $$0284284^2 + 1692000^2 := 1715716^2$$
- $$1020\ 0284284^2 + 170892000^2 := 1020\ 1715716^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0284284^2 + 17090892000^2 := 10203020\ 1715716^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0284284^2 + 1709090892000^2 := 102030403020\ 1715716^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0284284^2 + 170909090892000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1715716^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0284284^2 + 17090909090892000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1715716^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0284284^2 + 1709090909090892000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1715716^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0284284^2 + 170909090909090892000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1715716^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0284284^2 + 17090909090909090892000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1715716^2$$

- 847)
- $$0282591^2 + 1694000^2 := 1717409^2$$
- $$1020\ 0282591^2 + 171094000^2 := 1020\ 1717409^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0282591^2 + 17111094000^2 := 10203020\ 1717409^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0282591^2 + 1711111094000^2 := 102030403020\ 1717409^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0282591^2 + 171111111094000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1717409^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0282591^2 + 17111111111094000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1717409^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0282591^2 + 1711111111111094000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1717409^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0282591^2 + 171111111111111094000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1717409^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0282591^2 + 17111111111111111094000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1717409^2$$
- 848)
- $$0280896^2 + 1696000^2 := 1719104^2$$
- $$1020\ 0280896^2 + 171296000^2 := 1020\ 1719104^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0280896^2 + 17131296000^2 := 10203020\ 1719104^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0280896^2 + 1713131296000^2 := 102030403020\ 1719104^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0280896^2 + 171313131296000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1719104^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0280896^2 + 17131313131296000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1719104^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0280896^2 + 1713131313131296000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1719104^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0280896^2 + 171313131313131296000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1719104^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0280896^2 + 17131313131313131296000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1719104^2$$
- 849)
- $$0279199^2 + 1698000^2 := 1720801^2$$
- $$1020\ 0279199^2 + 171498000^2 := 1020\ 1720801^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0279199^2 + 17151498000^2 := 10203020\ 1720801^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0279199^2 + 1715151498000^2 := 102030403020\ 1720801^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0279199^2 + 171515151498000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1720801^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0279199^2 + 17151515151498000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1720801^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0279199^2 + 1715151515151498000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1720801^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0279199^2 + 171515151515151498000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1720801^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0279199^2 + 17151515151515151498000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1720801^2$$
- 850)
- $$0277500^2 + 1700000^2 := 1722500^2$$
- $$1020\ 0277500^2 + 171700000^2 := 1020\ 1722500^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0277500^2 + 17171700000^2 := 10203020\ 1722500^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0277500^2 + 1717171700000^2 := 102030403020\ 1722500^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0277500^2 + 171717171700000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1722500^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0277500^2 + 17171717171700000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1722500^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0277500^2 + 1717171717171700000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1722500^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0277500^2 + 171717171717171700000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1722500^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0277500^2 + 17171717171717171700000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1722500^2$$

- 851)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0275799^2 + 1702000^2 && := 1724201^2 \\ &1020\ 0275799^2 + 171902000^2 && := 1020\ 1724201^2 \\ &10203020\ 0275799^2 + 17191902000^2 && := 10203020\ 1724201^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0275799^2 + 1719191902000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1724201^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0275799^2 + 171919191902000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1724201^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0275799^2 + 17191919191902000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1724201^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0275799^2 + 1719191919191902000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1724201^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0275799^2 + 171919191919191902000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1724201^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0275799^2 + 17191919191919191902000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1724201^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 852)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0274096^2 + 1704000^2 && := 1725904^2 \\ &1020\ 0274096^2 + 172104000^2 && := 1020\ 1725904^2 \\ &10203020\ 0274096^2 + 17212104000^2 && := 10203020\ 1725904^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0274096^2 + 1721212104000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1725904^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0274096^2 + 172121212104000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1725904^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0274096^2 + 17212121212104000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1725904^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0274096^2 + 1721212121212104000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1725904^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0274096^2 + 172121212121212104000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1725904^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0274096^2 + 17212121212121212104000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1725904^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 853)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0272391^2 + 1706000^2 && := 1727609^2 \\ &1020\ 0272391^2 + 172306000^2 && := 1020\ 1727609^2 \\ &10203020\ 0272391^2 + 17232306000^2 && := 10203020\ 1727609^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0272391^2 + 1723232306000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1727609^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0272391^2 + 172323232306000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1727609^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0272391^2 + 17232323232306000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1727609^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0272391^2 + 1723232323232306000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1727609^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0272391^2 + 172323232323232306000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1727609^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0272391^2 + 17232323232323232306000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1727609^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 854)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0270684^2 + 1708000^2 && := 1729316^2 \\ &1020\ 0270684^2 + 172508000^2 && := 1020\ 1729316^2 \\ &10203020\ 0270684^2 + 17252508000^2 && := 10203020\ 1729316^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0270684^2 + 1725252508000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1729316^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0270684^2 + 172525252508000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1729316^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0270684^2 + 17252525252508000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1729316^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0270684^2 + 1725252525252508000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1729316^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0270684^2 + 172525252525252508000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1729316^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0270684^2 + 17252525252525252508000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1729316^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 855)
- $$0268975^2 + 1710000^2 := 1731025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0268975^2 + 172710000^2 := 1020\ 1731025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0268975^2 + 17272710000^2 := 10203020\ 1731025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0268975^2 + 1727272710000^2 := 102030403020\ 1731025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0268975^2 + 172727272710000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1731025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0268975^2 + 17272727272710000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1731025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0268975^2 + 1727272727272710000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1731025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0268975^2 + 172727272727272710000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1731025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0268975^2 + 17272727272727272710000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1731025^2$$
- 856)
- $$0267264^2 + 1712000^2 := 1732736^2$$
- $$1020\ 0267264^2 + 172912000^2 := 1020\ 1732736^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0267264^2 + 17292912000^2 := 10203020\ 1732736^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0267264^2 + 1729292912000^2 := 102030403020\ 1732736^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0267264^2 + 172929292912000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1732736^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0267264^2 + 17292929292912000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1732736^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0267264^2 + 1729292929292912000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1732736^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0267264^2 + 172929292929292912000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1732736^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0267264^2 + 17292929292929292912000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1732736^2$$
- 857)
- $$0265551^2 + 1714000^2 := 1734449^2$$
- $$1020\ 0265551^2 + 173114000^2 := 1020\ 1734449^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0265551^2 + 17313114000^2 := 10203020\ 1734449^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0265551^2 + 1731313114000^2 := 102030403020\ 1734449^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0265551^2 + 173131313114000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1734449^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0265551^2 + 17313131313114000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1734449^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0265551^2 + 1731313131313114000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1734449^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0265551^2 + 173131313131313114000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1734449^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0265551^2 + 17313131313131313114000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1734449^2$$
- 858)
- $$0263836^2 + 1716000^2 := 1736164^2$$
- $$1020\ 0263836^2 + 173316000^2 := 1020\ 1736164^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0263836^2 + 17333316000^2 := 10203020\ 1736164^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0263836^2 + 1733333316000^2 := 102030403020\ 1736164^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0263836^2 + 173333333316000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1736164^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0263836^2 + 17333333333316000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1736164^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0263836^2 + 1733333333333316000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1736164^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0263836^2 + 173333333333333316000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1736164^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0263836^2 + 17333333333333333316000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1736164^2$$

- 859)
- $$0262119^2 + 1718000^2 := 1737881^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0262119^2 + 173518000^2 := 1020 \ 1737881^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0262119^2 + 17353518000^2 := 10203020 \ 1737881^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0262119^2 + 1735353518000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1737881^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0262119^2 + 173535353518000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1737881^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0262119^2 + 17353535353518000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1737881^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0262119^2 + 1735353535353518000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1737881^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0262119^2 + 173535353535353518000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1737881^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0262119^2 + 17353535353535353518000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1737881^2$$
- 860)
- $$0260400^2 + 1720000^2 := 1739600^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0260400^2 + 173720000^2 := 1020 \ 1739600^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0260400^2 + 17373720000^2 := 10203020 \ 1739600^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0260400^2 + 1737373720000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1739600^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0260400^2 + 173737373720000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1739600^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0260400^2 + 17373737373720000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1739600^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0260400^2 + 1737373737373720000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1739600^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0260400^2 + 173737373737373720000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1739600^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0260400^2 + 17373737373737373720000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1739600^2$$
- 861)
- $$0258679^2 + 1722000^2 := 1741321^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0258679^2 + 173922000^2 := 1020 \ 1741321^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0258679^2 + 17393922000^2 := 10203020 \ 1741321^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0258679^2 + 1739393922000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1741321^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0258679^2 + 173939393922000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1741321^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0258679^2 + 17393939393922000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1741321^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0258679^2 + 1739393939393922000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1741321^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0258679^2 + 173939393939393922000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1741321^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0258679^2 + 17393939393939393922000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1741321^2$$
- 862)
- $$0256956^2 + 1724000^2 := 1743044^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0256956^2 + 174124000^2 := 1020 \ 1743044^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0256956^2 + 17414124000^2 := 10203020 \ 1743044^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0256956^2 + 1741414124000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1743044^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0256956^2 + 174141414124000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1743044^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0256956^2 + 17414141414124000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1743044^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0256956^2 + 1741414141414124000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1743044^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0256956^2 + 174141414141414124000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1743044^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0256956^2 + 17414141414141414124000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1743044^2$$

- 863)
- $$0255231^2 + 1726000^2 := 1744769^2$$
- $$1020 0255231^2 + 174326000^2 := 1020 1744769^2$$
- $$10203020 0255231^2 + 17434326000^2 := 10203020 1744769^2$$
- $$102030403020 0255231^2 + 1743434326000^2 := 102030403020 1744769^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0255231^2 + 174343434326000^2 := 1020304050403020 1744769^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0255231^2 + 17434343434326000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1744769^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0255231^2 + 1743434343434326000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1744769^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0255231^2 + 174343434343434326000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1744769^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0255231^2 + 17434343434343434326000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1744769^2$$
- 864)
- $$0253504^2 + 1728000^2 := 1746496^2$$
- $$1020 0253504^2 + 174528000^2 := 1020 1746496^2$$
- $$10203020 0253504^2 + 17454528000^2 := 10203020 1746496^2$$
- $$102030403020 0253504^2 + 1745454528000^2 := 102030403020 1746496^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0253504^2 + 174545454528000^2 := 1020304050403020 1746496^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0253504^2 + 17454545454528000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1746496^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0253504^2 + 1745454545454528000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1746496^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0253504^2 + 174545454545454528000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1746496^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0253504^2 + 17454545454545454528000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1746496^2$$
- 865)
- $$0251775^2 + 1730000^2 := 1748225^2$$
- $$1020 0251775^2 + 174730000^2 := 1020 1748225^2$$
- $$10203020 0251775^2 + 17474730000^2 := 10203020 1748225^2$$
- $$102030403020 0251775^2 + 1747474730000^2 := 102030403020 1748225^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0251775^2 + 174747474730000^2 := 1020304050403020 1748225^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0251775^2 + 17474747474730000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1748225^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0251775^2 + 1747474747474730000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1748225^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0251775^2 + 174747474747474730000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1748225^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0251775^2 + 17474747474747474730000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1748225^2$$
- 866)
- $$0250044^2 + 1732000^2 := 1749956^2$$
- $$1020 0250044^2 + 174932000^2 := 1020 1749956^2$$
- $$10203020 0250044^2 + 17494932000^2 := 10203020 1749956^2$$
- $$102030403020 0250044^2 + 1749494932000^2 := 102030403020 1749956^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0250044^2 + 174949494932000^2 := 1020304050403020 1749956^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0250044^2 + 17494949494932000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1749956^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0250044^2 + 1749494949494932000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1749956^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0250044^2 + 174949494949494932000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1749956^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0250044^2 + 17494949494949494932000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1749956^2$$

- 867)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0248311^2 + 1734000^2 && := 1751689^2 \\ &1020\ 0248311^2 + 175134000^2 && := 1020\ 1751689^2 \\ &10203020\ 0248311^2 + 17515134000^2 && := 10203020\ 1751689^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0248311^2 + 1751515134000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1751689^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0248311^2 + 175151515134000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1751689^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0248311^2 + 17515151515134000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1751689^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0248311^2 + 1751515151515134000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1751689^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0248311^2 + 175151515151515134000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1751689^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0248311^2 + 17515151515151515134000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1751689^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 868)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0246576^2 + 1736000^2 && := 1753424^2 \\ &1020\ 0246576^2 + 175336000^2 && := 1020\ 1753424^2 \\ &10203020\ 0246576^2 + 17535336000^2 && := 10203020\ 1753424^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0246576^2 + 1753535336000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1753424^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0246576^2 + 175353535336000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1753424^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0246576^2 + 17535353535336000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1753424^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0246576^2 + 1753535353535336000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1753424^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0246576^2 + 175353535353535336000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1753424^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0246576^2 + 17535353535353535336000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1753424^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 869)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0244839^2 + 1738000^2 && := 1755161^2 \\ &1020\ 0244839^2 + 175538000^2 && := 1020\ 1755161^2 \\ &10203020\ 0244839^2 + 17555538000^2 && := 10203020\ 1755161^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0244839^2 + 1755555538000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1755161^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0244839^2 + 175555555538000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1755161^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0244839^2 + 17555555555538000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1755161^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0244839^2 + 1755555555555538000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1755161^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0244839^2 + 175555555555555538000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1755161^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0244839^2 + 17555555555555555538000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1755161^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 870)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0243100^2 + 1740000^2 && := 1756900^2 \\ &1020\ 0243100^2 + 175740000^2 && := 1020\ 1756900^2 \\ &10203020\ 0243100^2 + 17575740000^2 && := 10203020\ 1756900^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0243100^2 + 1757575740000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1756900^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0243100^2 + 175757575740000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1756900^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0243100^2 + 17575757575740000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1756900^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0243100^2 + 1757575757575740000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1756900^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0243100^2 + 175757575757575740000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1756900^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0243100^2 + 17575757575757575740000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1756900^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 871)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0241359^2 + 1742000^2 && := 1758641^2 \\ &1020\ 0241359^2 + 175942000^2 && := 1020\ 1758641^2 \\ &10203020\ 0241359^2 + 17595942000^2 && := 10203020\ 1758641^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0241359^2 + 1759595942000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1758641^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0241359^2 + 175959595942000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1758641^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0241359^2 + 17595959595942000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1758641^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0241359^2 + 1759595959595942000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1758641^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0241359^2 + 175959595959595942000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1758641^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0241359^2 + 175959595959595942000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1758641^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 872)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0239616^2 + 1744000^2 && := 1760384^2 \\ &1020\ 0239616^2 + 176144000^2 && := 1020\ 1760384^2 \\ &10203020\ 0239616^2 + 17616144000^2 && := 10203020\ 1760384^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0239616^2 + 1761616144000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1760384^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0239616^2 + 176161616144000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1760384^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0239616^2 + 17616161616144000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1760384^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0239616^2 + 1761616161616144000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1760384^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0239616^2 + 176161616161616144000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1760384^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0239616^2 + 176161616161616144000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1760384^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 873)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0237871^2 + 1746000^2 && := 1762129^2 \\ &1020\ 0237871^2 + 176346000^2 && := 1020\ 1762129^2 \\ &10203020\ 0237871^2 + 17636346000^2 && := 10203020\ 1762129^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0237871^2 + 1763636346000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1762129^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0237871^2 + 176363636346000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1762129^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0237871^2 + 17636363636346000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1762129^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0237871^2 + 1763636363636346000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1762129^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0237871^2 + 176363636363636346000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1762129^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0237871^2 + 176363636363636346000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1762129^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 874)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0236124^2 + 1748000^2 && := 1763876^2 \\ &1020\ 0236124^2 + 176548000^2 && := 1020\ 1763876^2 \\ &10203020\ 0236124^2 + 17656548000^2 && := 10203020\ 1763876^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0236124^2 + 1765656548000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1763876^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0236124^2 + 176565656548000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1763876^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0236124^2 + 17656565656548000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1763876^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0236124^2 + 1765656565656548000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1763876^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0236124^2 + 176565656565656548000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1763876^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0236124^2 + 176565656565656548000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1763876^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 875)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0234375^2 + 1750000^2$ | $:= 1765625^2$ |
| $1020 0234375^2 + 176750000^2$ | $:= 1020 1765625^2$ |
| $10203020 0234375^2 + 17676750000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1765625^2$ |
| $102030403020 0234375^2 + 1767676750000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1765625^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0234375^2 + 176767676750000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1765625^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0234375^2 + 17676767676750000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1765625^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0234375^2 + 1767676767676750000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1765625^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0234375^2 + 176767676767676750000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1765625^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0234375^2 + 17676767676767676750000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1765625^2$ |
- 876)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0232624^2 + 1752000^2$ | $:= 1767376^2$ |
| $1020 0232624^2 + 176952000^2$ | $:= 1020 1767376^2$ |
| $10203020 0232624^2 + 17696952000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1767376^2$ |
| $102030403020 0232624^2 + 1769696952000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1767376^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0232624^2 + 176969696952000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1767376^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0232624^2 + 17696969696952000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1767376^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0232624^2 + 1769696969696952000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1767376^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0232624^2 + 176969696969696952000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1767376^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0232624^2 + 17696969696969696952000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1767376^2$ |
- 877)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0230871^2 + 1754000^2$ | $:= 1769129^2$ |
| $1020 0230871^2 + 177154000^2$ | $:= 1020 1769129^2$ |
| $10203020 0230871^2 + 17717154000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1769129^2$ |
| $102030403020 0230871^2 + 1771717154000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1769129^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0230871^2 + 177171717154000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1769129^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0230871^2 + 17717171717154000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1769129^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0230871^2 + 1771717171717154000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1769129^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0230871^2 + 177171717171717154000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1769129^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0230871^2 + 17717171717171717154000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1769129^2$ |
- 878)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0229116^2 + 1756000^2$ | $:= 1770884^2$ |
| $1020 0229116^2 + 177356000^2$ | $:= 1020 1770884^2$ |
| $10203020 0229116^2 + 17737356000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1770884^2$ |
| $102030403020 0229116^2 + 1773737356000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1770884^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0229116^2 + 177373737356000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1770884^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0229116^2 + 17737373737356000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1770884^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0229116^2 + 1773737373737356000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1770884^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0229116^2 + 177373737373737356000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1770884^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0229116^2 + 17737373737373737356000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1770884^2$ |

- 879)
- $$0227359^2 + 1758000^2 := 1772641^2$$
- $$1020 0227359^2 + 177558000^2 := 1020 1772641^2$$
- $$10203020 0227359^2 + 17757558000^2 := 10203020 1772641^2$$
- $$102030403020 0227359^2 + 1775757558000^2 := 102030403020 1772641^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0227359^2 + 177575757558000^2 := 1020304050403020 1772641^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0227359^2 + 17757575757558000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1772641^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0227359^2 + 1775757575757558000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1772641^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0227359^2 + 177575757575757558000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1772641^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0227359^2 + 17757575757575757558000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1772641^2$$
- 880)
- $$0225600^2 + 1760000^2 := 1774400^2$$
- $$1020 0225600^2 + 177760000^2 := 1020 1774400^2$$
- $$10203020 0225600^2 + 17777760000^2 := 10203020 1774400^2$$
- $$102030403020 0225600^2 + 177777760000^2 := 102030403020 1774400^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0225600^2 + 1777777760000^2 := 1020304050403020 1774400^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0225600^2 + 17777777760000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1774400^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0225600^2 + 177777777760000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1774400^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0225600^2 + 1777777777760000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1774400^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0225600^2 + 17777777777760000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1774400^2$$
- 881)
- $$0223839^2 + 1762000^2 := 1776161^2$$
- $$1020 0223839^2 + 177962000^2 := 1020 1776161^2$$
- $$10203020 0223839^2 + 17797962000^2 := 10203020 1776161^2$$
- $$102030403020 0223839^2 + 1779797962000^2 := 102030403020 1776161^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0223839^2 + 177979797962000^2 := 1020304050403020 1776161^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0223839^2 + 17797979797962000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1776161^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0223839^2 + 1779797979797962000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1776161^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0223839^2 + 177979797979797962000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1776161^2$$
- 882)
- $$0222076^2 + 1764000^2 := 1777924^2$$
- $$1020 0222076^2 + 178164000^2 := 1020 1777924^2$$
- $$10203020 0222076^2 + 17818164000^2 := 10203020 1777924^2$$
- $$102030403020 0222076^2 + 1781818164000^2 := 102030403020 1777924^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0222076^2 + 178181818164000^2 := 1020304050403020 1777924^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0222076^2 + 17818181818164000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1777924^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0222076^2 + 1781818181818164000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1777924^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0222076^2 + 178181818181818164000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1777924^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0222076^2 + 17818181818181818164000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1777924^2$$

- 883)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0220311^2 + 1766000^2 && := 1779689^2 \\ &1020\ 0220311^2 + 178366000^2 && := 1020\ 1779689^2 \\ &10203020\ 0220311^2 + 17838366000^2 && := 10203020\ 1779689^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0220311^2 + 1783838366000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1779689^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0220311^2 + 178383838366000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1779689^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0220311^2 + 17838383838366000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1779689^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0220311^2 + 1783838383838366000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1779689^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0220311^2 + 178383838383838366000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1779689^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0220311^2 + 17838383838383838366000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1779689^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 884)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0218544^2 + 1768000^2 && := 1781456^2 \\ &1020\ 0218544^2 + 178568000^2 && := 1020\ 1781456^2 \\ &10203020\ 0218544^2 + 17858568000^2 && := 10203020\ 1781456^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0218544^2 + 1785858568000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1781456^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0218544^2 + 178585858568000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1781456^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0218544^2 + 17858585858568000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1781456^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0218544^2 + 1785858585858568000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1781456^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0218544^2 + 178585858585858568000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1781456^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0218544^2 + 178585858585858568000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1781456^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 885)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0216775^2 + 1770000^2 && := 1783225^2 \\ &1020\ 0216775^2 + 178770000^2 && := 1020\ 1783225^2 \\ &10203020\ 0216775^2 + 17878770000^2 && := 10203020\ 1783225^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0216775^2 + 1787878770000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1783225^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0216775^2 + 178787878770000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1783225^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0216775^2 + 17878787878770000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1783225^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0216775^2 + 1787878787878770000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1783225^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0216775^2 + 178787878787878770000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1783225^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0216775^2 + 17878787878787878770000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1783225^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 886)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0215004^2 + 1772000^2 && := 1784996^2 \\ &1020\ 0215004^2 + 178972000^2 && := 1020\ 1784996^2 \\ &10203020\ 0215004^2 + 17898972000^2 && := 10203020\ 1784996^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0215004^2 + 1789898972000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1784996^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0215004^2 + 178989898972000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1784996^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0215004^2 + 17898989898972000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1784996^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0215004^2 + 1789898989898972000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1784996^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0215004^2 + 178989898989898972000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1784996^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0215004^2 + 17898989898989898972000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1784996^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 887)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0213231^2 + 1774000^2 && := 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0213231^2 + 179174000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0213231^2 + 17919174000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0213231^2 + 1791919174000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0213231^2 + 179191919174000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0213231^2 + 17919191919174000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0213231^2 + 1791919191919174000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0213231^2 + 179191919191919174000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1786769^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0213231^2 + 17919191919191919174000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1786769^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 888)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0211456^2 + 1776000^2 && := 1788544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0211456^2 + 179376000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1788544^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0211456^2 + 17939376000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1788544^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0211456^2 + 1793939376000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1788544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0211456^2 + 179393939376000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1788544^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0211456^2 + 17939393939376000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1788544^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0211456^2 + 1793939393939376000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1788544^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0211456^2 + 179393939393939376000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1788544^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0211456^2 + 17939393939393939376000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1788544^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 889)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0209679^2 + 1778000^2 && := 1790321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0209679^2 + 179578000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1790321^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0209679^2 + 17959578000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1790321^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0209679^2 + 1795959578000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1790321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0209679^2 + 179595959578000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1790321^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0209679^2 + 17959595959578000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1790321^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0209679^2 + 1795959595959578000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1790321^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0209679^2 + 179595959595959578000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1790321^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0209679^2 + 17959595959595959578000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1790321^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 890)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0207900^2 + 1780000^2 && := 1792100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0207900^2 + 179780000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1792100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0207900^2 + 17979780000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1792100^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0207900^2 + 1797979780000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1792100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0207900^2 + 179797979780000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1792100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0207900^2 + 17979797979780000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1792100^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0207900^2 + 1797979797979780000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1792100^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0207900^2 + 179797979797979780000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1792100^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0207900^2 + 17979797979797979780000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1792100^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 891)
- $$0206119^2 + 1782000^2 := 1793881^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0206119^2 + 179982000^2 := 1020 \ 1793881^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0206119^2 + 17999982000^2 := 10203020 \ 1793881^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0206119^2 + 1799999982000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1793881^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0206119^2 + 179999999982000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1793881^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0206119^2 + 17999999999982000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1793881^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0206119^2 + 1799999999999982000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1793881^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0206119^2 + 179999999999999982000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1793881^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0206119^2 + 1799999999999999982000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1793881^2$$
- 892)
- $$0204336^2 + 1784000^2 := 1795664^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0204336^2 + 180184000^2 := 1020 \ 1795664^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0204336^2 + 18020184000^2 := 10203020 \ 1795664^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0204336^2 + 1802020184000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1795664^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0204336^2 + 180202020184000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1795664^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0204336^2 + 18020202020184000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1795664^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0204336^2 + 1802020202020184000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1795664^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0204336^2 + 180202020202020184000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1795664^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0204336^2 + 18020202020202020184000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1795664^2$$
- 893)
- $$0202551^2 + 1786000^2 := 1797449^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0202551^2 + 180386000^2 := 1020 \ 1797449^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0202551^2 + 18040386000^2 := 10203020 \ 1797449^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0202551^2 + 1804040386000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1797449^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0202551^2 + 180404040386000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1797449^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0202551^2 + 18040404040386000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1797449^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0202551^2 + 1804040404040386000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1797449^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0202551^2 + 180404040404040386000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1797449^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0202551^2 + 18040404040404040386000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1797449^2$$
- 894)
- $$0200764^2 + 1788000^2 := 1799236^2$$
- $$1020 \ 0200764^2 + 180588000^2 := 1020 \ 1799236^2$$
- $$10203020 \ 0200764^2 + 18060588000^2 := 10203020 \ 1799236^2$$
- $$102030403020 \ 0200764^2 + 1806060588000^2 := 102030403020 \ 1799236^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 \ 0200764^2 + 180606060588000^2 := 1020304050403020 \ 1799236^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 \ 0200764^2 + 18060606060588000^2 := 10203040506050403020 \ 1799236^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 \ 0200764^2 + 1806060606060588000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 \ 1799236^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 \ 0200764^2 + 180606060606060588000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 \ 1799236^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 0200764^2 + 18060606060606060588000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 \ 1799236^2$$

- 895)
- $$0198975^2 + 1790000^2 := 1801025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0198975^2 + 180790000^2 := 1020\ 1801025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0198975^2 + 18080790000^2 := 10203020\ 1801025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0198975^2 + 1808080790000^2 := 102030403020\ 1801025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0198975^2 + 180808080790000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1801025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0198975^2 + 18080808080790000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1801025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0198975^2 + 1808080808080790000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1801025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0198975^2 + 180808080808080790000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1801025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0198975^2 + 18080808080808080790000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1801025^2$$
- 896)
- $$0197184^2 + 1792000^2 := 1802816^2$$
- $$1020\ 0197184^2 + 180992000^2 := 1020\ 1802816^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0197184^2 + 18100992000^2 := 10203020\ 1802816^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0197184^2 + 1810100992000^2 := 102030403020\ 1802816^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0197184^2 + 181010100992000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1802816^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0197184^2 + 18101010100992000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1802816^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0197184^2 + 1810101010100992000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1802816^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0197184^2 + 181010101010100992000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1802816^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0197184^2 + 18101010101010100992000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1802816^2$$
- 897)
- $$0195391^2 + 1794000^2 := 1804609^2$$
- $$1020\ 0195391^2 + 181194000^2 := 1020\ 1804609^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0195391^2 + 18121194000^2 := 10203020\ 1804609^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0195391^2 + 1812121194000^2 := 102030403020\ 1804609^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0195391^2 + 181212121194000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1804609^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0195391^2 + 18121212121194000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1804609^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0195391^2 + 1812121212121194000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1804609^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0195391^2 + 181212121212121194000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1804609^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0195391^2 + 181212121212121194000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1804609^2$$
- 898)
- $$0193596^2 + 1796000^2 := 1806404^2$$
- $$1020\ 0193596^2 + 181396000^2 := 1020\ 1806404^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0193596^2 + 18141396000^2 := 10203020\ 1806404^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0193596^2 + 1814141396000^2 := 102030403020\ 1806404^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0193596^2 + 181414141396000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1806404^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0193596^2 + 18141414141396000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1806404^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0193596^2 + 1814141414141396000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1806404^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0193596^2 + 181414141414141396000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1806404^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0193596^2 + 18141414141414141396000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1806404^2$$

- 899)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0191799^2 + 1798000^2 && := 1808201^2 \\ &1020\ 0191799^2 + 181598000^2 && := 1020\ 1808201^2 \\ &10203020\ 0191799^2 + 18161598000^2 && := 10203020\ 1808201^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0191799^2 + 1816161598000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1808201^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0191799^2 + 181616161598000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1808201^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0191799^2 + 18161616161598000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1808201^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0191799^2 + 1816161616161598000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1808201^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0191799^2 + 181616161616161598000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1808201^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0191799^2 + 18161616161616161598000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1808201^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 900)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0190000^2 + 1800000^2 && := 1810000^2 \\ &1020\ 0190000^2 + 181800000^2 && := 1020\ 1810000^2 \\ &10203020\ 0190000^2 + 18181800000^2 && := 10203020\ 1810000^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0190000^2 + 1818181800000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1810000^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0190000^2 + 181818181800000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1810000^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0190000^2 + 18181818181800000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1810000^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0190000^2 + 1818181818181800000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1810000^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0190000^2 + 181818181818181800000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1810000^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0190000^2 + 18181818181818181800000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1810000^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 901)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0188199^2 + 1802000^2 && := 1811801^2 \\ &1020\ 0188199^2 + 182002000^2 && := 1020\ 1811801^2 \\ &10203020\ 0188199^2 + 18202002000^2 && := 10203020\ 1811801^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0188199^2 + 1820202002000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1811801^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0188199^2 + 182020202002000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1811801^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0188199^2 + 18202020202002000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1811801^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0188199^2 + 1820202020202002000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1811801^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0188199^2 + 182020202020202002000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1811801^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 902)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0186396^2 + 1804000^2 && := 1813604^2 \\ &1020\ 0186396^2 + 182204000^2 && := 1020\ 1813604^2 \\ &10203020\ 0186396^2 + 18222204000^2 && := 10203020\ 1813604^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0186396^2 + 1822222204000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1813604^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0186396^2 + 182222222204000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1813604^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0186396^2 + 18222222222204000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1813604^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0186396^2 + 1822222222222204000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1813604^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0186396^2 + 182222222222222204000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1813604^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0186396^2 + 18222222222222222204000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1813604^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 903)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0184591^2 + 1806000^2$ | $:= 1815409^2$ |
| $1020\ 0184591^2 + 182406000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1815409^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0184591^2 + 18242406000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1815409^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0184591^2 + 1824242406000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1815409^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0184591^2 + 182424242406000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1815409^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0184591^2 + 18242424242406000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1815409^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0184591^2 + 1824242424242406000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1815409^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0184591^2 + 182424242424242406000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1815409^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0184591^2 + 18242424242424242406000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1815409^2$ |
- 904)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0182784^2 + 1808000^2$ | $:= 1817216^2$ |
| $1020\ 0182784^2 + 182608000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1817216^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0182784^2 + 18262608000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1817216^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0182784^2 + 1826262608000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1817216^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0182784^2 + 182626262608000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1817216^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0182784^2 + 18262626262608000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1817216^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0182784^2 + 1826262626262608000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1817216^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0182784^2 + 182626262626262608000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1817216^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0182784^2 + 18262626262626262608000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1817216^2$ |
- 905)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0180975^2 + 1810000^2$ | $:= 1819025^2$ |
| $1020\ 0180975^2 + 182810000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1819025^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0180975^2 + 18282810000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1819025^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0180975^2 + 1828282810000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1819025^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0180975^2 + 182828282810000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1819025^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0180975^2 + 18282828282810000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1819025^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0180975^2 + 1828282828282810000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1819025^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0180975^2 + 182828282828282810000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1819025^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0180975^2 + 18282828282828282810000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1819025^2$ |
- 906)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0179164^2 + 1812000^2$ | $:= 1820836^2$ |
| $1020\ 0179164^2 + 183012000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1820836^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0179164^2 + 18303012000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1820836^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0179164^2 + 1830303012000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1820836^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0179164^2 + 183030303012000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1820836^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0179164^2 + 18303030303012000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1820836^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0179164^2 + 1830303030303012000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1820836^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0179164^2 + 183030303030303012000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1820836^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0179164^2 + 18303030303030303012000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1820836^2$ |

- 907)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0177351^2 + 1814000^2 && := 1822649^2 \\ &1020\ 0177351^2 + 183214000^2 && := 1020\ 1822649^2 \\ &10203020\ 0177351^2 + 18323214000^2 && := 10203020\ 1822649^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0177351^2 + 1832323214000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1822649^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0177351^2 + 183232323214000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1822649^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0177351^2 + 18323232323214000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1822649^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0177351^2 + 1832323232323214000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1822649^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0177351^2 + 183232323232323214000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1822649^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0177351^2 + 18323232323232323214000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1822649^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 908)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0175536^2 + 1816000^2 && := 1824464^2 \\ &1020\ 0175536^2 + 183416000^2 && := 1020\ 1824464^2 \\ &10203020\ 0175536^2 + 18343416000^2 && := 10203020\ 1824464^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0175536^2 + 1834343416000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1824464^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0175536^2 + 183434343416000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1824464^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0175536^2 + 18343434343416000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1824464^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0175536^2 + 1834343434343416000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1824464^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0175536^2 + 183434343434343416000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1824464^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0175536^2 + 18343434343434343416000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1824464^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 909)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0173719^2 + 1818000^2 && := 1826281^2 \\ &1020\ 0173719^2 + 183618000^2 && := 1020\ 1826281^2 \\ &10203020\ 0173719^2 + 18363618000^2 && := 10203020\ 1826281^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0173719^2 + 1836363618000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1826281^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0173719^2 + 183636363618000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1826281^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0173719^2 + 18363636363618000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1826281^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0173719^2 + 1836363636363618000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1826281^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0173719^2 + 183636363636363618000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1826281^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0173719^2 + 18363636363636363618000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1826281^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 910)
- $$\begin{aligned} &0171900^2 + 1820000^2 && := 1828100^2 \\ &1020\ 0171900^2 + 183820000^2 && := 1020\ 1828100^2 \\ &10203020\ 0171900^2 + 18383820000^2 && := 10203020\ 1828100^2 \\ &102030403020\ 0171900^2 + 1838383820000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1828100^2 \\ &1020304050403020\ 0171900^2 + 183838383820000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1828100^2 \\ &10203040506050403020\ 0171900^2 + 18383838383820000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1828100^2 \\ &102030405060706050403020\ 0171900^2 + 1838383838383820000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1828100^2 \\ &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0171900^2 + 183838383838383820000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1828100^2 \\ &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0171900^2 + 18383838383838383820000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1828100^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 911)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0170079^2 + 1822000^2 & := & 1829921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0170079^2 + 184022000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1829921^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0170079^2 + 18404022000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1829921^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0170079^2 + 1840404022000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1829921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0170079^2 + 184040404022000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1829921^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0170079^2 + 18404040404022000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1829921^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0170079^2 + 1840404040404022000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1829921^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0170079^2 + 184040404040404022000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1829921^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0170079^2 + 18404040404040404022000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1829921^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 912)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0168256^2 + 1824000^2 & := & 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0168256^2 + 184224000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0168256^2 + 18424224000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0168256^2 + 1842424224000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0168256^2 + 184242424224000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0168256^2 + 18424242424224000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0168256^2 + 1842424242424224000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0168256^2 + 1842424242424224000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1831744^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0168256^2 + 184242424242424224000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1831744^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 913)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0166431^2 + 1826000^2 & := & 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0166431^2 + 184426000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0166431^2 + 18444426000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0166431^2 + 1844444426000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0166431^2 + 184444444426000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0166431^2 + 18444444444426000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0166431^2 + 1844444444444426000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0166431^2 + 184444444444444426000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1833569^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0166431^2 + 18444444444444444426000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1833569^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 914)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0164604^2 + 1828000^2 & := & 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0164604^2 + 184628000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0164604^2 + 18464628000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203020} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0164604^2 + 1846464628000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030403020} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0164604^2 + 184646464628000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0164604^2 + 18464646464628000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0164604^2 + 1846464646464628000^2 & := & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0164604^2 + 184646464646464628000^2 & := & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1835396^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0164604^2 + 18464646464646464628000^2 & := & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1835396^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 915)
- $$0162775^2 + 1830000^2 := 1837225^2$$
- $$1020\ 0162775^2 + 184830000^2 := 1020\ 1837225^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0162775^2 + 18484830000^2 := 10203020\ 1837225^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0162775^2 + 1848484830000^2 := 102030403020\ 1837225^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0162775^2 + 184848484830000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1837225^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0162775^2 + 18484848484830000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1837225^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0162775^2 + 1848484848484830000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1837225^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0162775^2 + 184848484848484830000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1837225^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0162775^2 + 18484848484848484830000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1837225^2$$
- 916)
- $$0160944^2 + 1832000^2 := 1839056^2$$
- $$1020\ 0160944^2 + 185032000^2 := 1020\ 1839056^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0160944^2 + 18505032000^2 := 10203020\ 1839056^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0160944^2 + 1850505032000^2 := 102030403020\ 1839056^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0160944^2 + 185050505032000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1839056^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0160944^2 + 18505050505032000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1839056^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0160944^2 + 1850505050505032000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1839056^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0160944^2 + 185050505050505032000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1839056^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0160944^2 + 18505050505050505032000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1839056^2$$
- 917)
- $$0159111^2 + 1834000^2 := 1840889^2$$
- $$1020\ 0159111^2 + 185234000^2 := 1020\ 1840889^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0159111^2 + 18525234000^2 := 10203020\ 1840889^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0159111^2 + 1852525234000^2 := 102030403020\ 1840889^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0159111^2 + 185252525234000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1840889^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0159111^2 + 18525252525234000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1840889^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0159111^2 + 1852525252525234000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1840889^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0159111^2 + 185252525252525234000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1840889^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0159111^2 + 185252525252525234000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1840889^2$$
- 918)
- $$0157276^2 + 1836000^2 := 1842724^2$$
- $$1020\ 0157276^2 + 185436000^2 := 1020\ 1842724^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0157276^2 + 18545436000^2 := 10203020\ 1842724^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0157276^2 + 1854545436000^2 := 102030403020\ 1842724^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0157276^2 + 185454545436000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1842724^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0157276^2 + 18545454545436000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1842724^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0157276^2 + 1854545454545436000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1842724^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0157276^2 + 185454545454545436000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1842724^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0157276^2 + 185454545454545436000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1842724^2$$

- 919)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0155439^2 + 1838000^2$ | $:= 1844561^2$ |
| $1020\ 0155439^2 + 185638000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1844561^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0155439^2 + 18565638000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1844561^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0155439^2 + 1856565638000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1844561^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0155439^2 + 185656565638000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1844561^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0155439^2 + 18565656565638000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1844561^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0155439^2 + 1856565656565638000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1844561^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0155439^2 + 185656565656565638000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1844561^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0155439^2 + 18565656565656565638000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1844561^2$ |
- 920)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0153600^2 + 1840000^2$ | $:= 1846400^2$ |
| $1020\ 0153600^2 + 185840000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1846400^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0153600^2 + 18585840000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1846400^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0153600^2 + 1858585840000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1846400^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0153600^2 + 185858585840000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1846400^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0153600^2 + 18585858585840000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1846400^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0153600^2 + 1858585858585840000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1846400^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0153600^2 + 185858585858585840000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1846400^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0153600^2 + 18585858585858585840000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1846400^2$ |
- 921)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0151759^2 + 1842000^2$ | $:= 1848241^2$ |
| $1020\ 0151759^2 + 186042000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1848241^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0151759^2 + 18606042000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1848241^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0151759^2 + 1860606042000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1848241^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0151759^2 + 186060606042000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1848241^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0151759^2 + 18606060606042000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1848241^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0151759^2 + 1860606060606042000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1848241^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0151759^2 + 186060606060606042000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1848241^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0151759^2 + 18606060606060606042000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1848241^2$ |
- 922)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0149916^2 + 1844000^2$ | $:= 1850084^2$ |
| $1020\ 0149916^2 + 186244000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1850084^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0149916^2 + 18626244000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1850084^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0149916^2 + 1862626244000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1850084^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0149916^2 + 186262626244000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1850084^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0149916^2 + 18626262626244000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1850084^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0149916^2 + 1862626262626244000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1850084^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0149916^2 + 186262626262626244000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1850084^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0149916^2 + 18626262626262626244000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1850084^2$ |

- 923)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0148071^2 + 1846000^2$ | $:= 1851929^2$ |
| $1020\ 0148071^2 + 186446000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1851929^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0148071^2 + 18646446000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1851929^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0148071^2 + 1864646446000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1851929^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0148071^2 + 186464646446000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1851929^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0148071^2 + 18646464646446000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1851929^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0148071^2 + 1864646464646446000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1851929^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0148071^2 + 186464646464646446000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1851929^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0148071^2 + 18646464646464646446000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1851929^2$ |
- 924)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0146224^2 + 1848000^2$ | $:= 1853776^2$ |
| $1020\ 0146224^2 + 186648000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1853776^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0146224^2 + 18666648000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1853776^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0146224^2 + 1866666648000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1853776^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0146224^2 + 186666666648000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1853776^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0146224^2 + 18666666666648000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1853776^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0146224^2 + 1866666666666648000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1853776^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0146224^2 + 186666666666666648000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1853776^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0146224^2 + 18666666666666666648000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1853776^2$ |
- 925)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0144375^2 + 1850000^2$ | $:= 1855625^2$ |
| $1020\ 0144375^2 + 186850000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1855625^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0144375^2 + 18686850000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1855625^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0144375^2 + 1868686850000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1855625^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0144375^2 + 186868686850000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1855625^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0144375^2 + 18686868686850000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1855625^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0144375^2 + 1868686868686850000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1855625^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0144375^2 + 186868686868686850000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1855625^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0144375^2 + 18686868686868686850000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1855625^2$ |
- 926)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0142524^2 + 1852000^2$ | $:= 1857476^2$ |
| $1020\ 0142524^2 + 187052000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1857476^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0142524^2 + 18707052000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1857476^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0142524^2 + 1870707052000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1857476^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0142524^2 + 187070707052000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1857476^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0142524^2 + 18707070707052000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1857476^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0142524^2 + 1870707070707052000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1857476^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0142524^2 + 187070707070707052000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1857476^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0142524^2 + 18707070707070707052000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1857476^2$ |

- 927)
- $$0140671^2 + 1854000^2 := 1859329^2$$
- $$1020\ 0140671^2 + 187254000^2 := 1020\ 1859329^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0140671^2 + 18727254000^2 := 10203020\ 1859329^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0140671^2 + 1872727254000^2 := 102030403020\ 1859329^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0140671^2 + 187272727254000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1859329^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0140671^2 + 18727272727254000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1859329^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0140671^2 + 1872727272727254000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1859329^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0140671^2 + 187272727272727254000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1859329^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0140671^2 + 18727272727272727254000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1859329^2$$
- 928)
- $$0138816^2 + 1856000^2 := 1861184^2$$
- $$1020\ 0138816^2 + 187456000^2 := 1020\ 1861184^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0138816^2 + 18747456000^2 := 10203020\ 1861184^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0138816^2 + 1874747456000^2 := 102030403020\ 1861184^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0138816^2 + 187474747456000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1861184^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0138816^2 + 18747474747456000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1861184^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0138816^2 + 1874747474747456000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1861184^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0138816^2 + 187474747474747456000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1861184^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0138816^2 + 18747474747474747456000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1861184^2$$
- 929)
- $$0136959^2 + 1858000^2 := 1863041^2$$
- $$1020\ 0136959^2 + 187658000^2 := 1020\ 1863041^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0136959^2 + 18767658000^2 := 10203020\ 1863041^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0136959^2 + 1876767658000^2 := 102030403020\ 1863041^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0136959^2 + 187676767658000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1863041^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0136959^2 + 18767676767658000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1863041^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0136959^2 + 1876767676767658000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1863041^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0136959^2 + 187676767676767658000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1863041^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0136959^2 + 18767676767676767658000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1863041^2$$
- 930)
- $$0135100^2 + 1860000^2 := 1864900^2$$
- $$1020\ 0135100^2 + 187860000^2 := 1020\ 1864900^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0135100^2 + 18787860000^2 := 10203020\ 1864900^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0135100^2 + 1878787860000^2 := 102030403020\ 1864900^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0135100^2 + 187878787860000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1864900^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0135100^2 + 18787878787860000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1864900^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0135100^2 + 1878787878787860000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1864900^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0135100^2 + 187878787878787860000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1864900^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0135100^2 + 18787878787878787860000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1864900^2$$

- 931)
- $$0133239^2 + 1862000^2 := 1866761^2$$
- $$1020\ 0133239^2 + 188062000^2 := 1020\ 1866761^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0133239^2 + 18808062000^2 := 10203020\ 1866761^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0133239^2 + 1880808062000^2 := 102030403020\ 1866761^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0133239^2 + 188080808062000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1866761^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0133239^2 + 18808080808062000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1866761^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0133239^2 + 1880808080808062000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1866761^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0133239^2 + 188080808080808062000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1866761^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0133239^2 + 18808080808080808062000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1866761^2$$
- 932)
- $$0131376^2 + 1864000^2 := 1868624^2$$
- $$1020\ 0131376^2 + 188264000^2 := 1020\ 1868624^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0131376^2 + 18828264000^2 := 10203020\ 1868624^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0131376^2 + 1882828264000^2 := 102030403020\ 1868624^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0131376^2 + 188282828264000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1868624^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0131376^2 + 18828282828264000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1868624^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0131376^2 + 1882828282828264000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1868624^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0131376^2 + 188282828282828264000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1868624^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0131376^2 + 188282828282828264000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1868624^2$$
- 933)
- $$0129511^2 + 1866000^2 := 1870489^2$$
- $$1020\ 0129511^2 + 188466000^2 := 1020\ 1870489^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0129511^2 + 18848466000^2 := 10203020\ 1870489^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0129511^2 + 1884848466000^2 := 102030403020\ 1870489^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0129511^2 + 188484848466000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1870489^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0129511^2 + 18848484848466000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1870489^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0129511^2 + 1884848484848466000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1870489^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0129511^2 + 188484848484848466000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1870489^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0129511^2 + 18848484848484848466000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1870489^2$$
- 934)
- $$0127644^2 + 1868000^2 := 1872356^2$$
- $$1020\ 0127644^2 + 188668000^2 := 1020\ 1872356^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0127644^2 + 18868668000^2 := 10203020\ 1872356^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0127644^2 + 1886868668000^2 := 102030403020\ 1872356^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0127644^2 + 188686868668000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1872356^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0127644^2 + 18868686868668000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1872356^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0127644^2 + 1886868686868668000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1872356^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0127644^2 + 188686868686868668000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1872356^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0127644^2 + 188686868686868668000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1872356^2$$

- 935)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0125775^2 + 1870000^2$ | $:= 1874225^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0125775^2 + 188870000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1874225^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0125775^2 + 18888870000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1874225^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0125775^2 + 1888888870000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1874225^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0125775^2 + 188888888870000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1874225^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0125775^2 + 18888888888870000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1874225^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0125775^2 + 1888888888888870000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1874225^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0125775^2 + 188888888888888870000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1874225^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0125775^2 + 18888888888888888870000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1874225^2$ |
- 936)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0123904^2 + 1872000^2$ | $:= 1876096^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0123904^2 + 189072000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1876096^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0123904^2 + 18909072000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1876096^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0123904^2 + 1890909072000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1876096^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0123904^2 + 189090909072000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1876096^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0123904^2 + 18909090909072000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1876096^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0123904^2 + 1890909090909072000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1876096^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0123904^2 + 189090909090909072000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1876096^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0123904^2 + 18909090909090909072000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1876096^2$ |
- 937)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0122031^2 + 1874000^2$ | $:= 1877969^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0122031^2 + 189274000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1877969^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0122031^2 + 18929274000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1877969^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0122031^2 + 1892929274000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1877969^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0122031^2 + 189292929274000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1877969^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0122031^2 + 18929292929274000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1877969^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0122031^2 + 1892929292929274000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1877969^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0122031^2 + 189292929292929274000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1877969^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0122031^2 + 18929292929292929274000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1877969^2$ |
- 938)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0120156^2 + 1876000^2$ | $:= 1879844^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0120156^2 + 189476000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1879844^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0120156^2 + 18949476000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1879844^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0120156^2 + 1894949476000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1879844^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0120156^2 + 189494949476000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1879844^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0120156^2 + 18949494949476000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1879844^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0120156^2 + 1894949494949476000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1879844^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0120156^2 + 189494949494949476000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1879844^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0120156^2 + 18949494949494949476000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1879844^2$ |

- 939)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0118279^2 + 1878000^2$ | $:= 1881721^2$ |
| $1020\ 0118279^2 + 189678000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1881721^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0118279^2 + 18969678000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1881721^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0118279^2 + 1896969678000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1881721^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0118279^2 + 189696969678000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1881721^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0118279^2 + 18969696969678000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1881721^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0118279^2 + 1896969696969678000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1881721^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0118279^2 + 189696969696969678000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1881721^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0118279^2 + 18969696969696969678000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1881721^2$ |
- 940)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0116400^2 + 1880000^2$ | $:= 1883600^2$ |
| $1020\ 0116400^2 + 189880000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1883600^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0116400^2 + 18989880000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1883600^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0116400^2 + 1898989880000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1883600^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0116400^2 + 189898989880000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1883600^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0116400^2 + 18989898989880000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1883600^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0116400^2 + 1898989898989880000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1883600^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0116400^2 + 189898989898989880000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1883600^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0116400^2 + 18989898989898989880000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1883600^2$ |
- 941)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0114519^2 + 1882000^2$ | $:= 1885481^2$ |
| $1020\ 0114519^2 + 190082000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1885481^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0114519^2 + 19010082000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1885481^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0114519^2 + 1901010082000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1885481^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0114519^2 + 190101010082000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1885481^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0114519^2 + 19010101010082000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1885481^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0114519^2 + 1901010101010082000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1885481^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0114519^2 + 190101010101010082000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1885481^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0114519^2 + 19010101010101010082000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1885481^2$ |
- 942)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0112636^2 + 1884000^2$ | $:= 1887364^2$ |
| $1020\ 0112636^2 + 190284000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1887364^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0112636^2 + 19030284000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1887364^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0112636^2 + 1903030284000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1887364^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0112636^2 + 190303030284000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1887364^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0112636^2 + 19030303030284000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1887364^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0112636^2 + 1903030303030284000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1887364^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0112636^2 + 190303030303030284000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1887364^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0112636^2 + 19030303030303030284000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1887364^2$ |

- 943)
- $$0110751^2 + 1886000^2 := 1889249^2$$
- $$1020\ 0110751^2 + 190486000^2 := 1020\ 1889249^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0110751^2 + 19050486000^2 := 10203020\ 1889249^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0110751^2 + 1905050486000^2 := 102030403020\ 1889249^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0110751^2 + 190505050486000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1889249^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0110751^2 + 19050505050486000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1889249^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0110751^2 + 1905050505050486000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1889249^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0110751^2 + 190505050505050486000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1889249^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0110751^2 + 19050505050505050486000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1889249^2$$
- 944)
- $$0108864^2 + 1888000^2 := 1891136^2$$
- $$1020\ 0108864^2 + 190688000^2 := 1020\ 1891136^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0108864^2 + 19070688000^2 := 10203020\ 1891136^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0108864^2 + 1907070688000^2 := 102030403020\ 1891136^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0108864^2 + 190707070688000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1891136^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0108864^2 + 19070707070688000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1891136^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0108864^2 + 1907070707070688000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1891136^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0108864^2 + 190707070707070688000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1891136^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0108864^2 + 19070707070707070688000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1891136^2$$
- 945)
- $$0106975^2 + 1890000^2 := 1893025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0106975^2 + 190890000^2 := 1020\ 1893025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0106975^2 + 19090890000^2 := 10203020\ 1893025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0106975^2 + 1909090890000^2 := 102030403020\ 1893025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0106975^2 + 190909090890000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1893025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0106975^2 + 19090909090890000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1893025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0106975^2 + 1909090909090890000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1893025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0106975^2 + 190909090909090890000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1893025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0106975^2 + 19090909090909090890000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1893025^2$$
- 946)
- $$0105084^2 + 1892000^2 := 1894916^2$$
- $$1020\ 0105084^2 + 191092000^2 := 1020\ 1894916^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0105084^2 + 19111092000^2 := 10203020\ 1894916^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0105084^2 + 1911111092000^2 := 102030403020\ 1894916^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0105084^2 + 191111111092000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1894916^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0105084^2 + 19111111111092000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1894916^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0105084^2 + 1911111111111092000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1894916^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0105084^2 + 191111111111111092000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1894916^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0105084^2 + 19111111111111111092000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1894916^2$$

- 947)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0103191^2 + 1894000^2$ | $:= 1896809^2$ |
| $1020\ 0103191^2 + 191294000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1896809^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0103191^2 + 19131294000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1896809^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0103191^2 + 1913131294000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1896809^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0103191^2 + 191313131294000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1896809^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0103191^2 + 19131313131294000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1896809^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0103191^2 + 1913131313131294000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1896809^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0103191^2 + 191313131313131294000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1896809^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0103191^2 + 19131313131313131294000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1896809^2$ |
- 948)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0101296^2 + 1896000^2$ | $:= 1898704^2$ |
| $1020\ 0101296^2 + 191496000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1898704^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0101296^2 + 19151496000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1898704^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0101296^2 + 1915151496000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1898704^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0101296^2 + 191515151496000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1898704^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0101296^2 + 19151515151496000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1898704^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0101296^2 + 1915151515151496000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1898704^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0101296^2 + 191515151515151496000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1898704^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0101296^2 + 19151515151515151496000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1898704^2$ |
- 949)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0099399^2 + 1898000^2$ | $:= 1900601^2$ |
| $1020\ 0099399^2 + 191698000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1900601^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0099399^2 + 19171698000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1900601^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0099399^2 + 1917171698000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1900601^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0099399^2 + 191717171698000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1900601^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0099399^2 + 19171717171698000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1900601^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0099399^2 + 1917171717171698000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1900601^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0099399^2 + 191717171717171698000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1900601^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0099399^2 + 191717171717171698000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1900601^2$ |
- 950)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0097500^2 + 1900000^2$ | $:= 1902500^2$ |
| $1020\ 0097500^2 + 191900000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1902500^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0097500^2 + 19191900000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1902500^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0097500^2 + 1919191900000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1902500^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0097500^2 + 191919191900000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1902500^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0097500^2 + 19191919191900000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1902500^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0097500^2 + 1919191919191900000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1902500^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0097500^2 + 191919191919191900000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1902500^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0097500^2 + 19191919191919191900000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1902500^2$ |

- 951)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0095599^2 + 1902000^2 && := 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0095599^2 + 192102000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0095599^2 + 19212102000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0095599^2 + 1921212102000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0095599^2 + 192121212102000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0095599^2 + 19212121212102000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0095599^2 + 1921212121212102000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0095599^2 + 192121212121212102000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1904401^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0095599^2 + 19212121212121212102000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1904401^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 952)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0093696^2 + 1904000^2 && := 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0093696^2 + 192304000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0093696^2 + 19232304000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0093696^2 + 1923232304000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0093696^2 + 192323232304000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0093696^2 + 19232323232304000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0093696^2 + 1923232323232304000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0093696^2 + 192323232323232304000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1906304^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0093696^2 + 19232323232323232304000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1906304^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 953)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0091791^2 + 1906000^2 && := 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0091791^2 + 192506000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0091791^2 + 19252506000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0091791^2 + 1925252506000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0091791^2 + 192525252506000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0091791^2 + 19252525252506000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0091791^2 + 1925252525252506000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0091791^2 + 192525252525252506000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1908209^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0091791^2 + 19252525252525252506000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1908209^2 \end{aligned}$$
- 954)
- $$\begin{aligned} & 0089884^2 + 1908000^2 && := 1910116^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020} 0089884^2 + 192708000^2 && := \mathbf{1020} 1910116^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203020} 0089884^2 + 19272708000^2 && := \mathbf{10203020} 1910116^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030403020} 0089884^2 + 1927272708000^2 && := \mathbf{102030403020} 1910116^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050403020} 0089884^2 + 192727272708000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050403020} 1910116^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0089884^2 + 19272727272708000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} 1910116^2 \\ & \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0089884^2 + 1927272727272708000^2 && := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 1910116^2 \\ & \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0089884^2 + 192727272727272708000^2 && := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 1910116^2 \\ & \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0089884^2 + 19272727272727272708000^2 && := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 1910116^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 955)
- $$0087975^2 + 1910000^2 := 1912025^2$$
- $$1020 0087975^2 + 192910000^2 := 1020 1912025^2$$
- $$10203020 0087975^2 + 19292910000^2 := 10203020 1912025^2$$
- $$102030403020 0087975^2 + 1929292910000^2 := 102030403020 1912025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0087975^2 + 192929292910000^2 := 1020304050403020 1912025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0087975^2 + 19292929292910000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1912025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0087975^2 + 1929292929292910000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1912025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0087975^2 + 192929292929292910000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1912025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0087975^2 + 19292929292929292910000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1912025^2$$
- 956)
- $$0086064^2 + 1912000^2 := 1913936^2$$
- $$1020 0086064^2 + 193112000^2 := 1020 1913936^2$$
- $$10203020 0086064^2 + 19313112000^2 := 10203020 1913936^2$$
- $$102030403020 0086064^2 + 1931313112000^2 := 102030403020 1913936^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0086064^2 + 193131313112000^2 := 1020304050403020 1913936^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0086064^2 + 19313131313112000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1913936^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0086064^2 + 1931313131313112000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1913936^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0086064^2 + 193131313131313112000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1913936^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0086064^2 + 19313131313131313112000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1913936^2$$
- 957)
- $$0084151^2 + 1914000^2 := 1915849^2$$
- $$1020 0084151^2 + 193314000^2 := 1020 1915849^2$$
- $$10203020 0084151^2 + 19333314000^2 := 10203020 1915849^2$$
- $$102030403020 0084151^2 + 1933333314000^2 := 102030403020 1915849^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0084151^2 + 193333333314000^2 := 1020304050403020 1915849^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0084151^2 + 19333333333314000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1915849^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0084151^2 + 1933333333333314000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1915849^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0084151^2 + 193333333333333314000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1915849^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0084151^2 + 19333333333333333314000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1915849^2$$
- 958)
- $$0082236^2 + 1916000^2 := 1917764^2$$
- $$1020 0082236^2 + 193516000^2 := 1020 1917764^2$$
- $$10203020 0082236^2 + 19353516000^2 := 10203020 1917764^2$$
- $$102030403020 0082236^2 + 1935353516000^2 := 102030403020 1917764^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0082236^2 + 193535353516000^2 := 1020304050403020 1917764^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0082236^2 + 19353535353516000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1917764^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0082236^2 + 1935353535353516000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1917764^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0082236^2 + 193535353535353516000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1917764^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0082236^2 + 19353535353535353516000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1917764^2$$

- 959)
- $$0080319^2 + 1918000^2 := 1919681^2$$
- $$1020\ 0080319^2 + 193718000^2 := 1020\ 1919681^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0080319^2 + 19373718000^2 := 10203020\ 1919681^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0080319^2 + 1937373718000^2 := 102030403020\ 1919681^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0080319^2 + 193737373718000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1919681^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0080319^2 + 19373737373718000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1919681^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0080319^2 + 1937373737373718000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1919681^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0080319^2 + 193737373737373718000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1919681^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0080319^2 + 19373737373737373718000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1919681^2$$
- 960)
- $$0078400^2 + 1920000^2 := 1921600^2$$
- $$1020\ 0078400^2 + 193920000^2 := 1020\ 1921600^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0078400^2 + 19393920000^2 := 10203020\ 1921600^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0078400^2 + 1939393920000^2 := 102030403020\ 1921600^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0078400^2 + 193939393920000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1921600^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0078400^2 + 19393939393920000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1921600^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0078400^2 + 1939393939393920000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1921600^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0078400^2 + 193939393939393920000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1921600^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0078400^2 + 19393939393939393920000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1921600^2$$
- 961)
- $$0076479^2 + 1922000^2 := 1923521^2$$
- $$1020\ 0076479^2 + 194122000^2 := 1020\ 1923521^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0076479^2 + 19414122000^2 := 10203020\ 1923521^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0076479^2 + 1941414122000^2 := 102030403020\ 1923521^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0076479^2 + 194141414122000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1923521^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0076479^2 + 19414141414122000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1923521^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0076479^2 + 1941414141414122000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1923521^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0076479^2 + 194141414141414122000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1923521^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0076479^2 + 19414141414141414122000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1923521^2$$
- 962)
- $$0074556^2 + 1924000^2 := 1925444^2$$
- $$1020\ 0074556^2 + 194324000^2 := 1020\ 1925444^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0074556^2 + 19434324000^2 := 10203020\ 1925444^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0074556^2 + 1943434324000^2 := 102030403020\ 1925444^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0074556^2 + 194343434324000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1925444^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0074556^2 + 19434343434324000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1925444^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0074556^2 + 1943434343434324000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1925444^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0074556^2 + 194343434343434324000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1925444^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0074556^2 + 19434343434343434324000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1925444^2$$

- 963)
- $$0072631^2 + 1926000^2 := 1927369^2$$
- $$1020 0072631^2 + 194526000^2 := 1020 1927369^2$$
- $$10203020 0072631^2 + 19454526000^2 := 10203020 1927369^2$$
- $$102030403020 0072631^2 + 1945454526000^2 := 102030403020 1927369^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0072631^2 + 194545454526000^2 := 1020304050403020 1927369^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0072631^2 + 19454545454526000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1927369^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0072631^2 + 1945454545454526000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1927369^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0072631^2 + 194545454545454526000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1927369^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0072631^2 + 19454545454545454526000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1927369^2$$
- 964)
- $$0070704^2 + 1928000^2 := 1929296^2$$
- $$1020 0070704^2 + 194728000^2 := 1020 1929296^2$$
- $$10203020 0070704^2 + 19474728000^2 := 10203020 1929296^2$$
- $$102030403020 0070704^2 + 1947474728000^2 := 102030403020 1929296^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0070704^2 + 194747474728000^2 := 1020304050403020 1929296^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0070704^2 + 19474747474728000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1929296^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0070704^2 + 1947474747474728000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1929296^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0070704^2 + 194747474747474728000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1929296^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0070704^2 + 19474747474747474728000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1929296^2$$
- 965)
- $$0068775^2 + 1930000^2 := 1931225^2$$
- $$1020 0068775^2 + 194930000^2 := 1020 1931225^2$$
- $$10203020 0068775^2 + 19494930000^2 := 10203020 1931225^2$$
- $$102030403020 0068775^2 + 1949494930000^2 := 102030403020 1931225^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0068775^2 + 194949494930000^2 := 1020304050403020 1931225^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0068775^2 + 19494949494930000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1931225^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0068775^2 + 1949494949494930000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1931225^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0068775^2 + 194949494949494930000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1931225^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0068775^2 + 19494949494949494930000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1931225^2$$
- 966)
- $$0066844^2 + 1932000^2 := 1933156^2$$
- $$1020 0066844^2 + 195132000^2 := 1020 1933156^2$$
- $$10203020 0066844^2 + 19515132000^2 := 10203020 1933156^2$$
- $$102030403020 0066844^2 + 1951515132000^2 := 102030403020 1933156^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0066844^2 + 195151515132000^2 := 1020304050403020 1933156^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0066844^2 + 19515151515132000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1933156^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0066844^2 + 1951515151515132000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1933156^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0066844^2 + 195151515151515132000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1933156^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0066844^2 + 19515151515151515132000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1933156^2$$

- 967)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0064911^2 + 1934000^2$ | $:= 1935089^2$ |
| $1020 0064911^2 + 195334000^2$ | $:= 1020 1935089^2$ |
| $10203020 0064911^2 + 19535334000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1935089^2$ |
| $102030403020 0064911^2 + 1953535334000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1935089^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0064911^2 + 195353535334000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1935089^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0064911^2 + 19535353535334000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1935089^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0064911^2 + 1953535353535334000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1935089^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0064911^2 + 195353535353535334000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1935089^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0064911^2 + 19535353535353535334000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1935089^2$ |
- 968)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0062976^2 + 1936000^2$ | $:= 1937024^2$ |
| $1020 0062976^2 + 195536000^2$ | $:= 1020 1937024^2$ |
| $10203020 0062976^2 + 19555536000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1937024^2$ |
| $102030403020 0062976^2 + 1955555536000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1937024^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0062976^2 + 195555555536000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1937024^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0062976^2 + 19555555555536000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1937024^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0062976^2 + 1955555555555536000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1937024^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0062976^2 + 195555555555555536000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1937024^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0062976^2 + 19555555555555555536000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1937024^2$ |
- 969)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0061039^2 + 1938000^2$ | $:= 1938961^2$ |
| $1020 0061039^2 + 195738000^2$ | $:= 1020 1938961^2$ |
| $10203020 0061039^2 + 19575738000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1938961^2$ |
| $102030403020 0061039^2 + 1957575738000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1938961^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0061039^2 + 195757575738000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1938961^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0061039^2 + 19575757575738000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1938961^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0061039^2 + 1957575757575738000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1938961^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0061039^2 + 195757575757575738000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1938961^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0061039^2 + 19575757575757575738000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1938961^2$ |
- 970)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0059100^2 + 1940000^2$ | $:= 1940900^2$ |
| $1020 0059100^2 + 195940000^2$ | $:= 1020 1940900^2$ |
| $10203020 0059100^2 + 19595940000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1940900^2$ |
| $102030403020 0059100^2 + 1959595940000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1940900^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0059100^2 + 195959595940000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1940900^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0059100^2 + 19595959595940000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1940900^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0059100^2 + 1959595959595940000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1940900^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0059100^2 + 195959595959595940000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1940900^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0059100^2 + 19595959595959595940000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1940900^2$ |

- 971)
- $$0057159^2 + 1942000^2 := 1942841^2$$
- $$1020 0057159^2 + 196142000^2 := 1020 1942841^2$$
- $$10203020 0057159^2 + 19616142000^2 := 10203020 1942841^2$$
- $$102030403020 0057159^2 + 1961616142000^2 := 102030403020 1942841^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0057159^2 + 196161616142000^2 := 1020304050403020 1942841^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0057159^2 + 19616161616142000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1942841^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0057159^2 + 1961616161616142000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1942841^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0057159^2 + 196161616161616142000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1942841^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0057159^2 + 19616161616161616142000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1942841^2$$
- 972)
- $$0055216^2 + 1944000^2 := 1944784^2$$
- $$1020 0055216^2 + 196344000^2 := 1020 1944784^2$$
- $$10203020 0055216^2 + 19636344000^2 := 10203020 1944784^2$$
- $$102030403020 0055216^2 + 1963636344000^2 := 102030403020 1944784^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0055216^2 + 196363636344000^2 := 1020304050403020 1944784^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0055216^2 + 19636363636344000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1944784^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0055216^2 + 1963636363636344000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1944784^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0055216^2 + 196363636363636344000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1944784^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0055216^2 + 19636363636363636344000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1944784^2$$
- 973)
- $$0053271^2 + 1946000^2 := 1946729^2$$
- $$1020 0053271^2 + 196546000^2 := 1020 1946729^2$$
- $$10203020 0053271^2 + 19656546000^2 := 10203020 1946729^2$$
- $$102030403020 0053271^2 + 1965656546000^2 := 102030403020 1946729^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0053271^2 + 196565656546000^2 := 1020304050403020 1946729^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0053271^2 + 19656565656546000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1946729^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0053271^2 + 1965656565656546000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1946729^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0053271^2 + 196565656565656546000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1946729^2$$
- 974)
- $$0051324^2 + 1948000^2 := 1948676^2$$
- $$1020 0051324^2 + 196748000^2 := 1020 1948676^2$$
- $$10203020 0051324^2 + 19676748000^2 := 10203020 1948676^2$$
- $$102030403020 0051324^2 + 1967676748000^2 := 102030403020 1948676^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0051324^2 + 196767676748000^2 := 1020304050403020 1948676^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0051324^2 + 19676767676748000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1948676^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0051324^2 + 1967676767676748000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1948676^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0051324^2 + 196767676767676748000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1948676^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0051324^2 + 19676767676767676748000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1948676^2$$

- 975)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0049375^2 + 1950000^2$ | $:= 1950625^2$ |
| $1020\ 0049375^2 + 196950000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1950625^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0049375^2 + 19696950000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1950625^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0049375^2 + 1969696950000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1950625^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0049375^2 + 196969696950000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1950625^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0049375^2 + 19696969696950000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1950625^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0049375^2 + 1969696969696950000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1950625^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0049375^2 + 196969696969696950000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1950625^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0049375^2 + 19696969696969696950000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1950625^2$ |
- 976)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0047424^2 + 1952000^2$ | $:= 1952576^2$ |
| $1020\ 0047424^2 + 197152000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1952576^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0047424^2 + 19717152000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1952576^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0047424^2 + 1971717152000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1952576^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0047424^2 + 197171717152000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1952576^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0047424^2 + 19717171717152000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1952576^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0047424^2 + 1971717171717152000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1952576^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0047424^2 + 197171717171717152000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1952576^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0047424^2 + 19717171717171717152000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1952576^2$ |
- 977)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0045471^2 + 1954000^2$ | $:= 1954529^2$ |
| $1020\ 0045471^2 + 197354000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1954529^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0045471^2 + 19737354000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1954529^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0045471^2 + 1973737354000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1954529^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0045471^2 + 197373737354000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1954529^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0045471^2 + 19737373737354000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1954529^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0045471^2 + 1973737373737354000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1954529^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0045471^2 + 197373737373737354000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1954529^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0045471^2 + 19737373737373737354000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1954529^2$ |
- 978)
- | | |
|---|--|
| $0043516^2 + 1956000^2$ | $:= 1956484^2$ |
| $1020\ 0043516^2 + 197556000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1956484^2$ |
| $10203020\ 0043516^2 + 19757556000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1956484^2$ |
| $102030403020\ 0043516^2 + 1975757556000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1956484^2$ |
| $1020304050403020\ 0043516^2 + 197575757556000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1956484^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020\ 0043516^2 + 19757575757556000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1956484^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020\ 0043516^2 + 1975757575757556000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1956484^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0043516^2 + 197575757575757556000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1956484^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0043516^2 + 19757575757575757556000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1956484^2$ |

- 979)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0041559^2 + 1958000^2$ | $:= 1958441^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0041559^2 + 197758000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1958441^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0041559^2 + 19777758000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1958441^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0041559^2 + 1977777758000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1958441^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0041559^2 + 197777777758000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1958441^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0041559^2 + 19777777777758000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1958441^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0041559^2 + 1977777777777758000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1958441^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0041559^2 + 197777777777777758000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1958441^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0041559^2 + 19777777777777777758000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1958441^2$ |
- 980)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0039600^2 + 1960000^2$ | $:= 1960400^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0039600^2 + 197960000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1960400^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0039600^2 + 19797960000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1960400^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0039600^2 + 1979797960000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1960400^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0039600^2 + 197979797960000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1960400^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0039600^2 + 19797979797960000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1960400^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0039600^2 + 1979797979797960000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1960400^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0039600^2 + 197979797979797960000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1960400^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0039600^2 + 19797979797979797960000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1960400^2$ |
- 981)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0037639^2 + 1962000^2$ | $:= 1962361^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0037639^2 + 198162000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1962361^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0037639^2 + 19818162000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1962361^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0037639^2 + 1981818162000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1962361^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0037639^2 + 198181818162000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1962361^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0037639^2 + 19818181818162000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1962361^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0037639^2 + 1981818181818162000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1962361^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0037639^2 + 198181818181818162000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1962361^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0037639^2 + 19818181818181818162000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1962361^2$ |
- 982)
- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | $0035676^2 + 1964000^2$ | $:= 1964324^2$ |
| | $1020\ 0035676^2 + 198364000^2$ | $:= 1020\ 1964324^2$ |
| | $10203020\ 0035676^2 + 19838364000^2$ | $:= 10203020\ 1964324^2$ |
| | $102030403020\ 0035676^2 + 1983838364000^2$ | $:= 102030403020\ 1964324^2$ |
| | $1020304050403020\ 0035676^2 + 198383838364000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020\ 1964324^2$ |
| | $10203040506050403020\ 0035676^2 + 19838383838364000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020\ 1964324^2$ |
| | $102030405060706050403020\ 0035676^2 + 1983838383838364000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020\ 1964324^2$ |
| | $1020304050607080706050403020\ 0035676^2 + 198383838383838364000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1964324^2$ |
| | $10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0035676^2 + 19838383838383838364000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1964324^2$ |

- 983)
- $$0033711^2 + 1966000^2 := 1966289^2$$
- $$1020 0033711^2 + 198566000^2 := 1020 1966289^2$$
- $$10203020 0033711^2 + 19858566000^2 := 10203020 1966289^2$$
- $$102030403020 0033711^2 + 1985858566000^2 := 102030403020 1966289^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0033711^2 + 198585858566000^2 := 1020304050403020 1966289^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0033711^2 + 19858585858566000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1966289^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0033711^2 + 1985858585858566000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1966289^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0033711^2 + 198585858585858566000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1966289^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0033711^2 + 19858585858585858566000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1966289^2$$
- 984)
- $$0031744^2 + 1968000^2 := 1968256^2$$
- $$1020 0031744^2 + 198768000^2 := 1020 1968256^2$$
- $$10203020 0031744^2 + 19878768000^2 := 10203020 1968256^2$$
- $$102030403020 0031744^2 + 1987878768000^2 := 102030403020 1968256^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0031744^2 + 198787878768000^2 := 1020304050403020 1968256^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0031744^2 + 19878787878768000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1968256^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0031744^2 + 1987878787878768000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1968256^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0031744^2 + 198787878787878768000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1968256^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0031744^2 + 19878787878787878768000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1968256^2$$
- 985)
- $$0029775^2 + 1970000^2 := 1970225^2$$
- $$1020 0029775^2 + 198970000^2 := 1020 1970225^2$$
- $$10203020 0029775^2 + 19898970000^2 := 10203020 1970225^2$$
- $$102030403020 0029775^2 + 1989898970000^2 := 102030403020 1970225^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0029775^2 + 198989898970000^2 := 1020304050403020 1970225^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0029775^2 + 19898989898970000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1970225^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0029775^2 + 1989898989898970000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1970225^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0029775^2 + 198989898989898970000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1970225^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0029775^2 + 19898989898989898970000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1970225^2$$
- 986)
- $$0027804^2 + 1972000^2 := 1972196^2$$
- $$1020 0027804^2 + 199172000^2 := 1020 1972196^2$$
- $$10203020 0027804^2 + 19919172000^2 := 10203020 1972196^2$$
- $$102030403020 0027804^2 + 1991919172000^2 := 102030403020 1972196^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0027804^2 + 199191919172000^2 := 1020304050403020 1972196^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0027804^2 + 19919191919172000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1972196^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0027804^2 + 1991919191919172000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1972196^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0027804^2 + 199191919191919172000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1972196^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0027804^2 + 19919191919191919172000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1972196^2$$

- 987)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0025831^2 + 1974000^2$ | $:= 1974169^2$ |
| $1020 0025831^2 + 199374000^2$ | $:= 1020 1974169^2$ |
| $10203020 0025831^2 + 19939374000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1974169^2$ |
| $102030403020 0025831^2 + 1993939374000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1974169^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0025831^2 + 199393939374000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1974169^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0025831^2 + 19939393939374000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1974169^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0025831^2 + 1993939393939374000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1974169^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0025831^2 + 199393939393939374000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1974169^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0025831^2 + 19939393939393939374000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1974169^2$ |
- 988)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0023856^2 + 1976000^2$ | $:= 1976144^2$ |
| $1020 0023856^2 + 199576000^2$ | $:= 1020 1976144^2$ |
| $10203020 0023856^2 + 19959576000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1976144^2$ |
| $102030403020 0023856^2 + 1995959576000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1976144^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0023856^2 + 199595959576000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1976144^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0023856^2 + 19959595959576000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1976144^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0023856^2 + 1995959595959576000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1976144^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0023856^2 + 199595959595959576000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1976144^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0023856^2 + 19959595959595959576000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1976144^2$ |
- 989)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0021879^2 + 1978000^2$ | $:= 1978121^2$ |
| $1020 0021879^2 + 199778000^2$ | $:= 1020 1978121^2$ |
| $10203020 0021879^2 + 19979778000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1978121^2$ |
| $102030403020 0021879^2 + 1997979778000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1978121^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0021879^2 + 199797979778000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1978121^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0021879^2 + 19979797979778000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1978121^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0021879^2 + 1997979797979778000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1978121^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0021879^2 + 199797979797979778000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1978121^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0021879^2 + 19979797979797979778000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1978121^2$ |
- 990)
- | | |
|--|---|
| $0019900^2 + 1980000^2$ | $:= 1980100^2$ |
| $1020 0019900^2 + 199980000^2$ | $:= 1020 1980100^2$ |
| $10203020 0019900^2 + 19999980000^2$ | $:= 10203020 1980100^2$ |
| $102030403020 0019900^2 + 1999999980000^2$ | $:= 102030403020 1980100^2$ |
| $1020304050403020 0019900^2 + 199999999980000^2$ | $:= 1020304050403020 1980100^2$ |
| $10203040506050403020 0019900^2 + 19999999999980000^2$ | $:= 10203040506050403020 1980100^2$ |
| $102030405060706050403020 0019900^2 + 1999999999999980000^2$ | $:= 102030405060706050403020 1980100^2$ |
| $1020304050607080706050403020 0019900^2 + 199999999999999980000^2$ | $:= 1020304050607080706050403020 1980100^2$ |
| $10203040506070809080706050403020 0019900^2 + 19999999999999999980000^2$ | $:= 10203040506070809080706050403020 1980100^2$ |

- 991)
- $$0017919^2 + 1982000^2 := 1982081^2$$
- $$1020 0017919^2 + 200182000^2 := 1020 1982081^2$$
- $$10203020 0017919^2 + 20020182000^2 := 10203020 1982081^2$$
- $$102030403020 0017919^2 + 2002020182000^2 := 102030403020 1982081^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0017919^2 + 200202020182000^2 := 1020304050403020 1982081^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0017919^2 + 20020202020182000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1982081^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0017919^2 + 2002020202020182000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1982081^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0017919^2 + 200202020202020182000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1982081^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0017919^2 + 20020202020202020182000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1982081^2$$
- 992)
- $$0015936^2 + 1984000^2 := 1984064^2$$
- $$1020 0015936^2 + 200384000^2 := 1020 1984064^2$$
- $$10203020 0015936^2 + 20040384000^2 := 10203020 1984064^2$$
- $$102030403020 0015936^2 + 2004040384000^2 := 102030403020 1984064^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0015936^2 + 200404040384000^2 := 1020304050403020 1984064^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0015936^2 + 20040404040384000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1984064^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0015936^2 + 2004040404040384000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1984064^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0015936^2 + 200404040404040384000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1984064^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0015936^2 + 20040404040404040384000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1984064^2$$
- 993)
- $$0013951^2 + 1986000^2 := 1986049^2$$
- $$1020 0013951^2 + 200586000^2 := 1020 1986049^2$$
- $$10203020 0013951^2 + 20060586000^2 := 10203020 1986049^2$$
- $$102030403020 0013951^2 + 2006060586000^2 := 102030403020 1986049^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0013951^2 + 200606060586000^2 := 1020304050403020 1986049^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0013951^2 + 20060606060586000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1986049^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0013951^2 + 2006060606060586000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1986049^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0013951^2 + 200606060606060586000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1986049^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0013951^2 + 20060606060606060586000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1986049^2$$
- 994)
- $$0011964^2 + 1988000^2 := 1988036^2$$
- $$1020 0011964^2 + 200788000^2 := 1020 1988036^2$$
- $$10203020 0011964^2 + 20080788000^2 := 10203020 1988036^2$$
- $$102030403020 0011964^2 + 2008080788000^2 := 102030403020 1988036^2$$
- $$1020304050403020 0011964^2 + 200808080788000^2 := 1020304050403020 1988036^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020 0011964^2 + 20080808080788000^2 := 10203040506050403020 1988036^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020 0011964^2 + 2008080808080788000^2 := 102030405060706050403020 1988036^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020 0011964^2 + 200808080808080788000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020 1988036^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020 0011964^2 + 20080808080808080788000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020 1988036^2$$

- 995)
- $$0009975^2 + 1990000^2 := 1990025^2$$
- $$1020\ 0009975^2 + 200990000^2 := 1020\ 1990025^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0009975^2 + 20100990000^2 := 10203020\ 1990025^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0009975^2 + 2010100990000^2 := 102030403020\ 1990025^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0009975^2 + 201010100990000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1990025^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0009975^2 + 20101010100990000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1990025^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0009975^2 + 2010101010100990000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1990025^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0009975^2 + 201010101010100990000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1990025^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0009975^2 + 20101010101010100990000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1990025^2$$
- 996)
- $$0007984^2 + 1992000^2 := 1992016^2$$
- $$1020\ 0007984^2 + 201192000^2 := 1020\ 1992016^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0007984^2 + 20121192000^2 := 10203020\ 1992016^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0007984^2 + 2012121192000^2 := 102030403020\ 1992016^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0007984^2 + 201212121192000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1992016^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0007984^2 + 20121212121192000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1992016^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0007984^2 + 2012121212121192000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1992016^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0007984^2 + 201212121212121192000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1992016^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0007984^2 + 20121212121212121192000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1992016^2$$
- 997)
- $$0005991^2 + 1994000^2 := 1994009^2$$
- $$1020\ 0005991^2 + 201394000^2 := 1020\ 1994009^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0005991^2 + 20141394000^2 := 10203020\ 1994009^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0005991^2 + 2014141394000^2 := 102030403020\ 1994009^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0005991^2 + 201414141394000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1994009^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0005991^2 + 20141414141394000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1994009^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0005991^2 + 2014141414141394000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1994009^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0005991^2 + 201414141414141394000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1994009^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0005991^2 + 20141414141414141394000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1994009^2$$
- 998)
- $$0003996^2 + 1996000^2 := 1996004^2$$
- $$1020\ 0003996^2 + 201596000^2 := 1020\ 1996004^2$$
- $$10203020\ 0003996^2 + 20161596000^2 := 10203020\ 1996004^2$$
- $$102030403020\ 0003996^2 + 2016161596000^2 := 102030403020\ 1996004^2$$
- $$1020304050403020\ 0003996^2 + 201616161596000^2 := 1020304050403020\ 1996004^2$$
- $$10203040506050403020\ 0003996^2 + 20161616161596000^2 := 10203040506050403020\ 1996004^2$$
- $$102030405060706050403020\ 0003996^2 + 2016161616161596000^2 := 102030405060706050403020\ 1996004^2$$
- $$1020304050607080706050403020\ 0003996^2 + 201616161616161596000^2 := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1996004^2$$
- $$10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0003996^2 + 20161616161616161596000^2 := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1996004^2$$

999)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0001999^2 + 1998000^2 && := 1998001^2 \\
 &1020\ 0001999^2 + 201798000^2 && := 1020\ 1998001^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0001999^2 + 20181798000^2 && := 10203020\ 1998001^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0001999^2 + 2018181798000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1998001^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0001999^2 + 201818181798000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1998001^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0001999^2 + 20181818181798000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1998001^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0001999^2 + 2018181818181798000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1998001^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0001999^2 + 201818181818181798000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1998001^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0001999^2 + 20181818181818181798000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1998001^2
 \end{aligned}$$

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